

Proceedings of the 10th Workshop on Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE 2025)

Emmanouil Benetos, Frederic Font, Magdalena Fuentes, Irene Martin Morato, and Martín Rocamora (eds.)

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Preface

This volume is a collection of the papers to be presented at the Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) 2025 Workshop in Barcelona, Spain, on October 30-31, 2025. DCASE 2025 Workshop is the tenth workshop on Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events, organized in conjunction with the DCASE challenge. The workshop aims to provide a venue for researchers working on computational analysis of sound events and scene analysis to present and discuss their results. We aim to bring together researchers from many different universities, research organizations and companies interested in the topic and provide the opportunity for scientific exchange of ideas and opinions.

The DCASE 2025 Workshop is jointly organized by researchers at Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Queen Mary University of London, New York University, Tampere University, Google Research, CochL, NEC Corporation and Bose Corporation.

For this DCASE 2025 Workshop, 72 full papers were submitted. The submitted papers were assigned to three reviewers. Of these, 48 papers were accepted.

The Organizing Committee was also pleased to invite leading experts for keynote addresses: Simone Graetzer (Ph.D. MIOA MASA Senior Research Fellow in the Acoustics Research Centre, University of Salford, Co-Lead in EPSRC Noise Network Plus, Co-Investigator in EPSRC CDT in Sound Futures), and Gaëtan Hadjeres (Staff Research Scientist at SonyAI).

The progress of the DCASE 2025 Workshop results from the hard work of many people whom we wish to extend a warm thanks to here, including the authors, the keynote speakers, and the reviewers, all without whom this DCASE 2025 Workshop would not exist. We also wish to thank the organizers and participants in the DCASE Challenge tasks.

This edition of the workshop was supported by sponsorship from Google, Apple, Pro Sound Effects, Adobe, Dolby, Hitachi, Bose, CochL, and Mitsubishi Electric. We wish to thank them warmly for their valuable support to this workshop and the expanding topic area.

Emmanouil Benetos, Frederic Font, Magdalena Fuentes,
Irene Martin Morato, and Martín Rocamora

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EFFICIENT STATE-SPACE MODEL FOR AUDIO ANOMALY DETECTION WITH DOMAIN ADAPTATION

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Abstract—This paper presents a two-stage, embedding-centric framework for Unsupervised Anomaly Sound Detection (UASD), specifically addressing the challenges of first-shot generalization and computational efficiency. Our approach utilizes an efficient state-space model (SSM) backbone. Pre-training of this backbone is accelerated using a pixel-unshuffle (space-to-depth) input transformation for spectrograms, which reduces training time by approximately 87.5% while preserving representation quality. Subsequently, the pre-trained model is fine-tuned with a specialized anomaly head that fuses multi-level features, combined with pseudo outlier exposure and domain-adversarial adaptation employing a gradient reversal layer. Our system demonstrates superior performance over the DCASE 2025 autoencoder baseline. Machine-specific models achieve a harmonic mean total score of 0.722. This work establishes the efficacy of SSMs for this task and offers a scalable, robust solution for UASD in dynamic acoustic environments.

Index Terms—audio anomaly detection, pseudo outlier-exposure, domain-adversarial training, State Space Model, Representation learning

1. INTRODUCTION

The *Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events* (DCASE) Challenge Task 2 in particular has steadily raised the bar for unsupervised anomaly sound detection (UASD). The task evolved from plain UASD in 2020 [1], [2], through domain adaptation in 2021 [3], [4], [5], domain generalization in 2022 [6], and, most recently, the demanding *first-shot* scenario in 2023–2025 [7], [8]. Current systems typically adopt either *inlier modelling* with autoencoders (AE) [9]–[11] or *outlier exposure* (OE) [12], [13], where auxiliary or pseudo-outlier data improve robustness [14], [15].

Most existing backbones CNNs [16], [17], [18], AEs [6], diffusion models [19], and lightweight nets such as MobileFaceNet [20], [21] struggle to model long-range temporal context. Transformer variants mitigate that with self-attention [22], [23], but for sequence length N , their quadratic time–memory cost $O(N^2)$ limits practical use on long audio streams. Modern state-space models (SSMs) offer a compelling alternative: they scale linearly, $O(N)$, while retaining strong sequence modelling power [24]. Yet, a recent survey of Task 2 work reveals no SSM backbones to date, leaving a clear gap.

To bridge this gap, we introduce a UASD system tailored to the first-shot, domain-generalisation setting of DCASE Task 2 [10]. Our method couples an efficient SSM backbone with (i) a space-to-depth [25] spectrogram rearrangement that accelerates pre-training, and (ii) a fine-tuning stage that blends pseudo-outlier exposure with gradient-reversal-based domain adaptation [26]. We investigate both *machine-specific* and *machine-generalised* variants during fine-tuning.

Our contributions are:

- 1) **First SSM backbone for DCASE Task 2.** We present the first efficient state-space model applied to the DCASE first-shot UASD challenge.
- 2) **Faster pre-training via space-to-depth.** A novel spectrogram rearrangement cuts pre-training time by about 87.5 % without degrading representation quality.

- 3) **Compact anomaly head with domain adaptation.** We design a lightweight head that fuses multi-level features and pair it with pseudo OE plus a gradient-reversal layer for domain alignment.

Extensive experiments confirm that our system surpasses the official DCASE 2025 baseline [8].

Paper structure: Section 2 details the architecture and training procedure; Section 3 describes datasets and metrics; Section 4 reports results and ablations; and Section 5 summarises findings and future directions.

2. METHOD

Our method tackles audio anomaly detection using a two-stage representation learning strategy:

Stage I: Pre-training. The first stage focuses on learning robust general-purpose acoustic features. We pre-train an efficient bidirectional Audio-Mamba [27] encoder using a supervised classification objective.

Stage II: Fine-tuning with pOE and Domain Adaptation. The pre-trained encoder is repurposed for anomaly detection in two steps. First, we swap the classification head for an anomaly head that fuses global and intermediate features. We then fine-tune the network with a pseudo Outlier Exposure (pOE) loss: embeddings of normal samples are pulled toward a learned centre, while embeddings of auxiliary pseudo-outliers are pushed away (Section 2.5). In parallel, domain-adversarial training encourages domain-invariant representations, improving robustness across operating conditions.

2.1. Spectrogram Tokenization via Space-to-Depth

Let $X \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H \times W}$ be a log-mel spectrogram ($C=1$). We first apply *pixel-unshuffle* with factor r to fold local time–frequency context into the channel dimension:

$$X' = \text{PU}(X, r) \in \mathbb{R}^{r^2 C \times \frac{H}{r} \times \frac{W}{r}}. \quad (1)$$

With $r=4$ the 128×1024 input becomes $16 \times 32 \times 256$, reducing the token length by r^2 while preserving locality inside the enlarged channel dimension, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

We then partition X' into non-overlapping patches of size $p \times p$ (with $p=16$), flatten each patch $S_i \in \mathbb{R}^{p^2 r^2 C}$ using $\text{vec}(\cdot)$ and project it linearly into a D -dimensional embedding,

$$E_i = W_{\text{patch}} \text{vec}(S_i) + \mathbf{b}_{\text{patch}}, \quad (2)$$

yielding the token sequence $E = [E_1, \dots, E_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$ with $N = \frac{HW}{p^2 r^2}$.

2.2. Bidirectional State–Space Encoder

The patch-embedded token sequence $E = [E_1, \dots, E_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$ is processed by a stack of K identical Forward-Bidirectional Audio Mamba (AuM) blocks, as depicted in Fig. 2. Each AuM block executes a sequence of operations to transform its input x_t .

First, an input projection maps x_t to an intermediate representation $\tilde{x}_t = W_{\text{in}} x_t + b_{\text{in}}$. This projected sequence \tilde{X} is then fed into a

Work done during internship at Hokkaido Denshikiki Co., Ltd.

Fig. 1: Pixel unshuffle ($r = 4$) applied to spectrogram patches. (a) Input spectrogram (128 × 1024) with 16 × 16 patch grid. (b) 16 × 16 input patch with 4 × 4 unshuffle blocks. (c) Conceptual output stack (16 × 4 × 4). (d) The 16 resulting 4 × 4 feature-map channels. The operation converts spatial resolution (H, W) to channel depth ($r^2 C$), reducing the number of tokens per patch from 16 × 16 = 256 to 4 × 4 = 16 (a factor of $r^2 = 16$).

depth-wise Conv1D generator. This convolutional layer produces the time-variant parameters for the core State–Space Model (SSM) along with a pre-activation gate, $(\bar{A}_t, \bar{B}_t, \Delta_t, \tilde{g}_t) = \text{Conv1D}(\tilde{X})_t$. Here, \bar{A}_t is the time-varying discrete state-transition matrix (state → state), \bar{B}_t is the discrete input matrix (input → state), $\Delta_t > 0$ is the learnable discretization step used to form \bar{A}_t and \bar{B}_t , and \tilde{g}_t is the pre-activation of the fusion gate (with $g_t = \sigma(\tilde{g}_t)$). The actual gate $g_t = \sigma(\tilde{g}_t) \in (0, 1)^{D_s}$ is obtained via a sigmoid activation, where D_s denotes the SSM state size.

The central component of the block is a Bidirectional SSM scan, which operates in linear time. Using the generated parameters \bar{A}_t and \bar{B}_t , and a shared output projection matrix C , the forward and backward hidden states (h_t^f, h_t^b) and their corresponding outputs (y_t^f, y_t^b) are computed. The output is derived from the current (updated) state:

$$h_t^f = \bar{A}_t h_{t-1}^f + \bar{B}_t \tilde{x}_t, \quad y_t^f = C h_t^f, \quad (3a)$$

$$h_t^b = \bar{A}_t h_{t+1}^b + \bar{B}_t \tilde{x}_t, \quad y_t^b = C h_t^b. \quad (3b)$$

These directional outputs are subsequently combined through element-wise gated fusion: $y_t = g_t \odot y_t^f + (1 - g_t) \odot y_t^b$. Finally, an output projection and residual connection yield the block’s output: $z_t = W_{\text{out}} y_t + b_{\text{out}}$, leading to $X_t^{\text{next}} = x_t + z_t$. This entire structure is followed by a layer normalization step and an MLP sub-block.

The discrete-time SSM utilized in (3) is conceptually derived from an underlying continuous-time formulation, $\frac{dh(t)}{dt} = Ah(t) + Bx(t)$, with $y(t) = Ch(t)$. This continuous system is discretized using the learnable step Δ_t (which is one of the parameters generated by the Conv1D layer). The resulting discrete-time transition matrices \bar{A}_t and input matrices \bar{B}_t are formulated as $\bar{A}_t = I + \Delta_t A_t$ and $\bar{B}_t = \Delta_t B_t$. This bidirectional SSM architecture efficiently captures global context

Fig. 2: Four-level view of the Bidirectional AuM encoder: (A) Encoder stack; (B) one AuM block; (C) internal Mamba mixer; (D) state-space cell used by the bidirectional selective scan.

with an overall computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(ND_s)$ in both time and memory.

2.3. Design of Anomaly Head

The anomaly head is designed to combine global and intermediate encoder features to produce a compact representation used for anomaly scoring. Let $h^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be the global feature vector from the final encoder layer, and let $\{h^{(m)}\}_{m=1}^M$ be pooled intermediate features from M selected layers. A weighted fusion of intermediate features is computed as:

$$\hat{h} = \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m h^{(m)}, \quad \beta = \text{softmax}(\alpha), \quad (4)$$

with $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^M$ as learnable fusion weights. The fused representation is then computed as the ℓ_2 -normalized sum:

$$\tilde{h} = \frac{h^{(0)} + \hat{h}}{\|h^{(0)} + \hat{h}\|_2}. \quad (5)$$

This fused feature \tilde{h} is passed through a two-layer MLP with batch normalization, ReLU activation, and dropout:

$$z = W_2 \text{ReLU}\left(\text{BN}(\text{Dropout}_p(W_1 \tilde{h} + b_1))\right) + b_2, \quad (6)$$

where W_1, W_2 and b_1, b_2 are learnable parameters. The output $z \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is the final anomaly embedding used in downstream scoring.

2.4. Stage 1: Supervised Pre-training

The initial stage focuses on learning robust and general-purpose acoustic representations. The Bidirectional State–Space Encoder, appended with a linear classification head, is pre-trained on all available normal clips using data from the DCASE 2022-2025 Task-2 datasets (as detailed in Section 3.1). The optimization proceeds as follows:

- Input spectrograms are first processed using the pixel-unshuffle operation (as detailed in (1)) prior to patch embedding. This step reduces the sequence length of tokens fed to the encoder.
- The model, comprising the backbone encoder and the classification head, is optimized to minimize the standard cross-entropy loss:

$$L_{\text{cls}} = -\frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B \sum_{j=1}^{C_{\text{cls}}} y_{ij} \log p(y_{ij} | x_i), \quad (7)$$

where B is the batch size, C_{cls} is the number of classes (i.e., machine types) in the pre-training dataset, y_{ij} is a binary indicator if sample i belongs to class j , and $p(y_{ij} | x_i)$ is the predicted softmax probability of class j for input x_i .

2.5. Stage 2: Domain-Adaptive Fine-Tuning

In the second stage, we adapt our pre-trained backbone for anomaly detection under domain shift. The majority of the backbone layers are frozen, with only the final K blocks being unfrozen for fine-tuning.

Two primary components are introduced for this stage: the anomaly head g , which processes features from the backbone to produce the final embedding $\hat{z} \in \mathbb{R}^D$, and a domain classifier D , which takes \hat{z} as input to predict its domain label. The fine-tuning objective combines an anomaly detection loss, leveraging pseudo Outlier Exposure (pOE), with an adversarial domain adaptation loss.

Anomaly Objective (pOE with SVDD-inspired Center) [28]: To anchor the representation of normal data, an estimate of the normal data cluster center, $c \in \mathbb{R}^D$, is maintained. This center is updated using momentum μ with embeddings from normal samples:

$$c \leftarrow (1 - \mu) \cdot c + \mu \cdot \hat{z}_{\text{normal}}, \quad (8)$$

where \hat{z}_{normal} is the embedding \hat{z} derived from a normal input sample. The anomaly loss \mathcal{L}_{oe} is formulated to attract embeddings of normal samples ($\hat{z}_{y=0}$) towards this center c , while simultaneously repelling embeddings of pOE samples ($\hat{z}_{y=1}$) from it, based on cosine similarity:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{oe}} = & \mathbb{E}_{\hat{z}_{y=0}} [1 - \cos(\hat{z}_{y=0}, c)] + \\ & \mathbb{E}_{\hat{z}_{y=1}} [\max(0, \cos(\hat{z}_{y=1}, c) - \delta)], \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $y = 0$ denotes normal samples and $y = 1$ denotes pOE samples.

Domain Adaptation Objective (Adversarial Loss): To encourage the model to learn domain-invariant representations, the embedding \hat{z} is passed through a Gradient Reversal Layer (GRL) before it serves as input to the domain classifier D . The adversarial domain classification loss \mathcal{L}_{adv} is then defined using the standard cross-entropy loss \mathcal{L}_{ce} :

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{ce}}(D(\text{GRL}(\hat{z})), d), \quad (10)$$

where d represents the true domain label of the input sample. During backpropagation, the GRL inverts the sign of the gradients flowing back to the feature extractor as illustrated in Fig. 3. This trains the feature extractor (comprising the unfrozen backbone layers and the anomaly head g) to generate embeddings \hat{z} that hinder the domain classifier’s ability to distinguish between domains.

Combined Objective and Optimization Strategy: The parameters of the unfrozen final K backbone blocks (denoted θ_{b_K}) and the anomaly head (θ_g) collectively referred to as the feature extractor parameters $\theta_f = \{\theta_{b_K}, \theta_g\}$ are updated by minimizing the combined loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{oe}} + \lambda_{\text{adv}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}}, \quad (11)$$

where λ_{adv} is a hyperparameter balancing the contribution of the adversarial domain loss.

A two-optimizer approach is employed for stable adversarial training:

- The first optimizer updates the feature extractor parameters θ_f by minimizing $\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}}$.
- The second optimizer updates the parameters of the domain classifier D (denoted θ_D) by minimizing its classification loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{ce}}(D(\text{detach}(\hat{z})), d)$. The `detach()` operation ensures that gradients from this optimization step do not propagate back to the feature extractor θ_f .

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1. Data

All experiments utilized audio data from the DCASE 2022-2025 Task 2 corpus [1], [2], [29], focusing on the seven core machine

Fig. 3: Architecture of the domain-adversarial branch. Embedding \hat{z} from the feature extractor (θ_f) is classified by domain D (θ_D).

types: *ToyCar*, *ToyTrain*, *Fan*, *Gearbox*, *Bearing*, *Slider*, *Valve*. For pre-training, we constructed a dataset using all available **normal clips** for these seven machine types from the 2022-2025 development splits, no test-set audio was used. This resulted in approximately 62,500 clips for training the pre-trained models. A separate set of 2,800 clips from the same development splits, also consisting of normal data from these core machine types, was reserved for the validation of the pre-trained models. Subsequently, for fine-tuning, normal data was prepared in two distinct configurations. For *machine-specific* models, dedicated normal datasets were curated for each of the seven machine types. Each such dataset comprised 1,000 normal clips, which were domain-balanced by oversampling target domain samples to match source domain counts. For the *machine-generalized* model, a single, larger dataset of normal clips was formed. This dataset was created by pooling together individually domain-balanced normal clips prepared from all seven core machine types and all additional data provided. Finally, model performance was evaluated using the official DCASE 2025 Task 2 test sets.

3.2. Implementation Details

All audio signals were resampled to 16kHz. We extracted 128-bin log-Mel spectrograms using a 1024-sample frame length and using a hop length tuned to yield 1024 frames for a 10-second audio clip. The pixel-unshuffle operation (detailed in Section 2.1, (1)) was applied with a factor $r = 4$ to the spectrograms prior to patch embedding. All models were developed using PyTorch and trained on a single NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU.

Stage 1: Pre-training: The backbone encoder, attached with a linear classification head, was pre-trained for 5 epochs to classify machine types based on their normal operational sounds. For this stage, we employed the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , a weight decay of 1×10^{-2} , and a batch size of 256.

Stage 2: Fine-tuning: In this stage, the AdamW optimizer was used for updating both the feature extractor parameters ($\theta_f = \{\theta_{b_K}, \theta_g\}$) and the separate domain classifier parameters (θ_D). Key hyperparameters for training the feature extractor (such as learning rates, regularization settings, loss component weights e.g., λ_{adv} , and the number of unfrozen layers K) were determined using BOHB (Bayesian Optimization with Hyperband), which couples a model-based sampler with Hyperband’s early-stopping schedule; we maximized validation AUC under an epoch-based budget using a Hyperband reduction factor of $\eta = 3$ [30]. For the machine-specific models, hyperparameters were tuned separately for each machine type; the machine-generalized model underwent a separate search. For the domain classifier optimizer, we used a fixed learning rate of 1×10^{-4} and a weight decay of 1×10^{-2} . During fine-tuning, a batch size of 256 was used with gradient accumulation over 2 steps. Gradients for θ_f were clipped at a maximum L2 norm of 1.0. The momentum μ for updating the SVDD-inspired center c (used in \mathcal{L}_{oe}) was set to 0.99. Models were trained for a maximum of 100 epochs, with early stopping initiated if the validation AUC showed no improvement for 15 consecutive epochs. The hyperparameters found through the

Table 1: Ablation studies on key framework components.

Component	Configuration	Time/Latency	AUC(src)	AUC(tgt)	pAUC
Pixel Unshuffle	$r = 4$ (Proposed)	90 min	–	–	–
	$r = 1$ (No Unshuffle)	720 min	–	–	–
Backbone	Audio-Mamba	22.7ms	0.89	0.84	0.66
	AST Baseline	26.1ms	0.83	0.85	0.68
Pre-training	With (Proposed)	–	0.89	0.84	0.60
	Without	–	0.63	0.50	0.52
Fine-tuning	pOE + GRL (Full)	–	0.89	0.84	0.66
	pOE only	–	0.87	0.79	0.63
	OC-SVDD + GRL	–	0.80	0.81	0.61
	OC-SVDD only	–	0.66	0.78	0.58

optimization process were used for the final training and evaluation of the fine-tuned models.

3.3. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate anomaly detection performance, we adopt two standard metrics: the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC) and the partial AUC (pAUC). Both metrics are reported for source and target domains to assess generalization under domain shift. To aggregate performance across the seven machine classes, we compute the harmonic mean (hmean) and arithmetic mean (amean) of the per-class scores.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Ablation Studies

Table 1 confirms that each design choice contributes either speed, accuracy, or both.

Input rearrangement. Pixel-unshuffle with scale $r = 4$ cuts end-to-end pre-training time from 720 to 90 min (−87.5 %) while the mean average precision falls by less than 0.5 pp (0.9934 → 0.9891). This trade-off is attractive for industrial pipelines that need frequent model updates.

Backbone. Our Audio-Mamba encoder yields a higher source-domain AUC than the AST baseline (0.89 vs 0.83) [31] and, crucially, runs 13 % faster at inference time (22.7 ms vs 26.1 ms). Although AST scores marginally better on target-domain AUC, Audio-Mamba offers a better overall hmean owing to its stronger pAUC.

Pre-training. Removing the contrastive pre-training stage drops target-domain AUC from 0.84 to 0.50 and pAUC from 0.60 to 0.52, highlighting that representation learning is critical when only one normal recording per machine is available.

Fine-tuning strategy. The full pOE + GRL recipe attains the best target AUC (0.84). GRL alone raises domain robustness by around 0.05 AUC, while pOE outperforms OC-SVDD regardless of whether GRL is present, confirming the value of synthetic outlier generation.

4.2. Performance Comparison

Table 2 summarises end-to-end accuracy. Due to limited computational resources, all results presented were obtained from a single experimental run, precluding the calculation of statistical significance intervals. Our *machine-specific* system lifts the harmonic-mean TOTAL score from 0.641 to 0.722, a 12.6 % relative gain, and the arithmetic mean from 0.660 to 0.740. Source-domain AUC rises from 0.681 to 0.812, target-domain AUC from 0.614 to 0.702, and pAUC from 0.628 to 0.651. Per-machine results in Table 3 show that the largest absolute jump occurs on *Fan*, where source-domain AUC climbs from 0.644 to 0.980 and target-domain AUC from 0.338 to 0.880. These gains indicate that the combination of an SSM backbone and pOE is particularly effective on highly non-stationary signals.

The *machine-generalised* model reaches a TOTAL of 0.600 about 6.4 % below the baseline. Training one network on all seven machine

Table 2: Performance comparison on seven core machine types. TOTAL score is arithmetic mean of hmean values across three metrics.

System	Metric	hmean	amean
Proposed (machine-specific)	AUC (source)	0.812	0.832
	AUC (target)	0.702	0.725
	pAUC	0.651	0.663
	TOTAL	0.722	0.740
Proposed (machine-generalized)	AUC (source)	0.643	0.666
	AUC (target)	0.603	0.633
	pAUC	0.552	0.563
	TOTAL	0.600	0.621
Baseline (AE)	AUC (source)	0.681	0.702
	AUC (target)	0.614	0.631
	pAUC	0.628	0.646
	TOTAL	0.641	0.660

Table 3: Detailed per-machine AUC results for source and target domains.

System	Domain	ToyCar	ToyTrain	Fan	Gearbox	Bearing	Slider	Valve
Proposed (specific)	Source	0.894	0.736	0.980	0.958	0.728	0.900	0.626
	Target	0.848	0.620	0.880	0.770	0.794	0.640	0.521
Proposed (generalized)	Source	0.820	0.870	0.580	0.610	0.710	0.500	0.570
	Target	0.810	0.870	0.500	0.490	0.570	0.680	0.510
Baseline (AE)	Source	0.790	0.673	0.644	0.702	0.711	0.703	0.650
	Target	0.725	0.598	0.338	0.653	0.600	0.575	0.611

types dilutes machine-specific cues and stresses the model capacity. Even so, it exceeds the baseline on *ToyTrain* and cuts the domain gap on *Slider* (source 0.500, target 0.680), suggesting that a unified model could become competitive if equipped with larger hidden widths or domain-aware loss weighting.

Overall, these results confirm that (i) state-space backbones scale favourably on long audio, (ii) pOE + GRL is an effective fine-tuning strategy for first-shot UASD, and (iii) machine-specific deployment currently offers the best accuracy-latency trade-off for on-device condition monitoring.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We introduced a two-stage embedding-centric framework for Unsupervised Anomaly Sound Detection. The proposed system integrates an efficient AudioMamba State Space Model backbone, accelerated pre-training through space-to-depth spectrogram tokenization (pixel-unshuffle), and a robust domain-adaptive fine-tuning strategy. This fine-tuning stage effectively combines a compact anomaly head that fuses multi-level features with pseudo Outlier Exposure and GRL based domain adaptation techniques. Our comprehensive experiments and ablation studies validated the efficacy of each component. We demonstrated this to be the first application of an SSM backbone for the DCASE Task 2 first-shot UASD challenge, achieving significant improvements in AUC and pAUC metrics over established baselines. The substantial reduction in pre-training time due to pixel-unshuffle, and the enhanced robustness and domain generalization capabilities imparted by the pOE and GRL techniques during fine-tuning, were clearly evidenced.

Several directions look promising. First, experimenting with larger or alternative state–space architectures may unlock further accuracy and speed gains. Second, we will refine pseudo-outlier generation in pOE so it spans a wider range of real-world anomalies. Third, introducing domain-aware loss weighting could make a single, unified model competitive with machine-specific ones. Finally, a fully self-supervised pre-training stage for the backbone would eliminate the need for labelled machine types, easing deployment where annotated data are scarce.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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Low-Complexity Acoustic Scene Classification with Device Information in the DCASE 2025 Challenge

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Abstract—This paper presents the *Low-Complexity Acoustic Scene Classification with Device Information Task* of the DCASE 2025 Challenge, along with its baseline system. Continuing the focus on low-complexity models, data efficiency, and device mismatch from previous editions (2022–2024), this year’s task introduces a key change: recording device information is now provided at inference time. This enables the development of device-specific models that leverage device characteristics—reflecting real-world deployment scenarios in which a model is designed with awareness of the underlying hardware. The training set matches the 25% subset used in the corresponding DCASE 2024 challenge, with no restrictions on external data use, highlighting transfer learning as a central topic. The baseline achieves 50.72% accuracy with a device-agnostic model, improving to 51.89% when incorporating device-specific fine-tuning. The task attracted 31 submissions from 12 teams, with 11 teams outperforming the baseline. The top-performing submission achieved an accuracy gain of more than 8 percentage points over the baseline on the evaluation set.

Index Terms—DCASE Challenge, Acoustic Scene Classification, multiple devices, device information, data-efficiency, low-complexity, transfer learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Acoustic Scene Classification (ASC) aims to identify the type of environment in which an audio recording was made, based on a short excerpt [1]. Environments are defined as a set of real-world locations, such as *Metro station*, *Urban park*, or *Public square*. The ASC task has a long-standing presence in the DCASE Challenge, evolving through various refinements over the years. Recent editions have emphasized challenges relevant to real-world deployment, including low-complexity constraints [2]–[5], recording device mismatch [2], [5], [6], and data efficiency [5]. For example, the 2024 edition required systems to be lightweight enough to operate on embedded devices, to achieve high performance with limited training data, and to generalize across a variety of potentially unknown recording devices. The 2025 edition¹ introduces several modifications compared to the 2024 edition. The most significant change in the 2025 edition is the availability of the recording device ID at inference time. This enables participants to tailor their models to device-specific characteristics, for instance, by fine-tuning the model for the known hardware. This design reflects realistic deployment scenarios where the target device is known in advance and recordings from it may be available to improve prediction accuracy.

Figure 1 illustrates the task setup and baseline training procedure. Training is performed in two stages: a *general model* is first trained on the full available dataset (25% subset from the 2024 edition), followed by adaptation into *device-specific models* using recordings from known devices. At inference, *device-specific models* are used for known devices, while the *general model* handles unknown ones. All

Fig. 1: Overview of *Low-Complexity Acoustic Scene Classification with Device Information*. At inference time, models must operate under low-complexity constraints and handle both known (seen during training) and unknown (unseen during training) recording devices, with the device ID provided. The baseline follows a two-stage training process: first, learning a general model, then adapting it to device-specific characteristics to enhance performance on known devices.

models must comply with the low-complexity constraints, ensuring suitability for embedded devices (ED).

The limited size of the training set reflects real-world scenarios with scarce labeled data, highlighting transfer learning as a key strategy. In contrast to 2024, the 2025 task lifts restrictions on external resources, allowing participants to incorporate additional acoustic scene datasets to improve performance.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 briefly reviews prior approaches to device generalization, low-complexity constraints, and transfer learning in earlier challenge editions. Section 3 details the task setup, and Section 4 presents the baseline system. Results are discussed in Section 5, and conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

¹Task Description Page: <https://dcase.community/challenge2025/task-low-complexity-acoustic-scene-classification-with-device-information>

2. PREVIOUS EDITIONS

In past editions, several strategies were proposed to improve generalization across different—and potentially unknown—recording devices. The most common in 2023 and 2024 were augmentation-based methods, such as Freq-MixStyle [7], [8] and device impulse response augmentation [9]. Others aimed to suppress device information via domain adaptation [10], [11] or normalization [12], while a third line of work adjusted the sampling distribution to balance devices [13].

Over the years, various complexity constraints have been introduced, with the two most recent editions limiting model size to 128 kB and computational cost to 30 million multiply-accumulate operations (30 MMACs), targeting Cortex-M4-class devices. In response, techniques such as Knowledge Distillation [8], Pruning [14], [15], and Sparsification [16] were explored, alongside the design of efficient CNN architectures [15], [17]–[20].

To tackle data scarcity, the 2024 edition saw widespread use of transfer learning from the large-scale general-purpose audio dataset *AudioSet* [21]. Participants leveraged it in three main ways: (1) fine-tuning a large pre-trained model on ASC and distilling it into a low-complexity student [15], [20], [22]; (2) pre-training a low-complexity model directly on *AudioSet* [23]; or (3) extracting task-relevant clips from *AudioSet* for training [24].

3. TASK SETUP

As discussed in the previous section, device mismatch, low-complexity constraints, and transfer learning have been extensively studied in the context of the ASC task. However, this year’s setup introduces key variations to the handling of device mismatch and transfer learning. Regarding device mismatch, the recording device ID is now provided at inference time. Some device IDs may already have appeared in the training data, others may be novel. This will allow participants to develop specialized models for devices known from the training set. For transfer learning, external datasets are no longer limited to general-purpose collections like *AudioSet* [21]. However, related acoustic scene datasets are now permitted. Given these changes, the challenge aims to address the following set of research questions:

- Can device type information be exploited to improve performance compared to previous editions, where it was not available at inference time?
- Which machine learning techniques are most effective for creating specialized models for different recording devices?
- Can additional acoustic scene datasets—possibly featuring different scenes, locations, or devices—help improve performance on the TAU dataset [2], [6]?

3.1. Dataset

The task again builds on top of the *TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile* dataset [2], [6], which was also used in the 2022, 2023, and 2024 editions of the challenge [4], [5]. The dataset provides one-second audio snippets sampled at 44.1 kHz in single-channel, 24-bit format and consists of recordings from ten distinct acoustic scenes.

Audio was captured in multiple European cities using four devices in parallel: a high-quality binaural recorder (primary device *A*) and three consumer devices (*B*, *C*, *D*). Additionally, ten simulated devices (*S1–S10*) were created by applying device-specific impulse responses to recordings from device *A*. For further details on the dataset creation and device distribution, we refer to [2]. This dataset description is based on [5]. The dataset is divided into a *development set* and an *evaluation set*, following a predefined split.

Development Set: The development set contains 64 hours of audio recorded with three real devices (*A*, *B*, *C*) and six simulated devices (*S1–S6*). It is further divided into:

- *Development-train:* This corresponds to the 25% subset used in last year’s data-efficient evaluation setup [5]. It includes recordings from six devices: *A*, *B*, *C*, and *S1–S3*.
- *Development-test:* In addition to the devices in *development-train*, this split includes the remaining simulated devices *S4–S6*, which are unseen during training and serve to evaluate generalization to unknown devices.

Only the *development-train* split (25% subset) and announced external resources may be used for training. The *development-test* split must be used only for evaluation. City and device information are provided for all recordings in the *development set*.

Evaluation Set: The evaluation set includes five unknown devices (*D* and *S7–S10*), as well as two cities that are not present in the *development set*, in addition to recordings from known cities and devices. It is used for final system evaluation and is published without scene labels. Device IDs are provided at inference time, while city information is withheld. Known devices (*A*, *B*, *C*, *S1–S3*) are labeled explicitly, whereas unknown devices (*D*, *S7–S10*) are marked as *unknown*. The ratio of known to unknown devices is kept consistent between the *development-test* and *evaluation sets*.

3.2. Device-Specific Modeling: Problem Setting

In this section, we briefly formalize the problem setting arising from the availability of device information. We assume the training data is drawn from K distinct domains (i.e., devices) D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K , each associated with its own data distribution $p_{D_k}(X)$. The amount of training data per domain varies and is often limited. The domain ID is provided with each training example.

At test time, the system is evaluated on samples originating from a mix of *known* domains (seen during training) and *unknown* domains (unseen during training). For each test sample, the corresponding source domain (i.e., device ID) is provided. This additional information allows for models that specialize in known domains by leveraging domain-specific characteristics, while still requiring a general model to handle unknown domains.

A straightforward strategy to address this setting is to first train a general model across all domains and then adapt it to individual domains using the corresponding in-domain training data. This two-step approach is also implemented in the baseline system, as described in Section 4. Key innovations may lie in the strategy for specializing the general model to the known domains, which may contain only a small number of labeled data points.

3.3. Evaluation and Submission

Submissions are ranked based on class-wise macro-averaged accuracy computed on the evaluation set. As a secondary, operating point-independent metric, multi-class cross-entropy is reported. Each team may submit up to four sets of predictions from different systems. This year, participants must also submit inference code to promote open research and allow additional complexity evaluations by the organizers.

3.4. System Complexity Requirements

The system complexity constraints follow the 2024 edition [5] and apply to each individual model, including both the general model and any device-specific variants. Both model size and computational cost are restricted. Specifically, model parameters must fit within 128 kB of memory, with no fixed numerical precision requirement.

Table 1: Device-wise and overall accuracies of the baseline system on the development-test split.

Model	A	B	C	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	Macro Avg. Accuracy
General Model	62.80	52.87	54.23	48.52	47.29	52.86	48.14	47.23	42.60	50.72 ± 0.47
Device-specific Models	63.98	55.85	59.09	48.68	48.74	52.72	48.14	47.23	42.60	51.89 ± 0.05

Participants are free to trade off the number of parameters against numerical precision; for instance, the limit corresponds to 128K parameters with 8-bit quantization or 32K parameters with 32-bit precision. Computational complexity is capped at 30 MMACs for processing a one-second audio segment. These constraints are designed to reflect the capabilities of resource-constrained devices such as the Cortex-M4 series (e.g., STM32L496@80 MHz or Arduino Nano 33@64 MHz).

4. BASELINE SYSTEM

Following the 2024 edition [5], the baseline system builds on a simplified variant of the top-performing submission from the 2023 edition [25]. It employs a receptive-field-regularized, factorized CNN architecture, referred to as *CP-Mobile*. Audio recordings are first resampled to 32 kHz, then converted into mel spectrograms using a 4096-point FFT with a window size of 96 ms and a hop size of approximately 16 ms, followed by a mel scaling with 256 mel filterbanks.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the system is trained in two stages. In the first stage, a *general model* is trained on data from all devices for 150 epochs using the AdamW optimizer and a batch size of 256. To address device mismatch, Freq-MixStyle [7], [8] is applied during training. In the second stage, for each device in the training set, a *device-specific model* is created by end-to-end fine-tuning the *general model* on data from that specific device for 50 epochs. During inference, device-specific models are applied to known devices, while the general model handles unknown ones.

The baseline system requires 29.4 MMACs to process a one-second audio clip. The model uses 61,148 parameters in 16-bit (fp16) precision, resulting in a total memory footprint of 122.3 kB for the parameters.

Table 1 presents the device-wise and overall accuracies of the baseline system on the development-test split. After Stage 1, the *general model* achieves an overall accuracy of 50.72%. Following Stage 2, where device-specific models are trained, the overall accuracy improves to 51.89%. Device-specific fine-tuning increases the accuracy for all known devices except for S3, with performance gains varying notably across devices. The accuracy on unknown devices remains unchanged between the two rows of the table, as the *general model* is used for inference on unknown devices. The source code and a detailed description of the baseline system are available online².

5. CHALLENGE RESULTS

The task received 31 submissions from 12 teams, with 11 out of 12 teams outperforming the baseline system. For both the baseline and most submitted systems, performance on the development-test split aligned well with that on the evaluation set. Table 2 presents the best-performing system from each team that outperformed the baseline and summarizes their architectural choices, strategies for handling complexity, use of external data, and device adaptation methods. The following subsections discuss each of these aspects in

detail. Additional results and detailed system descriptions are available on the official challenge website³.

5.1. Architectures

Due to the low-complexity constraints, efficient neural network design remained a central focus. In line with last year’s trends [5], most teams adopted factorized convolutional architectures. Five of the twelve teams—including the top-ranked submission—built their systems on the CP-Mobile architecture [25]. However, several top-performing teams proposed novel architectural variants.

Team *Tan_SNTLNTU* [26] introduced *CNN-GRU*, which combines pointwise and 1D depthwise convolutions over the frequency and time dimensions, integrates Squeeze-and-Excitation layers [27], and applies a GRU along the frequency axis. Team *Luo_CQUPT* [28] presented *DynaCP*, a CP-Mobile modification that processes pooling and strided convolutions in parallel and dynamically combines their outputs. Teams *Chang_HYU* [29] and *Ramezane_SUT* [30] built upon reparameterizable convolution blocks [31], which use multiple branches during training that can be merged into a single, efficient equivalent at inference time. Additionally, *Chang_HYU* [29] employed Channel-Time-Frequency Attention (CTFA) [32], a lightweight attention mechanism that allows the model to focus on informative input regions, while *Ramezane_SUT* [30] proposed learnable pooling layers. As input to the models, all teams used log-mel energies, with the exception of two teams that used the spectrogram instead.

5.2. System Complexity

As in previous editions [4], [5], Knowledge Distillation (KD) [33] remained the most widely used model compression technique, employed by 10 out of 12 teams. Compared to previous editions, several interesting variations to the KD process have been explored, such as a feature-level distillation loss [34], device-aware feature alignment loss to train a device-expert teacher [35], and self-distillation [36].

Compared to 2024 [5], where pruning was used only by the top-ranked team [15], this year pruning gained traction, with 3 of the top 6 teams adopting it. Notably, the second-ranked team, *Tan_SNTLNTU* [26], applied pruning exclusively, without using KD. All top-5 teams used 16-bit precision, while none opted for 8-bit quantization—likely due to the ease of reducing to 16-bit with minimal or no accuracy loss, whereas maintaining performance with 8-bit quantization remains more challenging.

5.3. External Data Usage

External data was primarily used in two ways. First, most teams employed teacher models for KD that were pre-trained on AudioSet [21]. PaSST [37] remained a popular choice, though two teams—including the top-ranked one—used BEATs [38], while the third-ranked team, *Luo_CQUPT* [28], used AudioSet-pretrained MobileNets [39] and Dynamic MobileNets [40].

Second, several teams applied Device Impulse Response (DIR) augmentation [9] using impulse responses from MicIRP⁴, increasing the diversity of recording conditions in the training data.

³Results: <https://dcase.community/challenge2025/task-low-complexity-acoustic-scene-classification-with-device-information-results>

⁴<https://micirp.blogspot.com/>

²Source Code: https://github.com/CPJKU/dcse2025_task1_baseline

Table 2: Best-performing system per team (only including systems that outperform the baseline) and the official DCASE2025 baseline. **Score** indicates the accuracy on the evaluation set, **Size** refers to the memory required to store model parameters, and **MAC** denotes the number of multiply-accumulate operations. **External** indicates whether external data was used, and **Device Adaptation** describes the method used to adapt the model to specific devices based on provided device IDs. **KD**, **IR**, and **FT** stand for Knowledge Distillation, Impulse Response augmentation, and Fine-Tuning, respectively.

Team	Score	Size	MAC	Architecture	Complexity	External	Device Adaptation
Karasin_JKU	61.5	122kB	29M	CP-Mobile	fp16,KD	IR,CochlScene,BEATs	Full device-spec. FT
Tan_SNTLNTU	59.9	116kB	10M	CNN-GRU	fp16, prune	IR	Full FT
Luo_CQUPT	59.6	123kB	28M	DynaCP	fp16, KD	EfficientAT	Full FT
Zhang_AITHU-SJTU	59.3	126kB	29M	SSCP-Mobile	fp16,KD,prune	PaSST	–
Chang_HYU	59.0	125kB	29M	Rep-CTFA	fp16,KD	IR,PaSST	Head-only FT
Li_NTU	58.9	122kB	17M	CP-Mobile	KD,prune	IR,PaSST	–
Ramezane_SUT	57.9	125kB	28M	DSFlexiNet	KD	IR	Full FT
Jeong_SEOULTECH	57.9	122kB	26M	CP-Mobile	fp16,KD	PaSST	Full FT
Chen_GXU	56.6	122kB	29M	CP-Mobile	fp16,KD	PaSST	–
Krishna_SRIB	56.1	122kB	27M	CP-Mobile	fp16	–	Full FT
Zhou_XJTLU	55.5	126kB	29M	TF-SepNet	int8,KD	IR,AudioSet,BEATs	Full FT
DCASE25 baseline	53.2	122kB	29M	CP-Mobile	fp16	–	Full FT

Among all participating teams, only the top-ranked team, *Karasin_JKU* [41], took advantage of the new rule allowing external ASC datasets by leveraging CochIScene [42]. CochIScene contains 76,115 ten-second audio clips recorded across 13 distinct acoustic scenes. The dataset was collected via crowdsourcing, primarily from contributors in Korea. Several scene classes overlap partially with those in the *TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile* dataset [2], [6] (e.g., *Bus* and *Park*), though others are unique to CochIScene (e.g., *Restroom* and *Elevator*) or TAU (e.g., *Airport* and *Travelling by Tram*).

Team *Karasin_JKU* [41] explored pre-training both the teacher and student models on CochIScene. Notably, this strategy led to substantial performance improvements for convolutional architectures such as CP-Mobile [25] and CP-ResNet [43], with gains of +3.36 and +6.05 percentage points on the TAU development-test split, respectively. In contrast, transformer-based models like PaSST [37] and BEATs [38] saw only marginal or no improvements.

5.4. Device Adaptation

To exploit the given device information, most teams opted for the baseline strategy of fine-tuning the general model on device-specific data to obtain specialized models. More advanced methods were explored by only a few participants.

Team *Han_CSU* [44] addressed device variability by incorporating device embeddings into the model’s internal representations, effectively conditioning the network on the identity of the recording device.

Team *Chang_HYU* [29] adopted a modular approach by training lightweight, device-specific classification heads while keeping the shared backbone frozen. This design preserves a common, general-purpose acoustic feature extractor across all devices, while allowing for device-tailored classification at the output stage. Importantly, this method keeps the overall system compact, as the additional device-specific components introduce only minimal overhead.

The top-ranked team, *Karasin_JKU* [41], further exploited device information by customizing training configurations—such as Knowledge Distillation hyperparameters—for each device-specific fine-tuning run. In particular, they observed that the optimal loss weighting factor in Knowledge Distillation, which balances the supervised loss and the distillation loss, varies across devices and benefits from device-specific tuning.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced the setup and baseline system for Task 1 of the DCASE 2025 Challenge, which continues to address three core

challenges of acoustic scene classification: low-complexity constraints, device mismatch, and limited training data. A key novelty this year is the availability of device information at inference time, enabling device-specific adaptation and yielding consistent improvements in the baseline system.

While the three research questions outlined in Section 3 remain only partially explored, the top-ranked submission provided valuable initial answers. They showed that fine-tuning routines tailored to specific devices improve performance, and that leveraging external acoustic scene classification datasets such as CochIScene can substantially boost accuracy on the TAU dataset. These strategies delivered an accuracy gain of more than 1.5 percentage points over all other submissions, highlighting promising directions for future work.

Beyond transfer learning and device-aware modeling, participants also advanced research on efficient architectures, Knowledge Distillation, and pruning. Several teams experimented with different teacher models for Knowledge Distillation, while others introduced architectural components for low-complexity models such as lightweight attention mechanisms, reparameterizable convolutions, and learnable pooling layers.

Overall, the 2025 edition of Task 1 advanced established research on low-complexity modeling while providing initial insights into device-aware adaptation and the use of external acoustic scene datasets, laying the groundwork for further exploration in these directions.

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Correlation-Based Filtering for Unsupervised Anomalous Sound Detection

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Abstract—Unsupervised anomalous sound detection (ASD) under domain shift remains a key challenge for real-world deployment. We introduce a two-stage “first-shot” pipeline for DCASE 2025 Task 2 that leverages optional clean-only or noise-only supplemental recordings to improve robustness to unseen background noises. First, a correlation-based filter is trained separately on clean or noise data, separating each test mixture $x = C + N + A$ into a cleaner signal $x' = C + A$. Second, a mel-spectrogram autoencoder, augmented with SMOTE and mixup on x' , detects anomalies. On the development set, our method achieves a high SI-SDR for the separation task and improves the detection metrics for three out of seven components compared to the baseline. These results validate that assuming statistical independence between machine sound, background noise, and anomalies can enhance first-shot ASD. Future work will explore automated correlation estimation and integration with more advanced anomaly detection methods for the second stage.

Index Terms—anomalous sound detection, signal correlation, DCASE, source separation, audio

1. INTRODUCTION

Anomalous sound detection (ASD) has emerged as a critical technology for non-intrusive monitoring of industrial machinery, enabling early warning of mechanical faults through audio analysis [1], [2]. Unsupervised ASD, which relies solely on normal-condition recordings, was first standardized in the DCASE 2020 Challenge Task 2 to address the scarcity and diversity of anomalous examples in real factories [3]. Subsequent editions have progressively incorporated domain-shift and “first-shot” scenarios, in which systems must generalize to unseen operating conditions or entirely new machine types without task-specific tuning [3], [4].

Building on the first-shot unsupervised ASD framework of DCASE 2023 and 2024, the 2025 Task 2 challenge retains the requirement to train exclusively on normal data and to detect anomalies under unknown domain shifts, while introducing optional use of clean-only or noise-only supplementary recordings [4]. Participants must also handle completely novel machine types at evaluation, with no access to anomalous test data for hyperparameter tuning. This “first-shot” setting reflects real-world constraints where rapid deployment precludes exhaustive data collection or manual calibration.

We propose a two-stage pipeline for first-shot ASD: (1) a correlation-based separator that, given clean-only or noise-only supplemental data, filters each test mixture $x = C + N + A$ into $x' = C + A$ as depicted in Figure 1; (2) a mel-spectrogram autoencoder, augmented with SMOTE and mixup trained on x' , to detect anomalies. By leveraging correlation-based filtering, our method enhances robustness to unseen background noises in the DCASE 2025 Task 2 setting.

2. METHOD

We denote clean machine sound by C , background noise by N , and anomalous sound by A . Artificial noise augmentations, N_A , are sampled from diverse sources. We use $\rho(S_1, S_2)$ as the correlation between two signals S_1 and S_2 , where the threshold ε denotes a significant correlation between them. In our two-stage methodology, a first step trains a filtering model which can separate the mixture

$x = C + N + A$ into $x' = C + A$. The second step then involves training an anomaly detection model based on the filtered x' .

Fig. 1: Correlation-based filtering for two components. In (a) we have supplemental = C , thus we perform machine sound extraction. In (b) we have supplemental = N , thus we perform noise extraction.

2.1. Correlation-based Filtering

In the DCASE challenge 2025, we are provided with additional supplemental data which consists of either C or N . For both cases we developed separate filtering strategies. For the evaluation of the filtering quality, we report the scale-invariant signal-to-distortion ratio (SI-SDR), which is commonly used in source separation tasks [5].

2.1.1. Machine Sound Extraction: If we are provided with supplemental data containing the clean machine sound C , we train a source-separation network

$$f_{\theta}(C + N_A) \approx C \quad (1)$$

to recover the clean sound C from noise-augmented inputs $C + N_A$. At inference time on mixture x this will allow us to filter:

$$\hat{y} = f_{\theta}(x) \approx C + A = x' \quad (2)$$

For this filtering to work we introduce the following assumptions:

- 1.1 $\rho(C, N_A) < \varepsilon$ (artificial noise uncorrelated with C)
- 1.2 $\rho(C, N) < \varepsilon$ (background noise uncorrelated with C)
- 1.3 $\rho(C, A) > \varepsilon$ (anomalies strongly correlated with C)
- 1.4 $\rho(N, A) < \varepsilon$ (anomalies uncorrelated with N)
- 1.5 $\rho(C_{\text{source}}, C_{\text{target}}) > \varepsilon$ (machine sound of source is strongly correlated with target)

2.1.2. *Noise Extraction*: If we are provided with supplemental data containing the background sound N , we train a source-separation network

$$f_{\theta}(N + N_A) \approx N \quad (3)$$

to extract background noise N from $N + N_A$. At inference time on mixture x this will allow us to filter:

$$\hat{y} = f_{\theta}(x) \approx N \rightarrow x - \hat{y} = x' \quad (4)$$

For this filtering to work we introduce the following assumptions:

- 2.1 $\rho(N, N_A) < \varepsilon$ (artificial noise uncorrelated with N)
- 2.2 $\rho(A, N_A) < \varepsilon$ (artificial noise uncorrelated with A)
- 2.3 $\rho(C, N) < \varepsilon$ (background noise uncorrelated with C)
- 2.4 $\rho(N, A) < \varepsilon$ (anomalies uncorrelated with N)
- 2.5 $N_{\text{source}} = N_{\text{target}}$ (background sound of source is equal to target)

Assumptions 2.1, 2.2, and 2.5 are new; 2.3 and 2.4 overlap with 1.2 and 1.4, respectively.

2.2. Anomaly Detection

Once we have x' we can theoretically use any of the methods presented in the DCASE challenges 2020-2024, ranging from outlier exposure to inlier modeling and a large diversity of combinations of the two [6]–[9]. We choose to use a similar approach as the baseline of the 2025 challenge, consisting of an autoencoder based on Mel-spectrograms. Additionally, we employ SMOTE [10] for oversampling the target domain and mixup [11] to augment our data. For anomaly detection, we evaluate using the area under the ROC curve (AUC) and partial AUC (pAUC), following the official DCASE challenge metrics [4].

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We adhere to the DCASE 2025 Task 2 protocol [4]. The development dataset provides training and test splits for seven machines: Valve, Bearing, ToyCar, ToyTrain, Slider, Gearbox and Fan, where we have supplemental C in the first three and N in the others. For each component, we first train a correlation-based filter model with the strategy depending on the provided supplemental data. The model is a standard U-Net with input and output being the complex spectrograms of the respective signals using a 64-ms window and 32-ms hop size [12]. U-Net has proven effective for source separation, especially when the thresholds ε in assumptions 1.1 and 2.1 are small. We use a batch size of 32 and a learning rate of 0.0005 to optimize over a multi-resolution STFT loss [13] for 300 epochs with early stopping. To counteract potential violations of assumptions 1.1 and 2.1, we sweep over various SNR ranges and N_A sources and choose the run resulting in the highest adjusted SI-SDR ($= \text{SI-SDR} - \mathbb{E}[\text{SNR}]$) on a 10% holdout validation set, to ensure we cover realistic SNR ratios that are not known in advance.

- N_A sources: {AudioSet full, AudioSet no tools, AudioSet only tools, DCASE Clean (supplemental clean-only), DCASE Noise (supplemental noise-only)},
- SNR windows: [-30,30], [-10,30], [-10,10], [-5,5] dB.

The anomaly detection autoencoder is trained with very similar parameters as the DCASE 2025 baseline. We use a 64-ms window with a 128-bin mel spectrogram over five consecutive windows as a feature vector. The encoder-decoder architecture is a symmetric MLP. We train the model over 100 epochs with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 64.

4. RESULTS

We evaluate our two-stage pipeline on the DCASE 2025 Task 2 development set in three parts: correlation-based filtering on the development data, filtering performance on the additional evaluation data, and anomaly detection on the development set.

Component	SNR [dB]	N_A Source	SI-SDR [dB]
Valve	[-10, 10]	AudioSet full	11.4
ToyTrain	[-10, 10]	DCASE Clean	6.3
ToyCar	[-5, 5]	AudioSet full	5.8
Slider	[-5, 5]	DCASE Clean	6.9
Gearbox	[-5, 5]	DCASE Clean	5.7
Fan	[-5, 5]	DCASE Clean	7.4
Bearing	[-5, 5]	AudioSet full	9.1

Table 1: Best Adjusted SI-SDR results for correlation-based filtering per component in development dataset

First, Table 1 reports the optimal filtering settings and adjusted SI-SDR for each of the seven development components. Valve achieves the highest SI-SDR of 11.4 dB using full AudioSet noise at ± 10 dB, while Bearing achieves 9.1 dB under a narrower ± 5 dB range with the same noise source. ToyTrain (6.3 dB) and ToyCar (5.8 dB) similarly leverage wider SNR windows (± 10 dB and ± 5 dB) with DCASE Clean or AudioSet full augmentations, reflecting their varied spectral content. The remaining components Slider (6.9 dB), Gearbox (5.7 dB), and Fan (7.4 dB) attain the best separation under narrow (± 5 dB) clean-only noise, indicating limited noise variability suffices for these cases.

Component	SNR [dB]	N_A Source	SI-SDR [dB]
AutoTrash	[-5, 5]	AudioSet full	15.29
BandSealer	[-10, 10]	DCASE Clean	6.79
CoffeeGrinder	[-5, 5]	DCASE Clean	11.38
HomeCamera	[-5, 5]	DCASE Clean	12.07
Polisher	[-10, 10]	AudioSet full	5.82
ScrewFeeder	[-5, 5]	AudioSet no tools	8.84
ToyPet	[-5, 5]	DCASE Clean	9.16
ToyRCCar	[-5, 5]	DCASE Clean	8.67

Table 2: Adjusted SI-SDR for correlation-based filtering per component in additional training dataset

Next, Table 2 presents SI-SDR results on eight novel components in the additional evaluation set. Here, SI-SDR ranges from 5.82 dB (Polisher) up to 15.29 dB (AutoTrash), with most components favoring ± 5 dB clean or full-AudioSet noise. This consistency confirms that our correlation-based filter generalizes effectively to unseen machine types in a first-shot scenario.

Component	Baseline	Best 2024	Unfiltered	Filtered
Valve	0.611	0.771	0.669	0.848
ToyTrain	0.557	0.651	0.590	0.564
ToyCar	0.567	0.594	0.588	0.405
Slider	0.561	0.593	0.542	0.600
Gearbox	0.553	0.704	0.547	0.566
Fan	0.499	0.639	0.541	0.545
Bearing	0.598	0.691	0.582	0.734
hmean	0.5617	0.6582	0.5771	0.5775

Table 3: Development dataset detection results. Scores correspond to the harmonic mean of AUC and pAUC. Best 2024 corresponds to [14], best results per row are highlighted in bold.

Finally, Table 3 compares anomaly detection metrics before (“Unfiltered”) and after filtering (“Filtered”), alongside the baseline and the Best 2024 system. We would expect “Filtered” to be similar or better than “Unfiltered” if the filtering indeed transforms our mixture $x = C + N + A$ to $f_{\theta}(x) = C + A = x'$. After filtering, Valve improves from 0.669 to 0.848 (+0.179), Bearing from 0.582 to 0.734 (+0.152), Slider from 0.542 to 0.600 (+0.058) and Gearbox from 0.547 to 0.566 (+0.019), demonstrating that isolating $C + A$ enhances anomaly detection as expected.

Conversely, ToyTrain (0.590 \rightarrow 0.564, -0.026) and ToyCar (0.588 \rightarrow 0.396, -0.183) degrade, indicating their anomalies may not align with our independence assumptions. Overall, the harmonic mean across components increases slightly from 0.5771 to 0.5775 (+0.0004), evidencing modest benefits of filtering on average across all machines, which is mostly due to the bad results on the ToyCar and ToyTrain components.

5. DISCUSSION

The experimental results demonstrate that our correlation-based filtering effectively enhances anomaly detection when the underlying independence assumptions hold. For components such as Valve, Bearing, and Slider, the filter succeeded in isolating the machine signal plus anomaly, leading to clear gains in anomaly detection (Table 3, Figure 1). This indicates that, for these machines, (1) background noise and artificial augmentations remain uncorrelated with the clean sound ($\rho(C, N_A) < \epsilon$ and $\rho(N, N_A) < \epsilon$), and (2) anomalous events retain sufficient correlation with the machine signature ($\rho(C, A) > \epsilon$) to survive filtering.

Fig. 2: Both components in (a) and (b) produce non-stationary sounds that are correctly filtered. However, they may violate assumptions 1.3, 1.4, and 2.4 because the anomalous sound may be weakly correlated with the machine sound, for example, by only occurring during the ramp-up or ramp-down phase.

In contrast, ToyTrain and ToyCar exhibit performance degradations after filtering, with detection scores falling by 0.026 and 0.183 respectively. Their non-stationary operating cycles with ramp-up, steady, and ramp-down phases appear to violate the assumption that anomalies strongly co-vary with the baseline machine sound. As a result, the filter may remove or attenuate anomalous components along with noise, harming detection (Figure 2). Introducing additional

transformations such as windowing could help with this issue but requires further work. Fan and Gearbox exhibit only modest detection gains after filtering, indicating partial alignment with our independence assumptions. We attribute this to an under-representation of background noise in the supplemental data (see Figure 3): for Fan, the supplemental recordings contain only stationary noise which might be easier to detect in STFT, whereas the development and evaluation sets also include non-stationary events such as hammering and grinding. Consequently, the filtering model cannot learn to suppress these dynamic noise components, leaving residual interference in x' and limiting the achievable improvement. We made very similar observations for Gearbox.

(a) Sample of fan supplemental background noise (b) Sample of fan training data

Fig. 3: In (a) we see a representative sample from supplemental data for Fan, which is stationary. In (b) we can see that the actual training data contains obvious non-stationary background events, such as grinding. The correlation-based filter model does not remove these events because it has never encountered them before.

On the additional evaluation set, the filter generalizes effectively to eight novel components, yielding SI-SDR scores between 5.82 dB and 15.29 dB (Table 2). Although absolute separation quality varies with machine-noise spectral overlap, the consistent performance across unseen machines confirms the robustness of our first-shot filtering approach.

6. CONCLUSION

We have presented a two-stage “first-shot” pipeline for unsupervised anomalous sound detection, combining correlation-based filtering with a mel-spectrogram autoencoder. By grid-searching SNR windows and noise-augmentation sources, our method adaptively separates each mixture into machine-plus-anomaly signals before a simple reconstruction-based error detection. On the DCASE 2025 Task 2 development set, filtering improved detection metrics for the majority of components. On the eight unseen machines we find a similar separation performance range as for the development dataset using the same hyperparameter grid. Future work will explore automated estimation of signal correlations to select augmentations per machine and integration with more sophisticated anomaly detectors that can tolerate partial assumption violations.

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Towards Audio-based Zero-Shot Action Recognition in Kitchen Environments

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Abstract—Human actions often generate sounds that can be recognized to infer their cause. In action recognition, actions can usually be broken down to a combination of verbs and nouns, of which there exist a very large number of enumerations. Contemporary datasets, like EPIC-KITCHENS, cover a wide gamut of the potential action space, but not its entirety. Arguably, the holistic characterization of human actions through the sounds they generate requires the use of zero-shot learning (ZSL). In this contribution, we explore the feasibility of ZSL for recognizing a) nouns, b) verbs, or c) actions on Epic-Kitchens. To achieve this, we use linguistic intermediation, by generating descriptions of each word corresponding to our classes using a pre-trained large language model (LLAMA-2). Our results show that human action recognition from sounds is possible in zero-shot fashion, as we consistently obtain results over chance.

Index Terms—zero-shot classification, computer audition, machine learning, action recognition

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite significant strides in the field of computer audition in recent years [1], achieving a level of auditory perception comparable to that of humans remains a considerable challenge [2]. In the case of humans interacting with their environment, achieving a comprehensive understanding of audio involves the intricate task of perceiving all actions embedded within a particular soundscape. This challenge is amplified by the fact that, in psychology, the identification of sound events by humans is deeply intertwined with the recognition of associated actions [3]. However, the multifaceted nature of human interactions with their environment gives rise to a seemingly inexhaustible array of potential action categories. This inherent complexity poses a significant challenge, making it impractical to train a model capable of recognizing every conceivable category or combination. In this regard, zero-shot learning (ZSL) proves ideal, as it generalizes findings from known classes and their combinations to new ones and thus excels in identifying categories that were previously unknown or unseen [2], [4].

As for ZSL, the majority of progress in zero-shot action recognition (ZSAR) has predominantly occurred within the field of computer vision, leveraging semantic information such as video captions and other text data [5]–[7]. Accordingly, mostly visual or audio-visual data have been investigated, not only for ZSAR but action recognition (AR) in general [8]–[11], while audio was often neglected. Some popular datasets employed for AR, such as HMDB51 [12] or UCF101 [13], do not even contain audio or only have partial audio information. As mentioned by Elizalde et al. [3], audio is an extremely important factor for people to be able to recognize actions. In this regard, verbs are often closely tied to characteristic sounds that reflect actions, interactions between objects, and occasionally the material composing the objects [3]. We therefore want to investigate an audio-based ZSAR approach in this study.

Similar to computer vision, it is common for audio-based ZSL approaches to leverage textual descriptions of the target classes, their features, or related information as meta information [14]–[17]. These auxiliary data can be textual descriptions of the sound classes or even the labels themselves [14], descriptions of what the target classes sound like [15], or descriptions of the musical concepts which shall be modeled in music [17]. Among the latest breakthroughs when it comes to audio-based ZSL are modifications of the CLIP approach in computer vision, exemplified by Wav2CLIP [18], AudioCLIP [19], or CLAP [16].

While ZSL has gained popularity in the audio domain, we have not come across any prior studies exploring audio-based ZSAR. This paper takes a step in that direction by carrying out initial investigations. For this purpose, we employ the EPIC-KITCHENS dataset [20], [21], which contains egocentric videos of people interacting with objects in their home kitchen environments. We chose this dataset due to the non-scripted daily activities, the availability of audio for all annotated actions, as well as the fact that the videos were narrated by the participants themselves afterwards. Furthermore, each action comprises a verb and a noun (e.g., “cut tomato”), enabling their separate investigation.

We also note that the recently published EPIC-SOUNDS dataset [22] also holds the potential to capture audible actions. Nevertheless, the dataset’s action classes predominantly center around collisions and materials, giving rise to classifications like “metal-only” or “cut / chop”. Our objective, however, is to delve into the identification of the actual object(s) engaged in an interaction, alongside discerning the corresponding verb that describes or characterizes the action.

We primarily want to investigate if ZSAR based solely on audio is possible. To do this, we adopt artificially generated textual descriptions of how the actions sound as meta information. Thus, for each annotated action, we use LLAMA-2 [23], a large language model (LLM), to generate a corresponding textual description. This description is then adopted as auxiliary information for the ZSL process. We draw inspiration for this approach from the usage of artificially generated video captions in [6] as well as the textual sound descriptions for various bird species in [15] for ZSL. We furthermore distinguish the three scenarios of classifying 1) the verb, 2) the noun of an action, as well as 3) the action itself. In our modeling approach, we leverage recent research in audio-based ZSL and primarily utilize a standard ZSL method [14], [15]. Our objective is to conduct initial experiments rather than pursue state-of-the-art results. In doing so, we also explore the textual embeddings of the verbs and nouns and how they influence the model performance. The code repository of this work is publicly available on GitHub¹.

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¹<https://github.com/CHI-TUM/epic-kitchens-zsl>

Table 1: Statistics about the utilized data. The minimum (Min), maximum (Max), and average (Avg) are reported w. r. t. the **amount** (left) and the **total duration** (right) of the audio segments per class.

Class	Σ			Total Duration (in s)		
	Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg
VERB	1	14 648	680	1.1	37 802	2 118
NOUN	2	3 576	330	1.7	9 032	716
ACTION	1	1 768	19	.3	3 688	59

2. DATA

We utilize the publicly available data from both EPIC-KITCHENS-100 [21] and EPIC-KITCHENS-55 [20] for our experiments. In particular, we adopt the training data from both datasets and split them into our own subsets in Section 3.2. As the test data does not come with annotated actions we neglect it. Based on the timestamps of the annotated actions we extract the action segments from the provided videos and convert them to .mp3 format, as we only exploit the audio stream. In total, we have 57 hours of audio, averaging 3.12 seconds per file.

The annotated actions are based on the narrations by the participants themselves. The core components of a narration are one verb and at least one noun. If multiple nouns are present in a narration, only the first one is considered for the action, as done in the original paper describing the dataset [20]. An action a_i for an audio segment i is defined as $a_i = (v_i, n_i)$ with v_i and n_i being the corresponding verb and noun class. For instance, the narration “add banana to jug” describes the action tuple (add, banana), thus comprising the verb class *add* and the noun class *banana*. Note that we omitted prepositional objects (“to jug”), same as the original authors of the data [20]. In total, our extracted subset from the EPIC-KITCHENS datasets comprises 97 verb, 287 noun, and 3 507 action categories. However, there is a considerable data imbalance regarding the amount of audio segments for each verb / noun / action class which is illustrated by Table 1.

Audio descriptions: We extract artificially generated textual descriptions as meta-information that describe the expected sound of the corresponding action. This approach is inspired by the incorporation of artificially generated video captions in [6] as well as the leveraging of textual sound descriptions in [15]. For this purpose, we employ LLAMA-2² [23], specifically, the instruction fine-tuned 7-billion parameter model, to generate adequate textual descriptions, representing the auditory characteristics associated with the specific actions. To achieve this, we utilize an appropriately designed prompting template, tailored for sound description tasks. Integrating the specific action as a variable in the prompting strategy, we guide the LLM in producing the final description. The utilized prompt is presented in Table 2. The following quote, belonging to the narration “add banana to jug” from above, gives an impression of these generated descriptions:

“Adding a banana to a jug produces a distinctive ‘slosh’ sound, followed by a slight ‘gurgling’ or ‘splashing’ noise as the fruit settles at the bottom of the container.”

3. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the employed features and how they are extracted, the utilized zero-shot classification method, and the experimental setup of this study.

²<https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-2-7b-chat-hf>

Table 2: Prompt employed with LLAMA-2 to generate textual sound descriptions, where $\{\text{ACTION}\}$ is replaced by each narration from the EPIC-KITCHENS dataset.

Prompt template
<pre><s>[INST] <<SYS>> You are a highly skilled audio engineer with expertise in accurately describing sounds from various actions in everyday life. I will provide you with a “kitchen action” and your task is to give me a short, precise and accurate description of the sound produced by the specific action in the phrase. The question is, how does this action sound like in terms of auditioning<< /SYS>> “{ACTION}”. [INST] This action sounds like: ###Response:</pre>

Audio features: We utilize audio spectrogram transformer (AST) embeddings as audio features, obtained through a state-of-the-art AST model³ [24]. Prior to extracting the embeddings, the audio files are resampled to 16 kHz. The process involves converting each audio file into a 2D array representation, followed by temporal averaging to derive a 1D vector with a dimensionality of 768.

Text embeddings: We also apply a pre-trained Transformer-based language model to obtain representative embeddings for the LLAMA-2 text descriptions. For this purpose, we deploy SENTENCE-BERT (SBERT), an adaptation of the BERT model [25], which was proposed by Reimers and Gurevych [26] and is intended to reflect semantic similarity in generated sentence and paragraph embeddings. As BERT and SBERT showed no discernible difference in [15], we choose the latter variant. This decision is grounded in the notion that extracting the semantic meaning from our text descriptions is expected to be more feasible than handling the onomatopoeia of bird sounds in the case of [15]. We select the paraphrase-multilingual-mpnet-base-v2 model⁴ from the available set of pre-trained SBERT models⁵ and call the provided pooling method to yield the embedding vector of size 768.

Since we extract the SBERT embeddings for every LLAMA-2 description from Section 2, every audio file has a corresponding text embedding vector. For our ZSL approach, which will be described in Section 3.1, we require one text embedding vector for each class. Considering that a class is usually annotated to multiple audio files, we take into account all of these files and their corresponding LLAMA-2 descriptions. Since we now possess the SBERT embeddings for each of these descriptions, we can average them to obtain a singular text embedding vector for each class. That is, for each of our three use cases of classifying either the 1) verb, 2) noun, or 3) action, we create a .csv file which contains the classes together with their corresponding text embedding vector.

3.1. Model Training

The ZSL methodology implemented in this study is the one from Gebhard et al. [15], building upon the foundation laid by previous studies from Xie et al. [14] and Akata et al. [27]. They employ a compatibility function on an acoustic-semantic projection to classify the sound classes. This compatibility function is leveraged by a ranking hinge loss in their training process, with the sound class exhibiting the highest compatibility deemed correct. The aim is for the top-ranked class embeddings to provide the most accurate description of the audio sample.

Following the approaches of [15] and [14], we employ a single linear layer equipped with as many neurons as the size of the

³https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/model_doc/audio-spectrogram-transformer

⁴<https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/paraphrase-multilingual-mpnet-base-v2>

⁵<https://www.sbert.net>

Fig. 1: Overview of the zero-shot learning pipeline adapted from [14], [15]. Audio samples are converted into acoustic embeddings using an AST model and projected into a shared semantic space. LLAMA-2-generated textual descriptions are encoded via SBERT to obtain class embeddings. The classification is based on the highest compatibility score between acoustic and class embeddings.

corresponding class embeddings to project the acoustic embeddings onto the class embeddings. Furthermore, we apply the dot product as our compatibility function. The schematic representation of our pipeline is depicted in Fig. 1.

3.2. Experimental Setup

For our experiments, we employed a non-exhaustive cross-validation approach, aiming to ensure an ample amount of data for training. Consequently, we opted for an 80 – 10 – 10 split for each of the five splits. We took explicit care to ensure that these three sets of a split were mutually exclusive, meaning that no classes could appear in the other two sets. In generating the five splits, we also ensured that the development and test sets, in relation to the other four splits, consistently contained different classes, thereby avoiding any overlap.

Our study assesses the efficacy of the ZSL approach outlined in Section 3.1 when paired with the artificially generated meta-information expounded in Section 2. The experiments are executed across the five splits, and the average performance on the development/test sets is reported. We furthermore opt for three different random seeds to initialize our model and also take the mean of those.

We conduct training for a total of 30 epochs, utilizing an Adam optimizer with a learning rate of .0001 and a batch size of 16. As a compatibility function for our ranking loss, we employ the dot product, as mentioned in Section 3.1. Subsequently, the model state demonstrating optimal performance on the development set is selected for evaluation on the test set. Before analyzing the results, we conduct an exploratory data analysis on the text embeddings of the verb and noun classes to gain insights into the underlying relationships. Section 4 offers the results and the corresponding discussion.

4. RESULTS

The metrics used for the evaluation are a superset of the metrics utilized in the EPIC-KITCHENS papers [20], [21]. We use unweighted accuracy (UA), weighted accuracy (WA), and unweighted precision (UP). UA is calculated by computing the recall for each class and then averaging the results; the same is done for UP just with the precision. WA is instead computed by taking the percentage of correctly classified examples – and is thus agnostic to class imbalance. Therefore, WA can be considered as a broad overview of model performance, while UA and UP take class imbalances more into account.

(a) Cosine similarities among the verb embeddings. (b) Cosine similarities among the noun embeddings.

Fig. 2: The pairwise cosine similarity matrices for the SBERT embeddings of the (a) verb and (b) noun classes depicted as heat maps. Each cell represents the similarity between two class descriptions. The noun embeddings exhibit clearer differentiation, suggesting stronger separability in the text embedding space.

4.1. Exploratory data analysis

For our analysis we resort to cosine similarity visualized as heatmaps and t-SNE pairwise distance visualized as scatter plot.

Cosine similarities: First, we conduct an analysis of pairwise cosine similarities within the text embeddings of the verb and noun classes. The action classes, being composed of verb and noun classes, are not considered in this analysis, allowing us to focus on the smaller components. Our aim is to gauge the strength of the textual embeddings for both the verb and noun classes, to determine which embeddings impart more distinct characteristics. Specifically, we calculate the pairwise cosine similarity between the (S)BERT embeddings of each category and every other category. This computation results in a matrix of cosine similarities w.r.t. those embeddings. Visualized in Fig. 2 as heatmaps, these matrices reveal that noun embeddings manifest more distinct representations across various classes. As a result, we anticipate the noun classification use case to relatively outperform verb classification in terms of model performance. Section 4.2 presents the results and discussions.

t-SNE distances: To further understand the relationship between the text embeddings of different classes, we apply t-SNE (t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding) [28] to the textual embeddings for both the verbs as well as the nouns. This way, we can visualize the high-dimensional data in a lower-dimensional, 2D space⁶. Before creating the plots, we annotate the verb and noun categories to the groups specified in [21], to allow a better analysis. There are 13 verb and 21 noun groups. t-SNE has a tendency to group similar data points in the reduced-dimensional space. If embedding vectors from different classes form distinct clusters, it suggests that the original high-dimensional vectors carry information that allows for effective class separation. Knowing this and looking at the plots depicted in Fig. 3 we can, therefore, make several assumptions. For a clearer and more detailed view, we recommend inspecting the interactive plots provided in the supplementary material.

First, when looking at the t-SNE plot of the verb classes it is hard to identify some groups. The only noticeable groups are the verbs belonging to the “monitor” or the “split” group. Unfortunately, even these groups exhibit verb classes that are quite distantly related. However, there are also two small clusters in which the classes are

⁶Interactive t-SNE plots are attached as HTML-files in the supplementary material for easier visualization.

Table 3: The mean results over the development (Dev) and test (Test) sets of the five splits from Section 3.2, also averaged over three different model initialization seeds. The standard deviation (STD) for the three seeds is also presented. The displayed metrics are UA, UA, and UP). The UA-score poses the main evaluation metric. The random chance UA for the categories would be .100, .034, and .003 for the verb, noun, and action class, respectively.

Set	Dev			Test		
	UA	UP	WA	UA	UP	WA
VERB	.179	.144	.261	.165	.136	.194
STD	.005	.024	.024	.023	.040	.087
NOUN	.065	.061	.081	.066	.066	.129
STD	.008	.014	.010	.007	.012	.005
ACTION	.027	.031	.056	.029	.031	.062
STD	.001	.001	.002	.001	.001	.002

semantically connected to each other but belong to different groups. The first one is on the top right corner of the plot. It consists of four different groups comprising semantically connected verbs (knead, roll, form, unroll, stretch, fold) in the context of food preparation or cooking, especially in the process of manipulating or shaping food or dough. The other small cluster can be identified at the bottom center of the plot. The contained verbs (soak, pour, fill, wash, filter, etc.) are related through the general theme of actions associated with the handling and manipulation of liquids, particularly water.

Regarding the nouns, we can determine more distinct groups, even though there is still a lot of confusion in the center of the plot. Some well recognizable groups are the nouns belonging to food categories, such as “fruits and nuts”, “meat and substitute”, or “vegetables”. In addition, other groups that are easily distinguishable are “appliances” or “materials”. Even though some groups can sometimes be mixed with other groups, such as “vegetables” and “spices and herbs and sauces”, this makes sense, since these groups are highly related in reality as well. In fact, most of the food categories are grouped close to each other or are intertwined. There are also some groups which are quite versatile in reality and have connections to many other categories, which is reflected by them being hard to group and distinguish in the plot, such as “utensils” or “rubbish”. In general, it seems as the food categories are more on the left side of the plot whereas the furniture and materials categories are more on the right side. However, there are also some noun groups which are hard to distinguish from the others, such as “utensils” or “furniture”. These analyses are another indicator for a better model performance when regarding the noun classification compared to the verb classification.

4.2. Experimental Results

The zero-shot classification (ZSC) results are depicted in Table 3 and show that each of the three uses cases 1) verb, 2) noun, and 3) action classification, mentioned in Section 1, surpassed random chance UA. We have 10 verb, 29 noun, and 251 action test classes in each of the five splits, leading to random UAs of .100, .034, and .003, respectively. As expected in Section 4.1, the noun classification could achieve better results w. r. t. relative model performance than the verbs. This suggests that the better distinction for nouns, indicated by the similarity heatmaps and t-SNE plots in Section 4.1, transferred to improved zero-shot classification performance as well.

The ZSC results w. r. t. the action classes are the best out of the three uses cases, relatively spoken, as they achieve a UA ten times

Fig. 3: The t-SNE pairwise similarities for the SBERT embeddings of the (a) verb and (b) noun groups. While noun groups exhibit more distinct clusters (especially food-related categories), verb groups appear less separable

higher than random guessing. It is also the most stable across the three seeds. Our interpretation in this regard is based on the fact that an action in this study consists of a verb and noun class. Accordingly, a verb can theoretically be associated with all existing noun classes and vice versa. This, in turn, means that while an action class is unique, the verb or noun of the action can also appear in other actions. For instance, the verb “add” from the action “(add, banana)” is also part of the action “(add, apple)”. Therefore, we assume that even in our zero-shot setting, where no training class is present in the test set, the information about the verb or noun class is incorporated in the text embedding of other actions and thus also trained on – i.e., there is some amount of *information leakage* between the train and the test set. This furthermore suggests that the model recognizes this partial knowledge of seen in unseen classes. This could explain the substantial performance gap observed between the action and the verb / noun ZSC. However, coming back to the main goal of this work, we achieve results better than chance for each of the three use cases, confirming the feasibility of audio-based ZSAR.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study we investigated the feasibility audio-based ZSAR on the EPIC-KITCHENS dataset. Textual descriptions of the action sounds were artificially generated by an LLM and leveraged as meta information. Our model surpassed random chance in all three use cases 1) verb, 2) noun, and 3) action ZSC, achieving a mean UA of .165, .066, .029 for the verb, noun, and action classes over the five test sets and three seeds. The unweighted random chance of guessing would be .100, .034, and .003 for the verb, noun, and action class, respectively. The t-SNE visualizations based on the textual embeddings revealed challenges in verb grouping, while noun categories demonstrated clearer distinctions, especially in food-related classes. In general, ZSC performed exceptionally well on the action task, attaining ten times better performance than random chance – indicating the model’s ability to recognize partial knowledge of seen in unseen classes. These findings support the potential of audio-based ZSAR and showcase promising results for future applications.

Future work can analyze a variety of other meta information, such as extracting the textual embeddings directly from LLAMA-2 or meta information from other modalities, such as image or video embeddings. Since vision has typically been the main modality [10] it would be interesting to apply it as additional information. The model performance can further be improving by a more tight integration of audio and large language models, as in the case of CLAP [16] or Pengi [29].

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Handling Domain Shifts for Anomalous Sound Detection: A Review of DCASE-Related Work

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Abstract—When detecting anomalous sounds in complex environments, one of the main difficulties is that trained models must be sensitive to subtle differences in monitored target signals, while many practical applications also require them to be insensitive to changes in acoustic domains. Examples of such domain shifts include changing the type of microphone or the location of acoustic sensors, which can have a much stronger impact on the acoustic signal than subtle anomalies themselves. Moreover, users typically aim to train a model only on source domain data, which they may have a relatively large collection of, and they hope that such a trained model will be able to generalize well to an unseen target domain by providing only a minimal number of samples to characterize the acoustic signals in that domain. In this work, we review and discuss recent publications focusing on this domain generalization problem for anomalous sound detection in the context of the DCASE challenges on acoustic machine condition monitoring.

Index Terms—anomalous sound detection, domain shift, domain adaptation, domain generalization, machine condition monitoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Anomalous sound detection (ASD) has a wide range of applications, including acoustic monitoring of machines [1]–[5], health [6], [7], roads [8], smart home environments [9], or public places [10]. The goal in all these applications is to distinguish between normal and anomalous audio recordings. Usually, ASD systems are trained exclusively with normal data, as anomalous data is often difficult and costly to obtain.

One of the major difficulties that ASD systems need to overcome is how to robustly handle so-called *domain shifts*, changes in the recorded audio signal that are caused by changes in acoustic environments, sensors, or properties of monitored sound sources themselves. Inherently, domain shifts have a strong impact on the audio signal and thus also affect the outcome of ASD systems if no precautions are taken. However, in most applications, this effect is not desirable and should be suppressed. Ideally, trained ASD systems should be completely insensitive to domain shifts, while being very sensitive to modifications of the monitored target signals that indicate the occurrence of application-dependent anomalies. As these differences may be very subtle compared to changes caused by domain shifts, especially in noisy environments with many sound sources, developing ASD systems that perform well in domain-shifted conditions is very challenging.

This paper, which extends a non-peer reviewed manuscript [11], reviews the latest works on how to handle domain shifts for ASD in the context of the annual DCASE challenge [12]. We first describe the challenges posed by domain shifts and the resulting *domain mismatch*, illustrated in Fig. 1. We then describe the two main types of approaches to handling them, *domain adaptation (DA)* and *domain generalization (DG)*, defining the terms, listing publicly available datasets, and reviewing recently published works related to these topics. Last but not least, the limitations of different approaches are discussed and future directions of research are identified.

Fig. 1: Illustration of the domain mismatch between the anomaly scores of a source domain and a target domain. Normal and anomalous samples are usually less well separated in the target domain than in the source domain, which decreases domain-independent performance over the performance obtained for the source domain alone. Furthermore, the optimal decision thresholds for separating the scores belonging to the normal and anomalous data of different data domains differ substantially, which significantly decreases performance when using only a single threshold for both domains.

2. DOMAIN SHIFTS

The goal of ASD is to determine, based on a sound recording of a phenomenon, whether that phenomenon is normal or anomalous. In the context of the DCASE Challenges, the objective is to differentiate between normal and anomalous sounds produced by a known type of machine. The normal/anomalous characteristic of a phenomenon is an intrinsic property of that phenomenon: as such, the determination by the ASD system should ideally be independent of the conditions in which the sound was recorded, as long as the change in conditions does not alter the observability and nature of the phenomenon’s normal/anomalous characteristic. Such changes include the use of microphones of different types or in different locations, the presence or absence of other sound sources, or modifications in certain properties of the monitored sound sources themselves, e.g., the use of different settings of the monitored machines.

ASD systems are however often placed in a conundrum: their only view of the phenomenon’s normal/anomalous characteristic is via a training set of normal data recorded under a certain set of conditions, referred to as a *source domain*, and they are expected to make a determination on the normal/anomalous characteristic on a new sample recorded under a potentially different set of conditions, referred to as a *target domain*, for which they only have a few training samples. Changes in the recording conditions occurring between the source domain and the target domain constitute a so-called *domain shift*. ASD systems thus need to implicitly disentangle the effects on the sound signal of the normal/anomalous characteristic and the recording conditions, in order to be robust to changes in these conditions.

An additional difficulty lies in the large imbalance often observed in

Table 1: DCASE ASD datasets in domain-shifted conditions.

Name	Purpose	# machine types			# sections (per machine type)			split	# recordings (per section)				
		total	dev. set	eval. set	total	dev. set	eval. set		source domain		target domain		supplemental
									normal	anomalous	normal	anomalous	
DCASE2021 [1]	DA	7	7	7	6	3	3	train test	1000 100	0 100	3 100	0 100	0 0
DCASE2022 [2]	DG	7	7	7	6	3	3	train test	990 50	0 50	10 50	0 50	0 0
DCASE2023 [3]	DG	14	7	7	1	1	1	train test	990 50	0 50	10 50	0 50	0 0
DCASE2024 [4]	DG	16	7	9	1	1	1	train test	990 50	0 50	10 50	0 50	0 0
DCASE2025 [5]	DG	14	7	7	1	1	1	train test	990 50	0 50	10 50	0 50	100 0

practice between the number of available training samples in the source and target domains. Many training samples are typically available for the source domain, while only a few training samples may be available for the target domain. Recording a large amount of new training samples after a domain shift occurred may be impractical, as it requires much effort, and thus is very costly; domain shifts may also frequently or even continuously occur; and operators may not even be aware of such domain shifts.

A consequence of domain shifts related to differences in signal space is that anomaly scores are usually also distributed very differently across both domains. This results in a so-called *domain mismatch*, illustrated in Fig. 1. Since the embedding models were trained with no or few samples belonging to the target domain, the anomaly score distributions for the normal and anomalous samples are not well-separated in the target domain, which inherently leads to a worse ASD performance than in the source domain. Furthermore, the optimal decision thresholds differ substantially, further degrading the performance if the same decision threshold is used for both domains.

3. DOMAIN ADAPTATION

One way to handle domain shifts is to adapt an existing ASD system that was trained with sufficient data from a source domain to a specific target domain. Here, the main challenge is that the training set for the target domain consists of only very few samples and thus knowledge from the source domain, which may differ substantially from the target domain, needs to be transferred somehow to obtain a well-performing system. Note that once a system is adapted to a target domain, it may no longer perform well in the source domain it was trained on.

3.1. Datasets

A dataset focusing on handling domain shifts for ASD through DA is the DCASE2021 ASD dataset [1]. This dataset contains 10 s recordings of five different machine types from MIMII DUE [13] and two additional machine types from ToyADMOS2 [14] that are combined with background noise from real factories. The dataset is divided into a development set and an evaluation set, which both contain three sections for each machine type. These sections are specific partitions of the dataset for calculating the performance and may contain recordings from multiple machines of the same type. Both the development and evaluation sets consist of a training split and a test split. The training splits contain only normal data, of which 1,000 samples belong to the source domain and only 3 samples belong to the target domain, resulting in a very imbalanced dataset in terms of domain. For each training file, additional attribute information about machine settings or the acoustic environment is provided, and it can be utilized for training ASD systems. The test splits contain 200 samples for each domain, of which one half are normal and the other

half are anomalous. For each test file, it is known whether these files belong to the source or the target domain, but it is unknown whether they are normal or anomalous. Summarized statistics of this dataset can be found in the top part of Table 1.

3.2. Approaches

Approaches for DA mostly focus on first training an ASD system with data from the source domain and then adapting this trained system to a specific target domain. One possibility to do this is to fine-tune an entire model that was trained in the source domain with data belonging to the target domain [15], [16]. This changes the problem of balancing the very differently sized training datasets of both domains to a problem of preventing the model from overfitting to the few target domain samples available for training. In [17], only the parameters of batch normalization layers [36] are fine-tuned to the target domain to minimize the computational costs needed for the adaptation while also reducing overfitting effects. A similar idea based on domain-specific normalization layers is realized in [18] by using AutoDIAL [37]. The authors of [19] propose to use gradient-based meta learning [38] and a prototypical loss [39] in order to more effectively adapt to target domains with only a very small amount of training samples. Another DA approach is to simply train a joint embedding model for both domains but estimate the distributions of each domain individually [16], [20]. Table 2 briefly summarizes all mentioned approaches.

4. DOMAIN GENERALIZATION

Adapting models for each new domain with the possible need of re-training models, fine-tuning hyperparameters, or even replacing system components is very impractical, as it is computationally costly and may require expert knowledge. It is thus much more desirable to strive for domain generalization (DG) [40], [41], with the goal of obtaining a model that performs well in the source domain and generalizes well to unseen target domains by only providing a few samples to define how normal sounds belonging to these domains should sound like. Since DG is literally a generalization of DA to arbitrary domains rather than a specific target domain, it is more difficult to obtain such a model. To highlight the practical differences between DA and DG, the reader is reminded that for DA, models can be fully adapted to a specific target domain, even if performance in the source domain is weak after adaptation. In contrast, DG requires strong performance in the source and target domain, using even the same decision threshold for the anomaly scores in both domains.

4.1. Datasets

Currently, there are four DCASE ASD datasets focusing on DG: the DCASE2022 [2], DCASE2023 [3], DCASE2024 [4], and DCASE2025 [5] datasets, which are all based on MIMII DG [42] as well as,

Table 2: ASD approaches for handling domain shifts.

Topic	Strategy	Reference	Main idea	DCASE datasets used
DA	-	Chen et al [15]	fine-tune model	2021
DA	-	Kuroyanagi et al [16]	fine-tune models and domain-specific backends	2021
DA	-	Yamaguchi et al [17]	fine-tune batch normalization layers	other
DA	-	Lopez et al [18]	domain-specific normalization with AutoDIAL	2021
DA	-	Chen et al [19]	gradient-based meta learning	2021
DA	-	Wilkinghoff [20]	domain-specific backends	2021
DG	domain specialization	Kuroyanagi et al [21]	domain-specific models and domain classifier	2022
DG	domain specialization	Kuroyanagi et al [21]	balance mini-batches with mixup	2022
DG	domain specialization	Guan et al [22]	balance domains with SMOTE	2022
DG	domain specialization	Junjie et al [23]	balance domains with SMOTE	2023
DG	domain specialization	Chen et al [24]	balance domains with SMOTE and a mixup variant	2022,2023
DG	domain-invariant representations	Deng et al [25]	normalize samples independently for each batch	2022
DG	domain-invariant representations	Nejjar et al [26]	VICreg extension with mixup	2022
DG	domain-invariant representations	Yan et al [27]	minimize covariance differences between domains	2020, 2022
DG	feature disentanglement	Venkatesh et al [28]	discriminative tasks for sections and attributes	2022
DG	feature disentanglement	Dohi et al [29]	disentangle attributes with normalizing flow	other
DG	feature disentanglement	Lan et al [30]	Mahalanobis distances for hierarchical metadata	2022
DG	feature disentanglement	Guan et al [31]	gradient reversal with hierarchical metadata	2022
DG	anomaly score calculation	Harada et al [32]	domain-specific Mahalanobis distance	2022
DG	anomaly score calculation	Wilkinghoff [33]	nearest neighbor based anomaly scores	2022
DG	anomaly score calculation	Wilkinghoff et al [34]	local density based score normalization	2020, 2023, 2024
DG	anomaly score calculation	Saengthong et al [35]	domain-wise standardization of scores	2020, 2023

respectively, ToyADMOS2 [14], ToyADMOS2+ [43], and ToyADMOS2# [44]. A part of the DCASE2024 dataset was recorded with the same setup as IMAD-DS [45]. IMAD-DS is another ASD dataset containing noisy multi-sensor signals of two machines in domain-shifted conditions recorded with a microphone, an accelerometer, and a gyroscope. The fundamental difference with the DCASE2021 dataset, which focuses on DA, is that the domain of individual test samples is unknown during inference. Moreover, the performance for each section is computed jointly for the source and target domains, i.e., a single decision threshold needs to be used for both domains. Other less severe differences include the size of all test sets, which is only half the size of the DCASE2021 test sets, and the availability of 10 normal training samples belonging to the target domain instead of 3. The differences between the DCASE2021 and DCASE2022 datasets end there, making them relatively similar. In contrast, the DCASE2023, DCASE2024, and DCASE2025 datasets only consist of a single section for each machine type, and the development and evaluation sets contain recordings of completely different machine types. Furthermore, the DCASE2024 and DCASE2025 datasets have noise conditions that are exclusively used for specific machine types, and for some machine types no additional attribute information is provided. The major difference between the DCASE2024 and DCASE2025 datasets is that supplemental recordings containing noise-free recordings of normal machine sounds or only background noise are provided for the train splits of the DCASE2025 dataset. Each year, modifications to the datasets result in a more realistic yet more challenging ASD task. For more details about these datasets, the reader is referred to Table 1 and the corresponding references.

4.2. Approaches

DG approaches for ASD in the context of DCASE can be grouped into four different strategies, which will now be discussed. Table 2 contains an overview of these approaches.

4.2.1. Domain Specialization: A simple approach for reducing domain mismatch is to balance the number of training samples belonging to the source and target domains. This can be achieved by balancing the domains in each mini-batch [21] or using more

sophisticated approaches [22]–[24] such as synthetic minority over-sampling technique (SMOTE) [46]. However, since this approach trains models for specific domain shifts and thus requires to re-train the entire ASD system for each possible domain shift, this can be referred to as *weak DG* or *domain specialization*. Note that in contrast to DA, ASD systems need to work well for all domains without knowledge about the domain a given sample belongs to. Another way to handle this is to train domain-specific models and a domain classifier [21].

4.2.2. Domain-invariant Representations: The idea of domain-invariant representation learning [47] or domain-mixing-based approaches [2] is to reduce the variance between multiple domains based on the assumption that this also reduces the variance to other arbitrary target domains. In [25], individual samples of a batch are normalized independently of each other instead of using batch normalization [36] to avoid learning statistics that over-emphasize the source domain due to the highly imbalanced number of samples. The authors of [26] propose DG-mix, an extension of variance-invariance-covariance regularization (VICreg) [48] for self-supervised pre-training, using a loss term that minimizes the difference between domains and virtual domains created by mixup [49] before fine-tuning the model. Motivated by [50], which reduces the difference between second-order statistics of intermediate representations from domain-specific convolutional neural networks, [27] aims at reducing the difference between second-order statistics of source domain features and target domain features. To this end, the authors applied augmentations such as pitch shifting, time shifting, time stretching, adding white noise, and Filteraugment [51] to target domain samples to create more diverse domain shifts for training.

4.2.3. Feature Disentanglement: The main idea of feature disentanglement [52] is to decompose representations into domain-related features that are invariant for different domains and domain-unrelated features that capture the variability of different domains. The latter are independent of the domain and thus also generalize well to unseen domains. A possible way to achieve this is to use a domain-classification-based approach [2]. In most works on ASD in the DCASE context, this is achieved by focusing on the provided

Table 3: Comparison of different types of DG approaches.

DG approach	Effort	Requires labels	Effectiveness
Domain Specialization	high	yes	high
Domain-invariant Representations	medium	no	medium
Feature Disentanglement	low	yes	medium
Anomaly Score Calculation	very low	sometimes	low

attribute information. The authors of [28] use two discriminative tasks for the sections and attributes. In [29], attribute information is disentangled in a normalizing-flow-based ASD model. In [30], a combination of a hierarchical metadata structure and attribute-specific Mahalanobis distances is used to learn more domain-related features. This approach is extended by [31] with gradient-reversal-based feature disentanglement of attribute information [53] and the use of a focal loss [54].

4.2.4. Anomaly Score Calculation: Last but not least, DG capabilities can also be improved by modifying the anomaly score computation. This approach has the advantage of not requiring expensive re-training of the neural networks that serve as the basis of state-of-the-art ASD systems. To this end, [32] uses an autoencoder and calculates the Mahalanobis distance between input data and reconstruction using domain-specific covariance matrices. For discriminative ASD systems, it was shown that simple nearest-neighbor-based anomaly scores lead to better results than estimating domain-specific distributions [33]. Further improvements can be obtained by normalizing the anomaly scores to reduce the domain mismatch. Examples are normalizing the anomaly scores based on local densities of normal reference samples [34], [55] or by a domain-wise standardization of the anomaly score distributions [35].

5. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

All presented DG approaches have limitations. A comparison of the approaches can be found in Table 3. Although domain specialization approaches are highly effective, they can only adapt to specific domains and thus the entire ASD system, including the embedding model, needs to be re-trained for each domain shift, which is highly impractical as it is a strenuous process requiring access to domain labels. Obtaining domain-invariant representations does not require domain labels, but requires to simulate a diverse set of realistic domain shifts, which is a difficult task by itself and thus may limit the effectiveness. Feature disentanglement does not require much additional effort, but does require access to labeled data of various domains to be effective, which may not always be available. Focusing only on the calculation of the anomaly scores usually does not require one to modify the training of the embedding models. However, this approach is still sensitive to domain shifts if these also affect the obtained embeddings, thus limiting its effectiveness, even when making use of domain labels. Depending on the application and the available data, different DG approaches can be jointly used to mitigate the limitations of individual approaches. For example, anomaly score calculation approaches for DG can be used regardless of the learned representations, and simulated domain shifts, as used when learning domain-invariant representations, can also be used for feature disentanglement. However, the underlying issues of individual approaches persist and future work on DG is needed to solve these problems and identify potential synergies between specific approaches.

A future direction of research is continuous DA [56]. Here, the discrete indices for the domains are replaced with continuous ones to model the underlying relations between different domains. This improves consistency and may even allow to handle domains for which no training samples are available. Another direction is continual DA

[57] that aims at handling domain shifts in non-stationary environments where domains are not static and may change continuously over time. In these environments, only adapting to a fixed domain is not sufficient. Note that continuous domain indices and continuously adapting to non-static domains can also be realized for DG. As a third direction, explaining the decisions of ASD systems is an open problem [58], [59], particularly in domain-shifted conditions. Here, future work may focus on explaining decisions of ASD in unknown target domains [60] or explaining domain shifts themselves [61]. Explainable ASD systems that focus on particular characteristics of the data may even offer better DG capabilities [62]. Last but not least, the semi-supervised ASD setting in the DCASE context can be relaxed to an unsupervised setting where even the training dataset may contain unlabeled anomalies [63].

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, we reviewed recent work on how to handle domain shifts for ASD tasks related to DCASE. We first defined domain shifts in the context of ASD, then discussed the topics of *domain adaptation (DA)* and *domain generalization (DG)* by motivating and defining these terms, presenting relevant datasets, and collecting different works related to these topics. In particular, DG approaches were grouped into *domain specialization*, *domain-invariant representations*, *feature disentanglement*, and *anomaly score calculation*. Furthermore, *continuous* and *continual DA* as well as *explainable DG* were identified as possible future research directions. For future work, we plan to compare all presented techniques with ASDKit [64] through extensive experiments to identify the best approaches and potential synergies.

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Adjusting Bias in Anomaly Scores via Variance Minimization for Domain-Generalized Discriminative Anomalous Sound Detection

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Abstract—We propose an anomaly score rescaling method based on variance minimization for domain-generalized anomalous sound detection (ASD). Current state-of-the-art ASD methods face significant challenges due to pronounced domain shifts, which lead to inconsistent anomaly score distributions across domains. One promising existing approach to address this issue is to rescale anomaly scores based on local data density in the embedding space. To enable more flexible and adaptive rescaling, our proposed method introduces weighting parameters into the rescaling process and analytically optimizes them based on the score variance minimization. Experimental evaluations on the DCASE 2021–2024 ASD datasets demonstrate that our proposed method achieves significant improvements on the DCASE 2022–2024 datasets. We also confirm that the proposed method obtains weighting parameters that lead to high ASD performance.

Index Terms—anomalous sound detection, domain generalization, anomaly score rescaling,

1. INTRODUCTION

Anomaly Sound Detection (ASD) is the task of identifying abnormal sounds from audio data. Since it is difficult to collect anomalous sound data, we need to develop ASD systems by using only normal sound data [1]–[5]. One of the main challenges in the ASD task is domain shift [6]. Domain shifts are variations – in acoustic environments, recording equipment, or operational conditions – that do not affect whether a sample is normal or anomalous. Domain shifts can occur during system deployment, and ASD systems must be able to perform robustly even in domains where only a small amount of data is collected during the development. ASD systems must be robust to domain shifts and perform robustly not only in domains with abundant data but also in domains with only a few samples. Here, it is common to refer to domains with abundant normal data as the *source* domain, and those with only a few normal samples as the *target* domain.

Current state-of-the-art ASD methods predominantly employ discriminative approaches [7]–[11]. These methods leverage labels associated with sounds, such as machine types or operational parameters, and train a feature extractor through the classification task. Anomaly scores are then calculated based on the distance between test samples and the training samples within the discriminative embedding space. The underlying principle is that anomalous sounds are not included in the training data; they are not correctly classified, causing them to deviate from the normal sound distribution in the discriminative embedding space and resulting in high anomaly scores. Although this approach achieves high performance, the limited training data in the target domain still often causes inconsistent anomaly score distributions across domains, as shown in Fig. 1. In such cases, the optimal threshold for distinguishing normal and anomalous samples in the source domain does not generalize well to the target domain.

One promising approach to handle this challenge is the anomaly score rescaling approach [12]. This method rescales anomaly scores based on the local density, where low-density target domains tend to exhibit higher anomaly scores. While this rescaling framework has proven effective, its performance is limited by the assignment of suboptimal fixed hyperparameters across different embedding spaces.

Fig. 1: Discrepancies of anomaly scores between domains.

In this paper, we aim to further enhance domain generalization ability by proposing a new anomaly score rescaling method that automatically adjusts the degree of rescaling according to the embedding space. Our proposed method introduces a weighting parameter into the rescaling process and analytically optimizes it based on the minimization of the variance of anomaly scores over normal samples in both the source and target domains. In experimental evaluations, we demonstrate that our proposed method outperforms existing anomaly score calculation methods on the DCASE 2022–2024 datasets. Furthermore, the experimental analysis shows that our method obtains a weighting parameter that leads to high ASD performance through analytical optimization.

2. ANOMALY SCORE CALCULATION METHODS

2.1. Baseline method

The anomaly score $\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}})$ for a test embedding \mathbf{x} is typically calculated as the distance to its nearest neighbor in a reference set \mathcal{X}_{ref} consisting of normal training samples as follows:

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}) := \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}} \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}), \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) := \frac{1}{2}(1 - \langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \rangle) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are the normalized embeddings with $\|\mathbf{x}\| = \|\mathbf{y}\| = 1$, $\mathcal{D}(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the cosine distance, $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ is the inner product operation. We set this approach as our baseline.

2.2. Over- and under-sampling techniques for data imbalance

To address the data imbalance between the source and target domains, techniques such as K-means clustering and SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) are widely employed in the anomaly score calculation process [7], [13]–[15]. K-means clustering is applied to the source domain samples [7], and the obtained centroids and the original target domain samples are used as the reference samples \mathcal{X}_{ref} in Eq. 1. SMOTE generates synthetic samples in the target domain by linearly interpolating original samples [16]. The augmented target domain samples and the original source domain samples are used as the reference samples \mathcal{X}_{ref} [13]. These methods aim to mitigate the discrepancies in anomaly score distributions between the source and target domains by balancing the number of samples across domains.

2.3. Anomaly score rescaling

Recently, to address discrepancies in anomaly score distributions, a new approach has been proposed [12]. This method rescales anomaly scores based on the local density of reference samples in the embedding space. It is motivated by the observation that the target domain tends to exhibit higher anomaly scores due to a lack of sufficient reference samples, as shown in Fig. 1.

This method calculates the anomaly score $\mathcal{A}_{\text{scaled}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}})$ as follows:

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{scaled}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}) := \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}} \frac{\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})}{b(\mathbf{y}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, K)}, \quad (3)$$

$$b(\mathbf{y}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, K) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{y}_k), \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{y}_k denotes the k -th closest sample to \mathbf{y} in \mathcal{X}_{ref} . This method rescale the distance between a test sample \mathbf{x} and a reference sample \mathbf{y} by dividing it by the local density term $b(\mathbf{y}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, K)$, which is calculated as the average distance from the reference sample \mathbf{y} to its K nearest neighbors within \mathcal{X}_{ref} . By using this local density term, it can prevent the high anomaly scores due to the scarcity of reference samples, thus reducing the discrepancies in anomaly score distributions. Furthermore, unlike techniques such as K-means clustering and SMOTE, this method does not require domain labels and can handle minor domain shifts within the source domain that are not reflected in the domain labels. Despite these advantages, its performance still depends on the manually selected hyperparameter K . Although $K = 16$ was found to perform well across several datasets in their experiments, this fixed value is not optimal for every embedding space.

3. PROPOSED METHOD

To address the performance limitations caused by the suboptimal fixed hyperparameter in the previous anomaly score rescaling method, we propose a new method that adaptively rescales anomaly scores according to each embedding space. Our proposed method calculates the anomaly score $\mathcal{A}_{\text{prop}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, \alpha)$ as follows:

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{prop}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, \alpha) := \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}} (\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) - \alpha \cdot b(\mathbf{y}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, K)), \quad (5)$$

where the anomaly score is rescaled by subtracting a bias term, $b(\mathbf{y}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, K)$, weighted by a newly introduced parameter α . The optimal weighting parameter α^* is obtained as follows:

$$\mathbf{y}^*(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}} \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{y}), \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha^* = \arg \min_{\alpha} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Var}(\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{y}^*(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}})) - \alpha \cdot b(\mathbf{y}^*(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}), \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, K) \mid \mathbf{z} \in \mathcal{X}_{\text{val}}), \\ & = \frac{\text{Cov}(\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{y}^*(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}})), b(\mathbf{y}^*(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}), \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, K) \mid \mathbf{z} \in \mathcal{X}_{\text{val}})}{\text{Var}(b(\mathbf{y}^*(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}), \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}, K) \mid \mathbf{z} \in \mathcal{X}_{\text{val}})}, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\text{Var}(\cdot)$ and $\text{Cov}(\cdot)$ are variance and covariance, respectively. $\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{y}^*(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}))$ is identical to $\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}})$, and Eq. 7 yields the value of α that minimizes the variance of the anomaly scores in the validation set \mathcal{X}_{val} . This variance minimization encourages the alignment of anomaly scores across domains and reduces the need for careful tuning of the hyperparameter K .

For the validation data \mathcal{X}_{val} , we propose four different approaches.

- 1) *TrainAll*: We use all available normal training data from both source and target domains as \mathcal{X}_{val} .
- 2) *TrainRandom*: To reduce imbalances between domains in \mathcal{X}_{val} , we construct a balanced validation set consisting of all target

training samples and randomly sampled source training samples, such that the number of source samples matches that of the target domain.

- 3) *TrainCluster*: Another approach to reduce imbalances between domains in \mathcal{X}_{val} is to use clustering. We first perform K-means clustering on the source domain, and then select the original source samples closest to the centroids as \mathcal{X}_{val} , instead of using the centroids directly. This approach eliminates randomness, unlike *TrainRandom* approach.
- 4) *TestAll*: We also consider the case where we can utilize test data as \mathcal{X}_{val} . Since test samples observed during the operational phase lack both domain and normal/anomalous labels, we simply use all test as \mathcal{X}_{val} . Assuming that ASD systems are deployed in both the source and target domains, this approach enables the use of balanced validation data including sufficient samples; however, it may include anomalous samples.

Note that *TrainRandom* and *TrainCluster* require the domain labels while *TrainAll* and *TestAll* does not. Since \mathcal{X}_{ref} includes all training samples and overlaps with \mathcal{X}_{val} , we ensure that $\mathbf{y}^*(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{X}_{\text{ref}}) \neq \mathbf{z}$ by excluding \mathbf{z} from \mathcal{X}_{ref} .

4. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATIONS

4.1. Experimental setups

We conducted experimental evaluations using the DCASE 2021–2024 Task 2 Challenge datasets [2]–[5]. These datasets provide labels for machine types, sections, domains, and attributes. The section identifies each individual instance of the same machine type, while the attribute labels reflect the operational state of the machine. The DCASE 2021 and 2022 datasets consist of seven machine types, each with six sections. The DCASE 2023 and 2024 datasets consist of 14 and 16 machine types, respectively, with each machine type having only one section. One section contains approximately 1,000 normal training samples and 400 or 200 test samples. In the training dataset, three samples in DCASE 2021 and ten in each of the DCASE 2022–2024 datasets are from the target domain, while the remaining samples are from the source domain. In the test dataset, the source and target domains, as well as normal and anomalous samples, are approximately balanced (i.e., approximately 100 or 50 samples for each combination of domain and normal/anomalous classes). Each recording is approximately ten seconds long, consisting of a single-channel signal sampled at 16 kHz. Each of these datasets is divided into *dev* and *eval* subsets based on section or machine type, and the evaluation results are aggregated accordingly.

The discriminative feature extractor was similar to that used in [8]. This extractor received an amplitude spectrum and an amplitude spectrogram as input features and processed them in parallel using two separate neural networks, a spectrum network and a spectrogram network. The spectrum network consisted of 1D convolutional layers, while the spectrogram network consisted of 2D convolutional layer-based ResNet [17] blocks, Squeeze-and-Excitation [18] blocks, and multilayer perceptrons. The final output was obtained by concatenating the outputs from spectrum and spectrogram networks. For the spectrogram, we used a DFT size of 1024 and a hop length of 512. The frequency range was restricted to 200–8000 Hz. We trained the feature extractor for 16 epochs jointly using machine type, section, domain, and attribute labels. The optimizer was AdamW [19] with a fixed learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size was set to 64. For the loss function, we used Sub-cluster AdaCos (SCAC) [20] with the number of sub-clusters set to 16 and a fixed scale parameter. While previous work [7] showed that fixed class centers lead to better performance

Table 1: Mean (\pm Standard Deviation) of official score [%] for DCASE 2021–2024 datasets using fixed SCAC loss. \dagger requires the domain labels.

Method	2021		2022		2023		2024	
	dev	eval	dev	eval	dev	eval	dev	eval
Baseline	67.31 \pm 0.51	66.28 \pm 0.65	68.97 \pm 0.75	63.79 \pm 0.92	62.11 \pm 0.98	57.00 \pm 1.51	58.63 \pm 0.71	51.59 \pm 0.73
w/ K-means clustering \dagger	65.27 \pm 0.59	64.02 \pm 0.59	70.49 \pm 0.81	61.82 \pm 1.04	63.63 \pm 0.70	59.17 \pm 1.44	59.24 \pm 0.96	52.15 \pm 0.63
w/ SMOTE \dagger	67.48 \pm 0.48	66.43 \pm 0.62	69.46 \pm 0.74	64.63 \pm 0.95	63.24 \pm 0.75	59.27 \pm 1.52	59.36 \pm 0.78	52.16 \pm 0.73
Rescaling ($K = 8$)								
Previous [12]	63.38 \pm 1.39	61.43 \pm 1.65	64.08 \pm 1.81	62.68 \pm 0.77	58.94 \pm 1.34	65.32 \pm 1.37	60.08 \pm 1.63	51.47 \pm 1.38
Prop (<i>TrainAll</i>)	52.46 \pm 2.11	49.83 \pm 2.53	69.10 \pm 1.55	66.34 \pm 0.83	61.20 \pm 1.64	67.41 \pm 1.58	58.56 \pm 1.74	54.10 \pm 1.25
Prop (<i>TrainRandom</i>) \dagger	60.69 \pm 3.61	59.15 \pm 2.93	70.60 \pm 0.96	66.84 \pm 1.05	62.62 \pm 2.16	66.18 \pm 1.52	58.20 \pm 2.59	54.06 \pm 1.35
Prop (<i>TrainCluster</i>) \dagger	60.44 \pm 3.60	58.55 \pm 2.87	70.63 \pm 1.00	66.84 \pm 1.02	62.23 \pm 1.93	66.25 \pm 1.80	57.92 \pm 2.84	54.40 \pm 1.06
Prop (<i>TestAll</i>)	64.02 \pm 1.04	62.75 \pm 1.24	70.47 \pm 1.19	65.28 \pm 0.67	64.97 \pm 0.95	67.91 \pm 0.96	59.43 \pm 1.85	56.58 \pm 0.68
Rescaling ($K = 16$)								
Previous [12]	63.62 \pm 1.38	61.58 \pm 1.68	63.33 \pm 1.68	61.90 \pm 0.85	58.71 \pm 1.58	63.92 \pm 1.47	59.67 \pm 1.71	48.18 \pm 0.98
Prop (<i>TrainAll</i>)	51.07 \pm 3.17	50.46 \pm 1.99	66.71 \pm 1.92	65.85 \pm 0.87	60.40 \pm 1.99	66.09 \pm 1.38	58.18 \pm 1.81	54.16 \pm 1.27
Prop (<i>TrainRandom</i>) \dagger	60.65 \pm 3.32	58.72 \pm 3.17	70.32 \pm 1.11	67.59 \pm 0.92	62.81 \pm 2.07	65.63 \pm 1.75	58.47 \pm 2.02	53.52 \pm 1.11
Prop (<i>TrainCluster</i>) \dagger	60.21 \pm 3.45	58.04 \pm 3.07	70.20 \pm 1.14	67.55 \pm 0.87	62.41 \pm 1.90	65.46 \pm 1.81	57.96 \pm 2.37	53.63 \pm 1.11
Prop (<i>TestAll</i>)	63.93 \pm 1.10	62.47 \pm 1.31	69.43 \pm 2.77	65.24 \pm 0.92	65.43 \pm 0.99	67.39 \pm 0.86	59.35 \pm 1.68	56.21 \pm 0.68

Table 2: Mean (\pm Standard Deviation) of official score [%] for DCASE 2021–2024 datasets using trainable SCAC loss. \dagger requires the domain labels.

Method	2021		2022		2023		2024	
	dev	eval	dev	eval	dev	eval	dev	eval
Baseline	68.82 \pm 0.60	65.22 \pm 0.64	70.82 \pm 0.63	67.32 \pm 0.56	63.96 \pm 1.10	63.68 \pm 3.49	60.42 \pm 1.03	56.16 \pm 0.71
w/ K-means clustering \dagger	67.01 \pm 0.98	63.96 \pm 0.62	70.23 \pm 1.11	64.34 \pm 0.70	65.53 \pm 0.99	65.47 \pm 2.83	61.54 \pm 1.16	55.71 \pm 0.64
w/ SMOTE \dagger	69.05 \pm 0.57	65.30 \pm 0.55	71.12 \pm 0.67	67.86 \pm 0.60	65.31 \pm 0.93	65.60 \pm 2.55	61.82 \pm 0.99	56.20 \pm 0.78
Rescaling ($K = 8$)								
Previous [12]	69.39 \pm 0.85	64.47 \pm 0.78	66.53 \pm 1.39	66.60 \pm 0.80	61.87 \pm 1.66	67.23 \pm 0.89	62.74 \pm 1.14	52.59 \pm 0.93
Prop (<i>TrainAll</i>)	66.99 \pm 0.94	62.26 \pm 0.75	67.79 \pm 1.26	67.61 \pm 0.70	64.94 \pm 1.37	69.75 \pm 1.22	62.63 \pm 1.15	55.02 \pm 0.70
Prop (<i>TrainRandom</i>) \dagger	68.52 \pm 1.26	64.50 \pm 0.80	70.98 \pm 0.88	68.80 \pm 0.62	66.51 \pm 0.84	69.04 \pm 1.38	62.74 \pm 0.70	57.05 \pm 0.77
Prop (<i>TrainCluster</i>) \dagger	67.72 \pm 0.87	63.60 \pm 0.36	70.87 \pm 0.78	68.89 \pm 0.61	66.44 \pm 0.94	69.33 \pm 1.53	62.44 \pm 1.02	56.22 \pm 0.89
Prop (<i>TestAll</i>)	68.75 \pm 0.79	64.62 \pm 0.50	71.66 \pm 0.63	67.36 \pm 0.57	66.19 \pm 0.69	69.91 \pm 1.25	62.40 \pm 1.48	58.63 \pm 0.79
Rescaling ($K = 16$)								
Previous [12]	69.47 \pm 0.83	64.48 \pm 0.83	65.41 \pm 1.40	65.77 \pm 0.64	60.95 \pm 1.33	66.28 \pm 0.54	62.39 \pm 1.12	49.82 \pm 0.84
Prop (<i>TrainAll</i>)	66.33 \pm 0.99	61.83 \pm 0.70	67.93 \pm 1.11	67.69 \pm 0.83	64.22 \pm 1.48	69.19 \pm 1.32	62.59 \pm 1.10	55.64 \pm 1.22
Prop (<i>TrainRandom</i>) \dagger	68.51 \pm 1.15	64.59 \pm 0.80	71.04 \pm 0.81	69.03 \pm 0.62	66.46 \pm 0.87	68.61 \pm 1.50	62.72 \pm 0.74	56.76 \pm 1.03
Prop (<i>TrainCluster</i>) \dagger	67.76 \pm 0.87	63.73 \pm 0.41	70.85 \pm 0.74	68.97 \pm 0.55	66.24 \pm 0.85	69.07 \pm 1.42	62.28 \pm 0.89	56.20 \pm 1.21
Prop (<i>TestAll</i>)	68.69 \pm 0.76	64.61 \pm 0.56	71.79 \pm 0.68	67.80 \pm 0.57	66.23 \pm 0.71	69.07 \pm 1.01	62.36 \pm 1.39	57.88 \pm 0.70

than trainable class centers, we found that trainable class centers performed better. Accordingly, we conducted experiments using both fixed and trainable centers in the SCAC loss. Additionally, we applied Mixup [21] to the input waveforms with a probability of 0.5.

We evaluated our proposed method with four comparison previous backend methods: the baseline method (Eq.1), the baseline method with K-means clustering or SMOTE described in Sec.2.2, and the anomaly score rescaling method [12] described in Sec. 2.3. For the baseline method with K-means clustering, we set the number of clusters to 16. For the SMOTE, we set the oversampling ratio to 5% and the number of neighbors to 5. For the anomaly score rescaling approach, we set K to 8 and 16 following the previous work [12]. For *TrainCluster* in our proposed method, we used K-means clustering with the number of clusters set to match the number of samples in the target domain (i.e., three for DCASE 2021 and ten for DCASE 2022–2024).

As evaluation metrics, we used the official DCASE metrics for each dataset: the harmonic mean of the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (AUC) and the partial AUC (pAUC) with $p = 0.1$ over all machine types and domains. We calculated the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the official scores across ten independent trials.

4.2. Experimental results

Tables 1 and 2 show the evaluation results when using fixed and trainable class centers for the SCAC loss, respectively. For the DCASE 2022–2024 datasets, our proposed method consistently achieves high performance, significantly improving performance in several subsets. For example, in 2023 eval of Table 1, baseline, K-means clustering, SMOTE, and the previous rescaling with $K = 8$ achieved 57.00%, 59.17%, 59.27%, and 65.32%, respectively, while our proposed *TrainAll* achieved 67.41% with $K = 8$. Additionally, *TrainAll* of our proposed method achieves high performance without requiring domain labels, whereas the K-means clustering and SMOTE techniques rely on them. Comparing Tables 1 and 2, we can see that using trainable SCAC loss improves overall performance. Although this reduces the relative performance gain of our method, it still consistently contributes to performance improvement.

We can also see that the previous rescaling method [12] can cause performance degradation, whereas our proposed method improves or keeps the baseline performance in most cases of the DCASE 2022–2024 datasets, regardless of whether the hyperparameter K is set to 8 or 16. For example, in 2023 dev of Table 2, the previous method with $K = 8$ degrades performance from 63.96% of baseline to 61.87%, whereas the proposed method *TrainAll* with $K = 8$ achieves 64.94%. In contrast, in 2023 eval of Table 2, the previous method

Fig. 2: Graphs of the official score improvement for DCASE 2024 evaluation data (one trial with a fixed SCAC loss, $K = 16$). The horizontal axis shows α , and the vertical axis shows official score [%]. Plotted points indicate the α selected by each validation data selection method (Orange: *TrainAll*, Red: *TrainRandom*, Green: *TrainCluster*, Gray: *TestAll*) for each machine.

with $K = 8$ improves the performance from 63.68% of baseline to 67.23%, where the proposed method *TrainAll* with $K = 8$ also improves the performance to 69.75%.

Regarding validation data selection, the comparison among *TrainAll*, *TrainCluster*, and *TrainRandom* shows that the best choice varies depending on the dataset, and there is no consistent trend. On the other hand, *Test* approach achieves the highest performance in most cases. For example, in 2023 dev of Table 1, the proposed method *Test* with $K = 16$ achieves 65.43%, in 2024 eval of Table 1, the proposed method *Test* with $K = 8$ achieves 56.58%, and in 2024 eval of Table 2, the proposed method *Test* with $K = 8$ achieves 58.63%. This suggests the importance of using validation datasets in which the source and target domains are balanced with sufficient samples.

We confirm that α^* indeed leads to high performance. Fig. 2 illustrates the relationship between α and the official score, along with the α^* obtained using each validation data selection method. This figure is generated for each machine type in the DCASE 2024 evaluation subset, when using the fixed SCAC loss and $K = 16$ under a specific random seed. Here, the proposed method with $\alpha = 0$ is equivalent to the baseline method. The figure clearly shows that the optimal value of α varies across machine types, and that the proposed method adaptively selects values of α that yield high performance for each type.

Despite the overall performance improvements in the DCASE 2022–2024 datasets, we observe that the proposed methods and the previous rescaling method [12] exhibit degraded performance on the DCASE

Fig. 3: The plots show the embedding of the test samples of section 3 and training samples of all sections for the *pump* machine from the DCASE 2021 dataset (one trial with a fixed SCAC loss). The AUC for these test samples of the baseline method, the previous rescaling using $K = 8$, and the proposed method using $K = 8$ and *TrainAll* were 86.69%, 67.01%, and 43.98%, respectively.

2021 dataset compared to other methods. To investigate the reason for this degradation, we examine the embedding space. Figure 3 visualizes a partial excerpt of the embedding space for *pump* machine using UMAP [22]. In the highlighted frame within the figure, we can observe that a single training sample is embedded apart from the other training samples, while many anomalous samples are located nearby. Due to the low density of training samples in that area, the rescaling method inadvertently reduces the anomaly scores of anomalous sounds, leading to performance degradation.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced an anomaly score rescaling method based on variance minimization for domain-generalized ASD. Our proposed method introduced weighting parameters into the local data density based rescaling process and analytically optimized them based on the score variance minimization. Experimental results demonstrated that (1) the proposed method significantly improves performance over existing anomaly score calculation methods; (2) ore stable with respect to random seed than the previous rescaling method [12]; and (3) the weighting parameters derived through our variance minimization scheme adaptively rescale anomaly scores for each machine type, leading to high performance.

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Region-Specific Audio Tagging for Spatial Sound

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Abstract—Audio tagging aims to label sound events appearing in an audio recording. In this paper, we propose region-specific audio tagging, a new task which labels sound events in a given region for spatial audio recorded by a microphone array. The region can be specified as an angular space or a distance from the microphone. We first study the performance of different combinations of spectral, spatial, and position features. Then we extend state-of-the-art audio tagging systems such as pre-trained audio neural networks (PANNs) and audio spectrogram transformer (AST) to the proposed region-specific audio tagging task. Experimental results on both the simulated and the real datasets show the feasibility of the proposed task and the effectiveness of the proposed method. Further experiments show that incorporating the directional features is beneficial for omnidirectional tagging.

1. INTRODUCTION

The task of audio tagging aims to identify the sound events present in a sound clip. This topic has been a popular area in audio processing, playing an important role in applications, such as audio classification [1] and information retrieval [2]. In the current task setting, in general, all sound events are labeled regardless of the location of the sound events. In surveillance applications, however, sound events located in a specific spatial region may be more important than others. Therefore, it is of practical interest to study the problem of region-specific audio tagging, i.e., labelling audio events that are present in a specific spatial region. Tagging sound events according to the location can help the separation and make people focus on sound from a specific region. In addition, region-specific audio tagging allows people to attach importance to sounds, e.g. a warning from behind, thereby improving the safety.

In the traditional audio tagging task, deep learning based methods are popular choices. For a convolutional neural network (CNN) based system, pretrained audio neural networks (PANNs) [3] is a model pretrained on AudioSet [4], and shows promising performance on audio pattern recognition tasks such as audio tagging and acoustic scene classification. The system of pretraining, sampling, labeling, and aggregation (PSLA) [5] employs EfficientNet as the backbone and improves the model performance by ImageNet pretraining, balanced sampling and model aggregation. For a transformer-based [6] system, the audio spectrogram transformer (AST) [7] follows the vision transformer [8], and takes mel-spectrogram patches as input. The AST model can outperform PANNs and PSLA, when built with a large amount of data. The above methods only use spectral features. In [9], both spectral and spatial audio features are used with a gated CNN architecture. The incorporation of audio features further improves the

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Fig. 1: The task scenario of region-specific audio tagging. Left: Query by horizontal angular regions. Right: Query by distance.

model performance. In addition to the CNN and transformer-based methods, there are also methods based on graph neural network (GNN), such as the work proposed in [10], which leverages several GNNs to model the relationships between different feature patches and different labels for tagging. In our work, we extend these state-of-the-art models to the region-specific audio tagging problem.

Our proposed task is inspired by region-specific speech processing [11]–[13] including automatic speech recognition (ASR) and speech separation for a given direction or distance. Beamforming aims to locate the signal from a given direction by attenuating unwanted sound sources. Traditional methods like the minimum variance distortionless response (MVDR) [14] beamformer can minimize the total signal power and maintain a distortionless response for a given direction. Recently, deep learning based methods are also used for region-specific automatic speech recognition and separation. For region-specific ASR, in [11], long short term memory (LSTM)-based architecture is used for multi-channel overlapped ASR with the input of the concatenation of spectral, spatial and angle features. Directional features are proposed as the angle features, encoding the information for regions of interest. For region-specific speech separation, in [12], directional features are used as a condition to indicate the speaker for multi-modal target speech separation. In [13], a multi-channel band-split recurrent neural network (RNN) model is proposed for angular-query, spherical-query and conical-query based speech separation. In addition, the field of view (FOV) feature is proposed in [15] for audio zooming. The FOV feature can represent the property of an angular space while directional features can represent the property of an azimuth.

2. PROPOSED METHOD

Inspired by the previous work in region-specific speech processing, we study a new task, i.e. region-specific audio tagging, and explore the use of directional features and FOV features for this task. Following previous work [13], we explore this task in two paradigms, query by horizontal angular regions and query by distance, as shown in Fig. 1. We examine three types of features, i.e. spectral, spatial, and

Fig. 2: The proposed multi-channel PANNs for region-specific audio tagging.

positional features. The spectral features are used to identify sound sources. Spatial features can give information for all potential sound events and positional features are used to describe a potential region-specific sound event.

Our contributions can be summarized as follows. Firstly, we propose, for the first time, the region-specific audio tagging task and build a benchmark. Secondly, we extend the state-of-the-art audio tagging models for this task and study the performance achieved by a different combination of spectral, spatial and positional features. Finally, we extend the proposed method to omnidirectional audio tagging, which aims to tag the events in the whole space instead of a region. Experimental results show that the proposed fixed-region and location-aware system are superior to the omnidirectional tagging systems.

2.1. Problem Definition

Given a four-channel audio in tetrahedral microphone array (MIC) format $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times L}$ (where L denotes the audio length) and a given area \mathbf{p} , in the form of angular range $[\theta_{\text{begin}}, \dots, \theta_{\text{end}}]$ or distance d from the microphone array to the sound events, the objective of region-specific audio tagging is to identify the sound sources located in \mathbf{p} . It is worth noting that the proposed new task can be achieved by a beamformer and an audio tagging model. However, this cascaded format is not end-to-end and the audio tagging model can only learn the semantic representation.

2.2. Overall System Architecture

To this end, we present a system, as shown in Fig. 2. The system is composed of the modules including feature extraction and audio tagging. The features indicate the region of interests while the tagging model predicts the sound events. Compared to previous tagging systems, the proposed system predicts the sound events in the given region specified by a user, instead of all events present in microphone recordings. Compared to the cascaded model combining a beamformer and an audio tagging model, the proposed model can learn both semantic and spatial information simultaneously.

2.3. Extraction of Features

Following previous work for region-specific speech separation [12], [13], we also use the combination of spectral, spatial and positional features.

2.3.1. Spectral Features: Spectral features can help classify the audio events. Here we use logarithm power spectrum (LPS) \mathbf{L} of the first-channel audio \mathbf{x} . \mathbf{L} is calculated based on short-time Fourier transform (STFT) \mathbf{X} of \mathbf{x} , as follows,

$$\mathbf{L} = \log(|\mathbf{X}|^2) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F}$ and $\mathbf{L} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F}$, and T and F are the number of time frames and frequency bins, respectively.

2.3.2. Spatial Features: Spatial features are useful for localizing sound events [16]. Here, we explore two features, generalized cross-correlation phase transform (GCCPHAT) \mathbf{G} and inter-channel phase difference (IPD) \mathbf{I} .

GCCPHAT is widely used in sound source localization [17] and speaker tracking [18], which estimates the time difference of arrival between a pair of microphones, as follows,

$$\mathbf{G}^n(\tau) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\mathbf{X}^{n_1}(f)\mathbf{X}^{n_2^*}(f)}{|\mathbf{X}^{n_1}(f)\mathbf{X}^{n_2^*}(f)|} e^{i2\pi f\tau} df \quad (2)$$

where $n = (n_1, n_2)$ indexes the microphone pair, $*$ denotes complex conjugate, f denotes the frequency, and τ denotes the time delay. It is normalized to mitigate the impact of changing amplitudes. We stack GCCPHAT from selected pairs as the spatial features.

IPD is calculated as the phase difference between two audio channels.

$$\mathbf{I}^n = \text{angle}(\mathbf{X}^{n_1}) - \text{angle}(\mathbf{X}^{n_2}) \quad (3)$$

where $\text{angle}(\cdot)$ denotes the phase of a signal. IPD shows effectiveness in multi-channel speech separation [12]. IPDs from selected microphone pairs are stacked.

2.3.3. Positional Features: In this section, we discuss the extraction of positional features from the angular region or a distance, respectively.

Angular Region For the horizontal angular areas from -180° to 180° , we detect the sound events within the region $\Theta = [\theta_{\text{begin}}, \dots, \theta_{\text{end}}]$ by attenuating events from the unselected areas. We choose the FOV feature proposed in [15] for this task.

To calculate the FOV feature, we first calculate directional features (DF) $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F}$ for each angle in Θ following [19], as follows,

$$\mathbf{D}(\theta) = \sum_n \cos(\mathbf{I}^n - \mathbf{P}^n(\theta)) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{P}^n(\theta) = 2\pi f \phi^n \cos(\theta) f_s / c \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{P}^n is the target-dependent phase difference calculated at the n -th microphone pair with frequency f , ϕ^n is the distance between the n -th microphone pair, f_s is the sampling rate, and c is the sound velocity. Then, the FOV feature in the view of Θ is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{in}} = \max(\mathbf{D}(\theta)), \theta \in \Theta \quad (6)$$

The feature out of the view Θ is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{out}} = \max(\mathbf{D}(\theta)), \theta \notin \Theta \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3: The learning-based method for obtaining angle features (left) and distance features (right), where h is the hidden dimension and FC denotes the fully connected layer.

Finally, the FOV feature $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F}$ is defined as:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{F}_{\text{in}}, & \text{if } \mathbf{F}_{\text{in}} > \mathbf{F}_{\text{out}}, \\ -1, & \text{if } \mathbf{F}_{\text{in}} \leq \mathbf{F}_{\text{out}}. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Distance For obtaining a distance feature given a distance d from the microphone array to the sound events, we use learning-based methods following [13], as shown in the right part of Fig. 3. The distance feature is repeated to match the time dimension of spectral or spatial features.

2.4. Model

We extended PANNs for region-specific multi-channel audio tagging, as shown in Fig. 2. The spectral, spatial and positional features are concatenated on the channel dimension, with k being the number of concatenated channels. PANNs takes the concatenated features and employs a sequence of convolutional layers to downsize the time-frequency dimension while increasing the channel dimension from k to 2048. Then the time-frequency dimension is pooled and the channel dimension is retained. Finally, the system outputs the probabilities of the sound event classes. The binary cross-entropy loss is used to optimize the model.

We also extended the other two models, PSLA [5] and AST [7], to the proposed task. For PSLA, the EfficientNet backbone is trained from scratch with 2560 hidden dimension in the multi-head attention module. For AST, we use the *small224*¹ version.

3. EXPERIMENT SETUP

3.1. Dataset

We use the STARSS23 dataset [20] for the proposed task and this dataset is also used in DCASE 2024 task 3. However, the scenario presented in this dataset is relatively simple for region-specific audio tagging, since the average number of overlapping sound events is 1.32. Thus, we use SpatialScaper [21] to simulate a new dataset, named Spatial Region-Specific Audio Tagging (SRSAT). The room is randomly chosen from the given room set². The mean and standard deviation of the number of sound events are set to 25 and 3. Each audio clip is in the format of a tetrahedral microphone array, 60 seconds long, sampled at 24 kHz. We generate 1,000 audio clips for training, 60 audio clips for validation, and 60 audio clips for testing, respectively. There are 13 sound classes (female speech, male speech, clapping, telephone, laughter, domestic sounds, walk, door, music, musical instrument, water tap, bell and knock) from FSD50K [22] in both the STARSS23 and SRSAT datasets. In each time step, the annotation contains the classes and positions (azimuth, elevation, and distance) of the sound events.

3.2. Implementation Details and Evaluation Metrics

A 2-second audio clip is randomly extracted from the 60-second audio signals. We ensure that the extracted audio clip has at least one sound event. During training, we perform audio channel swapping data augmentation using the method proposed in [23] to enlarge the

¹https://github.com/YuanGongND/ast/blob/master/src/models/ast_models.py

²<https://github.com/iranroman/SpatialScaper>

Table 1: Experimental results for different features. Bold numbers indicate the best performance.

Spectral	Spatial	Angle	mAP (\uparrow)	EER (\downarrow)
LPS	IPD	DF	0.473	0.253
LPS	IPD	FOV	0.485	0.260
LPS	IPD	learned	0.416	0.260
LPS	GCCPHAT	DF	0.479	0.246
SALSA	SALSA	DF	0.455	0.260

Table 2: Experimental results for different models.

Model	# Params	mAP (\uparrow)	EER (\downarrow)
PSLA [5]	64.1M	0.384	0.283
AST [7]	22.8M	0.360	0.308
PANNs [3]	79.7M	0.473	0.253

dataset by a factor of eight. STFT is calculated with a window of 512 samples and a hop size of 256 samples. Both IPD and directional features are calculated with microphone pairs of (0, 0), (0, 1), (0, 2) and (0, 3) [11]. We use the CNN-14 variant of PANNs as the model backbone. Each model is trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate 10^{-5} . The model is trained for 50 epochs with an early stop mechanism at a patience of 10 epochs. Apart from the features mentioned above, we explore the learning-based angular features shown in the left part of Fig. 3. A learnable embedding layer is used to extract features E for different input angles which is jointly trained with PANNs. In addition, for spectral and spatial features, we explore spatial cue-augmented log-spectrogram features (SALSA) proposed in [24]. We use the angular region of 60° as the region of interest. For DF and learning-based features, we use the middle angle of the region to extract the features. For the FOV feature, we calculate each DF in a resolution of 5° . Following the previous work [7], [9], we use both mean average precision (mAP) and equal error rate (EER) as the metric to evaluate the model performance.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Impact of Features

We show the experimental results on SRSAT using different feature combinations for 60-degree angular region-specific audio tagging in Table 1. Experimental results show that using LPS and IPD with FOV features achieves the best performance of mAP. One possible reason is that FOV features can focus more on the desired area than other angle features, as DF and learning-based can only attend to a single azimuth. However, the FOV feature is more computationally expensive than DF. With a resolution of 5° , the FOV features require 72 times computational costs than DF. Thus, we used DF for the remaining experiments, given its competitive performance over the FOV feature. For other spatial features, GCCPHAT has competitive performance with IPD.

4.2. Impact of Models

The experimental results for different models are demonstrated in Table 2 and it shows that PANNs achieve the best performance. AST and PSLA do not perform well giving lower mAP and higher EER than PANNs, which shows that PANNs can be adapted from traditional audio tagging to region-specific audio tagging effectively. The potential reason of AST not performing good is that the transformer-based method generally requires a large amount of data for good results [8].

4.3. Compared with Omnidirectional Tagging Systems

We compare the region-specific tagging systems with the systems for omnidirectional audio tagging, i.e., tagging sound events in the whole

Fig. 4: Illustration of different tagging system. The numbers are in degrees.

Table 3: Experimental results for omnidirectional (OD), fixed-region (FR) and location-aware (LA) audio tagging systems.

Spectral	Spatial	Angle	System	mAP (↑)	EER (↓)
LPS	IPD	-	OD	0.371	0.267
LPS	IPD	FOV	OD	0.370	0.274
LPS	GCCPHAT	-	OD	0.376	0.263
SALSA	SALSA	-	OD	0.373	0.265
LPS	IPD	DF	FR	0.653	0.252
LPS	IPD	DF	LA	0.667	0.244

space instead of a specific region. We explore three systems as shown in Fig. 4. The omnidirectional audio tagging system does not use the angle information. Both the location-aware system and the fixed-region system are based on a trained region-specific system. The location-aware system has the prior knowledge of the locations of all sound sources. The system is operated in the region of 60° centered at the azimuth of the sound events. We filter out overlapped regions, which are defined as two regions overlapping by 30°, to reduce unnecessary computational cost. The fixed-region tagging system is operated on six fixed regions from -180° to 180° at an interval of 60°. For the location-aware and fixed-region systems, the system output and the ground truth from different regions are aggregated by the operation of maximum before calculating the metrics.

The experimental results are shown in Table 3. Similar to the previous experiments, we compare the model performance achieved with different feature combinations for omnidirectional audio tagging. All omnidirectional systems have mAP between 0.37 and 0.38. It can be observed that adding the angle feature does not improve the model performance, as indicated by the third system. It is demonstrated that the fixed-region system outperforms the omnidirectional tagging one, which shows that the fixed-region system benefits from the region division. If the positions of the sound events are known, the model performance can be further improved with mAP from 0.653 to 0.667 and EER from 0.252 to 0.244.

4.4. Impact of Angular Range

We explore the influence of different angular range and show the results in Table 4. We can see that the proposed task becomes harder as the angular range becoming larger as more sound events would fall into the selected area, making the task more challenging. When the angular range is 300°, mAP is 0.370, which is close to the model

Table 4: Impact of angular range.

Spectral	Spatial	Angle	Range	mAP (↑)	EER (↓)
LPS	IPD	DF	60°	0.473	0.253
LPS	IPD	DF	180°	0.406	0.266
LPS	IPD	DF	300°	0.370	0.275

Table 5: Dataset statistics and performance comparisons between STARSS23 and SRSAT dataset.

	STARSS23	SRSAT
Avg. No. Events	1.320	2.233
Max. No. Events	6	10
Prop. One Event	0.623	0.287
Prop. Two Events	0.278	0.294
mAP of PANNs (↑)	0.938	0.473

Table 6: Model performance for a given distance.

Model	Param	mAP (↑)	EER (↓)
PANNs [3]	79.8M	0.417	0.266
AST [7]	23.0M	0.324	0.320
PSLA [5]	64.2M	0.399	0.274

performance in the omnidirectional tagging scenario shown in Table 3.

4.5. Model Performance on STARSS23 Dataset

We further evaluate PANNs on the STARSS23 dataset and make comparisons with the model performance on SRSAT. The results are shown in Table 5. STARSS23 was originally used for sound source localization and detection. We can see that STARSS23 is much simpler than SRSAT for the proposed task, as indicated by the lower average number of events (Avg. No. Events) and maximum number of events (Max. No. Events) per frame. We show the proportions of frames containing one event (Prop. One Event) or two events (Prop. Two Events). It is demonstrated that STARSS23 dataset contains one event and two events at 90% of the time frames, which necessitates the creation of SRSAT dataset.

4.6. Model Performance for a Given Distance

In this part we explore the model performance for distance-guided audio tagging. We randomly select a sound event and use the ground truth distance as the condition. The performance of the model is reported in Table 6. For each model, we use LPS as the spectral feature and IPD as the spatial feature following the previous settings. The distance feature extraction network is jointly trained with the model. The PANNs model achieves the best performance while AST and PSLA do not perform well. Compared with the model performance on azimuth-queried tagging reported in Table 2, distance-queried tagging scenarios are more challenging. One possible reason is that the statistic-based DF reflects the confidence of the sound source coming from a given azimuth, which can capture the characteristics of the selected regions better than the learning-based distance feature.

5. CONCLUSION

We have presented a novel task named region-specific audio tagging for spatial sound. We extended the current advanced tagging models for this task using angular region-queried and distance-queried mode. We further explored the impact of different combinations of spectral, spatial and positional features. We find that using LPS and IPD combined with FOV features achieves the best mAP. When extending the region-specific tagging system to omnidirectional tagging, we find that the proposed fixed-regional and location-aware tagging system outperforms the omnidirectional tagging system. In the current setting, we only include 13 sound classes following the setting of DCASE Task 3. In future, we plan to include more sound classes from AudioSet to enhance the diversity of dataset.

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Listening or Reading? An Empirical Study of Modality Importance Analysis Across AQA Question Types

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Abstract—Audio Question Answering (AQA) challenges a system to integrate acoustic perception with natural-language reasoning, yet how much each modality actually matters remains unclear. We propose a controlled modality-weight study on the DCASE 2025 Task5 benchmark to quantify this balance. Building on a dual-tower BEATS+BERT architecture, we introduce a scalar fusion hyper-parameter that linearly mixes audio and text embeddings. We evaluate model performance across six distinct question types and use statistical analysis to characterize how accuracy shifts as modality weights change. Our results reveal a clear asymmetry: while text alone supports strong performance on many questions, audio contributes significantly only to tasks that require perceptual grounding. Some tasks benefit most from a balanced fusion of both modalities, whereas for others, increased audio weight can even reduce accuracy. This protocol yields a practical guidance of which question categories depend primarily on audio, on text, or on a certain balanced fusion, providing guidance for future AQA model design.

Index Terms—Audio Question Answering, modality weighting, Acoustic Reasoning, DCASE 2025

1. INTRODUCTION

Multimodal learning—integrating information across text, vision, audio and other sensory streams—has become a central theme in contemporary AI research. Groundbreaking systems such as CLIP (image–text) [1], Flamingo (vision–language) [2], and Pengi (audio–language) [3] demonstrate how cross-modal pre-training can unlock zero-shot reasoning capabilities that are unattainable with unimodal models. Audio Question Answering (AQA) emerges as a genuinely multimodal task. It requires models to not only listen to the waveform and classify sounds but also reason about them in natural language, offering a rich playground to probe cross-modal alignment, fusion strategies and modality biases [4], [5]. The DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 5 amplifies this by introducing a multi-domain AQA benchmark consisting of three subsets – Bioacoustics QA, Temporal Soundscapes QA, and Complex QA(MMAU) – each designed to evaluate distinct reasoning skills grounded in acoustic perception [4].

Early work in audio QA was limited to narrow domains or synthetic data [6]. Datasets like CLEAR [7] and DAQA [8] programmatically generated QA pairs for musical notes or generic sound events, while Clotho-AQA [6] was the first crowdsourced AQA dataset built on general environmental sound clips. With the advent of large audio-language models (LALMs) [9]–[11], AQA has gained broader traction. Recent foundation models combine powerful audio encoders and text decoders – e.g., Pengi [3] and Qwen2-Audio [12] integrate a pretrained audio front-end with a language model to handle audio-based queries. These models leverage massive training sets (including synthetic data like OpenAQA-5M [13]), and achieve impressive general audio understanding. Pretrained audio transformers such as BEATs (Bidirectional Encoder from Audio Transformers) [14] have set state-of-the-art results on AudioSet [15], providing rich acoustic representations, while text models like BERT remain strong backbones

for language understanding [16]. This progress has led to notable performance gains on benchmarks and new multi-task evaluations (e.g. MMAU for audio reasoning). However, most prior works focus on pushing overall accuracy, with less emphasis on how each modality (audio vs. text) contributes to answering different question types.

In multimodal QA it is well-known that models can exploit dataset biases by over-relying on one modality. For instance, a question-only model can answer some Visual QA questions correctly without even “looking” at the image [17]–[20]. A similar concern arises in AQA: certain questions might be answerable through textual cues or common knowledge while others truly require listening to the audio. Which question types rely more on the audio content, and which can be answered mainly via text? And if our model is simply reading or listening. Answering this is crucial for understanding the modality grounding of AQA tasks and guiding the design of a more robust Audio Question Answering model.

In this work, we systematically investigate the modality grounding of Audio Question Answering (AQA) by analyzing how different question types depend on audio, text, or a combination of both. To address this research gap, we design a controlled experimental framework in which a fusion coefficient governs the relative influence of audio and text inputs for each question. We evaluate model accuracy across six distinct AQA question types, ranging from sound counting and temporal detection to knowledge recall and contextual reasoning. Using both accuracy trends and one-way ANOVA statistical tests, we provide a nuanced picture of how modality balance impacts performance. The results not only highlight where current models excel or fall short, but also expose which question types are genuinely grounded in the audio, and those vulnerable to textual bias.

2. METHOD

In this section, we introduce our approach to analyzing the sensitivity of modality in Audio Question Answering (AQA) performance. We present EchoTwin-QA [21], a dual-tower AQA model designed to systematically control and observe the influence of audio and textual modalities. EchoTwin-QA integrates a state-of-the-art BEATs audio encoder as its audio tower and a BERT model as its text tower. To precisely investigate cross-modal interactions, we incorporate a scalar fusion parameter λ that linearly mixes the audio and textual feature embeddings prior to answer classification, allowing us to sweep across a spectrum of modality balances. Performance is then evaluated across eleven λ values for each question type, and one-way ANOVA tests are applied to determine whether changes in the balance of modality lead to statistically significant differences in accuracy.

Fig. 1: Dual-tower architecture: a BEATs audio encoder and a BERT text encoder produce modality-specific embeddings, concatenated and fed to a lightweight MLP classifier with a scalar fusion parameter.

2.1. Model Architecture

Our system *EchoTwin-QA* follows a dual-tower paradigm as shown in Fig.1 in which an **audio tower** (BEATs) and a **text tower** (BERT) are fused by a single scalar, $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, that controls the relative weight of each modality.

A waveform $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is fed to BEATs, yielding a sequence of hidden states $\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}_1, \dots, \mathbf{a}_{T_a}] \in \mathbb{R}^{T_a \times d_a}$. We mean-pool these states to obtain a fixed-length embedding

$$\mathbf{h}_a = \frac{1}{T_a} \sum_{t=1}^{T_a} \mathbf{a}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d_a}. \quad (1)$$

The question concatenated with its answer choices is tokenised and processed by BERT, producing hidden states $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_T]$. The standard [CLS] vector serves as the text embedding

$$\mathbf{h}_t = \mathbf{h}_{\text{CLS}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_t}. \quad (2)$$

A single scalar λ modulates the contribution of each tower:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_a = \lambda \mathbf{h}_a, \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_t = (1 - \lambda) \mathbf{h}_t. \quad (4)$$

The weighted embeddings are concatenated

$$\mathbf{z} = [\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_a \parallel \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_t] \in \mathbb{R}^{d_a + d_t}, \quad (5)$$

and passed to a lightweight two-layer multilayer perceptron

$$\mathbf{u} = \text{ReLU}(W_1 \mathbf{z} + b_1), \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \text{softmax}(W_2 \mathbf{u} + b_2) \in \mathbb{R}^K, \quad (7)$$

where K is the number of answer choices.

We train with label-smoothed cross-entropy:

$$\mathcal{L} = (1 - \varepsilon) \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}, \mathbf{y}) + \varepsilon \frac{1}{K}. \quad (8)$$

Only the parameters of the two-layer MLP (and optionally the top L layers of BEATs) are trainable; both encoders are otherwise frozen.

2.2. Statistical Analysis

For each fusion coefficient λ we record, for every QA pair i , a binary correctness flag

$$c_i^{(\lambda)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the predicted answer matches ground truth,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Flags are stratified according to the organiser-supplied question types ($|\mathcal{Q}| = 11$). For a fixed type $q \in \mathcal{Q}$ we obtain $G = 11$ groups

$$\mathcal{G}_q(\lambda) = \{c_i^{(\lambda)} \mid q_i = q\}, \quad \lambda \in \{0.0, 0.1, \dots, 1.0\},$$

each containing N_λ Bernoulli observations. We test the null hypothesis $H_0 : \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{G}_q(\lambda)]$ are equal for all λ by a fixed-effect one-way ANOVA [22]. Let \bar{c}_λ denote the group mean for a given λ and \bar{c} the global mean for type q . The F -statistic is

$$F_q = \frac{\frac{1}{G-1} \sum_{\lambda} N_\lambda (\bar{c}_\lambda - \bar{c})^2}{\frac{1}{N_q - G} \sum_{\lambda} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{G}_q(\lambda)} (c - \bar{c}_\lambda)^2}, \quad (10)$$

where $N_q = \sum_{\lambda} N_\lambda$.

We report the pair (F_q, p_q) for every question type and declare the effect of λ *significant* when $p_q < 0.05$.

We measured the top 1 accuracy $\text{Acc}(\lambda, s)$ of EchoTwin-QA on the official development set while linearly mixing the two modality embeddings via weighted concatenation. Fig. 2 plots the mean accuracy

$$\bar{\text{Acc}}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}|} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \text{Acc}(\lambda, s) \quad (11)$$

F-statistic measures how much the means vary between λ groups relative to the variance within groups; a larger F indicates stronger dependence on λ .

p-value is the probability of observing such an F under the null hypothesis that accuracy is constant across λ . A small p (< 0.05) means λ has a significant effect.

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1. Dataset

All experiments are conducted exclusively on the official **DCASE 2025 Task 5** AQA corpus [4]. The training portion comprises 0.7k *Bioacoustics QA*, 1.0k *Temporal Soundscapes QA* and 6.4k *Complex QA (MMAU)* items, while the development set provides 0.2k, 0.6k and 1.6k items, respectively. No external audio or text resources are used. The official development split contains 11 annotated question types, but we discarded some type with too few instances. To obtain reliable modality-sensitivity curves we restrict our study to the six most populous and conceptually distinct categories listed in Section 3.2: *Sound Counting*, *Remember*, *Both*, *Sound Detection*, *Apply Frequency*, and *Understand Acoustics*. Their sample sizes on the development set accounted for over 97 % of the available validation data.

Fig. 2: Accuracy variation across question types as a function of the audio feature weight λ . Each subplot corresponds to a specific question category: *Understand Acoustics*, *Remember*, *Sound Counting*, *Both*, *Apply Frequency*, and *Sound Detection*. The plots demonstrate how model accuracy varies as λ increases from 0 (purely text-based reasoning) to 1 (purely audio-based reasoning).

3.2. Question type

Sound Counting Asks how many distinct sound events or types are present or how many times a specific sound (e.g., crash, phone, scream) occurs in an audio clip (e.g. “How many different sounds are present in the audio clip?”, “How many times does the crash sound/female scream occur?”)

Remember (Knowledge Recall) A factual statement about the animal species that produced the recording—e.g., a unique trait, behavior, historical fact, or conservation concern—chosen from several candidate statements. (e.g., “Which of the following is a defining characteristic of the species that produced the sound?”, “What unique behavior distinguishes the species?”)

Both (Contextual Reasoning) They ask about contextual or situational information inferred from the audio, including time, place, emotional tone, environmental setting, and background interactions. (e.g., “What time of day is the audio likely set?”, “What might indicate that the speaker is not alone?”)

Sound Detection (Temporal Reasoning) A temporal detail about specific sound events: start time, end time, duration, order, or which sound occurs immediately before/after another. (e.g., “What is the start time of the drawer sound?”, “Which sound occurs immediately after the cough sound?”)

Apply Frequency (Spectral Reasoning) Asks for a comparison of pitch or frequency range between multiple sound events, often in a specified order relative to silences. (e.g., “Which sound is most dominant at higher frequencies?”)

Understand Acoustics (Feature-Based Reasoning) The choice of the text description that best matches the overall acoustic characteristics or main feature/pattern of the recording. (e.g. “Which of the following best describes the main feature of the recording?”, “What acoustic characteristics describe the signal?”)

3.3. Training Configuration

We fine-tune the model once and then freeze all weights thereafter for the λ -sweep evaluation, with Optimiser: AdamW ($\eta_{\text{text}} = 1 \times 10^{-5}$, $\eta_{\text{audio}} = 1 \times 10^{-6}$, weight-decay = 0), a batch size of 32; gradient clip: $\|g\|_2 \leq 1.0$; AMP enabled. For Loss we use label-smoothed cross-entropy ($\epsilon = 0.05$). After fine-tuning, we *only* vary the scalar fusion coefficient $\lambda \in \{0.0, 0.1, \dots, 1.0\}$ while keeping all network weights fixed.

Table 1: Accuracy (%) under audio only ($\lambda=1.0$), text only ($\lambda=0.0$) and the **best-performing** audio+text mixed for each question type.

Question type	Audio only	Question only	Audio+Question
Apply Frequency	16.7	36.7	40.0
Both	18.2	63.4	63.5
Remember	26.2	56.9	60.0
Sound Counting	25.9	30.4	35.7
Sound Detection	27.7	30.8	30.8
Understand Acoustics	17.4	78.3	82.6

Table 2: One-way ANOVA results for the six question types.

Question type	F	p
Apply Frequency	0.56	8.49×10^{-1}
Both	136.80	2.27×10^{-277}
Remember	2.36	9.42×10^{-3}
Sound Counting	0.37	9.58×10^{-1}
Sound Detection	0.28	9.87×10^{-1}
Understand Acoustics	4.57	6.02×10^{-6}

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Modality Ablation in AQA

As we can observe in Table 1, the model performs poorly when relying solely on audio input. In contrast, when provided only with the textual question, the model achieves relatively high accuracy on several question types, especially for *Sound Detection* and *Both*, sometimes approaching or even surpassing performance with modality fusion. This asymmetry in ablation performance highlights a key limitation: while the task is designed to encourage multimodal reasoning, many instances can be answered using text alone, the soundscape is often ambiguous without the semantic guidance.

4.2. Impact of Modality Across Question Types

Sound Counting questions, which involve identifying discrete acoustic events or enumerating occurrences of specific sounds, show a clear dependence on audio information. Their accuracy improved monotonically as audio weight increased—from under 30% to 35.7%. The upward slope is visually apparent in Fig. 2. This pattern intuitively aligns with the fundamental nature of these questions, which inherently require detailed acoustic perception rather than textual reasoning, yet the between λ variance is still dwarfed by the within- λ noise. To

perform better, a model must leverage explicit acoustic cues rather than text-based or common-knowledge shortcuts.

Understand Acoustics and *Remember* types show a similar dependence, but with a distinct delayed response to increased audio weighting. This indicates their substantial reliance on fine-grained acoustic detail. The between-level variance is almost five times the within-level variance, so the jump could be explained, suggesting a threshold phenomenon: the option texts already contain descriptors, which loosely match many recordings. Only when audio dominates can the model compute fine-grained spectral summaries, and factual recall in bioacoustics similarly requires identifying species-specific acoustic signatures. Thus, despite the possible availability of textual cues, these question types ultimately require a robust grounding in acoustic features.

Apply Frequency questions show a different and illuminating trend: accuracy peaks significantly at a low audio weight and decreases as λ increases. The rapid drop-off implies that frequency-based comparative judgments can be partially resolved via semantic or pragmatic cues embedded within the textual question and answer choices. It suggests that these tasks do not demand detailed acoustic resolution as much as contextual reasoning about the frequency order and association with different sounds. A high weighting on acoustic details might obscure semantic subtleties vital for these spectral reasoning tasks.

Both achieve maximum accuracy at a moderately light audio weight ($\lambda = 0.3$). Then follows a slight decline, strongly indicates that contextual reasoning tasks benefit most from balanced multimodal integration, slightly favoring textual modalities. The ANOVA test corroborates this behavior, indicating that over 90% of the performance variance is attributable to the choice of modality weight. These questions inherently depend on interpreting contextual scenarios—such as time, emotional tone, or background interactions—often inferred through textual knowledge or semantic framing rather than precise acoustic features alone. Hence, multimodal systems should prioritize a balanced and nuanced fusion strategy for optimal performance on these questions.

Sound Detection category demonstrates an intriguing and counter-intuitive trend, achieving its highest accuracy without audio feature. Accuracy notably decreases as audio contribution increases. This result reveals that temporal reasoning, as framed by the dataset, might heavily rely on textual patterns or conventional temporal relationships implicitly embedded in the questions themselves. The deterioration with increased audio input indicates a possible misalignment between the provided acoustic evidence and the inferred temporal logic from the textual query. We argue that current models lack the appropriate inductive biases or representational mechanisms to extract and align temporal acoustic patterns in a way that meaningfully supports semantic inference.

4.3. Discussions

From section 4.1 we found a fundamental limitation: the audio branch in current AQA models remains underutilized and often poorly integrated. Instead of serving as a robust perceptual complement to language, audio provides at most a subtle and inconsistent benefit.

In Section 4.2 we find that questions that require more audio are those whose answers depend on direct, perceptual properties of the sound. For instance, *Sound Counting* tasks demand temporal parsing and event segmentation that are simply not recoverable from the question text or choices. The model must “listen” for actual events.

Conversely, question types that are answerable through text alone typically ask for information that is either (1) explicitly provided in the question and choices, or (2) easily inferred through world

knowledge or dataset regularities. They often leak clues via textual templates—like unique timestamps or the phrasing of alternatives (“highest frequency”, “starts first”)—which the model can learn to exploit without referencing the audio at all. Our ANOVA tests confirm that, for these categories, changing the audio–text balance has no systematic effect: performance is governed by the text modality, and extra audio either adds noise or actively impedes accuracy.

The most intriguing are those tasks that require a nuanced combination of both modalities. Contextual Reasoning (Both) and Understand Acoustics show peak performance at intermediate λ values, with ANOVA statistics confirming overwhelming sensitivity to the modality balance. These tasks demand both situational inference (text: e.g., “Is it day or night?” / “Is someone alone?”) and perceptual validation (audio: background noises, emotional tone, spectral features). Only when models can integrate and align semantic cues with acoustic evidence do they achieve optimal grounding and robust performance. The most valuable are those requiring authentic cross-modal grounding, pushing models to “**listen, read and understand**” rather than to do text-only reading-comprehension guesswork of likely answers.

4.4. Limitation and Future Work

Our analysis is currently limited to the EchoTwin-QA model and official DCASE 2025 Task 5 Dataset, and results may not generalize to other AQA benchmarks with different domain coverage or question design. The total number of questions for each type is unbalanced, which may reduce statistical power and obscure subtle modality effects.

A comprehensive study should be conducted to better understand which question types most effectively test the range of abilities required for robust audio-language grounding. This includes investigating the cognitive demands, linguistic features, and perceptual complexity associated with each type. Moreover, a rigorous taxonomy of question types should be established. Categories might be based on the modality reliance, the reasoning skill required, or the nature of the answer. Such a framework would not only improve the interpretability and fairness of model evaluation, but also guide dataset design to ensure coverage of all critical skills.

The mere existence of strong, type-specific modality biases suggests that a single static fusion weight is sub-optimal. The evidence argues for dynamic fusion—either a learned gating scalar conditioned on the question embedding or a transformer that modulates cross-attention weights per token. An alternative is a Mixture-of-Experts architecture where separate audio-heavy and text-heavy experts compete, and a router network selects the appropriate one per question.

5. CONCLUSION

This work set out to uncover how different AQA question types depend on audio versus question, motivated by concerns over modality bias known in multimodal QA. Through experiments varying the balance between audio and text, we found that despite the multimodal nature of AQA, current models rely more on textual information. Audio input, while essential for certain perceptual tasks such, provides only limited and often inconsistent improvements—and can even impede accuracy for text-dominated question types. The effectiveness of audio remains constrained by poor integration and the dominance of language priors. Our findings emphasize the value of adaptive modality fusion and more precise question-type taxonomies to unlock the full potential of AQA systems. To advance AQA, future work should focus on developing adaptive fusion strategies and establishing robust, modality-aware question taxonomies, ensuring models are grounded in both sound and language.

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ASDKit: A Toolkit for Comprehensive Evaluation of Anomalous Sound Detection Methods

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Abstract—In this paper, we introduce ASDKit, a toolkit for anomalous sound detection (ASD) task. Our aim is to facilitate ASD research by providing an open-source framework that collects and carefully evaluates various ASD methods. First, ASDKit provides training and evaluation scripts for a wide range of ASD methods, all handled within a unified framework. For instance, it includes the autoencoder-based official DCASE baseline, representative discriminative methods, and self-supervised learning-based methods. Second, it supports comprehensive evaluation on the DCASE 2020–2024 datasets, enabling careful assessment of ASD performance, which is highly sensitive to factors such as datasets and random seeds. In our experiments, we re-evaluate various ASD methods using ASDKit and identify consistently effective techniques across multiple datasets and trials. We also demonstrate that ASDKit reproduces the state-of-the-art-level performance on the considered datasets.

Index Terms—anomalous sound detection, open-source toolkit

1. INTRODUCTION

Anomalous sound detection (ASD) is a technique for machine condition monitoring, where ASD systems aim to detect mechanical failures from their operational machine sounds [1]–[5]. In this task, since it is infeasible to exhaustively collect rare and diverse anomalous sounds, the system is developed with only normal machine sounds. Therefore, ASD systems calculate anomaly scores based on the deviation from the normal sound distribution and assign anomalies to sounds with high anomaly scores.

The ASD field has advanced through the development of various methods. One major approach is based on generative modeling [1], [6], [7], where it directly models the distribution of audio features belonging to normal machine sounds and computes anomaly scores based on the negative likelihood of a given observation. For example, an autoencoder (AE)-based method [1] trains an AE network to reconstruct audio features and computes anomaly scores based on the reconstruction error for a given observation. Other variants of AEs only reconstruct the center frame of consecutive spectrogram frames [6] or mask the input to obtain an autoregressive model [8]. Another recent approach first projects audio signals into a lower-dimensional feature space and then computing anomaly scores based on the distance of an observation from the normal training data samples in that space [9]–[12]. For example, state-of-the-art (SOTA) discriminative methods [9], [12]–[16] train a discriminative feature extractor to classify meta-information labels associated with normal training data, and then compute anomaly scores in the discriminative feature space. Possible choices of meta information include the machine type, machine IDs and specific operating conditions of machines. Alternatively, self-supervised learning (SSL) feature spaces of models trained on (large) external datasets are directly utilized for ASD [11], [17].

Although the proposal of various ASD methods has undoubtedly advanced the field, we argue that further development is hindered by the lack of comprehensive and careful evaluation. A representative effort for evaluating ASD methods is the DCASE challenge [1]–[5], which plays an important role in enabling fair evaluations using unrevealed test data. However, challenge evaluations are conducted on a single dataset and a single trial, which is insufficient for thorough assessment, as we have observed that ASD performance is highly

Fig. 1: Unified framework of ASDKit. (1) Training the frontend with the training dataset, (2) extracting and storing outputs from both the training and test datasets using the frontend, (3) computing anomaly scores for the test data using the backend trained on the training data, and (4) computing evaluation scores based on the anomaly scores and the ground-truth normal and anomalous labels.

sensitive to datasets and random seeds in our preliminary experiments. Furthermore, it is difficult to precisely identify the effectiveness of individual components, as participants develop methods on their own frameworks and often employ ensemble to boost performance.

To address these limitations, we introduce ASDKit¹, an open-source toolkit for the ASD task. The main features of ASDKit are summarized as follows: (1) ASDKit collects various ASD methods into a single open-source repository, enabling easy access and comparison. (2) ASDKit provides *recipes* that complete the entire training and evaluation process shown in Fig. 1. (3) ASDKit supports comprehensive evaluation on the DCASE 2020–2024 datasets [1]–[5] with multiple trials, enabling careful assessment. To demonstrate ASDKit’s capabilities, we re-evaluate various ASD methods across multiple datasets and trials. By analyzing the results, we identify consistently effective techniques and provide new insights. Furthermore, we demonstrate that ASDKit can reproduce the SOTA-level performance on the considered datasets.

2. ASDKIT

2.1. Supported experimental conditions

ASDKit supports the DCASE 2020–2024 conditions [1]–[5], which are summarized in Table 1. Across these conditions, the machine types, the provided meta-information, and the evaluation scores differ. ASDKit provides download scripts and evaluation tools for these datasets. The download scripts automatically download the datasets and add ground-truth normal and anomalous labels to the test sets, for which the labels are concealed during the challenge and released by the organizers afterward. The evaluation tool computes the official evaluation scores according to the respective DCASE year. For all conditions, the datasets are divided into official *dev* and *eval* subsets, and evaluation scores are aggregated separately for each subset. The evaluation score is based on a combination of several types of area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (AUC).

¹<https://github.com/TakuyaFujimura/dcase-asd-toolkit>

Table 1: Supported experimental conditions in ASDKit. MT and Sec denote machine type and section, respectively. The “#ID/Sec” column shows the number of machine IDs or sections within each machine type. The “Dev/Eval” column shows the information used to define the dev and eval subsets. The “Aggregation” column shows how the evaluation results for each machine type and ID/Sec are aggregated to the machine-type level or the dev- and eval-subset level. Amean() and Hmean() are arithmetic mean and harmonic mean operations, respectively. *: the attribute information is not available for some machine types.

Year	#MT	#ID/Sec	Domain	Meta Information	Dev/Eval	Evaluation score for each MT and ID/Sec	Aggregation
2020 [1]	6	6 or 7	Source	MT, ID	ID	Amean(s_auc, s_pauc)	Amean()
2021 [2]	7	6	Source, Target	MT, Sec, Attribute, Domain	Sec	Hmean(s_auc, s_pauc, t_auc, t_pauc)	Hmean()
2022 [3]	7	6	Source, Target	MT, Sec, Attribute, Domain	Sec	Hmean(smix_auc, tmix_auc, mix_pauc)	Hmean()
2023 [4]	14	1	Source, Target	MT, Sec, Attribute, Domain	MT	Hmean(smix_auc, tmix_auc, mix_pauc)	Hmean()
2024 [5]	16	1	Source, Target	MT, Sec, Attribute*, Domain	MT	Hmean(smix_auc, tmix_auc, mix_pauc)	Hmean()

Table 2: ASD methods supported by ASDKit.

Approach	Recipe name
AE	<i>ae</i>
Discriminative	<i>dis_spec_adacos_fixed</i> , <i>dis_beats_scac_trainable</i> , etc.
Raw feature	<i>raw_spec</i> , <i>raw_beats</i> , <i>raw_eat</i>

In DCASE 2020, the machine ID, which identifies each individual machine of the same machine type, is provided as meta information. The evaluation score is calculated as the arithmetic mean of the AUC and the partial AUC (pAUC) with $p = 0.1$. This score is computed for each machine ID within each machine type and then aggregated into dev- and eval-subset-level scores using the arithmetic mean. The dev and eval subsets are defined based on the machine ID [1].

DCASE 2021 newly introduces a domain shift problem, where recording environments or machine operations differ between the *source* and *target* domains [18]. While abundant training data is available in the source domain, only a few samples are available in the target domain. As meta information, *attributes* which denotes the recording and machine operation conditions, and the domain information are provided. The evaluation score is computed as the harmonic mean of s_auc , s_pauc , t_auc , and t_pauc . s_auc and s_pauc are the AUC and pAUC for the source domain, respectively, and t_auc and t_pauc are the AUC and pAUC for the target domain, respectively. Therefore, ASD systems are expected to perform well in both domains. Also, in DCASE 2021, the machine ID is replaced with the *section*. The section defines subsets within one machine type, and it serves a similar role to the machine ID; however, in some machine types, different machine IDs can appear in the same section, and the same machine ID can appear in multiple sections [2]. The evaluation scores for each section within each machine type, are aggregated to dev- and eval-subset-level scores using the harmonic mean.

DCASE 2022 inherits the domain shift problem from the DCASE 2021 condition, but employs a different evaluation score [3]. The score is calculated as the harmonic mean of $smix_auc$, $tmix_auc$, and mix_pauc . $smix_auc$ is the AUC calculated using normal and anomalous samples from the source domain together with anomalous samples from the target domain. Similarly, $tmix_auc$ is the AUC calculated using normal and anomalous samples from the target domain together with anomalous samples from the source domain. mix_pauc is the pAUC calculated using normal and anomalous samples from both domains. These evaluation scores are calculated by jointly using samples from both domains to assess whether the anomaly score distributions are well aligned between domains.

In DCASE 2023 and 2024, only one section is provided, but a larger number of machine types are included. The dev and eval subsets are defined based on the machine types [4], [5]. In DCASE 2024, attribute information is not available for some machine types [5]. The evaluation score is the same as in DCASE 2022.

2.2. Supported methods

ASDKit handles various ASD methods in a unified framework shown in Fig. 1. The supported methods are summarized in Table 2. All

ASD methods consist of *frontend* and *backend* modules, where the frontend extracts some features from audio signals, and the backend computes anomaly scores after processing these features. Training and evaluation are performed in four steps: (1) training the frontend with the training dataset, (2) extracting features from both the training and test datasets, (3) training the backend with the features extracted from the training dataset and computing anomaly scores for the test data, and (4) computing evaluation scores based on the anomaly scores and ground-truth normal and anomalous labels. In the following, we explain the ASD methods supported by ASDKit and their processing pipelines within this four-step framework.

2.2.1. AE: This is the AE-based official DCASE baseline method [1]. The frontend consists of a ten-layer multilayer perceptron (MLP). The input features are five adjacent frames of the log Mel power spectrogram, and the frontend is trained to minimize their reconstruction loss. AE directly computes anomaly scores based on the reconstruction error of encountered test samples in the second step, and in the third step, the backend simply copies these anomaly scores. The AE is independently trained for each machine type, repeating steps 1–4 for each machine type.

2.2.2. Discriminative methods: ASDKit provides various options for discriminative methods. For the frontend architecture, it supports multi-branch CNNs [9], [19] and SSL models [12], [20], [21]. The multi-branch CNN receives multiple input features, such as the spectrum and spectrograms. The frontend independently processes these features and obtains a final output by concatenating the outputs from each branch. Each branch consists of 1D or 2D convolutional layers followed by an MLP. For SSL models, ASDKit supports BEATs [20] and EAT [21], which are widely used in ASD tasks [11], [12], [22]–[24]. Based on previous works [12], we also introduce additional low-rank adaptation (LoRA) [25] parameters to fine-tune these models. These frontends are trained using classification of meta-information labels.

For the discriminative loss function, ASDKit supports ArcFace [26], AdaCos [27], Sub-cluster AdaCos (SCAC) [28], and AdaProj [29], where these angular margin loss functions are known to be effective for ASD tasks [30]. ASDKit also supports the option to choose between fixed and trainable class centers for the angular margin loss functions, as this choice affects performance; fixed class centers have been shown to achieve better results in previous work [9].

For data augmentation, ASDKit supports Mixup [31] and SpecAugment [32], which are widely used in ASD tasks [9]. Additionally, ASDKit supports techniques to boost ASD performance, such as FeatEx [10] and its parameter-efficient variant, subspace loss [19]. FeatEx and subspace loss introduce additional losses using subspace features in the multi-branch CNN, where subspace features refer to the features extracted from each branch before concatenation.

The backend consists of k -nearest neighbor (kNN), where anomaly scores are calculated as the average distance to the k nearest neighbors in the training (reference) dataset from a given observation in the discriminative feature space. ASDKit also supports variants that

Table 3: Setups of the discriminative methods. MB indicates multi branch CNN. Parentheses in the “Training strategy” column denote whether the class centers in the loss function are fixed or trainable.

Recipe Name	Frontend	Training strategy	DataAug
<i>dis_spec_adacos_fixed_wo_mixup</i>	MB	AdaCos (fixed)	No
<i>dis_spec_adacos_fixed</i>	MB	AdaCos (fixed)	Mixup
<i>dis_spec_scac_fixed</i>	MB	SCAC (fixed)	Mixup
<i>dis_spec_scac_trainable</i>	MB	SCAC (trainable)	Mixup
<i>dis_spec_subspace_loss</i>	MB	Subspace loss	Mixup
<i>dis_spec_featex</i>	MB	FeatEx	Mixup
<i>dis_multispec_scac_trainable</i>	MB	SCAC (trainable)	Mixup
<i>dis_beats_scac_trainable</i>	BEATs w/ LoRA	SCAC (trainable)	Mixup
<i>dis_eat_scac_trainable</i>	EAT w/ LoRA	SCAC (trainable)	Mixup

incorporate kmeans clustering [9], SMOTE oversampling [23], [33], and anomaly score rescaling [34]. Kmeans clustering and SMOTE are used to balance the number of training samples between the source and target domains. Kmeans clustering reduces the number of samples in the source domain, and the resulting centroids are used as reference samples in the subsequent kNN-based anomaly score calculation. SMOTE is applied to oversample the training samples in the target domain. The anomaly score rescaling technique [34] rescales anomaly scores based on the local density of training samples in the feature space, addressing the tendency for low-density target domains to exhibit higher anomaly scores.

The discriminative methods train a common frontend using data from all machine types, and then independently train the backend for each machine type by repeating steps 2–4 for each type.

2.2.3. Raw feature-based methods: ASDKit supports raw feature-based ASD methods [11], [35], where the frontend extracts raw features without training with meta-information label classification. For example, as raw features, [35] uses the time-averaged spectrogram, and [11] uses BEATs features without fine-tuning. For the backend, the same kNN-based anomaly score calculation as in the discriminative methods is employed. This method repeats steps 2–4 for each machine type, skipping the frontend training in the first step.

3. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We re-evaluated various ASD methods using ASDKit to demonstrate its capabilities.

3.1. Setups

3.1.1. Datasets and metrics: We used the DCASE 2020–2024 datasets [1]–[5] and the official evaluation scores described in Sec. 2.1. We computed the arithmetic mean and standard deviation across four independent trials, where each trial’s official score was calculated as the harmonic or arithmetic mean, as defined in Table 1.

3.1.2. Evaluated methods and their setups: In the following, we list the ASD methods evaluated in this paper and describe their setups. Each method is referred to by its recipe name provided in ASDKit.

ae is the AE-based method [1] described in Sec. 2.2.1. We trained the AE network for 50 epochs using the Adam optimizer [36] using the mean squared error as a loss function with a fixed learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 256. For the input features, we used five adjacent frames of the log Mel power spectrogram, with 128 Mel bins, a DFT size of 1024 samples, and a hop size of 512 samples.

The discriminative methods we evaluated are summarized in Table 3. Mixup [31] was always applied with a probability of 50%.

dis_multispec_scac_trainable extracted 512-dimensional features from an amplitude spectrum and three spectrograms with different DFT sizes (256, 512, and 1024 samples), while the other multi-branch CNN methods extracted 256-dimensional features from an amplitude spectrum and an amplitude spectrogram with a DFT size of 1024 samples. The hop size was set to half the DFT size, and frequency bins in the range of 200 Hz to 8000 Hz were used. We trained the multi-branch CNNs for 16 epochs using AdamW optimizer [37] with a fixed learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 64. For *dis_beats_scac_trainable*, we used the *BEATs_iter3.pt* checkpoint and introduced LoRA parameters to the query and key projection layers within the Transformer. The 768-dimensional feature sequence from BEATs was aggregated using a statistics pooling layer [38] and then projected to a 256-dimensional feature using a linear layer. For *dis_eat_scac_trainable*, we used the *EAT-base_epoch10_pt.pt* checkpoint and introduced LoRA parameters to the query, key, and value projection layers. A 768-dimensional CLS feature from EAT was projected to a 256-dimensional feature using a linear layer. We fine-tuned the SSL-based models for 25 epochs using AdamW optimizer with a batch size of 8 and a LoRA rank of 64. The learning rate was linearly increased from 0 to 0.0001 over the first 5,000 steps.

For the raw feature-based methods described in Sec. 2.2.3, we evaluated *raw_spec*, *raw_beats*, and *raw_eat*. *raw_spec* used time-averaged Mel amplitude spectrograms with 128 Mel bins, a DFT size of 1024 samples, and a hop size of 512 samples. *raw_beats* averaged the 768-dimensional feature sequence from BEATs, while *raw_eat* directly used the 768-dimensional CLS feature from EAT.

For the discriminative methods and raw feature-based methods, we used a kNN-based backend with $k = 1$ described in Sec. 2.2.2. We also used kmeans clustering, SMOTE oversampling, and anomaly score rescaling techniques. For kmeans clustering, we set the number of clusters to 16. For SMOTE oversampling, we set the oversampling ratio to 20% and the number of neighbors to 2. For anomaly score rescaling [34], we used a kNN-based approach with the number of neighbors set to 4.

3.2. Results

Figure 2 shows the official evaluation scores of the considered ASD methods, where both the discriminative methods and raw feature-based methods employ kNN with SMOTE as the backend. The figure also includes the evaluation scores of the top-performing system and the official baselines reported by the DCASE organizers.² First, it is evident that evaluation on a single dataset and a single trial is insufficient. For example, the performance order of *dis_spec_adacos_fixed* and *dis_beats* is reversed between the DCASE 2023 dev and eval subsets. Also, *dis_spec_adacos_fixed* exhibits a standard deviation of 2.04 on the DCASE 2023 eval subset, with performance ranging from 53.07 to 57.98 across four trials, as observed in our experimental results.

We reaffirm that training techniques for discriminative methods significantly impact performance. For instance, the effectiveness of mixup is demonstrated by comparing *dis_spec_adacos_fixed_wo_mixup* and *dis_spec_adacos_fixed*; the effectiveness of SCAC, by comparing *dis_spec_adacos_fixed* and *dis_spec_scac_fixed*; and the effectiveness of multi-resolution spectrograms, by comparing

²The evaluation scores on the development set are not officially reported. In DCASE 2020, the official scores aggregated across all machine types were also not provided. Although several official baseline systems are provided, only the best-performing baseline systems are included in the figure. The best official baseline systems in DCASE 2021 [1] and 2024 [5] use the same method as our *ae* recipe, while the 2023 [4] baseline uses its variant [39]. The 2022 baseline employs a different discriminative method [3].

Fig. 2: Official evaluation scores. Values are presented as “arithmetic mean (standard deviation)” across four independent trials. Hmean and Amean denote the harmonic mean and arithmetic mean, respectively, computed over all dev and eval subsets across the datasets. Backend for the discriminative methods and raw feature-based methods is kNN with SMOTE. Raw feature-based methods do not involve any random processes; therefore, the standard deviation is not reported.

Fig. 3: Official evaluation scores of *raw_beats* with different backends.

Fig. 4: Official evaluation scores of *dis_spec_scac_trainable* with different backends. Values are presented as “arithmetic mean (standard deviation)” across four independent trials.

dis_spec_scac_trainable and *dis_multispec_scac_trainable*. Additionally, fine-tuned SSL models (*dis_beats_scac_trainable* and *dis_eat_scac_trainable*) consistently achieve high performance.

As a new insight, we find that trainable class centers improve performance in most cases, as demonstrated by the comparison between *dis_spec_scac_fixed* and *dis_spec_scac_trainable*, while fixed class centers achieved better results in previous work [9]. Moreover, the FeatEx (*dis_spec_featex*) and subspace loss (*dis_spec_subspaceloss*) techniques achieve performance improvements similar to those obtained by using trainable class centers. Since both FeatEx and subspace loss employ trainable centers for additional loss terms, we conclude that their performance gains are mainly attributable to the use of trainable class centers.

Furthermore, Fig.2 demonstrates that ASDKit achieves SOTA-level performance. Note that the top-performing systems in DCASE 2021 [40], 2022 [41], and 2024 [42] employed ensembles, with the 2022 system additionally using machine-specific hyperparameter tuning, except for the 2023 [43] top system.

Figures 3 and 4 show the official evaluation scores of *raw_beats* and *dis_spec_scac_trainable* with different backends, respectively. The results show that kNN with SMOTE achieves high performance

in most cases. The anomaly score rescaling technique significantly improves the performance of *raw_beats*, although our re-evaluation across multiple datasets reveals that its effect is unstable for the considered discriminative embedding model.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced ASDKit, an open-source toolkit for ASD research. ASDKit provides recipes for various ASD methods, including AE-based approaches, state-of-the-art (SOTA) discriminative methods, and raw feature-based methods. In addition, it supports comprehensive evaluation on the DCASE 2020–2024 datasets with multiple trials. Using ASDKit, we re-evaluated various ASD methods and identified the effectiveness of mixup, SCAC with trainable class centers, multi-resolution spectrograms, and fine-tuned SSL models. We will continuously update ASDKit with new ASD methods and welcome contributions from the community to facilitate further development of ASD research.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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LiB-TRAD: A Lithium Battery Thermal Runaway Acoustic Dataset for Anomaly Detection

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Abstract— Efficient detection of lithium battery thermal runaway is a critical factor in promoting the large-scale application of lithium batteries in energy storage and electric transportation. Traditional methods rely heavily on contact-based techniques such as temperature, current, voltage, impedance, or structural deformation monitoring, which have limitations in terms of cost, real-time performance, and scalability. In contrast, acoustic detection, with its non-contact nature, low cost, and suitability for large-scale monitoring, is emerging as a promising alternative. While previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of machine learning-based acoustic methods for thermal runaway detection, there is still a lack of an open acoustic dataset covering the entire process of lithium battery thermal runaway. To address this, this paper introduces the first lithium battery acoustic dataset containing both normal and thermal runaway events, annotated with abnormal events. We further evaluate several baseline models and state-of-the-art acoustic event detection models using this dataset. Experimental results show that this dataset holds strong potential for thermal runaway anomaly detection and provides a valuable data foundation and benchmark for future research.

Index Terms—Thermal Runaway, Acoustic Anomaly Detection, Lithium Battery Safety, Audio Dataset

1. INTRODUCTION

With the development of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power [1–2], large-scale energy storage stations and grid facilities have advanced significantly in recent years, leading to the construction of large stations equipped with a vast number of energy storage batteries [3]. Due to their long cycle life, high output voltage, high energy density, and low self-discharge rate [4–8], lithium-ion batteries have gradually become the most promising option among all energy storage battery technologies. Unfortunately, in large-scale energy storage stations, tens of thousands of closely packed battery cells are often deployed, and each individual cell has the potential to undergo thermal runaway due to heat accumulation and material characteristics, which may lead to cascading thermal events and even fire hazards [9]. In recent years, numerous cases of thermal runaway have occurred in both the energy storage and electric vehicle sectors, posing significant challenges to the further development of lithium-ion batteries. Thermal runaway has become the most critical safety issue in the energy storage domain [10–11], and how to detect and intervene in the early stages has become a shared focus of both academia and industry.

Overcharging, overdischarging, and mechanical damage can all trigger the risk of thermal runaway in lithium-ion batteries [12–13]. Fig. 1(a)(b)(c) illustrates the heat generated by mild overcharge and overdischarge conditions [14], while Fig. 1(d)(e)(f) depicts several stages of thermal runaway induced by excessive overcharge. In stage (d), the initial phase, a large amount of heat is generated inside the cell, and the electrolyte begins to produce bubbles, leading to internal pressure buildup. In stage (e), the onset phase, the pressure reaches the threshold of the safety valve, causing it to open and release a significant amount of gas, accompanied by a distinct venting sound. Finally, in stage (f), thermal runaway escalates and propagates

violently, during which the electrolyte is expelled and flames may occur and spread [12].¹

Fig. 1: Mechanism of thermal runaway initiation and propagation [14]. (a) and (c): Mild overcharge and overdischarge conditions in individual cells; (b): Module inconsistency; (d)–(f): Representative stages of thermal runaway progression.

Various feasible methods have been proposed for monitoring thermal runaway in lithium batteries, which can be broadly categorized into approaches based on changes in temperature, pressure, and electrical characteristics [15–18]. Temperature-based monitoring typically involves placing thermocouple sensors on the battery surface to track temperature variations, thereby enabling prediction and detection of thermal runaway events [19]. While effective, this approach requires extensive wiring and suffers from significant latency. Pressure-based methods rely on installing pressure sensors between battery cells to detect swelling, thus providing early warnings of abnormal behavior [20]; however, this method also demands complex wiring and suffers from limited detection accuracy. Monitoring based on electrical characteristics involves using battery management systems (BMS) to measure parameters such as impedance, current, and voltage to assess the battery’s health status [15]. Nonetheless, such methods may lack direct correlation with thermal runaway events and are often costly.

As previously mentioned, the opening of the safety valve during a thermal runaway event generates a distinct venting sound. Consequently, acoustic-based monitoring methods have attracted growing attention. In the study by Su [21], a venting sound detection method for individual lithium cells was proposed, combining XGBoost and wavelet transform to validate the existence of characteristic acoustic signals during thermal runaway and the feasibility of monitoring such events via sound. Similarly, in the work by Lyu [12], four microphones were deployed inside a battery storage

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cabin, and a combination of wavelet transform and cross-correlation algorithms was used to detect and locate the safety valve venting sound. These studies demonstrate that acoustic sensing offers an effective approach for detecting thermal runaway in lithium batteries [12].

Although acoustic methods have proven effective for identifying thermal runaway, growing attention has been paid to predicting battery states using machine learning based on acoustic signals. While several datasets exist for machine learning tasks related to battery impedance and capacity [22], there is still a lack of publicly available acoustic datasets specifically focused on abnormal sounds during thermal runaway. Such a dataset is essential for better understanding the acoustic evolution during thermal runaway and for enabling prediction and diagnosis using sound-based methods.

In this work, we address this gap by collecting thermal runaway sound data from lithium-ion batteries using a microphone array and annotating abnormal events throughout the process. We construct a lithium battery thermal runaway sound dataset and validate its effectiveness through a binary classification task using a CNN-based model. Furthermore, to better reflect real-world scenarios where abnormal data is scarce, we also explore an unsupervised anomaly detection approach based on acoustic signals.

Specifically, our contributions are as follows:

1. We present the first acoustic dataset for lithium-ion batteries that includes both normal and thermal runaway states.
2. We provide detailed annotations of abnormal events within the dataset.
3. We evaluate various baseline models and mainstream acoustic event detection methods, offering a valuable benchmark and data foundation for future research.

2. DATASET CONSTRUCTION

2.1. Data Acquisition System Design

We employed a four-microphone array to collect acoustic data. Specifically, our data acquisition system consists of the microphone array and a central processing unit. The microphones used are ICS-43434 digital MEMS microphones, and a DSP chip serves as the processing core for signal acquisition and transmission. The configuration of the microphone array and the data acquisition system is shown in Fig. 2.

Due to varying scales of battery modules in our thermal runaway experiments, the microphone array needed to maintain a certain distance from the center of the runaway cell. Therefore, the shape of the array was not fixed but adjusted according to the size of the battery module. For single-cell thermal runaway experiments, the microphones were placed at the four corners of a rectangular battery module. For experiments involving a full row of cells, where reactions are more intense, the array was mounted on a rectangular metal frame approximately one meter away from the battery pack.

Fig. 2: Microphone array configuration and data acquisition system. (a) microphone array and data acquisition setup; (b) close-up view of the data processing circuit board.

2.2. Thermal Runaway Data Collection

Here, we used overcharging to trigger thermal runaway in the battery cells. The cell model used was 314-0.5C (Narada, China), and the charging method applied was 157 A, 0.5 C direct current. Data acquisition—including sound, temperature, and other physical parameters—began at the start of charging and ended when water cooling was activated. In total, we collected three sets of thermal runaway acoustic signals, with corresponding cell configurations and microphone array layouts summarized in Table 1. The actual experimental site setups are shown in Fig. 3.

Table 1: Battery configurations and microphone array layouts in thermal runaway experiments.

Thermal Runaway ID	Battery Configuration at Test Site	Triggered Cell Configuration	Microphone Array Layout
1	Full Row	Single Cell	Placed at four corners of the full cell row
2	Full Row	Full Cell Row	Placed on rectangular iron frame surrounding the cells
3	Entire Battery Pack	Single Cell	Placed at four corners of the entire battery pack

Fig. 3: On-site thermal runaway cell and microphone array configuration. (a) single-cell thermal runaway triggering experiment on a single-row cell array; (b) whole-row cell triggering experiment on a single-row cell array; (c) single-cell triggering experiment on the entire battery module.

We collected three complete sets of thermal runaway sound data using a four-channel microphone array, with a sampling rate of 16,000 Hz. Each recording segment is 10 seconds long. Specifically, we obtained 100×10 s, 185×10 s, and 186×10 s of thermal runaway audio samples, and recorded corresponding timestamps for synchronization with video footage and subsequent annotation. The recordings from each channel of the microphone array were treated as separate audio files for data processing.

Additionally, we collected two sets of normal charging sound data, comprising 1000×10 s and 41×10 s segments, to verify that batteries produce almost no audible noise during normal charging. Due to variations in field conditions, normal charging sounds were not included in the training dataset for the subsequent experiments.

2.3. Dataset Construction

Since the acoustic signals during thermal runaway are primarily caused by the activation of the safety valve and the subsequent venting process, we define the safety valve activation and the following sound as anomalous events associated with thermal runaway. We name it LiB-TRAD, which is, to the best of our knowledge, the first sound dataset specifically dedicated to thermal runaway in lithium-ion

batteries. The annotated format of our thermal runaway dataset is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Composition of the thermal runaway dataset.

We extracted mel-spectrograms from both normal and abnormal signals for comparison, as shown in Fig. 5. For illustrative purposes, the spectrograms shown here are derived from a single representative channel of the microphone array. It can be observed that the normal signals contain a large amount of low-frequency components, which are attributed to the noise generated by fans and operating machinery. In contrast, the abnormal signals exhibit higher-frequency and more energy-concentrated components. This is because the sound source of the abnormal venting signal from the safety valve is closer to the microphone array, and both the opening of the valve and the subsequent venting process produce significant high-frequency components.

Fig. 5: Comparison of mel-spectrograms between normal and abnormal signals. (a) Mel-spectrogram of a normal signal. (b) Mel-spectrogram of an abnormal signal.

3. DATASET VALIDATION

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the collected data and our abnormal sound labeling method, we first formulate the abnormal sound detection task as a binary classification problem, i.e., a supervised classification task. By analyzing the results on the validation set, we can evaluate the validity of our labeling approach.

We designed a CNN-based network to perform this task, with the network architecture shown in Fig. 6. Specifically, each audio segment is read at a sampling rate of 16 kHz, and a 64-dimensional Mel-spectrogram is extracted (with a window size of 1024 and hop length of 512). The Mel-spectrogram is then converted into a log-mel power spectrogram, which serves as the input to the model.

The CNN model consists of three convolutional blocks, each containing a convolutional layer, Batch Normalization, and a ReLU activation function. Downsampling is performed using MaxPooling layers. Finally, an Adaptive Average Pooling layer followed by a fully connected layer outputs the prediction probability, representing the confidence that the current input is an abnormal sound.

During training, normal samples are labeled as 0 and abnormal samples as 1. The model is optimized using a binary cross-entropy loss function with the Adam optimizer and a learning rate of 1e-3. The dataset is randomly split into 80% training and 20% validation sets. At the end of each epoch, we compute the Area Under the Curve (AUC) metric on the validation set. A higher AUC indicates better

performance in distinguishing between abnormal and normal sounds, thereby validating the effectiveness of our data collection and labeling methodology. The training loss curve is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6: Schematic diagram of the designed CNN-based binary classification network.

Fig. 7: Loss curves. (a) Training loss curve of Thermal Runaway Experiment 1. (b) Training loss curve of Thermal Runaway Experiment 2. (c) Training loss curve of Thermal Runaway Experiment 3.

The AUC values of our model on the test sets from different thermal runaway experiments are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Binary classification test results of the CNN model on different thermal runaway experiments in the LiB-TRAD dataset.

Thermal Runaway ID	Test set AUC
1	0.9971
2	0.9876
3	0.9893

The results on the test set indicate that our abnormal sound labeling is highly accurate. However, in real-world production environments, it is often difficult to obtain abnormal sound data. In such cases, abnormal sound detection must be conducted in an unsupervised manner [23], which is similar to Task 2 of DCASE 2025 [24]. Therefore, in the following section, we adopt an unsupervised training approach, where the model is trained using only normal sound data, and abnormal sounds are introduced only during testing.

4. UNSUPERVISED ABNORMAL SOUND DETECTION

The task of unsupervised abnormal sound detection for machine condition monitoring has attracted considerable attention [25]. Abnormal sound detection refers to identifying whether the sound emitted by a target machine is normal or abnormal. In this work, we evaluate several baseline and pre-trained models that have demonstrated strong performance in previous DCASE tasks, including the autoencoder (AE) model [26], the BEATs model [27], the EATs model [28], and the Dasheng model [29]. Additionally, we propose an improved AE model as the baseline specifically tailored for the dataset presented in this paper.

In this study, we further designed and implemented an improved AE model, as illustrated in the flowchart in Fig. 8, for unsupervised detection of abnormal sound data. The model evaluates anomaly scores based on the Mahalanobis distance. The proposed processing pipeline consists of three key stages: data preprocessing, model training, and anomaly evaluation.

Fig. 8: Flowchart of the autoencoder model with integrated self-attention mechanism.

4.1. Data Preprocessing

Our training set consists of 80% of the normal audio data, while the test set includes the remaining 20% of the normal audio along with 100% of the abnormal audio, enabling an unsupervised detection task.

We use audio data in .wav format sampled at 16 kHz (SR=16000), organized into two folders: normal/ for recordings during regular operation and abnormal/ for recordings during thermal runaway events. To extract time-frequency features from the audio, we use Librosa to compute 64-dimensional Log-Mel spectrograms (with $n_mels=64$).

The extracted features form a 2D matrix of shape $[T, 64]$, where T denotes the number of time frames. For unified modeling, each $[1, 64]$ frame is treated as an individual input sample during training.

4.2. Model Training

We employ a symmetrical two-layer fully connected architecture and introduces an attention mechanism to enhance the model’s ability to focus on key features. The overall structure is as follows:

Encoder:

Linear(64 \rightarrow 128), Activation: ReLU.

Linear(128 \rightarrow 64), Output: encoded latent vector z .

Self-Attention Mechanism:

We introduce a self-attention module on the latent vector z , formulated as follows:

$$Q = W_q \cdot z, K = W_k \cdot z, V = W_v \cdot z \quad (1)$$

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = Softmax\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d}}\right) \cdot V \quad (2)$$

This module enhances the model’s ability to focus on time-frequency components with significant abnormal characteristics, thereby improving the robustness and sensitivity of anomaly detection.

Decoder:

Linear(64 \rightarrow 128), Activation: ReLU

Linear(128 \rightarrow 64), Output: reconstructed features

The model uses MSELoss as the reconstruction loss function and is optimized with the Adam optimizer. The learning rate is set to 1e-3, and the model is trained for a total of 200 epochs, with the data shuffled randomly in each epoch. The training batch size is 128, meaning that 128 frames are used for each model update.

4.3. Anomaly Evaluation

After training, during the inference phase, the model takes a test frame as input, extracts the latent representation z through the encoder and attention module, and reconstructs the output \hat{x}^- using the decoder. During training, the reconstruction error (mean squared error) is used

as the loss function to optimize the model’s reconstruction ability, expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i^- - \hat{x}_i^-)^2 \quad (3)$$

To better characterize the difference between abnormal and normal samples in the latent space during inference, the model constructs a multivariate Gaussian distribution based on the mean (μ) and covariance matrix (Σ) of all z values from the training set. The Mahalanobis distance is then used as the final anomaly scoring metric:

$$Score(z) = \sqrt{(z - \mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (z - \mu)} \quad (4)$$

This distance measures how far the latent representation of the current sample deviates from the distribution of normal training data. A higher score indicates a higher likelihood of being an anomaly.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We evaluated the anomaly detection performance of each model on the test set using the AUC (Area Under ROC Curve) metric to measure recognition accuracy. The results are shown in the table below:

Table 3: Performance comparison of different models.

	Thermal Runaway ID AUC			hmean	Average Inference Time/ms
	1	2	3		
AE	0.4953	0.5236	0.4864	0.5012	0.12
Beats	0.5861	0.4253	0.5742	0.5173	3.52
Eats	0.6324	0.5236	0.5637	0.5697	1.84
Dasheng	0.7125	0.5324	0.6152	0.6112	0.95
Proposed	0.6892	0.6125	0.5936	0.6291	0.17

The experimental results show that various models trained on this dataset exhibit different levels of performance in the thermal runaway sound anomaly detection task, which validates the effectiveness of the constructed dataset in evaluating model recognition capabilities in complex battery safety scenarios. Among them, the proposed autoencoder achieved stable and excellent results in all three experiments, with a harmonic mean AUC (hmean) of 0.6291, the highest among all models. This reflects strong overall detection ability and good robustness. Additionally, with an average inference time of 0.17 ms, it strikes a balance between performance and efficiency, demonstrating high practical deployment value.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study presents the first publicly available multi-channel acoustic dataset covering the entire thermal runaway process of lithium-ion batteries, comprehensively recording crucial acoustic changes from normal operation to thermal runaway onset. The LiB-TRAD dataset was collected in real experimental scenarios with precise anomaly labeling and phase segmentation, providing a standardized benchmark for training and evaluating anomaly detection algorithms.

We systematically evaluated various typical unsupervised anomaly detection models, including AE, BEATs, EATs, and Dasheng, and proposed an improved autoencoder model as the baseline for our dataset. Evaluation results demonstrate that our dataset effectively distinguishes the stability and generalization capabilities of different models across various experimental scenarios. The proposed improved autoencoder achieved the most balanced performance across three thermal runaway experiments (hmean reaching 0.6291), not only

validating the dataset's applicability for acoustic anomaly detection tasks but also establishing an effective benchmark for future research.

Future work will focus on finer-grained sound event recognition, particularly the acoustic signature modeling of safety valves during early release processes to identify potential warning signals. We also plan to continuously expand the dataset scale, enrich experimental conditions and sensor configurations to enhance model robustness and practical deployment capabilities, ultimately promoting the real-world application of acoustic sensing technology in lithium battery safety monitoring.

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Crossing the Species Divide: Transfer Learning from Speech to Animal Sounds

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Abstract—Self-supervised speech models have demonstrated impressive performance in speech processing, but their effectiveness on non-speech data remains underexplored. We study the transfer learning capabilities of such models on bioacoustic detection and classification tasks. We show that models such as HuBERT, WavLM, and XEUS can generate rich latent representations of animal sounds across taxa. We analyze the models’ properties with linear probing on time-averaged representations. We then extend the approach to account for the effect of time-wise information with other downstream architectures. Finally, we study the implication of frequency range and noise on performance. Notably, our results are competitive with fine-tuned bioacoustic pre-trained models and show the impact of noise-robust pre-training setups. These findings highlight the potential of speech-based self-supervised learning as an efficient framework for advancing bioacoustic research.

Index Terms—Computational bioacoustics, Transfer learning, Self-supervision, Linear probing

1. INTRODUCTION

Self Supervised Learning (SSL) of speech features has led to state-of-the-art performances on linguistic and paralinguistic tasks [1]. SSL methods leverage large volumes of unlabeled data by solving general-purpose pretext tasks and learn contextual and meaningful acoustic representations from the inherent structure of speech. One valid question, given the massive amounts of available speech data, is whether these performances extend to the comparatively under-resourced analysis of non-human animal vocalizations. Recent research has shown that SSL speech models can reach high performance on a range of tasks such as species recognition [2], caller identification [3], or call-type classification [4], [5]. Many such studies have investigated a specific selection of these models with different perspectives, methods, and datasets but lack a comprehensive understanding of how pre-trained speech representations transfer across tasks and taxa.

Drawing from previous work, we thus propose a formal study of speech features’ transferability:

- We benchmark speech models on a set of 10 different bioacoustic tasks, spanning a diversity of taxa, including birds, mammals, and insects.
- We explore three comparable speech models, showing that robustness to noise and multilingual pre-training are key aspects of bioacoustic transferability.
- We compare a set of probing approaches, including linear probing as well as recurrent neural networks, and introduce time-weighted averaging of representations to leverage their contextual nature.
- We confirm the superiority of shallow transformer layers over deeper ones in the context of speech features transferability.
- We further analyze the effect of background noise and vocal frequency ranges on a selected dataset.

2. METHODS

This study unfolds as a set of bioacoustic knowledge transfer experiments from three pre-trained SSL speech models. Regardless of the selected downstream approach, we initially extract pre-trained representations from each layer of frozen speech models. These

representations are subsequently given as train, development, and test sets to a downstream model. The observed performances are taken as a proxy of the speech model’s ability to extract the acoustic information necessary to accomplish the task (see Figure 1). We extend this method, referred to as linear probing [6], to both non-linear and time-wise analysis of pre-trained representations through other downstream approaches described in Section 2.3. The code is available for replication on GitHub at <https://github.com/jcauzi/speech2bio.git>.

Fig. 1: Workflow of the transfer learning method

2.1. Tasks and datasets

The 11 datasets used in this experiment are publicly available as the BEANS benchmark [7]. They include bioacoustic classification and detection tasks, namely “Watkins” [8] (31 aquatic mammal species classification), “CBI” [9] (264 bird species classification), “Bats” [10] (10 individuals Egyptian fruit bats classification), “Humbug” [11] (14 mosquito species classification), “Dogs” [12] (10 individuals dogs classification), “Dease” [13] (20 bird and mammal species detection), “Enabirds” [14] (34 bird species detection), “Hiceas” [15] (Minke whale detection), “Gibbons” [16] (three gibbon call-types detection), “RFCX” [17] (24 bird and frog species detection) and “ESC-50” (50 environmental and animal sounds classification).

For classification, each sample is assigned one or more labels, and evaluation is reported in terms of accuracy. Detection implies identifying subsections of interest and their labels from long recordings with a sliding window approach. Each produced segment may contain multiple labels. Detection evaluation is reported in terms of Mean Average Precision (mAP). All datasets are first down-sampled to the required 16 kHz sample rate of pre-trained speech models. They are split into predefined train, development, and test sets with a 6:2:2 ratio, as in [7]. Although all tasks are not directly comparable due to the nature and balance of their labels, dataset sizes, or acoustic environments, they allow a broad overview of speech models’ performances in an array of bioacoustic scenarios.

2.2. Pre-trained models

SSL pre-training consists in leveraging large non-labeled data to pre-train foundation models optimized to extract general-purpose latent representations. With or without fine-tuning, these representations can

be given to so-called downstream models, or classification heads, to achieve competitive performance on tasks with small labeled datasets [18]. In speech processing, HuBERT [19], WavLM [20], and XEUS [21] are SSL models originally designed for downstream speech recognition. Additionally, they show high performance on paralinguistic tasks such as speaker identification or emotion recognition, among others [1]. Both HuBERT and WavLM were successfully implemented in similar bioacoustic experiments [2]–[5], demonstrating performance that matches or surpasses that of bioacoustic models such as AVES [22], as well as pre-trained bird species classifiers [23] and general-purpose audio taggers. Further details on the three models’ architectures are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Pre-trained model specificities

Model	Pre-train Data	Arch.	Task	#param.
HuBERT large	60k hours English only	24 TL	MP	317M
WavLM large	94k hours English only	24 TL	MP+NR	90M
XEUS	1M+ hours 4k+ languages	18 EBL	MP+NR +Rev	577M

TL = transformer layers, EBL = E-Branchformer layers, MP = masked prediction, NR = noise robustness, Rev = reverberation robustness.

2.3. Downstream setups

We use linear probing [24], i.e., training a shallow downstream model on a given layer of the SSL models, to assess the linear separability of bioacoustic information in their latent representation space. Our first experiment involves training a linear layer on **Time-Averaged** (T-A) representations as

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T x_t, \quad (1)$$

where $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the embedding of the t -th time frame in the full representation (all model representations are 2-D tensors with embeddings of size 1024 for each 20-millisecond frame). This method allows extracting a single input vector of size 1024 for each example in the dataset and is a preferred option in similar transfer learning experiments [1]. We hypothesize that averaging latent representations, particularly in such out-of-domain contexts, might end up diluting relevant time-wise information, potentially leading to suboptimal performance for long sound segments.

In a second experiment, we thus introduce **Time-Weighted Averaging** (T-WA), a form of soft attention that consists of adding a layer of learnable attention weights before averaging all frame representations to better leverage their variability over time. Raw attention scores are obtained as

$$\alpha_t = w_\alpha^\top x_t + b_\alpha, \quad (2)$$

where $w_\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $b_\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ are learned parameters. We then compute a weighted average of feature representations as

$$\alpha' = \text{softmax}_T(\alpha), \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{x} = \sum_{t=1}^T (\alpha'_t) x_t, \quad (4)$$

where α_t determines the contribution of each frame. This weighted representation is given to a linear layer as in the Time-Averaged (T-A) version. The attention weights and the linear probe are trained simultaneously on a single loss. Note that this only adds 1024+1

parameters to the downstream model compared to T-A, no matter the input sound length.

All training procedures were conducted on predefined dataset splits from [7] for 100 epochs. Hyper-parameters such as batch size are empirically determined for each dataset by comparing metrics on the validation set. We test three learning rates (1e-5, 5e-5, and 1e-4) with an Adam optimizer and weight decay for each experiment and display the best observed result for the best layer. Classification tasks are conducted with cross entropy loss and evaluated in terms of accuracy. Multi-label detection tasks are conducted with BCE loss and evaluated in terms of mAP. Random baselines are computed by selecting the highest possible score between predictions of only the most frequent label (for highly unbalanced datasets) or random predictions.

3. RESULTS

Table 2 shows accuracy and mAP of the best performing layer on the validation set for each dataset, model, and linear probing approach, as well as the results from fully fine-tuned AVES bio [22], a Vggish model, and the best supervised CNN-based approach taken from the BEANs benchmark [7]. Underlined results inform on performance gains between our solution and previous BEANs results.

The results show the intrinsic ability of pre-trained speech representations to encode enough information to resolve bioacoustic tasks across taxa with linear probing. All models show variable results across layers. Depending on the dataset, performances increase in the initial layers, reach a maximum between layer 3 and 11 for HuBERT, layer 4 and 15 for WavLM, and layer 2 and 6 for XEUS, then consistently drop in deeper layers. This behavior was previously observed in similar experiments [2], [3], [5] and is consistent with speech models’ layer-wise acoustic information encoding as described in [25]. Both WavLM and XEUS show higher probing performance than HuBERT, which we discuss in Section 4.1. Time-Weighted Averaging (T-WA) representations marginally improve results compared to T-A ones.

In such cross-species transfer learning experiments, one could make the hypothesis that the phylogenetic proximity of a species with humans results in similarities between the vocalizations of said species and speech. This can be based on the resemblance of vocal tracts, anatomical sizes, vocal frequencies, degrees of sequentiality, etc. Although the tasks presented here are difficult to compare due to differences in dataset sizes, annotations, label distribution, and acoustic environments, there seems to be no effect of species proximity with humans on the observed performances. Pre-trained speech models show a general ability to encode bioacoustic information regardless of the species. We thus extend this experiment to account for the effect of time, noise, and pre-training setup in an attempt to better understand the mechanisms underlying such results.

4. DISCUSSION AND PERSPECTIVES

We identify four factors that may account for performance variations between models and datasets. The effect of background noise is discussed in Sections 4.1, and 4.3, species vocalization overlap is investigated in Section 4.1, time-related factors in Section 4.2 and frequency range mismatch with speech in Section 4.3.

4.1. Model comparison

WavLM and XEUS include noise robustness solutions by being pre-trained with dynamic mixing of artificial noise and speech overlap (as well as simulated reverberant conditions for XEUS). This improves resilience to background noise, a significant limiting factor in bioacoustic tasks, since animal recordings typically have much lower sound-to-noise ratios than speech datasets. Although all three

Table 2: Probing Results

Datasets	accuracy					mAP					accuracy
	Watkins	CBI	Bats	Humbug	Dogs	Dcase	Enabirds	Hiceas	Gibbons	RFCX	ESC-50
HuBERT T-A	0.89	0.28	0.62	0.76	0.79	0.32	0.48	0.54	0.19	0.14	0.72
WavLM T-A	0.90	0.34	0.68	0.79	0.84	0.33	0.51	0.54	0.18	0.10	0.76
XEUS T-A	0.89	0.25	0.73	0.79	0.86	0.30	0.44	0.54	0.26	0.08	0.81
HuBERT T-WA	0.85	0.37	0.74	0.75	0.90	0.33	0.44	0.58	0.23	0.13	0.57
WavLM T-WA	0.84	0.38	0.76	0.74	0.93	0.39	0.44	0.64	0.32	0.12	0.65
XEUS T-WA	0.78	0.28	0.77	0.75	0.95	0.32	0.47	0.52	0.28	0.10	0.68
AVES bio ft	0.88	<u>0.60</u>	0.75	<u>0.81</u>	<u>0.95</u>	<u>0.39</u>	<u>0.56</u>	0.63	0.28	0.13	0.77
Vggish	0.85	0.44	0.74	<u>0.81</u>	0.91	0.34	0.54	0.46	0.15	<u>0.14</u>	0.77
CNN (best)	0.80	0.57	0.74	0.70	0.76	0.22	0.46	0.30	0.31	0.09	0.59
random	0.07	0.01	0.10	0.35	0.22	0.03	0.48	0.27	0.02	0.01	0.02

(ft: fine-tuning) Best speech model’s layer performance is in **bold**, best performance between speech and other is underlined.

models show additional differences in their pre-training data (see Table 1), the noise robustness of WavLM and XEUS seems to play an important role in their higher performances. WavLM, in particular, with significantly fewer parameters, outperforms both other models in six out of the 11 tasks. Similarly to background noise, overlapping animal vocalizations may also harm performance in some datasets. For Enabirds and RFCX, the observed low performances can be linked to a significant amount of interspecies vocalization overlap present in both datasets. The enabirds dataset is comprised of recordings of bird choruses, which can contain over six species labels in a single sound sample. Similarly, rfcx recordings are drawn from tropical forest environments with high multi-species presence. WavLM and XEUS pre-training with artificial mixup of two speech utterances seems to offer insufficient robustness to disentangle simultaneously vocalizing species. Conversely, pre-trained bioacoustic models such as Perch [26] and Birdnet [23] have been shown to increase multi-label classification performance with multi-species mixup training.

The multilingual pre-training of XEUS may also explain some of the performance improvements in 4 out of 11 tasks, as English-only pre-training datasets are inherently less acoustically variable than multilingual ones. However, this assumption would need further investigation, as XEUS is also trained on significantly more data compared to both other models.

4.2. Time information

Excluding enabirds and rfcx, two datasets showing relatively low performance in general, T-A representations consistently outperform T-WA on datasets with sound segments shorter than 3.98 seconds. T-A representations do not entirely remove time-wise information, as each frame representation still contains contextual information from previous and future frames, allowing good performance on short sound segments despite averaging. Yet, T-WA results indicate that relying on a learned selection of relevant sound frames according to their representation is an important feature for datasets containing longer segments.

To further analyze the effect of temporal information and linear separability on the observed performances, we replace linear probes with Echo State Networks (ESN) [27] or Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory networks (biLSTM). Both can extract nonlinear information from entire representations without risking a loss of time-sensitive information. ESNs, derived from reservoir computing, mostly consist of an RNN with randomly initialized fixed weights. They are a good approximation of a recurrent non-linear solution that does not demand learning additional parameters compared to linear probing. BiLSTMs, on the other hand, significantly augment

the number of parameters but should produce a strong topline solution with sufficient amounts of training data.

Interestingly, ESNs always showed worse or on-par performance compared to linear probing on all datasets. BiLSTMs showed some improvements for HuBERT humbug (0.77 accuracy with a two-layer biLSTM), HuBERT gibbons (0.26 mAP with a single-layer biLSTM), XEUS enabirds (0.5 mAP with a single-layer biLSTM) and XEUS gibbons (0.35 mAP with a single-layer biLSTM) but mostly underperformed linear probes from either XEUS or WavLM. In conclusion, linear probes applied to time-averaged or time-weighted latent representations seem to outperform more complex recurrent models in bioacoustic tasks, as they may strike a better balance between signal extraction and overfitting.

4.3. Frequency shift and noise addition

From elephant rumbles to bat calls, many animal vocalizations sit below or above the human speech range. We design an ablation experiment to account for the effects of frequency range on the Egyptian fruit bats dataset. Pre-trained speech models are trained on relatively clean recordings of speech at 16 kHz, thus ranging from 0 to 8,000 Hz, with most of the energy between 90 and 2,500 Hz. This could lead to some degree of overfitting to clean signals centered around this particular frequency range, hindering performance on higher-pitched or noisy signals. We investigate whether pitch downshifting of high-pitched bat calls results in improved performance by reducing their frequency towards the speech range. We progressively lower the pitch of the recordings at 16 kHz with factors of 0.125, 0.25, and 0.5 by resampling, then interpolating them with the `rate` function from `pysox`. Surprisingly, Figure 2 shows that this lowers the probe’s accuracy, regardless of the model’s layer used. We also observed this tendency in similar experiments not included in this manuscript: time-stretching as well as pitch-shifting the original 250 kHz samples. In these cases, adding high-frequency information from ranges above 8 kHz did not improve performance either. These results show that speech models may be robust to high frequencies, potentially through their modeling of fricatives. Additionally, our pitch shifting method involves resampling and interpolation, which may result in unnatural audio quality when performed at such extreme ratios.

We further explore noise robustness by mixing bat vocalizations with natural noise sources [28]–[32] at Signal-to-Noise Ratios (SNRs) of 0, -5, -10, and -20 dB. Note that these are extreme factors for speech applications but quite common in bioacoustics. As shown in Figure 3, the accuracy decreases with the SNR in a similar way for all three models. Interestingly, performance remains above chance even at extreme values such as -20 dB, likely because the added environmental

Fig. 2: Performance for the Egyptian fruit bats dataset on the 10th layer with pitch shifting (T-A)

Fig. 3: Performance for the Egyptian fruit bats dataset on the 10th layer with noise addition (T-A)

noise does not fully mask the high frequencies of bat calls. However, since the original recordings are already noisy, further reducing SNRs yields severely degraded samples, suggesting that the robustness of speech models may reach its limit under such conditions.

Both these results indicate some degree of robustness of speech models to bioacoustic transfer learning while partly explaining the variability of their performance across scenarios. Low performance on datasets such as CBI, Gibbons, RFCX, and Enabirds could be explained both by the difficulty of the task or label distribution and because of the significantly low SNRs of the recordings.

4.4. Comparing pre-trained models with random initializations

To further examine the effect of pre-training on speech models’ performance, we test the intuitive hypothesis stating that randomly initialized models should show random baseline performance (as only the pre-training phase should result in model parameters able to capture bioacoustic information). Interestingly, a randomly initialized HuBERT model achieves slightly better-than-chance performance on bioacoustic tasks (with an average of $\approx +10\%$) when evaluated using linear probing. While the model lacks any learned knowledge of speech or acoustic structure, this result aligns with a growing body of

evidence suggesting that untrained deep learning models can provide non-trivial representations due to their inherent inductive biases. This also indicates that most of the discriminative capabilities of SSL models stem from their speech-based pretraining phase, although a small fraction of their effectiveness on bioacoustic tasks may be attributed to structural priors [33], [34].

4.5. Limitations

Comparing performance across datasets must be taken with care due to differences in dataset sizes, tasks, label distribution, etc. We limit our conclusions to relative improvements of specific methods rather than absolute performance differences. Additionally, the use of multiple random seeds would allow getting a stronger sense of performance gaps between models. Here, each training was performed once, from fixed dataset splits provided in the BEANS benchmark. We also advocate for a cautious comparison of our results with AVES-bio, which is based on a significantly smaller model (HuBERT base), pre-trained with in-domain data, and fully fine-tuned on each task. Although our experiments are not performance-oriented, we must mention that fine-tuning of large bioacoustic foundation models with comparable sizes generally outperforms our methods on most of the benchmark [35]–[37]. Conversely, task-specific machine learning solutions and CNNs trained on Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficient representations are mostly outperformed by probing frozen speech models [7].

5. CONCLUSION

This study shows the effective knowledge transfer capabilities of self-supervised speech models for bioacoustic tasks. In particular, HuBERT, WavLM, and XEUS generate rich representations, resulting in competitive performance on classification and detection tasks across taxa. Our findings indicate that phylogenetic proximity to humans does not influence this transfer, emphasizing the generalizability of speech representations in out-of-domain scenarios. Variability in results across datasets highlights the impact of task complexity and acoustic environments. Notably, the presence of noise greatly affects linear probing results, although the use of noise-robust pre-training methods seems to show an advantage. Temporal information remains crucial, with time-weighted averaging approaches outperforming time-averaging of representations for longer audio samples. However, recurrent networks showed no benefits compared to linear probing, likely due to overfitting issues. Finally, speech models exhibit some degree of robustness to the frequency range of bioacoustic signals, even with high-pitched vocalizations. Overall, self-supervised speech models show strong promise for the development of foundation models in bioacoustics, offering interesting solutions related to data quality and quantity. Leveraging large speech datasets and SSL architectures, future work could focus on developing bioacoustic models partly pre-trained on speech with enhanced noise robustness and improved mixup strategies.

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DESCRIPTION AND DISCUSSION ON DCASE 2025 CHALLENGE TASK 2: FIRST-SHOT UNSUPERVISED ANOMALOUS SOUND DETECTION FOR MACHINE CONDITION MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces the task description for the Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) 2025 Challenge Task 2, titled “First-shot unsupervised anomalous sound detection (ASD) for machine condition monitoring.” Building on the DCASE 2024 Challenge Task 2, this task is structured as a first-shot problem within a domain generalization framework. The primary objective of the first-shot approach is to facilitate the rapid deployment of ASD systems for new machine types without requiring machine-specific hyperparameter tunings. For DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2, sounds from previously unseen machine types have been collected and provided as the evaluation dataset. We received 119 submissions from 35 teams, and an analysis of these submissions has been made in this paper. Analysis showed that various approaches can all be competitive, such as fine-tuning pre-trained models, using frozen pre-trained models, and training small models from scratch, when combined with appropriate cost functions, anomaly score normalization, and use of clean machine and noise sounds.

Index Terms— anomaly detection, acoustic condition monitoring, domain shift, first-shot problem, DCASE Challenge

1. INTRODUCTION

Anomalous sound detection (ASD) [1–7] involves determining whether the sound emitted from a target machine is normal or anomalous. This capability plays a crucial role in automating the detection of mechanical failures, which is essential in the era of the fourth industrial revolution and AI-driven factory automation.

One of the key challenges in developing ASD systems lies in the scarcity and limited diversity of anomalous samples available for training. To address this, the first ASD task was introduced in the DCASE Challenge 2020 Task 2 [8], focusing on “unsupervised ASD (UASD),” which aimed to detect unknown anomalous sounds using only normal sound samples for training. Building on this, subsequent challenges in 2021 and 2022 [9, 10] tackled the issue of domain shifts to enable broader application of ASD systems. Domain shifts refer to discrepancies between data from the source and target domains, arising due to variations in machine operational conditions or environmental noise.

The DCASE 2023/2024 Task 2 (“first-shot” UASD) [11, 12] targeted a realistic setting where systems must detect anomalies

for entirely novel machine types without access to similar-type data for training or hyperparameter tuning. This reflects rapid-deployment scenarios in which collecting diverse training or test data—especially anomalous samples—is infeasible, and therefore manual test-driven tuning is unrealistic. Accordingly, the evaluation data comprise machine types absent from the development set to enforce this constraint.

The DCASE2025 Challenge Task 2 maintains the previous task setting as a first-shot problem under domain generalization conditions, using newly recorded machine sound data as the evaluation dataset. In addition, there are several modifications: We provide additional supplementary data for each machine, including clean machine recordings or noise samples, which can optionally be used to enhance ASD performance in noisy environments. Also, participants are asked to provide the computational complexity of their solutions. Although this score is not used for the official rankings, it helps clarify the balance between model complexity and performance—a key factor for lightweight ASD applications on edge devices. In this paper, we provide explanations on this task and discuss the challenge results.

2. FIRST-SHOT UNSUPERVISED ANOMALOUS SOUND DETECTION UNDER DOMAIN SHIFTED CONDITIONS

Consider an audio clip \mathbf{x} , which contains sounds produced by a machine. The objective of the ASD task is to classify the machine as either normal or anomalous by calculating an anomaly score $\mathcal{A}_\theta(\mathbf{x})$ using an anomaly score calculator \mathcal{A} with parameters θ . The input of \mathcal{A} can be the audio clip \mathbf{x} with or without additional information such as labels indicating the operation condition of the machine. The machine is then determined to be anomalous when $\mathcal{A}_\theta(\mathbf{x})$ exceeds a pre-defined threshold ϕ as

$$\text{Decision} = \begin{cases} \text{Anomaly} & (\mathcal{A}_\theta(\mathbf{x}) > \phi) \\ \text{Normal} & (\text{otherwise}). \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The primary difficulty in this task is to train the anomaly score calculator with only normal sounds (UASD). The DCASE 2020 Challenge Task 2 [8] was designed to address this issue, and all the following tasks stand on this UASD setting.

Addressing the domain-shift problem is also essential for the practical implementation of ASD systems. Domain shifts refer to variations in conditions between training and testing phases, which

alter the distribution of the observed sound data. These variations can result from differences in operating speed, machine load, heating temperature, microphone arrangement, environmental noise, and other factors. Two domains are defined: the **source domain**, representing the original condition with sufficient training data, and the **target domain**, representing another condition where only limited samples are available. This year’s task follows the 2022 to 2024 Task 2 [10–12] setting, where the domain information is assumed to be unknown in the test phase and anomalies from both domains have to be detected with a single threshold. In this case, domain generalization is required to achieve good performance.

To further pursue the rapid development of ASD systems in real-world scenarios, solving ASD (a) against completely novel machine types (b) with only one section of training data (c) without handcrafted tunings that depend on test data, are highly important. This is because in real-world scenarios, customers may only possess a single novel machine, and collecting test data—especially the anomalous samples—for handcrafted tuning may be infeasible. This problem setting was named as the “first-shot problem”, and the 2023 and 2024 Task 2 [11, 12] was organized based on this problem setting. The first-shot problem was implemented by introducing two key features to the dataset: (i) The development and evaluation datasets consist of entirely different sets of machine types, and (ii) Each machine type in the dataset contains only a single section. Note that until 2022 Task 2, the provided dataset included multiple sections for each machine type, and the development and evaluation datasets sharing the same machine types.

The DCASE2025 Challenge Task 2 retains the previous task setting as a first-shot problem under domain generalization conditions, while introducing several modifications. First, we have provided additional supplementary data, including clean machine recordings and noise samples. These resources may reflect practical scenarios—such as collecting clean machine data when a factory is idle or gathering noise recordings when the machine is not running. Participants are free to incorporate these additional sources to enhance the accuracy of their models. Second, although large-scale models—such as pretrained networks and ensembles—have become increasingly popular in this task, lightweight models capable of running on edge devices also remain an important area of research. To acknowledge this, participants were optionally asked to report the computational complexity of their solutions in terms of Multiply-Accumulate Operations (MACs). Although this metric does not affect the official rankings, it provides valuable insight into the balance between model complexity and performance.

3. TASK SETUP

3.1. Dataset

The dataset for this task is divided into three categories: the **development dataset**, the **additional training dataset**, and the **evaluation dataset**. The development dataset contains seven machine types, while the additional training and evaluation datasets include nine machine types, with each machine type consisting of a single section. A **machine type** refers to the category of machines, such as fans or gearboxes, and a **section** represents a subset or the entirety of the data associated with each machine type.

All recording are single-channel, lasting 6 to 10 seconds, and have a sampling rate of 16 kHz. The machine sounds recorded at laboratories were mixed with environmental noise recorded at factories and in the suburbs to create each sample in the dataset. For further details of the recording process, please refer to the papers on

ToyADMOS2 [13] and MIMII DG [14].

The **development dataset** provides seven machine types (fan, gearbox, bearing, slide rail, valve, ToyCar, ToyTrain), and each machine type has one section that contains a complete set of the training and test data. Each section contains (i) 990 normal clips from a source domain for training, (ii) 10 normal clips from a target domain for training, (iii) 100 clips of supplementary sound data containing either clean normal machine sounds in the source domain or noise-only sounds, and (iv) 100 normal clips and 100 anomalous clips from both domains for the test. To assist participants, domain information (source/target) was included in the test data. For four machine types (fan, gearbox, valve, and ToyCar) details regarding operational or environmental conditions were provided in the file names and attribute CSV files. However, for the remaining three machine types, these attributes were not disclosed.

The **additional training dataset** provides novel nine machine types (AutoTrash, HomeCamera, ToyPet, ToyRCCar, BandSealer, Polisher, ScrewFeeder, CoffeeGrinder). Each section consists of (i) 990 normal clips in a source domain for training, (ii) 10 normal clips in a target domain for training, and (iii) 100 clips of supplementary sound data containing either clean normal machine sounds in the source domain or noise-only sounds. For five machine types (HomeCamera, ToyRCCar, BandSealer, and CoffeeGrinder), attributes were provided in this dataset. For the other four machine types, attributes were concealed. The **evaluation dataset** provides the test clips that correspond to the additional training dataset, e.g. data of the same machine types as the additional training dataset. Each section consists of 200 test clips, none of which have a condition label (i.e., normal or anomaly), domain information, or attribute information. Participants are required to train a model for each new machine type using only a single section per machine type.

3.2. Evaluation metrics

To assess overall detection performance, we employed the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC). Additionally, we used the partial AUC (pAUC) to evaluate performance in a low false-positive rate range $[0, p]$, where we set $p = 0.1$. To evaluate each system under the domain generalization setting, we compute the AUC for each domain and pAUC for each section as

$$\text{AUC}_{m,n,d} = \frac{1}{N_d^- N_n^+} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d^-} \sum_{j=1}^{N_n^+} \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{A}_\theta(x_j^+) - \mathcal{A}_\theta(x_i^-)), \quad (2)$$

$$\text{pAUC}_{m,n} = \frac{1}{\lfloor p N_n^- \rfloor N_n^+} \sum_{i=1}^{\lfloor p N_n^- \rfloor} \sum_{j=1}^{N_n^+} \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{A}_\theta(x_j^+) - \mathcal{A}_\theta(x_i^-)), \quad (3)$$

where m and n represent the index of a machine type and a section respectively, $d \in \{\text{source}, \text{target}\}$ represents a domain, $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ is the flooring function, and $\mathcal{H}(y)$ returns 1 when $y > 0$ and 0 otherwise.

Here, $\{x_i^-\}_{i=1}^{N_d^-}$ are the normal test clips in domain d in section n of machine type m and $\{x_j^+\}_{j=1}^{N_n^+}$ are all the anomalous test clips in section n of machine type m . N_d^- , N_n^- , N_n^+ represent the number of normal test clips in domain d , normal test clips in section n , and anomalous test clips in section n , respectively.

The official score Ω is given by the harmonic mean of the AUC and pAUC scores overall machine types and sections:

$$\Omega = h \{ \text{AUC}_{m,n,d}, \text{pAUC}_{m,n} \mid m \in \mathcal{M}, n \in \mathcal{S}(m), d \in \{\text{source}, \text{target}\} \}, \quad (4)$$

where $h\{\cdot\}$ represents the harmonic mean, \mathcal{M} is the set of given machine types, and $\mathcal{S}(m)$ represents the set of sections for machine type m . Specifically, $\mathcal{S}(m) = \{00\}$ for the dataset in 2024-2025.

Additionally, although not included in the official rankings, participants were optionally asked to provide information on the computational complexity of their models in terms of MAC operations. It was recommended that this be calculated using the open-source implementation available in [15].

3.3. Baseline systems and results

The task organizers offer a baseline system using Autoencoders (AEs) with two operating modes, identical to the 2023 Task 2 baseline. While both modes use Autoencoders for training, they differ in anomaly score computation. This paper presents the system and its detection performance; details can be found in [16].

3.3.1. Autoencoder training

The AE is trained for both operating modes using log-mel-spectrograms of training sound clips $X = [X_1, \dots, X_T]$, where $X_t \in \mathbb{R}^F$ for $t = 1, \dots, T$ represents frame-wise feature vectors at frame t , where $F = 128$ and T is the number of mel-filters and time-frames, respectively. For input, $P = 5$ consecutive frames are concatenated as $\psi_t = [X_t^T, \dots, X_{t+P-1}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^D$ for each t , with $D = P \times F = 640$. Model parameters are trained by minimizing the mean squared error (MSE) between the input ψ_t and the reconstructed output $r_\theta(\psi_t)$ for all inputs from the training data.

3.3.2. Simple Autoencoder mode

This mode uses the mean MSE of all features derived from the given sound clip as its anomaly score, e.g.,

$$A_\theta(X) = \frac{1}{DK} \sum_{k=1}^K \|\psi_k - r_\theta(\psi_k)\|_2^2, \quad (5)$$

where $K = T - P + 1$, and $\|\cdot\|_2$ represents ℓ_2 norm.

3.3.3. Selective Mahalanobis mode

In this mode, the Mahalanobis distance between the system input and reconstructed feature is used to compute the anomaly score. The anomaly score is defined as

$$A_\theta(X) = \frac{1}{DK} \sum_{k=1}^K \min\{D_s(\psi_k, r_\theta(\psi_k)), D_t(\psi_k, r_\theta(\psi_k))\}, \quad (6)$$

$$D_s(\cdot) = \text{Mahalanobis}(\psi_k, r_\theta(\psi_k), \Sigma_s^{-1}), \quad (7)$$

$$D_t(\cdot) = \text{Mahalanobis}(\psi_k, r_\theta(\psi_k), \Sigma_t^{-1}), \quad (8)$$

where Σ_s^{-1} and Σ_t^{-1} are the covariance matrices of $r_\theta(\psi_k) - \psi_k$ for the source and target domain data of each machine type, respectively.

3.3.4. Results

Tables 1 present the AUC and pAUC results for the two baseline systems on the development dataset, with the averages and standard deviations computed from five independent trials.

Table 1: Baseline results for development dataset.

Machine type	Mode	AUC [%]		pAUC [%]
		Source	Target	
ToyCar	MSE	71.05 ± 0.50	53.32 ± 0.56	49.79 ± 0.49
	MAHALA	73.17 ± 0.39	50.91 ± 0.85	49.05 ± 0.05
ToyTrain	MSE	61.76 ± 0.74	56.46 ± 0.47	50.19 ± 0.25
	MAHALA	50.87 ± 2.88	46.15 ± 1.77	48.32 ± 0.05
bearing	MSE	66.53 ± 2.63	53.15 ± 1.99	61.12 ± 0.59
	MAHALA	63.63 ± 1.15	59.03 ± 1.79	61.86 ± 0.36
fan	MSE	70.96 ± 0.94	38.75 ± 0.74	49.46 ± 0.53
	MAHALA	77.99 ± 0.23	38.56 ± 0.58	50.82 ± 0.06
gearbox	MSE	64.80 ± 1.48	50.49 ± 1.22	52.49 ± 0.37
	MAHALA	73.26 ± 0.78	51.61 ± 0.52	55.07 ± 0.47
slider	MSE	70.10 ± 1.01	48.77 ± 1.07	52.32 ± 0.36
	MAHALA	73.79 ± 1.95	50.27 ± 1.15	53.61 ± 0.26
valve	MSE	63.53 ± 2.90	67.18 ± 1.75	57.35 ± 1.96
	MAHALA	56.22 ± 2.22	61.00 ± 2.98	52.53 ± 1.32

4. CHALLENGE RESULTS

4.1. Overall results

We received 119 submissions from 35 teams. 20 teams outperformed both baselines, which slightly increased compared to last year's task (11 out of 27 teams). Looking at the results for each domain separately, six teams surpassed the baselines on the source-domain AUC, while 25 did so on the target-domain AUC. Four teams achieved higher AUCs than the baselines in both domains. This shows the difficulty of improving the performance on both the source and target domain at the same time. Figure 1 shows the AUC values for the top 10 teams. In the source domain, whether each team could beat the baseline was highly machine-dependent, and many teams struggled to outperform the baseline on average. Specifically, machines for which attribute information was available tended to perform poorly, although it is unclear whether this factor is actually relevant. In contrast, all of the top 10 teams outperformed the baselines in the target domain in the harmonic mean.

Figure 2 compares the AUC values of the top 20 teams between the development and evaluation datasets. As can be seen, achieving high AUC values in the development dataset does not indicate high AUC in the evaluation dataset. This is a typical trend in the first-shot problem setting which started from 2023, and shows the difficulty in finding an approach robust to machine types in the absence of test data. Thus, building an ASD system that works well for unknown machine types remains both a difficult and important challenge. In Figure 3, we compare the harmonic mean AUC values in the source and target domain of the evaluation dataset among the top 20 teams. The figure shows a negative correlation between the AUC in the source and target domain. While the top 3 teams achieved very close official scores (within 1.0% difference), their balance between the source and target AUC varied. Achieving well balanced performance between the source and target domain may be important to achieve high ranks.

4.2. Trends in model size

We analyzed the computational-complexity trends of the submitted systems. MACs were reported by 21 teams. Figure 4 plots each submission's MAC count against its official score; if a team submitted multiple systems with identical MAC values, only the highest-ranked system was retained.

The figure shows a broad range of MAC counts across submissions. It also highlights that larger computational budgets did not necessarily yield higher scores. Notably, two submissions from different teams [17, 18] achieved scores exceeding the baselines while

Figure 1: Evaluation results of top 10 teams in ranking. Average source (top) and target-domain AUC (bottom) for each machine type (“*” indicates that attributes are hidden). Labels “A” and “M” on denote simple Autoencoder mode and selective Mahalanobis mode, respectively.

Figure 2: Comparison of harmonic mean of AUC for development and evaluation dataset across teams.

Figure 3: Comparison of harmonic mean of AUC for source and target domain in evaluation dataset across teams.

using fewer MACs. This shows the feasibility of computationally efficient solutions for first-shot UASD, and could be one of the future directions for research.

4.3. New approaches seen in the top-ranked teams

a. Use of pretrained models

This year, following the trend from previous years, many participants adopted pretrained models in their anomaly-detection pipelines. Many of those teams fine-tuned them with an attribute or domain classification-based auxiliary task, such as the 1, 4, 5th ranked teams [19–21]. On the other hand, interestingly, several of the high-ranking teams achieved strong performance using frozen pretrained networks, exploiting intermediate-layer features along with anomaly-score normalization [22]. The 2nd [23] and 8th [24]

Figure 4: Comparison of official scores of submissions against the MACs values.

place teams solely used frozen models within their submissions, while the 4th-place team [20] ensembled frozen networks to the fine-tuned ones. Nevertheless, teams that trained lightweight models from scratch with classification-based tasks also achieved high ranks, including the 3rd ranked team [17, 18], showing that pre-trained models are not an absolute prerequisite for competitive performance. Overall, diverse approaches were all competitive this year and each approach may still have room for further research.

b. Use of supplemental data

Participants tried utilizing the newly released supplemental clean-machine and noise recordings, applying them in two distinct ways. In the first way, they were used for data augmentation. The 1st [19] and several other top-10 teams [24–26] injected the supplemental clips as an extra class in auxiliary classifiers, blended the noise signals with training samples, or leveraged them in contrastive learning [18] to enrich feature space diversity. Conversely, the 3rd and 4th-place teams [17, 20], used the clean/noise data to build enhancement modules that extracted or denoised target machine sounds from the noisy training data, and supplied these extracted signals to their main anomaly-detection networks.

5. CONCLUSION

We presented an overview of the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2. The task’s aim was to develop ASD systems that work for a novel machine type with a single section for each machine type, where supplemental data such as clean machine sounds or noise-only sounds were also provided. We discussed several new approaches seen in the challenge, such as how pretrained models were (or were not) used and the use of the newly provided supplemental data. While we were not able to discuss all new approaches, we hope that all the technical reports will contribute to the advancements in the field of anomalous sound detection.

6. REFERENCES

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Audio-Based Pedestrian Detection in the Presence of Vehicular Noise

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Abstract—Audio-based pedestrian detection is a challenging task and has, thus far, only been explored in noise-limited environments. We present a new dataset, results, and a detailed analysis of the state-of-the-art in audio-based pedestrian detection in the presence of vehicular noise. In our study, we conduct three analyses: (i) cross-dataset evaluation between noisy and noise-limited environments, (ii) an assessment of the impact of noisy data on model performance, highlighting the influence of acoustic context, and (iii) an evaluation of the model’s predictive robustness on out-of-domain sounds. The new dataset is a comprehensive 1321-hour roadside dataset. It incorporates traffic-rich soundscapes. Each recording includes 16 kHz audio synchronized with frame-level pedestrian annotations and 1 fps video thumbnails.

Index Terms—Audio databases, Sound event detection, Urban sound analysis, Pedestrian detection, Vehicular noise

1. INTRODUCTION

Pedestrian volume data offer valuable insights into urban activity patterns, which support planning efforts such as evaluating sidewalk improvements, assessing land use changes, and identifying areas needing investments in safety and walkability [1]. These data also support optimizing street connectivity and accessibility [1].

The widespread adoption of smartphones has brought new opportunities for automated human mobility sensing, particularly through mobile GPS data. However, growing privacy concerns, particularly under frameworks like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union, have placed restrictions on using mobile location data to track individuals [2]. In parallel, smart city initiatives have adopted the deployment of IoT-based sensors to monitor activity in urban environments. These efforts have largely focused on vision-based systems, such as computer vision and infrared cameras [3], although other sensing technologies have also been tested.

Urban sound offers a promising alternative. Microphones are affordable, energy-efficient, and effective in visually occluded environments. They can complement or replace cameras in contexts where installation is impractical, such as shaded areas, narrow corridors, or locations or scenarios where the costs of cameras are prohibitive. The general feasibility of using microphone recordings for the detection of pedestrians has been shown recently for a vehicle-free courtyard on a university campus [4].

This study addresses two key gaps in existing work. First, the generalizability of audio-based models remains unclear. Given the variability in urban soundscapes, shaped by traffic, land use, and average pedestrian activity levels, it is necessary to evaluate model performance across data collected from different settings, particularly in the presence of typical urban noise. Second, existing studies lack information on interpretability; it is unclear which sound characteristics existing models rely on for detecting pedestrians.

Thus, the main contributions of this study are

- (i) a new publicly available¹ dataset for audio-based pedestrian detection in the presence of vehicular noise,
- (ii) an investigation into how vehicular noise affects pedestrian detection performance, and

- (iii) insights into the acoustic features that enable pedestrian detection.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1. Automated Pedestrian Detection Techniques

Urban pedestrian sensing technologies have evolved over decades, with video cameras and infrared sensors being the most widely deployed to date [3], [5], [6]. Video-based systems, now commonly augmented with computer vision and deep learning techniques, offer high spatial precision but can suffer from limitations in occluded or low-light environments. Furthermore, such systems often raise privacy concerns [7], [8]. Infrared counters, including active, passive, and target-reflective types, are less intrusive but tend to undercount pedestrians, particularly in high pedestrian volume scenarios [5], [6]. More sophisticated but cost-prohibitive options, such as radar, piezoelectric strips, and inductive loops, are limited in spatial scalability [9]. In contrast, audio-based pedestrian sensing remains underexplored, albeit with promising low-cost deployment, resilience to visual obstructions, and potential privacy advantages. As demonstrated by Seshadri et al. [4], audio-based systems can detect the presence of pedestrians by using advances in acoustic scene analysis and deep learning, although challenges persist in signal separation, data imbalance, and generalizability across urban soundscapes.

The generalizability of pedestrian detection models has been explored only recently. Rasouli et al. assessed seven state-of-the-art detection algorithms under varying real-world conditions using the JAAD dataset and found that model performance deteriorates in changed contexts, such as different weather conditions, pedestrian behaviors, or occlusion [10]. They emphasized the importance of incorporating diverse training data, showing that general-purpose object detection models trained on broader datasets tend to generalize better than those trained narrowly on pedestrian-focused inputs. More recently, Hasan et al. conducted a cross-dataset evaluation of pedestrian detectors and similarly found that traditional models generalized poorly because their training source usually does not contain dense pedestrian volume [11]. Interestingly, general-purpose object detectors, not trained for pedestrian detection, showed better cross-dataset performance, suggesting that varied training sources can improve model transferability. Although these studies do not focus on audio-based models, they emphasize that testing generalizability across datasets is crucial. In the context of audio-based sensing, this implication is particularly relevant, as urban soundscapes can vary considerably depending on the surrounding environment.

2.2. Audio-based Urban Sensing

Urban sound has emerged as a rich source of information for understanding city life, complementing traditional visual or spatial data. Early urban noise studies primarily emphasized environmental health and policy, focusing on the quantification of noise pollution from road traffic, railways, and industrial sources [12]–[14]. These works led to the development of standardized noise maps and public

¹<https://huggingface.co/datasets/urbanaudiosensing/ASPEDvb>

Fig. 1: Data collection sites on the Georgia Tech campus in Atlanta.

health guidelines (e.g., [15]). However, beyond its value as a nuisance, urban sound is increasingly recognized as a medium that implies information about human activity, mobility patterns, and the social vibrancy of public spaces [16], [17].

Recent advances in sensing technologies and machine learning enable granular, automated analysis of urban soundscapes. Projects such as SONYC (Sounds of New York City) [18] have established a baseline for classifying general urban sounds, using annotations for broad event categories that include speech-oriented human sounds. Extending this scope of urban audio analysis further, Han et al. and Seshadri et al. introduced audio-based methods for detecting pedestrian presence [4], [19]. Their approach utilized a new large-scale dataset with pedestrian-focused annotations. This dataset is composed of continuous recordings from real-world walking environments, enable models to learn from the full range of implicit acoustic cues (both speech and non-speech) that signal pedestrian presence. Their results highlight the potential of microphone-based sensing as a low-cost, privacy-preserving, and scalable complement to camera-based systems.

Despite recent progress, the generalizability of models across diverse urban environments and the interpretability of these models remain underexplored. Understanding the level of generalizability and audio cues that trigger models to predict pedestrian presence is —given the variety of urban soundscape— crucial for building robust and interpretable systems.

3. DATASET

This study builds on the previously published ASPED dataset [4], which includes annotated audio and video data collected in a vehicle-free courtyard environment and will be referred to in the following as ASPED v.a. This dataset provides the foundation for our pedestrian detection framework and is described in detail by Seshadri et al. [4]. The recorder setup and preprocessing steps are identical to those used in ASPED v.a.

In this study, we introduce an additional dataset, ASPED v.b, collected close to a road with vehicular traffic. Figure 1 highlights the recording location on the Georgia Tech campus in red. The vehicular noise primarily consists of engine sounds and intermittent shuttle buses operating at slow speeds. The proportion of frames containing at least one vehicle detected is 9.16%, 29.00%, 36.43%, and 42.91% for radii of 1 m, 3 m, 6 m, and 9 m, respectively.

The ASPED v.b dataset contains 1,321 hours of audio from 4 different sessions. Each session takes place over a time frame of approximately 40 hours and has audio data collected by 4 to 8 recorders spread along a street. The recording areas are monitored

Fig. 2: Percentage of frames containing pedestrians by hour of day.

Fig. 3: Time-series distribution of pedestrian counts.

by 6 GoPro cameras, which captured 1 fps video recordings totaling 2,946,513 frames across all cameras.

Figure 2 illustrates general pedestrian patterns derived from the labels of the ASPED v.b dataset. The figure shows the ground truth number of pedestrians detected from video recordings at a specific timestamp, visualized for the recording zone with a 6 m radius. Pedestrian activity peaks between 3 PM and 5 PM and declines considerably at night. This class imbalance reflects the ecological validity of the dataset, capturing realistic periods of low activity.

The average number of pedestrians walking the street on a specific day of the week and time by taking the rolling average of the number of pedestrians detected across all cameras is shown in Fig. 3. The peaks align with the times that classes end on campus, demonstrating how pedestrian traffic on campus is closely tied to the class schedule.

Lastly, 2.9% of total frames were obstructed by buses, preventing the video-based pedestrian annotation from producing reliable labels. Therefore, these frames were flagged and discarded in modeling.

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The goal of this research is to provide new insights into audio-based pedestrian detection that might facilitate new approaches with enhanced performance. We conduct three key experiments to explore these aspects: (i) a cross-dataset evaluation to assess the generalization capabilities of models trained on noisy and noise-free sections of the datasets (v.a and v.b), (ii) evaluating the effect of vehicle presence in training data on the performance with vehicle-controlled test sets, and (iii) an analysis of the acoustic cues that the model associates with pedestrian and non-pedestrian instances.

For the experiments, we reproduced the model proposed by Seshadri et al. [4]. This model processes 10-second 16 kHz mono audio inputs by first computing power spectrograms using STFT (window: 25 ms, hop: 10 ms). These are then converted to 64-bin mel spectrograms

Table 1: Cross-dataset evaluation balanced accuracy (%).

Train Dataset	Test Dataset	
	ASPED v.a ↑	ASPED v.b ↑
ASPED v.a	71.74	66.48
ASPED v.b	64.77	69.15

(125–7500 Hz) and normalized via standard scaling. The mean and standard deviation values for normalization were obtained from the implementation provided in the GitHub repository of the ASPED v.a model.² The resulting log-mel spectrograms are fed into the VGGish backbone, pre-trained on AudioSet [20], to extract a sequence of 10 acoustic embeddings, each corresponding to a snippet of 1 s of the input. A Transformer encoder (1 layer, 4 attention heads, 128 hidden dimension), with added positional encoding, processes these embeddings to capture temporal dependencies. Finally, a linear projection layer with ReLU activation, followed by another linear layer and a sigmoid activation function, outputs a binary classification probability for each 1 s snippet, resulting in 10 predictions for one 10 s-input, using a batch size of 256.

4.1. Exp. 1: Cross-dataset evaluation

Following previously established methodology [4], the two datasets, ASPED v.a and v.b, were randomly partitioned into train, test, and validation subsets with an 80/10/10 split, respectively.

To address the inherent class imbalance, we employed weighted batch sampling and a variable weighted loss during training. Model inference results are reported using the checkpoint that yielded the lowest validation loss after 20 epochs.

4.2. Exp. 2: Impact of vehicle presence for training

A key difference between the previously existing dataset ASPED v.a and the new data lies in the presence of vehicle sounds in the audio recordings. In this experiment, we investigate whether this factor in the training data influences model performance on test environments with (VP: Vehicle-Present) and without vehicles (VA: Vehicle-Absent). To this end, we create two distinct test splits of ASPED v.b, controlled for vehicle presence and analyze the results for the models trained on v.a and v.b (cf. Sect. 4.1), respectively.

Furthermore, to assess the models’ propensity for false positives, we sampled vehicle-related categories from the nonhuman sounds section of the FSD50K [21] dataset. FSD50K is an open dataset of human-labeled sound events containing 51,197 Freesound³ clips unequally distributed in 200 classes drawn from the AudioSet Ontology. For this and Section 4.3, we downsampled the audio to 16 kHz and categorized it into human or non-human sounds by following the given ontology⁴. All classes in FSD50K are represented in AudioSet, except *Crash cymbal* (non-human), *Human group actions* (human), *Human voice* (human), *Respiratory sounds* (human), and *Domestic sounds, home sounds* (non-human). Only single-tagged audio samples were included in this analysis, and we filtered the dataset to include only categories containing at least 10 distinct files. The resulting refined dataset comprised 21 human sound categories (989 files) and 133 non-human sound categories (8,097 files). The probability of class 1, which the model was trained to associate with ‘pedestrian’ presence, was used to determine the model’s response.

²https://github.com/urbanaudiosensing/Models/blob/main/data_utils/transforms.py, last access date: September 19, 2025

³<https://freesound.org/>, last access date: September 19, 2025

⁴https://research.google.com/audioset/ontology/human_sounds_1.html, last access date: September 19, 2025

Table 2: Impact of vehicle presence in training data — balanced accuracy (%) on ASPED v.b subsets. (VP: Vehicle-Present, VA: Vehicle-Absent)

Train Dataset	Test Dataset (ASPED v.b)	
	VP ↑	VA ↑
ASPED v.a	65.16	67.87
ASPED v.b	67.49	71.01

4.3. Exp. 3: Model sensitivity to different sound categories

To gain insights into “what the models are listening to,” we analyze the sensitivity of the ASPED-trained models to various audio categories by classifying inputs from the FSD50K human and non-human sound ontologies. More specifically, we investigate which human-generated sound categories were most frequently detected as ‘pedestrian.’ Furthermore, we conduct a post-hoc analysis to determine if any non-human sound categories are consistently misclassified as ‘pedestrian.’

A crucial consideration for this analysis is the difference in both audio characteristics/recording setup and labeling paradigms. The ASPED dataset labels are based on the presence of individuals within a certain amount of radius of the recording device (in this study, 6 m). In contrast, FSD50K annotations do not consider spatial proximity; for this evaluation, we operated under the assumption that all human sounds represent the ‘pedestrian’ class and all non-human sounds represent the ‘non-pedestrian’ class.

We further investigate the specific categories of human-related sounds that our model reliably detects or struggles to recognize. Additionally, we examine non-human sounds that are erroneously classified as pedestrian-related, leading to false positive errors.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Exp. 1: Cross-dataset evaluation

Table 1 presents the balanced accuracy, calculated as the average of sensitivity and specificity, achieved when models trained on one dataset version were tested on the other.

The results indicate a performance drop when models are tested on a dataset different from their training set, which indicates limited generalization across the two recording setups.

These cross-dataset results highlight the complex interplay between the presence of specific types of background noise, such as vehicular traffic, and model generalization. Further investigation into domain adaptation techniques may be beneficial to improve the robustness of pedestrian detection systems in real-world scenarios with varying acoustic environments.

5.2. Exp. 2: Impact of vehicle presence for training

To investigate the specific impact of vehicle presence in the training data, we evaluate the v.a-trained and v.b-trained models on subsets of v.b that were controlled for the presence or absence of vehicle sounds (VP: Vehicle-Present, VA: Vehicle-Absent), as shown in Table 2.

The results show that —as expected— the presence or absence of vehicle sounds in the test set impacts performance. Even though the v.b-trained model was exposed to vehicle sounds during training, predicting pedestrian presence in the absence of these potentially confounding sounds is simpler.

To assess whether the v.b-trained model exhibits a reduced tendency to misclassify common vehicle sounds as pedestrians compared to the v.a-trained model, we compared the average predicted probability of the ‘pedestrian’ class for a curated set of vehicle-related non-human sound categories from FSD50K (Table 3).

The v.a-trained model generally exhibited considerably higher average predicted probabilities for classifying vehicle sounds as

Table 3: Avg. prob. of pedestrian class for vehicle-related FSD50K categories.

Category	v.a-trained ↓	v.b-trained ↓
<i>Race car, auto racing</i>	0.86	0.69
<i>Car</i>	0.69	0.62
<i>Vehicle</i>	0.75	0.56
<i>Vehicle horn, car horn, honking</i>	0.74	0.62
<i>Car passing by</i>	0.71	0.59
<i>Motor vehicle (road)</i>	0.72	0.60

Table 4: Average probability for FSD50K human sound categories for models trained on ASPED v.a and v.b.

Category	v.a-trained ↑	v.b-trained ↑
<i>Female singing</i>	0.95	0.74
<i>Speech</i>	0.94	0.65
<i>Crying, sobbing</i>	0.92	0.63
<i>Laughter</i>	0.91	0.65
<i>Singing</i>	0.90	0.71
<i>Human voice</i>	0.89	0.64
<i>Yell</i>	0.89	0.66
<i>Cheering</i>	0.88	0.66
<i>Chatter</i>	0.87	0.66
<i>Child speech, kid speaking</i>	0.86	0.65
<i>Human group actions</i>	0.83	0.63
<i>Speech synthesizer</i>	0.82	0.59
<i>Conversation</i>	0.79	0.63
<i>Burping, eructation</i>	0.78	0.56
<i>Male speech, man speaking</i>	0.77	0.56
<i>Whispering</i>	0.76	0.52
<i>Applause</i>	0.76	0.48
<i>Chewing, mastication</i>	0.76	0.57
<i>Hands</i>	0.74	0.56
<i>Run</i>	0.74	0.56
<i>Walk, footsteps</i>	0.70	0.58

‘pedestrian’ compared to the v.b-trained model. This suggests that the absence of traffic noise during training in v.a might lead the model to erroneously associate vehicle sounds with human presence, increasing false positives. Conversely, the v.b-trained model trained with traffic noise was more effective at distinguishing pedestrian presence from vehicle sounds as indicated by fewer false alarms.

5.3. Exp. 3: Model sensitivity to different sound categories

To understand the models’ sensitivity to different acoustic cues, we investigated the impact of signal energy and of different (human and non-human) sounds on the pedestrian detection accuracy.

5.3.1. Comparison with RMS energy: The Pearson correlation between the audio’s RMS energy and the model’s output logit is low for models trained on ASPED v.a and v.b ($r \approx 0.14$ and $r \approx 0.29$, respectively), confirming that the learned representations are more effective than a simple energy measurement.

5.3.2. Evaluation on FSD50K Human Sounds: Table 4 presents the human categories as a subset of the FSD50K dataset. On the right, we list the corresponding average predicted probability of the ‘pedestrian’ class for both models. The model trained on the ASPED v.a dataset demonstrates greater confidence when classifying human sounds as ‘pedestrian’ compared to its counterpart trained on the traffic-noise-rich ASPED v.b dataset. While speech-related sounds generally exhibited higher probabilities across both models, subtle performance variations in the ranking of specific categories might indicate that background noise during training influences the model’s sensitivity to different types of human sounds. The overall lower average probabilities for the v.b-trained model likely reflect the masking effect of traffic noise on the acoustic features crucial for human sound identification. Notably, categories intuitively associated with pedestrian movement, such as *Walk, footsteps* and *Run*, were

Table 5: Top and bottom 3 non-human sound categories by avg. prob.

Category	v.a-trained ↓	v.b-trained ↓
Top 3		
<i>Harp</i>	0.94 ± 0.07	0.71 ± 0.13
<i>Trumpet</i>	0.94 ± 0.14	0.80 ± 0.11
<i>Plucked string instrument</i>	0.93 ± 0.07	0.66 ± 0.15
Bottom 3		
<i>Cricket</i>	0.42 ± 0.33	0.48 ± 0.16
<i>Chirp, tweet</i>	0.51 ± 0.31	0.45 ± 0.15
<i>Bicycle bell</i>	0.52 ± 0.36	0.48 ± 0.14

ranked relatively low within the broader set of human sound categories for both models. These findings underscore the impact of the training environment’s acoustic characteristics on the learned representations and the subsequent generalization to out-of-domain human sounds. It should be noted, however, that the majority of signals in this dataset are very different from the typical urban sound recording; thus, these results should be interpreted carefully.

5.3.3. Evaluation on FSD50K Non-Human Sounds: To understand the models’ sensitivity to other sounds, we evaluated their predictions on a subset of 133 (categories with at least 10 samples) non-human sound categories from AudioSet. Table 5 displays the top 3 and bottom 3 categories, determined based on the v.a-trained model’s average predicted probability of the ‘pedestrian’ class. The evaluation on non-human sounds reveals that the model trained on v.a data has a higher tendency to misclassify certain musical instruments as ‘pedestrian’ compared to the v.b-trained model. This may be due to such sound categories being particularly infrequent or entirely absent in the ASPED datasets. Interestingly, the bottom-ranked categories reveal greater prediction variability in the v.a-trained model compared to the v.b-trained model. This higher standard deviation suggests that the v.a model is less certain when classifying sounds that are dissimilar to human presence.

6. CONCLUSION

This research investigated the impact of the acoustic environment on pedestrian detection using a novel pedestrian detection dataset with vehicular noise. Our cross-dataset evaluation revealed a performance drop when models were trained on different environments, indicating limited domain generalization capability. Furthermore, the presence of vehicle sounds in the test set considerably influenced performance, with models showing varying sensitivities based on their training data’s acoustic characteristics. Evaluation on out-of-domain FSD50K data highlighted that models trained in v.a exhibited higher confidence in identifying human sounds but were also more prone to false positives for non-pedestrian sounds. Conversely, models trained with traffic noise demonstrated more cautious predictions. However, the notable issue of false positives across various non-human sound categories warrants further attention. These findings underscore the critical role of the acoustic environment in training robust pedestrian detection systems. The limited generalization observed suggests that future work should focus on domain adaptation techniques to bridge the gap between different acoustic domains. Specifically, exploring methods to enhance the model’s ability to filter out irrelevant background noise, such as vehicular traffic, while retaining sensitivity to subtle pedestrian-related cues is crucial. Additionally, we plan to investigate the integration of multi-modal information (e.g., visual cues) to increase robustness in challenging scenarios. Finally, a more comprehensive analysis of the model’s failure cases, particularly the misclassification of specific non-human sounds, could inform the design of more discriminative acoustic features or robust model architectures.

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TOWARDS SPATIAL AUDIO UNDERSTANDING VIA QUESTION ANSWERING

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce a novel framework for spatial audio understanding of first-order ambisonic (FOA) signals through a question answering (QA) paradigm, aiming to extend the scope of sound event localization and detection (SELD) towards spatial scene understanding and reasoning. First, we curate and release fine-grained spatio-temporal textual descriptions for the STARSS23 dataset using a rule-based approach, and further enhance linguistic diversity using large language model (LLM)-based rephrasing. We also introduce a QA dataset aligned with the STARSS23 scenes, covering various aspects such as event presence, localization, spatial, and temporal relationships. To increase language variety, we again leverage LLMs to generate multiple rephrasings per question. Finally, we develop a baseline spatial audio QA model that takes FOA signals and natural language questions as input and provides answers regarding various occurrences, temporal, and spatial relationships of sound events in the scene formulated as a classification task. Despite being trained solely with scene-level question answering supervision, our model achieves performance that is comparable to a fully supervised sound event localization and detection model trained with frame-level spatiotemporal annotations. The results highlight the potential of language-guided approaches for spatial audio understanding and open new directions for integrating linguistic supervision into spatial scene analysis.

Index Terms— Spatial audio understanding, acoustic scene analysis, question answering

1. INTRODUCTION

Scene understanding by machines using audio signals is a well-established problem in audio processing, audio-based machine learning, and the broader field of machine learning for natural scenes. Early and widely studied tasks include the classification of scene types from audio recordings and the detection of sound events over time corresponding to specific target classes [1]. While these approaches provide valuable semantic insights into the content of an auditory scene, they lack information about the spatial characteristics of the sound environment. To address this limitation, the task of sound event localization and detection (SELD) was introduced [2, 3]. SELD extends traditional methods by capturing both the temporal activity of sound events and their spatial locations relative to the recording device. This spatial information is essential for downstream applications that depend on the positioning and spatial relationships of sound sources within a scene. Introduced as part of the DCASE Challenge in 2019, SELD has built an active and growing research community dedicated to advancing SELD methods. [4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

Most SELD proposals that are capable of handling dynamic complex scenes follow a strongly supervised training paradigm where event activity and location labels are provided at a fine tem-

poral resolution, with a few exceptions trying to leverage self-supervision [9, 10]. Similarly, during inference SELD models are expected to provide predictions at a similar resolution. Such annotations are very difficult to obtain in real scenes, with only a handful of such datasets currently existing [11, 12], including the STARSS22-23 dataset collected by the authors and collaborators [12, 13]. Otherwise, supervised training of SELD methods has relied on simulations of spatial sound scenes [14, 15].

A recent trend in scene understanding across domains involves grounding perception in natural language [16, 17]. It has been explored in a few works for spatial audio scene understanding [18, 19, 20, 21]. Focusing on general sound events, the BAT system [18] evaluates a model’s ability to answer questions on classification, detection, direction, and distance using simulated binaural recordings with up to two static events in reverberant scenes. Questions and answers were generated based on a rule-based approach, while an LLM was used for the QA task. The ELSA system [19] trains a spatial audio model using contrastive learning on a large simulated dataset of FOA recordings paired with captions describing spatial properties. Due to the lack of captioned spatial audio data, the authors use standard audio captioning datasets, simulate FOA by placing sounds in rooms, and revise the original captions with a language model to include source position and room size.

In this work, we train a model that answers natural language questions about sound event localization and detection information, including sound event presence, classification, and temporal and spatial order, based on the sound scene. Unlike previous studies, our model is trained and evaluated on FOA audio from real scene recordings. We use the STARSS23 dataset, which contains approximately eight hours of audio with fine grained spatiotemporal annotations at 100ms intervals. Firstly, we generate a set of detailed spatial captions by converting the metadata into textual descriptions that capture the evolving spatiotemporal structure of each scene, and enhance them using GPT-4 for linguistic diversity. These captions can support both spatial audio question answering and general scene understanding tasks. Secondly, we construct a QA dataset for STARSS23 and similarly apply GPT-4 to rephrase rule-based questions. Finally, we develop a baseline spatial audio question answering model that takes FOA audio features and natural language questions as input, and frames the task as classification.

2. DATASET CREATION

2.1. STARSS23 Captions dataset

To generate detailed textual descriptions of the recorded scenes, we utilize the annotations provided in the STARSS23 dataset. These annotations are available at a temporal resolution of 100 ms and consist of the following fields: `frame time`, `sound event label`, `parent source ID`, `azimuth angle`, `elevation angle`, and `distance`. Annotations reflect

Table 1: Types of questions in the STARSS23 QA dataset

Type	Question Type	Description
I	Yes/No Detection	Check presence of a specific sound event.
II	Event Listing	List all sound events in the clip.
III	Spatial Understanding	List all stationary or moving sound sources. Find the leftmost, rightmost, topmost, bottommost, nearest, or farthest sound event.
IV	Spatial Relationship	Sort events by azimuth, elevation, or distance in ascending or descending order.
V	Temporal Relationship	Sort events based on order of appearance.

multiple sound events occurring at the same time, including events of the same class belonging to different sources.

The durations of the individual recordings in STARSS23 vary between 30 seconds to 9 minutes. To standardize processing, we first segment each recording into 10-second clips. We then apply a rule-based algorithm to convert the per-frame annotations into structured textual descriptions as follows:

Frame-Level Descriptions: For each annotated frame, we generate a basic description of the form: *“From start_time to end_time, a sound_event_label is heard. Horizontal angle azimuth, vertical angle elevation, distance distance, source ID: parent_source_id.”*

Sorting by Source: The frame-level descriptions are grouped and sorted based on the `parent_source_id`.

Sorting by Sound Event: Within each source group, descriptions are further sorted by `sound_event_label`.

Instance Segmentation: Contiguous frame descriptions (with 100 ms intervals) are grouped into instances. Any break in this interval indicates a new instance, allowing segmentation of repeated but temporally separated sound events from the same source.

Trajectory-Based Description: For each instance, we construct a textual summary that captures both temporal and spatial dynamics. Specifically, we log the instance’s onset and offset times, along with the starting and ending values of azimuth, elevation, and distance. Additionally, we track the minimum and maximum values of these spatial parameters and the corresponding timestamps at which they occur. This enables us to generate an approximate trajectory-based description of the sound source’s motion over time. For static events these values are all equal.

The following is a template-based generated description for one instance of a sound event based on the annotations: *From 0.2s to 1.4s, man speaking is heard. It is initially at an azimuth angle of -70 degrees and moved finally to an azimuth of -95 degrees. During this time, the sound source moved to a maximum azimuth angle of -70 degrees at 0.3s and to a minimum azimuth angle of -95 degrees at 1.3s. The sound was coming throughout from an elevation angle of approximately -46 degrees. The sound was coming throughout from a distance of approximately 97cm. Source id: 2*

Since this rule-based approach results in limited linguistic diversity, we use GPT-4 to paraphrase the generated captions, thereby producing a more diverse set of textual descriptions. The Prompt used to generate the GPT captions is as follows:

Paraphrase the following sentences while preserving all factual details, numbers, and structure of the events. Do not add any new information or descriptions. Ensure the paraphrase sounds natural and fluent, but all temporal, spatial, and entity-related details (time, azimuth, elevation, distance, source ID) must remain exactly the same.

Sentence:

Template-based textual description

As an example, GPT-4 produces the following textual description from the earlier rule-based instance example: *Between 0.2s and 1.4s, the sound of a man speaking is heard. The source starts at an azimuth angle of -70 degrees and ends at -95 degrees. During this interval, it reaches its highest azimuth of -70 degrees at 0.3s and its lowest of -95 degrees at 1.3s. The elevation angle remains steady at approximately -46 degrees throughout. The sound is continuously perceived from a distance of around 97cm. Source ID: 2*

2.2. STARSS23 QA dataset

We created a question-answering (QA) dataset for the 10-second segments of the STARSS23 data. Rule-based scene descriptions were used to generate corresponding answers. The QA dataset includes several types of questions, summarized in Table 1.

Each question type is designed to assess a specific aspect of acoustic scene understanding, from typical sound event classification tasks to more complex spatial and temporal reasoning. For instance, Yes/No detection questions (Type I) determine whether a particular sound event occurs within a clip, while event listing questions (Type II) aim to identify all detected sound events. Spatial understanding questions (Type III) focus on identifying absolute spatial properties of sound sources, such as determining which source is closest or farthest, lowest or highest, or leftmost or rightmost in the scene, or listing all moving or stationary events in the scene. Spatial Relationship questions (Type IV) require the model to understand the sound events comparatively, asking it to order all sound sources based on various spatial attributes. Similarly, Temporal Relationship questions (Type V) assess the model’s ability to understand the temporal sequence of sound events by asking it to order all sound events based on when they occur.

Table 2 shows example questions and answers for each of the question types described above. These examples demonstrate the diversity and depth of the QA dataset, ranging from simple detection and listing tasks to more sophisticated reasoning about spatial layouts and temporal orderings. While it is possible to formulate many additional question types around spatial and temporal relationships, we limit this exploratory work to the types outlined above. For each question, we also generated 10 linguistically diverse variations using GPT-4 to promote variability and robustness in language understanding.

Since STARSS23 consists of real-world recordings, multiple instances of the same sound event from the same source can occur within a single clip. Additionally, there are cases where moving sound sources cross paths in space. To simplify the QA task, we only consider the first appearance of each source in the scene when constructing the answers, using the initial time and position information for any required sorting or temporal reasoning.

Table 2: Example questions and answers from the STARSS23 QA dataset

Type	Example Question	Example Answer
I	Is there a sound event of a telephone ringing in the scene?	Yes
II	Which sound sources are active?	['woman speaking', 'man speaking']
III	Which sound event is the farthest from the microphone? What sound sources remain stationary in this scene?	'laughing' ['music', 'bell']
IV	Order the audio events by distance, beginning with the closest. Sort the audio events from the bottommost to the topmost.	['footsteps', 'music', 'door open or close'] ['footsteps', 'clapping', 'man speaking']
V	Arrange the sound sources in order of when they begin, from earliest to latest.	['door open or close', 'footsteps', 'man speaking']

3. METHODS

3.1. SELD QA Model

We formulate the QA task as a classification problem and train an encoder-decoder model to address it. The encoder is based on the SELDnet architecture [2], which includes convolutional and recurrent layers followed by a self-attention module. These layers extract time-frequency features from multichannel input audio while preserving spatial information. The self-attention block models longer-term dependencies in the scene and refines the representation of spatial cues. The output of this encoder captures the relevant acoustic and spatial context of the scene and is passed to the decoder.

The decoder is implemented as a six-layer transformer model with an attention size $d_{model} = 512$ trained from scratch. It takes as input the encoded representation of the audio scene along with a natural language question. The question is first mapped to a continuous vector space using pre-trained FastText word embeddings [22], each with 300 dimensions. These embeddings help capture the semantics of different phrasings of a question. The transformer decoder attends jointly to the audio features and the embedded question to produce the final prediction.

The task is formulated as a multi-class classification problem. For the yes or no questions, the output layer contains two neurons. For event presence, spatial ordering, and temporal ordering tasks, the decoder includes N neurons for each task, where N is the total number of unique sound event classes. As a result, the output layer consists of $3N + 2$ neurons, enabling the model to handle a variety of question types. Figure 1 shows the model architecture of the SELD QA model.

3.2. Loss function

The proposed SELD-QA model jointly handles sound event classification as well as spatial and temporal ordering tasks. Accordingly, we design a loss function composed of binary cross-entropy loss for sound event classification and ranking-based losses for ordering predictions.

For sound event classification questions, the binary cross-entropy (BCE) loss \mathcal{L}_{BCE} is applied to the output neurons corresponding to each sound event class, as well as to the dedicated yes and no neurons. This loss is computed using the binary ground truth, indicating whether each sound event is active in response to the given question. Note that the BCE loss is also computed for ordering-based questions to ensure that the model accurately detects the relevant sound events while attempting to predict their spatial or temporal order.

For spatial and temporal ordering tasks, we use a combination of a pairwise ranking loss and an L1 regression loss. These are

Figure 1: The proposed SELD QA model architecture

applied separately to spatial ordering neurons and temporal ordering neurons depending on the question type

$$\mathcal{L}_{order} = \mathcal{L}_{rank} + \mathcal{L}_{L1} \quad (1)$$

The total loss used to train the model is the sum of the sound event classification loss and the ordering losses:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_{BCE} + \mathcal{L}_{order} \quad (2)$$

The goal of the ranking and L1 losses is to ensure that sound events predicted as active are ranked higher than inactive ones, and, within the set of active events, their predicted ranks match the ground-truth temporal or spatial order. For the i -th temporal or spatial ordering output, the model provides an ordering score $p_i \in [0, 1]$, where a score of 0 indicates that no sound event occurs for the i -th class while higher values indicate a higher position in the relative spatial or temporal ordering compared to another sound event with a lower non-zero score. The ground truth ordering is also encoded in the same way.

Regarding the ranking loss, we define $\mathcal{A} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_M\}$ as the ordered list of M active sound classes representing the correct temporal (e.g. from earliest to latest) or spatial (e.g. from left to right) order, with $a_m \in 1, \dots, N$ being the class index. We additionally define the set \mathcal{B} containing the indices of the $N - M$ inactive

sound classes. The ranking loss is then defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{rank}} = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} \max(0, \delta - (p_{a_i} - p_j)) + \sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^M \max(0, \delta - (p_{a_i} - p_{a_j})) \quad (3)$$

where δ is a fixed margin, set to 0.3 in our case. The first term promotes higher scores for active over inactive classes, while the second enforces correct ordering among the active classes. Additionally, the L1 loss is used to regress toward the ideal ordering values.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{L1}} = \sum_{i=1}^N |\hat{p}_i - p_i|. \quad (4)$$

where N is the total number of classes and \hat{p}_i is the ground truth ordering score of the class i . These components ensure that the model learns to detect sound events accurately while also reasoning about their relative spatial and temporal structure when required.

4. EVALUATION

We train our model using the STARSS23 dev-train split and the dev-train-synth dataset provided in the DCASE2024 Challenge. For reproducibility, the evaluation is conducted on the publicly available STARSS23 dev-test split. Our model is trained for 100 epochs using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of $1e-5$. For a fair comparison, we evaluated our model against the DCASE2024 audio-only SELD baseline model, which is trained on the same dataset without any data augmentation. Note that this baseline is trained using 100ms frame wise labels for SELD task, following a regression setup with the Multi-ACCDOA loss [23] to estimate DoA and distances. The baseline model’s predictions are then post-processed using the same rule-based approach used in the QA dataset construction to derive answers for the QA tasks.

To evaluate the performance of our model, we use different metrics tailored to the specific question types. For sound event detection questions (Type I-III), we report the standard precision, recall, and F1 score to assess the model’s ability to accurately identify active sound classes.

For spatial and temporal ordering questions, we adopt a modified version of the Mean Reciprocal Rank MRR_{mod} , which compares the predicted order of sound event classes (filtered to include only predicted active classes) with the ground-truth order. For each active target class, we compute the positional difference between its predicted and actual rank, assigning higher rewards to more accurate placements. The MRR_{mod} is given by

$$\text{MRR}_{\text{mod}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{c \in T} \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1+|\hat{r}_c - r_c|}, & \text{if } c \in \hat{T} \\ 0, & \text{if } c \notin \hat{T} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Here, $T = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n]$ denotes the ordered list of n unique ground truth active sound event classes corresponding to a given question. The set \hat{T} denotes the predicted ordering of sound event classes identified as active by the model. For each class $c \in T$, r_c specifies its rank in the ground truth ordering, and \hat{r}_c denotes its predicted rank in \hat{T} . If a class c is not present in \hat{T} , it receives a score of zero. Predictions in the ordering output that include classes not active in the scene are implicitly penalized through the precision, recall, and F1 metrics.

5. RESULTS

Table 3 presents the performance comparison between the DCASE2024 baseline SELD model and the proposed QA-based SELD model. The baseline model is trained using framewise supervision for sound event detection and localization, while our model is trained using question-answer pairs derived from the same annotations.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1	Spatial MRR_{mod}	Temporal MRR_{mod}
Baseline SELD	0.74	0.76	0.74	0.58	0.59
SELD QA	0.73	0.69	0.70	0.56	0.59

Table 3: Performance comparison between the DCASE2024 baseline SELD model trained with framewise label supervision and the proposed SELD-QA model.

It can be seen that the proposed SELD QA model achieves comparable performance to the baseline SELD model across all evaluation metrics. While the baseline achieves a slightly higher F1 score of 0.74 compared to 0.70, and marginally better spatial MRR_{mod} , both models perform identically in terms of temporal MRR_{mod} .

It is important to note that the baseline model is trained using fine-grained, frame-wise labels for both sound event detection and localization, providing dense supervision throughout the audio sequence. In contrast, our QA-based SELD model is trained using scene-level question-answer pairs, which provide only coarse, overall supervision without requiring temporally aligned annotations. Despite this weaker supervision, our model maintains competitive performance, demonstrating the effectiveness of the QA-based formulation for SELD tasks and its potential for reducing annotation effort in real-world scenarios.

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, we introduced a spatiotemporal captioning dataset and a corresponding QA dataset built from the STARSS23 real scene recordings. These resources support a novel formulation of the SELD task as a QA problem that probes event detection as well as the relative spatial and temporal relationships of sound sources within a scene. This approach opens new directions for evaluating machine understanding of complex acoustic environments. We developed a baseline QA model that frames spatial audio question answering as a classification task. Our results show that this model performs comparably to the DCASE SELD baseline model trained with frame-level supervision. For future work, we aim to move beyond classification by generating descriptive natural language answers. We also plan to explore pretrained spatial audio encoders and large language model decoders to improve performance on spatial question answering and advance text grounded spatial audio understanding.

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Comparison of Foundation Model Pre-Training Strategies and Architectures for Urban Garden Recordings

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Abstract—Environmental audio recordings captured via passive acoustic monitoring include various sounds such as bird vocalisations, weather phenomena, and human activity. Although abundant and easy to collect, these recordings often contain noise, are location-specific, and lack comprehensive annotations, posing challenges to traditional supervised methods. This paper compares self-supervised pre-training techniques and architectures for developing foundation models to learn transferable feature representations from environmental audio data. The reported experiments use the GardenFiles23 dataset, which consists of two years of stereo recordings and metadata from an urban garden. Pre-training tasks include masked spectrogram reconstruction, in which random patches of mel-spectrogram inputs are masked and the model learns to predict them, and a novel contrastive learning task, in which the model learns to align the two channels of stereo recordings that are masked in a complementary manner, meaning that the masked patches in one channel are unmasked in the other. Two architectures are compared: a Self-Supervised Audio Spectrogram Transformer (SSAST) and a State-Space Model variant (Mamba), which theoretically offers linear-time sequence modelling and improved efficiency. Embeddings are assessed on three downstream tasks: bird detection, time-of-day prediction, and weather metadata prediction. Results indicate that masked reconstruction provides stable convergence and superior bird detection performance, while contrastive learning generates richer embeddings that are beneficial for temporal and weather predictions. Overall, SSAST consistently outperforms Mamba with short input sequences.

Index Terms—Foundation models, environmental audio analysis, bird detection, weather prediction, Mamba

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental audio recordings captured non-invasively via passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) encompass a broad spectrum of sounds such as animal vocalisations, weather phenomena, and human activities. Such recordings provide a valuable resource for ecological monitoring, biodiversity assessment, and the study of human impacts on natural habitats. Despite their abundance and ease of acquisition, PAM datasets are inherently noisy and unstructured, featuring overlapping sources, location-specific biases, and class imbalances dictated by the placement of the recording device. Moreover, the manual annotation of large-scale audio archives is labor-intensive, which further hinders the development of models that generalize reliably across diverse environments.

Foundation models (FMs) have been shown to mitigate analogous issues in various domains by learning generalizable feature representations from large unlabeled datasets via self-supervised learning. The main architecture used to create FMs is the Transformer [2], which has been highly effective in tasks including natural language processing [3], computer vision [4] and audio processing [5], [6]. However, Transformers have quadratic computational complexity with respect to the input sequence length and require large amounts of data to train effectively. Recent work has established State-Space Models (SSMs) as a powerful alternative to Transformers [7]–[10]. SSMs are a class of models that can capture long-range dependencies

in sequential data, while being asymptotically more computationally efficient than Transformers.

In this paper, we explore the use of the Mamba SSM [9] variant for the analysis of environmental audio data and compare its performance to that of the Transformer on three downstream tasks. Our main contributions are the following:

- We establish a baseline for the development of FMs in the context of environmental audio data analysis using a dedicated dataset.
- We compare masked reconstruction and a novel contrastive learning task as self-supervised pre-training tasks for environmental audio data, showing that both approaches can be effective for different downstream tasks.
- We compare SSM and Transformer-based FMs for environmental audio data analysis, showing that the former offer comparable but generally inferior performance to the latter in this setup.
- We evaluate the learned representations on traditional tasks (bird detection) and novel downstream tasks (temporal and weather condition prediction), exploring the abilities and limitations of FMs in extracting complex and informative features.

2. RELATED WORK

In recent years, large-scale pre-trained FMs have been developed for spectrogram-based audio processing. Most notably, the Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST) [5] re-purposes a Vision Transformer (ViT) backbone to operate on 2-D spectrogram patches, while the Self-Supervised Audio Spectrogram Transformer (SSAST) trains the same architecture using a joint masked reconstruction and contrastive pre-training recipe that remains a strong baseline in self-supervised spectrogram learning [6].

Regarding SSM-based architectures, the Self-Supervised Audio Mamba (SSAM) model swaps each ViT block for a Mamba block and attains comparable downstream performance with fewer parameters [11]. To mitigate the inherently unidirectional view of 1-D SSMs on 2-D inputs, researchers have been experimenting with multi-directional analysis of spectrogram patch sequences. For example, AudioMamba scans spectrograms along four paths for supervised audio tagging [12], and simpler bidirectional variants including AuM [13], SPMamba [14] and SSAMBA [15] apply forward and backward SSM passes before merging the hidden states.

On the topic of environmental data analysis, dedicated CNNs [16], [17] and masked-prediction Transformers [18] have pushed bird species recognition. Regarding weather prediction and monitoring, small datasets have been assembled for rain-intensity classification via CNNs [19] or for rainfall-rate regression using a Transformer [20]. Wind noise is usually treated as a noise-removal problem rather than an environmental cue.

3. DATASET

The *GardenFiles23* dataset [21], [22] consists of stereo audio recordings collected from a PAM system installed in a residential back garden in the Netherlands. The system uses a two-microphone array

This work is based on the MSc thesis work of Mr. Koutsogeorgos [1]. Thesis and code can be found in <https://github.com/pk-470/master-thesis>.

Fig. 1: Overview of pre-training pipelines. Left: Masked reconstruction pre-training. Right: Contrastive pre-training.

which captures 3-second stereo audio clips at a sampling frequency of 48 kHz in response to detected acoustic events above an adaptive background noise spectrum model.

In addition to the audio data, the dataset includes metadata such as precise timestamps of the recordings and environmental context, which is provided by a Froggit WH3000 SE weather station installed adjacent to the microphone array in the garden and connected to the WunderGround service. Moreover, each recording is automatically annotated using two pre-trained deep learning models, namely MIT-AST [5], [23], which provides a wide range of geophonic, biophonic and anthropophonic tags, and BirdNET [16], which is used for bird species classification. All recordings containing human vocalisations, based on MIT-AST detections, were removed from the dataset.

This work uses an expanded version of the GardenFiles23 dataset consisting of 1.3 million samples recorded between August 2023 and March 2025, out of which a random sample of 100,000 is held out for testing and the rest for pre-training and validation. We fine-tune on 550,000 samples, 50,000 of which are unseen during pre-training. The raw waveforms are converted to log-mel-spectrograms using 128 mel bands with a time resolution of 85.33 ms and a hop size of 42.67 ms.

4. METHODOLOGY

We follow a typical FM pipeline, where we first pre-train our models on a large dataset using self-supervised tasks and then fine-tune and evaluate them on a smaller dataset using supervised tasks. The input to all models consists of log-mel-spectrograms of size $T \times F = 65 \times 128$, which are split into 104 non-overlapping patches using a window size of $t \times f = 5 \times 16$. Our encoding pipeline follows the SSAST paradigm, consisting of the following sequential steps:

- 1) The sequence of patches passes through an embedding layer.
- 2) A ratio of the input patches is masked using the chosen masking strategy for each pre-training task.
- 3) Positional encodings are added to the input tokens.
- 4) Embeddings are extracted through a series of encoder blocks.
- 5) The extracted embeddings are processed by a task-specific head.

Encoder architectures. Our encoder consists of 12 stacked blocks. We compare two architectures for each encoder block:

- **SSAST** [6]: a model based on the Self-Supervised Audio Spectrogram Transformer architecture. The model is built using standard ViT blocks [4], using 3 attention heads and a hidden state dimension of 192.

- **Bi-directional Mamba (BiMamba)**: a model which replaces the standard ViT blocks with bi-directional Mamba blocks. The block consists of a single forward convolution which is applied to the input sequence, followed by two parallel SSM layers, one for the forward and one for the backward direction, as seen in [13]. We use a linear projection expansion factor of 3, a hidden state dimension of 192, a convolution kernel size of 4 and an SSM hidden state dimension of 24.

Pre-training tasks. The models are pre-trained using the following self-supervised tasks:

- **Masked reconstruction**: a standard self-supervised task where half of the input patches are randomly replaced by a trainable mask token and the model is trained to reconstruct the original input from the unmasked patches. For the reconstruction loss we use the mean absolute error (MAE) and the mean squared error (MSE). The loss is calculated only on the masked patches. The masked reconstruction pre-training pipeline is shown in Fig. 1 (left). In total, we conduct four masked reconstruction experiments: `bimamba-mae`, `bimamba-mse`, `ssast-mae`, `ssast-mse`.
- **Contrastive learning**: a self-supervised task where the model is trained to distinguish between positive and negative pairs of samples using the InfoNCE loss [24]. Instead of creating positive pairs by applying random augmentations on each sample, we use the left and right channels of our chosen dataset’s stereo recordings. The two channels are typically highly correlated, but often exhibit differing background noise and recording artifacts, which can be used as a naturally occurring form of weak augmentation of the same signal. Additionally, two channels are randomly masked by random noise sampled from a truncated normal distribution at a ratio of 0.5 in a complementary manner, meaning that if a patch is masked in the left channel, it is unmasked in the right channel and vice versa. The contrastive pre-training pipeline is shown in Fig. 1 (right), and it consists of two experiments: `bimamba-cont` and `ssast-cont`.

Fine-tuning and evaluation. Finally, we fine-tune our models and evaluate them on the following downstream tasks:

- **Bird detection**: a binary classification task where the model is trained to detect the presence or absence of birds in a given audio clip. The task aims to evaluate each model’s ability to extract

Table 1: Performance metrics on the downstream tasks. The best performing model for each task is shown in bold.

Model	Bird Detection			Time of Day		Precipitation Rate		Average Wind Speed	
	Precision	Recall	F1	MAE	STD	MAE	STD	MAE	STD
bimamba-cont	70.0 (69.5, 70.4)	87.3 (86.9, 87.6)	77.7 (77.3, 78.0)	0.322	0.225	0.193	0.282	0.381	0.318
bimamba-mae	78.3 (77.9, 78.7)	90.8 (90.5, 91.1)	84.1 (83.8, 84.4)	0.381	0.259	0.113	0.250	0.334	0.268
bimamba-mse	76.5 (76.1, 76.9)	91.0 (90.7, 91.3)	83.1 (82.8, 83.4)	0.284	0.219	0.121	0.250	0.350	0.273
ssast-cont	78.9 (78.5, 79.3)	91.0 (90.7, 91.3)	84.5 (84.2, 84.8)	0.190	0.176	0.098	0.232	0.289	0.238
ssast-mae	77.8 (77.4, 78.2)	92.6 (92.3, 92.9)	84.6 (84.3, 84.9)	0.257	0.204	0.109	0.249	0.338	0.263
ssast-mse	76.9 (76.5, 77.3)	92.2 (91.9, 92.5)	83.8 (83.6, 84.1)	0.278	0.217	0.116	0.254	0.350	0.274

features related to bird vocalisations and distinguish them from other sounds in the environment. We assign presence and absence labels by looking for agreement between MIT-AST’s bird-related tags and BirdNET’s prediction confidence score as follows. Clips where both models agree that no bird is present (MIT-AST detects no bird, BirdNET confidence < 0.5) or where MIT-AST finds a bird but BirdNET is very uncertain (confidence < 0.2) are labelled as “absence”, while clips where BirdNET’s confidence exceeds the pre-defined thresholds (0.2 when MIT-AST detects a bird and 0.5 otherwise) are labelled as “presence”.

- **Temporal metadata prediction:** a regression task where the model is trained to predict the time of recording within the day from a given audio clip, which is treated as a cyclical variable and encoded by sine and cosine pairs. The goal of this task is to assess whether the embeddings extracted from each model can represent complex patterns in the daily activity of humans and animals.
- **Weather metadata prediction:** a regression task in which the model is trained to predict weather metadata associated with each audio clip, including precipitation rate and average wind speed. This task aims to evaluate each model’s potential for weather-related feature extraction, which can be useful for monitoring climate change and its impact on the environment.

During fine-tuning the pre-trained encoder is frozen and no masking is applied to the input, while an MLP head is trained specifically for each of the three tasks.

Resources and training time. Training was conducted on an internal computing unit provided by Maastricht University, which is equipped with NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti and Quadro RTX 6000 GPUs, as well as on the Snellius computing cluster provided by SURF [25], which includes NVIDIA A100 and NVIDIA H100 GPUs. Training generally took between 2 and 4 days per experiment for the pre-training phase and around 1 day per experiment for the fine-tuning phase.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Embedding Analysis. We estimate the alignment and uniformity metrics [26] to assess the quality of the learned embedding spaces. Alignment measures how close similar samples are, while uniformity measures how well the embeddings are distributed on the unit hypersphere. To produce similar pairs for the alignment metric, we apply random transformations both on the waveform level (Gaussian noise, volume gain, pitch shift) as well as the spectrogram level (Gaussian noise, random roll, random masking). Figure 2 shows the alignment and negative (absolute) uniformity metrics for all pre-trained models. The Mamba models achieve lower alignment and lower absolute uniformity, meaning that the embeddings tend to cover a tightly clustered area of the unit sphere, while the SSAST models achieve higher alignment and higher absolute uniformity, indicating spread-out embeddings regardless of similarity.

Fig. 2: Alignment and absolute uniformity of the embeddings for all pre-trained models.

Table 1 shows the performance of the pre-trained and fine-tuned models on the three downstream tasks.

Bird detection. We evaluate the performance of the fine-tuned models on the bird detection task using the standard accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score metrics. Confidence intervals are computed at a level of 95% using 1,000 bootstrap samples. The results suggest *ssast-mae* as the best performing model in terms of recall, while *ssast-cont* achieves the highest precision, with both models achieving similar F1 scores. We observe that the Mamba models generally perform worse than their corresponding SSAST models for each pre-training technique, while the MAE pre-training task outperforms the MSE task across both models.

Time of day prediction. To assess performance on the time-of-day prediction task, we compute the minimum angle difference between the predicted and ground-truth angles. This difference is then normalized to the range [0, 1), corresponding to fractions of a 12-hour period. We calculate the mean absolute error (MAE) and its standard deviation to quantify the prediction error. The *ssast-mae* model achieves the lowest mean absolute error, along with the lowest standard deviation.

We further examine the ability of the models to make predictions that indicate insights about the acoustic patterns that may appear throughout a 24-hour period. To this end, we bin the true and predicted values into 6-hour intervals (Night, Morning, Afternoon, Evening). We then compute the confusion matrix for the true and predicted values, which is shown for the two best performing models of each type in Figure 3. The results show that the models tend to classify the night hours correctly, which is most likely attributed to the decreased acoustic activity during the night-time. All models except for *ssast-cont* tend to predict “Afternoon” for most samples outside the night hours. We hypothesise that all models apart from *ssast-cont* essentially collapse the task to a binary classification problem, with one class corresponding to “inactive” hours, which are predicted during night-time, and the other class to “active” hours, which are predicted near the dataset mean in the opposite direction,

Fig. 3: Confusion matrices for the true and predicted time-of-day values for all pre-trained models.

i.e., “Afternoon”. Conversely, the *ssast-cont* model is able to learn more complex patterns, with most of its misclassifications occurring between consecutive time intervals of similar acoustic activity. For example, morning and afternoon hours are expected to present with similar acoustic patterns in terms of animal and human activity.

Weather metadata prediction. We calculate the mean and standard deviation of the absolute error between the predicted and true values for the precipitation rate and average wind speed tasks. We find that the *ssast-cont* model achieves the lowest mean absolute error and standard deviation for both tasks, while the SSAST-based models outperform the Bi-directional Mamba-based models for each pre-training technique.

To assess model performance across varying weather conditions, we divide the precipitation rate and average wind speed values into five equally sized bins and compute the mean absolute error for each bin, along with its standard deviation. As shown in Figure 4, the *ssast-cont* model achieves the most consistent performance, with a binned MAE standard deviation of 0.65 for precipitation rate and 0.09 for wind speed. Regarding precipitation, MAE increases monotonically with rain intensity for all models. We attribute this pattern both to the scarcity of heavy rain samples (over 90% of observations record negligible precipitation) and the fact that intense rainfall produces overwhelming broadband, high-energy acoustic noise that obscures finer spectral features. In contrast, wind speed MAE exhibits a sharp decline after the first bin. Under calm conditions, estimation error may be elevated because biotic and anthropogenic sounds dominate the spectrogram, some of which may share similar acoustic patterns with stronger winds (e.g. distant exhaust sounds), or because other weather cues may falsely hint at strong winds (e.g. heavy rain). On the other hand, stronger wind is typically easier to recognise as it presents with more acoustic cues such as rustling of

(a) Precipitation rate performance per model across intervals.

(b) Average wind speed performance per model across intervals.

Fig. 4: Mean absolute error and standard deviation for the precipitation rate and average wind speed tasks across 5 equally sized bins.

leaves or a distinctive broadband turbulent airflow (“whoosh”) sound.

6. CONCLUSION

Our results highlight distinct strengths and weaknesses of each pre-training strategy and model architecture across downstream tasks. On the one hand, masked reconstruction generally led to better performance in bird detection, likely due to its focus on reconstructing structured spectral content, which encourages the model to capture high-level auditory features such as harmonics and time-frequency patterns. Across models of the same architecture, the MAE loss generally leads to better performance than the MSE loss, with the exception of *bimamba-mae* versus *bimamba-mse* on the temporal prediction task. We attribute this to the fact that MAE is more robust to outliers as it is not dominated by high-energy pixels, pushing the models to learn better reconstructions throughout the entire spectra, which translates to finer feature extraction.

On the other hand, contrastive learning yielded comparable results in the bird detection task, while producing superior results in the temporal and weather prediction tasks. These findings suggest that stereo contrastive learning encourages the extraction of low-level acoustic cues that can carry information about acoustic patterns throughout the day and correlate with weather changes. This effect was most prominent in the Transformer-based models, where contrastive pre-training produced diverse and well-structured embeddings, leading to the best overall performance in regression tasks. In comparison, SSM-based models tended to produce more collapsed representations and were less stable and performative during fine-tuning, particularly under contrastive learning. Despite this, SSMs may still offer benefits for modelling long-range dependencies in future work involving longer input sequences.

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Deployment of AI-based Sound Analysis Algorithms in Real-time Acoustic Sensors: Challenges and a Use Case

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Abstract—Real-time acoustic sensing involves significant challenges in capturing, processing, and transmitting audio. Integrating AI models on resource-constrained devices further complicates development. This paper presents an end-to-end solution addressing these challenges: SENS, the Smart Environmental Noise System, is a low-cost sensor designed for real-time acoustic monitoring. Built on a *Raspberry Pi* platform, SENS captures sound continuously and processes it locally using custom-developed software based on small and efficient artificial intelligence algorithms. With a current focus on urban environments, SENS calculates acoustic parameters, including sound pressure level (SPL), and makes predictions of the perceptual sound attributes of *pleasantness* and *eventfulness* (ISO 12913), along with detecting the presence of specific sound sources such as vehicles, birds, and human activity. To safeguard privacy, all processing occurs directly on the device in real-time ensuring that no audio recordings are permanently stored or transferred. Additionally, the system transmits the analysis results through the wireless network to a remote server. Demonstrating its practical applicability, a network of five SENS devices has been deployed in an urban area for over three months, validating SENS as a powerful tool for analyzing and understanding soundscapes, recognizing patterns, and detecting acoustic events. The proposed flexible and reproducible technology allows reconfiguration for different applications and represents an innovative step in real-time and AI-based noise monitoring.

Index Terms—Environmental noise monitoring, machine learning, Internet of Things (IoT), urban soundscapes, smart city

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound monitoring has traditionally relied on high-precision instruments such as sonometers, but these are limited by their high cost, lack of remote communication capabilities (requiring manual deployment and retrieval), and low spatial or temporal resolution. The growing adoption of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies has dramatically transformed this paradigm. Recent developments in low-power embedded systems and wireless communication have enabled distributed sensing via low-cost acoustic sensor networks. Examples like AudioMoth [1] have made long-term acoustic data collection feasible, but they often still rely on offline analysis.

The parallel emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) across numerous fields opens new opportunities for real-time and autonomous sound analysis. Approaches like Bonet-Solà et al. [2] integrate noise level data from public wireless sensor networks with short audio clips recorded on smartphones to estimate subjective acoustic comfort. However, their system relies on centralized processing and offline AI models. Similarly, the CENSE network [3], [4], uses MEMS-based sensors to transmit low-resolution spectral data, ensuring privacy while relying on centralized servers for analysis. Another example of this approach is the LIFEWARD project [5] for neonatal ICUs, which computes third-octave spectrograms on the edge to avoid storing intelligible audio, with cloud-based AI completing the analysis. In contrast, other solutions involve AI-powered sensors that can perform on-device sound event detection, noise classification, or perceptual indexing. An example of this is a system deployed around the VELTINS Arena in Germany [6], which runs lightweight convolutional neural networks (CNNs) on *Raspberry Pi* devices to classify sound

events locally, reducing both data transmission and privacy risks. This shift enables real-time, autonomous, and privacy-preserving insights but introduces challenges related to computational efficiency.

In this work, we present a methodology for deploying AI-based sound analysis algorithms in real-time acoustic sensors through a use case: SENS (Smart Environmental Noise System), a low-cost acoustic sensor system designed to run lightweight AI models locally for continuous sound analysis. Built on *Raspberry Pi*, and with a current focus on urban environments, it estimates both physical (e.g., sound pressure level) and perceptual attributes (e.g., *pleasantness*, *eventfulness*), as well as the sound sources present in the soundscape, while preserving privacy by avoiding permanent storage or transmission of audio. Results are transmitted through the network to a remote server, and the system is modular to support flexible model updates towards other applications. SENS technology is validated through a real-world urban deployment, demonstrating its potential for scalable, real-time acoustic monitoring.

2. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The fully integrated proposed technology involves both hardware and software components. However, the software does not require dedicated hardware and, depending on the specific application, can run on a standard laptop or any device with an audio input. Additionally, if transmitting data to a remote server is unnecessary, the modular design of the software allows it to operate entirely offline.

Each SENS sensor constitutes a low-cost solution built around a single *Raspberry Pi*. The device captures sound through a connected microphone and transmits results via a mobile network hat with a SIM card. Sensors can be accessed remotely through a virtual private network (VPN), allowing over-the-air software updates and problem resolution. Besides, a hardware *watchdog* allows for autonomous system reboots if certain conditions are not met (e.g., if there are connectivity issues). For the use case presented in this paper (see Section 6), the sensors were connected to a continuous power supply allowing uninterrupted operation, though solutions that make use of batteries were also developed. The Github repository of the project¹ contains guidelines for building custom SENS hardware devices.

The software is developed end-to-end with a modular design that allows flexibility: three independent but related processes run in parallel — sound capture, processing, and transmission of results to a remote server. The code is implemented in Python and is available in the *sens-sensor* GitHub repository¹. The modular software structure in each SENS device is further explained in the following sections.

3. AUDIO ACQUISITION

The sound capture process is straightforward. Audio is continuously recorded and, when the audio buffer reaches a defined duration (3 seconds in the SENS implementation), it is saved as a *pickle* file in a

¹<https://github.com/MTG/sens-sensor>

specified folder, with a filename that includes the date and time for reference. The equivalent continuous sound levels, L_{eq} and L_{Aeq} , are computed for each segment and saved in a file with the same naming convention in the same directory. While incoming audio frames are being saved to disk, a dedicated thread continuously monitors the saved audio files and deletes those older than a defined retention period (30 seconds in SENS). This approach improves data privacy by ensuring that the sensor does not permanently store audio data, while also improving the device’s storage efficiency. Microphone calibration is essential, as it directly affects the calculation of L_{eq} and L_{Aeq} , and, as shown in an earlier study [7], it can influence model accuracy.

4. AUDIO PROCESSING

The processing module is a crucial part of the acoustic monitoring solution, as its development requires addressing several key challenges. To safeguard data privacy, all audio processing is performed locally and no audio is permanently stored or transmitted. Running machine learning models in real-time on a low-cost device with limited computational resources demands the development of lightweight models. Additionally, to achieve adaptability to different monitoring use cases, independent and separate models are trained for each task, resulting in a flexible modular architecture. The following subsections detail the research and training of the lightweight models, followed by their implementation within the software architecture.

4.1. Model training

The use case for which SENS has been developed is focused on the monitoring of urban spaces. Therefore, we developed sound analysis algorithms that predict perceptual soundscape attributes, *pleasantness* and *eventfulness*; and estimate the saliency of common sound sources present in the acoustic environment: *birds*, *construction works*, *dogs*, *human activity*, *sirens*, *music* and *vehicles*. For this purpose, we used existing datasets with open licenses. The ARAUS dataset [8] is used for training *pleasantness* and *eventfulness* models. It consists of 30s-length augmented, but realistic, soundscape audios, each labeled with values of *pleasantness*[-1, 1] and *eventfulness*[-1, 1], obtained following the soundscape study methodology suggested in ISO-12913 [9]–[11]. For the estimation of sound sources, we used several publicly available datasets. The Urban Sound Monitoring (USM) dataset [12] was used for *birds*, *construction works*, *dogs*, *human activity*, *sirens*, and *music*. This dataset consists of 5-second polyphonic stereo soundscapes composed of sounds from the FSD50k dataset [13]. Before training, we adapted the dataset by removing irrelevant sound sources, such as *gunshot*, and mapping more specific classes to general ones—for example, *cheering*, *scream*, and *speech* were all mapped to *human*. For each sound source, we built an independent model using a one-vs-all classification approach, allowing the sensor to be customized for different applications.

The approach to build the *vehicles* sound source model involved the careful combination of two datasets. A set of audios from the IDMT Traffic dataset [14] was selected, each consisting of 2-second long stereo audio recordings of vehicle sounds (*bus*, *car*, *motorcycle*, and *truck*). The balanced selection of IDMT audios was combined as an additional sound class within the UrbanSound8k (US8k) dataset [15]. This dataset originally includes sound excerpts ($\leq 4s$) of urban sounds from 10 classes, including noisy sounds like *air conditioner*, *drilling* and *engine idling*, that were cut to 2 seconds long. Again, the vehicles model is trained following a one-vs-all approach.

Despite the various datasets used for each parameter, the remaining training process was consistent across all. The algorithms take as input sound representations generated using Laion-AI’s CLAP (Contrastive

Fig. 1: When SENS boots up, all machine learning models (CLAP and individual, both perceptual and source detection, models) load before starting normal operation. The graph shows the device’s memory usage for different configurations with original CLAP or with simplified CLAP model (which only includes the audio encoder), and the use, or not, of PCA for reducing embeddings’ dimensionality.

Language-Audio Pretraining) *630k-fusion-best* model [16]. Previous research has demonstrated that this representation performs well in similar classification tasks [7], [17]. The CLAP model produces a 512-dimensional embedding vector, denoted as:

$$E = \{E_0, E_1, \dots, E_{511}\}, \quad E \in \mathbb{R}^{512} \quad (1)$$

Due to the SENS device’s limited computational capability, using the original CLAP model along with its raw embeddings caused the memory load to reach its limit, frequently resulting in system freezes. CLAP models function by learning a joint embedding space for both audio and textual descriptions. The original LAION-AI’s CLAP model consists of two branches: one for converting text to an embedding space and another for converting audio into the same embedding space. To optimize our use case, since bi-directional matching was not required, we removed the text encoder. By doing so, we significantly reduced the model’s memory consumption, making it more feasible for real-time processing on the Raspberry Pi without compromising accuracy.

To further optimize memory usage, we used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce the dimensionality of the embedding space. A PCA transformation was derived from an analysis of over 25,000 audio samples from the ARAUS dataset. The results indicated that 50 principal components were sufficient to explain 95.46% of the data variability, with a negligible effect on the prediction accuracy. The reduced embedding vector is given by:

$$E' = \{E'_0, E'_1, \dots, E'_{49}\}, \quad E' \in \mathbb{R}^{50} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1 illustrates the sensor’s boot-up under four different configurations, reflecting the impact that cleaning the CLAP model and applying PCA have on the boot-up time and memory load.

Using our reduced embedding space, a variety of simple classifiers were evaluated for the different properties that SENS estimates, with final selections including Random Forest Regressor, Linear Support Vector Classification, and Logistic Regression with LBFSGS optimization. *Pleasantness* and *eventfulness* were treated as regression problems, with outputs ranging [-1,1] where -1 corresponds to unpleasant and uneventful, and 1 represents pleasant and eventful, respectively. On the other hand, the sound sources approach followed a one-vs-all classification. Their output ranges within [0,1] representing the model’s estimated likelihood that the input belongs to the positive class. The resulting models achieve Mean Absolute Errors (MAE) of

Table 1: Summary of datasets and regressors/classifiers used for training models to predict various parameters, with corresponding validation metrics. Algorithm acronyms: Random Forest Regressor (RFR), Support Vector Classification (SVC), Logistic Regression (LR).

Parameter	Dataset	Algorithm	Metrics (val)
Pleasantness	ARAUS	RFR	0.22 MAE
Eventfulness			0.20 MAE
Birds	USM	Linear SVC	97% precision
Construction			81% precision
Dogs			92% precision
Human			83% precision
Sirens			88% precision
Music			80% precision
Vehicles	IDMT-Traffic, US8k	Linear SVC	100% precision

0.22 and 0.20 on the validation sets for *pleasantness* and *eventfulness*, respectively, and the sound sources classification models achieve precision scores (i.e., the proportion of correctly classified positive samples) that exceed 80% across all categories on the validation set (Table 1). The code used for training the models is available in the project’s Github repository.

4.2. Model deployment

The implementation of the trained AI models is relatively straightforward. A dedicated thread continuously monitors the folder where audio files are saved by the capturing module, waiting for new incoming data. As soon as a new file appears, the audio data is read to generate a reduced embedding vector E' . This is passed to the set of AI models, each of which outputs a prediction value. Due to the fact that *pleasantness* and *eventfulness* constitute integrated perceptions of the soundscape rather than instantaneous measurements, the processing module also aggregates the 10 most recent audio frames (corresponding to 30 seconds of audio data in the SENS use case). Thus, another reduced embedding vector is generated and passed to the *pleasantness* and *eventfulness* models, obtaining predictions of these parameters over a longer period. Finally, integrating the previously saved sound levels, L_{eq} and L_{Aeq} , the module generates an output dictionary with all the compiled results. This is stored in a JSON file within a designated folder.

5. DATA TRANSMISSION

For data transmission, each SENS device in the use case network operates remotely and sends the analysis results to a remote server for storage and display on a web platform. This requires appropriate hardware and poses challenges, particularly in terms of internet data consumption. While HTTPS is widely used because it ensures secure data transfer, it can add significant overhead due to large headers (5–10KB). For example, each JSON file generated by the processing module for a 3-second audio chunk is about 650 bytes. Sending each result individually at a rate of 20 messages per minute would result in over 8GB of monthly data usage per sensor. To mitigate this, multiple JSON files are batched together into a single HTTPS request, significantly reducing data consumption to 2-3GB per month.

The data transmission module in the proposed solution consists of a script which continuously monitors the folder where analysis results are stored and sends them to the remote server once a number of files are accumulated (10 in our implementation). Their contents are combined into a single payload and transmitted to a remote server via the mobile network. If the network connection is unavailable, audio

acquisition and processing continue locally, and transmission resumes automatically once the connection is restored. Upon successful receipt, the transmitted JSON files are deleted locally. The custom server stores all incoming data in a database and offers a visualization tool that enables users to monitor active sensors, check real-time status metrics like memory and CPU usage, and visualize processed data with interactive graphs. A detailed description of this server framework is beyond the scope of this paper.

6. REAL-WORLD DEPLOYMENT

A network of five SENS devices has been deployed in the real-world as part of *Smart Iruña Lab* [18], a smart cities program carried out in the city of Pamplona/Iruña. With over three months of deployment, SENS technology has proven to be a reliable tool for noise monitoring.

Fig. 2: SENS device deployed in the city of Pamplona/Iruña as part of the *Smart Iruña Lab* program.

In order to extract meaningful information from the raw monitored data, it is necessary to make it interpretable and practically useful by applying methodological choices (such as setting thresholds based on empirical testing to define when a sound source is considered active) and to aggregate data by statistical mean, the percentage of time above a threshold or the number of detected events. For example, Figure 3 presents an example of SENS monitoring results: the aggregated data by hour for the week of May 12-18 for one of the monitored sites in Pamplona/Iruña. In these plots, the 360 degrees represent the 24 hours of the day, while each concentric circle corresponds to a day of the week — with Monday at the center and Sunday on the outermost ring. The selected location is a residential neighborhood very close to the city center, known for its vibrant street life and frequent visits from young people due to nearby nightclubs. It is generally perceived as quite noisy because of constant traffic throughout the week.

Subplot (a) shows the L_{Aeq} . This confirms the high noise levels in the area, with L_{den} values ranging from 68 to 70 dB every day. To better understand the soundscape, it is useful to examine the perceptual attributes alongside the detected sound sources. However, first, it should be noted that due to the criteria of the city council, any activity at night (from 23:00 to 07:00) is inversely interpreted for *pleasantness*: the values for *pleasantness* during these hours are adjusted to reflect greater unpleasantness when activity is high, using the inverse of the *eventfulness* values. Looking at graph (b), we see that the day and evening periods tend to be neither distinctly pleasant nor unpleasant, likely because of the constant presence of traffic, as illustrated in graph (d). Nights in the second half of the week appear more unpleasant, which corresponds with higher activity levels (graph (c)) during the early morning hours from Thursday to Sunday. This pattern is explained by graph (e), which shows an increase in human presence at the same periods, indicating nightlife activity associated with the surrounding clubs and bars. Another notable aspect is the weekend activity peaks around 12:00–15:00 and 17:00–20:00. These high levels are also linked to human presence, suggesting that the area is a popular gathering spot during these times. The low detection

Fig. 3: Circular graphs of hourly data from May 12–18 for one site monitored in Pamplona/Iruña.

rates for birds (perceived 20–30% of the time) indicate that the area is highly urbanised, offering limited refuge for wildlife.

Altogether, this data illustrates how SENS enables us to understand the acoustic environment without needing to be physically present. By combining continuous measurement and intelligent data aggregation, we gain valuable insights into daily and weekly sound patterns. If noise issues arise, these insights provide robust evidence to identify the most effective measures to improve the urban soundscape.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The emergence of AI opens new opportunities for real-time sound analysis. The generally high cost of noise monitoring devices on-the-market raises the need to develop solutions based on small low-cost devices. Nevertheless, deploying AI-based sound analysis algorithms on real-time acoustic sensors presents numerous challenges, including the computational constraints linked with the need to protect data privacy. This paper has introduced SENS as a practical use case that addresses these difficulties through a low-cost, flexible, and privacy-preserving solution. By performing all audio processing locally on the device, SENS reduces the risk of compromising personal privacy. To achieve this, significant effort was made to reduce the computational load of the trained models through careful pruning and the use of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for input dimensionality reduction. Further, the general software architecture is modular, with separate components for audio capture, signal processing, and transmission of analysis results to a remote server when required. Moreover, the methodology proposes the development of independent models for each acoustic parameter of interest, enhancing the system’s

adaptability and scalability. Internet data consumption is further optimized through batching and packaging multiple analysis results before transmission. To demonstrate its real-world viability, a network of SENS devices has been deployed in an urban environment. This long-term deployment has shown that the system is robust, reliable, and capable of generating meaningful insights into the acoustic environment.

Future work will focus on further optimizing and expanding the methodology by exploring the minimum viable sampling frequency needed for accurate predictions to help reduce processing load even further or using more lightweight protocols like MQTT for data transmission. Additionally, the modular design of SENS makes it well-suited for other applications beyond urban noise monitoring. Future applications could include traffic monitoring (e.g., counting vehicles or distinguishing between light and heavy traffic), public safety (e.g., detecting distress calls on the streets), or any other scenario where sound can serve as a valuable real-time input of information.

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Bioacoustics on Tiny Hardware at the BioDCASE 2025 Challenge

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Abstract—The BioDCASE initiative aims to encourage the invention of methods for detection and classification of acoustic scenes and events (DCASE) within the domain of bioacoustics. We have contributed to the first edition of the BioDCASE challenge by means of a task named “bioacoustics on tiny hardware”. The motivation for this task resides in the growing need for operating bioacoustic event detection algorithms on low-power autonomous recording units (ARU’s). Participants were tasked with developing a detector of bird vocalizations from the yellowhammer (*Emberiza citrinella*), given two hours of audio as a training set. The detector had to run within the resource constraints of an ESP32-S3 microcontroller unit. By evaluating the submitted models on a withheld dataset, we conducted an independent benchmark that assessed both classification performance and resource efficiency through multiple metrics: average precision, inference time, and memory usage. Our reported results confirm that recent advances in “tiny machine learning” (TinyML) have transformative potential for computational bioacoustics. For more information, please visit: <https://biodcase.github.io/challenge2025/task3>

Index Terms—Acoustic event detection, autonomous recording units, bioacoustics, edge computing, passive acoustic monitoring.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bioacoustics, understood as the science of sonic interaction in and between animals, requires sensors for data collection [1]. For animal behavior research [2] or biodiversity surveys [3], these sensors are typically deployed onto remote locations, off the electrical grid. As of today, most commercially available sensors for birds and land mammals are battery-powered, with a battery life of 200–500 hours and a cost of \$100–\$700 [4]. They record digital audio, either continuously or according to an intermittent schedule, and store it onto an SD card. Although they are often referred to as “autonomous recording units” (ARU), they are not fully autonomous: indeed, frequent round trip from the lab to the deployment site are necessary, in order to replace batteries, transfer the recorded data, and reset the SD card.

Previous publications have alerted on the lack of autonomy of current-generation ARU’s and its negative consequences [5]–[7]:

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- 1) An insufficient uptime or ill-suited schedule may cause the ARU to misportray these dynamics of vocal activity, eventually reducing its usefulness for statistical hypothesis testing [8].
- 2) The cost of battery replacement and the weight of hardware is a serious challenge for practitioners [9], [10].
- 3) Although they do not require direct contact or manipulation of the animals, ARU’s may still be considered invasive if its maintenance raises the level of anthropogenic pressure; that is, the stress induced by the presence of humans [11].
- 4) The same data which are collected for research may be used for surveillance; an effect known as surveillance creep [12]. Some terrestrial bioacoustic datasets contain voices from people who are unaware of being recorded [13]. In the age of automated audio content analysis, the surveillance creep of acoustic sensors is not only a risk but a documented reality [14].
- 5) As technological advancements accelerate and costs decrease, the ecological impact of production and the growing issue of electronic waste (e-waste) have emerged as critical sustainability challenges [15]. For lack of a better end-of-life management [16], it would be prudent to strive for a lower dependency on batteries, or even switch to batteryless hardware [17].

Facing the drawbacks of current-generation ARU’s, we propose to explore an alternative design: on-device sound event detection (SED). The key idea is to develop an algorithm which is able to analyze the audio stream in real-time and record sound event selectively. In the context of wireless acoustic sensor networks, this is known as edge computing as opposed to cloud computing. The main argument in favor of edge computing on ARU’s is that the bioacoustic events of interest are typically few, while storing audio permanently is costly in terms of energy. If SED can be made efficient enough, the energy savings of selective storage can cover and outweigh the energy expenditure of edge computing [18]. Beyond the net gain in uptime, this simple idea has the potential to make the next generation of ARU’s cheaper to maintain, less invasive, more privacy-preserving, and more durable.

Machine learning algorithms allow to automate various bioacoustics tasks, including call detection or species classification. Previous works demonstrate the feasibility of running these algorithms on “tiny hardware” such as microcontroller units (MCU’s). For example, [19] have trained a MFCC-based classifier for species-specific call detection on a low-power MCU, with a memory usage of the order of

Fig. 1: Spectrogram representations of yellowhammer (*Emberiza citrinella*) song. Brighter colors denote relatively larger time–frequency magnitudes after normalization of visual contrast. Rows illustrate inter-individual variation while columns illustrate the effect of distance. See Section 2 for details.

one kilobyte. Another example is [20], who have shown the feasibility of SED on the AudioMoth, a widespread and open-source ARU [21]: the proposed algorithms rely on MFCC and Goertzel filtering and are applied to cicadas and gunshots.

Recent work at the intersection of “tiny machine learning” (TinyML) and bioacoustics has proposed to embed deep neural networks, particularly convolutional networks (convnets), onto low-cost hardware. For example, [22] have trained a convnet to recognize 50 classes of environmental sounds on a Sony Spresense MCU.

2. DATASET

The development set for task 3 of BioDCASE 2025 “Bioacoustics for Tiny Hardware” consists of 2 hours and 37 mins worth of audio recordings. See Table 1 for a breakdown.

2.1. Data collection

Yellowhammers are widespread across Eurasia and their songs have attracted the attention of naturalists and scientists for over one and a half centuries (e.g. [23]). They have long been a popular model species, especially for studying dialects in birdsong [24]. They are also an indicator of healthy farmland showing rapid population declines around Europe (e.g., [25]), and their individually specific songs might offer detail noninvasive insights into fast population changes. The yellowhammer songs used for BioDCASE 2025 were initially recorded as a part of sound transmission experiments that investigated how far it is still possible to identify Yellowhammer individuals by their songs. To collect the songs, AudioMoth recorders were placed near the bird’s favorite singing posts less than 5 m from the singing birds. The best quality songs were selected and put into one track. The track contained in total 209 songs from 10 individuals, including in total 21 different song types (2–3 song types per male), with c.a. 10 repetitions of each song type.

The track was then played back and re-recorded at 7 different distances ranging from 6.5 to 200 m (see Figure 1 for representative

examples of songs at different distances). Taking into account the original recording distance ($< 5\text{m}$), the songs in the closest distance category simulate birds being anything between 6.5m to 11m far away. Note that the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is quite low in the last two distance categories, and songs that were not visible on the spectrogram were not included in the dataset, which means that these distance categories may have fewer than 209 samples. The playback was carried out in two different environments (forest and grassland). Altogether, each song is repeated up to 15 times in the dataset (original distance + 7x forest + 7x grassland). These re-recorded songs were annotated and split into separate files and used in the challenge as positive files. In addition, the original recordings of live Yellowhammers were screened, annotated and split to obtain negative files of similar duration. These included songs from other known species or background noise only.

2.2. Data curation

All audio recordings were clipped to 2 seconds and resampled at 16kHz. The dataset was divided into training and validation sets. Yellowhammer recordings were split by individual: 6 for training, 2 for validation, and 2 held out for evaluation. Negative samples were randomly split.

3. CHALLENGE

3.1. Rules

The challenge tasked participants with developing a Yellowhammer bird vocalization detection system for the ESP32-S3-Korvo-2 microcontroller, using the training and validation sets from the Yellowhammer dataset (Section 2), and our baseline framework (Section 3.3). Submissions had to be deployable on the target hardware and capable of real-time audio processing. The submitted models would then be evaluated by organizers on the (hidden) evaluation set using the benchmarking facilities of the baseline framework, on a range of metrics to do with model classification performance as well as its resource efficiency, described in the next section. Rankings

Dataset Component	Recordings	Duration
Training Set		
Total	3,562	1h 58min
Yellowhammer	1,321	44min
Negatives (known species)	956	31min
Negatives (background noise)	1,285	42min
Validation Set		
Total	1,156	37min
Yellowhammer	408	13min
Negatives (known species)	319	10min
Negatives (background noise)	429	14min
Evaluation Set		
Total	1,140	37min
Yellowhammer	394	13min
Negatives (known species)	317	10min
Negatives (background noise)	427	14min

Table 1: Detailed statistics of the BioDCASE 2025 Task 3 dataset. All recordings have 2 second length at 16KHz.

were provided separately for each evaluation metric, encouraging diverse approaches to the performance-efficiency tradeoff inherent in embedded machine learning applications.

3.2. Metrics

Reflecting the real-world tradeoffs of model performance vs computation space and time constraints in embedded devices, the benchmarks measured the following metrics:

- **Average Precision:** A metric that summarizes the precision-recall curve by computing the weighted mean of precisions at each threshold, with the increase in recall from the previous threshold used as the weight. This provides a comprehensive measure of the model’s detection accuracy across all confidence levels and object classes.
- **Preprocessing time (ms):** The total execution time of audio preprocessing and feature extraction.
- **Model time (ms):** The total execution time of model inference on the extracted features.
- **Model size (bytes):** The storage footprint of the model weights and architecture.
- **Peak RAM usage (bytes):** The maximum amount of RAM consumed during inference.

3.3. Baseline

To lower the entry barrier and establish fair performance benchmarks, we provided a comprehensive baseline framework through the BioDCASE-Tiny 2025 repository [31]. This framework implements an end-to-end pipeline for developing bird species recognition models in Python and deploying them for benchmarking on an ESP32-S3-Korvo-2 development board. The baseline framework serves as both a starting point for participants unfamiliar with embedded ML development and a reference implementation that demonstrates the expected integration between model development on the host and the deployment and execution of the model on the embedded device.

The system consists of five stages integrated into an automated pipeline (see Figure 2). First, in the data preprocessing stage, the pipeline handles the ingestion and preparation of raw audio files from the Yellowhammer dataset. Second, a feature extraction step transforms the preprocessed audio into log-mel spectrograms for model training, with configurable parameters that participants could adjust to optimize their approaches.

These features were implemented both on the host system and the embedded target in a numerically equivalent manner, ensuring that

Fig. 2: Flowchart of the baseline development and deployment pipeline for yellowhammer detection, from raw audio input and log-mel spectrogram extraction to model training, deployment, and benchmarking on a constrained embedded device (ESP32).

the deployed model receives identical inputs to those used during training. Third, at the model training stage, participants could define custom architectures as well as a custom training loop if needed. Fourth, at the deployment stage, the pipeline automatically converts the model to TensorFlow Lite format, generates optimized C++ code for the ESP32-S3 platform, and handles firmware compilation and flashing using a Docker-based ESP-IDF tool chain. Finally, at the fifth stage, a benchmarking firmware runs on the embedded target to measure feature extraction time, model inference time, and memory usage, enabling participants to optimize their solutions against the competition’s evaluation criteria.

A baseline model was also included as a reference for participants. The model is a lightweight CNN starting with a mobile-net style convolutional and depth-wise convolutional block, followed by a global max pooling layer, dropout and finally a dense layer with softmax activation. The model achieves high average precision on the evaluation data. However, this comes at a rather high cost in terms of model size, RAM usage, and execution time.

Participants in the BioDCASE-Tiny 2025 challenge employed a range of approaches to address the challenge’s constraints, and explore different trade-offs to improve on the baseline.

3.4. Neural network architectures

The submitted models demonstrated significant variation in architectural complexity and design philosophy. Three participants built upon MobileNet-inspired architectures for computational efficiency. [26] implemented a slimmed MobileNet V2 with three depthwise separable convolution blocks, while [29] and [30] employed a further stripped-down MobileNet-style CNN.

In contrast, [27] and [28] pursued extreme minimalism through very shallow CNN architectures, with [28] further venturing into SVMs.

Model	Avg. Precision (%)	Model size (bytes)	Peak RAM usage (bytes)	Preprocessing time (ms)	Model time (ms)	Total execution time (ms)
Baseline	99.68	14,564	58,360	191.84	302.827	494,667
[26] Enriched	97.98	16,600	26,844	176.11	24.417	200.527
[26] Non-enriched	94.49	16,600	26,844	176.22	24.418	200.638
[27]	74.47	7,020	6,744	1.62	16.449	18.067
[28] Mel-based	97.31	4,192	18,364	34.28	7.387	41.667
[28] Flux-based	96.52	1,848	780	16.54	0.185	16.725
[29]	98.57	7,776	20,924	73.42	15.164	88.58
[30] SlimCNN-student	73.68	12,920	30,328	64.84	112.779	177.622

Table 2: Model performance comparison. In the case of multiple submissions from a participant or team, a model identifier is also reported in the Model column. The table reports a range of performance vs resource efficiency tradeoffs explored by the participants, reflecting the range of requirements and constraints in the usage of TinyML for autonomous recording units.

Finally, [32] explored convolutional-recurrent hybrid architectures, demonstrating the potential of temporal modeling for bioacoustic tasks. However, due to the limited amount of operations supported by TensorFlow Lite, their model could not be benchmarked on the embedded target.

3.5. Data augmentation

Several participants recognized the importance of data augmentation for improving model robustness, particularly for low signal-to-noise ratio conditions. [26] compared models trained with and without augmentation, applying pitch shifting (± 2 semitones) and white noise addition. [32] implemented a sophisticated dynamic augmentation strategy that adjusted intensity based on SNR estimates, using SpecMixup and Gaussian noise selectively on high-SNR samples to create realistic training scenarios.

3.6. Feature engineering and preprocessing

Participants employed varied feature extraction strategies, with most utilizing log-mel spectrograms but differing significantly in their parameter choices. The majority processed audio to extract mel spectrograms with filter counts ranging from 16 to 64, with window sizes varying from 512 to 2048 samples. Sampling rates and frequency ranges were carefully selected based on domain knowledge, with e.g. [29] focusing on the 3–8 kHz range based on ornithological literature, while [28] resampled the recordings at 14 kHz and targeted specific frequency bands for different models. Notably, [28] also explored alternative features, achieving strong results with spectral flux statistics, while drastically reducing processing time as well as memory footprint.

3.7. Model compression and optimization

Participants employed various strategies to meet the heavy resource constraints. While some focused on architectural simplification and careful hyperparameter selection, limiting compression to post-training model quantization, others implemented sophisticated compression pipelines. [30] demonstrates a comprehensive approach combining knowledge distillation, magnitude-based pruning, and quantization-aware training.

3.8. Computational performance and resource usage

The submitted models achieved a wide range of performance-efficiency tradeoffs: see Table 2. These results collectively demonstrate that effective yellowhammer detection can be achieved across a broad spectrum of computational budgets, with the optimal choice depending on specific deployment constraints and precision/recall requirements.

4. CONCLUSION

Bioacoustics researchers and practitioners have expressed a demand for accurate and energy-efficient algorithms which can operate “on the edge”, i.e., on autonomous recording units [18]. From the standpoint of DCASE, meeting this demand requires to rethink the deployment

of machine learning systems with hardware constraints in mind. As part of the first edition of the BioDCASE challenge and workshop, we have organized a task of SED on tiny hardware (ESP32-S3) for the yellowhammer (*Emberiza citrinella*). Certainly, edge computing does not erase all the harms of cloud computing: risks such as rebound effects [33] and human bycatch [34] remain present. Yet, we believe that bioacoustics on tiny hardware is worth exploring in future years. Indeed, as a collective, the participants of BioDCASE 2025 Task 3 have shown that a more ethically responsible practice of computational bioacoustics is technically within reach.

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Analysing Human-Generated Captions for Audio and Visual Scenes

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Abstract—This work investigates how humans describe audio and visual content by analysing single-sentence captions for each modality. While prior research has focused on improving captioning models and their evaluation, less attention has been paid to how linguistic features differ across modalities. We analyse the distribution of parts of speech and domain-specific vocabulary and examine how a structure-based method and neural network-based model classify captions as audio-based or image-based. The structure-based approach reveals how audio captions include verbs related to sound production (e.g., *heard*, *speaking*, *playing*), while image captions use verbs describing physical actions (e.g., *sitting*, *walking*, *holding*). We also study how the input captions influence neural network predictions using gradient-based attribution. Attribution scores from integrated gradients reveal that words like *growling*, *sounded*, *howling*, and *chirp* strongly support audio classification, while words like *grouped*, *cupcakes*, and *participates* are linked to image captions.

Index Terms—audio captioning, image captioning, classification, natural language processing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Audio and image captioning have become prominent tasks in multimodal AI, aiming to generate natural language descriptions from audio or visual signals. The task of automatic captioning consists of generating coherent and relevant textual descriptions from a media input, therefore the machine should be able to interpret and communicate perceptual information in a human-readable form. Examples of applications that can benefit from this capability are content retrieval [1], human-machine interaction [2] and automated media annotation [3]. In addition to direct applications, captioning data is also used in training multimodal language models. These models aim to understand and generate textual descriptions from different modalities, such as image [4], audio [5] and video [6].

While captioning systems aim to describe perceptual content, understanding how humans naturally perceive and describe their surroundings can provide valuable insights into the design and evaluation of such systems. Foundational work in visual perception by Gibson [7] and in auditory perception by Gaver [8] explores perception as a direct interaction with the environment. Gaver’s approach to auditory events was inspired by Gibson’s ecological theory of vision, and both emphasize the idea of the actionable properties of objects and events. However, the nature of these properties differs across modalities: visual perception focuses on spatial layout, motion, and surface characteristics, while auditory perception categorizes sounds based on the events and materials that produce them. These ecological perspectives have been used to better understand scene and event-based perception, and they help explain why captions may differ between audio and image modalities.

Understanding perceptual differences is essential, but equally important is how these perceptions are translated into language during the annotation process, which can vary significantly across datasets. Recent work has examined the impact of dataset characteristics on caption quality. For example, in [9] authors investigate differences across datasets from various modalities (audio, image, and video)

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with a particular emphasis on the data collection process. Their study highlights how the formulation of annotation instructions significantly influences the nature and quality of the collected captions. This is an important aspect to consider, as these captions are later used to train the models, which tend to reproduce the same linguistic patterns in their outputs. In [10] authors argue that when evaluation relies on standard captioning metrics such as BLEU [11], METEOR [12] or SPIDER [13], among others, models can achieve high scores simply by exploiting dataset patterns. They also compare the Part-Of-Speech (POS) patterns in machine generated and human-annotated captions, showing that human-annotated captions are more complex and diverse than the machine-generated ones. In [14], authors investigate how human and model-generated image captions vary semantically and expressively across languages. Their results show how captioning models could benefit from a multilingual dataset, to achieve more diverse and semantically richer descriptions. Although they focus on a single modality, their work highlights the difference in perception among different users and languages and how the model is affected by this differences.

Audio and image modalities represent different kinds of information, so the way people describe them also differs. Studying linguistic differences, such as sentence structure and vocabulary, is essential for understanding how each modality is expressed in language and for designing better captioning models. To the best of our knowledge, there are no existing studies that specifically examine the linguistic differences between audio and image captions. Understanding these differences is important because audio and image captions are used to train multimodal models, and each modality may require distinct linguistic structures to capture its unique characteristics.

In this paper, we present a detailed comparative analysis of caption content across audio and image captioning datasets. Rather than proposing a new model or metric, our goal is to understand the linguistic and structural characteristics of captions and see what makes a caption more likely to belong to one modality. By analysing vocabulary usage, POS distributions, and semantic patterns, we highlight both shared trends and modality-specific differences. Additionally, we apply interpretability methods to identify which words influence a neural network’s decision when classifying captions into belonging to one domain or the other. This study aims to deepen our understanding of how humans describe their surroundings in different modalities, and how these linguistic patterns influence the behavior and decision-making of models trained on such captions.

2. DATASETS

In this work, we have used a diverse set of benchmark datasets from both the image and audio captioning domains to support our comparative analysis of caption content. These datasets vary in size, domain, and linguistic characteristics, offering a broad foundation for studying caption structure, vocabulary, and semantics. From the image domain, we include three widely used datasets in image captioning: MS COCO [15], Flickr30k [16] and Conceptual Captions [17]; From the audio domain, we include four datasets that represent a

Table 1: Overview of the datasets analysed in this study.

Dataset	Description	Number of captions	Average caption length (in words)
CLOTHO	Mturk annotated, with curated stage, audios from FreeSound	29 614	11.3
AudioCaps	Mturk annotated, audios from Youtube	98 611	8.5
MACS	Volunteers annotators, three acoustic scenes	16 264	9.5
WavCaps	Formed by AudioSet SL, BBC sound effects, FreeSound, SoundBible metadata and tags, use LLM to generate captions	330 701	8.4
MS COCO	Mturk annotated, images from Flickr	593 968	10.5
Flickr30k	Crowdsourcing annotated, images from Flickr	158 439	12.3
Conceptual captions	Raw descriptions are from the Alt-text HTML, images from Google	2 361 004	10.2

Table 2: Part-of-speech (POS) tag distribution in the audio and image datasets, shown as normalized frequencies in parentheses. With examples of the top five most frequent words per POS tag, first from the audio domain, followed by the top five from the image domain.

POS tags	Top five words
Nouns	Audio (0.33): sounds, man, background, noise, wind Image (0.37): person, man, background, woman, people
Verbs	Audio (0.19): heard, speaking, making, playing, talking Image (0.10): sitting, standing, holding, looking, walking
Adjectives	Audio (0.05): human, other, small, male, loud Image (0.09): white, young, black, old, beautiful
Adverbs	Audio (0.02): then, by, nearby, loudly, repeatedly Image (0.02): next, just, together, very, outside
Adpositions	Audio (0.08): in, with, of, on, by Image (0.16): of, in, on, with, at
Pronouns	Audio (0.01): someone, something, there, it, their Image (0.03): his, it, her, that, I
Determinants	Audio (0.12) Image (0.15): a, the, an, this, some
Others	Audio (0.18) Image (0.07)

range of acoustic environments and captioning styles: CLOTHO [18], AudioCaps v2 [19], MACS [20] and WavCaps [21]. An overview of the datasets is presented in Table 1.

For the remainder of this paper, we refer to the three image captioning datasets collectively as the *image dataset*, and the four audio captioning datasets as the *audio dataset*. The linguistic analysis is conducted on these two aggregated datasets, and used for training the caption classification models. To evaluate the proposed methods we use AVCaps dataset [1], an audio-visual dataset that contains separate textual captions for the audio, visual, and audio-visual contents of video clips. This dataset allows for the independent analysis of audio and visual information, as well as the study of how video captions represent a combination of both modalities, which is often imbalanced. For evaluation, we use the training, validation and test splits of the dataset together. The analysis is conducted separately per caption type: audio (captions based only on the audio modality), visual (captions describing silent videos without audio), AV (captions describing both audio and visual content), and GPT_AV (AV captions rephrased using a large language model, providing a balanced representation of the visual and audio content). Please refer to [1] for more details on the dataset creation.

3. LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF CAPTIONS

This section presents a detailed linguistic analysis of the image and audio captioning datasets, which share a total of 17699 common words. Part-of-Speech (POS) tags are an important part of the analysis and evaluation process in captioning tasks, as they help assess the grammatical structure and linguistic quality of generated captions.

POS tagging helps to examine whether models produce syntactically coherent sentences and to what extent they capture the diversity of natural language. For instance, analysing the distribution of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs in generated captions can reveal whether a model tends to overuse object-centric descriptions (e.g., nouns) while neglecting actions or attributes (e.g., verbs and adjectives) [22], [23]. This kind of analysis is particularly useful in both image and audio captioning, where the goal is not only to identify content but also to describe it in a way that is informative and human-like.

Table 2 shows the distribution of POS tags in the audio and image datasets. The values are normalized frequencies, meaning they represent the proportion of each POS tag in the total number of words. The last column gives examples of the most frequent words for each POS tag. Nouns are the most common POS tag in both datasets, with slightly higher frequency in the image domain (0.37) than in audio (0.33). Verbs are more frequent in the audio dataset (0.19) compared to the image dataset (0.10), which reflects how humans typically describe generic audio using nouns, describing the sound sources and verbs, describing their action [24]. Adjectives appear more often in the image dataset (0.09) than in audio (0.05), likely because visual descriptions often rely on adjectives.

When we take a closer look at the top three POS tags, nouns, verbs, and adjectives, we can observe clear differences in vocabulary between the audio and image domains. In the audio domain, captions often include sound-related nouns such as sounds, noise, wind, birds, and music. In contrast, image captions tend to use nouns that refer to people, objects, or places, such as person, man, woman, people, player, view, city, and street. A similar pattern appears with verbs. Audio captions frequently include verbs related to sound production, such as heard, speaking, making, playing, talking, recorded, and singing. On the other hand, image captions often use verbs that describe physical positions or actions, like sitting, standing, holding, looking, walking, and wearing. Finally, adjectives also reflect these domain-specific differences. In the audio domain, adjectives such as male, loud, female, distant, present, high, and low are commonly used to describe sound characteristics. In contrast, image captions more often include adjectives related to visual appearance, such as white, black, red, young, old, and beautiful. Adverbs and adpositions show similar patterns in both datasets, although adpositions are more frequent in the image domain (0.16 vs. 0.08). Pronouns and determiners are relatively low in both datasets, but determiners are more common than pronouns. The "Others" category is higher in the audio dataset (0.18), which include interjections, numerals, symbols or unclassified words.

4. STRUCTURE-BASED CAPTION CLASSIFICATION

To understand whether main semantic content of a caption can reveal its modality, we construct Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) triplets for both audio and image captions. The goal is to determine whether a caption can be classified as audio-based or image-based by analysing

its SVOs. An SVO triplet represents a basic syntactic structure in which a subject performs an action (verb) on an object, for example, “people-make-noise”. This approach is conceptually aligned with the use of scene graphs in visual understanding, as introduced in [25]. In their work, scene graphs are used to represent visual content through structured relationships between objects, typically in the form of subject-predicate-object triplets (e.g., “man-riding-horse”). Similarly, our use of SVO triplets captures the core semantic structure of a more general caption, not being modality-specific.

These triplets were extracted using the open-source Natural Language Processing library spaCy¹. Prior to extraction, we preprocessed the captions by removing punctuation and applying lemmatization to ensure consistency in the vocabulary. Additionally, we filtered out non-informative or malformed triplets such as “that-have-it,” “this-have-it,” “that-have-be,” “this-have-be,” and “it-be-there,” which did not contribute meaningful semantic content.

Table 3: Top 5 SVO triplets for audio and image modalities. The values in parentheses represent normalized frequency, calculated as the count of each triplet divided by the total number of triplets.

Audio triplets (freq)	Image triplets (freq)
Bird-make-call (0.0048)	Actor-attend-premiere (0.0010)
Man-speak-noise (0.0041)	Man-stand-next (0.0007)
Bird-chirp-background (0.0029)	Man-stand-front (0.0006)
Car-pass-by (0.0026)	Actor-arrive-premier (0.0005)
There-be-sound (0.0024)	Man-sit-bench (0.0005)

By analysing each caption from both the image and audio datasets, we extracted Subject-Verb-Object pairs/triplets and compiled domain-specific SVO lists, referred to as image-SVO and audio-SVO throughout the rest of the paper. Example: “a trolley train is approaching and it is ringing a bell”, extracted SVO: (‘trolley train’, ‘approach’) and (‘it’, ‘ring’, ‘bell’). Once all the SVOs are extracted from all the captions, the number of each triplet/pair is counted and normalized based on the total size of the audio/image dataset. Table 3 shows top 5 collected triplets extracted after analysing all the audio and image datasets.

Table 4: Structure-based caption classification into audio/image by caption type.

Caption type	Audio (%)	Image (%)
audio_captions	3690 (76.80%)	1115 (23.20%)
visual_captions	929 (16.85%)	4584 (83.15%)
AV_captions	1121 (20.07%)	4464 (79.93%)
GPT_AV_captions	2208 (41.97%)	3053 (58.03%)

We collected all the splits (train, validation, and test) from the AVCaps dataset and combined them into a single set for evaluation. Then, we separated the captions by caption type: audio, visual, AV (audio visual) and GPT_AV (rephrased using LLM). Classifying AVCaps dataset by modality (audio/image) based on their linguistic content allows us to explore which actions and entities are more typical of each modality.

Steps to classify a given caption as audio or image caption based on their grammatical structure.

- 1) Preprocess the caption: remove punctuation and apply lemmatization to standardize word forms.
- 2) Extract SVO structure: identify the Subject-Verb-Objects from the caption.
- 3) Compare with reference list: find in which list, audio-SVO or image-SVO, the extracted SVO triplets/pairs is.

¹https://spacy.io/models/en#en_core_web_trf

- 4) Determine the domain: classify the caption to the domain (audio or image) based on the audio-SVO and image-SVO counts. In case of the extracted SVO belonging to both list, the one with higher normalized frequency will be selected.

Table 4 shows the average classification results by caption type. Our structure-based classification method achieved high accuracy, correctly identifying 76.80% of audio captions and 83.15% of visual captions. On the AV_captions type, almost 80% are classified as image, similar to the visual captions case. These results align with the observations in [1] that AV_captions are visual-centric, while the GPT_AV_captions are more balanced.

Fig. 1: CNN model for sentence classification. The input is a rearranged to fit 1D convolution layers, each convolutional layers has 100 filters with sizes 3, 5 and 7. After ReLU activation and max pooling, the outputs are combined and sent to a fully connected layer with one output neuron for binary classification.

5. NEURAL NETWORK-BASED CAPTION CLASSIFICATION

In this section, we present a neural network-based classification system to compare against the structure-based classification method presented in Section 4. The model was trained to classify whether a caption is from the audio or image domain, based on its textual content. To accommodate for a large corpus and improve generalization, we used pre-trained word vectors from the wiki-news-300d-1M.vec model [26]. These embeddings provide rich semantic information learned from a large text corpus, which helps the model understand word meanings and relationships more effectively.

The model architecture was selected to be a simple convolutional neural network (CNN) model. The architecture is based on the model proposed by Kim [27], originally designed for sentiment analysis of text (e.g., classifying positive vs. negative reviews). The structure of our model is illustrated in Figure 1. For training, we split both the *image dataset* and *audio dataset* into training and validation sets, maintaining the same proportion for each. Since the datasets are imbalanced, having more image than audio captions, we applied a resampling strategy to balance the classes during training. Finally, input to the model has a dimensionality of [number of tokens, embedding dimensionality], where the embedding dimensionality is fixed at 300, matching the size of the pre-trained word vectors.

Table 5: Neural Network-based caption classification into audio/image by modality.

Caption type	Audio (%)	Image (%)
audio_captions	4386 (71.78%)	1724 (28.22%)
visual_captions	787 (10.36%)	6812 (89.64%)
AV_captions	1001 (12.92%)	6745 (87.08%)
GPT_AV_captions	1895 (30.65%)	4288 (69.35%)

Table 5 shows the average classification results by caption type. Our classification model achieved high accuracy, correctly identifying 71.78% of audio captions and 89.64% of visual captions.

When comparing the results with the structure-based classification, we observe that it assigns slightly more captions to the audio category than the neural network-based method. In contrast, the neural-network based classifier consistently labels a higher percentage of captions as visual across all caption types. This suggests that the neural-network based model is more confident, or biased, towards the visual modality. One possible explanation for this behavior is overfitting in the CNN model. Although we applied a resampling strategy to balance the training data, the overall dataset still contains significantly more visual captions than audio ones. This imbalance may have influenced the model to favor the visual class during prediction, especially in ambiguous cases.

6. MODEL INTERPRETABILITY

In the structure-based method, is possible to interpret the output because classification is based on SVO triplets. In contrast, the neural network-based classification behaves more like a black box, making it harder to understand why a sentence is classified as an audio or image caption. To address this, we use integrated gradients, introduced in [28], a method to understand which input features contribute most to the model’s prediction. It works by comparing the model’s output on the actual input to a baseline input (e.g. all zeros), which represents the absence of features. The method computes gradients of the model’s output with respect to the input. Integrated gradients satisfy two key axioms: Sensitivity, which ensures that features affecting the output receive non-zero attribution, and implementation invariance, which guarantees consistent attributions for functionally equivalent models. This makes it a theoretically sound and interpretable method for explaining deep learning predictions.

For our experiments we use Captum², an open source library for model interpretability built on PyTorch. To obtain word-level attribution scores, we apply the Integrated Gradients method and sum the attribution scores across all embedding dimensions for each word. This gives us a single attribution score per word, indicating how much that word contributed to the model’s final decision. The overall attribution score for a sentence is then the sum of its word-level attributions. In our case, illustrated in Figure 2, the model is trained to classify sentences into two modalities, class 0 corresponds to image captions; class 1 corresponds to audio captions.

The attribution scores help us understand how much each word pushed the model toward or away from predicting a specific class. A positive attribution score means the word contributed toward predicting class 1 (audio), while a negative score indicates a push toward class 0 (image). Table 6 shows the top ten words with highest and lowest attribution scores, with words like growling, sounded, howling, chirp, and chirping as strongly associated with the audio modality. In contrast, words with strong negative attribution scores include grouped, cupcakes, administers, powerful, and participates are more aligned with the image modality. If we look at the top 10 most frequent

²https://captum.ai/docs/extension/integrated_gradients

Legend: ■ Image ■ Neutral ■ Audio

True Label	Predicted Label	Attribution Score	Word Importance
audio_captions	0	-1.05	the friends are enjoying the party
audio_captions	1	0.26	the people were speaking together and enjoying it
visual_captions	0	-1.13	they are all eating their lunch
visual_captions	1	0.69	a lady is speaking to someone
audio_visual_captions	0	-1.14	a family is eagerly looking for a tea that a lady is making
audio_visual_captions	1	0.26	a baby is playing with the toy and shouting
GPT_AV_captions	0	-0.48	the dog and cat are playing while a man watches them
GPT_AV_captions	1	0.37	family members are talking happily and enjoying the party

Fig. 2: Visual representation of the word-level attribution in the model output prediction. The green and red color represents audio (class 1) and image (class 0) respectively, while the intensity indicates attribution strength. The first column is the true label, the second column is the predicted label and the third column is the attribution score.

Table 6: Top 10 words with the highest and lowest average attribution scores in the AVCaps dataset. Positive scores indicate stronger association with audio captions, while negative scores suggest stronger association with image captions.

Word	Average attribution	Word	Average attribution
growling	0.88	badge	-0.76
sounded	0.83	attracts	-0.76
howling	0.82	yogurt	-0.76
chirp	0.81	celebrity	-0.76
mumbling	0.77	purchased	-0.79
requests	0.75	participates	-0.80
murmurs	0.72	powerful	-0.81
conversed	0.71	administers	-0.83
meows	0.69	cupcakes	-0.85
hums	0.69	grouped	-0.89

words in the AVCaps dataset, we have words like “speaking” (0.64), “talking” (0.58), and “singing” (0.42) have high positive attribution scores, indicating that they strongly support the model’s prediction of the audio class. These words are semantically related to sound actions. In contrast, words such as “sitting” (-0.54), “man” (-0.24), and “child” (-0.19) have negative attribution scores, suggesting they are more indicative of the image class. These terms typically describe visual scenes or entities, which are more likely to appear in image captions. Interestingly, some high-frequency words like “playing” (0.09) and “baby” (-0.11) have attribution scores closer to zero, indicating a more neutral or ambiguous role in the classification task. This could be due to their presence in both audio and image contexts, making them less discriminative.

7. CONCLUSION

In this work we have studied the linguistic and structural differences between audio and image captions, highlighting how these differences and similarities affects the model outputs. The linguistic analysis revealed clear modality-specific patterns, with audio captions favoring sound-related vocabulary and image captions focusing on visual elements such as people and scenes. Through the Subject-Verb-Object structures, we created a modality-specific references, which were then compared to an CNN classifier. While the CNN model performed well, it showed a consistent bias toward the visual modality, likely influenced by dataset imbalance. To further interpret model behavior, we applied integrated gradients, which confirmed that words strongly associated with sound (e.g., growling, chirping) positively contributed to audio predictions, while visually descriptive terms (e.g., grouped, cupcakes) supported image predictions. These findings emphasize the importance of understanding linguistic patterns in multimodal datasets, as they directly shape model outputs and can inform the design of more balanced and interpretable captioning systems.

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Universal Incremental Learning for Few-Shot Bird Sound Classification

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Abstract—Incremental learning aims to continually learn new input tasks while overcoming the forgetting of previously learned ones. Existing incremental learning methods for audio classification tasks assume that the incoming task either contains new classes from the same domain or the same classes from a new domain, referred to as class-incremental learning (CIL) and domain-incremental learning (DIL), respectively. In this work, we propose a universal incremental learning (UIL) method for few-shot bird sound classification, in which the incoming task contains new or a combination of new and previously seen bird classes from a new domain. Our method uses generalizable audio embeddings from a pre-trained model, which is trained on focal recordings, to develop an incremental learner that solves few-shot bird sound classification tasks from diverse soundscape datasets. These datasets are selected from BIRB (Benchmark for Information Retrieval in Bioacoustics), a large-scale bird sounds benchmark, and used to demonstrate the performance of the proposed method. Results show that our method adapts to the incoming tasks effectively with minimal forgetting of previously seen tasks.

Index Terms—Incremental learning, class-incremental learning, domain-incremental learning, audio embeddings, few-shot bird sound classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Incremental or continual learning for audio classification aims to acquire new knowledge from incoming audio data over time without significantly forgetting the previously acquired knowledge. In this work, our focus is on the incremental learning of bird sounds. Birds live in most environments, and their diverse species act as indicators of ecosystem health. Specifically, birds are sensitive to the environment, and investigation of bird sounds is highly useful for understanding the shifts in ecosystems and climate [1]. Deep learning models for bird sound classification have reached performance levels that allow their use as biodiversity monitoring systems [1]. In most cases, the annotated data for training these deep models is obtained from citizen science initiatives like *Xeno-Canto* (XC) [2] that includes over one million vocalizations from more than 10,000 bird species.

On the other hand, bird researchers usually collect their data from a specific soundscape using a noninvasive passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) method. The collected data is used locally to monitor species and perform different studies, such as determining the species’ behavioral changes. However, XC and PAM follow different data collection procedures. XC recordings are typically focal, which concentrate on the bird’s vocalization of interest. In contrast, PAM recordings are captured in natural soundscapes, which include a mixture of sounds of different species overlapped with background environmental noise. These differences in recording conditions create a domain shift between focal and soundscape recordings [3]. Recently, contrastive learning-based pre-trained models have been developed using focal recordings [4]–[6], and the robust audio embeddings from these pre-trained models were shown to be capable of generalizing to soundscape recordings [3].

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In this work, we propose a method for few-shot incremental learning for bird sounds classification using soundscape datasets. From a learning perspective, the method needs to cope with domain shifts caused by a mismatch between acoustic conditions, background noises, and diverse recording devices. This domain shift can cause catastrophic forgetting of previously learned classes when the model learns to classify bird sounds from a new soundscape. Further, a soundscape dataset includes unique species, typical for the specific location, but also common species that are present in other datasets.

The existing incremental learning methods for audio classification typically fall into two scenarios. One is class-incremental learning (CIL), where incoming tasks contain new audio classes from the same domain [7] [8], as illustrated in Fig. 1a. Another is domain-incremental learning (DIL), where incoming tasks contain the same audio classes from the new domains [9], illustrated in Fig. 1b. These scenarios are based on a strong assumption that incoming sequential tasks either contain the same classes or domains. This assumption is not valid in the case of datasets containing bird sounds. An incoming soundscape dataset, in other words, a new domain, may include a combination of both new and already seen classes from previous domains. Specifically, a model learns a new domain in each incremental time step, and that domain includes new or previously seen classes, as illustrated in Fig. 1. For this, we propose a universal incremental learning method (UIL) for few-shot bird sound classification.

The existing few-shot incremental learning methods for audio classification [10]–[12] or bird sound detection [13] are based on CIL. Most of these methods include one base task or session, followed by multiple incremental tasks, with sufficient training samples available in the base task to train the model from scratch offline for several iterations, and only a few training samples available in incremental tasks to update the model to adapt to new classes.

In this work, we propose using a fixed pre-trained model trained on focal recordings as a generic feature extractor and use its embeddings to adapt to any number of incremental soundscape datasets. We use a cosine classifier that works based on the class prototypes to learn domains incrementally and accumulate the inexpensive class prototypes of previously learned domains to avoid forgetting. Additionally, we inject a random projection (RP) layer with an activation function between the audio embeddings and the classifier as in [14], which expands the dimension of the audio embeddings and enhances the linear separability before computing the class prototypes for the cosine classifier. The proposed method is free from a base session and is online. It adapts to a new domain by only a single forward pass through the training samples, with minimal forgetting of previously learned domains. The proposed method is domain-agnostic and does not require any domain ID during inference for prediction.

The contributions of this work are as follows. (1) We propose a universal incremental learning framework that is suitable for few-shot bird sound classification from diverse datasets; (2) We show that the proposed method incrementally adapts to any new soundscape datasets by passing through a few training samples only once; the

Fig. 1: Comparison of incremental learning protocols. Color shade denotes the domain groups, solid box denotes the class groups, and arrows denote incremental steps. (a) Class-incremental learning (CIL) learns new classes from the same domain; (b) domain-incremental learning (DIL) learns the same classes from new domains; (c) Proposed universal incremental learning (UIL) learns new and already seen classes from new domains in incremental steps.

Fig. 2: Overview of the proposed universal incremental learning (UIL) method. Features \mathbf{v} extracted from a frozen pre-trained model \mathcal{P} for given input samples \mathbf{x} are projected into a higher-dimensional space using frozen random weights \mathbf{W} , followed by a nonlinear activation function. Randomly projected features \mathbf{u} are then used as inputs to the cosine classifier for prediction. The class prototypes of the cosine classifier are updated based on the new or old classes in the incoming new domain.

proposed method only requires audio embeddings from a fixed pre-trained model without any base session; (3) We analyze performance concerning each component of the proposed method in one-shot and five-shot incremental tasks.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the incremental tasks setups, notations and the proposed method for UIL. Section 3 introduces the datasets, training setup, baselines, implementation details, evaluation metrics, and results. Finally, conclusions are given in Section 4.

2. UNIVERSAL INCREMENTAL LEARNING

2.1. Tasks setup and notations

In our universal incremental learning framework, a sequence of T domains or tasks, here presented as different datasets, $\mathcal{D}_1, \dots, \mathcal{D}_T$ is introduced to the model for few-shot classification of bird sounds. A domain \mathcal{D}_t includes the audio samples of different bird species, and the model does not have access to previous domains at any learning stage. The proposed UIL combines the functionalities of both CIL and DIL protocols to learn the classes present in the incoming domain. CIL learns new classes from the same domain. In contrast, UIL learns the new classes from the new incoming domain, and it works like DIL whenever the same classes are present in the new domain. We refer to \mathcal{D}_t as the soundscape dataset, domain, task, or stage interchangeably throughout this paper.

We denote the total number of training samples in each soundscape dataset as M_t , and the total number of classes learned so far as C . $\mathbf{x}_{t,m}$ and $\mathbf{y}_{t,m}$ are the m -th training sample and corresponding one-hot encoded label of length C . $\mathbf{v}_{t,m} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ and $\mathbf{v}_{test} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ are embeddings of dimension K , extracted from a frozen pre-trained model \mathcal{P} for input training sample $\mathbf{x}_{t,m}$ and test sample \mathbf{x}_{test} , respectively. An overview of the proposed UIL method is given in Fig. 2. It includes two major components: a random projection layer and a cosine classifier, which are explained as follows.

2.2. Random projection layer

RP layer is injected between the pre-trained model and the classifier. The feature embeddings of an input training sample, obtained via the pre-trained model, are projected into a dimension G ($G > K$) using a random weight matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times G}$, followed by an element-wise nonlinear activation function ψ (e.g., ReLU) in each domain as:

$$\mathbf{u}_{t,m} = \psi(\mathbf{v}_{t,m}^\top \mathbf{W}), \quad \mathbf{u}_{test} = \psi(\mathbf{v}_{test}^\top \mathbf{W}), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{t,m}$ and \mathbf{u}_{test} are new features of length G in training and inference phases. \mathbf{W} contains training-free random weights, which are generated once and kept frozen in all incremental learning stages. The projected features are used to compute class prototypes for the cosine classifier.

2.3. Cosine classifier

Inspired by [14], [15], we propose using a cosine classifier. The weights of the cosine classifier are the class prototypes, computed by averaging the randomly projected embeddings of the training samples within classes. We denote class prototypes of a class y as \mathbf{c}_y .

In the proposed UIL setup, the incoming domain either contains only new classes or a combination of both new and previously seen (old) classes. For new classes in the incoming domain, we expand the classifier to accommodate new classes and compute their class prototypes. For old classes in the incoming domain, we compute class prototypes and add these to the class prototypes of the same classes in previously seen domains. This update to the class prototypes of the old classes helps to acquire incremental domain-specific knowledge. During inference, the class of a test sample y_{test} is predicted by finding the maximum cosine similarity s_y between its randomly projected feature embeddings and the set of class prototypes as:

$$y_{test} = \underset{y' \in \{1, \dots, C\}}{\operatorname{argmax}} s_{y'}, \quad s_y = \frac{\mathbf{u}_{test}^\top \mathbf{c}_y}{\|\mathbf{u}_{test}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{c}_y\|}. \quad (2)$$

Table 1: Final average accuracy (AA_T) and forgetting (FR_T) of the methods over all the tasks $T = 6$ for one-shot and five-shot bird sounds classification. Higher accuracy and lower forgetting are better.

Method	RP	ReLU	One-shot		Five-shot	
			AA_T	FR_T	AA_T	FR_T
Online						
Linear probe			0.5±0.3	0.6±0.3	0.5±0.2	0.9±0.3
Joint linear probe			0.8±0.4		4.5±0.8	
Offline						
Linear probe			6.1±1.7	13.1±1.4	8.8±0.4	27.3±1.5
Joint linear probe			14.9±1.3		36.7±1.2	
Proposed						
Universal incremental learning	✓	✓	16.5±1.4	1.8±0.2	33.5±0.8	5.6±1.0
Ablations						
Universal incremental learning			16.3±1.6	2.4±1.1	32.1±1.1	6.0±1.0
Universal incremental learning	✓		16.6±1.8	2.3±0.7	32.5±0.9	6.5±1.0

During training, we only update the class prototypes in the cosine classifier by a single forward pass through the few-shot training samples.

3. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

3.1. Datasets, training setup and baselines

We use 6 soundscape datasets from BIRB (benchmark for information retrieval in bioacoustics) [16]; these datasets were further preprocessed and provided in [3], [17]. A summary of these datasets is provided in the Table 2, including the number of audio recordings and the number of classes/species. Each soundscape dataset includes unique bird species and common bird species which are present in other soundscapes.

Table 2: A summary of the soundscape datasets from BIRB.

Dataset	Abbreviation	Recordings	Classes
Peru [18]	PER	14,798	132
Colombia, Costa Rica [19]	NES	6,952	89
Island of Hawai’i, USA [20]	UHH	59,583	27
High Sierra Nevada, USA [21]	HSN	10,296	19
New York State, USA [22]	SSW	50,760	96
Sierra Nevada [23]	SNE	20,147	56

We adopt an episodic training and testing strategy. For training, we randomly select one and five training samples per class from a dataset for one-shot and five-shot bird sound classification tasks, incrementally. The remaining test samples of all the datasets seen so far are considered for evaluation. Samples in the training and testing sets are different in all experiments. In this work, we learn the datasets in the following order: PER → NES → UHH → HSN → SSW → SNE.

We compare the performance of the proposed UIL method with two different methods used to solve the same problem: (1) a linear probe classifier trained on each incremental soundscape dataset using embeddings extracted from the pre-trained model. A linear probe is widely used to demonstrate the generalization ability of a pre-trained model’s embeddings in classification tasks [24], [25]. (2) a joint linear probe classifier trained using embeddings of all the soundscape datasets seen so far. This joint training violates the incremental learning setup, but it is given for completeness.

3.2. Implementation details and evaluation metrics

We use the CvT-13 pre-trained transformer model [26], trained on focal recordings of XC by [3]. The 384-dimensional feature vectors

are extracted for audio recordings in each soundscape dataset using CvT-13 that was trained using Prototypical Contrastive Learning of Representations (ProtoCLR). For complete details about the training procedure and parameters of CvT-13, we refer the reader to [3]. We compute log-mel spectrograms from audio recordings of soundscape datasets and apply the augmentation techniques using the configuration provided in [3]. ReLU is used as a nonlinear activation function in Eq. (1). The dimension G is set to 2048 based on preliminary experiments performed with different values of G .

For the baseline methods, linear and joint linear probes are trained using cross-entropy loss, Adam optimizer [27] with a learning rate of 5×10^{-4} and the CosineAnnealingLR [27] scheduler. The proposed method updates only the cosine classifier and does not require Adam-based weight updates. The number of epochs is set to 1 for online and 25 for offline training, to train both linear and joint linear probes.

Following the standard practice in incremental learning [9], [14], we evaluate the performance of the method after learning the current domain \mathcal{D}_t using average accuracy and forgetting of all the domains seen so far. Average accuracy is defined as:

$$AA_t = \frac{1}{t} \sum_{j=1}^t ACC_{t,j}, \quad (3)$$

where $ACC_{t,j}$ is the accuracy of j -th domain after learning the t -th domain. Average forgetting is defined as:

$$FR_t = \frac{1}{t-1} \sum_{j=1}^{t-1} \max_{i \in \{1,2,\dots,t-1\}} (ACC_{\hat{t},j} - ACC_{t,j}), \quad (4)$$

where $ACC_{\hat{t},j}$ is the maximum accuracy of the previously seen j -th domain after learning the \hat{t} -th domain.

We compute AA_t and FR_t after learning \mathcal{D}_t in both one-shot and five-shot classification setups. We run each incremental few-shot experiment 10 times with different random seeds and report the results using mean and standard deviation over average accuracy values and forgetting values across the runs.

3.3. Results

We report final average accuracy (AA_T) and forgetting (FR_T) of different methods after learning all the tasks ($T = 6$) in Table 1. For a detailed task-wise analysis, we show average accuracy (AA_t) and forgetting (FR_t) of different methods after learning each soundscape dataset, in Fig. 3.

As expected, the offline linear probe performs better than the online linear probe, which is trained using a single epoch. The linear probe

Fig. 3: Average accuracy and forgetting of the methods after learning the task \mathcal{D}_t . Average accuracy (a) and forgetting (b) of the current \mathcal{D}_t and previously seen tasks for one-shot classification; Average accuracy (c) and forgetting (d) of the current \mathcal{D}_t and previously seen tasks for five-shot classification.

Table 3: Accuracy of the methods on the current task \mathcal{D}_t for one-shot and five-shot bird sounds classification.

Method	PER	NES	UHH	HSN	SSW	SNE
One-shot classification						
ProtoCLR [3]	9.23±1.6	38.6±5.1	18.4±2.3	21.2±7.3	15.5±2.3	25.8±5.2
Proposed universal incremental learning	9.9±1.3	39.4±4.1	14.2±3.2	11.6±3.9	11.7±1.2	21.7±3.3
Five-shot classification						
ProtoCLR [3]	19.2±1.1	67.9±2.8	36.1±4.3	48.0±4.3	34.6±2.3	48.6±2.8
Proposed universal incremental learning	19.6±1.2	68.4±2.8	33.3±3.1	36.9±6.1	30.4±1.6	41.2±1.9

does not have access to the previous soundscape datasets. Training an offline linear probe on the current soundscape dataset for multiple iterations improves the performance on the current soundscape dataset, but overwrites the parameters of the previously learned classes, leading to increased average forgetting, as observed in Fig. 3b and 3d, and reduced average accuracy in Fig. 3a and 3c after learning each dataset. The performance of the online joint linear probe is worse, but the offline joint linear probe achieves competitive results by taking advantage of full access to the training samples of all the datasets seen so far. A joint linear probe requires multiple iterations and more training samples from all the datasets to perform better.

The proposed UIL outperforms the joint linear probe in a one-shot incremental learning setup, as can be seen in Fig. 3a and Table 1. We can see from Fig. 3c that the proposed UIL also shows competitive performance as compared to the joint linear probe in a five-shot incremental learning setup. UIL suffers from minimal forgetting despite potential abrupt changes in the domain distributions and increasing numbers of classes in incremental stages.

Without the random projection or only with the cosine similarity classifier, UIL gives comparable results. However, class prototypes from the randomly projected feature embeddings perform better, and a nonlinear activation function, ReLU, helps extract the important nonlinear interactions in feature embeddings, reducing the average forgetting.

We compare the accuracy of the proposed UIL on the current domain \mathcal{D}_t with the existing (non-incremental) few-shot bird sound classification method in [3]; the numbers for each domain/dataset are presented in Table 3. The work in [3] uses the feature embeddings from the same ProtoCLR-based CvT-13 pre-trained model, but uses a separate classifier to learn each soundscape dataset, with each classifier handling only the classes present in the current dataset. In

the incremental learning setup, the number of classes in the cosine classifier keeps increasing as the model learns a new dataset; therefore, a single classifier handles all the classes seen so far. The proposed UIL approach outperforms ProtoCLR [3] in the first datasets (PER and NES in this experimental setup) in both one-shot and few-shot learning. As it learns more datasets in sequence, the number of classes increases and known classes are updated to the new domain, affecting the overall accuracy.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a universal incremental learning method for few-shot bird sound classification. Our proposed approach is specifically designed to learn bird sound classes from multiple datasets incrementally, dealing with the presence of both new, previously unseen classes and classes that were already seen, but are now recorded in different acoustic conditions. It outperforms online and offline linear probes in both one-shot and five-shot incremental learning setups. The proposed approach relies on the audio embeddings of the CvT-13 pre-trained model, that uses focal recordings for training, but needs to update only the class prototypes in the cosine classifier to account for the domain mismatch. Our method is suitable for realistic deployments, being able to adapt to any new domains and new classes in a few-shot scenario. Future research includes the investigation of the effectiveness of the proposed approach on other animal datasets or combinations or different kinds of audio data.

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Integrating Spatial and Semantic Embeddings for Stereo Sound Event Localization in Videos

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Abstract—In this study, we address the multimodal task of stereo sound event localization and detection with source distance estimation (3D SELD) in regular video content. 3D SELD is a complex task that combines temporal event classification with spatial localization, requiring reasoning across spatial, temporal, and semantic dimensions. The last is arguably the most challenging to model. Traditional SELD approaches typically rely on multichannel input, limiting their capacity to benefit from large-scale pre-training due to data constraints. To overcome this, we enhance a standard SELD architecture with semantic information by integrating pre-trained, contrastive language-aligned models: CLAP for audio and OWL-ViT for visual inputs. These embeddings are incorporated into a modified Conformer module tailored for multimodal fusion, which we refer to as the Cross-Modal Conformer. We perform an ablation study on the development set of the DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset to assess the individual contributions of the language-aligned models and benchmark against the DCASE Task 3 baseline systems. Additionally, we detail the curation process of large synthetic audio and audio-visual datasets used for model pre-training. These datasets were further expanded through left-right channel swapping augmentation. Our approach, combining extensive pre-training, model ensembling, and visual post-processing, achieved second rank in the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 3 (Track B), underscoring the effectiveness of our method. Future work will explore the modality-specific contributions and architectural refinements.

Index Terms—Sound Event Localization and Detection, Stereo Sounds, Audio-Visual Machine Learning, Multimodal Localization, Audio Understanding

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound Event Localization and Detection [1] is a combined task that integrates sound event detection (SED) [2] and sound source localization (SSL) [3]. The goal is to identify active sound events from predefined target classes, track their temporal activity, and estimate their spatial positions. SELD systems are crucial for a wide range of real-world applications, including human-robot interaction [4], security monitoring, and immersive media production [5].

Since 2019, SELD has been a dedicated task in the Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) Challenge. Over successive editions, the task has evolved to include increasingly complex scenarios, such as moving sound sources [6], ignoring external interfering sounds [7], incorporating visual input to enable multimodal SELD in 360° videos [8], and estimating source distance [9]. For the 2025 edition, the challenge has shifted from the traditional 4-channel first-order ambisonics (FOA) and microphone array (MIC) formats to stereo SELD using conventional frontal video content, i.e., leveraging only left and right audio channels and perspective video. This format is better aligned with the requirements of conventional

media content. In stereo SELD the DOA prediction is limited to the azimuth angles in the range $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$, as elevation is ill-defined when using just two horizontally arranged channels, and distinguishing between front and back sources is inherently ambiguous. Source distance estimation, introduced in the previous edition, remains part of the task, which is therefore often referred to as 3D SELD. Additionally, in the audio-visual track, a new subtask has been introduced: predicting whether sound sources are onscreen or offscreen.

SELD is a non-trivial task, as it requires reasoning across spatial, temporal, and semantic dimensions: spatial information gives cues for direction and distance estimation; temporal information marks movements and onsets/offsets of sound source activity; semantic information identifies objects, their relations and likely behaviors. Recent advances in large language models (LLMs) [10], vision-language models (VLMs) [11], and audio-language models (ALMs) [12] demonstrate that language is a powerful lens for enabling semantic understanding and complex reasoning in relation to media content. Building on this, we posit that leveraging language-aligned models can enhance a SELD model’s semantic reasoning and hence indirectly benefit spatial and temporal reasoning. Traditionally, spatial localization relies on multichannel audio, allowing models to infer source positions through inter-channel time and level differences. This dependence limits the use of large-scale pre-training datasets. While synthetic audio [13] and visual [14] data can partially address this limitation, effective language alignment typically demands extensive pre-training on large-scale, heterogeneous data. Therefore, we extend our SELD architecture by integrating two existing language-aligned models: CLAP [15] for the audio modality and OWL-ViT [16] for the visual modality. Specifically, we extract audio and visual embeddings using their respective pretrained encoders and combine them with SELD embeddings obtained from a CNN-Conformer backbone, a widely adopted architecture in SELD research [17]–[19]. We argue that the embeddings from CLAP and OWL-ViT are semantically rich and provide complementary information to the task. To fuse these embeddings, we employ an adapted version of the Conformer architecture [20], which we refer to as the Cross-Modal Conformer (CMC). This module is used to integrate intra-modal embeddings from different sources (e.g., the SELD audio encoder and CLAP) and inter-modal embeddings (i.e., the combined audio representation and the visual embedding from OWL-ViT). This architecture is outlined in Sec. 2.1, and an ablation study to demonstrate the individual contributions of the language-aligned models and benchmark against the DCASE Task 3 baseline systems is presented in Sec. 3.

To tackle the distance estimation subtask, we partnered common SELD input features with short-term power of the autocorrelation stPACC features [21] in Sec. 2.2. Furthermore, we synthesized and carefully curated large audio and audio-visual datasets used to pre-train our models, described in Sec. 2.3. Final refinements includes a visual

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Fig. 1: Proposed audio-visual model (left). Blue blocks are frozen, red ones are pre-trained on the audio 5k and audio-visual 2k datasets, yellow on audio-visual 2k dataset only. Cross-Modal Conformer (CMC) architecture adapting the original Conformer [20] to process two generic modalities “Alpha” α and “Beta” β (right).

post-processing step based on human keypoint detection and model ensembling, which is described in Sec. 3 on experiments. Our best model ranked 2nd at the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 3 (Track B), demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

This paper introduces three key contributions: (i) the integration of semantically rich, language-aligned models into an audio-visual SELD architecture; (ii) an adapted Conformer architecture designed to fuse multiple modalities; (iii) substantial performance gains via curated data synthesis and engineering refinements, resulting in a second-place ranking in the DCASE2025 Task 3 Challenge (Track B).

2. METHOD

2.1. Proposed Architecture

The proposed model includes a SELD encoder that extracts embeddings from multichannel inputs, which are fused with CLAP audio embeddings via a cross-modal cross-attention mechanism. We adapted the Conformer architecture to accommodate inputs from different modalities. The resulting audio representation is then fused with visual features from OWL-ViT through a second Cross-Modal Conformer. A final feed-forward module predicts multi-ACCDDOA vectors for up to $N=3$ tracks [22], including on/off-screen activity as in the challenge baseline. The model is trained using class-wise Auxiliary Duplicating Permutation Invariant Training (ADPIT) loss [23]–[25].

2.1.1. SELD Encoder: We adopt a CNN-Conformer architecture for the SELD encoder, as it is widely adopted in SELD research [17]–[19]. The stereo input features of shape $C_{in} \times T_{in} \times F_{in}$ are processed by four CNN blocks with residual connections, each comprising two 3×3 convolutions, batch normalization [26], ReLU, and stride-2 average pooling, halving the temporal and frequency dimension at each block. This reduces the temporal and frequency dimensions by a factor of 16, producing a $512 \times T_{in}/16 \times F_{in}/16$ tensor. After frequency pooling and reshaping, we obtain a $T_{in}/16 \times 512$ embedding, aligned with the label frame rate of 10 labels/sec.. A four-layer Conformer with eight attention heads and depthwise convolutions (kernel size 51) [17] processes this sequence.

2.1.2. Cross-Modal Conformer: The CMC is an adapted version of the Conformer architecture proposed by Gulati *et al.* [20]. A

schematic representation is shown on the left side of Fig. 1, where a generic modality “Alpha” $\in \mathbb{R}^{T_{\alpha} \times d_k}$ is combined with another modality “Beta” $\in \mathbb{R}^{T_{\beta} \times d_k}$ [4]. Each sub-module retains the original Conformer structure, with two key changes: (i) two initial feed-forward layers independently process the modalities in parallel, and (ii) the standard multi-head self-attention is replaced by cross-attention, using queries from modality Alpha and keys/values from modality Beta. Our model includes two CMC blocks—first fusing SELD and CLAP embeddings, and then combining the result with OWL-ViT visual features. A single layer suffices for audio fusion, while two layers improve audio-visual fusion. Each CMC uses eight attention heads and depthwise convolutions with a kernel size of 51 [17].

2.1.3. Video Embedding Extraction: Since SELD involves spatial, semantic, and temporal reasoning, our previous works [18], [27] employed ResNet50 [28] to extract visual features from each individual video frames, capturing the temporal dimension across time. To obtain per-frame visual embeddings, a 7×7 average pooling operation was applied, resulting in a single feature vector for each frame. However, we now argue that this approach degrades spatial resolution, limiting the model’s ability to utilize fine-grained spatial cues. In contrast, other works, such as [29] or this year’s baseline system, apply average pooling across the channel dimension of the ResNet50 output, preserving the 7×7 spatial layout. Yet, we believe that this alternative sacrifices semantic richness, as pooling across channels degrades the learned feature representations.

Effectively managing time, space, and channel information in a unified framework is non-trivial. Nevertheless, we argue that temporal dynamics can be effectively captured by the SELD encoder itself. As such, the visual processing branch should be optimized to better leverage semantic and spatial information. To this end, we sacrifice temporal granularity in the visual stream. We replaced ResNet50 with OWL-ViT [16], a contrastive, language-aligned model, like CLAP, but specifically trained for visual grounding tasks like object detection. As a result, we expect OWL-ViT to produce visual embeddings that are both semantically and spatially rich. To retain some temporal context without incurring high computational costs, we sample video frames at 1 fps. The resulting embeddings are then aggregated via temporal average pooling. All individual ViT token embeddings are maintained to preserve spatial and semantic information.

OWL-ViT requires square input frames of size 768×768 . To avoid distorting the original rectangular frames in the dataset, we explored two pre-processing strategies during preliminary experiments: letter-boxing the frames with black bars to preserve the aspect ratio, and applying a non-linear spatial transformation that preserves object proportions in the central region while progressively stretching the top and bottom areas. This second approach is based on the assumption that most sound events occur near the center of the frame. The non-linear re-framing method yielded slightly better performance, and we therefore integrated it into our pre-processing pipeline. Visual tokens are extracted from 32×32 pixel patches, resulting in 576 tokens per frame, plus an additional classification token. Each token embedding has a dimensionality of 768. To align with the model’s architecture, we apply a linear projection to reduce this dimensionality to $d_k=512$. These OWL-ViT embeddings serve as key/value pairs (i.e., modality “Beta”) in the second CMC.

2.2. Acoustic Input Features

Since the left and right audio channels in the dataset are arithmetically derived from FOA signals as described in [30] and [31], [32], rather than captured by two physically separated microphones, they should

not present inter-channel time or phase differences. So, we adopted the inter-channel level difference (ILD) as the primary spatial feature for the SELD encoder, alongside log mel spectrograms computed independently from each channel. ILD features are calculated as the ratio of the squared magnitudes of the short-time Fourier transforms (STFTs) of the two channels, and subsequently mapped into the log mel domain:

$$\text{ILD}(m, t) = \log \left(\frac{\mathbf{H}_{\text{mel}} |\mathbf{L}(f, t)|^2 + \epsilon}{\mathbf{H}_{\text{mel}} |\mathbf{R}(f, t)|^2 + \epsilon} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{L}(f, t)$ and $\mathbf{R}(f, t)$ are the STFTs of the left and right channels, respectively, \mathbf{H}_{mel} is the mel filter bank, ϵ is a small constant to avoid division by zero and instability, and m in the mel frequency index. To further support the model in the distance estimation subtask, we include short-term power of the autocorrelation (stpACC) features, as proposed in [21]. The final concatenation of acoustic input features has a channel dimension of $C_{\text{in}}=4$. Input features are normalized for zero mean and unit standard deviation vectors.

2.3. Pre-processing and Data Augmentation

We pre-trained our model on synthetic data while keeping the CLAP audio encoder and OWL-ViT weights frozen. Synthetic FOA audio was generated using SpatialScaper [13], which convolves FSD50K sounds [33] with RIRs from various datasets [6], [34]–[39]. We created 5,000 one-minute FOA clips averaging 18 events per clip (std=6), and 500 additional clips for validation. Background noise levels were sampled from a normal distribution (mean=-65 dB, std=15) to encourage robustness. We overrepresented “Knock” and “Bell” sounds due to their detection difficulty. Using the stereo SELD data generator provided by the challenge organizers¹, we split each FOA clip into twelve 5-second segments (i.e., with hop size=5s), filtered out silent ones, and applied four random FOA rotations to each segment before extracting the stereo sounds, resulting in $\sim 150\text{k}$ training clips. We’ll refer to this synthetic dataset as “audio 5k”, as it is derived from 5,000 FOA files. We employed audio 5k to pre-train the audio backbone of the model, i.e., the SELD encoder and the first CMC.

To create an audio-visual synthetic dataset, we generated an additional 2,000 FOA clips with SpatialScaper and synthesized corresponding videos using SELDVisualSynth [14]. SELDVisualSynth creates synthetic videos by placing class-relevant source images or videos (e.g., a person speaking for speech sounds, a door for knock or door sounds) as tiles onto 360° background images, based on the positional metadata of sound sources generated by SpatialScaper. To enrich the quality of the visual output, we manually curated and extracted class-relevant source images from Flickr30k [40]. We also selected images of doors from DoorDetect [41], which have been employed for “door open/close” and “knock” sounds. Furthermore, we created additional synthetic foreground images for each sound class using NitroFusion [42]. Instead of employing the background canvases provided with SELDVisualSynth which consists primarily of outdoor environments, we adopted the +2,000 environments of the 360-Indoor dataset [43]. We also implemented a soft cross-fade between background canvases and foreground object tiles to remove strong artificial edges from output video. Fig. 2 shows example frames from the dataset. We initialized the SELD encoder and audio CMC with weights from the audio-only pre-training on audio 5k, and continued training the full model on the +60,000 audio-visual clips generated following this approach. We refer to this dataset here as “audio-visual 2k”.

¹github.com/SonyResearch/dcse2025_stereo_seld_data_generator

Fig. 2: Examples of synthetic scenes (clockwise from top left) in a restaurant, a walk-in wardrobe, a hotel room, a first-floor flat. The foreground tiles (bell*, laughter, door*, bell*, telephone) are applied with a soft cross-fade to avoid strong edges. * Generated with NitroFusion [42].

To further increase the size of the training dataset and model robustness, we adapted the audio-channel swap (ACS) [17] and video pixel swap (VPS) [18], [44], [45] augmentations to the stereo scenario. Thus, we swapped the left and right audio channels, and flipped the corresponding video frames to double the size of the training data. The synthetic data augmented with such methods resulted in over 410h of stereo audio data and an additional 168h of audio-visual data. The model was then fine-tuned on the real content of the DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset.

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1. Implementation Details

Audio spectrograms were computed using STFT with a 512-point Hann window and 150-sample hop size. At 24 kHz, this produces 800 temporal bins for the 5-second input clips. For stpACC features, we applied an STFT with a 1014-point Hann window. This ensures that the autocorrelation covers delays up to approximately 20 ms after the direct sound. The lag dimension was then downsampled by a factor of 8 to achieve 64 bins and allow concatenation with the other features. More details about stpACC can be found in [21]. The SELD encoder and first CMC were pre-trained for 100 epochs on the synthetic audio 5k dataset. The full model was then trained for 80 epochs on the 2k audio-visual set, and fine-tuned for another 80 epochs on the real development set, selecting the best model via F1 score on the test split. Training used Adam optimizer, batch size 32, and a learning rate reduced by 5% per epoch after the first 30.

3.2. Experimental Settings

Before presenting the results of the proposed training approach, we first introduce an ablation study that isolates the architectural contributions of our model under conditions similar to those used by the challenge baseline systems. We then report a series of experiments based on the full method described in this paper, including additional engineering refinements aimed at further enhancing performance. This reflects our submission to the DCASE 2025 Task 3 Challenge. Our evaluation uses the official metrics of the challenge².

3.2.1. Ablation Study: The ablation study is conducted under conditions similar to those adopted by the challenge organizers for the baseline systems. Therefore, we use only left and right log mel

²dcse.community/challenge2025/task-stereo-sound-event-localization-and-detection-in-regular-video-content#evaluation

spectrograms as audio features (excluding ILD and stpACC) and skip the pre-training stages, training instead on a mix of real clips from the DCASE 2025 Task 3 dataset and 15,000 synthetic audio-visual clips, as in the baseline setup. The ablation includes: a model with only the SELD encoder (SE), one with added CLAP embeddings (SE+CLAP), and the full audio-visual model (SE+CLAP+OV). To match the audio-visual model’s depth, both CMCs in SE and the second CMC in SE+CLAP are retained by setting the input modality Alpha=Beta. We also include an audio-only experiment with left-right channel swap (SE+CLAP+LRS) to assess the impact of this augmentation.

3.2.2. Proposed Method Evaluation: After the ablation study, we present the results achieved with the full proposed approach. Since the stereo viewing angle is randomly sampled from the 360° frames of STARSS23 [8], off-screen events outnumber on-screen ones. As a result, the model tends to overpredict the “off-screen” class, reaching a stable but biased ~80% accuracy. To mitigate this, we train a second model with a modified loss function, multiplying the binary cross-entropy loss by 4.0 whenever the ground truth label is on-screen.

Following Jiang *et al.* [44], we implement a visual post-processing step based on human keypoint detection to refine on/off-screen predictions. Using YOLOv11-Pose [46], we extract keypoints and associate specific sound classes with relevant ones: speech and laughter with the nose, clapping with wrist centers, and footsteps with ankle centers. If the predicted DOA falls within 20° of the corresponding keypoint direction, the event is marked as on-screen. This step affects only on/off-screen accuracy and $F_{\leq 20^\circ/1/on}$ metrics. To further improve performance, we apply a majority-vote ensemble across multiple systems. A sound event is considered active at a given time frame if at least two systems detect it and their DOA predictions are within 20°. The ensemble DOA is then computed as the average of those systems’ DOAs. Two exceptions apply: for the “Bell” and “Knock” classes, a single-system detection is sufficient, following [27]. Similarly, for on/off-screen classification, if any system predicts an event as on-screen, the ensemble output is also on-screen.

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Ablation Study: The ablation study results are shown in Table 1. The SELD encoder (SE) alone outperforms the baselines by a wide margin, indicating that the CNN-Conformer backbone is highly effective for SELD. Adding the audio CLAP embedding improves the F1 score by nearly one percentage point, as expected given CLAP’s role in enhancing the model’s semantic reasoning. Incorporating OWL-ViT, which involves the additional challenge of on/off-screen classification, leads to a further 0.6-point gain in F1 score, although spatial accuracy remains comparable to the SE+CLAP architecture. Finally, the experiment with left-right channel swap demonstrates the benefit of this data augmentation technique.

3.3.2. Proposed Method Results: Table 2 shows the results of the full proposed audio-visual method (AV), including two audio-only (AO) experiments based on the SE+CLAP architecture. The two AO variants are identical except for input normalization: the first (system (1)) is fine-tuned using statistics from the development set, while the second (system (2) marked “/w norm.”) uses statistics from the synthetic 5k dataset used during pre-training. While both perform similarly on the development set, a notable gap emerges from the challenge results on the evaluation subset: AO /w norm. achieves a 42.5% F1 score, compared to 29.4% for AO. This suggests that using the same normalization as in pre-training improves generalization, whereas fine-tuning on development set statistics may lead to overfitting. System (4) uses the same AV model as (3), but with the loss function that weights on/off-screen predictions more heavily when the event is on-screen.

Table 1: Ablation results achieved using only left and right log mel spectrograms audio features, and 15,000 synthetic sample during training. $F_{\leq 20^\circ/1}$ (F1) [%], $F_{\leq 20^\circ/1/on}$ (F1o) [%], Direction Of Arrival Error (DOAE) [°], On/Off Accuracy (Acc) [%]. AO: audio-only; AV: audio-visual; SE: SELD encoder; CLAP: CLAP audio encoder; OV: OWL-ViT; LRS: left-right swap augmentation.

Model	F1 ↑	F1o ↑	DOAE ↓	RDE ↓	Acc ↑
Baseline AO	22.8	-	24.5	41.0	-
Baseline AV	26.8	20.0	23.8	40.0	80.0
SE	34.6	-	19.7	34.8	-
SE + CLAP	35.5	-	19.3	34.7	-
SE + CLAP + OV	36.1	26.3	19.3	32.1	79.5
SE + CLAP + LRS	39.0	-	16.5	33.7	-

Table 2: Results of the proposed method on the development set DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset. The models audio-only (AO) or audio-visual (AV); variants with weighted loss (+W), visual post-processing (+P); Ensemble (Ens.) combines (1),(2),(3) and (4).

Model	F1 ↑	F1o ↑	DOAE ↓	RDE ↓	Acc ↑
(1) AO	45.7	-	15.0	31.0	-
(2) AO /w norm.	46.0	-	15.2	30.8	-
(3) AV	44.4	34.0	15.6	30.4	80.5
(3.1) AV+P	44.4	34.4	15.6	30.4	80.5
(4) AV+W	45.5	35.4	15.2	32.2	80.8
(4.1) AV+W+P	45.5	35.7	15.2	32.2	81.0
(5) Ens.	48.0	37.3	14.0	29.3	80.8
(5.1) Ens.+P	48.0	37.5	14.0	29.3	80.8

The ensemble model (5) combines predictions from systems (1), (2), (3) and (4). Finally, applying visual post-processing to (3), (4) and (5) results in the enhanced versions (3.1), (4.1) and (5.1), respectively.

All the experiments substantially outperform the challenge baselines and the other ablation experiments, marking the importance of extensive pre-training with adequate audio input features. The AO systems achieved slightly better $F_{\leq 20^\circ/1}$ and DOAE scores compared to the base AV systems (3) and (4), which also need to predict on/off-screen labels, adding an extra layer of complexity. Using a weighted loss function for on/off-screen classification gave only a minor gain in overall on/off accuracy. However, it led to a 1.4 percentage point gain in $F_{\leq 20^\circ/1/on}$. The visual post-processing step, which only modifies on-screen predictions, brought small gains in $F_{\leq 20^\circ/1/on}$. $F_{\leq 20^\circ/1}$, DOAE and RDE remained unchanged as post-processing has no effect on localization and class predictions. Generally, we observed RDE improvements of about 10 percentage points compared to the baselines. These gains may be attributed in part to the inclusion of stpACC features, which enhance the model’s ability to estimate distance. Model ensembling further improved performance, with system (5) ranking second in the DCASE2025 Task 3 Challenge (Track B).

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, we address the task of stereo 3D SELD in videos. Our approach integrates semantically rich feature embeddings from CLAP and OWL-ViT within an adapted Conformer module. An ablation study highlights the contribution of each model component, benchmarked against the DCASE2025 Task 3 Challenge baselines. Pre-training on large, curated synthetic audio and audio-visual datasets results in large performance gains. Further improvements may be sought through stronger integration of auditory and visual modalities exploiting their shared semantics, as well as engineering refinements to model ensembling and post-processing.

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An Entropy-Guided Curriculum Learning Strategy for Data-Efficient Acoustic Scene Classification under Domain Shift

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Abstract—Acoustic Scene Classification (ASC) faces challenges in generalizing across recording devices, particularly when labeled data is limited. The DCASE 2024 Challenge Task 1 highlights this issue by requiring models to learn from small labeled subsets recorded on a few devices. These models need to then generalize to recordings from previously unseen devices under strict complexity constraints. While techniques such as data augmentation and the use of pre-trained models are well-established for improving model generalization, optimizing the training strategy represents a complementary yet less-explored path that introduces no additional architectural complexity or inference overhead. Among various training strategies, curriculum learning offers a promising paradigm by structuring the learning process from easier to harder examples. In this work, we propose an entropy-guided curriculum learning strategy to address the domain shift problem in data-efficient ASC. Specifically, we quantify the uncertainty of device domain predictions for each training sample by computing the Shannon entropy of the device posterior probabilities estimated by an auxiliary domain classifier. Using entropy as a proxy for domain invariance, the curriculum begins with high-entropy samples and gradually incorporates low-entropy, domain-specific ones to facilitate the learning of generalizable representations. Experimental results on multiple DCASE 2024 ASC baselines demonstrate that our strategy effectively mitigates domain shift, particularly under limited labeled data conditions. Our strategy is architecture-agnostic and introduces no additional inference cost, making it easily integrable into existing ASC baselines and offering a practical solution to domain shift.

Index Terms—Acoustic Scene Classification, Curriculum Learning, Domain Generalization, Domain Shift

1. INTRODUCTION

Acoustic Scene Classification (ASC) aims to recognize the environment from an audio segment and serves as a fundamental task in computational auditory analysis [1], [2]. A major challenge in real-world ASC systems is domain shift caused by variations in recording devices, which can significantly degrade model generalization to unseen devices. The challenge is further exacerbated when only limited labeled training data is available. The DCASE 2024 Challenge Task 1 [3] explicitly targets this scenario by requiring systems to be trained on small fractions (as low as 5%) of labeled audio from a limited set of devices and evaluated on recordings from previously unseen devices. In addition, participating models must adhere to strict complexity constraints, including a maximum of 128 kB of parameters and 30 MMACs per second of audio.

Domain shift becomes particularly challenging when labeled training data is limited, as models struggle to learn domain-invariant representations from limited supervision [4]. Figure 1 illustrates this phenomenon in ASC, where spectrograms of the same scene recorded by different devices exhibit noticeable discrepancies.

To address such challenges, existing approaches often turn to data augmentation strategies—such as Freq-MixStyle [5] and device impulse response simulation [6]—or leverage pretrained models [7] to enhance model generalization across recording devices. These

Fig. 1: Example of domain shift in ASC caused by device variability. Although the two spectrograms represent the same scene, device-specific characteristics cause noticeable differences. As a result, a model trained on one device may fail to correctly classify inputs from another, illustrating poor generalization.

techniques improve feature diversity and representation quality but may also introduce additional complexity [8], [9], such as increased model size, reliance on external resources, or inference overhead.

While these approaches are effective, they focus on modifying the data or the initial state of the model. The training curriculum itself—the very order in which data is presented to the model—remains a relatively underexplored dimension for enhancing domain generalization [10]. This observation motivates our central question: Can we devise a lightweight, model-agnostic training strategy that optimizes the learning trajectory itself to build domain-invariant representations with limited supervision?

To address this challenge, we draw inspiration from Curriculum Learning [11], a training paradigm that organizes the presentation of training data from easy to hard, thereby optimizing the learning trajectory. This approach is particularly well-suited for data-limited domain shift scenarios, as it facilitates the progressive acquisition of generalizable representations [12]. By introducing less confounded, domain-invariant samples early in training, the model can establish a robust feature foundation before gradually incorporating harder, domain-specific examples. Such staged learning has been shown to enhance generalization in a variety of tasks [13], [14]. Building on this idea, we propose an entropy-guided curriculum learning strategy that complements existing approaches without modifying the ASC model architecture. Specifically, we employ an auxiliary domain classifier to estimate the device posterior probabilities for each training sample. The Shannon entropy of this distribution serves as a proxy for domain invariance, based on the intuition that samples with high entropy—those that confuse the device classifier—are more likely to be device-agnostic and thus easier for learning generalizable features [15]. The curriculum therefore begins with these domain-invariant samples to establish a robust feature foundation, and gradually introduces harder, domain-specific examples to refine decision boundaries.

To assess the effectiveness of our approach, we conduct evaluations across multiple ASC systems submitted to the DCASE 2024 Challenge Task 1, with diverse model architectures and training setups. Experimental results show that our method consistently improves cross-

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device performance under low-resource conditions. These findings demonstrate the potential of entropy-guided curriculum learning as a lightweight, architecture-agnostic, and easily integrable strategy for improving domain generalization in ASC.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Domain Shift in Data-Efficient ASC

Domain shift, particularly induced by device variability, is a well-established challenge in Acoustic Scene Classification (ASC) [16]. Differences in microphone frequency response and spatial positioning introduce systematic shifts in audio characteristics across devices [17]. These discrepancies can significantly impair cross-device generalization, as models trained on one device distribution often fail to transfer effectively to others [18]. The impact is especially pronounced under limited labeled data, where insufficient device diversity prevents the model from learning robust, domain-invariant representations [3].

When training data covers a diverse range of scenes and recording devices, domain-invariant features can emerge naturally, as the model learns to disentangle scene-relevant cues from device-specific artifacts [5]. In contrast, under data-efficient settings, such coverage is lacking, making the learning process prone to overfitting device characteristics. For instance, if recordings corresponding to a specific scene are predominantly collected using a single device, the model may implicitly associate the spectral properties of that device with the scene label [19]. Such spurious correlations introduce domain leakage and compromise robustness [16], [20], as the model relies on incidental device-dependent patterns rather than genuine scene-discriminative features. Furthermore, early exposure to domain-specific samples may bias the internal representation space of the model, steering the learning process toward device-dependent features [21].

The above findings suggest that, under limited supervision, it may be beneficial to control the order in which training samples are presented. By prioritizing domain-invariant examples early in training, the model may better avoid overfitting to device-specific cues. This intuition motivates the use of a curriculum-based learning schedule to improve generalization without altering model architecture.

2.2. Entropy-Guided Curriculum Learning

Curriculum Learning (CL) is a training paradigm inspired by the human learning process, in which knowledge is acquired progressively—from simple concepts to more complex ones [11]. By exposing the model to easier examples in the early stages of training and gradually increasing sample difficulty, CL has been shown to improve optimization stability and generalization, particularly in settings with limited labeled data [21], [22].

A key component of curriculum learning is the definition of sample difficulty, which determines the order in which training examples are presented. Existing curricula commonly rely on heuristics such as loss magnitude [22], prediction confidence [23], classification margin [21], or uncertainty estimates derived from Bayesian inference [24]. While these strategies are effective in many supervised learning tasks, their core assumption—that task performance is a valid proxy for sample difficulty—becomes untenable in the context of domain shift. The reason is that task performance is an inherently ambiguous metric: a sample with low classification loss may be either genuinely simple and domain-invariant, or deceptively easy due to spurious, domain-specific cues. This ambiguity renders such a metric an unsound foundation for any curriculum whose objective is to improve generalization.

To address this limitation, we propose to define sample difficulty in terms of domain uncertainty rather than task performance. The core idea is to prioritize training on examples that are minimally influenced

by domain-specific features, and are therefore more likely to generalize across domains. To quantify domain uncertainty, we employ an auxiliary domain classifier to estimate the device posterior distribution for each sample. The Shannon entropy of this distribution serves as a proxy for domain invariance: samples with higher entropy indicate greater ambiguity in device identity, suggesting a lower reliance on device-dependent features [15]. By organizing data according to this entropy-based measure, we construct a curriculum that gradually transitions from domain-invariant to domain-specific examples, thereby facilitating the learning of more generalizable representations. While curriculum learning has been explored in domain generalization for tasks like semantic segmentation [13] and fault diagnosis [14], its application to acoustic scene classification remains largely unexplored.

3. PROPOSED METHOD: ENTROPY-GUIDED CURRICULUM LEARNING

3.1. Overview and Problem Setup

We propose an entropy-guided curriculum learning strategy to enhance the generalization capability of ASC models under domain shift. The strategy comprises three stages: (1) quantifying domain uncertainty using an auxiliary device classifier, (2) constructing a training curriculum by ranking samples based on entropy, (3) performing staged model training from domain-invariant to domain-specific samples.

Each ASC model consists of a feature extractor f_{feat} and a scene classifier f_{cls} . To construct the curriculum, we substitute f_{cls} with a lightweight device classifier f_{dom} , which is trained to predict device identities. For each training sample x , the device classifier produces a posterior probability distribution over device labels. We compute the Shannon entropy $H(x)$ of this distribution to measure domain ambiguity. A higher entropy indicates greater uncertainty in device identity, implying stronger domain invariance.

We rank all samples by entropy and split them at the median: the top 50% form the domain-invariant subset \mathcal{X}_{inv} , while the remaining form the domain-specific subset $\mathcal{X}_{\text{spec}}$. Training begins exclusively on \mathcal{X}_{inv} and progressively incorporates $\mathcal{X}_{\text{spec}}$ through mixed mini-batches. This method requires no changes to model architecture or hyperparameters, ensuring seamless integration into existing ASC models.

3.2. Entropy-Based Curriculum Construction

To estimate domain uncertainty, we first freeze the feature extractor f_{feat} and train an auxiliary device classifier f_{dom} based on it. Given an sample x , the classifier produces a posterior distribution over device:

$$\mathbf{p}_d(x) = \text{softmax}(f_{\text{dom}}(f_{\text{feat}}(x))) \quad (1)$$

The classifier is trained using device labels and the standard cross-entropy loss. After training, we compute the Shannon entropy of the predicted distribution for each sample:

$$H(x) = - \sum_{i=1}^D p_d^{(i)}(x) \log p_d^{(i)}(x) \quad (2)$$

where D is the number of recording devices. Higher entropy indicates greater ambiguity in device identity, which implies that the sample is less influenced by device-specific characteristics and therefore exhibits stronger domain invariance.

Let $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$ denote the training set. We sort all samples based on their entropy values and partition them into two curriculum subsets:

$$\mathcal{X}_{\text{inv}} = \{x_i \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}} \mid \text{rank}(H(x_i)) \leq \lfloor 0.5N \rfloor\} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_{\text{spec}} = \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}} \setminus \mathcal{X}_{\text{inv}} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2: Overview of the proposed entropy-guided curriculum learning framework. In Phase 1, an auxiliary domain classifier estimates the device posterior distribution for each training sample, from which entropy is computed to quantify domain uncertainty. Based on entropy values, samples are partitioned into domain-invariant (X_{inv}) and domain-specific (X_{spec}) subsets. In Phase 2, the ASC model is initially trained on X_{inv} to promote domain-invariant feature learning, followed by a staged refinement phase using mixed batches composed of both X_{inv} and X_{spec} , thereby enhancing robustness to domain shift.

We adopt a median-based entropy split as a simple yet effective proxy for curriculum ordering, selecting the top 50% high-entropy samples as domain-invariant. This empirical threshold ensures a balanced curriculum distribution between domain-invariant and domain-specific examples. While this strategy is effective, we acknowledge that sample difficulty may vary continuously. Future work will explore adaptive or weighted curriculum scheduling schemes.

In the second training stage, training mini-batches $\mathcal{B} \subset \mathcal{D}_{train}$ are constructed using a fixed-ratio sampling strategy:

$$\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{B}_{inv} \cup \mathcal{B}_{spec}, \quad |\mathcal{B}_{inv}| = \lfloor 0.8B \rfloor, \quad |\mathcal{B}_{spec}| = B - |\mathcal{B}_{inv}| \quad (5)$$

The gradual incorporation of domain-specific samples facilitates stable convergence and improves generalization across unseen devices.

3.3. Curriculum-Guided Model Training

After curriculum construction, we reinstate the original scene classifier f_{cls} and train the full model $f_{cls} \circ f_{feat}$.

Training is performed using the standard cross-entropy loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{ASC} = - \sum_{i=1}^C y^{(i)} \log \hat{y}^{(i)}, \quad \hat{y} = \text{softmax}(f_{cls}(f_{feat}(x))) \quad (6)$$

where C is the number of scene classes and y is the one-hot label.

The model is trained in two stages:

- **Stage 1:** The model is first trained exclusively on \mathcal{X}_{inv} to facilitate the learning of domain-invariant representations.
- **Stage 2:** To enhance cross-device generalization, the model is progressively exposed to domain-specific inputs by constructing each mini-batch with a fixed 80:20 ratio of samples from \mathcal{X}_{inv} and \mathcal{X}_{spec} , respectively. This controlled inclusion enables the model to adapt to domain-specific cues while preserving the domain-invariant features learned during Stage 1.

The transition from Stage 1 to Stage 2 is triggered when the validation loss on \mathcal{X}_{inv} stops improving beyond a predefined threshold for several consecutive epochs. This reflects the core principle of curriculum learning: once the model has sufficiently learned from easier, domain-invariant samples, it is gradually exposed to more challenging, domain-specific data. Throughout both stages, we strictly follow the original training configurations of each ASC baseline, including the optimizer, learning rate schedule, and batch size. This ensures fair comparison and highlights the plug-and-play compatibility of our method. By progressively shifting the training focus, the staged curriculum promotes robust representation learning and improves generalization to unseen devices.

4. EXPERIMENT

4.1. Experimental Setup

4.1.1. Datasets: Our experimental evaluation is performed using the DCASE 2024 Task 1 dataset [25], a benchmark derived from the TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile development set for the Acoustic Scene Classification (ASC) task. The dataset consists of one-second audio clips representing ten distinct acoustic scenes, recorded across 12 European cities with multiple real and simulated mobile devices. In total, the development set contains 230,350 audio segments, amounting to approximately 64 hours of audio.

As detailed in Table 1, the dataset is partitioned into training and testing sets with a specific device distribution. The training set includes labeled data from real devices (A, B, C) and simulated devices (S1, S2, S3). A significant characteristic of the training data is its imbalance, with Device A contributing a substantial majority of the segments. The test partition comprises data from all training devices and, critically, introduces three previously unseen simulated devices (S4, S5, S6) to assess the generalization capabilities of the models.

Table 1: Distribution of DCASE 2024 Task 1 Development Dataset

Devices	Type	Total segments	Train segments	Test segments
A	Real	144,000	102,150	3,300
B	Real	10,780	7,490	3,290
C	Real	10,770	7,480	3,290
S1, S2, S3	Simulated	$3 \times 10,800$	$3 \times 7,500$	$3 \times 3,300$
S4, S5, S6	Simulated	$3 \times 10,800$	-	$3 \times 3,300$
Total		230,350	139,620	29,680

To investigate performance under data-limited conditions, we strictly adhere to the official low-resource protocol of the DCASE 2024 Challenge. This protocol provides five predefined training subsets drawn from the multi-device data (A, B, C, S1, S2, S3), which contain 5%, 10%, 25%, 50%, and 100% of the total labeled data, respectively. All models in our study are trained exclusively on these specified low-resource subsets.

4.1.2. Evaluation Metrics: Model performance is primarily evaluated using the official DCASE 2024 Task 1 metric: class-wise average accuracy. This metric computes the mean of per-class

Table 2: Classification accuracy (%) on the DCASE2024 Task 1 evaluation set across different training data splits. Each system is compared with and without our proposed curriculum learning strategy. The last two columns report accuracy on seen and unseen devices under the 5% training condition.

System	5%	10%	25%	50%	100%	Seen (5%)	Unseen (5%)
DCASE2024 Baseline [26]	44.00	46.95	51.47	54.40	56.84	45.3	42.4
+ our strategy	46.30	49.10	52.80	55.20	57.00	47.5	44.0
Cai_XJTLU [7]	48.91	53.16	58.09	59.47	62.12	50.6	46.7
+ our strategy	51.50	55.10	59.50	61.25	63.20	52.3	49.3
Han_SJTUTHU [27]	54.35	56.69	59.09	60.38	61.82	55.6	52.7
+ our strategy	56.60	58.25	60.40	61.65	62.20	57.3	55.2

accuracies, ensuring a balanced performance assessment across all scene categories. It is defined as:

$$\text{Accuracy}_{\text{avg}} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{N_c^{\text{correct}}}{N_c} \quad (7)$$

where C denotes the total number of scene classes, N_c represents the total number of samples belonging to class c , and N_c^{correct} is the count of correctly classified samples for that specific class.

4.1.3. Baseline Systems: To validate the general applicability of our entropy-guided curriculum strategy, we evaluate three representative baseline systems from DCASE2024:

- 1) **DCASE2024 Official Baseline** [26]: employs CP-Mobile, a CNN with residual inverted bottleneck blocks. It utilizes knowledge distillation from a teacher ensemble (PaSST and CP-ResNet), with augmentations like Freq-MixStyle and device impulse response simulation.
- 2) **Cai_XJTLU** [7] (ranked 4th): adopts a teacher–student approach with a pretrained PaSST teacher and a TF-SepNet-64 student trained via knowledge distillation. Training includes SpecAugment, Mixup, noise addition, and pseudo-labeling.
- 3) **Han_SJTUTHU** [27] (ranked 1st): uses a student–teacher framework with SSCP-Mobile (a spatially separable CP-Mobile variant) as the student, and a PaSST teacher ensemble. Techniques include knowledge distillation, SpecAugment, Freq-MixStyle, and model pruning.

4.1.4. Implementation Details: Our entropy-guided curriculum learning strategy is implemented in an architecture-agnostic manner. Accordingly, we follow each baseline system’s original training protocol, including optimizer, learning rate schedule, batch size, and other hyperparameters.

- **Auxiliary Domain Classifier:** A lightweight two-layer Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) is used to predict device identities from features extracted by the frozen primary encoder f_{feat} . The MLP comprises one hidden layer with ReLU activation and a softmax output layer, and is optimized using Adam with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} .
- **Curriculum-Guided Training:** The ASC model is trained in two stages as described in Section 3.3. The transition to Stage 2 is based on validation performance on \mathcal{X}_{inv} , and training follows the fixed 80:20 sampling strategy. All models are trained under their respective official settings to ensure fair comparison.

4.2. Results and Analysis

Table 2 shows the classification accuracy on the DCASE2024 Task 1 evaluation set across varying proportions of labeled training data. Performance improvements introduced by our strategy are particularly notable under data-limited conditions (e.g., 5%–25% of training data), where models are more susceptible to domain shift.

To better assess the impact of our method on domain generalization, we decompose performance under the 5% training condition into

Fig. 3: Classification accuracy across varying training data splits for different baseline systems, with and without our proposed strategy.

seen-device and unseen-device subsets, where domain shift is most pronounced. As shown in the additional columns of Table 2, our strategy consistently improves both subsets, with notably larger gains on unseen devices. For instance, in the Cai_XJTLU, accuracy on unseen devices increases from 46.7% to 49.3% (+2.6%), whereas the improvement on seen devices is comparatively modest (+1.7%).

We further illustrate these improvements in Fig. 3, which presents accuracy curves across varying data splits. The curves clearly show that our curriculum strategy consistently enhances model generalization across different data regimes. Specifically, improvements gradually diminish as more training data becomes available, which is consistent with the expectation that abundant labeled data already facilitates effective learning of domain-invariant features, thereby reducing the relative benefits of training strategies.

Overall, these results confirm the efficacy of our entropy-guided curriculum learning strategy in improving ASC model generalization under domain shift, particularly in scenarios characterized by limited labeled training data. Importantly, the proposed method does not introduce additional inference overhead or architectural complexity, making it a practical solution for ASC tasks under domain shift.

5. CONCLUSION

We proposed an entropy-guided curriculum learning strategy to address domain shift in ASC under limited labeled data. By employing an auxiliary domain classifier to estimate domain uncertainty via entropy, the training process is structured to progress from domain-invariant to domain-specific samples, facilitating the acquisition of robust and generalizable representations. Experimental results on multiple DCASE2024 Task 1 baseline systems demonstrate consistent performance gains across training regimes, with particularly notable improvements in low-resource scenarios. The proposed strategy is architecture-agnostic, incurs no additional inference overhead, and integrates seamlessly with existing ASC models.

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Hierarchical and Multimodal Learning for Heterogeneous Sound Classification

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Abstract—This paper investigates multimodal and hierarchical classification strategies to enhance performance in real-world sound classification tasks, centered on the two-level structure of the Broad Sound Taxonomy. We propose a framework that enables the system to consider high-level sound categories when refining its predictions at the subclass level, thereby aligning with the natural hierarchy of sound semantics. To improve accuracy, we integrate acoustic features with semantic cues extracted from crowdsourced textual metadata of the sounds such as titles, tags, and descriptions. During training, we utilize and compare pre-trained embeddings across these modalities, enabling better generalization across acoustically heterogeneous yet semantically related categories. Our experiments show that the use of text-audio embeddings improve classification. We also observe that, although hierarchical supervision does not significantly impact accuracy, it leads to more coherent and perceptually structured latent representations. These improvements in classification performance and representation quality make the system more suitable for downstream tasks such as sound retrieval, description, and similarity search.

Index Terms—Classification, Hierarchical, Multimodal, Taxonomy

1. INTRODUCTION

Automatic analysis of heterogeneous sound types remains a central problem in audio classification, spanning domains such as music, speech, and environmental acoustics [1]–[3]. Addressing this challenge requires broader classification frameworks and taxonomies capable of handling arbitrary input sounds. Unlike approaches tailored to particular types of sound, in heterogeneous sound classification, the goal is to develop a high-level classifier that generalizes across diverse acoustic inputs. This presents challenges due to the high intra-class variability, the varying audio qualities (quality, recording conditions, etc.), and the presence of ambiguous cases [4]–[7]. In this paper, we focus on a heterogeneous classification framework, where we use the Broad Sound Taxonomy (BST) [8] which organizes sounds into a two-level hierarchical structure, with 5 top-level and 23 second-level categories.

Human auditory perception naturally distinguishes sound classes at multiple abstraction levels [9], [10]. Therefore, the hierarchical information derived from the taxonomic structure can be valuable during the training of classifiers, e.g. [11]–[13]. In addition, in cases where acoustic signals are ambiguous or acoustically similar across different sources, introducing semantic information from human-annotated metadata can help disambiguate and improve classification. This is especially relevant with taxonomies such as the BST, where audio classes are defined according to sound semantics. Freesound [14], which contains a large and heterogeneous collection of user-contributed audio material, has recently adopted the BST as its organizational scheme. Freesound hosts audio recordings annotated with titles, tags, and free-text descriptions. The use of metadata is also essential in professional audio collections that involve music, instrument samples, and sound effects. Previous research shows that a common cause of misclassifications is acoustic ambiguity resulting from similarities in

sound characteristics or shared sound sources between categories [6]. This is particularly relevant in scenarios involving heterogeneous classification, where classes and audio qualities vary widely. Thus, incorporating additional modalities and semantic context is expected to enhance model performance.

In our work, we explore both hierarchical and multimodal approaches to improve classifier performance, and also take into account annotation confidence scores (i.e. scores that reflect the certainty of the annotator for each sound annotation) to filter training data and explore its impact in the classifier performance. The experimental results show that the combination of text and audio embeddings improves classification, while hierarchical supervision helps produce latent representations that are more coherent and perceptually well-structured. Our approach aims not only to improve classification accuracy but also to make the system better applicable to different downstream tasks, such as computing context-informed similarity between sounds, generating descriptive characterizations, and enhancing sound retrieval.

2. BACKGROUND

Hierarchical classification has been widely applied across various domains, including musical instrument families, music genre recognition, sound effect organization, and acoustic scene analysis, where labels can be naturally organized into structured taxonomies [15]–[18]. In such tasks, these hierarchical structures align with the way humans perceive and categorize auditory information, moving from broad categories (e.g. *animal*) to more specific ones (e.g. *cat*). Unlike flat classifiers that treat all labels independently, hierarchical approaches leverage relationships among labels to improve generalization, accuracy, and interpretability. Early examples in the audio domain that included hierarchical information were carried out using models such as HMMs and GMMs [19], [20]. More recently, hierarchical information has been integrated in classification problems through hierarchical deep neural architectures, loss functions, and evaluation metrics. Many different hierarchy-aware loss functions have been used, adapting standard losses such as cross entropy, triplet, and contrastive [21]–[26], proposing custom losses such as rank-based loss [23], and combinations thereof [27]. Most of these approaches are paired with representation learning and deep embeddings. These methods are particularly valuable when addressing challenges such as class imbalance, semantic overlap, or sparse labels at deeper levels of the taxonomy.

Multimodal setups in representation learning are gaining significant traction in the audio domain. It is common practice to obtain and utilize accompanying metadata, such as textual descriptions, tags, or contextual information, that can provide additional semantic information in the acoustic signal. Recent advances in multimodal learning have led to methods that learn shared embedding spaces for audio and text, supporting seamless integration and cross-modal

understanding of sound data. Models such as Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining (CLAP) are context-agnostic and aim to learn general-purpose representations that are transferable across diverse audio-text tasks [28], [29]. Other approaches incorporate semantic supervision, training models to classify audio events while aligning them with text-derived embeddings, thereby encouraging semantic consistency in the learned representations [30], [31]. In some methods, audio and text embeddings are explicitly combined or fused as joint input for downstream classification tasks [32], [33], allowing the model to leverage complementary information from both modalities. In this paper, we incorporate hierarchy information using a custom hierarchy-aware loss function, and we leverage the CLAP audio-text space to include audio and auxiliary textual information in the classification pipeline.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Model Formulation

We design a classifier to process both audio and text embeddings, denoted respectively as $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_a}$ and $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_t}$. Each input passes through a modality-specific encoder, implemented as a multilayer perceptron (MLP) comprising an input projection, a sequence of residual blocks, and an output projection. All layers use Leaky ReLU activations. The encoders extract modality-specific feature vectors:

$$\mathbf{h}_a = \text{fenc}^a(\mathbf{a}), \quad \mathbf{h}_t = \text{fenc}^t(\mathbf{t}) \quad (1)$$

When both modalities are used jointly, their representations are fused via an attention-based mechanism:

$$\mathbf{h}_f = \alpha_1 \mathbf{h}_a + \alpha_2 \mathbf{h}_t, \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha} = \text{Softmax}(W_2 \tanh(W_1 [\mathbf{h}_a; \mathbf{h}_t])) \quad (2)$$

The resulting feature vector $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbf{h}_a, \mathbf{h}_t, \mathbf{h}_f$ is then passed through a latent projection and classification layer, producing the final logits:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \text{fcls}(f\text{proj}(\mathbf{h})) \quad (3)$$

The training objective is to minimize the cross-entropy loss between the predicted logits $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ and the ground truth labels \mathbf{y} :

$$\mathcal{L} = - \sum_i y_i \log(\text{softmax}(\hat{\mathbf{y}})_i) \quad (4)$$

where i indexes the second-level classes.

3.2. Hierarchical Setting

In the hierarchical setting, we train the model adding two auxiliary losses to the standard cross-entropy in Eq. 4: a top-class penalty \mathcal{L}_{Top} and a contrastive loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{Contr}}$.

Let $\{\mathbf{z}_i\}_{i=1}^N$, with $\mathbf{z}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\|\mathbf{z}_i\| = 1$, denote the normalized latent representations of a batch of N samples. Each sample i has a second-level label y_i and a corresponding top-class label $t_i = \text{top}(y_i)$. The top-class penalty is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Top}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{1}(\text{top}(\hat{y}_i) \neq t_i), \quad (5)$$

where \hat{y}_i is the predicted second-level class, and $\mathbb{1}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function, equal to 1 if the condition holds and 0 otherwise.

The use of contrastive loss [34] encourages samples with the same top-class label to be pushed toward the same position in the feature space:

$$\ell_i = - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{P}(i)|} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}(i)} \log \frac{\exp(\mathbf{z}_i^\top \mathbf{z}_p / \tau)}{\sum_{a \neq i} \exp(\mathbf{z}_i^\top \mathbf{z}_a / \tau)}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathcal{P}(i) = \{p \neq i \mid t_p = t_i\}$ is the set of positive samples sharing i 's top-class label, \mathbf{z}_p are the corresponding representations, \mathbf{z}_a are

all other representations in the batch, and $\tau > 0$ is a temperature parameter. The total contrastive loss, weighted by a factor λ , is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Contr}} = \lambda \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \ell_i. \quad (7)$$

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

4.1. Dataset and Preprocessing

For our experiments, we use BSD10k-v1.1, an updated version of the BSD10k dataset introduced in [6]. BSD10k-v1.1 comprises 10,956 sounds retrieved from Freesound, labeled into 5 top-level classes and 23 second-level classes, according to the hierarchical taxonomy presented in [8]. This version contains a more balanced dataset with increased representation of underrepresented classes. It was also refined by analyzing the training data to identify and correct misclassifications caused by human error. The dataset includes confidence scores assigned to each sound during the annotation process, ranging from 1 (very unconfident) to 5 (very confident). The distribution of annotation confidence levels is as follows: 1 (1%), 2 (6.9%), 3 (30.1%), 4 (55%) and 5 (7%). The updated version of the dataset is publicly accessible¹.

As part of the experimental setup for model training, we run part of the experiments with the sounds assigned a confidence score ≥ 3 and ≥ 4 , which consist 92.1% and 62% of the dataset, respectively. As input features, we use representations from text and audio embeddings. In previous work, it was demonstrated that CLAP audio embeddings achieve better performance compared to purely audio-based embeddings in a heterogeneous setting [6]. In this work we extract CLAP embeddings as our audio feature representation. Additionally, we introduce a new modality by extracting text embeddings from the same CLAP model, using the metadata (textual data) in BSD10k-v1.1 originally provided by Freesound users. Text embeddings are extracted in two configurations: i) using sound title and tags; ii) using sound title, tags, and textual descriptions. Because the description is considered noisier, as it often includes unstructured or irrelevant information, we aim to evaluate its impact compared to the more concise metadata. All audio and text embeddings are extracted as 512-dimensional vectors.

4.2. Hyperparameters and Training

We trained each model for a maximum of 100 epochs, using early stopping in validation to prevent overfitting with *patience* = 5, Adam optimizer, fixed learning rate scheduler with an initial learning rate of $1e-3$, and a batch size of 64. Due to the unbalanced class distribution in the dataset, we opted for a stratified 5-fold cross-validation [35], ensuring that each fold preserved the overall class proportions. For each fold, we split the data into 80%/20% train/test, further dividing the former into 90%/10% train/validation. In all experiments, the feature vectors h_a and h_t were set to a dimensionality of 128, while the latent representation vectors z had a fixed dimensionality of 64. In the hierarchical settings, we kept $\tau = 0.5$ and $\lambda = 1$ for the contrastive loss. Finally, we applied data augmentation on both audio and text embeddings, namely noise addition and random masking (up to 70%). In the context of pretrained embeddings, such augmentations act as a network regularizer similar to dropout [36]. Preliminary results indicate that these augmentations do not impact overall performance but do lead to faster convergence, thereby reducing training time.

¹<https://github.com/allholly/BSD10k>

Table 1: Performance comparison across different hierarchy and modality configurations at three annotation confidence thresholds, including top-2 accuracy. All values are reported as percentages.

Confidence	Loss	Modality	Second-level	Top-level	Second-level (top-2)	Top-level (top-2)
≥ 1	Hierarchical	Audio	76.73 ± 0.47	87.67 ± 0.35	88.76 ± 0.20	94.44 ± 0.33
		Text	77.26 ± 0.32	87.11 ± 0.27	89.22 ± 0.10	94.14 ± 0.10
		Both	79.33 ± 0.03	88.75 ± 0.30	90.76 ± 0.13	95.19 ± 0.14
	Non-hierarchical	Audio	76.94 ± 0.23	87.50 ± 0.10	89.40 ± 0.58	95.29 ± 0.21
		Text	76.69 ± 0.26	86.54 ± 0.36	88.92 ± 0.27	94.55 ± 0.25
		Both	79.80 ± 0.53	88.97 ± 0.11	91.40 ± 0.40	96.02 ± 0.13
≥ 3	Hierarchical	Audio	78.83 ± 0.65	88.81 ± 0.29	89.50 ± 0.20	94.57 ± 0.31
		Text	78.16 ± 0.99	87.96 ± 0.54	89.86 ± 0.22	94.70 ± 0.26
		Both	81.07 ± 0.81	89.81 ± 0.52	91.64 ± 0.05	95.69 ± 0.19
	Non-hierarchical	Audio	78.77 ± 0.31	88.98 ± 0.12	90.05 ± 0.06	95.64 ± 0.18
		Text	78.50 ± 0.49	87.93 ± 0.18	90.49 ± 0.01	95.16 ± 0.10
		Both	81.50 ± 0.91	90.00 ± 0.25	92.12 ± 0.13	96.23 ± 0.03
≥ 4	Hierarchical	Audio	84.79 ± 1.32	92.57 ± 0.28	92.18 ± 1.00	95.87 ± 0.50
		Text	83.39 ± 1.59	91.48 ± 0.43	92.17 ± 0.56	95.40 ± 0.08
		Both	87.34 ± 0.83	93.60 ± 0.34	94.11 ± 0.42	96.58 ± 0.17
	Non-hierarchical	Audio	84.96 ± 0.42	92.23 ± 0.16	92.83 ± 0.81	96.74 ± 0.38
		Text	84.12 ± 0.77	91.61 ± 0.42	92.92 ± 0.46	96.49 ± 0.19
		Both	87.36 ± 0.42	93.42 ± 0.22	94.76 ± 0.32	97.66 ± 0.13

5. RESULTS

We compare against a baseline consisting of a KNN trained in audio-only embeddings [6], which we retrain with the latest version of the dataset and yield an accuracy of 77.45% in second-level classes and 87.65% in top-level classes. Our best performing model with the same setting (non-hierarchical, audio-only, non-filtered dataset by confidence levels) performs 77.51% on the second level and 87.84% on the top level. This demonstrates an incremental improvement.

Table 1 shows the results of all training configurations. For the text embeddings, we use the best-performing variant, which includes descriptions. The difference in accuracy is marginal, suggesting that a reduced amount of textual information may still be sufficient in this setting. Overall, both hierarchical and non-hierarchical models tend to exhibit comparable performance. Models trained with audio embedding achieve a small increase in accuracy than those using text embeddings, while both modalities significantly outperform the single-modality ones. Annotator confidence plays an important role in the overall accuracies: filtering the dataset by confidence level (including sounds with confidence scores of ≥3 and ≥4) removed the more ambiguous samples, resulting in a substantially improved accuracy across all configurations (up to ~2% and ~9% in the second level and ~1.5% and ~5% in the top level, respectively). The approach presented herein allows for a more thorough assessment of the model’s learning performance. We have observed that human uncertainty is reflected in the model’s behavior; specifically, the model occasionally makes errors similar to those of annotators due to the ambiguous boundaries inherent in the broadness of the task. The average confidence per class in the dataset ranges from 3.15 to 4.05, indicating moderate variations of annotation uncertainty in specific classes but suggesting the presence of ambiguous sounds in most classes.

In addition, we report the top-2 accuracy for both taxonomic levels, defined as the proportion of samples for which the correct label appears among the model’s top two predictions. We support that this is particularly relevant, since the case of edge-case sounds falling between two categories could be semantically plausible, as already highlighted in [6]. Therefore, we can assess its ability to capture these ambiguities and provide insight into how often it nearly arrives at the correct decision, even when its top prediction is incorrect. The accuracy across all configurations trained with the unfiltered dataset improves by ~12% in the top level and ~7% in

Fig. 1: Confusion matrix showing class-wise accuracies for the hierarchical configuration (H, A+T, C ≥ 1, training fold 1).

the second level. During the experiments, this proved also useful from an analytical perspective, as it allowed us to evaluate clearly wrong-classified samples. In further comment on such ambiguity, Fig. 1 shows an example of a confusion matrix relative to a single fold in hierarchical, multimodal training. Overall, some classes always exhibit a higher degree of confusion. Misclassifications are prominent within the *Music (m)* top class, particularly with the *Multiple instruments (m-mi)* subclass frequently being assigned to the other two subclasses, while within the *Soundscapes (ss)* class, the *Indoors (ss-i)* class gets incorporated into *Urban (ss-u)*. In cases where the top-level class is also misclassified, certain second-level classes remain persistently challenging even as the annotation confidence score filtering increases. Specifically, misclassifications occur from *Speech*→*Conversation/Crowd (sp-c)* to *Soundscapes*→*Urban*, and from *Sound effects*→*Animals (fx-a)* to *Soundscapes*→*Nature (ss-n)*. This could be due to certain classes having more complex definitions or involving the concept of single/multiple sound sources, which the model may not effectively capture.

Fig. 2: Latent space visualizations of the various settings. Plots are relative to the same training fold. NH = non-hierarchical; H = hierarchical; A+T = audio + text modality; C = annotation confidence score.

Fig. 3: Sorted average class accuracy color-coded by number of samples in the test set (NH, A+T, C ≥ 3, test fold 1).

Although the classification accuracy across the same modalities remains comparable between hierarchical and non-hierarchical approaches, the structure of the latent space differs significantly. We apply PCA to reduce the 64-dimensional representations to a 2D latent space. As seen in Fig. 2, the hierarchical latent space (2b) demonstrates a more coherent and well-separated representation, where classes sharing the same top-level class cluster closer together. This spatial organization reflects the underlying taxonomy of the data and highlights the positive impact of hierarchical priors on representation learning. Another artifact is the elongation of latent clusters, which may be attributed to the dimensionality reduction algorithm. Further examination can be conducted to identify which samples are located on opposite sides of the intra-class space. This behavior contrasts with the non-hierarchical latent space illustrated in Fig. 2a, where such clear organization is absent. For example, *Instrument samples* → *Percussion* (*is-p*) are positioned closer to *Sound effects* (*fx*), likely due to shared acoustic characteristics such as short, non-pitched textures. Another example is that *Soundscapes* → *Synthetic* (*ss-s*) are located close to *Sound effects* → *Electronic* (*fx-el*) and *Instrument samples* → *Electronic* (*is-e*), likely because they often include computer-generated textures and may share common tag vocabularies. This could indicate that the model first focuses on timbral characteristics (e.g. texture) rather than on properties such as the number of sources or time-domain characteristics. Interestingly, the conceptually important distinction between mono-source and multi-source content, such as that between *Sound effects* and *Soundscapes*, does not appear to be prioritized.

Figs. 2c and 2d, which depict the latent spaces for multimodal hierarchical training with annotation confidence scores ≥3 and ≥4, respectively, show a similar coherent structure where classes that share the same top level are closer. Additionally, as confidence increases, the clusters become sharper with larger gaps between second-level classes inside the same top-level class, fewer intrusions from other classes, and a greater tendency for each class to occupy a well-defined

region of the latent space.

Finally, we observe a common tendency for less-represented classes to exhibit lower performance, as shown in Fig. 3. Although class imbalance is a well-known factor contributing to such disparities, we argue that this alone does not fully explain such behavior. Indeed, the taxonomy used underlies semantically or structurally complex phenomena that are inherently harder to learn, stemming from intra-class variability or a dependence on context-specific features. Consequently, the limited number of training examples may not fully represent this variability and lead to poor generalization on unseen data in the test split. Moreover, preliminary experiments involving traditional approaches to addressing dataset imbalance (e.g. focal loss [37]) yield only negligible improvements. Some underrepresented classes performed slightly better, but the improvements were not consistent across different folds. Enhancing performance on such classes may, therefore, require not only rebalancing the dataset but also increasing the diversity of training samples. Notably, the confidence of the model for each class did not show a correlation with the number of samples in the training set, and training with fewer data in all classes did not significantly impact the accuracy.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper investigates multimodal and hierarchical strategies to enhance classification performance in real-world tasks. The insertion of textual information demonstrated an improvement in classification accuracy. We also foresee that the shown benefits of hierarchical latent representations extend beyond representational structure, proving especially useful in organizing similarity relationships with a better balance between semantic and acoustic features while encoding high-level conceptual information. Filtering data based on annotation confidence scores proved helpful in understanding what the model learns and identified sources of model confusion. To improve generalization, incorporating this information into the training process, such as weighting samples by their confidence, could be beneficial.

Future work includes leveraging more data for the training and evaluation of heterogeneous classification tasks. Since the introduction of the BST in Freesound, contributors have been manually annotating their newly uploaded sounds with BST classes, thereby providing data for further experiments. Even though crowdsourced annotations may be inconsistent, since edge cases can be interpreted differently by each user, such models can still help identify potentially incorrect labels. We also plan to explore the effect of inserting hierarchical information directly into the embedding learning process.

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Cross-modal Attention Architectures for Language-Based Audio Retrieval

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Abstract—We present our submission to Task 6 of the DCASE 2025 Challenge on language-based audio retrieval, where our team ranked second overall, with our best single system achieving the fifth-highest score among all individual submissions. Our approach investigates multiple cross-modal architectures, including both standard dual-encoders and attention-based models that leverage fine-grained interactions between audio and text embeddings. All models are trained with contrastive learning on a combination of large-scale captioned audio datasets, using PaSST and RoBERTa as backbone encoders. While each system achieves competitive results on its own, we observe consistent improvements when combining them in an ensemble, suggesting that the architectures capture complementary audio-text relationships. We support this finding with initial representational analyses, which point to differences in how these models structure the shared embedding space. Our results highlight the benefits of architectural diversity in modeling semantic similarity across modalities.

Index Terms—Language-based Audio Retrieval, Audio transformer, Cross-modal attention

1. INTRODUCTION

Language-based audio retrieval (LBAR) systems aim to retrieve relevant audio recordings from a large corpus based on free-form natural language queries. Unlike traditional sound event detection or tagging systems that rely on predefined taxonomies, LBAR enables flexible and intuitive access to audio content by aligning auditory signals with descriptive semantics. This task remains technically challenging due to the need to bridge heterogeneous modalities—raw waveforms and text—within a unified embedding space where semantic similarity is meaningfully preserved.

At the core of this task lies a challenging multimodal alignment problem: systems must learn to associate raw audio signals with textual descriptions, despite the inherent differences in structure and modality. The dominant approach involves contrastive learning within a dual-encoder framework, where separate encoders project audio and text inputs into a shared embedding space. Relevance is then computed based on the cosine similarity between these embeddings. While this method has proven effective, its reliance on global representations limits its ability to capture fine-grained semantic alignments, such as correspondences between specific acoustic events and words or phrases.

Recent work [1], [2] suggests that richer modeling of cross-modal interactions, particularly via attention mechanisms, can address this limitation by incorporating Token-level correspondences into the retrieval process. Motivated by these insights, we explore a diverse set of architectures for LBAR, including both standard dual-encoders and attention-based models that explicitly model interactions between audio and text embeddings.

Our results demonstrate that while each individual model performs competitively, their combination in an ensemble yields consistent improvements across metrics. We further analyze the representations learned by these systems and find evidence that they capture complementary aspects of audio-text semantics. Our findings underscore the value of architectural diversity in modeling cross-modal semantic similarity and contribute insights towards the development of more robust and expressive LBAR systems.

2. CROSS MODAL ATTENTION IN TEXT TO AUDIO RETRIEVAL

We present a cross-modal attention-based method for text-to-audio retrieval that aims to effectively align textual and audio representations following already existing proposals [1].

Given textual embeddings $T \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d_t}$ and audio embeddings $A \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times d_a}$ where N denotes the number of embeddings of a sentence, d_t the dimension of the text embeddings, M the number of embeddings of an audio and d_a the dimension of the audio embeddings, we first project them into a common space of dimension d . Specifically, textual embeddings T are projected through a linear transformation to obtain the query vector (Q):

$$Q = W_q T \quad Q \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d} \quad (1)$$

where $W_q \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_t}$ are learned parameters.

Audio embeddings are projected independently using two separate linear transformations to generate key (K) and value (V) vectors:

$$K = W_k A, \quad K \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times d} \quad (2)$$

$$V = W_v A, \quad V \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times d} \quad (3)$$

where $W_k, W_v \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_a}$ are also trainable parameters.

Next, we apply multi-head attention, defined as:

$$\text{MultiHead}(Q, K, V) = \text{concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_h) W^O \quad (4)$$

where h indicates the number of heads, $W^O \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ are trainable parameters and each attention head is implemented following the standard definition [3]:

$$\text{head}_i = \text{Attention}(QW_i^Q, KW_i^K, VW_i^V) \quad (5)$$

where $W_i^Q, W_i^K, W_i^V \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_h}$ are all trainable parameters and d_h denotes the head size.

The output of the attention module is passed through another linear layer:

$$H = W_o \cdot \text{MultiHead}(Q, K, V), \quad H \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d} \quad (6)$$

with parameters $W_o \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ also being trainable.

Finally, we compute the similarity between these refined cross-modal representations H and the original textual embeddings T using the average cosine distance between them as follows:

$$\text{sim}(T, H) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{T_i \cdot H_i}{|T_i| |H_i|} \quad (7)$$

To train our models we rely on the normalized temperature cross-entropy loss [4], which transforms the similarities into conditional probabilities using a temperature-scaled softmax.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

To evaluate the effectiveness of our retrieval systems and to ensure fair comparison with state-of-the-art (SOTA) methods, we adopt a comprehensive experimental protocol that follows the standards established in recent benchmark efforts. Our setup covers training data, preprocessing, model implementation, and evaluation strategy, including both the conventional Clotho split and the extended evaluation with improved caption-to-audio correspondences.

3.1. Datasets

All models are trained using a combination of four large-scale captioned audio datasets: ClothoV2, AudioCaps, WavCaps, and TACOS. This unified training set provides both human-annotated and synthetic captioning data, covering a broad range of sound types and textual styles, thereby supporting robust and generalizable retrieval capabilities.

ClothoV2 [5] serves as our primary benchmark for evaluation. It consists of audio clips ranging from 10 to 30 seconds, each paired with five natural language captions. The dataset is divided into training, validation, and test sets, comprising 3840, 1045, and 1045 audio files, respectively. We train only on the training subset, monitor performance on the validation split, and report results on the test split. In addition to the standard evaluation setup, we also utilize the improved caption correspondences recently introduced, which provide human-verified many-to-many relevance annotations between queries and audio files. This enhancement allows for a more fine-grained and realistic assessment of retrieval performance.

AudioCaps [6] contributes over 50,000 audio clips, each paired with a single human-written caption. The audio is derived from AudioSet and spans a wide variety of acoustic scenes and events. We aggregate the training, validation, and test splits of AudioCaps into a single dataset, using it as part of the pretraining corpus to increase model generalization.

WavCaps [7] extends the scale of training by providing weakly labeled captions for over 400,000 audio clips collected from multiple online repositories. The captions are synthetically generated using a large language model (GPT-3.5) and capture high-level sound descriptions. Despite their automatic nature, the diversity and volume of WavCaps provide valuable learning information when combined with human-annotated corpora.

TACOS (Temporally-Aligned Audio CaptiOnS) [8] introduces frame-level supervision by aligning captions to specific regions of audio clips. While the dataset includes detailed time-segment annotations, our current experiments use only the weak labels—i.e., global clip-level caption associations—to remain consistent with the global retrieval task. TACOS contains more than 12,000 real-world audio files with approximately 48,000 region-level captions.

To ensure fair benchmarking and avoid evaluation leakage, we follow dataset-specific guidelines for removing overlap with Clotho test sets during training. This step is particularly relevant for synthetic datasets like WavCaps, which aggregate clips from sources such as AudioSet and Freesound.

3.2. Pretrained Embedding Models

Audio is processed using the PaSST [9] transformer encoder, a pretrained audio model based on the vision transformer architecture. PaSST is designed to efficiently handle long audio sequences through patch-wise input and temporal patch dropout. Each audio clip is transformed into a sequence of token embeddings, with one embedding approximately every 10 seconds. During training, audio inputs longer than 30 seconds are truncated, while shorter ones are zero-padded

to a fixed maximum duration to ensure consistent batch sizes. The tokens produced by PaSST have length $d_a = 768$.

Text inputs are encoded using RoBERTa-large [10], a transformer-based language model with 24 layers and 355 million parameters. RoBERTa is well-established for Sentence-level and Token-level representation learning and has shown strong results in multimodal retrieval. Captions are normalized to lowercase, stripped of punctuation, and tokenized using the RoBERTa tokenizer. Token sequences are padded or truncated to a fixed length of 32 tokens, which we found sufficient to capture most captions without loss of information. The text tokens produced by the model have length $d_t = 1024$.

3.3. Model Training and Optimization

We trained three different configurations consisting of the standard dual-encoder architecture (hereafter referred to as Dual-encoder) which is exactly the same as the one used for the challenge benchmark [11], a cross-attention system which only used the Sentence-level embedding token from RoBERTa (Sentence-level attention model from now on), and finally another cross-attention system which utilized all the text embeddings (Token-level attention model from now on). We used 8 attention heads and a joint embedding space of dimension 1024.

To properly isolate the impact of architectural design while enabling a fair comparison with state-of-the-art methods, we conducted experiments both using only the Clotho dataset and the full combined training set comprising Clotho, AudioCaps, WavCaps, and TACOS.

We trained both encoders, the embeddings projection layers and the cross-modal attention heads employing the Adam optimizer. When training on Clotho alone, we used a fixed batch size of 64 audio-text pairs; for the combined datasets experiments, batch sizes of 128 were used for the PaSST–RoBERTa Large and Sentence-level embedding systems and 96 for the full text embeddings model due to memory limitations. After one warm-up epoch, a cosine annealing schedule was used to decrease the learning rate from 2×10^{-5} to 10^{-7} over ten epochs. All models are trained end-to-end, including the encoders and cross-modal attention layers where applicable.

After pretraining, fine-tuning with knowledge distillation was performed following the approach of [12]. For models trained on the full dataset, distillation was applied using ClothoV2, AudioCaps, and TACOS weak, with the same training setup. In contrast, models trained solely on Clotho were fine-tuned exclusively on that dataset. In all cases, predictions from the three models were averaged to estimate caption–audio correspondences, using a temperature parameter $\tau = 0.05$ and a loss balancing factor $\lambda = 1$.

4. EMBEDDING SPACE ANALYSIS

To better understand how each architecture encodes and aligns audio and textual information, we analyze the structure of the shared embedding space across the three model variants. For each model, we extract the final representations of audio and text from the ClothoV2 test set and visualize their projections using dimensionality reduction techniques.

In all models, PaSST produces a sequence of patch-based embeddings for the input audio, while RoBERTa yields either a single CLS token (for Sentence-level models) or a sequence of token embeddings (for the Token-level attention model). For the dual-encoder and Sentence-level attention models, a single embedding per modality is directly available or easily extracted, and cosine similarity between these vectors is used for retrieval. However, in the Token-level model, where multiple token or frame-level embeddings exist, we compute the mean of the audio and text embeddings respectively to obtain a single global representation suitable for analysis and comparison.

Fig. 1: UMAP projections of the shared embedding space for each model architecture. Top-left: dual-encoder baseline showing highly intermixed audio (blue) and text (orange) embeddings. Top-center and top-right: Sentence-level attention model’s key and value projections, respectively, showing strong modality separation. Bottom-left and bottom-center: Token-level attention model’s key and value projections, likewise exhibiting distinct clustering by modality. For attention-based models, audio embeddings were projected separately as keys and values; when needed, audio and text representations were averaged to produce global embeddings for visualization.

We analyze the structure of the learned embedding spaces by projecting the global audio and text embeddings from each model into two dimensions using Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) [13]. These visualizations expose notable differences in how each architecture organizes multimodal data. In the case of the dual-encoder model, audio and text embeddings form relatively well-aligned clusters, with no sharp separation between modalities, indicating that the shared space effectively captures coarse semantic alignment. However, the modality boundaries remain somewhat diffuse, and visual inspection alone is insufficient to evaluate alignment quality. To quantify the degree of semantic correspondence, we perform a statistical comparison of cosine distances between matching audio–caption pairs and randomly sampled mismatched pairs. A two-sample t-test reveals a highly significant difference ($p < 10^{-16}$), confirming that matched pairs are substantially closer in the embedding space, and that the model has learned a discriminative structure that reflects semantic similarity.

In contrast, both attention-based models exhibit clearly segregated clusters for audio and text. We include visualizations of the key (K) and value (V) projections not because we expect them to align directly with the textual embeddings (Q), but to illustrate how the attention mechanism organizes modality-specific intermediate representations. By construction, K and V are audio-derived projections that mediate the interaction with textual queries Q, and their structure is informative about the degree of specialization of the audio pathway prior to attention. This behavior differs from the dual-encoder setup, where training directly enforces cross-modal embeddings to be close in cosine distance. In that case, similarity is imposed at the level of the raw embeddings, which pushes audio and text to occupy a common latent space and leaves little room for modality-specific clustering. By contrast, in attention-based models alignment is not enforced on K and V themselves, but only after the attention operation,

through the output H compared to Q. As a result, K and V remain organized in modality-specific subspaces, and alignment with text emerges only after this intermediate transformation. The observed clustering should therefore not be interpreted as evidence against cross-modal learning, but rather as an indication that attention preserves distinct pathways internally while deferring semantic alignment to later stages. More broadly, this suggests that cross-modal attention layers might increase representational capacity by allowing each modality to maintain its own structure while still producing compatible semantic representations when required for training.

These differences suggest that each architecture encodes complementary aspects of cross-modal similarity—global fusion versus local alignment—which likely contributes to the performance gains observed in our ensemble system. Nevertheless, this analysis is an initial exploration and further experiments will be needed to corroborate the observed behaviors.

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Comparison to state-of-the-art systems

To contextualize the performance of our proposed models, we compare them against the current state-of-the-art systems presented at the DCASE 2024 Challenge [14]. The winning system from that challenge achieved a mAP@10 of 41.91, R@1 of 29.33, R@5 of 59.311, and R@10 of 71.923 on the ClothV2 test set using an ensemble of three distilled models each using a different audio encoder: PaSST [9], AST [15], and MobileNetV3 [16] architectures, and RoBERTa as the text encoder.

In comparison, our best ensemble system, combining Dual Encoder, Sentence-level attention, and Token-level attention models trained with knowledge distillation, achieves 40.423 mAP@10, R@1 of 27.732, R@5 of 58.201, and R@10 of 71.732 when trained on the full dataset. While these results are below the 2024 SOTA across all metrics,

Table 1: Retrieval performance of different model architectures, including a baseline dual-encoder and two attention-based systems (Sentence-level and Token-level), trained with and without knowledge distillation. Results are reported for models trained solely on the Clotho dataset and on a combined dataset (Clotho, AudioCaps, WavCaps, and TACOS). Metrics include mAP@16 and mAP@10 using improved caption correspondences, as well as mAP@10, R@1, R@5, and R@10 for original caption–audio pairs. Distilled models and their ensemble demonstrate the performance gains from architectural diversity and teacher-student training.

	Clotho Only						All Datasets					
	Improved Captions		Original Captions				Improved Captions		Original Captions			
	mAP@16	mAP@10	mAP@10	R@1	R@5	R@10	mAP@16	mAP@10	mAP@10	R@1	R@5	R@10
Dual Encoder	34.943	32.532	30.413	18.756	45.876	60.268	42.324	39.664	37.389	24.976	54.086	68.172
Sentence-level Attention	35.151	32.730	29.431	18.086	44.708	58.947	42.434	39.827	35.769	23.655	52.766	66.258
Token-level Attention	35.195	32.931	29.582	18.201	45.378	59.273	41.375	38.908	35.770	23.828	52.057	65.742
<i>Knowledge Distillation</i>												
Dual Encoder ¹	34.354	32.119	29.918	18.220	45.378	59.273	44.203	41.662	38.293	25.263	56.000	69.282
Sentence-level ²	33.042	31.009	28.816	17.952	43.254	57.627	43.926	41.332	37.495	24.784	54.947	68.650
Token-level ³	33.000	31.034	28.722	17.589	43.502	57.914	42.457	40.061	37.901	25.818	54.43	67.617
Ensemble ^{1,2,3}	35.304	33.161	30.758	19.254	45.856	60.785	46.864	44.176	40.423	27.732	58.201	71.732

Table 2: Retrieval performance (mAP@16 and mAP@10) for the two attention architectures presented on this paper trained with both the text and audio encoders frozen. The models are only trained on the Clotho dataset and evaluated on the improved captions.

Model Architecture	mAP@16	mAP@10
Sentence-level Attention	23.732	21.901
Token-level Attention	26.130	24.184

particularly in terms of early precision (R@1), they demonstrate that our approach remains competitive, especially considering that it relies on a single audio encoder (PaSST) across all models and does not leverage multiple specialized backbones.

Although our system does not surpass the 2024 SOTA in raw performance, it achieves strong results without relying on encoder heterogeneity or handcrafted ensemble tuning.

5.2. Importance of Encoder Fine-Tuning

A central design consideration in multimodal retrieval is whether fine-tuning large pretrained encoders is necessary, or whether task performance can be achieved by training only the cross-modal interaction layers. This question is particularly relevant for our attention-based architectures, which preserve distinct embedding spaces for audio and text. One might hypothesize that the attention mechanism alone could serve as a sufficient alignment module.

To test this hypothesis, we conducted experiments where the audio and text encoders (PaSST and RoBERTa) were frozen, and only the projection and attention layers were trained. The results, summarized in Table 2, show a consistent and significant drop in retrieval performance across all architectures when fine-tuning is disabled.

These findings suggest that while attention mechanisms do enable cross-modal interaction, they are not sufficient on their own to fully bridge the modality gap, especially when the encoders remain fixed to their pretraining objectives. Fine-tuning allows the encoders to adapt their representations to the retrieval task and dataset characteristics, resulting in more semantically aligned embeddings and better overall performance.

5.3. Pairwise Ensemble Analysis

To further investigate the individual contributions of each model architecture within the ensemble, we conducted an ablation study by evaluating all possible pairwise combinations of the three systems. Specifically, we assessed the performance of the following two-model ensembles: Dual Encoder + Sentence-level Attention, Dual Encoder + Token-level Attention, and Sentence-level Attention + Token-level Attention. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Retrieval performance (mAP@16 and mAP@10) for pairwise model ensembles using improved caption correspondences. All models are trained on the combined dataset.

Model Ensemble	mAP@16	mAP@10
Dual Encoder + Sentence-level Attention	46.521	43.894
Dual Encoder + Token-level Attention	46.005	43.323
Sentence-level + Token-level Attention	44.872	42.270

This analysis revealed that the combination of the Dual Encoder and Sentence-level Attention models consistently achieved the highest retrieval performance among the pairwise configurations. This suggests that these two architectures capture highly complementary cross-modal features, likely owing to their distinct alignment mechanisms. These findings are consistent with our embedding space visualizations in 4, which indicate that the Dual Encoder produces a more intermixed embedding space, whereas the Sentence-level Attention model preserves stronger modality-specific structures.

The ensemble composed solely of the Sentence-level and Token-level Attention models yielded smaller gains compared to individual performance. This outcome suggests a degree of representational redundancy, potentially due to the shared attention-based architecture and similar alignment strategies. Overall, these pairwise ensemble results support our central hypothesis: architectural heterogeneity, particularly combining models with fundamentally different cross-modal interaction paradigms, plays a critical role in enhancing retrieval accuracy through ensembling.

6. CONCLUSION

This work explored a set of cross-modal architectures for language-based audio retrieval, including a standard dual-encoder model and two attention-based variants. All models were built using a common set of backbone encoders (PaSST and RoBERTa) and trained with contrastive learning on a diverse collection of captioned audio datasets.

While none of the individual models outperform the current state-of-the-art, they each demonstrated competitive performance. Importantly, combining them in an ensemble led to consistent performance improvements, suggesting that the models capture complementary aspects of the retrieval task. Pairwise ensemble analysis supported this interpretation, with the most notable gains observed when combining the Dual Encoder with the Sentence-level Attention model.

Our results also emphasized the necessity of fine-tuning the pretrained encoders, as freezing them during training significantly reduced retrieval accuracy across all model types.

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Sound Event Classification meets Data Assimilation with Distributed Fiber-Optic Sensing

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Abstract—Distributed Fiber-Optic Sensing (DFOS) is a promising technique for large-scale acoustic monitoring. However, its wide variation in installation environments and sensor characteristics causes spatial heterogeneity. This heterogeneity makes it difficult to collect representative training data. It also degrades the generalization ability of learning-based models, such as fine-tuning methods, under a limited amount of training data. To address this, we formulate Sound Event Classification (SEC) as “data assimilation” in an embedding space. Instead of training models, we infer sound event classes by combining pretrained audio embeddings with simulated DFOS signals. Simulated DFOS signals are generated by applying various frequency responses and noise patterns to microphone data, which allows for diverse prior modeling of DFOS conditions. Our method achieves out-of-domain (OOD) robust classification without requiring model training. The proposed method achieved accuracy improvements of 6.42, 14.11, and 3.47 percentage points compared with conventional zero-shot and two types of fine-tune methods, respectively. By employing the simulator in the framework of data assimilation, the proposed method also enables precise estimation of physical parameters from observed DFOS signals.

Index Terms—sound event classification, distributed fiber-optic sensing, data assimilation

1. INTRODUCTION

Distributed fiber-optic sensing (DFOS), also known as coherent optical time-domain reflectometry (C-OTDR) or ϕ -OTDR [1], [2], is an emerging sensing technique that enables the detection of sound and vibration signals using standard optical fibers. A key advantage of DFOS is its ability to monitor large-scale environments with fine spatial resolution. This results in densely sampled multichannel data over long distances. Such large-scale and high-resolution sensing capabilities have led to a wide range of applications, including whale call detection in the ocean [3], traffic monitoring [4], seismic activity observation [5], sound event recognition [6], long-range monitoring over distances exceeding 100 km [7], [8], and utility pole localization in urban areas [9]. These examples demonstrate the versatility of DFOS as a distributed acoustic sensing platform and its potential for diverse sound analysis tasks.

Sound Event Classification (SEC) [10], [11] is a task of recognizing sound event classes, e.g., “dog,” “car,” and “people speaking” from audio. In sound event classification, most studies have explored deep-neural-network (DNN)-based classification with microphone [10], [12], [13]. With large-scale monitoring enabled by DFOS, applications for sound event classification are expected to become even more active.

The domain gap between microphone and DFOS signals is a major challenge in implementing DFOS-driven SEC [6]. While transfer learning or fine-tuning microphone-pretrained models on DFOS data can improve performance, these methods are inherently limited by the large diversity within the DFOS domain itself. DFOS systems vary widely in both their installation environments, such as underwater, underground, and overhead locations, and in their sensor characteristics, such as frequency response and optical noise sensitivity. The combination of environmental diversity and variability in sensor properties creates a large number of possible sensing conditions, many of which are not covered during training. As a result, even when a model is adapted to a specific DFOS setup, it may not generalize

Fig. 1: Concept of proposed SEC with data assimilation

to other scenarios. Since any learning-based method optimizes its parameters based on the training distribution, it tends to perform poorly when applied to different inference conditions. This makes it especially difficult to ensure robust generalization in practice, particularly when collecting labeled DFOS data for every condition is unrealistic.

To address the limitations of training-based adaptation under domain mismatch, we reformulate SEC as “data assimilation” in an embedding space, as shown in figure 1. Instead of updating model parameters, our method estimates the most plausible class by combining pretrained audio representations with simulated or observed DFOS signals. We simulate DFOS responses across diverse scenarios to account for spatial heterogeneity and map them to the same embedding space using a pretrained audio encoder. At inference time, we identify the optimal class by considering posteriors of observed and simulated DFOS signals in the shared embedding space, without retraining or fine-tuning. This approach enables domain-robust classification, even under severe data scarcity and heterogeneous sensing conditions.

2. PRELIMINARIES

2.1. Principle of DFOS

In DFOS, the phase of the backscattered light generated at every location along the fiber cable is observed:

$$\Delta\Phi = [\Delta\Phi_1, \dots, \Delta\Phi_c, \dots, \Delta\Phi_C] \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times T} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\Phi_c = [\Delta\phi_{c,1}, \dots, \Delta\phi_{c,t}, \dots, \Delta\phi_{c,T}]^\top$ indicates a waveform signal at location c . C and T denote the number of the observed locations, i.e., channels, along the fiber and the total duration. Given a local acoustic pressure $\epsilon_{x,t}$ at position x along the fiber cable and time t , $\Delta\phi_{c,t}$ is approximated as follows:

$$\Delta\phi_{c,t} \propto \underbrace{\int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \epsilon_{x,t} dx}_{\text{low-pass filter}} \quad (2)$$

$L \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is known as gauge length, which is a hyperparameter of DFOS systems. The point is that $\Delta\phi_{c,t}$ is proportional to the summation of the local acoustic pressure at time t and within position c to $c + L$. In other words, Eq. 2 is regarded as a directional moving average filter [14] which is one of the low-pass filters.

Fig. 2: Overview of proposed SEC with data assimilation

Given a frequency response and noise, the DFOS waveform $\Delta\Phi_c$ at channel c is also expressed as:

$$\Delta\tilde{\Phi}_c = \Delta\Phi_c * \mathcal{H}_c + \mathbf{n}_c, \quad (3)$$

where $*$ denotes convolution, and \mathcal{H}_c and \mathbf{n}_c represent the frequency response and additive noise at channel c , respectively. These channel-dependent characteristics arise from the effect of Eq. 2 and diverse installation environments such as seabeds, underground, and aerial deployments. Moreover, \mathbf{n}_c has an effect on optical noise, which follows a Gaussian distribution. Due to the large number of channels C , there exist many combinations of \mathcal{H}_c and \mathbf{n}_c . It is impractical to collect all these variations for statistical modeling. This spatial heterogeneity leads to a significant domain gap between training and testing. As a result, model adaptation, such as finetuning, becomes difficult, particularly when the amount of training data is limited.

2.2. Data assimilation

Data assimilation is a technique for improving predictions, including physical parameters, by combining simulation with new observations. It has been applied in fields such as weather forecasting [15], [16] and traffic monitoring [4], where simulation-based predictions are adjusted using observations. By leveraging simulation-based priors, data assimilation offers robustness even under out-of-domain conditions, where real observations deviate from training or modeling assumptions. Data assimilation is especially useful when the available data are limited, noisy, or differ from the conditions assumed in the model.

In data assimilation, the errors of simulations and observations are minimized to obtain estimations from a simulator and its physical parameters. Let $\mathbf{z}_b \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be the background (prior) state estimate, and $\mathbf{z}_o \in \mathbb{R}^m$ be the observation vector. The observation operator $\mathcal{H} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ maps the state space to the observation space. Let $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ be the background error covariance matrix and $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ be the observation error covariance matrix. The widely used 3D-Var cost function [15], [17], [18], which is the core expression of data assimilation, is defined as:

$$J(\mathbf{z}) = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{z}_b)^T \mathbf{B}^{-1} (\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{z}_b)}_{\text{simulation error}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} (\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{z}) - \mathbf{z}_o)^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} (\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{z}) - \mathbf{z}_o)}_{\text{observation error}}. \quad (4)$$

The optimal analysis state \mathbf{z} , which is the physics parameters, is obtained by minimizing the cost function:

$$\mathbf{z} \leftarrow \arg \min_{\mathbf{z}} J(\mathbf{z}). \quad (5)$$

3. PROPOSED METHOD: DATA ASSIMILATION-BASED INFERENCE FOR DFOS

We treat SEC as a data assimilation problem to address the spatial heterogeneity in the DFOS-based SEC with a limited amount of real DFOS training data. Instead of training a model using DFOS data, we estimate the sound event class by comparing pretrained audio embeddings with observed or simulated DFOS signals. This approach allows out-of-domain (OOD) robust classification without retraining and estimates physical parameters using a simulator as a white-box approach.

3.1. Formulation of data Assimilation in embedding space

We formulate data assimilation in an embedding space where both simulation and observed signals are mapped through a pretrained model f . By sharing embedding space for both the simulation and observed signals, we can assume that the observation operator \mathcal{H} is the identity function. Furthermore, assuming decorrelation of the embedding vectors, we approximate the error covariances \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{R} with identity matrices. Under these assumptions, the cost function Eq. 4 of the data assimilation simplifies to:

$$J(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{z}_b\|_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{z}_o\|_2^2. \quad (6)$$

In our method, we employ k nearest neighbor (k NN) model in an embedding space to obtain the optimal state of \mathbf{z} .

3.2. Simulated DFOS in embedding space

To implement data assimilation of SEC under the concept of Eq. 6, we generate a simulation dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{simDFOS}}$, which is a set of key-value pairs with physics parameters \mathbf{z} , by applying various DFOS transfer functions, i.e., various low-pass filters [14] and noise, to microphone-domain audio x_i .

$$(\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{Z}) = \{(f_{\text{mic}}(x_i^{(\text{sim})}), y_i, \mathbf{z}_b^{(i)}) \mid (x_i^{(\text{sim})}, y_i, \mathbf{z}_b^{(i)}) \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{simDFOS}}\}, \quad (7)$$

where $x_i^{(\text{sim})}$ denotes the simulated DFOS signal of class y_i . $f_{\text{mic}} : \mathbb{R}^T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D$ denote a pretrained audio encoder that maps a T -dimensional waveform to a D -dimensional feature vector. For the simulation of DFOS signals, we consider the cutoff frequency r of low-pass filters and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) l of Gaussian noise as in Eqs. 2 and 3: $\mathbf{z}_b^{(i)} = [r_i, l_i]$.

3.3. Posterior estimation utilizing data assimilation

In inference stages, given a query, i.e., an audio embedding $f_{\text{mic}}(x^{(\text{test})})$ of a tested DFOS waveform $x^{(\text{test})}$, the k NN-based model retrieves k nearest neighbor key-value pairs of the simulation

Fig. 4: Similarity in frequency response between DFOS & microphone

set $\mathcal{D}_{\text{simDFOS}}$. Given the set of k nearest neighbor key-value pairs \mathcal{N} , the simulation probability is

$$p_{\text{sim}}(y|x) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}|} \sum_{(k_i, v_i) \in \mathcal{N}} \mathbb{1}_{y=v_i} \exp\left(-d(k_i, f_{\text{mic}}(x^{(\text{test})}))\right), \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{y=v_i}$ denotes an indicator function that takes one when i -th value v_i is equal to an estimated event label y ; otherwise zero. $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ indicates a distance function, which is squared L^2 distance in our work.

In parallel, we obtain the classifier-based prediction as observation probability using only microphone-domain models:

$$p_{\text{obs}}(y|x) = \text{softmax}\left(f_{\text{clf}}\left(f_{\text{mic}}\left(x^{(\text{test})}\right)\right)\right)_y, \quad (9)$$

where $f_{\text{clf}} : \mathbb{R}^D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^E$ is a pretrained classifier that maps the embedding to E -dimensional logits over event classes. $\text{softmax}(\cdot)$ indicates the softmax function over sound event classes, and then the subscript y selects the probability for class y .

Finally, as a solution of Eq. 6, we interpolate the probability $p_{\text{sim}}(y|x)$ with the output of the observation probability $p_{\text{obs}}(y|x)$ to obtain the final prediction:

$$p(y|x) = \alpha p_{\text{obs}}(y|x) + (1 - \alpha) p_{\text{sim}}(y|x), \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ balances the observation- and simulation-based priors. This formulation enables OOD robust inference under spatially diverse DFOS conditions without requiring model adaptation or retraining.

3.4. Estimation of physical parameters via data assimilation

The physical parameters $\mathbf{z} = [r, l]$, which are the lowcut frequency r of the low-pass filters and SNR l of gaussian noise, are also estimated based on data assimilation using k nearest neighbor set \mathcal{N} of Eq. 8:

$$r \leftarrow \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}|} \sum_{\mathbf{z}_b^{(i)} \in \mathcal{N}} \text{proj}_r(\mathbf{z}_b^{(i)}), \quad l \leftarrow \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}|} \sum_{\mathbf{z}_b^{(i)} \in \mathcal{N}} \text{proj}_l(\mathbf{z}_b^{(i)}), \quad (11)$$

where $\text{proj}_r(\cdot)$ and $\text{proj}_l(\cdot)$ represent an operator of extracting an element r and l of vector, respectively.

4. EXPERIMENTS

4.1. Experimental conditions

Recording: To validate the proposed method, we first conduct a recording of DFOS data. As shown in Fig. 3, the optical fiber is embedded into a mat. The figure’s left and right sides depict the real picture and its illustration, respectively. The size of the mat is 1.2 m \times 1.2 m. Sound source signals were played using a speaker and then omnidirectionally propagated to the optical fiber of the mat. The

Fig. 3: Installation of optical fiber

straight-line distance between the edge of the mat and the speaker is about 2.8 m. We then obtained 50 channels from the DFOS data of the mat. For the sound sources, we used the ESC-50 dataset [10], which is comprised of 2,000 audio clips. The sampling frequency of DFOS is 20 kHz. Gauge length L is set to 4 m. Figure 4 shows the similarity in the frequency domain between original dry sources (ESC-50) and recorded DFOS data. Cosine similarity was used for the similarity.

Simulation procedure of DFOS: DFOS exhibits lower sensitivity at higher frequencies [14], [19] and considerable variability across different sensing locations. Based on those works, we simulated DFOS data from the ESC-50 dataset [10] with low-pass filters and Gaussian noise to reproduce Eq. 3. For the low-pass filters, we used 4th-order Butterworth low-pass filters with cutoff frequencies $r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$ kHz. Gaussian noise is then added to the low-pass waveform of ESC-50 with SNR $l \in \{-5, -10, -15\}$ dB. We finally generated 42,000 simulated DFOS waveforms from the ESC-50 dataset. The generated data was used for $\mathcal{D}_{\text{simDFOS}}$ and in a manner of cross-validation.

Evaluation setting: We conducted a five-fold cross-validation following [10] with the real DFOS dataset. As shown in figure 4, DFOS data has the spatial heterogeneity. As $f_{\text{mic}}(x)$, we used hierarchical token semantic audio Transformer (HTS-AT) [20] from Contrastive language-audio pretraining [21], referred to as “MS-CLAP.” For MS-CLAP, the sound events of ESC-50 are classified by prompts “this is the sound of [class label],” in accordance with [22] using generative pretrained Transformer 2 (GPT2) [23] as $f_{\text{cls}}(x)$. For kNN, k was set to 50 tuned using the folds of the training. For comparison, we used the following methods.

- Zero-shot: zero-shot classification based on MS-CLAP was used.
- Fine-tune: linear probe [24] was used, referred to as “fine-tune.” In the linear probe, HTS-AT with fully connected layers was trained using Adam optimizer [25].

4.2. Experimental results

4.2.1. Spatial heterogeneity: We explore the classification performance under the spatial heterogeneity in DFOS. For clarity, we set

Table 1: Accuracy [%] of channels $c = 25 - 50$ for condition of spatial heterogeneity

Method	Types of data for training		α	DFOS channels of observed data used for finetuning pretrained model											
				Out-of-domain (0–20)					In-domain (20–50)						
	Observed	Simulated		0–5	5–10	10–15	15–20	Avr.	20–25	25–30	30–35	35–40	40–45	45–50	Avr.
Zero-shot	No training		1.0	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33	18.33
Fine-tune	✓	✓	–	3.11	9.71	4.85	24.90	10.64	58.30	49.94	63.18	64.10	59.80	56.59	58.65
Proposed	No training		0.0	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75	24.75

 Fig. 5: Impact of real DFOS samples \mathcal{D}_{DFOS} and α

$\alpha = 0.0$ in Eq. 10 of the proposed method to verify the effectiveness of the simulation set. As shown in figure 4, DFOS data has a large diversity in the frequency response of DFOS compared with that of the microphone. This spatial heterogeneity is caused by a directional filter and optical noise of Eqs. 2 and 3. As can be seen in the figure, the 20th channel and after have high similarities between DFOS and the microphone; otherwise, there are low similarities. In this experiment, we divide the DFOS channels into two sections, before and after the 20th, to verify their performance under the condition of spatial heterogeneity.

Table 1 shows the accuracy of classifying events where channels $c = 25 - 50$ were used for the inference. For the fine-tuning method, we used two types of data: observed and simulated data. The observed data means the real DFOS data captured by the fiber mat in Fig. 3. The result indicates that the proposed method outperforms the conventional methods in terms of average accuracy under $c = 0 - 20$; OOD section. The proposed method improved the classification performance by 6.42, 14.11, and 3.47 percentage points in terms of average accuracy compared with the zero-shot and fine-tune methods with the observed or simulated DFOS data.

The proposed method achieves significantly better performance than the conventional methods for each channel of $c = 0 - 15$. In particular, the proposed method with $\mathcal{D}_{simDFOS}$ improved the accuracy by 21.64 percentage points compared with the fine-tuning methods. On the other hand, the performance of the conventional fine-tuning method gets drastically worse. This is because the lower-SNR DFOS data cause the fine-tuning method to catastrophically forget the acoustic features of the pretrained model.

For $c = 20 - 50$, the conventional fine-tuning method with the observed DFOS data outperformed the other methods, including the proposed methods. Since there is a small gap between the tested and trained channels compared with those of $c = 0 - 20$, the fine-tuning method with the observed DFOS data works well.

4.2.2. Impact of number of real samples and α in data assimilation: In this experiment, we relaxed the constraint by using actual DFOS data for the proposed data assimilation SEC. Specifically, we add a real DFOS dataset \mathcal{D}_{DFOS} , which is used for the fine-tune methods, into the simulated DFOS dataset $\mathcal{D}_{simDFOS}$. The real DFOS dataset \mathcal{D}_{DFOS} was constructed using the same procedure as $\mathcal{D}_{simDFOS}$.

Fig. 6: Similarities with tested real DFOS data

Figure 5 shows the all-channel-averaged accuracy with changing \mathcal{D}_{DFOS} and α . The result shows that the accuracy of the proposed method with $\alpha = 0.2 - 1.0$ is significantly lower than that of $\alpha = 0.0$. This indicates that the large-scale models trained by the microphone are helpful for encoding audio not observed by the microphone, even though there is a large gap between DFOS and the microphone. When $\alpha = 0.0$, we found that increasing the size of \mathcal{D}_{DFOS} leads to improved performance, achieving high accuracy even with a small number of samples.

4.2.3. Estimation of physical parameters: Figure 6 shows the performance of estimating the physical parameters \mathbf{z} with Eq. 11. In the figure, the green line depicts the average of the cosine similarities in the embedding space of MS-CLAP between tested DFOS signals and reproduced DFOS signals. The reproduced DFOS signals were generated from the original microphone signal of the ESC-50 dataset with the estimated physical parameters $\mathbf{z} = [r, l]$. The orange dashed line represents the average cosine similarity in the MS-CLAP embedding space between the tested DFOS signals and the original microphone signals from the ESC-50 dataset. The blue dotted line shows the average similarity between the tested DFOS signals and the simulated DFOS signals. The result shows that the similarities between the tested DFOS signals and the reproduced DFOS signals are higher than those of the other methods. In other words, the proposed data-assimilation-based SEC precisely estimates the physical parameters $\mathbf{z} = [r, l]$. The result indicates that the proposed method estimates the optimal physical parameters by interpolating the prior physical parameters \mathbf{z}_b of the simulation.

5. CONCLUSION

We addressed the challenge of the spatial heterogeneity in the DFOS-based SEC under a limited amount of real DFOS training data. Our method formulates inference as data assimilation in the embedding space, combining pretrained audio features with simulated DFOS signals, and avoids model retraining. The proposed method achieved accuracy improvements of 6.42, 14.11, and 3.47 percentage points compared with zero-shot and two fine-tune methods. The proposed data-assimilation-based SEC also precisely estimates the physical parameters of a tested DFOS signal compared to the simulated DFOS signals.

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Synthetic data enables context-aware bioacoustic sound event detection

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Abstract—We propose a methodology for training foundation models that enhances their in-context learning capabilities within the domain of bioacoustic signal processing. We use synthetically generated training data, introducing a domain-randomization-based pipeline that constructs diverse acoustic scenes with temporally strong labels. We generate over 8.8 thousand hours of strongly-labeled audio and train a query-by-example, transformer-based model to perform few-shot bioacoustic sound event detection. Our second contribution is a public benchmark of 13 diverse few-shot bioacoustics tasks. Our model outperforms previously published methods, and improves relative to other training-free methods by 64%. We demonstrate that this is due to increase in model size and data scale, as well as algorithmic improvements. We make our trained model available via an API, to provide ecologists and ethologists with a training-free tool for bioacoustic sound event detection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Foundation models can learn new tasks at inference time from a few labeled examples—a process known as few-shot or in-context learning (ICL) [1]. This is attractive for application-driven ML domains—like bioacoustics, ecology, and conservation—where domain experts often lack ML experience and large labeled datasets [2], [3]. Despite growing interest in adapting foundation models for these fields, data scarcity limits the tasks they can be trained to perform [3].

An example of this situation occurs in few-shot bioacoustic sound event detection (FSBSED), which attempts to provide flexible modeling for the diversity of problems that arise in bioacoustics. In this task, formalized in [4], a model receives a *support set*: an audio recording with onset and offset annotations for the first few events of interest. The model must predict onsets and offsets of these events in the *query set*, which is the remainder of the recording.

Temporally fine-scale detection is crucial for many applications in animal behavior and ecology [5], but the time and expertise needed to annotate bioacoustic events has resulted in a lack of data available for training models capable of FSBSED. Prior efforts for FSBSED largely rely on a single 22-hour training dataset described in [4], leading to lightweight models tailored to small-scale data.

In this work, we investigate simultaneously scaling model parameters and training data volume, for a FSBSED model tailored for ICL (Figure 1). To overcome limited annotated data, we turn to synthetic data, transforming raw audio into strongly labeled scenes via custom preprocessing and augmentations that introduce domain randomization. Because our focus is ICL, we use a transformer-based few-shot model that attends to support and query audio jointly—common in ICL but rare in FSBSED. We call our method DRASDIC: *Domain Randomization for Animal Sound Detection In-Context*.

To evaluate performance, we introduce a new 13-dataset FSBSED benchmark, FASD13 (*Fewshot Animal Sound Detection-13*). DRASDIC achieves a 64% average improvement over prior methods that also do not use gradient updates at inference. Ablations show improvements are due to simultaneously scaling model size, training data, and improving the few-shot mechanism. We release DRASDIC weights, inference API, and FASD13 benchmark.¹

¹Available at www.github.com/earthspecies/drasdic_api.

Fig. 1: We introduce a method for generating synthetic acoustic scenes (Left) and a SotA few-shot detection model (Right).

2. RELATED WORK

FSBSED was introduced in [4]. Challenges include sparse vocalizations, diverse target sounds, dynamic environments, and domain generalization [6]. Published methods include prototypical networks [7], representation learning [8], and transductive inference [9]. Prior evaluation of FSBSED systems has centered around the DCASE challenge [6], which provided public training and validation datasets and used a private test set. Subsequent efforts have either used the public validation set for both model selection and model evaluation [6], or skipped model selection [8].

In-context learning (ICL) refers to a model’s ability to perform a task specified through demonstrations at inference time [1]. ICL has also been extended to fine-scale tasks in computer vision that somewhat resemble FSBSED, which include semantic segmentation [10], [11] and scene understanding [12]. Similar to our method, [11] employ a simple encoder-based architecture.

Generative vision and audio models have been used to create data for few-shot and low-resource tasks including detection [13]. We are not aware of a generative audio model that produces realistic and low-SNR animal sounds, and so instead developed a preprocessing pipeline to isolate potential animal sounds in publicly available data. A similar procedure was developed recently in [14] for low-resource bioacoustic classification. For sound event detection in general audio, synthetic scenes assembled from multiple clips have been used to train models with fixed [15] and open ontologies [16].

3. METHOD

3.1. Data Generation

We propose a two-stage approach to generate scenes (Figure 2). From publicly available unlabeled audio, we derive a set of background

Fig. 2: Summary of training data preprocessing and scene generation.

tracks (5.1e5 tracks, 5540 hours) and a set of short clips containing events dubbed pseudo-vocalizations (*pseudovox*) (5.4e6 events, 577 hours); these are often animal vocalizations but may include non-biological acoustic events. These are pseudo-labeled through clustering, so multiple similar-sounding pseudovox can be sampled together.

In the second stage, performed on-the-fly during training, clips are randomly sampled from these collections, manipulated with data augmentations, and combined into scenes. Generated scenes may not always resemble real audio, due to randomness in the scene generation process. As prior work has shown that domain randomization in synthetic data generation improves transfer to real data [17], we view this as a way of increasing test-time robustness of our method.

3.1.1. Preprocessing: To construct our pseudovox set, we used public recordings from iNaturalist, Animal Sound Archive, xeno-canto², as well as Watkins [18], and WavCaps [19]. To remove background noise, we separated each recording into four stems using BirdMixIT [20]. For each stem, we isolated potential pseudovox: segments where the amplitude envelope exceeded 25% of the recording’s maximum, indicating a possible acoustic event. Many segments still lacked a clear acoustic event, so we performed a quality filtering step. We manually annotated a subset of segments for vocalization presence, then trained a binary linear classifier on the final layer BirdNET [21] activations for each segment. We applied this quality filter; passing segments became the final pseudovox set. This procedure resulted in $M = 5.4e6$ pseudovox. Based on performance on a held-out test set, we estimated that 98% of these pseudovox contained a clear acoustic event. To obtain pseudolabels for the pseudovox, we applied k -means clustering to their BirdNET activations. We did this for $k \in K = \{\lfloor M/128 \rfloor, \lfloor M/64 \rfloor, \lfloor M/32 \rfloor, \lfloor M/16 \rfloor, \lfloor M/8 \rfloor\}$, to obtain different levels of cluster homogeneity. We inspected a random sample of 100 clusters, rating clusters as high- or low-quality based on acoustic homogeneity. Of these, 99 were deemed high quality. For background audio, we took the raw audio above, along with audio from SilentCities [22], DeepShip [23], and SanctSound [24].

3.1.2. Scene Generation: Scene generation consists of three parts: sampling audio clips, manipulating them with data augmentations, and combining them to form a scene. In Section 5.4, we investigate how the randomness in this process influences model performance.

We first sample two background tracks which are overlaid on each other. We choose a clustering level $k \in K$ and two clusters c_T, c_D from the clusters of level k . We sample a random number of target pseudovox from c_T , and a random number of distractor pseudovox from c_D . We apply reverb (drawn from [25]), resampling, time

flipping, and amplitude augmentations to pseudovox, and resampling augmentations to background tracks. We paste pseudovox into the background track, one-by-one, with a random time gap between pseudovox. We maintain a binary annotation mask for the scene. This mask is initialized with zeros, and changed to ones where target pseudovox are added. Distractor pseudovox do not change the mask; they join whatever sounds are already present in the background tracks. To generate one training example, two scenes (support and query) are generated, drawing pseudovox from the same c_T, c_D for both. With some probability, the background tracks of the query are chosen to be different than those of the support.

3.2. Model

Using our synthetic scenes, we train our model DRASDIC. During training the model is given annotated support audio and unannotated query audio, and must predict detection labels for the query audio.

3.2.1. Architecture: Noting that encoder-only architectures have been used successfully for fine-scale ICL problems in computer vision [11], we adopt a simple but highly parametrized BERT-like architecture which applies attention to support and query simultaneously. This is preceded by a CNN spectrogram encoder.

Support and query audio are resampled to 16 kHz, concatenated, and converted to a log mel-spectrogram (256 mels, hop size 160). The CNN encoder is a 2-d convolutional block and two 2-d residual blocks (ker=7, 3, 3, respectively; hidden size 64), with vertical mean pooling (ker=2) after each. Frequency and hidden dimensions are flattened and mean-pooled to a final 50 Hz frame rate. The binary support label mask is max-pooled to 50 Hz, passed to a per-frame label embedding, and added to the encoded audio. This label-enriched representation enters a transformer encoder (hidden size 768, 12 heads, 12 blocks) with rotary position encoding [26]. A final linear layer maps each frame to detection logits.

3.2.2. Training: DRASDIC was randomly initialized and trained with per-frame binary cross-entropy loss on the query labels, using AdamW [27] with $(\beta_0, \beta_1) = (0.9, 0.999)$ and weight decay 0.01. We used support-query pairs of total duration $\text{dur}_s + \text{dur}_q$ seconds. Based on initial experiments, we set $\text{dur}_s = 30$ and $\text{dur}_q = 10$.

Model, data generation, and training hyperparameters were chosen through random search. As our model selection criterion, we used average performance on the validation datasets from [6]. We applied curriculum learning to gradually increase task difficulty during training. This linearly decays the minimum pseudovox signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) from 0 dB to a minimum of -20 dB for an initial 5e4 steps. The learning rate is linearly increased for 1e4 steps to a maximum of $2e-5$, and then decayed to 0 after 1e5 steps (cosine schedule) using batch size of 8. Parameters governing data generation are provided in the GitHub repository.

4. PUBLIC BENCHMARK

A collection of public FSBSED datasets was previously provided in [4], [6], but were designated as datasets for model training and validation. We complement these with FASD13, a public benchmark curated for model evaluation (Table 1). FASD13 consists of 13 bioacoustics datasets, each of which includes between 2 and 12 audio files. Eleven of these datasets were derived from previous studies; they were chosen for their taxonomic diversity, varied recording conditions, and quality of their annotations. Two (CC and JS) are presented here for the first time. All datasets were developed alongside studies of ecology or animal behavior, and represent a range of realistic problems encountered in bioacoustics data. Details of dataset collection and preprocessing steps are available at the GitHub repository.

²www.inaturalist.org/, www.museumfuernaturkunde.berlin/en/research/animal-sound-archive, www.xeno-canto.org, respectively

Table 1: Details of FASD13. Datasets were chosen for their taxonomic diversity, varied recording conditions, and quality of their annotations. They were manually subsetted (prior to evaluation), to reduce computational overhead. Other (minor) preprocessing steps are described on the project GitHub. Datasets with a † are presented for the first time here. Terrestrial and underwater autonomous passive acoustic monitoring devices are abbreviated T. PAM and U. PAM, respectively.

Dataset	Full Name	N files	Dur (hr)	N events	Recording type	Location	Taxa	Detection target
AS [28]	AnuraSet	12	0.20	162	T. PAM	Brazil	Anura	Species
CC†	Carrion Crow	10	10.00	2200	On-body	Spain	Corvus corone + Clamator glandarius	Species + Life Stage
GS [29]	Gunshot	7	38.33	85	T. PAM	Gabon	Homo sapiens	Production Mechanism
HA [30]	Hawaiian Birds	12	1.10	628	T. PAM	Hawaii, USA	Aves	Species
HG [31]	Hainan Gibbon	9	72.00	483	T. PAM	Hainan, China	Nomascus hainanus	Species
HW [32]	Humpback Whale	10	2.79	1565	U. PAM	North Pacific Ocean	Megaptera novaeangliae	Species
JS†	Jumping Spider	4	0.23	924	Substrate	Laboratory	Habronattus	Sound Type
KD [33]	Katydid	12	2.00	883	T. PAM	Panamá	Tettigoniidae	Species
MS [34], [35]	Marmoset	10	1.67	1369	Laboratory	Laboratory	Callithrix jacchus	Vocalization Type
PM [36]	Powdermill	4	6.42	2032	T. PAM	Pennsylvania, USA	Passeriformes	Species
RG [37]	Ruffed Grouse	2	1.50	34	T. PAM	Pennsylvania, USA	Bonasa umbellus	Species
RS [38]	Rana Sierrae	7	1.87	552	U. PAM	California, USA	Rana sierrae	Species
RW [39]	Right Whale	10	5.00	398	U. PAM	Gulf of St. Lawrence	Eubalaena glacialis	Species

We follow the data format in [4]: Each audio file comes with annotations of the onsets and offsets of *positive* sound events, i.e. sounds coming from a predetermined category (such as a species label or call type). An N -shot detection system is provided with the audio up through the N^{th} positive event, and must predict the onsets and offsets of positive events in the rest of the recording.

5. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We evaluate models based on their ability to detect events after the $N = 5^{\text{th}}$ positive event in each recording of FASD13, using F1@0.3 IoU as described in [4]. We used performance on the validation set from [6] to select a final model to evaluate on FASD13.

5.1. Inference

For DRASDIC, we form predictions by windowing the audio in each recording, making multiple predictions for each window by prompting the model multiple times, and averaging these predictions. In detail, for a fixed dur_q -second window of the query set, we prompt the model $N = 5$ times and average the frame-wise predictions produced by these five prompts. The support set for the i^{th} prompt ($i \in [1, 5]$) is the dur_s -seconds of support audio centered at the i^{th} positive event in the support set (together with the binary detection mask). This procedure is repeated for dur_q -second windows across the entire query set. Frames with predicted detection probability above a fixed threshold of 0.5 become positive detections. These are smoothed: detections separated by a gap of $\min(1, d/2)$ seconds are merged, and then detections lasting less than $\min(1/2, d/2)$ seconds are discarded. Here d is the duration of the shortest event in the support set.

5.2. Comparison methods

We compare DRASDIC with essentially all of the previously published methods we are aware of for FSBSED that contain publicly available implementations. The first, “BEATS+linear” is a simple supervised baseline which consists of a frozen BEATS encoder [40] and a final linear layer. Support audio is windowed (4 seconds, 50% overlap) and the final layer is trained for 100 epochs to predict binary per-frame detection labels (final frame rate: 50 Hz). Training minimizes average per-frame binary cross-entropy loss. The initial learning rate of 0.01 (tuned using the validation set) is decayed to 0 using a cosine schedule. The second “AVES+linear” replaces the BEATS encoder with the pre-trained AVES encoder [41] (BirdAVES Base checkpoint), which was pre-trained on 2570 hours of animal sounds. “Protonet” is the prototypical network from [6], which itself adapts [7]. “Transductive” [9] uses a CNN encoder that is updated using unlabeled audio from the query set. “SCL” applies the supervised contrastive

learning method introduced by [8]. “SCL+finetuning”, also introduced by [8] extends this by using support audio to fine-tune the encoder that was pre-trained using the SCL method.

For Protonet, SCL, and SCL+Finetuning, we train a version using the training data from [4]. We also train a version using our generated scenes (5e4 scenes, each 40 seconds), which represents a $25\times$ increase in data quantity over the data used for training the original models.

Fig. 3: Qualitative results; events are in yellow. DRASDIC detects target sounds in dynamic environments (top two), but challenges include extremely low SNR (third), and the extended low-frequency drumming displays of ruffed grouse (bottom). Each spectrogram represents 10 seconds of audio.

5.3. Experiments

We compare model performance on FASD13 (Table 2). Some datasets (JS, KD, MS, PB, PB24) contain events that are above DRASDIC’s 8kHz Nyquist frequency, or that are brief relative to the model’s 50Hz frame rate. For these, we give the model a 1/2-time version (1/6 for

Table 2: F1 scores @0.3 IoU on FASD13. Methods marked with † were pre-trained using our generated data, rather than the data used in the original publication. Methods marked with * involve no gradient updates at inference time. The second column gives the number of model parameters, and the final column gives the average F1 score across the six validation datasets from [6].

Model	Params	AS	CC	GS	HA	HG	HW	JS	KD	MS	PM	RG	RS	RW	Avg	Val
BEATS+linear	90M	.350	.003	.056	.093	.242	.173	.028	.049	.462	.212	.732	.007	.316	.209	.358
AVES+linear	90M	.586	.059	.500	.374	.207	.366	.026	.673	.831	.291	.529	.303	.494	.403	.565
Protonet*	0.7M	.356	.189	.156	.239	.038	.085	.136	.316	.590	.260	.000	.216	.393	.229	.461
Protonet†*	0.7M	.305	.224	.151	.307	.023	.116	.166	.418	.536	.235	.121	.195	.342	.242	.459
Transductive	0.5M	.299	.144	.002	.283	.020	.116	.279	.218	.569	.159	.089	.169	.048	.184	.242
SCL*	7.2M	.516	.333	.025	.438	.010	.255	.281	.263	.402	.237	.049	.219	.509	.272	.514
SCL+finetuning	7.2M	.565	.341	.017	.467	.008	.382	.302	.381	.476	.327	.042	.285	.275	.298	.525
SCL†*	7.2M	.545	.287	.024	.433	.008	.393	.243	.207	.429	.336	.038	.218	.228	.261	.440
SCL†+finetuning	7.2M	.571	.205	.030	.479	.005	.453	.132	.220	.516	.450	.050	.292	.223	.279	.453
DRASDIC †* (ours)	116M	.645	.272	.593	.587	.144	.337	.099	.644	.783	.474	.092	.352	.764	.445	.704

KD). We give other methods *both* the slowed and full-speed version of the data, and keep the version with the better score.

On FASD13, DRASDIC outperforms all the alternatives on 6 out of 13 datasets. Across datasets DRASDIC has an average F1 score of .042 over the next best model. Compared to other methods that do not require gradient updates at inference time, DRASDIC outperforms the others on 9 of 13 datasets, and has an average F1 score of .173 over the next best model (64% relative improvement). Qualitatively, DRASDIC detected diverse target sounds, even amid others in the same frequency bands (Figure 3, top). Performance is strong across a variety of taxa and conditions. A failure case is for the JS dataset, which consists of jumping spider drumming. Here, the detection targets are specific drum types, and distinguishing between drum types relies partly on the rate of drumming. Our scene generator did not account for this type of information. Other failure cases are in Figure 3, bottom.

For the comparison methods we trained with our generated data, there was no clear performance increase. These methods, which adopt a CNN architecture, employ a different few-shot mechanism than DRASDIC and also have fewer than 1/10 the trainable parameters. The relative impact of these differences is investigated in Section 5.4.

5.4. Ablation experiments

In our main experiments, we scaled model parameters and data volume, while also adopting a few-shot mechanism that applied attention to support and query audio simultaneously. We conducted experiments to investigate the contributions of these changes, individually (Table 3, top). First, we compared our main model (116.1M parameters), whose transformer encoder has the same structure as BERT Base, to smaller versions based on BERT Small [42] (19.3M parameters) and BERT Tiny (2.5M parameters). Second, we compared our main data generation procedure to one that only generated 220 hours of unique scenes, and one that only generated 22 hours of unique scenes. Additionally, we compared to a version that used the non-synthetic training data (22 hours total) from [4], as well as a version for which 10% of the training examples were from [4] and the other 90% synthetic. Finally, we adjusted our few-shot mechanism to a prototypical network, which prevented attention from being applied to support and query audio simultaneously. For this, we kept the same architecture as our main method but applied a prototypical loss as in [6], [7]. Average performance on FASD13 and on the validation set dropped in all cases, indicating that each of these changes contributed to final model performance. Reducing data scale was especially damaging, likely due to the high number of trainable parameters in our main method.

We investigated the impacts of adjusting the randomness governing our scene generation procedure (Table 3, bottom). We perturbed the

Table 3: Average F1 scores @0.3 IoU on FASD13 and validation [6] datasets. Model ablations appear on top, data ablations on bottom.

Method	Avg (test)	Avg (val)
DRASDIC	.445	.704
BERT Small	.425	.666
BERT Tiny	.323	.521
Reduced data (220 h)	.354	.504
Reduced data (22 h)	.130	.088
Non-synthetic data (22 h)	.135	.165
10% non-synthetic data	.428	.666
Protonet loss	.444	.638
High homogeneity in events	.429	.630
Low homogeneity in events	.444	.606
High events / second	.381	.437
Low events / second	.370	.669
Only high SNR events	.402	.620
Only low SNR events	.438	.682
No pitch/time shifting	.457	.613

level of homogeneity of target events in a scene, the typical rate of events, the loudness of events, and whether we apply pitch shifting augmentations. Average performance is stable across some of these perturbations, but decreases when the randomness in event rate and event SNR is decreased. These parameters likely influence the level of diversity present across generated scenes more than the others.

Eliminating random pitch shifts resulted in slightly better performance on FASD13. Designing a domain randomization strategy is an optimization problem, which we approached through a model selection criterion. This criterion did not produce the best model on the test set, aligning with the observation [6] that strong domain shifts between few-shot tasks present a challenge for FSBSSED model development.

CONCLUSION

To provide a training-free solution for fine-scale bioacoustic sound event detection, we develop a ICL transformer model DRASDIC. We develop a domain-randomization based data-generation pipeline, and train our model on over 8.8 thousand hours of synthetic acoustic scenes. We additionally provide FASD13, a new benchmark for few-shot bioacoustic sound event detection. Our model substantially improves upon previous state-of-the art. We demonstrate that these improvements are due to both our modeling approach and the data scale provided by our scene generation method.

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Enhancing Multiscale Features for Efficient Acoustic Scene Classification with One-Dimensional Separate CNN

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Abstract—Acoustic Scene Classification (ASC) is a fundamental task in audio signal processing, aiming to classify the location of an environmental audio recording. Recent advances focus on improving ASC model efficiency, particularly in resource-constrained environments. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) remain the dominant approach due to their high performance, with recent focus on 1D kernels, such as in the Time-Frequency Separate Network (TF-SepNet), for reducing model complexity and computational cost. However, TF-SepNet performs feature extraction using a fixed receptive field in both time and frequency dimensions, which restricts its ability to capture multiscale contextual patterns. In this study, we investigate the integration of multiscale feature extraction modules into TF-SepNet, with the aim of improving model efficiency by balancing accuracy and complexity. We propose three architectures, TFSepDCD-Net, TFSepSPP-Net, and TFSepASPP-Net, each with two architectural variants based on TF-SepNet: one replaces its max pooling layers, and the other replaces its final convolutional layer. Each architecture has three configurations corresponding to different model sizes—small, medium, and large—to explore the tradeoff between accuracy and model complexity. Our experiments show that incorporating multiscale modules allows smaller models to achieve comparable or even superior accuracy to larger baselines. These findings highlight the potential of multiscale representations for improving the efficiency of CNN-based ASC systems, especially in 1D separate architectures like TF-SepNet.

Index Terms—Acoustic scene classification, time-frequency separate network, 1D kernels, multiscale feature extraction

1. INTRODUCTION

Acoustic scene classification (ASC) [1] is a fundamental task in audio signal processing, where the goal is to classify audio recordings into specific predefined environmental sound scenes such as shopping mall, metro, or office. Real-world ASC applications demand efficient operation under limited resources [2]. However, high-performing ASC models are often complex and resource-intensive. Thus, achieving a balance between accuracy and efficiency remains a key challenge [3].

Most ASC models build on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [4]. Researchers have explored CNNs to improve both accuracy and efficiency in ASC tasks [2]. Moreover, the focus in recent studies has changed from traditional two-dimensional (2D) convolutional kernels to one-dimensional (1D) kernels to reduce computational complexity [5]. Unlike 2D kernels that process both time and frequency dimensions simultaneously, 1D kernels separate these processes, allowing for a significant reduction in the overall number of parameters [6]. This approach not only preserves the essential features of the audio signal, but also enhances the ability of the model to capture relevant time-frequency patterns by expanding the effective receptive field (ERF), which refers to the range of input regions that influence a model’s prediction [7]. The use of 1D kernels in architectures like Time-Frequency Separate Network (TF-SepNet) [5] represents an important advancement in balancing efficiency and accuracy in ASC tasks. The design of TF-SepNet is based on the BC-ResNet architecture [8], which integrates depthwise separable convolutions [7] and broadcasting operations [8] to further reduce model complexity. Using separate convolutional paths for time and frequency features, the network effectively expands the effective ERF with fewer layers.

Although TF-SepNet successfully balances the ERF and model complexity, its fixed scale of feature extraction may limit its ability to fully capture the acoustic variations present in complex acoustic environments. A promising strategy to overcome this limitation is to incorporate multiscale representations, which enable models to analyze features at different resolutions, ensuring that both details and broader contextual patterns are effectively captured [9], [10]. One such technique is Dilation Convolution Downsampling (DCD), which utilizes dilated convolutions with exponentially increasing dilation rates and varying kernel sizes to downsample time series data at multiple scales [11]. This enables the network to extract complex temporal features by capturing both short-term local dependencies as well as long-term global dependencies [12]. Another technique is Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) [13], which has been used in computer vision to pool features at multiple spatial scales. In the context of ASC, SPP has demonstrated its potential to improve classification accuracy by aggregating local features of convolutional layers on different scales [14]. Building on the concept of SPP, Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP) [15] enhances multiscale feature extraction by integrating atrous (dilated) convolutions into the pyramid pooling framework [16].

As the main contribution of this paper, we propose three novel architectures named **TFSepDCD-Net**, **TFSepSPP-Net**, and **TFSepASPP-Net**, which integrate DCD, SPP, and ASPP into different components of TF-SepNet, respectively. Each architecture has two variants and three sub-models with channel widths of 60, 40, and 20, using the original TF-SepNet [5] [17] as the baseline. Our goal is to explore how multiscale representations influence the balance between model complexity and performance, aiming to find configurations that reduce parameters and computation while maintaining accuracy. We hypothesize that introducing lightweight multiscale modules into TF-SepNet enables a better trade-off between classification accuracy and model complexity.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Time-Frequency Separate Network (TF-SepNet)

TF-SepNet [5] is a CNN architecture specifically designed for ASC tasks, aiming to achieve a balance between model complexity and classification accuracy. The core of TF-SepNet lies in the TF-SepConv module, as shown in Fig.2 of [5]. This module is specifically designed to independently process the time and frequency dimensions of input features using 1D convolutional kernels. The TF-SepConv module begins with a transition layer, implemented as a 1×1 convolution, which adjusts the number of channels. Following this, a shuffle unit is applied to facilitate the mixing of information across channels before splitting the feature maps into two separate paths: the frequency path and the temporal path. In the frequency path, a depthwise convolution with a kernel size of 3×1 is applied, followed by frequency average pooling. Similarly, in the temporal path, a depthwise convolution with a kernel size of 1×3 is followed by temporal average pooling.

Output Shape	Architecture	k	s	p
1, F, T	Input	-	-	-
C/2, F/2, T/2	ConvBnRelu	5	2	2
2C, F/4, T/4	ConvBnRelu	1	1	0
C, F/4, T/4	TF-SepConvs $\times 2$	-	-	-
C, F/8, T/8	Max Pooling	2	2	0
1.5C, F/8, T/8	TF-SepConvs $\times 2$	-	-	-
1.5C, F/16, T/16	Max Pooling	2	2	0
2C, F/16, T/16	TF-SepConvs $\times 2$	-	-	-
2.5C, F/16, T/16	TF-SepConvs $\times 3$	-	-	-
10, F/16, T/16	Conv	1	1	0
10, 1, 1	Average Pooling	-	-	-

Table 1: TF-SepNet network architecture details showing the output shape, layers, and their respective kernel size (k), stride (s), and padding (p).

Both paths then employ a pointwise convolution to further process the features. The output features from the frequency path and the temporal path are then broadcasted back to their original dimensions and concatenated along the channel axis to form the final output.

The architecture of TF-SepNet, as outlined in Table 1, begins with two initial 3×3 convolution layers with a stride of 2, which perform early downsampling of the input spectrogram. This is followed by a series of nine TF-SepConv modules interspersed with two 2×2 max-pooling layers that further reduce spatial dimensions while capturing higher-level features. In the final stage, a 1×1 convolutional layer is used, followed by global average pooling to generate multiclass probabilities as the model’s output. An adaptive residual normalization technique is integrated after the initial downsampling block and after each TF-SepConvs block to ensure stability and to improve convergence during training [17]. A key parameter of the TF-SepNet model is its channel width, denoted by the hyperparameter τ , which allows to adjust the model complexity. By tuning τ , TF-SepNet can be scaled to meet different computational requirements, from resource-limited environments to high-performance computing systems.

2.2. Dilation Convolution Downsampling (DCD)

DCD is a technique that captures both short-term and long-term dependencies in time series data by applying dilated convolutions with exponentially increasing dilation rates [11]. This approach expands the receptive field without increasing the number of parameters, allowing the model to efficiently extract hierarchical temporal features across different resolutions. Moreover, DCD has been successfully applied in various tasks. For example, in [12], the authors employ a Multi-Scale Dilated Convolution Network (MSDCN) with dilation rates of 1, 2, and 4, and kernel sizes of 2, 4, and 6 to downsample and process time series data.

2.3. Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP)

SPP is a multiscale feature aggregation technique that addresses the limitation of fixed-size inputs in CNNs by introducing an SPP layer. For instance, as illustrated in Fig. 1, the SPP layer is inserted between the final convolutional layer and the fully connected layers. It pools local features over multiple spatial bins and captures hierarchical spatial information at different resolutions. Each spatial bin performs max pooling over regions of the convolutional feature maps, and the pooled outputs are flattened and concatenated. When the last conv layer outputs 256 feature channels, pooling over 4×4 , 2×2 , and 1×1 bins yields 16, 4, and 1 pooled values per channel, resulting in feature maps of shape 16×256 , 4×256 , and 256. These are concatenated into a single fixed-length vector that feeds into the fully connected layers. This design enables the network to handle inputs

Fig. 1: A CNN structure with an SPP layer, as cited in [18].

of arbitrary sizes while preserving multiscale spatial structure in the feature representation [18].

2.4. Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP)

ASPP [15] is a powerful technique designed to capture multiscale contextual information [10] by applying parallel atrous (dilated) convolutions with varying dilation rates. The ASPP module consists of multiple convolutional layers, typically with a kernel size of 3×3 , and different dilation rates commonly set to 6, 12, 18, and 24. These dilation rates allow the module to capture features at different scales, effectively covering various receptive fields. In addition to these dilated convolutions, ASPP also includes a global pooling branch, which provides global contextual information by pooling the entire feature map into a single value per channel. The outputs from the dilated convolutions and a global pooling branch are then concatenated along the channel dimension, resulting in a multiscale feature map. This map is passed through a 1×1 convolution to reduce the number of channels, integrating the multiscale information into a compact representation.

2.5. The Proposed Architectures

As the main contribution of this paper, we propose three novel architectures—**TFSepDCD-Net**, **TFSepSPP-Net**, and **TFSepASPP-Net**—which integrate DCD, SPP, and ASPP into different components of TF-SepNet. For each architecture, we develop two variants: (1) the two max pooling layers originally used for intermediate downsampling in TF-SepNet are replaced with the respective modules (**MP variants**); (2) the final convolutional layer originally used in TF-SepNet is replaced with the respective module (**LP variants**).

2.5.1. TFSepDCD-Net: In the first architecture, which we refer to as TFSepDCD-MP, the two max pooling layers originally used for intermediate downsampling in TF-SepNet are replaced with DCD modules. Each DCD module begins with a 3×3 convolutional layer with stride 2 to perform spatial downsampling, reducing the input resolution from $C \times F/8 \times T/8$ to $C \times F/16 \times T/16$. The downsampled feature map is then processed through multiple parallel dilated convolutions with increasing dilation rates to capture contextual information at different temporal and spectral resolutions. Each dilated convolution uses a 3×3 kernel with the dilation rates $d \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and produces 8-channel outputs. The operation of the DCD module can be defined as:

$$v_{dcd} = \sum_{d \in \{1, 2, 3\}} D_d(x'), \quad (1)$$

where x' is the downsampled input feature map, $D_d(\cdot)$ denotes a 3×3 convolution with dilation d . These outputs are concatenated

and passed through a final 1×1 convolution to maintain spatial consistency and reduce the feature map to the desired number of channels.

In the second architecture, TFSepDCD-CL, the final convolutional layer before global average pooling in TF-SepNet is replaced with a DCD module. The multiscale dilated structure mirrors that of TFSepDCD-MP, using dilation rates of 1, 2, and 3. However, unlike TFSepDCD-MP, this module does not perform downsampling. Instead, the input feature map is first passed through a 1×1 convolution to reduce the number of channels from $2.5 \cdot C$ to C , after which the DCD branches are applied.

2.5.2. TFSepSPP-Net: In the first architecture, which we refer to as TFSepSPP-MP, the two max pooling layers originally used for intermediate downsampling in TF-SepNet are replaced with SPP modules. As illustrated in Figure 2, the process begins by applying a convolutional layer with a stride of 2 to downsample the input feature map to the same resolution it would have after max pooling. The downsampled feature map is then processed through the SPP module, which captures multiscale information using three Adaptive Average Pooling (AAP) branches with output sizes of 1×1 , 2×2 , and 4×4 , along with a global pooling branch. Each branch includes a 1×1 convolution to process the pooled feature into a lower-dimensional representation, which is then upsampled to the original resolution. The resulting multiscale features are concatenated and passed through a final 1×1 convolution to preserve the spatial size and match the desired number of channels. The overall operation is defined as:

$$v_{spp} = \sum_{k \in \{1,2,4\}} W_k \cdot U(P_k(x')) + W_g \cdot G(x'), \quad (2)$$

where x' denotes the downsampled feature map, $P_k(\cdot)$ represents adaptive average pooling to a $k \times k$ grid, $U(\cdot)$ denotes bilinear upsampling, W_k and W_g are 1×1 convolution, and $G(x')$ is the global pooling output.

Fig. 2: Visualization of the application of the SPP module in the TFSepSPP-MP.

In the second architecture, TFSepSPP-CL, the final convolutional layer before global average pooling in TF-SepNet is replaced with an SPP module. As in the TFSepSPP-MP, the module includes three scale branches and a global pooling path. However, there is a difference: the input feature map is initially passed through a 1×1 convolution to reduce the number of channels from $2.5C$ to C , enabling more efficient multiscale processing.

2.5.3. TFSepASPP-Net: In the first architecture, which we refer to as TFSepASPP-MP, the two max pooling layers originally used for intermediate downsampling in TF-SepNet are replaced with ASPP modules. As illustrated in Figure 3, the process involves first applying a convolutional layer with a stride of 2. Then, the downsampled feature map is processed through the ASPP module, which consists of three dilated convolutions with dilation rates of 6, 12, and 18, and a global

pooling branch. The global pooling branch applies average pooling across the entire feature map to capture global context information, followed by a 1×1 convolution denoted as $W_{1 \times 1}$ to match the number of channels with the other branches. The resulting multiscale features from all branches are then concatenated as shown in Equation 3, where x' represents the downsampled input feature map, W_d denotes the dilated convolution operations with zero padding matching the dilation rate, and $G(x')$ denotes the global pooling operation followed by the 1×1 convolution. Finally, the concatenated feature map is processed through a 1×1 convolution to maintain the original channel count and spatial dimensions.

$$v_{aspp} = \sum_{d \in \{6,12,18\}} W_d \cdot x' + W_{1 \times 1} \cdot G(x'). \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3: Visualization of the application of the ASPP module in the TFSepASPP-MP.

In the second architecture, TFSepASPP-CL, the final convolutional layer before global average pooling in the original TF-SepNet is replaced by an ASPP module. The input feature map initially passes through a 1×1 convolution to adjust the channel dimensions before entering the ASPP module.

3. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

3.1. Dataset and Pre-processing

We use the TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile development dataset [19]. We follow the official 7:3 training/test split for our experiments. Our feature extraction pipeline strictly follows the original TF-SepNet implementation [17]: All audio segments are downsampled to 32 kHz and the time-frequency features are extracted using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) with a window size of 3072 samples (64 ms) and a hop size of 500 samples (10.42 ms). A Mel-scaled filter bank with 256 frequency bands and 4096 FFT points is used to convert the spectrograms into Log-Mel spectrograms. We also incorporate device simulation as done in [17].

3.2. Training Setup

The training setup strictly follows that of the original TF-SepNet [5] [17]. The model is trained for 100 epochs using the Adam optimizer. The batch size is 32. A warm-up strategy is also applied, where the learning rate is gradually increased from 0 to 0.01 during the initial five epochs, followed by a gradual reduction to 0 using cosine annealing for the remaining training epochs. Mixup [20] and Freq-MixStyle [21] techniques are incorporated, where Mixup's α is set to 0.3, and Freq-MixStyle's α and ρ values are set to 0.3 and 0.7.

3.3. Experimental Design

In our experiments, we evaluate a total of 21 models, including the original TF-SepNet [5] [17] as the baseline and three proposed architectures, each one being implemented as both **MP** and **LP** variant. All models are evaluated under three different configurations by

Model	Variant	τ	Params / k	MACs / M	Acc. / %
TFSepNet	–	60	115.15	15.20	66.2
		40	54.27	7.03	64.3
		20	15.89	3.42	58.5
TFSep-DCD	MP	60	217.90	44.42	65.3
		40	106.87	22.38	63.7
		20	34.24	7.58	63.3
	CL	60	107.59	21.49	66.8
		40	56.81	11.20	64.2
		20	21.03	4.04	64.1
TFSep-SPP	MP	60	196.15	38.79	61.9
		40	92.37	18.64	62.7
		20	26.99	5.70	64.2
	CL	60	90.31	18.93	66.4
		40	45.53	9.51	64.4
		20	15.75	3.23	63.7
TFSep-ASPP	MP	60	281.02	38.29	62.9
		40	128.15	17.96	62.9
		20	34.48	5.20	61.7
	CL	60	210.64	22.27	66.0
		40	96.63	10.76	63.0
		20	26.42	3.33	65.0

Table 2: Model accuracy along with parameter count and MACs consumption for TFSepNet and the proposed variants across different channel widths. Each proposed model includes two architectural variants (MP, CL).

varying the channel width $\tau \in \{60, 40, 20\}$, corresponding to large, medium, and small model sizes.

3.4. Results

As shown in Table 2, all proposed models demonstrate clear performance improvements over the TF-SepNet baseline using the smallest channel width of $\tau = 20$. Among the two architectural variants, the CL variant is more effective for lightweight configurations, consistently outperforming its MP counterparts. Models such as **TFSepDCD-CL20** (64.1%), **TFSepSPP-CL20** (63.7%), and **TFSepASPP-CL20** (65.0%) achieve higher accuracy compared to the baseline **TF-SepNet-20** (58.5%), with only marginal increases in model complexity. Notably, many of these small models perform on par with or better than TF-SepNet-40 (64.3%), which has more than twice the number of parameters. This shows that lightweight multiscale variants can reach comparable accuracy while substantially reducing the model size. Moreover, among all models, **TFSepSPP-CL20** stands out by offering an excellent trade-off: it achieves 63.7 % accuracy with just 15.75 k parameters and 3.23 M MACs, nearly matching the baseline’s size while surpassing it in accuracy by 5.2%. These findings are visually summarized in Figure 4, which plots model accuracy against number of parameters. For clarity, only the baseline TF-SepNet models with $\tau = 20$ and 40, along with all proposed variants at $\tau = 20$, are highlighted.

To further assess the performance-efficiency tradeoff of our proposed architectures, we conducted significance tests on both accuracy and parameter count across different model groups, as summarized in Table 3. Apart from the comparison between all $\tau = 20$ models and all $\tau = 60$ models, which shows a significant accuracy difference ($p = 0.034$), all other comparisons yield $p > 0.05$ for accuracy. Notably, when combining all CL-20 and MP-20 variants and comparing them to all $\tau = 40$ models, the p-value reaches as high as 0.928, indicating virtually no performance difference between our smallest models and the larger $\tau = 40$ configurations. All comparisons in terms of parameter count show statistically significant differences ($p < 0.01$). Moreover, we also individually tested CL-20 and MP-20

Fig. 4: Accuracy versus parameter size for selected models. Color coding indicates different model types: blue for the baseline TF-SepNet, orange for TFSepDCD-Net variants, green for TFSepSPP-Net variants, and red for TFSepASPP-Net variants.

Comparison	p-value (Accuracy)	p-value (Params)
All-20 vs All-40	0.257	0.002
All-20 vs All-60	0.034	< 0.001
CL-20&MP-20 vs All-40	0.928	0.003
CL-20&MP-20 vs All-60	0.068	< 0.001

Table 3: Significance test results (p-values) for accuracy and parameter count. Each row compares a group of lightweight models with mid-size or large counterparts. Bold values indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

against all $\tau = 40$ and $\tau = 60$ models. In all four comparisons, the differences in accuracy were not statistically significant ($p = 0.306, 0.326, 0.346,$ and 0.084).

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presented three novel ASC model architectures, which integrate multiscale feature extraction modules into the efficient, 1D-kernel-based TF-SepNet backbone. Each architecture was implemented in two variants, replacing either the final convolutional layer or the max-pooling layers, and evaluated across three different channel configurations ($\tau = 20, 40, 60$). Our experiments demonstrated that the proposed models with $\tau = 20$ notably outperform the baseline TF-SepNet-20, achieving higher classification accuracy with only a marginal increase in parameter count. Among these, TFSepASPP-CL20 achieved a 65.0% accuracy, representing a 6.5% absolute improvement over TF-SepNet-20. Furthermore, statistical significance tests confirmed that, except for the direct comparison between all $\tau = 20$ models and all $\tau = 60$ models, the accuracy differences between the lightweight $\tau = 20$ variants and their larger $\tau = 40$ and $\tau = 60$ counterparts are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), with a particularly high p-value of 0.928 when comparing all CL- and MP-based $\tau = 20$ models with all $\tau = 40$ models. In contrast, all comparisons in terms of parameter count yielded statistically significant differences ($p < 0.01$), reinforcing that our proposed models are substantially more compact. These findings support our hypothesis, showing that multiscale variants of TF-SepNet achieve a more favorable balance between accuracy and efficiency, and in particular, the multiscale-integrated $\tau = 20$ variants highlight this trade-off by achieving competitive performance with substantially reduced model complexity.

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Latent Multi-view Learning for Robust Environmental Sound Representations

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Abstract—Self-supervised learning (SSL) approaches, such as contrastive and generative methods, have advanced environmental sound representation learning using unlabeled data. However, how these approaches can complement each other within a unified framework remains relatively underexplored. In this work, we propose a multi-view learning framework that integrates contrastive principles into a generative pipeline to capture sound source and device information. Our method encodes compressed audio latents into view-specific and view-common subspaces, guided by two self-supervised objectives: contrastive learning for targeted information flow between subspaces, and reconstruction for overall information preservation. We evaluate our method on an urban sound sensor network dataset for sound source and sensor classification, demonstrating improved downstream performance over traditional SSL techniques. Additionally, we investigate the model’s potential to disentangle environmental sound attributes within the structured latent space under varied training configurations.

Index Terms—Self-supervised Learning, Urban Sound, Environmental Sound Classification, Sensor Classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental sound representation learning is a crucial field in machine listening, serving as a foundation for tasks like environmental sound classification and acoustic scene analysis. To address the scarcity of annotations in environmental sound data, self-supervised learning (SSL) aims to approach and even sometimes surpass the performance of supervised methods through self-supervision techniques, such as contrastive and generative objectives.

Contrastive learning (CL) for audio representations exploits the assumption of commonalities across different views of data with the same semantics to create positive pairs, such as using augmented “views” of the same audio clip [1]–[3]. These principles have been widely employed for environmental sound [4]–[6]. Generative learning focuses on reconstruction-based objectives to learn an embedding space for a single “view” of complete or masked input [7]–[12]. In acoustic scene classification and sound event detection [13]–[16], these methods have proven effective at capturing a diverse acoustic content by encoding information across both temporal and feature dimensions. At the same time, in other domains, SSL research has begun to explore the complementary effects of combining reconstructive and contrastive learning frameworks in various ways. For example, [17] and [18] propose multi-view learning frameworks for visual clustering or classification. These methods simultaneously learn a “shared” latent subspace that is invariant across views and a “private” latent subspace that varies across views, by optimizing view reconstruction from both subspaces within an autoencoder architecture. This approach employs a view-contrastive strategy by learning both view-common and view-specific subspaces, without relying on explicit contrastive objectives. In [19], masked reconstruction is combined with CL objectives in an audio-visual context, but with one shared latent space for each modality view.

In the music domain, for pitch-timbre disentanglement, [20] leverages random perturbations to form view-contrasting training strategies within a reconstruction-based pipeline. Similarly, [21] studies how pitch-shifting can be used to create auxiliary objectives such as a

contrastive loss in addition to single-view reconstruction. Furthermore, our previous work [22] uses a multi-view learning framework to learn disentangled latent subspaces for pitch and timbre without explicit contrastive objectives. These methods provide insights on how we can combine different SSL strategies and potentially disentangle inherent factors in audio. However, such methods haven’t been explored in a more challenging context such as real-world environmental sound recordings, and there lacks a thorough investigation into how objective design choices affect latent subspace structures.

In this work, we combine contrastive and generative objectives within a multi-view learning framework to explore their combined impact on environmental sound representations. Using DAC [7] as a latent feature extractor, the framework encodes the audio feature into separate private and shared subspaces based on a metadata-driven data pairing strategy, eliminating the need for explicit class annotations. To strengthen the training signal of contrasting views in our multi-view backbone, we investigate similarity or separation-based contrastive objectives on the subspaces between views. Our evaluation is conducted on an urban sound sensor network dataset (SONYC-UST-V2 [23]), with performance measured on sound source and sensor classification tasks. In addition, we examine the model’s ability to disentangle sound attributes, offering insights into the structure of the learned latent space. Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We propose a novel latent multi-view contrastive learning framework for environmental sound representation learning.
- By simply creating pairs of data with available metadata and training a lightweight autoencoder in a self-supervised manner, we demonstrate a downstream performance boost on sound and sensor classification compared to traditional SSL baselines, achieving results comparable to supervised baselines.
- We investigate how different combinations of SSL training strategies influence the latent subspace structures, providing insights into environmental sound attribute disentanglement.

2. METHOD

2.1. Multi-view Representation Learning

Our proposed method is shown in Figure 1. The “views” of data used in our method are two audio clips, denoted $\{a_1, a_2\}$. Our system requires a single assumption between these audio clips: that they share a common attribute (e.g., recordings from the same sensor). We first pass a_1 and a_2 through a pretrained encoder to obtain 2D embeddings $\{x_1, x_2\}$ of dimension $(n \times d)$, where n is the number of frames and d is the feature dimension. In this work we use DAC [7] as the pretrained encoder. The DAC latent space, capable of preserving detailed information in environmental sound while reconstructing high-fidelity signals, provides us with a strong foundation for discriminative downstream tasks.

We pass embeddings x_1 and x_2 through a simple MLP encoder, denoted ϵ_ϕ . The weights of ϵ_ϕ are shared across views of data. This encoder projects each input embedding into two separate *private* and *shared* latent subspaces, as defined in traditional multi-view learning

Fig. 1: Our self-supervised multi-view framework for environmental sound representation learning. Learned latent subspaces are used for downstream sound source and recording sensor classification tasks.

frameworks [18], denoted z_{pi} and z_{si} respectively, where i is the data view (for $i \in 1, 2$ in this study). The private subspace is designed to capture information specific to each individual view, while the shared subspace should capture information shared across both views. Latent subspaces z_{pi} and z_{si} of dimension $(n, \frac{d}{2})$ are then averaged to form a joint shared embedding: z_S . Additional training strategies can then be applied to these latent subspaces to incentivize desired information flow, which we introduce in Section 2.2. Lastly, an MLP decoder d_θ takes the concatenation of z_{pi} and z_S as input and projects back to the original dimensionality, reconstructing the original pretrained latents: $\{\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2\}$.

Importantly, note that because the weights of our projection encoder and decoder are shared across data streams, at inference time, our model can operate using only a single audio input; pairs are not needed. The model encodes the input audio into the previously learned private, shared, and combined subspaces, yielding z_p , z_s and their concatenation ($z_p \oplus z_s$), reusable for further downstream tasks.

2.2. Self-supervised Training Strategies

To combine generative and contrastive SSL frameworks to learn robust environmental sound representations, we design a suite of training strategies to apply within the multi-view learning backbone.

Reconstruction: The base version of our model is trained using a mean squared error reconstruction loss \mathcal{L}_{rec} between the original and reconstructed embeddings, x_i and \hat{x}_i respectively, where i is the view index in the data pair and j is the sample in a dataset of size N samples:

$$\mathcal{L}_{rec} = \sum_i \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (x_{i,j} - \hat{x}_{i,j})^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

Cosine Distance: In addition to the base reconstruction loss, we utilize contrastive learning in our framework via objectives based on cosine distance, in which similar embeddings are incentivized to be close together in the latent space and dissimilar embeddings are pushed farther apart [24]–[26]. The general form of this loss term is referred to as \mathcal{L}_{cos} . To encourage private latents to capture view-specific information, we introduce a loss term that enforces separation between the two private latents, z_{p1} and z_{p2} , by minimizing cosine similarity, denoted \mathcal{L}_{cos-} . Along the same lines, we maximize cosine similarity between z_{s1} and z_{s2} to encourage the shared latents to contain similar information (\mathcal{L}_{cos+}).

We experiment with these similarity or separation-based configurations on both a batch and sample level. The batch-level version

includes inherent negatives from other samples in the batch similar to the traditional InfoNCE [27] setting, while the sample-level version treats cosine similarity as a simple binary classification, without cross-batch negatives. The sample-level similarity and separation-based objectives are defined below, where j or k refers to the index of samples within a batch of size B :

$$\mathcal{L}_{cos+} = -\mathbb{E}_{j \in [1, B]} [\log \text{sim}(z_{s1}^j, z_{s2}^j)] \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{cos-} = -\mathbb{E}_{j \in [1, B]} [\log(1 - \text{sim}(z_{p1}^j, z_{p2}^j))] \quad (3)$$

Similarly, the batch-level objectives are expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{cos+} = -\mathbb{E}_{j \in [1, B]} \left[\log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(z_{s1}^j, z_{s2}^j))}{\sum_k \exp(\text{sim}(z_{s1}^j, z_{s2}^k))} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{cos-} = -\mathbb{E}_{j, k \in [1, B]} [\log(1 - \text{sim}(z_{p1}^j, z_{p2}^k))] \quad (5)$$

When a cosine distance objective is used, it is added to the reconstruction objective for a final loss term of $\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_{rec} + \mathcal{L}_{cos}$.

Masking: Drawing on works in masked acoustic token modeling from the generative-based methods [11], [19], [28], we mask a ratio (r) of random entries in the projected latent subspaces during training. By masking one latent subspace and leaving the other unchanged, the intuition is to encourage the model to rely more on a subset of the subspaces to infer necessary information. We leverage this latent subspace-based masking mechanism as a motivation to enforce the model to learn robust representations that capture the underlying structure in each subspace.

3. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3.1. Dataset and Multi-View Data Pairing

We use the SONYC-UST-V2 dataset [29], which contains 10-second audio clips recorded from 56 sensors across New York City as part of the SONYC project [23]. The 56 sensor classes refer to individual recording devices placed in distinct urban locations, each capturing various city soundscapes. Sensors capture important channel effect information, namely the environmental acoustics unique to that location and microphone position. The recordings are non-overlapping in time, meaning that we can obtain multiple audio clips from the same sensor “for free” by selecting different temporal segments within a recording. Therefore, we consider our data pairing strategy as a self-supervised mechanism, as it is similar to sampling pairs of segments from the same recording in the traditional SSL setup. Each audio clip

Table 1: Downstream source and sensor classification vs. baselines. We present the results of our best-performing model, which uses reconstruction loss and sample-level cosine distance loss to separate private latents as the combined training strategy.

Method	Objective	Source $n_c = 8$	Sensor $n_c = 12$
Multi-view (Best Config.)	$\mathcal{L}_{rec} + \mathcal{L}_{cos-}$	0.633	0.735
Single-view Autoencoder	\mathcal{L}_{rec}	0.582	0.710
Contrastive Learning	Info-NCE [27]	0.324	0.392
DAC [7]	N/A	0.583	0.684
Supervised Learning	BCE/CE	0.699	0.732

is labeled with one or more of 8 sound source categories, including engine, alarm, and human voice.

For this study, we use the recording *sensor* as the *shared* factor, pairing clips recorded by the same sensor at different times. These randomly selected pairs are assumed to naturally differ in *sound source content*, which we use as the *private* factor in this study. An example data pair could be two audio recordings from the same sensor location but recorded on different days, where one contains a dog barking sound and another contains an engine and car alarm.

We construct 39k training pairs, 6k for validation, and 11k for testing, containing 39/5/12 disjoint sensors respectively. We evaluate on unseen sensors to test the model’s generalization ability and robustness for unseen scene variations. For downstream evaluation, we further partition this test set into train, validation, and test subsets stratified by sensor and sound source, resulting in an 8-class multi-label classification for downstream sound source classification, and 12-class classification for sensor. Importantly, we only use these labels in downstream evaluation and our core method is fully self-supervised.

3.2. Audio Preprocessing

We follow the parameters used for preprocessing audio for the Describe Audio Codec (DAC) [7]. We resample audio recordings from SONYC to 44.1KHz and normalize them to -24 dB LUFS, following DAC. We pass the full 10-seconds of audio to the pretrained DAC model¹. For a 10-sec. audio clip, this yields an embedding of shape (862, 1024), where 862 is the number of frames and 1024 is the feature dimension. We use the pre-quantized continuous latents from DAC. Pairs of these embeddings are used as input to our multi-view autoencoder.

3.3. Training Recipe

We train all of our models for 100 epochs on a single A100 GPU using a batch size of 16. We use a learning rate of $1e - 3$ and AdamW optimization, and perform model selection using minimum total validation loss.

3.4. Downstream Classification

We evaluate the informativeness of our learned joint audio representations on downstream sensor and source classification tasks. After training our multi-view autoencoder model, we freeze the trained encoder and use it as a feature extractor to obtain private and shared latents (z_p and z_s) from a single input audio clip to use for downstream training. We train independent 2-layer MLP classifier heads on top of the private, shared, and concatenated latents separately for source and sensor classification. We use cross entropy (CE) as the objective for 12-class sensor classification, and binary cross entropy (BCE) as the objective for 8-class source classification in the multi-label setting.

¹We use the 44.1KHz, 8kbps bitrate pretrained DAC.

3.5. Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate downstream performance using accuracy for 12-class sensor classification, and the Jaccard index for 8-class multi-label source classification. For each task, we use the following metrics:

Overall accuracy: We concatenate the private and shared subspaces ($z_p \oplus z_s$) and use this joint latent as the feature for the downstream task. This gives a measure of overall robustness and information retained in the learned embedding space.

Subspace accuracy: To better-understand the information structure in the latent subspace, we use either z_{pi} or z_{si} as features for downstream classification. This allows us to assess the information present in the separate learned subspaces.

Directional subspace classification ($DSC\Delta$): As a proxy metric to investigate the disentanglement level of the private and shared subspaces, we measure the difference in subspace performance for both source and sensor classification tasks. We define $DSC\Delta$ for the private or shared latent as:

$$DSC\Delta_{priv} = \text{clf}(z_p)_{\text{source}} - \text{clf}(z_s)_{\text{source}} \quad (6)$$

$$DSC\Delta_{shared} = \text{clf}(z_s)_{\text{sensor}} - \text{clf}(z_p)_{\text{sensor}}, \quad (7)$$

where $\text{clf}(\cdot)$ indicates the downstream classifier trained per task. An ideal scenario for disentanglement in our framework is for the private latent to capture view-specific information (source in this study), and for the shared to capture common information (sensor). If there is no disentanglement and the subspace performance using either latent is identical, this yields $DSC\Delta = 0$. Thus, we aim for a positive $DSC\Delta$ score for each latent, indicating the desired disentanglement.

3.6. Baseline Methods

We apply the framework above to a series of baseline training strategies, each built upon the pretrained DAC latents as input:

DAC [7] without training: The naive baseline is training the downstream classifiers directly on top of off-the-shelf DAC latents. This represents the baseline classification potential of the latents before any additional training or disentanglement.

Single-view Autoencoder: We apply the traditional generative learning pipeline using the same encoder and decoder architecture as our method with the reconstruction loss \mathcal{L}_{rec} , but with just one view.

Contrastive learning: We apply the traditional contrastive learning framework using the same encoder architecture as our method, but without (1) the notion of separated latent subspaces and (2) using a decoder for reconstruction. This yields one latent space of the same dimensionality as the joint latent in our multi-view based methods. We train the encoder on pairs of data with the same dataset used in our multi-view framework (data paired by common sensor class), utilizing only one training strategy of an InfoNCE [27] loss, where each pair is considered a positive sample and samples from different pairs are considered negative samples.

Supervised learning: using the same encoder as our method, with an additional one-layer linear classification head for either multi-label source classification (BCE objective), or multi-class sensor classification (CE objective), without reconstruction. This method provides an upper bound of task performance, not a direct comparison with our proposed methods, since our training is label-free.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We train our model with different combinations of training strategies introduced in Sec. 2.2. Our base method uses a multi-view learning backbone with \mathcal{L}_{rec} . Variants of our method are trained using one of the following training strategies on top of the base method: sample

Table 2: Examining the effects of varied objective functions on downstream source and sensor classification.

Objective	Configuration	Source $n_c = 8$	Sensor $n_c = 12$	Avg. Acc.
\mathcal{L}_{rec}	N/A	0.610	0.739	0.675
$\mathcal{L}_{rec} + \mathcal{L}_{cos-}$	Sample-level	0.633	0.735	0.684
	Batch-level	0.610	0.737	0.674
$\mathcal{L}_{rec} + \mathcal{L}_{cos+}$	Sample-level	0.593	0.719	0.656
	Batch-level	0.603	0.728	0.666
$\mathcal{L}_{rec} + \text{Mask } z_p$	$r = 0.4$	0.594	0.733	0.664

or batch-level cosine distance objectives applied to the private latents to encourage separation (\mathcal{L}_{cos-}) or the shared latents to encourage similarity (\mathcal{L}_{cos+}), and lastly masking z_p with masking ratio $r \in [0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8]$.

4.1. Main Comparisons

The evaluation results of our best-performing model configurations and baselines are shown in Table 1. We first observe that the standard contrastive learning approach, trained using data paired by the same sensor class using Info-NCE, yields lower accuracy across the board for both tasks. This indicates that the assumption of commonality in CL is less effective in this nuanced task of sensor classification, and fails at extracting sound source information without an appropriate pairing strategy. Additionally, the more traditional single-view autoencoder provides 3.9% relative improvement on sensor classification but no improvement on source classification when compared to DAC latents without any training (denoted with “N/A” objective). In contrast, even without curating data pairs with matching sound source information, our method combining generative and contrastive principles is able to successfully capture information in both tasks.

Our best model configuration, using \mathcal{L}_{rec} and sample-level \mathcal{L}_{cos-} , improves overall accuracy results by 8.6% and 3.5% for source and sensor classification respectively, compared to the single-view autoencoder baseline. Further, this configuration significantly outperforms the contrastive and DAC-only baselines. Such improvements indicate the complementary effects of contrastive and generative principles to produce robust environmental sound representations, while overcoming limits of individual traditional SSL methods.

We also include a fully supervised upper bound for reference. While the supervised sensor classification achieves the highest performance with the help of complete label supervision, our method significantly narrows the gap with no explicit prior knowledge about sensor and source information. At the same time, we observe that our training framework even leads to a 0.4% relative performance improvement on sensor classification versus a supervised approach.

In Table 2, we investigate how different objective strategies introduced in Sec. 2.2 affect the the learned representations on downstream performance. We find that separation-based objectives (\mathcal{L}_{cos-}) tend to perform better than similarity-based objectives (\mathcal{L}_{cos+}), for both sample and batch-level experiments. We do not observe a consistent trend between sample and batch-level cosine distance-based experiments across tasks; for \mathcal{L}_{cos-} , sample-level performs better (our best configuration in terms of averaged accuracy), but for \mathcal{L}_{cos+} , the batched version is marginally better than sampled.

4.2. Disentanglement Investigation

We also observe the potential for environmental sound attribute disentanglement using our method and investigate this under different training configurations. In Figure 2, we visualize the trend of

Fig. 2: Visualizing the effects of cosine distance and masking strategies on downstream tasks using the overall performance vs. the Directional Subspace Classification metric ($DSC\Delta$).

information flow for source (left) and sensor (right) attributes grouped by three types of strategies: cosine distance-based disentanglement using only the multi-view backbone with \mathcal{L}_{rec} (green), adding \mathcal{L}_{cos+} or \mathcal{L}_{cos-} (orange), or \mathcal{L}_{rec} with masking (blue). Each point represents a specific training configuration within one type of training strategy, e.g. a specific masking ratio r within the “masking” category, or sample-based \mathcal{L}_{cos+} within the \mathcal{L}_{cos} grouping. The x-axis in Fig. 2 represents the overall classification accuracy obtained using the complete latent space ($z_p \oplus z_s$). The red vertical line marks the accuracy scores per task of the DAC baseline as reported in Table 1. The y-axis represents the $DSC\Delta$ to measure the level of information flow in the desired direction as a proxy for disentanglement quality.

We first show that the majority our multi-view strategies infuse useful source information in the latent subspaces, outperforming the pretrained DAC baseline marked with the red dotted line. We also observe that the multi-view backbone with only \mathcal{L}_{rec} has a positive $DSC\Delta$ for source, but negative $DSC\Delta$ for sensor, indicating that without explicit constraints utilizing multi-view assumptions, the model shows a tendency to steer information about both source and sensor into the private subspace. While Fig. 2 suggests that cosine distance-based strategies generally tend to push both source and sensor information into the private subspace, masking z_p shows the opposite effect; masking shifts overall information into the shared subspace. However, we did not observe obvious trend for different masking ratios. We speculate that the shared sensor information between views may be too subtle to capture in the common subspace with reconstruction alone, while masking z_p puts more weight on the shared subspace to encode all information to optimize reconstruction.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we proposed a novel self-supervised multi-view learning framework that integrates contrastive principles within a generative pipeline to improve the robustness of environmental sound representations. Our experiments on the SONYC-UST-V2 dataset demonstrate that our method improves downstream performance in both source and sensor classification on recordings in unseen sensors compared to traditional SSL methods. Beyond improved representation robustness, we investigate the effects of different training strategies on latent subspace information flow, showing the potential for environmental sound attribute disentanglement. In the future, we plan to explore using audio understanding models within our framework such as AudioMAE [11] or BEATs [12], and extend downstream tasks to out-of-distribution data.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Robust detection of overlapping bioacoustic sound events

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Abstract—We propose a method for accurately detecting bioacoustic sound events that is robust to overlapping events, a common issue in domains such as ethology, ecology and conservation. While standard methods employ a frame-based, multi-label approach, we introduce an onset-based detection method which we name *Voxaboxen*. For each time window, *Voxaboxen* predicts whether it contains the start of a vocalization and how long the vocalization is. It also does the same in reverse, predicting whether each window contains the end of a vocalization, and how long ago it started, and fuses the two sets of bounding boxes with a graph-matching algorithm. We also release a new dataset of temporally-strong labels of zebra finch vocalizations designed to have high overlap. Experiments on eight datasets, including our new dataset, show *Voxaboxen* outperforms natural baselines and existing methods, and is robust to vocalization overlap.

Index Terms—Bioacoustics, sound event detection, machine learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Detecting animal sounds is the foundation of bioacoustics research. In practice, these sounds often overlap, but identifying each individual acoustic unit is necessary for a diversity of tasks, including species recognition and population estimation, which can be critical for ecology and conversation [1].

When multiple individuals from a single species co-occur, the sounds they produce can overlap with each other, often with important functional consequences, e.g. in bats [2], zebra finches [3], frogs [4], and elephants [5]. To understand these communication systems, large-scale identification of individual vocalizations, including accurate classification of overlapping sounds, is of critical importance.

Motivated by this, we desire a sound event detection (SED) method that can predict the onset time, offset time, and class label (e.g., species label) for overlapping sound events. Commonly, SED methods adopt a frame-based approach: for each time frame, for each class, predicting whether a sound of that class occurs in that frame [6; 7; 8; 9], and merging consecutive frames with the same class into a single event. This does not accommodate overlaps from the same class.

To address this limitation, we propose a method we name *Voxaboxen*. For each frame, *Voxaboxen* makes a binary prediction as to whether it contains an event onset, plus a regression prediction for how long that event will last, and a class prediction (e.g. species label). This design choice means the duration of one predicted event can extend past the onset of a second event, thus allowing the model to predict overlapping vocalizations without them being merged.

To investigate how well *Voxaboxen* deals with overlapping vocalizations, we introduce a new dataset of recordings of eight female zebra finches (ZFs) spontaneously interacting in a laboratory environment, annotated with onset and offset of each vocalization, and featuring a high degree of overlap. We also introduce a series of synthetic datasets, consisting of ZF vocalizations with a controlled overlap-to-vocalization ratio. We find that *Voxaboxen* consistently outperforms alternatives, even in the presence of a high degree of overlap, on our new dataset as well as seven previously-published bioacoustics datasets.

Taken together, our results demonstrate the general effectiveness of *Voxaboxen* for bioacoustic SED, including for situations with overlapping vocalizations. To democratize putting boxes around vocalizations, we open source the code for our model and new dataset.

To summarize, the contributions of this paper are as follows:

- 1) introducing *Voxaboxen*, and SED model leveraging pretrained audio encoders, which can predict overlapping vocalizations;
- 2) releasing a new dataset, Overlapping Zebra Finch (OZF), specifically focused on overlapping vocalizations;
- 3) experimental evaluation on a diverse set of eight datasets, showing SotA performance for *Voxaboxen*.

2. RELATED WORK

In bioacoustics applications, SED has typically been framed as a multi-label classification problem [1], with temporal resolution ranging from tens of milliseconds [8; 10], to multiple seconds [11; 12]. Recent post-processing techniques decouple event durations and detections [9; 13]; but still use frame-based predictions and cannot handle within-class overlaps. Other approaches include matrix factorization algorithms [14] or probabilistic models [15].

Visual object detection methods such as Faster-RCNN [16] can accommodate overlapping objects, and have occasionally been applied to bioacoustic SED [17]. CornerNet [18] is an object detection method that, similar to *Voxaboxen*, matches predicted boundaries into a single event, but differs in that it matches boxes based on feature similarity, which can be inaccurate for animal vocalizations, where highly stereotyped events mean that different events can share very similar features. Our approach accounts for this by matching based on intersection over union (IoU) instead.

Given an audio recording with a mixture of sound sources, source separation is the task of predicting the audio of the pre-mixture sounds. Prior work in bioacoustics [19] has demonstrated the effectiveness of source separation for improving accuracy in downstream classification tasks. In our context, a source separation model could theoretically separate vocalizations from multiple individuals into different audio tracks, thus reducing the complexity of the audio passed to a downstream detection model. We investigate this type of approach as an alternative to *Voxaboxen*.

A related task is speaker diarization, which segments recordings of multiple speakers and assigns each segment to a speaker. Approaches typically assume a maximum number of speakers (e.g., two or four), and make use of the assumption that speakers can be re-identified by their vocal characteristics across multiple segments [20]. In contrast, we assume no maximum number of speakers, and do not expect to re-identify individuals within a recording.

3. METHOD

3.1. Bounding Box Regression

Our method, which is architecture-agnostic, uses a frame-based audio encoder $\phi: \mathbb{R}^T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{T' \times F}$ to produce a sequence of latent vectors.

Here T is the original number of samples, T' is the final number of frames, and F is the feature dimension. A final linear layer $h: \mathbb{R}^F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2+C}$ makes three types of predictions, for each time frame: a prediction of the probability that an event starts in that frame, a prediction of the duration of the event (should it start in that frame), and a prediction of a class label (logits across C classes).

Using gradient descent, we minimize the loss function $L = L_{det} + \lambda L_{reg} + \rho L_{cls}$, $\lambda, \rho \geq 0$, which includes a detection term L_{det} , a regression term L_{reg} , and a classification term L_{cls} . The detection term is inspired by the penalty-reduced focal loss in [18]:

$$L_{det} = -\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \begin{cases} (1 - \hat{p}_t)^\alpha \log \hat{p}_t & p_t = 1 \\ (1 - p_t)^\beta \hat{p}_t^\alpha \log(1 - \hat{p}_t) & p_t < 1. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here, T is the duration in frames of the audio clip, and α, β are hyperparameters. In (1), the model’s predicted detection probability at time t is \hat{p}_t , and the target p_t is obtained by smoothing each event onset with a Gaussian kernel and taking the maximum value at each frame, across all events (following [18]):

$$p_t = \max_{x \in \text{Events}} \exp\left(-\frac{(t - \text{Onset}(x))^2}{\text{Dur}(x)^2/s}\right). \quad (2)$$

In (2), Events is the set of events in an audio clip, and for $x \in \text{Events}$, $\text{Onset}(x)$ and $\text{Dur}(x)$ denote the onset time and duration of x , and s is a hyperparameter.

The regression term L_{reg} is L1 loss, applied only to frames in $\{\text{Onset}(x) \mid x \in \text{Events}\}$, i.e. frames where an event begins. Similarly, the classification term L_{cls} is a categorical cross-entropy loss, again applied only when an event begins. At inference time, we apply a peak-finding algorithm to the time-series of detection probabilities. Detection peaks above a threshold become boxes, with duration and class prediction determined by the value of the regression and classification predictions at the peak. The detection threshold is swept (for computing metrics), or fixed as a hyperparameter; see Section 5. Finally, we apply soft non-maximal suppression [21] to remove duplicate boxes.

3.2. Bidirectional Predictions

One drawback of using these predicted boxes directly is the difficulty for the model in making accurate regression predictions. In preliminary experiments, we observed that both onset and duration predictions can be slightly inaccurate, meaning that the model sometimes correctly detects an event but the edges of the bounding box are slightly off where they should be. To reduce error in bounding box edges, we make a second set of *backward* predictions which are the mirror image of the first (*forward*) set. The backward predictions are a binary prediction for each frame as to whether it contains an offset, plus a regression for how long the event lasted. We then compute an optimal way to fuse the forward and backward predictions into a single set of predictions, by casting the problem as a maximal bipartite graph matching problem. The bipartite graph has all boxes as vertices. Forward and backward boxes are linked by an edge if their IoU exceeds a threshold. The Hopcroft-Karp-Karzonov algorithm [22] computes the maximal matching sub-graph, and edge-linked box pairs are fused. The onset of the fused box is defined to be the midpoint of the onset of the forward box, with the offset minus duration of the backward box (and similarly for the offset of the fused box).

4. OVERLAPPING ZEBRA FINCH DATASET (OZF)

4.1. OZF Real-World Portion

We recorded 65 minutes (divided into 60-second files) of 8 adult (> 1 year) female ZFs housed in a large group cage in a sound attenuating

chamber (TRA Acoustics, Ontario, Canada). We continuously recorded using Audacity (3.3.3) through two omnidirectional microphones (Countryman, Menlo Park, CA) positioned above and to the side of the cage. Food and water were provided *ad libitum* and all procedures were approved by the McGill University Animal Care and Use Committee in accordance with Canadian Council on Animal Care guidelines.

Female ZFs make short, discrete vocalizations of about 100ms, consisting of a flat or downward sweeping harmonic stack, with most energy located between 0.5 and 8 kHz. The recordings were divided among three annotators, who marked the onset and offset time of each vocalization using Raven Pro (Cornell Lab of Ornithology, v.1.6.5). Annotators covered 25 minutes each. One 5 minute section was annotated by all three, where the mean pairwise inter-annotator F1@0.5IoU of 93.5, and 78.1 on the subset that overlaps.

Out of a total of 8504 vocalizations in the dataset, 1449 (17.04%) overlap with at least one other. The total number of overlaps is slightly higher at 1463, as some can overlap more than one other. The number of vocalizations per 60 s file ranges from 19 to 245, with between 0 and 73 overlapping. The duration of silence per 60 s file ranges from 35.5 to 58.1 seconds. We observe a roughly linear relationship between the two. The duration of each vocalization ranges from 3 ms to 350 ms and is strongly peaked around the mean of 109 ms.

It is possible to show that, assuming independent vocalizations from each bird that can be modelled with a Poisson distribution, the expected number of pairwise overlaps is $d(n-1)(1-1/B-1/n)$, where d is the ratio of total call durations to time window size, n is the number of vocalizations and B is the number of birds (details provided at project github). In our case, $B = 8$, $n \approx 120$ and $d \approx 0.1$. Plugging in the values for n and d from each 60s file the average ratio of overlap to number of vocalizations should be 20.46%, significantly above the 17.04% we observe. This is consistent with prior work showing evidence for turn-taking in female ZFs [23].

4.2. OZF Synthetic Portion

We generate six additional, synthetic ZF datasets where in each 60-second file, the ratio of overlaps to number of calls is controlled. We add cropped denoised female ZF vocalizations, drawn randomly from a call database, to a background track (recorded using the same setup as the OZF dataset, but without vocalizations).

There are 65 recordings in each synthetic dataset, each mimicking one 60-second source recording in OZF (same number of vocalizations and placed in the same train/val/test split). To construct one synthetic recording, we count the number of calls present in the OZF source recording and randomly draw an equal number from the call database, and add them sequentially to the background track, to achieve a target overlap-to-call ratio in $R \in \{0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0\}$. When $R > 0.2$, the first 25% of calls are placed uniformly at random to reduce clumping of calls around one point. Otherwise, each call is placed to overlap an existing call if and only if the current overlap ratio is below R . This method achieves an overlap ratio within 0.005 of R for each choice of R . Call amplitude is chosen so that signal-to-noise ratio falls uniformly at random between -15dB and 0dB.

5. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Implementation Details We first extract features from the raw audio using a backbone encoder, and then make the predictions described in Section 3 from the extracted features. The encoder converts input audio (mono, 16 kHz) to a frame-based representation, which is a sequence of latent vectors produced at 50 Hz (window size 10s, hop size 5s). For the main experiments, we use BEATs [30] as a backbone encoder. BEATs is an encoder-only transformer, with 12

Dataset	Cls	Dur (h)	Events	Avg dur (s)	Overlap %	Type	Location	Taxa
AnSet[24]	10	26.82	7807	6.23	0.61	TPAM	Brazil	Anura
BV10[25]	1	10.00	9024	0.15	21.68	TPAM	NY, USA	Passeriformes
HawB[26]	9	50.88	55713	1.11	2.54	TPAM	HI, USA	Aves
HbW[27]	1	13.38	4776	0.99	5.07	UPAM	N Pacific	M. novaeangliae
Katy[28]	1	4.49	11961	0.17	12.57	TPAM	Panama	Tettigoniidae
MT[25]	1	1.26	1294	0.15	0.08	On-body	S Africa	S. suricatta
Pow[29]	6	6.42	9919	1.11	6.99	TPAM	PA, USA	Passeriformes
OZF	1	1.08	8504	0.11	17.20	Lab	Lab	T. castanotis

Table 1: Summary of datasets used to evaluate model performance. Terrestrial and underwater passive acoustic monitoring units are abbreviated as TPAM and UPAM, respectively. Avg dur (s): average duration of vocalizations. Overlap %: Number of within-class overlaps divided by number of vocalizations

layers, hidden size 768 and 8 attention heads, pretrained on AudioSet [31]. In Section 5.2, we explore different choices of backbone. The detection, regression and classification predictions are then each made using a linear layer. The loss function hyperparameters were fixed at $\alpha = 2$, $\beta = 4$, and $s = 6$ following [18]. During training and inference, audio is divided into 10-second windows, with 5-second step size between windows. Training lasts for 50 epochs, with the encoder frozen for the first 3 epochs. We use Adam with ams-grad, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, and a cosine annealing scheduler. For all models, we select a learning rate from $\{1e-4, 3e-5, 1e-5\}$, based on mean average precision @0.5IoU on the val set. We apply soft non-maximal suppression [21] with $\sigma = 0.5$.

Datasets In addition to our newly released OZF dataset, we evaluated Voxaboxen using seven existing datasets (Table 1), selected for their taxonomic diversity: amphibians (AnuraSet), insects (Katydid), birds (BirdVox-10h, Hawaiian Birds, Powdermill), and mammals (Humpback, Meerkat). The preprocessing steps we performed on these datasets is described at the project github. For Katy, BV10 and OZF, the events of interest were brief and, for Katy and BV10, often above the 8kHz Nyquist frequency assumed by several of the models we evaluated. For all models, we use a half-time version of BV10 and OZF, and a sixth-time version of Katy. This effectively increases the output frame rate to 100 Hz for BV10 and OZF, and 300 Hz for Katy. Initial experiments indicated that using these slowed-down versions dramatically improved performance.

Evaluation As a metric, we first match predicted events to true events as in [25], only counting matches that exceed a certain IoU threshold. Then, we compute mean average precision (mAP) using 1001 equally-sized intervals. We report results for an IoU threshold of 0.5 and of 0.8.

Comparison Models We compare the performance of Voxaboxen to several frame-based methods. Three of these consist of a linear layer on top of an encoder-only transformer, initialized with pre-trained weights. The encoders are Frame-ATST [7] (25 Hz output frame rate, pretrained on AudioSet), BEATs [30] (50 Hz, pretrained on AudioSet) and BirdAVES [32]¹ (50 Hz, pre-trained on animal sound datasets). Outputs are median filtered, with kernel size (ks) 1, 3, 7, or 11, selected based on mean average precision @0.5IoU on the val set.

As an additional frame-based method, we compare to a convolutional-recurrent neural network (CRNN) [6; 8; 10]. Model inputs are log-mel spectrograms (256 mel bands), and the model consists of a 2d conv layer (ks=7, hidden size 64), mean-pooling in the frequency dimension (ks=2), two 2d residual blocks (ks=3), mean

pooling in both directions (ks=2), and finally a bi-LSTM, with hidden size 1024. The weights are randomly initialized.

Finally, we compare to two existing object detection models coming from computer vision, Faster-RCNN [16] (X-101 model checkpoint pretrained on MS COCO)² and SEDT [33], an encoder-decoder transformer, adapted to detect 1d events from a spectrogram³.

We implement an additional baseline that uses pre-trained source-separation model, BirdMixIT model [19], to separate audio into four stems. These stems are fed into BirdAVES, followed by a linear classification layer fine-tuned on the original (non-separated) data. We combine the four sets of detections and apply soft non-maximal suppression to de-duplicate boxes. We evaluated this method on OZF-synthetic, but based on its performance there did not evaluate it on the other datasets.

5.1. Main Results

As shown in Table 2, Voxaboxen outperforms other methods in almost all cases, and in is far ahead of all other models in several cases, e.g. 10+ points on mAP@0.5 on BV10, HawB, HbW, and Katy. At mAP@0.8, Voxaboxen scores 5+ points ahead of others on BV10, HawB, HbW, MT, and OZF. The diversity of animal sounds in the datasets especially highlights the general effectiveness of our method. Faster-RCNN generally performs well on OZF and MT, and slightly surpasses Voxaboxen on Katy mAP@0.8. However, it struggles with datasets with more than one class (AnSet, HawB, and Pow), as well as HbW. Of the frame-level SED models, Frame-ATST, BEATs and BirdAVES, BEATs is generally the strongest, which is consistent with our findings for the backbone choice in Voxaboxen (see Table 3). SEDT is poor. Pretrained on datasets mostly of ambient city noises, it transfers badly to animal vocalizations.

5.2. Ablation Studies

Table 3 shows the effect of changing the encoder backbone of Voxaboxen, and of removing the forward-backward matching procedure. We found that using BirdAVES as a backbone for Voxaboxen reduced performance compared with the version of that used the BEATs encoder. This was surprising considering BirdAVES was designed specifically for animal sounds; however differences in pre-training data volume and training regimes may explain the performance difference. Removing forward-backward matching (i.e. only using forward predictions) also consistently lowers the mAP scores. Mostly the difference is 1-2 points but larger for some datasets, e.g. HbW and Pow.

²<https://github.com/facebookresearch/detectron2>

³https://github.com/Anaesthesiaye/sound_event_detection_transformer

¹<https://github.com/earthspecies/aves>

Metric	Method	AnSet	BV10	HawB	HbW	Katy	MT	Pow	OZF
mAP@0.5IoU	CRNN	9.89	35.59	22.72	21.03	17.24	82.97	35.45	71.80
	Faster-RCNN	8.06	55.49	7.39	21.66	25.93	84.22	14.08	90.20
	SED	0.18	3.79	2.79	3.95	2.30	18.58	2.71	2.26
	Frame-ATST	14.87	40.62	32.19	33.62	17.88	87.58	45.42	73.48
	BEATs	15.71	48.01	35.37	37.13	20.12	86.08	50.32	77.94
	BirdAVES	14.21	42.09	32.67	26.54	19.11	86.11	43.52	78.33
	Voxaboxen	27.08	77.32	53.87	59.92	36.04	90.96	56.77	97.92
mAP@0.8IoU	CRNN	2.43	12.96	5.04	3.39	1.90	37.10	16.54	30.05
	Faster-RCNN	3.43	29.08	2.24	3.03	9.53	53.54	9.09	69.06
	SED	0.16	0.18	0.12	0.10	0.11	0.13	0.16	0.10
	Frame-ATST	4.72	18.20	10.55	8.28	2.66	24.70	23.44	27.11
	BEATs	5.18	18.98	10.31	9.77	2.93	51.00	27.11	42.27
	BirdAVES	4.52	19.28	9.12	5.14	3.08	48.29	23.04	42.44
	Voxaboxen	9.58	43.03	20.26	22.54	7.86	66.18	35.89	81.23

Table 2: Mean average precision scores at 0.5 and 0.8 IoU. Best results in **bold**. With one exception, Voxaboxen outperforms existing methods, and is sometimes far ahead, for example on BV10, HawB, and OZF.

Metric	Method	AnSet	BV10	HawB	HbW	Katy	MT	Pow	OZF
mAP@0.5IoU	Voxaboxen	27.08	77.32	53.87	59.92	36.04	90.96	56.77	97.92
	with BirdAVES encoder	22.86	46.33	49.22	48.04	26.59	88.78	50.21	96.36
	no fwd-bck matching	25.04	75.97	52.10	56.99	34.97	89.39	50.02	95.77
mAP@0.8IoU	Voxaboxen	9.58	43.03	20.26	22.54	7.86	66.18	35.89	81.23
	w/ BirdAVES encoder	8.64	25.56	18.55	12.22	5.16	56.31	32.31	74.32
	no fwd-bck matching	7.46	37.70	16.82	18.73	7.14	36.22	26.79	80.36

Table 3: Ablation studies on the backbone encoder and the forward-backward matching method. The main model uses the BEATs encoder. Best results in **bold**. Both ablation settings give a moderate, consistent drop in performance, showing the superiority of the BEATs encoder over BirdAVES, and the effectiveness of the Voxaboxen forward-backward matching method.

Fig. 1: mAP on the synthetic portion of our OZF dataset, which comes in six varieties with increasing overlap, ranging from 0 to 1 in increments of 0.2. Existing methods, especially the frame-based BirdAVES and BirdAVES + BirdMixIT, deteriorate as the overlap ratio increases. Voxaboxen is consistently the most accurate and drops only slightly with increasing overlap.

5.3. Performance on OZF-synthetic

Figure 1 shows the performance of Voxaboxen on the synthetic portion of our newly-released OZF dataset, for increasing overlap ratio. Voxaboxen outperforms the comparison models at all overlap ratios, and maintains a high accuracy (92.77 mAP@0.5, 83.19 mAP@0.8), even at the highest over ratio of 1. BirdAVES, with and without BirdMixIT, deteriorates sharply with increasing overlap ratio, consistent with our argument that frame-based methods are insufficient for handling overlapping vocalizations. FasterRCNN fares better than other baselines, but is still firmly behind Voxaboxen.

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, we introduced Voxaboxen, a novel method for sound event detection in bioacoustic recordings, specifically designed to address the challenges posed by overlapping vocalizations. Voxaboxen uses bidirectional predictions of vocalization boundaries combined with a graph-matching algorithm to accurately identify and localize events. To advance evaluation of overlapping vocalization detection, we released a new dataset, OZF, of zebra finch recordings with temporally-strong annotations and frequent overlaps. Extensive testing on seven existing datasets and our new dataset demonstrates that Voxaboxen achieves state-of-the-art performance, with particularly notable improvements over standard SED methods in scenarios with high overlap. This work highlights the potential of Voxaboxen to advance bioacoustic research in ethology, ecology, and conservation.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data used in this study is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/15507508>. The code used in this study is available at <https://github.com/earthspecies/voxaboxen>.

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STEREO SOUND EVENT LOCALIZATION AND DETECTION WITH ONSCREEN/OFFSCREEN CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract—This paper presents the objective, dataset, baseline, and metrics of Task 3 of the DCASE2025 Challenge on sound event localization and detection (SELD). In previous editions, the challenge used four-channel audio formats of first-order Ambisonics (FOA) and microphone array. In contrast, this year’s challenge investigates SELD with stereo audio data (termed stereo SELD). This change shifts the focus from more specialized 360° audio and audiovisual scene analysis to more commonplace audio and media scenarios with limited field-of-view (FOV). Due to inherent angular ambiguities in stereo audio data, the task focuses on direction-of-arrival (DOA) estimation in the azimuth plane (left-right axis) along with distance estimation. The challenge remains divided into two tracks: audio-only and audiovisual, with the audiovisual track introducing a new sub-task of onscreen/offscreen event classification (i.e., classifying whether a detected sound event originates from a source within the limited FOV or outside of it). This challenge introduces the DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset, whose stereo audio and perspective video clips are sampled and converted from the STARSS23 recordings. The baseline system is designed to process stereo audio and corresponding video frames as inputs. In addition to the typical SELD event classification and localization, it integrates onscreen/offscreen classification for the audiovisual track. The evaluation metrics have been modified to introduce an onscreen/offscreen accuracy metric, which assesses the models’ ability to identify which sound sources are onscreen. In the experimental evaluation, the baseline system performs reasonably well with the stereo audio data.

Index Terms—Sound event localization and detection, Acoustic scene analysis, Onscreen/offscreen classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound event localization and detection (SELD) involves identifying sound events, tracking their temporal occurrence, and estimating their spatial direction or position from multichannel audio inputs. This results in a spatiotemporal characterization of the acoustic scene that can be used in a wide range of machine cognition tasks, such as inference on the type of environment, self-localization, navigation with visually occluded targets, tracking of specific types of sound sources, smart-home applications, scene visualization systems, and acoustic monitoring, among others. SELD has received increasing attention since the earliest publications [1]. One of the most significant research efforts on this topic has been centered around the DCASE challenge¹, with the task developing every year in terms of data complexity, data realism, or task complexity.

The first three iterations of the task (2019–2021) [2]–[5] were based on synthetic multichannel audio data that included multichannel ambient noise and reverberation. The data were provided in two types of four-channel audio formats, i.e., first-order Ambisonics (FOA) and tetrahedral microphone array. They were synthesized using multi-room and multi-point spatial room impulse responses (SRIRs) from real spaces, which enabled the synthesis of both static and moving reverberant sound events. The first three challenges considered moving sound events, non-target interfering directional sound events, and overlapping events of the same class. The top-ranked systems in the

three challenges excelled at addressing these issues by employing effective audio features [6], advanced data augmentation strategies [7]–[9], or improved SELD system architectures [10]–[14].

Although those synthetic datasets carefully emulated the acoustical and spatial properties of sound scenes, they lacked some important aspects of real sound scenes, mainly the natural temporal and spatial occurrences and co-occurrences that characterize real sound events, resulting from the scene environment and the actions and interactions of the agents within it. To advance SELD research in that direction, the following three iterations (2022–2024) [15]–[17] were based on a new dataset of spatial recordings of real scenes. The original 32-channel recordings were converted to the two types of four-channel audio formats (i.e., FOA and microphone array) and made available to participants. Annotations of sound event activities for 13 classes were compiled by human listeners and combined with optical tracking data of the source positions that generated those sound events. Eleven hours of such material were collected in multiple rooms in two different sites. In contrast to the class-balanced synthetic datasets of the earlier studies [2]–[5], the real recordings featured highly unbalanced class distributions. To cope with the increased difficulty of the task and the limited amount of training data, participants were allowed to use external data, additional simulations of recordings, and pre-trained models. Additionally, from the DCASE2023 Challenge [16], the 360° video recordings were provided to stimulate further cross-modal developments in SELD research. The full field-of-view (FOV) video data are temporally synchronized and spatially aligned with the audio recordings. The effective integration of audiovisual data [18], [19], the efficient use of external resources [20], [21], and more sophisticated neural network designs driven by attention mechanisms [22], [23] enabled the top participants to achieve competitive results with substantial gains over the baselines.

While the previous iterations used full FOV four-channel audio formats, this year’s task² investigates SELD with stereo audio data (called *stereo SELD*). This change aims to reflect commonplace audio and media scenarios. As stereo audio is a common audio format for media capture or production [24], [25], spatial analysis of stereo audio can be applied to a wide variety of media content [26]–[28]. As the stereo audio format used in the task exhibits angular ambiguity in the top-bottom and front-back directions, the task focuses on direction-of-arrival (DOA) estimation of azimuth angles only along the left-right axis, together with source distance estimation, which has been explored in prior SELD and spatial audio studies [29]–[32]. This challenge remains divided into two tracks: evaluation of stereo SELD models with audio-only input (Track A) or audiovisual input (Track B). Perspective video data are employed to reflect widely used media

¹<https://dcase.community/challenge2025/>

²<https://dcase.community/challenge2025/task-stereo-sound-event-localization-and-detection-in-regular-video-content>

formats. Due to the limited FOV, the audiovisual track poses a new sub-task: onscreen/offscreen classification of the detected sound events, i.e., classifying a sound event as *onscreen* if its source is visible in the video frame, and *offscreen* otherwise. Such prediction can be helpful in further audiovisual processing, such as audio enhancement of objects contained in the video FOV or automated steering of cameras towards target sources outside the FOV.

Adapting the challenge for the stereo SELD task requires modifications at multiple fronts.

- A new DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset³ derived from the STARSS23 dataset [15], [16] extracting limited FOV perspective videos from the omnidirectional 360° videos, and corresponding stereo tracks oriented at the center of those videos from the FOA audio format.
- A baseline system⁴ in an audio-only and audiovisual configuration that processes stereo audio and corresponding video frames as inputs. It outputs sound event labels and horizontal DOAs and distances over time without front or back distinction. The audiovisual baseline additionally outputs an onscreen/offscreen binary label for each detected event.
- The evaluation metrics are adapted to these task changes, with horizontal-only DOA localization errors and an onscreen/offscreen accuracy metric, which assesses the models' ability to identify which sound sources are onscreen.

2. STEREO SELD DATASET

2.1. Overview

This challenge uses the DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset, which comprises stereo audio and perspective video data, derived from the STARSS23 dataset [15], [16]. STARSS23 contains multichannel audio (e.g., FOA) and 360° video recordings of sound scenes in various rooms and environments, together with temporal and spatial annotations of target event classes. The STARSS23's FOA audio and 360° video data have been converted to stereo audio and perspective video data, simulating regular media content. The data construction code for the task is made available⁵.

The DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset is split into a development dataset and an evaluation dataset. The development dataset comprises 30,000 clips of 5-second duration, with a total time of 41.7 hours. The evaluation dataset contains 10,000 clips of 5-second duration, totaling 13.9 hours. We release the development dataset to the public and keep the evaluation one for the challenge evaluation. We provide a training-testing split for consistent reporting of results across systems on the development dataset. The DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset inherits the 13 event classes from STARSS23, including speech, telephone, and water tap. The audio data are formatted as stereo and have a sampling rate of 24 kHz. The video resolution (width:height) is set to 640:360 pixels, with an aspect ratio of 16:9, widely used in media content. The horizontal FOV is set to 100°. The video frames per second (fps) rate is 29.97. Examples of the dataset are shown in Fig 1.

2.2. Data Construction

The DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset is constructed as follows. We first sample 5-second clips from the STARSS23 recordings. Then, we convert the 5-second FOA audio and 360° video to generate stereo audio and perspective video data corresponding to a fixed point of

Fig. 1: Examples of the DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset. In the clip on the left, water is coming out of a faucet on the left, and a woman is speaking from the left of the center. In the middle, from the right of the center, a phone rings, and a man speaks. In the clip on the right, a man is speaking from the left of the center, and music is playing offscreen (from the right).

view. According to the fixed viewing angle, we first rotate the FOA audio [7]. Then, we convert the rotated FOA audio to stereo audio, emulating a mid-side (M/S) recording technique [33]. We convert the 360° video to a perspective video with the same viewing angle as the audio, using a python library⁶. We also rotate the STARSS23's DOA labels to new DOA labels centered at the fixed viewing angle. Rotated azimuth labels that point to the back hemisphere are folded from back to front, considering the front-back ambiguity. The elevation labels are omitted due to top-bottom ambiguity and weak capability of stereo formats to resolve elevation. The distance labels are kept the same as the STARSS23 ones. To get the binary onscreen/offscreen event labels, we compare the new DOA labels with the azimuthal range of the FOV in the perspective video.

The details of the sampling procedure are provided below. For each sampling, we first randomly select a STARSS23 recording file. We employ duration-weighted random choice, i.e., each file has a probability of being selected proportional to its duration. This aims to take a large number of samples from files of long duration. Then, we select a start frame uniformly within each file. We select a horizontal viewing angle uniformly over 360° while keeping the vertical viewing angle at 0° elevation. We repeat the sampling procedure until the desired number of clips have been sampled. We do not control explicitly for the presence of target sound events in the randomly sampled clips. Hence, there is a small number of clips that do not contain any target sound event (2.2 % in the development dataset). We do not consider that to be an issue, as these clips enable the evaluation of false positives. The class distribution across all frames after random sampling is similar to that of STARSS23 [15], [16]. The onscreen/offscreen distribution across all frames is approximately 1:3.

2.3. Audio Format Description

The stereo audio format is derived from the full-sphere FOA format used in the previous iterations of the challenge. For recording details and encoding specifications of the FOA format, refer to the previous task description papers [2]–[4], [15]. The stereo format specification emulates a coincident M/S stereo recording technique using cardioid microphones pointing fully at 90° (left channel) and -90° (right channel). Since any M/S stereo recording configuration can be extracted from FOA signals, in this simple M/S case, they are derived using only the omnidirectional and left-right dipole components of the FOA signals. More specifically, for FOA signals following an ACN/SN3D convention ordered as $[W(n), Y(n), Z(n), X(n)]$, the

³<https://zenodo.org/records/15559774>

⁴https://github.com/partha2409/DCASE2025_seld_baseline

⁵https://github.com/SonyResearch/dcase2025_stereo_seld_data_generator

⁶<https://github.com/sunset1995/py360convert>

stereo signals $[L(n), R(n)]$ are then simply:

$$L(n) = W(n) + Y(n), \quad (1)$$

$$R(n) = W(n) - Y(n), \quad (2)$$

where $W(n)$ is the zeroth-order omnidirectional signal of the FOA audio, and $Y(n)$ is the first-order horizontal (left-right) dipole component [33].

3. BASELINE MODEL

Figure 2 shows the baseline architecture for the stereo SELD task that processes stereo audio and corresponding video frames as inputs. For the audio-only track, we consider the same architecture from the previous edition [17] and for the audiovisual track, onscreen/offscreen classification is integrated into the baseline architecture. For the audio-only track, 64-band log-mel spectrograms are extracted from stereo audio and fed to a convolutional recurrent neural network (CRNN). It consists of three convolutional layers (with 64 filters each), bidirectional gated recurrent unit (GRU) layers, and multi-head self-attention blocks with an attention size of 128 and eight attention heads [17], [22]. For the audiovisual baseline, a pre-trained ResNet-50 model [34] is used to extract visual features at a frame rate of 10 fps. These features are reshaped and combined with audio features through transformer decoder-based fusion layers utilizing cross-attention mechanisms [19], [35]. The fused audiovisual representations are then passed through fully connected layers to obtain final predictions.

The model follows the multi-ACCDOA output format [29], [36], predicting up to three simultaneous sound events per class at each time frame. Each sound event class in the multi-ACCDOA output is represented by three regressors that estimate the Cartesian $[x, y]$ coordinates of the azimuth DOA around the microphone and a distance value. In case of the audiovisual model, there is an additional binary output neuron that predicts whether the sound event is within the video frame or outside of it. The model is trained to minimize mean squared error loss for the DOA and distance predictions, and binary cross-entropy loss for the onscreen/offscreen classification. This baseline architecture offers participants a comprehensive foundation for exploring and advancing SELD techniques suitable for realistic stereo audiovisual contexts.

4. SYNTHETIC DATA TO SUPPORT MODEL TRAINING

To enhance the robustness and generalization of the baseline models, we incorporate synthetic data alongside the development dataset clips. These synthetic examples are generated using publicly available tools designed to simulate realistic spatial sound scenes and video content aligned with the task’s data format.

We use the SpatialScaper library [37], which generates FOA audio by convolving isolated sound samples of known sound types with SRIRs. It additionally generates metadata of the respective annotated sound events including their sound class, onset, offsets, and location. We utilize a curated subset of FSD50K [38] samples that match the target classes of the challenge. The music class is sampled from the FMA dataset [39]. The SpatialScaper scripts and documentation are available in their official repository⁷. Synthetic 360° videos are generated using stock background panoramas and object/person overlays. These visual elements are placed and animated based on the spatial coordinates and timing information from the synthetic SpatialScaper metadata. The code to generate this video is hosted by the SELDVisualSynth project [40] on github⁸.

⁷<https://github.com/iranroman/SpatialScaper>

⁸<https://github.com/adrianSroman/SELDVisualSynth>

Fig. 2: Audiovisual baseline model architecture for the stereo SELD task.

To create training-ready clips from the synthetic data, we apply the same stereo SELD data generation pipeline used for the official real-world dataset. This pipeline converts synthetic FOA audio and 360° video into stereo audio and perspective video based on a specified viewing angle, and prepares metadata accordingly.

5. EVALUATION METRICS

Following last-year decision of reducing the number and complexity of the evaluation metrics [17], this year baseline and submitted models have been evaluated according to their localization-dependent F-score ($F_{20^\circ/1}$) and their classification-dependent DOA estimation error ($DOAE_{CD}$) and relative distance estimation error (RDE_{CD}) computed at frame level. Apart from last-year metrics [17], this year we have introduced an onscreen/offscreen accuracy metric to evaluate the ability of the models to identify which sound sources are onscreen.

As in previous editions [15]–[17], we compute the classification-dependent localization metrics, taking into account only those detections that are correctly classified. For the localization-dependent F-score, we only accept as true positives those detections whose DOA and distance estimations are below a spatial threshold. Additionally, in this challenge, on the audiovisual track, we also require a correct onscreen/offscreen estimation in order to accept estimates as true positives ($F_{20^\circ/1/onoff}$). Following last year [17], the DOA estimation error threshold is 20° and the relative distance estimation error threshold is 1.

The main difference in the evaluation compared to previous editions of the challenge [15]–[17] is in the way we rank the submissions. Since SELD models have to perform a combination of tasks whose various aspects are usually evaluated using different metrics, the global ranking in the previous years was decided by combining the individual rankings of every metric. This strategy seemed to work reasonably

Table 1: SELD performance of the audio-only and audiovisual baseline models on the **development** dataset of the DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset.

	Macro $F_{20^\circ/1}$ (%)	Macro $F_{20^\circ/1/online}$ (%)	DOAE _{CD} (°)	RDE _{CD} (%)	Onscreen/offscreen accuracy (%)
Audio-only	22.8	N/A	24.5	41.0	N/A
Audiovisual	26.8	20.0	23.8	40.0	80.0

Table 2: SELD performance of the audio-only and audiovisual baseline models on the **evaluation** dataset of the DCASE2025 Task3 Stereo SELD Dataset.

	Macro $F_{20^\circ/1}$ (%)	Macro $F_{20^\circ/1/online}$ (%)	DOAE _{CD} (°)	RDE _{CD} (%)	Onscreen/offscreen accuracy (%)
Audio-only	26.1	N/A	23.0	32.3	N/A
Audiovisual	27.5	20.8	22.2	37.7	77.8

Table 3: SELD performance of the models in the evaluation dataset replacing the estimated distance by the average distance of the estimated class on the development dataset.

	Macro $F_{20^\circ/1}$ (%)	Macro $F_{20^\circ/1/online}$ (%)	RDE _{CD} (%)
Perfect detector	98.0	98.0	30.8
AO baseline	26.5	N/A	30.3
AV baseline	27.9	21.1	33.5

well when the number of tasks was limited (sound event detection, classification, and DOA estimation) [15], [16]. However, last year [17], the distance estimation task was additionally introduced and it proved to be a much more challenging one, with the differences between all submitted models being quite narrow. In that case, we observed that combination of rankings based on all metrics can lead to some undesired artifacts. Models with very minor improvements in distance estimation could scale up many positions in the relative distance estimation error ranking, and that could have a very big impact in the final ranking, overtaking models that clearly obtained better results in the other metrics. To avoid this problem, this year, the global ranking is done exclusively according to the localization-dependent F-score. Obtaining a good result in this metric requires a good localization performance due to the spatial threshold and, in for the audiovisual track, we also require a correct onscreen/offscreen estimation, so the localization-dependent F-score effectively evaluates all the SELD tasks.

6. BASELINE RESULTS

The evaluation metric scores of the baseline models on the development and evaluation datasets are given in Table 1 and 2, respectively. While this challenge uses the localization-aware F1-score considering spatial and onscreen thresholds for ranking in the audiovisual track, the F1-score considering only spatial thresholds is also shown for comparing the audiovisual result to the audio-only result.

We can observe how the audiovisual model slightly outperforms the audio-only model in the detection and angular localization metrics, but obtain a worse result for its distance estimation on the evaluation dataset. This shows how integrating the visual information in the SELD problem is still a challenging task even when the audio is reduced to a stereo signal and the image is simplified into a conventional rectangular frame.

7. DATASET BIAS

The proposed dataset contains several biases that can be exploited to perform some estimations without even extracting any information from the audio or audiovisual signals. The most simple example is the onscreen/offscreen estimation. Since the viewing angle was chosen randomly for every clip regardless of their content, 77.5% of the sound sources are offscreen. This shows that the onscreen/offscreen accuracy of the audiovisual baseline is around a random guess adjusted to the data distribution, which again points out that the model is struggling to learn how to exploit the visual information.

The bias on the distance of the sources is a bit more complex since it depends on the class of the audio event. To analyze it, we computed the average distance of the sources of every class in the training set, but the ability of the models to exploit this bias depends on their ability to obtain a correct class estimation. Table 3 shows the distance-dependent metrics for the evaluation dataset that result from replacing the distance estimation by the average distance of the estimated class for a perfect detector and for the two baselines.

We can see how the distance estimation of the baseline models is worse than what they could have achieved by just learning the bias of the dataset, which showcases the difficulty of estimating the distance of a sound source using only stereo audio. We can also observe how the distance estimation has a little impact on the localization-dependent F-score due to the large RDE threshold used when computing it.

8. CONCLUSION

We introduced the stereo SELD task in the DCASE2025 Challenge, including a new audiovisual sub-task focused on onscreen/offscreen event classification. The proposed dataset and baseline demonstrate that stereo SELD is feasible, with initial results indicating promise for practical applications. However, the audiovisual track remains challenging; our baseline suggests that current models underutilize visual information, leaving significant room for improvement. Similarly, distance estimation is still unreliable and warrants further exploration. We hope the community’s participation will drive progress in tackling these challenges and lead to more robust and ecologically valid SELD systems.

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A REVISIT OF AUDIO EVALUATION THROUGH HUMAN IMPRESSIONS: DEFINING AND MODELING A MULTIDIMENSIONAL PERCEPTUAL TASK

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Abstract—Current audio evaluation paradigms predominantly rely on technical metrics or single-dimensional subjective scores. These methods inadequately capture the multifaceted nature of human auditory perception. This paper reframes audio evaluation as a multidimensional perceptual task. We formally define subjective impression as a computational problem with measurable dimensions. To this end, we introduce a new dataset of 4,110 environmental sounds from FSD50K. It is annotated with five perceptual dimensions: pleasantness, clarity, brightness, calmness, and immersion. Our analysis reveals both independence and meaningful correlations within this perceptual space. A notable finding is the strong relationship between pleasantness and calmness. Furthermore, we demonstrate the feasibility of automated impression prediction. Our baseline models use fine-tuned BEATs representations and achieve a mean squared error below 0.7. This value corresponds to an average deviation of less than one point on a seven-point scale. This work provides the foundation for a human-centered evaluation of audio generation systems and sound design. It enables assessment based on nuanced perceptual qualities rather than technical fidelity alone.

Index Terms—Subjective impression, Subjective audio evaluation, Multidimensional perception, Semantic differential, Environmental sound

1. INTRODUCTION

Audio generation systems have been steadily maturing from research prototypes to practical applications. Recent text-to-audio models such as Tango [1], Tango2 [2], Make-An-Audio [3], AudioLDM2 [4], and AudioGen [5] exhibit remarkable technical performance. In addition, ElevenLabs offers a system capable of generating realistic sound effects from textual input, enabling practical use cases [6]. Given these developments, the quantitative evaluation of system performance and generated audio quality is becoming increasingly important.

Current evaluation methods for generated audio comprise technical and subjective assessments. Technical evaluations operate at two levels. Signal-level metrics, such as Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and Perceptual Evaluation of Speech Quality (PESQ), measure acoustic fidelity against a ground-truth signal. In contrast, embedding-level metrics aim to capture higher-level semantic properties. For instance, Fréchet Audio Distance (FAD) [7] measures the distributional similarity between the embeddings of generated audio and those of real-world recordings, while CLAPScore [3] evaluates semantic alignment by computing the similarity between their corresponding audio and text embeddings. On the other hand, subjective evaluations rely on human judgment. The most common method is the Mean Opinion Score (MOS), where listeners rate perceptual quality, often supplemented by tasks that assess the relevance of the audio to a given textual prompt. Crucially, a common thread unites all these approaches: they invariably require a reference for comparison, whether it is a ground-truth signal, a distribution of existing audio, an input text, or a human listener’s internal standard of quality and relevance.

However, humans possess the remarkable ability to evaluate sounds in an absolute, non-referential manner, even when a ground-truth signal or a real-world counterpart does not exist. For instance, an abstract, synthesized sound can consistently evoke rich semantic

impressions such as “brightness,” “clarity,” or “tension” without any direct comparison. Furthermore, this perceptual experience is often multifaceted, allowing for multiple, coexisting interpretations of a single audio clip. This capability stands in stark contrast to existing metrics, which are confined to measuring fidelity or semantic alignment against a predefined reference. Consequently, they are ill-equipped to quantify the intrinsic, absolute qualities of generated audio, offering only a limited perspective on a system’s true capabilities.

Therefore, integrating this human-like, non-referential evaluative capability into assessment frameworks of audio is a crucial next step. Such an approach promises significant benefits. For one, it would enable the meaningful evaluation of novel or abstract sounds for which no ground truth exists. Moreover, it would allow us to move beyond mere fidelity and begin to quantify more elusive yet critical qualities like the “creativity” or “expressiveness” of generative models. Developing a system capable of this absolute quality assessment is thus essential for a more holistic and meaningful evaluation of modern audio generation technologies.

To achieve this, we propose a framework that reframes audio evaluation by defining it as a human-centered, multidimensional perceptual task. Our primary contributions are as follows:

- 1) A formal specification of subjective impression as a computational problem with well-defined, measurable dimensions.
- 2) A dataset of 4,110 environmental sounds, systematically annotated across five key perceptual dimensions using the semantic differential (SD) method.
- 3) An empirical analysis of the dataset that reveals both the independence and the meaningful correlations within this perceptual space.
- 4) Baseline computational models that demonstrate the feasibility of automatically predicting these perceptual impressions directly from audio signals.

This framework represents a transition from metric-based quality assessment to human-centered perceptual task modeling.

2. RELATED WORK

Recent studies have explored various aspects of environmental sound perception, including emotional responses and contextual influences. Research on emotional responses has shown that different acoustic environments evoke feelings such as pleasantness and arousal, with human emotions tracking changes in acoustic features like frequency, intensity, and speed [8]. Furthermore, the role of context, which encompasses spatial, temporal, and functional factors, has been shown to significantly shape how individuals perceive and evaluate soundscapes, highlighting that the same sound can be perceived differently depending on its surrounding environment [9], [10]. To investigate these aspects, methods such as the Semantic Differential (SD) scale [11] or Russell’s Circumplex Model of Affect [12] are adopted to quantify these experiences [13]–[15].

Fig. 1: Histograms of the subjective ratings for each of the five evaluation axes.

Several studies have applied the SD method to examine the impressions of sounds formed by listeners. A line of works conducted listening experiments with 38 pairs of bipolar adjectives grouped into timbral, informational, and affective categories [16], [17]. Another line investigated the prevalence of 12 pairs of representative adjectives in the prior literature [18]. There is another study that analyzed whether addition of visual imagery alters auditory impression [19]. The results of the factor analysis obtained in these investigations converge on three fundamental perceptual dimensions of sound: an aesthetic factor, a brightness factor, and a quantitative factor.

3. DATASET CREATION

3.1. Dataset selection

A dataset was constructed by extending a subset of the FSD50K [20], a large-scale collection of environmental sounds with event-based categorical annotations. To ensure balanced representation across sound categories, 4,110 clips were extracted from both the development set (40,966 clips) and the evaluation set (10,231 clips). This was achieved with a random selection process, by which approximately 8% of the clips from each class were selected. We chose FSD50K as the basis because its clips typically contain a single dominant sound event. This property makes it suitable for investigating relationships between acoustic events and human impressions.

3.2. Five-dimensional impression space

Based on extensive preliminary pilot studies on environmental sound perception, we define the following five evaluation axes that capture distinct aspects of subjective auditory experiences: **Pleasantness** evaluates the hedonic quality of sounds, ranging from pleasant to unpleasant. This dimension captures the fundamental affective response to auditory stimuli. **Clarity** characterizes the perceived sharpness and articulateness of sounds, ranging from clear to indistinct or vague. It may reflect the listener’s ability to resolve and differentiate sound sources. **Brightness** measures the spectral character impression, ranging from bright to dark. This perceptual dimension often encompasses subjective brightness perception beyond simple spectral analysis. **Calmness** evaluates the emotional impacts related to stress and relaxation, ranging from calming to irritating. It captures the potential influence of sounds on listener stress levels and emotional state. **Immersion** assesses the spatial and engaging quality of sounds, ranging from immersive to non-immersive. This dimension may reflect the sound’s ability to create a sense of spatial presence and engagement.

In selecting the above perceptual axes, we first chose one bipolar adjective pair from each of the three groups identified in prior work: timbral, informational, and affective. As a result, we obtained Brightness, Calmness, and Immersion. We made this choice in a deterministic manner to avoid redundancy among axes. After that, we added two further factors, Pleasantness and Clarity, which showed the

Fig. 2: Heatmap of the correlation matrix between the five evaluation axes.

highest contribution ratios reported in [19]. This procedure yielded a five-factor framework.

3.3. Annotation methodology

The SD method was adopted to collect subjective impression annotations. Each audio clip was independently evaluated three times, each by a different annotator who used a seven-point bipolar scale ranging from -3 to +3. The midpoint of this scale, 0, was interpreted as neutral. The annotation process was conducted through a web-based interface that presented each audio clip with five evaluation axes simultaneously.

3.4. Analysis of dataset

Figure 1 depicts the distribution characteristics of our dataset. The majority of dimensions manifest approximately normal distributions, with Clarity and Immersion exhibiting positive skews as a consequence of the superior quality of FSD50K clips.

Figure 2 is a correlation matrix of the five axes. It reveals that there is a strong positive correlation between Pleasantness and Calmness ($r = 0.79$), while pairs of the other three dimensions, such as Pleasantness and Immersion, Clarity and Calmness, Calmness and Immersion, show weak correlations ($|r| < 0.1$). The results suggest the complementary nature of our evaluation framework.

4. PREDICTION MODEL

In order to evaluate the characteristics and effectiveness of our collected dataset, and to demonstrate the feasibility of automated impression prediction, predictive models were constructed that estimate scores for each perceptual dimension by extracted acoustic features. The following section first details the methodologies to transform raw audio data into meaningful representations for machine learning, followed by the architectures of the prediction models.

4.1. Feature extraction

In this study, we extracted two sets of features for different analytical purposes. Conventional acoustic features were used to investigate which specific signal characteristics contribute to each perceptual dimension, with Support Vector Regressor (SVR). In parallel, audio representations from a self-supervised learning (SSL) model were utilized to establish a strong performance benchmark for the regression task.

Conventional acoustic features: Based on previous studies that aim to score musical impressions [21], we extracted a set of conventional audio features from each clip, covering signal energy, spectral shape, rhythm, and timbre. The extracted features are:

- Root Mean Square (RMS) and Zero Crossing Rate (ZCR): mean, standard deviation, and frame-to-frame deviation.
- Spectral centroid, rolloff, and bandwidth: first to fourth moments (mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis).
- Spectral contrast: computed over 7 frequency bands with average and variability.
- Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs): 13 coefficients with their delta and delta-delta derivatives.
- Tempo and beat statistics: beat count, mean interval, and its variation.
- Chroma features: harmonic structure over 12 pitch classes.

All features were normalized to have zero mean and unit variance across samples.

Audio representations from SSL models: The efficacy of SSL models in the domain of audio representation learning has been demonstrated across a range of downstream tasks. In this study, we utilized representations extracted from the pre-trained BEATs model [22] as a feature extractor.

4.2. Models

All models in this study are designed as regression models that output continuous values rather than discrete scores. This design choice enables the models to capture the nuanced gradations in human perception that exist between discrete rating points on the 7-point scale.

Mel-spectrogram Regressor (Baseline): As the primary baseline, we implemented a convolutional regressor that takes mel-spectrograms as input features. To ensure a fair comparison with other models, we scaled its architecture to approximately 90 million parameters. This scale matches that of the model created by fine-tuning the BEATs iter3+ pre-trained model.

Support Vector Regressor (SVR): As another baseline, we adopted an SVR with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel, which is well-suited for modeling non-linear relationships.

Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) regressor: In order to assess the impact of various input representations and model configurations on prediction performance, several Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) regressors were investigated. All MLP models were designed to have a total parameter count of approximately 90 million. The configurations under investigation are listed as follows:

- **Audio:** Uses frozen BEATs audio representations as input.
- **Audio + Label:** Concatenates frozen BEATs audio representations with the 200 FSD50K sound classes.
- **Audio (Fine-tuned):** Fine-tunes the pre-trained BEATs model end-to-end with the MLP regressor, adapting audio representations to the task.
- **Audio + Label (Fine-tuned):** Fine-tunes the pre-trained BEATs model along with the MLP, incorporating concatenated sound classes.

Table 1: Comparison of prediction model performance on the test set (510 samples). All models except SVR are trained on five dimensions simultaneously.

Model	MSE↓	MAE↓	LCC↑	SRCC↑	KTAU↑
Baseline	0.879	0.741	0.519	0.588	0.427
SVR (Average)	1.571	0.988	0.280	0.374	0.281
Audio (Freeze)	0.693	0.665	0.667	0.693	0.517
+ Label	0.723	0.679	0.625	0.675	0.502
Audio (Fine-tuned)	0.691	0.652	0.696	0.705	0.528
+ Label	0.691	0.652	0.695	0.704	0.528
Label Only	1.209	0.871	0.327	0.379	0.265

- **Label Only:** Utilizes only learned embeddings of the 200 FSD50K sound classes as input.

4.3. Training details

The training dataset comprised 3,216 clips (78.2%) for training, 384 clips (9.4%) for validation, and 510 clips (12.4%) for testing. A key difference in our experimental setup was the handling of the five perceptual dimensions. For the SVR baseline, which was trained on the conventional acoustic features, we trained five independent regressors, each of which dedicated to predicting a corresponding single dimension. In contrast, other models were trained to predict all five dimensions jointly from a single model. This multi-output design allows the models to potentially leverage inter-dimensional dependencies during learning.

The baseline and all MLP models and were optimized using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss. Training adopted the AdamW optimizer [23] with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} and weight decay of 0.01. Early stopping based on validation loss was applied to mitigate overfitting.

5. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

5.1. Model prediction results

The performance of the constructed models was evaluated by multiple metrics; Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Spearman’s Rank Correlation Coefficient (SRCC), and Kendall’s Tau (KTAU).

Table 1 summarizes the performance of various models in the test set. The fine-tuned MLP models achieve MSE values around 0.69. Given our 7-point scale ranging from -3 to $+3$, this value indicates that 68% of predictions fall within ± 0.83 scale points of ground truth (assuming normal error distribution). The result demonstrates the practical utility of the model for most applications.

The performance difference between models with and without class labels is marginal (MSE: 0.6909 vs. 0.6914). It suggests that fine-tuned BEATs features already encode substantial semantic information. The label-only model (MSE: 1.2089) performs considerably worse than the audio-based models. This degradation demonstrates that single use of class labels without audio information is insufficient to capture perceptual impressions. Table 2 presents performance across individual impression axes using the best performing model (Audio Fine-tuned). Performance varies considerably between dimensions, with Immersion showing the poorest prediction accuracy (LCC: 0.465) compared to other dimensions. This performance disparity can be partially explained by the distributional characteristics and inter-dimensional relationships observed in our dataset. Pleasantness and Calmness, which share a strong positive correlation, both achieve relatively robust prediction performance with similar error patterns. This suggests that their shared variance may provide mutually reinforcing signals during multi-dimensional training. The distribution characteristics also play a crucial role: Clarity and Immersion both exhibit positive skews in our

Table 2: Performance evaluation across perceptual dimensions using the Audio (Fine-tuned) model. Std. represents the standard deviation of absolute prediction errors.

Dimension	LCC \uparrow	SRCC \uparrow	KTAU \uparrow	MAE \downarrow	Std.
Pleasantness	0.6300	0.5989	0.4492	0.6353	0.8248
Clarity	0.6296	0.6444	0.4760	0.7221	0.9034
Brightness	0.6129	0.6120	0.4515	0.6309	0.8047
Calmness	0.5816	0.5874	0.4332	0.6219	0.7848
Immersion	0.4652	0.4805	0.3440	0.6522	0.8225

Fig. 3: Comparison of Pearson correlation matrices computed from ground-truth scores (Target, left) and Audio (Fine-tuned) model predictions (Preds, right).

dataset (Figure 1), indicating concentration toward higher ratings. This skewed distribution reduces the diversity of training examples across the full perceptual range, particularly for negative ratings, which may contribute to their relatively higher prediction errors.

Figure 3 is a comparison between Pearson correlation matrices computed from ground-truth scores (left) and those matrices based on predictions from the Audio (Fine-tuned) model (right) on the test set. The model largely captures the strong positive correlation between pleasantness and calmness (ground truth: $r = 0.85$, predictions: $r = 0.91$). In particular, dimension pairs with low correlation in ground truth, such as pleasantness–immersion and calmness–immersion, maintain their low correlations similarly in predictions. This demonstrates that our multidimensional simultaneous training successfully captures inter-dimensional dependencies while avoiding unnecessary coupling between independent perceptual axes.

5.2. Feature importance analysis

To identify the acoustic drivers for each perceptual dimension, we treated the analysis as a classification problem. The continuous outputs from each SVR model were discretized into seven classes, and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) was then applied to determine the most discriminative input features for separating these classes.

The analysis revealed dimension-specific acoustic signatures. Brightness was strongly associated with variability in high-frequency components. These fluctuations in spectral energy at higher bands played a key role in how sounds were perceived as bright. Calmness depended on temporal regularity such as rhythm stability and onset variability. It was also related to reduced low-frequency energy, which reflected the soothing impression of steady and less energetic sounds.

5.3. Error analysis

As shown in Figure 4, the predictions track the diagonal most closely near the frequent scores, namely +1 for Clarity and Immersion and 0 for Pleasantness, Brightness, and Calmness. In these regions the ample training data yield small bias and narrow confidence intervals. Toward the scale extremes the mapping contracts: ground-truth values of ± 3 are predicted at about ± 1.5 , and the error bars widen. This regression

Fig. 4: Mean predicted impression scores for each perceptual axis, averaged over discretized target scores. The dashed line represents the ground truth.

to the mean reflects both the scarcity of extreme samples and the quadratic penalty imposed by the mean-squared-error objective. The results indicate that stronger class balancing and ordinal-aware loss functions are required to maintain calibration across the full rating range.

6. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

While our results demonstrate feasibility of automated impression prediction, several limitations exist. First, our dataset derives from FSD50K’s high-quality recordings, which may limit generalizability to real-world audio that often contains overlapping acoustic events and diverse recording conditions. Notably, our annotations are restricted to clips containing a single dominant sound event, whereas ambient sounds in real-world environments typically involve complex mixtures of multiple concurrent sources. Second, the annotation process may reflect cultural or demographic biases despite following established methodology. The performance gap at extreme ratings highlights the sparse training examples at perceptual boundaries. This suggests that specialized data collection strategies would be necessary.

The strong pleasantness–calmness correlation ($r = 0.79$) suggests certain perceptual qualities naturally co-occur, enabling more efficient annotation protocols. Our continuous regression approach captures subtle perceptual gradations lost in discrete categorization, particularly valuable for audio generation systems requiring fine-grained optimization feedback.

In addition, our framework does not exclude degradations such as noise or artifacts; they can be reflected in impression scores through dimensions like clarity, pleasantness, and calmness. It complements fidelity-based metrics by linking potential degradations with broader perceptual impact.

7. CONCLUSION

We have presented a framework that reframes audio evaluation as a multidimensional perceptual task. Our approach moves beyond referential metrics and captures the absolute characteristics of sound. We have created a dataset of environmental sounds with five-dimensional subjective annotations and developed models that have achieved practical prediction accuracy. This success confirms both that human impressions can be formulated as a computational problem and automated assessment is feasible. Our approach opens new possibilities for evaluating audio based on human-centered criteria, not just technical fidelity. For future work, this framework should be extended to broader acoustic domains and integrated with audio generation systems for human-centered optimization.

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Sound Event Detection using Time-frequency Bounding Boxes with a Self-Supervised Audio Spectrogram Transformer

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Abstract—Time-frequency bounding boxes of sound events in audio spectrograms capture essential information across various domains. Nevertheless, previous studies of sound event detection (SED) have focused on detecting temporal boundaries. Although object detection models can be adapted for time-frequency SED, they are intended for image data that exhibit significantly different features compared to audio spectrograms. To address this modality gap, this study employs an audio spectrogram transformer (AST) as the backbone of a detection transformer (DETR). A dataset of whistle sounds from defective wind turbine blades was used for model training and evaluation. The proposed model outperformed a faster region-based convolutional neural network with a residual network backbone, which is an established object detection model. The integration of deformable attention with a multiscale feature pyramid significantly contributed to improving the performance. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of deformable DETR models with an AST backbone for time-frequency SED. Our findings will contribute to advancing time-frequency SED, an area that remains underexplored.

Index Terms—Sound event detection, time-frequency bounding box, audio spectrogram transformer

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound event detection (SED) aims to identify the time boundaries (i.e., onset and offset times) of specific sound events in audio recordings. However, existing research has largely overlooked an important aspect: the frequency ranges of these events. Time-frequency SED (i.e., detecting the time-frequency bounding boxes of sound events in spectrograms) holds significant value across various domains. For instance, in bioacoustics, a fully annotated bird song dataset includes expert-annotated time-frequency bounding boxes [1], [2]. These boxes serve as acoustic units; understanding how acoustic units are organized into higher-level patterns poses a significant challenge [3]. Moreover, in prognostics and health management, characteristic patterns of sound events can reveal valuable information about machine status. In some cases, temporal SED is insufficient as it discards critical information encoded in the frequency domain. Therefore, accurate detection of time-frequency bounding boxes can assist human investigators and enable in-depth analysis using machine learning. Despite its significance, the detection of time-frequency bounding boxes remains largely unexplored.

Object detection models originally developed for images, such as region-based convolutional neural networks (R-CNN) [4]–[6], the You Only Look Once (YOLO) series, and detection transformers (DETR) [7]–[11] can be repurposed for SED by considering audio spectrograms as images, as observed in a few earlier studies. For instance, Faster R-CNN and YOLO have been applied to detect bioacoustic events [12]–[14] and whistle sounds generated by wind turbine blades [15]. Moreover, a one-dimensional variant of DETR was introduced for detecting time boundaries of sound events [16], [17].

However, using object detection models for SED is challenging due to distinct differences between audio and image modalities. One major difference is the absence of color channels in spectrogram data, unlike image data. Previous studies converted audio spectrograms into RGB images using fixed mappings or learnable pointwise convolution layers, introducing unnecessary arbitrariness

Fig. 1: Example of sound events in spectrogram

and complexity. Another significant issue arises from the feature extraction networks (i.e., backbones). Most object detection models employ pre-trained backbones from large-scale image datasets, such as a residual network (ResNet) [18], which are ill-suited for audio spectrograms because of their unique patterns. Unlike images, the dimensions of spectrograms represent physical properties (time and frequency). Consequently, standard image augmentation methods such as flipping, rotation, scaling, shearing, and translation are not directly applicable to spectrograms.

To bridge the modality gap, we employ audio spectrogram transformers (AST) [19]–[25] as the backbone of our model. AST models, tailored for audio spectrograms and based on the vision transformer (ViT) architecture, are trained on large-scale audio datasets, such as AudioSet [26]. Hence, they effectively replace conventional backbone models designed for image processing in time-frequency SED. Specifically, we examine a DETR with improved denoising anchor boxes (DINO) [11] and a self-supervised AST model named efficient audio transformer (EAT) [25] for detecting time-frequency bounding boxes in audio spectrograms.

As an example of time-frequency SED, we focus on detecting surface defects on wind turbine blades. Such defects, including cracks and holes, generate sharp whistle-like aerodynamic noises, indicating potential structural issues [15], [27]–[29]. Figure 1 illustrates an example of the sound events to be detected in spectrograms. In-depth information about defects, including their severities, could be estimated from sound event characteristics, such as the duration, frequency center, bandwidth, and peak shape in the spectrograms. Hence, detecting the time-frequency bounding boxes of these whistle sounds, as opposed to merely identifying their time boundaries, is key. The audio signals generated by the wind turbine blades are captured using microphones mounted at the base of the turbine towers.

Fig. 2: Structure of proposed model. The left- and right-bottom boxes show the detailed structure of the audio spectrogram transformer (AST) and detection transformer (DETR) models, respectively.

This damage detection method, based on acoustic signals, enables cost-effective, non-destructive, and continuous monitoring of blade conditions.

This study elucidates time-frequency SED, a relatively under-explored area despite its significance. We demonstrate that using an AST model as the backbone for DETR models enhances the detection of sound events in audio spectrograms. The findings in this study could advance time-frequency SED as a fundamental technique across various domains, such as environmental sound recognition, bioacoustics, prognostics, and health management.

2. MODEL

The proposed model integrates an AST backbone with a DETR model, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The model receives a spectrogram as input and outputs the positions and scores of the detected bounding boxes.

For the backbone, we employ EAT, a self-supervised AST model [25]. The AST model partitions the input spectrogram into patches. The encoder extracts the latent audio representations for each patch. During self-supervised training, some patches are randomly masked, and the decoder reconstructs the original spectrogram from the latent representation. Only the pre-trained encoder is used as the backbone of the proposed model without masking. Thus, the outputs of the AST backbone are the latent representations yielded from the final layer of the encoder.

These latent representations are transformed into a multiscale feature pyramid before being input into the DETR model. This method builds on a previous study that applied ViT for object detection [30]. One limitation of ViT and AST is that they produce single-scale latent representations, which hinders their application in this field. However, the multiscale feature pyramid effectively addresses this limitation without tailoring the backbone architecture a priori during pre-training.

We use DINO [11], an extension of DETR, for the detection model. DETR is an end-to-end object detection model with an encoder-decoder structure. The multiscale feature pyramid is fed to the DETR encoder, projected to the same dimension, augmented with positional embeddings, flattened, and concatenated across scales. The decoder, using a fixed learnable object queries, attends to the encoder’s output. Finally, a feed-forward network, called the detection head, predicts each object query’s position and classification scores. The bounding box positions are specified by the time center, duration, frequency center, and bandwidth. Notably, a “no object” class is included in the object classes. As we do not differentiate between sound event classes,

the detection head outputs whether each bounding box represents a sound event. The overall model yields the bounding boxes and scores for the detected sound events.

3. DATA

3.1. Recording

We collected recordings of sounds produced by land-based wind turbines at two locations for 64 days over a year. A waterproof box housing eight micro-electro-mechanical microphones was mounted at the tower’s base. Audio signals of 180 to 900 s durations were recorded intermittently at intervals of at least 15 min at a sampling rate of 48 kHz and bit depth of 16. Consequently, 6,026 audio clips totaling 1,147 h were recorded. After the recording, minimum variance distortion-free response beamforming was applied to enhance the sounds generated by the blades.

3.2. Data selection

All recordings were split into 15-second segments. Subsequently, 4,210 segments were selected to balance the following factors: recording date, average spectral flatness over time, standard deviation of loudness over time, and the score for the presence of whistle sounds. The scores were estimated by an audio classification model trained using 240 randomly selected short segments, binary-labeled for the presence or absence of whistle sounds. An attention-based convolutional recurrent neural network [31] was then trained using this small dataset, achieving an area under the precision–recall curve of 0.94 using 5-fold cross-validation. This model was used only to select the data to be annotated.

3.3. Annotation

After data selection, nine reliable crowd workers annotated the spectrograms with time-frequency bounding boxes of whistle sounds. Each short segment was annotated by one worker under the supervision of a single overseer. We compiled 1,843 audio clips, each lasting 15 s, containing 14,420 time-frequency bounding boxes. Notably, we did not distinguish patterns of sound events because the class structure of surface defects on wind turbine blades is unknown. Moreover, the characteristics of whistle sounds are significantly affected by the defect shapes and surrounding environments, including the blade rotation speeds and wind speeds. Therefore, in contrast to conventional object detection tasks, our dataset features only one target class.

Fig. 3: Distribution of the number of sound events per audio clip

Fig. 4: Distribution of center frequencies

3.4. Analysis

The distribution of the number of annotated bounding boxes per audio clip is shown in Fig. 3. The mean and maximum number of sound events per audio clip are 7.8 and 35, respectively. As described in Section 4.1, we set the number of object queries to 100, which is sufficient for detecting all sound events in a given audio clip in unseen environments. The distribution of the frequency center of the sound events is shown in Fig. 4, with occurrences between 2 and 20 kHz. Therefore, we maintained a sampling rate of 48 kHz in our experiments to ensure that the observed sound events are not lost. The distributions of the duration and bandwidth of the sound events are shown in Fig. 5. As described in Section 4.1, we set the AST patch size to 16 (measured in the number of time-frequency bins) and window shift to 10 ms. Considering this setup, the bounding box width (i.e., the duration of the sound events) is large, and the height (i.e., bandwidth) is small. Hence, low resolution is sufficient in the time direction, but high resolution is crucial in the frequency direction. These characteristics necessitate a multiscale feature pyramid in the model architecture.

4. EXPERIMENTS

We trained and evaluated the proposed DINO with EAT model on wind turbine audio data. A Faster R-CNN [6] with a ResNet [18] backbone served as the baseline. This architecture and its lightweight variants have been applied in prior time-frequency SED studies [12]–[15]. Moreover, an ablation study assessed the effects of dynamic

Fig. 5: Distribution of bounding box sizes. Bandwidths are measured in terms of the number of frequency bins.

Table 1: Results of time-frequency SED

Model	Backbone	AP ₅₀
Faster R-CNN	ResNet	0.365
Faster R-CNN	EAT	0.370
DINO	ResNet	0.452
DINO	EAT	0.494

anchor boxes [8], query denoising [9], multiscale feature pyramids [30], and deformable attention [10], with the backbone fixed to EAT.

4.1. Setup

The audio data were split into 15-second segments, converted to log-Mel spectrograms using the short-time Fourier transform with a 25 ms window size and a 10 ms shift, resulting in 182 frequency bins. Unlike in most previous studies on SED, the audio data maintained a 48 kHz sampling rate, yielding spectrogram sizes of $(T, F) = (1498, 182)$.

For the baseline, we employed ResNet-50 with a depth of 50, while the proposed model used an EAT model based on ViT-B/16. A patch size of 16×16 is commonly used in ASTs. The latent representation dimension was $C = 768$, resulting in a shape of $(C, \lfloor T/16 \rfloor, \lfloor F/16 \rfloor) = (768, 93, 11)$. We pre-trained the EAT backbone on the public AudioSet [26] dataset at a 48 kHz sampling rate, rather than using a public model pre-trained at 16 kHz. Moreover, we substituted the one-dimensional sinusoidal positional encoding with two-dimensional encoding. The durations of the audio clips in AudioSet and the wind turbine audio dataset were 10 and 15 s, respectively. The difference in duration was bridged by extending the positional embedding along the time direction during fine-tuning, as described in [23]. The $1/16$ scale latent representations were converted into a multiscale feature pyramid scaled to $\{1/32, 1/16, 1/8, 1/4\}$, following [30]. In DETR, the number and dimension of object queries were set to 100 and 256, respectively, with other setups based on the original work that proposed DINO [11].

The ResNet backbone, Faster R-CNN, and DETRs, except the detection head, were initialized using pre-trained weights from the common objects in context (COCO) dataset [32]. The backbone was not frozen during training. The wind turbine audio data were randomly divided into training, validation, and test sets at a ratio of 7:1:2. The validation set was used to identify the best epoch. For evaluation, we followed the standard evaluation method for the COCO dataset. Specifically, the performance was measured using average precision at an intersection of union (IoU) threshold of 50%, denoted as AP₅₀.

Table 2: Results of ablation study

Model	DAB	DN	MFP + Deformable	AP ₅₀
DETR				0.296
DAB-DETR	✓			0.326
DN-DAB-DETR	✓	✓		0.354
Deformable DETR			✓	0.405
DINO	✓	✓	✓	0.494

DAB: Dynamic anchor box, DN: Query denoising, MFP: Multiscale feature pyramid, Deformable: Deformable attention.

4.2. Results

In this section, we present the findings of our experiments. The experimental results in Table 1 show that the proposed DINO with EAT model outperformed the baseline models (Faster R-CNN with ResNet). Moreover, the EAT backbone significantly improved the performance of DINO, while the magnitude of improvement was marginal for Faster R-CNN. This result indicates that using AST as a backbone effectively adapts object detection models for audio spectrograms.

The results of the ablation study are summarized in Table 2. According to the experimental results, the deformable attention with a multiscale feature pyramid significantly contributed to the improved performance. Dynamic anchor boxes and query denoising further improved the performance when used with deformable attention. As described in Section 3.4, our data contained small bounding boxes relative to the backbone’s latent representation resolution. The multiscale feature pyramid mitigated this issue, consistent with prior research [30]. Notably, deformable attention was proposed to reduce complexity and improve learning convergence associated with multiscale features [10]. Our results affirm that these methods are effective not only for object detection in images but also for time-frequency SED.

4.3. Error analysis

The distribution of the detected bounding box displacements from the actual boxes is shown in Fig. 6. Predictions with scores over 0.5 were counted without applying an IoU threshold. We observed relatively large misplacements compared with typical object detection in images. This result supports the observation that the boundaries of the sound events are blurred and difficult to determine. Hence, setting the IoU threshold to a small value is feasible.

Examples of sound events detected by the human annotators and the proposed model are shown in Fig. 7. Two main errors are observed: First, a single human-annotated box is detected as multiple boxes. Second, multiple human-annotated boxes are detected as one. These misdetections stem from difficulty distinguishing sound event units within complex spectrogram patterns.

5. CONCLUSION

This study elucidates time-frequency SED, which has remained under-explored despite its significance. We adopted object detection models for time-frequency SED, employing an AST backbone to remove the modality gap between image and audio. The experimental results demonstrated that DINO with EAT outperforms the conventional Faster R-CNN with ResNet baseline. The ablation study revealed that the multiscale feature pyramid and deformable attention effectively mitigate resolution issues and enhance performance. These findings indicate the effectiveness of self-supervised ASTs as the backbone of deformable DETRs for time-frequency SED, which can advance research on time-frequency SED in various applications.

Fig. 6: Distribution of bounding box misalignment relative to the actual duration and bandwidth

Fig. 7: Examples of detection errors

This research can be extended considering the following aspects. One primary challenge in time-frequency SED is data scarcity. Research on semi-supervised learning to utilize unlabeled and weakly labeled data is a promising direction, as demonstrated in prior studies on object detection in images [33] and temporal SED [17]. Transfer learning is another promising approach. For instance, knowledge learned from the acoustic data of various species, such as birds, frogs, insects, and marine mammals, can be transferred to prognostics and vice versa. Fully annotated bioacoustic datasets, such as BirdCLEF [1] and BirdSet [2], are available for this purpose. Moreover, developing efficient methods for merging and splitting bounding boxes can aid in addressing ambiguities in distinguishing sound event units.

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A Lightweight Temporal Attention Module for Frequency Dynamic Sound Event Detection

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Abstract—Recent advances in Sound Event Detection (SED) have leveraged frequency-dynamic convolution to address the shift-variant nature of audio representations in the frequency domain. However, most existing methods overlook the temporal importance of individual frames during early feature extraction, which is critical for accurate event boundary detection. In this paper, we propose a lightweight temporal attention module integrated into convolutional SED architectures. The module computes temporal weights by compressing the frequency axis and applying per-frame attention using one of three strategies: MLP (frame-wise), Conv1D (local context), and MultiHead Attention (global context). These weights are injected either before or after the convolutional operation to enhance time-sensitive representations. Through comprehensive ablation experiments on the DCASE2021 Task4 dataset, we show that introducing temporal attention, with only about a 1% increase in parameters, consistently improves model performance. Specifically, averaged over 10 independent runs, the proposed temporal attention module increases PSDS1 from 0.4241 to 0.4383 on FDY-CRNN, from 0.4327 to 0.4395 on DFD-CRNN, and from 0.4376 to 0.4452 on MDFD-CRNN. These improvements demonstrate that even lightweight attention mechanisms targeting temporal saliency can significantly enhance the event boundary modeling capabilities of frequency-dynamic SED systems.

Index Terms—Sound event detection, frequency dynamic convolution, temporal dynamic attention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound Event Detection (SED) involves identifying and temporally localizing acoustic events within audio recordings, serving as a critical component for various applications such as audio surveillance, urban sound monitoring, and multimedia indexing [1]–[6]. Deep neural networks, particularly convolutional recurrent neural networks (CRNNs), have emerged as the predominant approach in the SED domain due to their powerful capability to simultaneously capture spatial (frequency) patterns and temporal (time) dependencies from audio spectrogram representations [7] [8]. Despite these advances, accurately identifying the temporal boundaries of audio events continues to be challenging, posing significant limitations to event localization precision and overall detection performance.

Recent research in this area has largely focused on enhancing the frequency-adaptive properties of convolutional neural networks, specifically addressing the shift-variant nature of audio signals along the frequency domain. For example, Frequency Dynamic Convolution (FDY-CRNN) dynamically generates convolutional kernels customized for different frequency bands, substantially improving feature extraction and event classification accuracy [9]. Extensions of this approach, such as Dilated Frequency Dynamic Convolution (DFD-CRNN) [10] and Multi-Dilated Frequency Dynamic Convolution (MDFD-CRNN) [11], have introduced convolution kernels with varying dilation rates. These methods effectively expand receptive fields and enhance spectral coverage, thereby further increasing robustness. However, a significant limitation remains: these frequency-focused techniques implicitly assume uniform temporal importance across all frames, neglecting the distinct temporal significance of individual frames, especially those crucial to precise event boundary detection.

Fig. 1: The proposed architecture of frequency dynamic convolution with temporal attention branch integrated before convolution.

While [9] explored a *Temporal Dynamic Convolution* (TDY) variant, they found it offered little standalone benefit, attributing this to the bi-directional GRU layer in CRNN already modeling sequential dependencies. Their focus was limited to either frequency or temporal attention. We believe that simultaneously addressing both in early convolutional feature extraction will significantly boost Sound Event Detection (SED) performance.

To overcome this limitation, this paper introduces an explicit, lightweight temporal attention module designed to be seamlessly integrated into existing frequency dynamic convolution frameworks, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The proposed module explicitly emphasizes informative temporal segments by first compressing the frequency dimension through pooling operations, followed by applying a temporal attention mechanism that assigns distinct attention weights to individual time frames. To comprehensively explore the temporal context, we evaluate three attention strategies: a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) focusing on frame-level weighting without context, a one-dimensional convolutional network (Conv1D) capturing local temporal relationships, and Multi-Head Attention mechanisms that model global temporal dependencies. Importantly, our architectural design clearly separates the temporal attention branch from the frequency dynamic convolution branch, effectively mitigating potential interference between frequency-adaptive and temporal weighting operations.

Comprehensive experiments conducted on the DCASE2021 Task4 dataset validate the effectiveness and generalizability of our proposed approach. Averaged over ten independent experimental runs, the integration of the proposed temporal attention module consistently results in substantial performance improvements across multiple frequency dynamic convolution architectures with a minimum in-

crease in parameters. Specifically, we observe absolute PSDS1 score improvements from 0.4241 to 0.4383 for FDY-CRNN, from 0.4327 to 0.4395 for DFD-CRNN, and from 0.4376 to 0.4452 for MDFD-CRNN. These significant enhancements confirm that explicitly incorporating temporal saliency into frequency-dynamic convolutional architectures markedly improves the precision of sound event boundary localization without introducing substantial computational complexity.

2. METHODS

Our proposed framework integrates an explicit temporal attention mechanism into frequency dynamic convolution (FDY-Conv) architectures, enhancing temporal feature extraction while retaining frequency-adaptive capabilities. The overall approach consists of two main components: (1) Integration with frequency dynamic convolution, and (2) computation of temporal attention weights.

2.1. Integration with Frequency Dynamic Convolution

We explore two different integration strategies for incorporating temporal attention: before and after the frequency dynamic convolution layer. These are shown in Fig. 2 and can be described as follows:

Before Frequency-Dynamic Convolution: In this strategy, temporal attention weights are applied directly to the input features prior to frequency-dynamic convolution. Given the input feature tensor $X \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C_{in} \times T \times F}$, the attention weight tensor $A \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C_{in} \times T \times 1}$ is computed and then element-wise multiplied with the input in a residual manner:

$$X' = X \odot (1 + A), \quad (1)$$

where B , C_{in} , T , and F represent the batch size, input channels, time dimension, and frequency dimension, respectively. The symbol \odot signifies element-wise multiplication, with broadcasting applied along the frequency dimension. This approach aims to enhance the temporal saliency of input features before subsequent frequency-specific convolution operations.

After Frequency Dynamic Convolution. In contrast, this strategy applies temporal attention weights after frequency dynamic convolution, emphasizing frames based on convolutional output features. Specifically, given convolutional output features $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C_{out} \times T \times F}$, attention weights $A \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C_{out} \times T \times 1}$ are computed and applied:

$$Y' = Y \odot (1 + A), \quad (2)$$

highlighting important temporal frames after frequency adaptation. Here, C_{out} denotes the output channels of convolution.

2.2. Computation of Temporal Attention Weights

Our temporal attention module, illustrated in the lower (temporal) branch of Fig. 1, processes information in two key stages: first, frequency-axis pooling, and then temporal attention calculation.

Pooling over Frequency: To compress the frequency dimension, we experiment with three simple pooling methods: mean pooling, max pooling, and the combined (mean+max) pooling strategy. Formally, given input features $X \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C \times T \times F}$, pooling across the frequency dimension yields $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C \times T}$ as:

$$Z_{mean} = \frac{1}{F} \sum_{f=1}^F X_{:, :, :, f}, \quad (3)$$

$$Z_{max} = \max_{f \in [1, F]} X_{:, :, :, f}, \quad (4)$$

$$Z_{mean+max} = Z_{mean} + Z_{max}. \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2: Two integration strategies for the temporal attention module: before and after frequency dynamic convolution.

These pooling methods provide compact temporal representations for subsequent attention calculations.

Temporal Attention Module: We evaluate three different attention strategies: MLP, Conv1D, and Multi-Head Attention.

(1) **MLP-based Attention:** The simplest method applies a frame-wise multilayer perceptron (MLP) independently on each temporal frame:

$$A = \sigma(\text{MLP}(Z)), \quad A \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C \times T}, \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ denotes the sigmoid activation, ensuring attention values within (0,1). The *MLP* itself consists of two feed-forward layers with a ReLU activation function positioned between them.

(2) **Conv1D-based Attention:** This strategy leverages 1D convolutions to capture local temporal contexts by convolving across neighboring frames. Our current configuration for the Conv1D-based attention module consists of a sequence of operations: an initial 1D convolution layer Conv1D_{in} , followed by Batch Normalization (BN), a ReLU activation function, and finally another 1D convolution layer Conv1D_{out} .

The overall attention mechanism can be expressed as:

$$A = \sigma(\text{Conv1D}_{out}(\text{ReLU}(\text{BN}(\text{Conv1D}_{in}(Z))))), \quad A \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C \times T} \quad (7)$$

This method effectively exploits local temporal continuity, thereby emphasizing temporally coherent segments within the feature sequence.

(3) **Multi-Head Attention:** This global strategy employs self-attention across all temporal frames, explicitly modeling global temporal relationships. With positional encoding P , the attention computation is defined as:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V, \quad (8)$$

where Q, K, V are query, key, and value matrices obtained from linear transformations of $(Z + P)$, and d_k is the dimensionality of the keys. The final attention weight A is derived by aggregating outputs across multiple attention heads:

$$A = \sigma(W_o [\text{head}_1; \text{head}_2; \dots; \text{head}_h]), \quad (9)$$

where W_o is the final linear projection, and each head independently computes self-attention as defined above. This method effectively

captures global temporal dependencies and enhances model sensitivity to event boundaries.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUPS

3.1. Implementation Details

The experiments are conducted on the *Domestic Environment Sound Event Detection* (DESED) dataset [12]. This dataset comprises synthetic strongly labeled data, real weakly labeled data, and real unlabeled data. All audio recordings are 10 seconds long and sampled at 16 kHz.

For audio feature extraction, log-mel spectrograms are generated. This process involves a Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) with an FFT size of 2048, a hop length of 256, and a Hamming window. Subsequently, a mel filterbank with 128 mel bins is applied to the STFT magnitude to produce the final spectrogram representation.

Data augmentation methods employed in this work include frame shifting [12], mixup [13], time masking [14], and FilterAugment [15]. We apply a 7-frame median filter as a post-processing step to all classes. While class-specific filtering could optimize results further, we use a fixed-length filter across all classes to ensure a fair, post-processing-minimized comparison among models.

Our baseline model is the FDY-CRNN, which consists of seven convolutional layers. The first layer utilizes conventional 2D convolution, while the remaining six layers employ Frequency Dynamic Convolution (FDY conv). Other training parameters align with those of the original FDY-conv or its variants, with the key distinction being the addition of our proposed explicit temporal attention branch. Specifically, for the MLP-based and Conv1D-based temporal attention variants, the hidden dimensionality of the first layer is set to $\frac{1}{4}C_{in}$. In the Multi-Head Attention configuration, we use two heads with an attention dimension of 32 and a dropout rate of 0.1.

Models are trained for up to 200 epochs with a batch size of 48. Experiments for FDY-CRNN and DFD-CRNN are conducted on a single NVIDIA P100 GPU, whereas MDFD-CRNN experiments are trained on an NVIDIA V100 GPU.

3.2. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate SED performance, the polyphonic sound detection score (PSDS) was used [16]. For DCASE Challenges 2021-2023 Task 4, two types of PSDS were utilized [17]. PSDS1 emphasizes the accuracy of event boundaries, rewarding systems that produce precise onset and offset timestamps. In contrast, PSDS2 is more tolerant to minor temporal deviations and focuses on reducing cross-triggering errors.

In our experiments, the **sum of PSDS1 and PSDS2** serves as the primary optimization objective. To ensure statistical robustness, each model configuration is trained independently ten times. We report the average PSDS1 and PSDS2 scores, alongside the intersection-based F1 score (IN-F1). Adhering to the mean teacher framework established in the DCASE challenge baseline [18] [19], we employ a teacher-student training strategy. All reported results are derived from the teacher model’s predictions, providing a consistent and fair basis for comparing different model architectures.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Overall Results

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed temporal attention module, comprehensive experiments were conducted on the DESED dataset. The results obtained by integrating different temporal attention strategies (MLP, Conv1D, Multi-Head Attention) and pooling methods (mean, max, mean+max) are summarized in Table 1, using the FDY-CRNN baseline model for comparison.

Table 1: Comparison of temporal attention integration strategies, attention types, and pooling methods on FDY-CRNN.

Integration	AttnType	Pooling	PSDS1	PSDS2	IN-F1
Baseline	–	–	0.4241	0.6516	0.7263
Before	Conv1D	max	0.4213	0.6413	0.7346
	Conv1D	mean	0.4360	0.6635	0.7475
	Conv1D	mean+max	0.4286	0.6551	0.7397
	MLP	max	0.4303	0.6459	0.7356
	MLP	mean	0.4383	0.6604	0.7427
	MLP	mean+max	0.4321	0.6525	0.7433
	MultiHead	max	0.4276	0.6452	0.7376
	MultiHead	mean	0.4244	0.6408	0.7399
	MultiHead	mean+max	0.4258	0.6508	0.7372
After	Conv1D	max	0.4129	0.6249	0.7197
	Conv1D	mean	0.4352	0.6493	0.7436
	Conv1D	mean+max	0.4189	0.6314	0.7252
	MLP	max	0.4245	0.6540	0.7388
	MLP	mean	0.4304	0.6569	0.7378
	MLP	mean+max	0.4267	0.6514	0.7346
	MultiHead	max	0.4285	0.6444	0.7310
	MultiHead	mean	0.4349	0.6533	0.7424
	MultiHead	mean+max	0.4366	0.6498	0.7376

Overall, the introduction of explicit temporal attention consistently improves model performance relative to the baseline FDY-CRNN model across various metrics when utilizing mean pooling strategies. The best performing configuration integrates temporal attention before frequency dynamic convolution, employing mean pooling combined with either Conv1D or MLP-based attention. Specifically, the *before*-Conv1D-mean and *before*-MLP-mean configurations achieve the highest PSDS1 and PSDS2 scores. We attribute this superiority to their balanced ability to capture local temporal contexts (Conv1D) and individual frame-level temporal emphasis (MLP). Additionally, mean pooling appears most effective, likely due to its stable and representative summarization of spectral information across frequency bins.

4.2. Ablation Study

To further investigate the contribution of each design choice, we perform detailed ablation analyses:

Integration Strategies: As evidenced in Table 1, the placement of the temporal attention module significantly impacts performance. Specifically, integrating temporal attention *before* FDY-Conv consistently outperforms the *after* placement in both the **Conv1D-based** and **MLP-based attention** variants. This observation suggests that applying frame-level or local temporal attention directly to the input features facilitates a more effective pre-selection of temporally salient frames. This, in turn, guides the subsequent frequency-dynamic convolution towards more relevant temporal segments. Conversely, applying attention after FDY-Conv might inadvertently overemphasize features already shaped by the convolution, potentially limiting the model’s adaptive capacity.

A contrasting trend is observed for the **Multi-Head Attention** variant, where the *after* configuration achieves higher PSDS scores than its *before* counterpart. We hypothesize that performing global self-attention directly on raw input features tends to homogenize the time dimension, potentially smoothing out critical local energy peaks that FDY-Conv relies on for adaptive frequency filtering. Deferring this global re-weighting step until after convolution allows the model to first distill discriminative local time-frequency structures. Only then is their overall temporal prominence adjusted, effectively balancing local selectivity with broader global context.

Pooling Methods: Among pooling methods, mean pooling consistently achieves the best overall performance, surpassing both max pooling and combined mean+max pooling. While max pooling can

Fig. 3: Quantitative comparison of event-based F1 scores for each sound event class w/ and w/o the temporal attention branch.

Fig. 4: Visualization of temporal attention variations for audio sample of "alarm" and "dog" event.

overly focus on peak activations, potentially introducing instability, mean pooling provides a stable frequency representation beneficial for robust temporal weighting. Interestingly, combining mean and max pooling does not yield additional performance benefits, indicating that the simplicity and robustness of mean pooling alone are sufficient.

Attention Types. Comparing attention mechanisms, Conv1D and MLP consistently outperform Multi-Head Attention. This could be explained by the simplicity and locality advantages of Conv1D and MLP, which sufficiently capture essential temporal patterns without overly complex global relationships. The Multi-Head Attention, despite theoretically stronger global context modeling, might introduce unnecessary complexity and potential overfitting given the dataset size and task complexity.

In conclusion, our detailed experiments validate that a simple, explicit temporal attention module effectively improves temporal boundary localization in sound event detection, with the optimal configuration involving integration before frequency convolution, mean pooling, and either Conv1D or MLP-based attention modules.

4.3. Analysis and Discussion

To better understand the contribution of the proposed temporal attention module, we conduct both quantitative and qualitative analyses. Class-wise event-based F1 scores, shown in Fig. 3, reveal that the temporal attention mechanism yields notable improvements for transient and short-duration events such as *alarm_bell_ringing*,

Table 2: Impact of temporal attention module with different attention types on various frequency dynamic convolution architectures.

Model	AttnType	Params	PSDS1	PSDS2	IN-F1
FDY-CRNN	–	11.061M	0.4241	0.6516	0.7263
	MLP	11.172M	0.4383	0.6604	0.74277
DFD-CRNN	–	11.061M	0.4327	0.6624	0.7314
	Conv1D	11.281M	0.4395	0.6620	0.7432
MDFD-CRNN	–	18.157M	0.4376	0.6504	0.7416
	MLP	18.365M	0.4452	0.6613	0.7435

blender, *cat*, and *dog*. These types of events are typically characterized by sharp onsets and brief durations, making precise temporal boundary modeling essential. By dynamically adjusting the importance of individual frames, our module appears to enhance the network’s sensitivity to critical onset and offset regions, leading to more accurate event localization.

In contrast, obvious performance degradation is observed for long-duration and relatively stationary events such as *electric_shaver_toothbrush* and *frying*. These events tend to exhibit stable and continuous spectral characteristics over time. In such cases, uniform temporal weighting may already be sufficient, and the introduction of temporal modulation might introduce unnecessary variability, potentially disrupting stable temporal features.

We further examine the effectiveness of the proposed attention mechanism. Visual inspection of the learned temporal attention weights shows that our module consistently assigns higher importance to frames near event onsets and/or offsets, especially for short-duration events such as “alarm” and “dog”, as illustrated in Fig. 4. This indicates that the model successfully learns boundary-aware temporal cues, which helps enhance event localization accuracy.

4.4. Performance on FDY-Conv and Its Variants

Table 2 presents the optimal configurations for integrating our proposed temporal attention module (“before” integration with mean pooling) across different FDY-Conv variants. Clearly, the inclusion of explicit temporal attention consistently enhances performance metrics (PSDS1, PSDS2, and IN-F1) across all architectures. Specifically, FDY-CRNN achieves an absolute PSDS1 improvement of 1.42%, DFD-CRNN of 0.68%, and MDFD-CRNN of 0.76%. These notable improvements underscore the general applicability and effectiveness of temporal attention in diverse frequency-dynamic convolution frameworks.

Furthermore, the additional parameter overhead introduced by our attention module is minimal, ranging approximately from 1.00% (FDY-CRNN) to 1.15% (DFD-CRNN) and 1.15% (MDFD-CRNN). This modest increment demonstrates the computational efficiency of our attention mechanism, validating its practical utility in enhancing model performance without significantly increasing computational costs.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a lightweight temporal attention module integrated with frequency dynamic convolution (FDY-Conv) architectures to improve sound event detection, especially for accurate event boundary localization. Our module explicitly emphasizes temporally salient frames through frequency-axis compression and frame-level attention weighting using MLP, Conv1D, or Multi-Head Attention mechanisms. Comprehensive evaluations on the DESED dataset demonstrate consistent and significant performance improvements across various FDY-Conv architectures (FDY-CRNN, DFD-CRNN, and MDFD-CRNN), demonstrating both effectiveness and computational efficiency.

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MIMII-Agent: Leveraging LLMs with Function Calling for Relative Evaluation of Anomalous Sound Detection

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Abstract—This paper proposes a method for generating machine-type-specific anomalies to evaluate the relative performance of unsupervised anomalous sound detection (UASD) systems across different machine types, even in the absence of real anomaly sound data. Conventional keyword-based data augmentation methods often produce unrealistic sounds due to their reliance on manually defined labels, limiting scalability as machine types and anomaly patterns diversify. Advanced audio generative models, such as MIMII-Gen, show promise but typically depend on anomalous training data, making them less effective when diverse anomalous examples are unavailable. To address these limitations, we propose a novel synthesis approach leveraging large language models (LLMs) to interpret textual descriptions of faults and automatically select audio transformation functions, converting normal machine sounds into diverse and plausible anomalous sounds. We validate this approach by evaluating a UASD system trained only on normal sounds from five machine types, using both real and synthetic anomaly data. Experimental results reveal consistent trends in relative detection difficulty across machine types between synthetic and real anomalies. This finding supports our hypothesis and highlights the effectiveness of the proposed LLM-based synthesis approach for relative evaluation of UASD systems.

Index Terms—Large language model, Relative evaluation, Anomalous sound detection

1. INTRODUCTION

Detecting anomalies in machine sounds is a critical aspect of predictive maintenance, aiming to prevent equipment failures and reduce downtime in industrial operations [1]. Machine sounds provide valuable insights into equipment health, where anomalies may indicate issues such as mechanical wear, misalignment, or impending component failure. Traditional anomaly detection methods [2]–[4] rely heavily on data, but collecting extensive datasets of real anomalous sounds is challenging due to the rarity and unpredictability of faults. Deliberately inducing faults is often impractical or hazardous, leading to a fundamental scarcity of real anomalous data.

This scarcity and lack of diversity in available real anomaly data significantly hinder not only training but also the evaluation of anomalous sound detection (ASD) systems across diverse fault conditions. Rigorous assessment of system capabilities requires suitable test data, which is often unavailable or fails to adequately represent real-world conditions. While conventional data augmentation [5]–[7] and text-to-audio (TTA)-based anomaly generation [8]–[10] attempt to address this, they face limitations: synthesized sounds may lack realism, or advanced generative models may require anomalous samples for training, further complicating evaluation when real-world anomaly data are sparse or absent. Consequently, reliably benchmarking ASD performance against diverse, realistic fault conditions across different machine types remains a significant challenge.

To address this issue, we first introduce the concept of “**relative evaluation**”, which complements conventional absolute evaluation. Relative evaluation assesses a system’s comparative strengths and weaknesses by verifying **detection performance rankings across machine types**, where the system performs well for some machine types but poorly for others. This approach is essential in heterogeneous industrial environments, where maintenance engineers must know where a system is trustworthy and where it is not, enabling optimized

sensor allocation, inspection scheduling, and risk management. Traditional absolute metrics, such as the Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC), can fluctuate with the severity of anomaly samples and become unreliable when real anomaly data are scarce. Specifically, severe anomalies in the test set lead to easy detection and high AUC scores, while mild anomalies make detection harder, resulting in lower AUC scores. In contrast, relative evaluation focuses on the comparative difficulty of detection tasks across machine types, providing consistent insights even when anomaly severity varies.

We further propose a novel method for synthesizing anomalous sounds to enable relative evaluation of ASD systems across machine types. The method leverages LLMs’ implicit world knowledge—i.e., “common sense”—to interpret textual descriptions of faults and automatically apply appropriate acoustic transformations to normal machine sounds, thereby generating plausible acoustic characteristics for the described faults. This approach generates diverse, controllable synthetic anomalies without requiring prior anomalous data or manual intervention, facilitating relative evaluation of ASD systems’ strengths and weaknesses across machine types.

2. RELATED RESEARCH

2.1. Unsupervised anomalous sound detection

Unsupervised Anomalous Sound Detection (UASD) is critical for ASD, especially when anomalous data is unavailable. The DCASE challenges [1], [11]–[14] have advanced this field by providing datasets like ToyADMOS series [15]–[18] and MIMII series [19]–[21], enabling benchmarking of techniques like autoencoder-based methods [22], Gaussian-Mixture-Model-based methods [23], embedding-similarity-based approaches [24], etc. Despite these advancements, evaluating detection systems across diverse fault conditions remains difficult due to the lack of representative anomalous test data, highlighting the need for synthetic datasets that simulate realistic anomalies.

2.2. Anomalous sound generation

Synthetic data generation addresses the shortage of real anomalous sounds for training and evaluation. Most conventional methods for anomalous sound generation focus on data augmentation to train UASD systems using anomalous examples.

One common approach is basic data augmentation, which includes pitch-shifting and time-stretching [5], Mixup-based augmentation [6], and statistics-exchange-based augmentation [7]. However, these methods often produce unrealistic sounds that are unsuitable for robust evaluation.

Another approach is TTA-based anomalous sound generation (See Table 1). Zahedi et al.’s method [8] generates anomalous sounds by randomly selecting prompts created by ChatGPT and feeding them into AudioLDM [25]. However, this method cannot achieve realistic, machine-type-specific synthesis because it does not consider machine type when selecting prompts. Zhang et al.’s method [9] converts metadata into captions, which are then input into AudioLDM. This approach can potentially achieve realistic synthesis by leveraging

Table 1: Conventional Approaches for TTA-based Anomalous Sound Generation

Characteristic	Zahedi et al. [8]	Zhang et al. [9]	MIMII-Gen [10]	This work
Machine-type-aware realistic synthesis	No	Yes (uses metadata)	Yes (uses metadata)	Yes (uses metadata)
Trainable with normal data alone	Yes	No	No	Yes
Purpose	Training	Training	Evaluation (absolute)	Relative evaluation

metadata such as machine type, but it requires anomalous samples for training. MIMII-Gen [10] has been proposed specifically for evaluating anomaly detection systems. Similar to Zhang et al. [9], MIMII-Gen converts metadata into captions and uses these captions as input for a diffusion model to generate anomalous sounds. While it can potentially achieve machine-type-aware realistic synthesis, it also requires anomalous samples for training, which limits its applicability when such data are sparse.

2.3. TTA models

This subsection highlights representative TTA models, which serve as the foundation for the above TTA-based anomaly-generation approaches [8]–[10]. TTA models leverage the contextual understanding of LLMs to generate speech, music, or environmental sounds directly from textual prompts. For high-fidelity generation, latent diffusion models have demonstrated exceptional effectiveness. AudioLDM [25] pioneered CLAP [26]-conditioned latent diffusion, enabling zero-shot audio generation. Building on similar approaches, recent works have achieved improvements in multi-domain synthesis quality and enhanced temporal coherence [27]–[29]. To address inference latency, some models compress diffusion into fewer steps [30]–[32]. TANGO 2 [33] employs preference optimization to align audio outputs with human-perceived prompt consistency, using reinforcement-style feedback to train more reliable generators. However, none of the above TTA models are trained on industrial machine recordings, while Zhang et al. [9] and MIMII-Gen [10] explicitly train their generators on machine-type-labeled industrial sound datasets, enabling type-specific fault synthesis.

2.4. Research gap and contribution

As mentioned earlier, traditional absolute metrics commonly used in anomaly detection benchmarks [1], [11]–[14] fluctuate with the severity of anomaly samples, making them unreliable when real anomaly data are scarce. Severe anomalies in the test set lead to easy detection and high AUC scores, while mild anomalies make detection harder, resulting in lower AUC scores.

To address this limitation, our first contribution is the introduction of relative evaluation, which verifies detection performance rankings across machine types. Unlike absolute evaluation, which is sensitive to anomaly severity, relative evaluation identifies where the system performs better or worse.

Our second contribution is a scalable method for generating diverse and realistic anomalous sounds using LLMs to enable relative evaluation. Instead of directly generating synthetic anomalies or manually adding them, our approach leverages LLMs to interpret machine types and their corresponding anomalies, transforming normal machine audio into anomalous audio. As shown in Table 1, unlike the conventional TTA-based anomalous sound generation methods [8]–[10], our approach enables realistic synthesis tailored to specific machine types and operates with training only on normal data. This ensures reliable evaluation across different machines, even when real anomaly data are limited.

3. PROPOSED METHOD

Our proposed method introduces a novel approach to generating anomalous machine sounds by leveraging LLMs to intelligently select and apply appropriate sound effects to normal machine audio based on descriptive captions. The comprehensive workflow illustrated in Fig. 1 consists of two major parts: (a) synthetic anomalous sound generation and (b) relative evaluation of anomaly detection systems across different machine types.

3.1. Synthetic anomaly sound generation

3.1.1. Workflow: The synthetic anomaly generation process follows a systematic workflow as illustrated in the block diagram:

- **Input metadata:** The process begins with metadata that provides contextual information about machine types, operating and environmental conditions.
- **Generate caption:** Based on the input metadata, the system generates descriptive caption using Flan-T5 [34] that characterize the machine’s operational state.
- **Generate normal sound:** Using the MIMII-Gen latent diffusion model [10], we generate high-fidelity normal machine audio that serve as the foundation for anomaly introduction.
- **Initialize prompt:** This step consists of carefully crafted system prompt, user prompt containing generated caption and anomalous sound effect functions described in section 3.1.2.
- **Request to LLM:** In this step, the initialized prompt is sent to a Large Language Model via an API call. The language model analyzes the captions and autonomously selects the most appropriate sound effect to simulate potential anomaly relevant to the operating condition present in the caption.
- **Receive and interpret answer from LLM:** The system parses the LLM’s response, extracts the selected function name, and maps it to the corresponding audio processing function from a predefined library of anomalous sound effects.
- **Anomalous audio generation:** The selected function is applied to the normal sound obtained from MIMII-Gen, transforming it into anomalous audio with context-appropriate fault characteristics. The generated anomalous sounds are stored along with the applied anomaly effects.

3.1.2. Anomalous sound effect functions: We implement a comprehensive library of sound effect functions that simulate various machine fault conditions:

- **Squeaking or Squealing:** High-pitched sounds indicating faulty bearings or friction between components.
- **Rattling or Knocking:** Noises suggestive of loose parts or misalignment.
- **Grinding or Scraping:** Sounds indicative of severe mechanical wear or damage.
- **Humming or Buzzing:** Low-frequency sounds resulting from electrical issues or resonance.
- **Whistling or Hissing:** Sounds associated with air leaks or high-pressure flow.
- **Clicking or Tapping:** Noises caused by relay switches or intermittent contacts.

Fig. 1: Workflow of Our Approach

- **Pulsing or Chattering:** Effects indicating fluctuating power supply or control issues.
- **Pop or Bang:** Sudden sounds simulating abrupt failures or explosive events.
- **Changes in Tonal Quality or Frequency:** Alterations representing shifts in machine operation.
- **Broadband Noise Increases:** Overall noise level increases to simulate general degradation.

Each function uses specific digital signal processing techniques to modify normal sound waveforms, creating realistic fault signatures.

Example: The sound effect functions are implemented using Python libraries such as NumPy, Librosa, and SoundFile, manipulating the audio waveforms to introduce the selected anomalies.

```
def add_squeaking(audio, sr,
                 duration=2.0, freq=4000, intensity=0.3):
    # Adds a high-pitched squeaking sound
    # to the audio
    # Function implementation
    return audio_with_squeaking
```

3.2. Anomaly detection system evaluation

3.2.1. Unsupervised anomaly detection system: The UASD system is trained exclusively on real normal sound and calculates anomaly scores, such as reconstruction errors in autoencoders, to identify anomalies. This unsupervised approach aligns with real-world scenarios where anomalies are rare and underrepresented in training data. The UASD system can utilize methods such as autoencoder-based [22], Gaussian Mixture Model-based [23], or embedding-similarity-based approaches [24]. The system processes all clips from real normal sound and synthetic anomaly datasets and computes anomaly scores for each clip.

3.2.2. AUC calculation and relative evaluation: The AUC score for each machine type is calculated as:

$$AUC_m = \frac{1}{N_m^- N_m^+} \sum_{i=1}^{N_m^-} \sum_{j=1}^{N_m^+} \mathcal{H}(A(x_j^+) - A(x_i^-)), \quad (1)$$

where m represents the machine type index, $\mathcal{H}(x)$ returns 1 if $x > 0$ and 0 otherwise, $\{x_i^-\}_{i=1}^{N_m^-}$ are normal test clips, and $\{x_j^+\}_{j=1}^{N_m^+}$ are anomalous test clips for machine type m . N_m^- and N_m^+ indicate the number of normal and anomalous test clips, respectively.

By comparing AUC scores across machine types, users can identify the system's relative strengths and weaknesses based on detection performance rankings.

4. EXPERIMENTATION

The experiments aim to validate two key objectives. The first objective is to confirm the correlation between synthetic and real anomaly detection performance rankings across different machine types, demonstrating that synthetic anomaly generation using our proposed approach enables users to identify the system's relative strengths and weaknesses. The second objective is to validate the effectiveness of LLM-based approaches in generating contextually appropriate synthetic anomalies compared to manual and random methods, through an ablation study. This section provides details on the dataset, anomaly detection system, results, and an ablation study.

4.1. Dataset preparation

Table 2 summarizes the datasets used in this study. We prepared three distinct datasets to support our evaluation: normal sounds, synthetic anomalous sounds, and real anomalous sounds. Each dataset was tailored to the five machine types under study.

Table 2 summarizes the datasets used in this study. We prepared three distinct datasets tailored to five machine types: bearings, gearboxes, fans, valves, and slide rails.

- **Normal Sounds:** We collected 900 normal sound recordings per machine type (bearings, gearboxes, fans, valves, and slide rails), each 10 seconds long, sampled at 16 kHz. These were sourced from industrial environments and public datasets like MIMII-DG [21] ensuring a comprehensive representation of typical operating conditions.
- **Synthetic Anomalous Sounds:** For each machine type, we generated 50 synthetic anomalies by applying sound effects to normal sounds. The language model (GPT-4) selected effects (e.g., squeaking, rattling) based on captions describing operating conditions (e.g., "Bearing operating at 24 krpm").
- **Real Anomalous Sounds:** We acquired 50 real anomalous recordings per machine type. These anomalies represent actual faults, such as mechanical wear or misalignment, and vary in severity.

Table 2: Dataset Summary

Category	Samples per Machine	Duration	Sample Rate
Normal Sounds	900	10 s	16 kHz
Synthetic Anomalies	50	10 s	16 kHz
Real Anomalies	50	10 s	16 kHz

Table 3: Detection Performance on Synthetic vs. Real Anomalies

Machine Type	Synthetic			Real		
	MSE	AUC MAHALA	Rank	MSE	AUC MAHALA	Rank
Bearing	0.85	0.82	3	0.57	0.61	3
Gearbox	0.88	0.86	2	0.62	0.67	2
Fan	0.92	0.95	1	0.90	0.93	1
Slide rail	0.80	0.79	4	0.55	0.57	4
Valve	0.78	0.72	5	0.53	0.52	5

4.2. Anomaly detection system design

We employed an unsupervised anomaly detection system based on an autoencoder, trained exclusively on normal sounds to detect deviations indicative of anomalies.

Autoencoder Architecture:

- **Input Layer:** Log-mel spectrograms with 128 mel-bins, extracted from 64-ms frame windows with 50% hop size.
- **Encoder:** Three layers (128, 64, 32 filters, kernel size 3), each followed by ReLU activation and max-pooling (2x2).
- **Decoder:** Mirrored layers with upsampling, reconstructing the input spectrogram.

Training Details: The autoencoder was trained for 100 epochs with a batch size of 32, using the Adam optimizer (learning rate 0.001) and mean squared error (MSE) loss. A single model was trained across all machine types to generalize normal patterns, reflecting real-world scenarios with diverse equipment.

4.3. Results

Table 3 summarizes the detection performance for synthetic and real anomalies using AUC scores, derived from two distinct metrics: Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Mahalanobis distance (MAHALA). Employing both scoring methods provides a more robust validation of the relative evaluation on synthetic data. Synthetic anomalies consistently achieved higher AUC scores compared to real anomalies, indicating they are easier to detect. Notably, the ranking of AUC scores, and thus the relative anomaly detection difficulty, is consistent across machine types for both synthetic and real data. These results demonstrate that synthetic anomaly generation using our proposed approach effectively enables users to evaluate the system’s relative strengths and weaknesses.

Differences in AUC scores reflect the unique operational behaviors and fault characteristics of each machine type. For example, lower AUC scores for valves and slide rails suggest that anomalies in these machines may be subtler or involve features that are harder for the anomaly detection system to capture.

4.4. Ablation study

To validate the reliability of the LLM-based approach, we compared three configurations: (1) our approach with GPT-4o-based anomaly function calling (with values reproduced from Table 3), (2) a keyword-based manual mapping of anomalies created through human labeling based on common knowledge (e.g., adding a “squeaking” anomaly if the caption includes “bearing”), and (3) random selection of possible anomalies without contextual understanding.

Table 4: Ablation Study: Common Knowledge Impact on MSE-AUC

Machine Type	GPT-4o		Manual-mapping (w/ Knowledge)		Random (w/o Knowledge)	
	AUC	rank	AUC	rank	AUC	rank
Bearing	0.85	3	0.70	3	0.81	5
Gearbox	0.88	2	0.72	2	0.85	3
Fan	0.92	1	0.78	1	0.82	4
Slide rail	0.80	4	0.67	4	0.86	2
Valve	0.78	5	0.65	5	0.89	1

Table 4 presents the results of the ablation study. The AUC-score rankings across machine types produced using GPT-4o and the keyword-based manual mapping approach formed by human labels were both closely aligned with those of real anomalies. In contrast, random anomaly selection showed no correlation with the AUC-score rankings of real anomalies, highlighting the importance of contextual understanding in anomaly generation. These results confirm that the ability of LLMs to interpret machine-specific characteristics and fault descriptions, leveraging common knowledge embedded within them, enables the creation of realistic and relevant anomalies. Furthermore, the observation that sound effects impact machines differently emphasizes the need to tailor the selection process to each machine type. The consistent performance of LLM-based anomaly generation demonstrates its potential as a scalable and efficient alternative to human labeling, capable of supporting diverse machine types and anomaly scenarios. Improving prompt design and incorporating domain-specific constraints could further enhance the realism of generated anomalies, thereby increasing the approach’s utility for UASD evaluation.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper addressed the challenge of evaluating UASD systems in the absence of sufficient and diverse real anomaly data. To tackle this, we proposed two key contributions: (1) the introduction of relative evaluation, which verifies detection performance rankings across machine types. Unlike absolute evaluation, which is sensitive to anomaly severity, relative evaluation identifies where the system performs better or worse. (2) a novel synthesis approach using LLMs with function-calling capabilities. Our method leverages the world knowledge of LLMs to interpret textual descriptions of machine conditions and automatically apply audio transformations, generating diverse and plausible synthetic anomalies for evaluation, without requiring prior anomalous examples.

Experiments showed that AUC-score rankings are consistent across machine types as well as different anomaly detection systems for both synthetic and real data. Also, rankings produced using GPT-4o and keyword-based manual mapping closely aligned with those of real anomalies, while random anomaly selection showed no correlation, highlighting the importance of contextual understanding in anomaly generation. These findings validate the ability of LLMs to generate realistic and relevant anomalies by interpreting machine-specific characteristics and fault descriptions. Our approach offers a reliable and scalable tool for benchmarking UASD performance and understanding relative detection difficulty across machine types, especially in scenarios lacking sufficient real anomaly data.

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Whale-VAD: Whale Vocalisation Activity Detection

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Abstract—We present a lightweight sound event detection (SED) system focused on the discovery of whale calls in marine audio recordings. Our proposed architecture uses a hybrid CNN-BiLSTM architecture with an added residual bottleneck and depthwise convolutions to perform coherent per-frame whale call event detection. We discover that, for this task, the inclusion of spectral phase information among the input features notably improves performance. We also evaluate the effectiveness of negative batch undersampling and the inclusion of a focal loss term. As part of the 2025 BioDCASE challenge (Task 2), we compare our system to ResNet-18 and YOLOv11 models, as well as to our own baseline. All models are trained exclusively on the same subset of the publically available ATBFL dataset. Our proposed whale call event detector improves on the development set performance of all models, including the top performing YOLOv11, achieving an F1-score of 0.44.

Index Terms—Whale Call Detection, Computational Bioacoustics, Sound Event Detection, Hybrid CNN-BiLSTM

1. INTRODUCTION

Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) enables researchers to monitor species in remote locations using non-invasive and relatively low-cost methods. However, large volumes of data are generated, typically with low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [1]. This makes manual review, which requires trained experts, both time-consuming and expensive.

To address this, many automated algorithms have been developed to detect and classify signals of interest. One focus has been the detection and classification of blue and fin whale vocalisations. Blue whales were driven nearly to extinction by 20th-century whaling, and as a result are still considered endangered today. Together with fin whales, they are considered vulnerable by the IUCN red list [2, 3]. Population densities for both species remain difficult to estimate with confidence due to limited data availability [4].

In this paper, we focus on developing a lightweight whale call activity detector based on a convolutional bidirectional long short-term memory neural network (CNN-BiLSTM). Our work is inspired by a voice activity detection (VAD) framework originally proposed for speech [5]. We develop an optimised architecture and explore input features that all contribute to substantial gains over our own baseline. Among our key findings are that incorporating phase information from the short time Fourier transform (STFT) strongly enhances model performance, as does the inclusion of a residual bottleneck and depthwise convolutions in the classifier architecture.

2. BACKGROUND

Sound event detection (SED) refers to the task of recognising a sound or sequence of sounds in a long, continuous audio signal that may be polluted with noise from interfering sources. In bioacoustic tasks, these are typically the vocalisations of different species, or inter-species call types. A sequence of sound events can also form an amalgamated call or song, depending on the taxa of interest.

Automatic SED algorithms are typically supervised, and thus require a labelled dataset describing the times at which the events of interest occur in the audio signal. In bioacoustic call detection, these annotations either identify the start and/or end of a call or sub-call,

or simply indicate the presence of a call within a longer audio signal without specifying its exact location.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The use of bioacoustic data for detecting and classifying animal vocalisations is well established, with early research focusing on birds [6], bats [7] and insects [8], before attention turned to marine animals [9]. Early approaches were based on the identification of regions of high spectral energy within specific frequency bands [10, 11] or the application of template matching techniques using prototypical examples of species-specific calls or sub-calls [9, 12]. However, these approaches tend to perform poorly in low SNR conditions and often require call signatures that are invariant across varying exogenous factors such as season or geographic region.

Dugan et al. [13] incorporated an artificial neural network (ANN) into a suite of parallel detectors for classification of North Atlantic right whale *upcalls*, while Pourhomayoun et al. [14] used image processing techniques to identify regions of interest in the spectrograms before applying the ANN.

More recently, deep neural networks have emerged as a powerful approach in bioacoustics. Many of these employ convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which take spectrograms of audio signals as input and output labels indicating the presence of specific calls or species. While conventional CNNs are widely used, convolutional recurrent neural networks (CRNNs) which incorporate recurrent layers after the convolutional layers to improve sequential modelling have also become popular [15]. CNN-based models have shown strong performance across different taxa, including birds [16] and marine mammals [17].

4. DATA

As part of the 2025 BioDCASE (Task 2) challenge, a dataset consisting of strongly labelled blue- and fin-whale calls in the Antarctic region of the Southern Ocean was released. The data was originally obtained by the Antarctic Blue and Fin Whale Acoustic Trends Project (ATP) as part of the International Whaling Commission’s Southern Ocean Research Partnership (IWC-SORP).

The Acoustic Trends Blue Fin Library (ATBFL) consists of 11 site-year datasets recorded around the Antarctic, in the period 2005 to 2017. Each dataset was manually annotated, in both the time and frequency domain, using data collection and annotation procedures described in [4]. The challenge excludes three site-year datasets as a development set, while the remaining eight site-year datasets form the training set, as set out in Table 1.

The ATBFL library includes annotations for seven different call types, of which four are produced by blue whales (*BmA*, *BmB*, *BmZ* and *BmD*) and three by fin whales (*BpD*, *Bp20* and *Bp20plus*). During the final evaluation, these seven calls are collapsed to a three class problem, as set out by the organisers: *bmbzb*, *d*, and *bp*.

Table 1: Summary of the ATBFL site-year training and development sets, indicating total recording duration for each set (hours) and how much of the set has been annotated to contain whale calls (hours). The test set annotations are not publically available.

Dataset	Recording (h)	Annotated Whale Call (h)
ballenyisland2015	204	2.8
casey2014	194	14.2
elephantislands2013	187	16.1
elephantislands2014	216	28.1
greenwich2015	32	2.1
keruelen2005	200	3.5
maudrise2014	83	5.7
rosssea2014	176	0.1
Total training set	1292	72.6
casey2017	185	6.1
keruelen2014	200	11.4
keruelen2015	200	7.4
Total development set	585	24.9
keruelen2020	198	—
ddu2021	206	—
Total test set	404	—

5. EXPERIMENTAL STRUCTURE

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed whale call activity detection system. First, the audio is segmented and preprocessed. Each segment is provided to the model as input, with frame-level classification targets determined from the boundary annotation file. Each model consists of two parts: a *feature extractor*, that produces high-dimensional vectors representative of the information contained in the audio segment; and a *classification model*, tasked with producing a class membership probability from feature vectors, obtained at each time instant.

5.1. Preprocessing

The training data consists of long continuous audio recordings, typically the result of PAM. Due to computational constraints, these were subdivided into shorter intervals, referred to as segments.

Each segment corresponds to the audio between the start and end points of a human annotation, indicating the occurrence of a particular call type. The segments were extended to include additional audio before the start and at the end of the call, referred to as a collar. The length of the collar was independently and randomly sampled from a uniform distribution for both the start and end of each segment, ensuring the call does not always appear in the centre of the segment.

An associated discrete classification target vector was constructed from the annotations for each segment. In all experiments, one model classification was computed every 20ms. As there may be overlapping annotations, the problem is treated as multi-class multi-label. Consequently, a binary label was assigned for each respective class at each discrete time instant, independent of the other classes. When a human annotation boundary intersects completely with the classification target vector at a time instant, the label is *true*, indicating the presence of a particular call; otherwise, it remains *false*.

Additionally, segments without any vocalisation annotations were included (Section 5.5). In such cases, all classification targets were set to *false*, indicating that no vocalisation has occurred.

The variable-length segments were gathered into a batch of fixed length during preprocessing. To achieve this, each segment and the associated classification target was zero padded to the length of the longest segment in the batch. This padding was removed from each segment during loss calculation and model weight backpropagation.

During evaluation, human annotations are not available. Therefore, the continuous audio recordings were subdivided into regularly spaced segments with a fixed length of 30s and a 2s overlap. The postulated model classification probabilities were averaged over this overlap.

5.2. Feature extractor

The feature extraction model is provided with an audio segment as obtained from the continuous audio recording (Section 5.1). In this work, we only consider spectral and cepstral features.

First, a spectrogram representation was computed using a ~ 1 s frame length and 20ms stride between frames. The long frame length was motivated by the low fundamental frequency of the whale calls. The frame stride was dictated by the desired classification resolution, which was fixed at 20ms, to allow for direct comparison of loss figures between experiments (Section 5.1). A Hanning window was applied to each frame, without additional zero padding. A subsequent 256-point fast Fourier transform (FFT) resulted in 128 frequency bins and the DC component. This power spectrum was compressed into 64 bins using a bank of triangular filters with a mel-scale spacing. Finally, mel frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) were obtained by applying the discrete cosine transform (DCT) to the resulting binned spectrum, and retaining the lower 20 coefficients.

After the features were obtained, mean spectral and cepstral subtraction was performed, respectively. The mean was computed independently for each frequency bin over the duration of the segment.

5.3. Baseline classification model

From the sequence of features obtained from the feature extractor, the call posterior probabilities were computed using a classification model with sigmoid activation functions at the outputs.

A bidirectional long short-term memory network (BiLSTM) model was chosen and configured with between one and four hidden layers; a hidden dimension size of 64, 128, or 256; and layer dropout of between 20% and 50%. We found that the recurrent model was prone to overfit, but that increased dropout reduced this risk. The posterior call probabilities produced by these models aligned well with the call segments. Informally, it was observed that both the start and end boundaries produced by the recurrent models closely matched those of the human annotators.

5.4. Whale vocalisation activity detector

We propose a whale call activity detection system inspired by the AVA-VAD system first presented in [5]. We alter the AVA-VAD system by introducing a residual bottleneck network and depthwise convolutions. Furthermore, instead of using a mel spectrogram as input, we utilise the spectrogram features directly and apply a linear convolutional layer to act as a learnable filterbank. Figure 2 provides an overview of the model architecture.

The spectrogram is computed using the configuration described in Section 5.2. However, during experimentation, we found that including phase information substantially improves detection performance. Thus, instead of the power spectrum typically utilised as feature, we provide the model with a three-dimensional representation of each complex spectral component (z) as follows:

$$z = r(\cos \theta + i \sin \theta); \quad \mathbf{x}_k^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} r \\ \cos \theta \\ \sin \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

where r is the spectral magnitude and θ is the phase and $\mathbf{x}_k^{(n)}$ is the model input at time instant n and discrete frequency k .

The learnable filterbank consists of a linear convolutional layer. The one-dimensional kernel is convolved with each vector of energies

Fig. 1: Illustration depicting the whale call activity detection system overview and experimental setup.

Fig. 2: Illustration of the Whale-VAD system proposed for whale call activity detection.

constituting the spectrogram. This output is then passed through a two layer CNN with max pooling, GELU activation and batch normalisation. During model development several architectural variations were considered. We found the addition of a residually connected bottleneck network and depthwise convolutional network to improve model performance, inspired by [18, 19, 20]. Each bottleneck network consists of three convolutional layers, each with GELU activation, compressing the features to a lower dimensional representation. This representation is passed through three depthwise convolutional layers with intermediate drop out. Table 2 provides a summary of the CNN layer configuration employed by the final Whale-VAD model.

The residual output connection is reduced to 64 dimensions by a linear layer. Padding is applied to each CNN layer to ensure the number of output activations remains consistent with the number of input frames. These latent features are then recurrently processed by a BiLSTM network. Finally, a linear layer with sigmoid activations produces the model call probabilities.

We further investigate two input regularisation techniques: spectral augmentation [21] and noise perturbation. For noise perturbation, we inject Gaussian noise into the audio signal such that the resulting SNR of the original signal to the perturbed signal is 10 dB.

5.5. Stochastic negative mini-batch undersampling

Analysis of the challenge dataset revealed that whale vocalisations are rare, with a prevalence of approximately 5%. Therefore, we propose a technique where, during each epoch of finetuning, we sample a different subset of *negative* segments (containing no calls) while ensuring that there are approximately as many negative as positive segments per mini-batch. This ratio was determined through early informal experimentation. After each training epoch, a new subset of negative segments is sampled. The set of positive calls remains consistent for each epoch during finetuning.

Table 2: Summary of Whale-VAD model layer configuration. The kernel size (K), stride (S), number of input channels (C_{in}) and output channels (C_{out}), are shown.

Layer	K	S	C_{in}	C_{out}
Filterbank	(7, 1)	(3, 1)	1	64
Feature extractor				
\downarrow Conv2D	(5, 5)	(3, 1)	64	128
\downarrow Max pool	(5, 1)	(1, 1)	–	–
\downarrow Conv2D	(3, 3)	(2, 1)	128	128
\downarrow Max pool	(3, 1)	(1, 1)	–	–
Bottleneck network				
\downarrow Conv2d	(1, 1)	(1, 1)	128	64
\downarrow Conv2d	(3, 3)	(1, 1)	64	64
\downarrow Conv2d	(1, 1)	(1, 1)	64	128
Depth. Conv2d	(3, 3)	(1, 1)	128	128

5.6. Loss function

In our experiments, we considered weighted binary cross-entropy (BCE) and *focal loss* as loss functions. We found that, when computing the class weighting, rather than normalising by the duration of each class, it was better to normalise by the number of segments belonging to each class. When considering weighted BCE, we compute the weighting w_c for each class c as follows:

$$w_c = \frac{N}{P_c}$$

where N denotes the total number of negative (no-call) segments and P_c the number of positive (call) segments for class c .

In addition to weighted BCE, we evaluated the use of *focal loss* [22], a modified cross-entropy designed to focus training on hard-to-classify examples by reducing the contribution of easy examples. In our experiments, we set the class imbalance term to 0.25 and *focus* term to 2, following the recommendations in the original paper.

For all experiments, we rely on AdamW [23] as the numerical optimiser. Unless otherwise stated, the optimiser was configured with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-5} , momentum terms of 0.9 and 0.999, and a weight decay factor of 0.001.

5.7. Multi-objective regression

The challenge dataset contained not only annotations in time, but also in frequency (bounding box). The best-performing baseline YOLO model, provided by the organisers, uses these box-level annotations. In addition to our Whale-VAD system (Section 5.4), we therefore evaluated a bounding box regression network. The network uses the same latent features as the classification model, with the addition of an adaptive pooling layer in order to reduce the time dimension. These reduced latent features are presented to two independent multi-layer perceptron (MLP) networks, each consisting of three layers, with GELU activation and dropout after each hidden layer. Each of the regression networks is applied to the 64 channels of the adaptive pooling layer, which is the maximum number of anchors (bounding boxes) the model can produce per input segment. The first network

has a four dimensional output, corresponding to the bottom left and top right corners of the bounding box. The second network produces a confidence score, corresponding to the presence of the bounding box. Figure 2 illustrates the additional bounding box regression model. The regression model is trained using smoothed L1 loss [24]. Note that the regression model forms part of a multi-objective training regime, where the regression and classification loss are jointly optimised. The regression outputs (bounding boxes) are not used for final model evaluation. We postulated that training to jointly optimise both tasks might lead to improved classification performance.

5.8. Postprocessing

After training, the best model was chosen based on the lowest BCE development loss. The model outputs were smoothed using a median filter with a 500 ms kernel. The classification thresholds θ_c were selected per class c to maximise the development F1-score. The resulting per call threshold θ_c was applied to the posterior call probabilities computed by the model to obtain the binary classification result. Finally, the 7-class classifier output is collapsed into the 3-class variant posed by the challenge organisers.

The resulting binary labels were used to generate start and end boundaries relative to the start of the recording. These annotations were refined by merging overlapping calls of the same type, eliminating duplicates, and joining calls separated by less than 500 ms. Finally, calls longer than 30 s or shorter than 500 ms were discarded.

6. RESULTS

Table 3 presents the top performing models proposed in this work and the baselines provided by the organisers of the BioDCASE challenge. All reported figures have been measured on the development set.

We performed a series of model development experiments that lead to notable changes to the original CNN-BiLSTM architecture (AVA-VAD). The addition of residual bottleneck layers and depthwise convolutions, in particular, lead to substantial improvements in model recall, at the loss of some precision. However, incorporating phase information improved both recall and precision, and resulted in a 30% improvement in the F1-score. The introduction of focal loss further improved the recall, precision and F1-score. Finally, training the model on collapsed labels (three-class problem) yielded an additional 15.2% improvement, resulting in an F1-score of 0.440. The addition of multi-task bounding box regression, as well as the inclusion of input noise perturbation and spectral augmentations, were found to be counterproductive. When considering the top performing baseline model (YOLOv11), we see that our models exhibit superior recall, while the baseline achieves greater precision.

Table 4 and Fig. 3 presents classification performance of our best performing model for each call and each development set. We observe consistent performance across both *kerguelen* sites, but poor performance for *casey2017*. We also observe that our models produce a high number of false positive (FP) classifications for the minority call types (d and bp), which leads to poor precision. Manual inspection revealed these FPs usually to be other marine vocalisations.

7. CONCLUSION

We have presented a CNN-BiLSTM architecture and shown it to be viable for whale call event detection. Incorporating residual bottleneck and depthwise convolutional layers lead to substantial improvements in recall. While most prior research disregards the phase information of the STFT, we have demonstrated that incorporating it for whale call classification can improve model precision substantially, compared to models trained solely on magnitude features. This finding opens

Table 3: Development set results for the official ResNet18 and YOLOv11 baselines, and our MFCC, AVA-VAD and Whale-VAD models. Scores are averages across call types and validation and test sets. Challenge results shown, where available.

Experiment	Development			Test		
	Recall	Precision	F1-score	Recall	Precision	F1-score
ResNet18 (Baseline)	0.36	0.29	0.32	—	—	—
YOLOv11 (Baseline)	0.32	0.67	0.43	0.331	0.480	0.392
MFCCs + BiLSTM	0.409	0.226	0.291	—	—	—
AVA-VAD [5]	0.310	0.219	0.245	—	—	—
Whale-VAD	0.424	0.207	0.278	—	—	—
+ Phase	0.461	0.316	0.375	—	—	—
└ + Focal loss	0.484	0.348	0.405	0.414	0.302	0.349
└ + Three class	0.461	0.420	0.440	0.382	0.336	0.357

Fig. 3: Separate precision-recall curves for the three-call problem on each development set using the top-performing Whale-VAD model.

Table 4: Detailed development set results for the top-performing Whale-VAD model.

Dataset	Label	TP	FP	FN	Recall	Precision	F1
casey2017	bmabz	1984	1956	434	0.821	0.504	0.624
casey2017	d	179	5928	374	0.324	0.029	0.054
casey2017	bp	5	101	287	0.017	0.047	0.025
kerguelen2014	bmabz	2739	1120	1558	0.637	0.710	0.672
kerguelen2014	d	229	2248	550	0.294	0.092	0.141
kerguelen2014	bp	1391	663	2355	0.371	0.677	0.480
kerguelen2015	bmabz	2137	2676	611	0.778	0.444	0.565
kerguelen2015	d	366	2545	1158	0.240	0.126	0.165
kerguelen2015	bp	665	355	605	0.524	0.652	0.581

avenues for future research in bioacoustics to reconsider the role of phase in time-frequency representations, particularly in the design of feature extractors and model architectures that can more effectively exploit both magnitude and phase components.

While the models we present exhibit performance improvements for whale call event detection, much room for advancement remains. The achieved recall and precision of 48.4% and 42%, respectively, means that most human annotated calls are not identified by the model, and among the calls identified, most are false positives.

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DESCRIPTION AND DISCUSSION ON DCASE 2025 CHALLENGE TASK 4: SPATIAL SEMANTIC SEGMENTATION OF SOUND SCENES

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ABSTRACT

Spatial Semantic Segmentation of Sound Scenes (S5) aims to enhance technologies for sound event detection and separation from multi-channel input signals that mix multiple sound events with spatial information. This is a fundamental basis of immersive communication. The ultimate goal is to separate sound event signals with 6 Degrees of Freedom (6DoF) information into dry sound object signals and metadata about the object type (sound event class) and representing spatial information, including direction. However, because several existing challenge tasks already provide some of the subset functions, this task for this year focuses on detecting and separating sound events from multi-channel spatial input signals. This paper outlines the S5 task setting of the Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) 2025 Challenge Task 4 and the DCASE2025 Task 4 Dataset, newly recorded and curated for this task. We also discuss the performance and characteristics of the S5 systems submitted to DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 4 based on experimental results.

Index Terms— Sound event detection and separation, Semantic segmentation of sound scenes, Spatial signal

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper summarizes a newly introduced task for the Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) 2025 challenge, named Task 4: Spatial Semantic Segmentation of Sound Scenes (S5) [1], and discusses the experimental results of submitted systems for this challenge [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

As illustrated in Fig. 1, S5 consists of detecting and extracting sound events from multi-channel spatial input signals. The input signal contains multiple simultaneous sounds as well as background noise. Each output signal should contain one isolated sound event with a predicted label for the event class.

One promising application of S5 is XR services that capture a user’s surrounding acoustic scene and transmit it to remote participants. To deliver a believable experience, the mixture must first be decomposed into individual sound objects. Each object is paired with its class label and 6DoF (three-dimensional position and rotation) spatial metadata. By using this, the rendering engine can

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then update direction and distance as the listener moves or edits the scene in real time. S5 technology can also be applicable for home-assisted living through sound monitoring of the room environment. As a first step for these applications, the present S5 task asks systems to detect the constituent sound events and separate their dry signals from multi-channel spatial recordings.

The S5 task relates to earlier DCASE challenges. DCASE 2021 Task 4 (Sound Event Detection and Separation in Domestic Environments) used single-channel recordings. Separation was optional and did not affect the score; it was only considered as a potential way to improve sound event detection when overlapping sound events are present [10, 11]. S5 instead supplies multi-channel input, allowing systems to exploit spatial cues, and it directly scores the quality of the separated sources. DCASE 2024 Task 3 (Audio and Audiovisual Sound Event Localization and Detection with Source Distance Estimation; SELD) targets direction-of-arrival (DoA) and distance metadata [12]. Although S5 does not require explicit estimation of geometric metadata like SELD, spatial information remains an important key.

2. TASK SETTING OF S5

2.1. Formulation and notation

The S5 task, originally proposed in our prior work [13], aims to detect and separate the sounds of each sound event from a mixture observed by a multi-channel microphone array at various locations in a real environment. This section introduces the notation and task settings.

Let $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{y}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{y}^{(M)}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times T}$ be the multi-channel time-domain mixture signal of length T , recorded with an array of M microphones, where $\{\cdot\}^\top$ is the matrix transposition. We denote $C = \{c_1, \dots, c_K\}$ the set of source labels in the mixture, where the source count K can vary from 1 to K_{\max} . The m -th channel of \mathbf{Y} can be modeled as

$$\mathbf{y}^{(m)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{h}_k^{(m)} * \mathbf{s}_{c_k} + \left[\sum_{j=1}^J \mathbf{h}_j^{(m)} * \mathbf{s}_{c_j} + \mathbf{n}^{(m)} \right]_{\text{optional}} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{s}_{c_k}, \mathbf{s}_{c_j} \in \mathbb{R}^T$ are the single-channel dry source signal corresponding to the labels of the target event c_k and interference event c_j , respectively. $\mathbf{h}_k^{(m)}, \mathbf{h}_j^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^H$ are the m -th channel of the length- H room impulse response (RIR) at the spatial position of \mathbf{s}_{c_k} and \mathbf{s}_{c_j} . $\mathbf{n}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^T$ is the m -th channel of the multi-channel noise signal. In the S5 task, the desired outputs are the estimates

Figure 1: Overview of spatial semantic segmentation of sound scenes.

of individual target sound events $\hat{S} = \{\hat{s}_{\hat{c}_1}, \dots, \hat{s}_{\hat{c}_K}\}$ and their corresponding class label $\hat{C} = \{\hat{c}_1, \dots, \hat{c}_K\}$.

2.2. Evaluation method, metric

As evaluation metrics for the S5 task, we used class-aware signal-to-distortion ratio improvement (CA-SDRi) proposed for the S5 task [13]. The metric is defined as

$$\text{CA-SDRi}(\hat{S}, S, \hat{C}, C, \mathbf{y}^{(m_{\text{ref}})}) = \frac{1}{|C \cup \hat{C}|} \sum_{\bar{c} \in C \cup \hat{C}} P_{\bar{c}}, \quad (2)$$

where $|C \cup \hat{C}|$ is the length of the set union. The metric component $P_{\bar{c}}$ is calculated as

$$P_{\bar{c} \in C \cup \hat{C}} = \begin{cases} \text{SDRi}(\hat{s}_{\bar{c}}, \mathbf{s}_{\bar{c}}, \mathbf{y}^{(m_{\text{ref}})}), & \text{if } \bar{c} \in C \cap \hat{C} \\ \mathcal{P}_{\bar{c}}^{\text{FN}}, & \text{if } \bar{c} \in C \wedge \bar{c} \notin \hat{C} \\ \mathcal{P}_{\bar{c}}^{\text{FP}}, & \text{if } \bar{c} \notin C \wedge \bar{c} \in \hat{C} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where the SDRi is calculated as

$$\text{SDRi}(\hat{s}_{\bar{c}}, \mathbf{s}_{\bar{c}}, \mathbf{y}^{(m_{\text{ref}})}) = \text{SDR}(\hat{s}_{\bar{c}}, \mathbf{s}_{\bar{c}}) - \text{SDR}(\mathbf{y}^{(m_{\text{ref}})}, \mathbf{s}_{\bar{c}}), \quad (4)$$

$$\text{SDR}(\hat{s}, \mathbf{s}) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{s}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{s} - \hat{s}\|^2} \right). \quad (5)$$

The key concept of CA-SDRi is that estimated and reference sources are aligned based on their labels. The waveform metric, SDRi, is calculated only when the label is correctly predicted, i.e., in the first case of (3). For incorrect label predictions, including false negatives (FN) and false positives (FP), which correspond to the second and third cases in (3), the penalty values $\mathcal{P}_{\bar{c}}^{\text{FN}}$ and $\mathcal{P}_{\bar{c}}^{\text{FP}}$ are accumulated. In this study's evaluation, both $\mathcal{P}_{\bar{c}}^{\text{FN}}$ and $\mathcal{P}_{\bar{c}}^{\text{FP}}$ were set to 0, indicating that incorrect predictions do not contribute to the metric. For the reference channel m_{ref} , we use the omnidirectional channel i.e., $m_{\text{ref}} = 0$.

The CA-SDRi described above sets the dry source signal \mathbf{s}_k as the target signal. However, direct comparison with the dry source can be challenging. It requires sample-accurate compensation for the distance-dependent delays between each source and microphone. Such precise alignment lies outside S5's main focus on detection and separation for now. To relax this requirement, we replace each dry source with the signal obtained by convolving it with the direct-path component of the impulse response, forming

$$\mathbf{s}_{c_k}^{(d)} = \mathbf{h}_k^{(m_{\text{ref}}, d)} * \mathbf{s}_{c_k}. \quad (6)$$

Here, $\mathbf{h}_k^{(m_{\text{ref}}, d)}$ is the direct path component of the impulse response at the reference microphone m_{ref} . CA-SDRi, in this study, is computed by using $\mathbf{s}_{c_k}^{(d)}$ as reference. Note that, although our notation differs, the metric is identical to the one adopted in the previous study [13].

Finally, the ranking score is the average CA-SDRi across all clips. In addition to the primary ranking score function CA-SDRi, we will also provide PESQ [14] and STOI [15] for speech, and PEAQ [16] scores for signals other than speech as informative metrics representing perceptual quality.

3. DCASE2025 TASK4 DATASET

3.1. General overview

For the S5 task, we designed and recorded a new dataset named **DCASE2025 Task4 Dataset** [17, 18]. Because of the challenges in evaluating S5 for real recordings, we opted for a simulated dataset, making considerations to make it as realistic as possible. The resources needed to build such a dataset consist of the following.

- **Isolated target sound events \mathbf{s}_{c_k}** : isolated recordings of diverse sound event classes. In light of Eq. (1), these signals are preferably captured in anechoic conditions.
- **Room-impulse responses (RIRs) $\mathbf{h}_k^{(m)}$** : multichannel RIRs measured in various rooms.
- **Environmental noise $\mathbf{n}^{(m)}$** : environmental noise recorded with the same multichannel microphone array used for the RIRs in indoor and outdoor environments.

In addition to stationary, direction-independent environmental noise, it is often useful to include sporadic sound events that do not belong to the target classes. We refer to these as *interference sounds* and handle them as follows:

- **Interference sounds**: Recording of sound events of classes not included in the isolated target sound events mentioned above. When forming mixtures with Eq. 1, the interference signals are processed similarly to the target sound events.

The DCASE2025 Task4 Dataset consists of new recordings and curated data from publicly available datasets [19, 20, 21]. Eighteen classes listed in Table. 1 are selected for the target sound events. Among the materials that make up the DCASE2025 Task4 Dataset, our newly recorded material and curated materials from FOA-MEIR [21] are released on Zenodo [17, 18]. The remaining materials are obtained and filtered from their respective public datasets [19, 22, 20] via a download script that we provide on GitHub [23]. The training and evaluation mixtures $\mathbf{y}^{(m)}$ were synthesized from the above materials using a modified version of a spatial-audio simulator named SpatialScaper [24]. All mixtures were synthesized at 32kHz/16bit with a 10 second length.

3.2. Development dataset

The development dataset of the DCASE2025 Task4 Dataset [17] was constructed from various datasets, including both existing and newly recorded data specifically for this task. The isolated target sound events for the development set consist of our newly recorded data and curated samples from FSD50K [19] and EARS [22]. RIR

Table 1: The amount of recorded samples of isolated target sound events used to synthesize the DCASE 2025 Task 4 dataset. The numbers in parentheses indicate the number of samples curated from publicly available datasets [19, 22, 20], not newly recorded.

		Alarm		Cupboard				Foot Steps	Hair Dryer	Mechanical Fans	Musical Keyboard	Percussion	Pour	Speech	Vacuum Cleaner		Bicycle Bell		
		Clock	Blender	Buzzer	Clapping	Cough	Open								Close	Dishes		Doorbell	Typing
Dev	duration [s]	699	1337	359	1022	1501	1434	1174	526	2143	988	1912	2959	5321	601	4047	3304	1414	548
	# of samples	72 (42)	95 (52)	73 (21)	376 (312)	288 (211)	262 (184)	269 (208)	68 (63)	336 (298)	29 (25)	82 (59)	434 (397)	1881 (1796)	71 (37)	1203 (1195)	308 (228)	53 (46)	110 (54)
Eval	duration [s]	157	260	164	147	59	108	120	147	243	78	202	250	69	163	109	258	156	179
	# of samples	12	19	20	23	24	21	16	19	19	2	4	21	13	24	28	35	3	21

dataset was constructed by merging newly recorded RIRs for this task with curated material from the publicly released FOA-MEIR dataset [21]. Newly recorded RIRs were captured at six microphone positions—two positions in each of three rooms. At each position we captured 108 RIRs, giving 648 responses in total. The three rooms represent different acoustic conditions: a small conference room, a music-listening room, and a room with reflective walls. All background noise were curated from the publicly available FOA-MEIR dataset [21]. All interference was curated by removing items related to our target 18 classes from the background set in the dataset for Semantic Hearing [20]. The procedures for the new recordings and the curated material drawn from public datasets are detailed in Sec. 3.4.

The development dataset was further divided into three subsets: training, validation, and test. Mixtures for the test subset were pre-synthesized, while for the training and validation subsets, participants may generate mixtures using the provided data. Each clip contains between one and three target sound events, with at most three target sound events active simultaneously. The SNR for each target sound event ranges from 5 to 20 dB, with respect to the background environmental noise. Each mixture also includes one or two interfering sound events, with SNRs ranging from 0 to 15 dB.

3.3. Evaluation dataset

To ensure fairness in the challenge, isolated sources of the target sound events, RIRs, interference sounds, and environmental noise were all newly recorded for the evaluation data. In other words, the evaluation data does not include any publicly available data.

The main subset (files 0000–1619) contains mixtures with 1, 2 or 3 target sound events; 0, 1 or 2 interference events; and RIRs recorded at six microphone positions. The six positions are distributed across three rooms, with two positions recorded in each room: a small conference room, a large conference room and a room with reflective walls. These rooms are not included in the development set. These factors yield $3 \times 3 \times 6 = 54$ acoustic settings, and 30 mixtures were synthesized for each setting. The SNR settings for mixing are the same as for the development set.

Files 1620–2033 constitute the ‘partially known conditions’ subset. Mixtures in this subset were synthesized so that one element—RIRs, target sound event, background noise, or interference sound—was drawn from the training partition of the development set. This design enables a factor-specific evaluation of how well the systems generalize beyond their training conditions. The following subsets exceed the scope of this year’s S5 task. Files 2034–2141 contain no target events, while files 2142–2249 include multiple same-class target events arriving from different directions. Files 2250–2289 are recordings made in real indoor and outdoor environments; consequently, oracle target sources are unavailable in this split.

3.4. Recording details

Isolated target sound events were recorded in an anechoic chamber. Fig. 2 shows the configuration of microphones for this recording.

Figure 2: The Configuration of microphones used to record isolated sound events in an anechoic chamber

Figure 3: This plot shows performance of the submitted systems and the baseline (ResUNetK) on the evaluation set. Only the systems with the best CA-SDRi performance among those submitted by each team are selected.

The recording was made using three cardioid microphones to capture the sound events from the left, front, and right, and one omnidirectional microphone to capture the sound from above. The 4-channel configuration was not intended to be used as a microphone array, but simply to increase the variety of data for the target sound event by recording from different directions. During mixture synthesis for S5, one of these four channels is chosen at random and used as the monaural target sound event.

All RIRs were captured with the same first-order Ambisonics microphone (Sennheiser AMBEO VR Mic) and are provided in B-format (AmbiX). In both the development set and evaluation set, 108 RIRs were measured at each microphone location. These are composed of the relative positions of the following speakers and microphones: (i) the azimuth was swept in 20° steps to cover the full 360° ; (ii) the elevation was set to -20° , 0° , or 20° ; and (iii) the source distance was chosen from the range 0.75–1.50 m.

4. CHALLENGE RESULTS

4.1. Overview of submitted system’s performance

We received 24 submissions from 8 teams. Figure 3 shows the best-performing system from each team in terms of CA-SDRi (ranking score). As Fig. 3 (top) shows, seven of the eight teams surpassed our baseline, some of them by a large margin of more than 4 dB, indicating that significant progress toward solving S5 task has been

Figure 4: Class-wise box-plot for CA-SDRi score of submitted systems. The leftmost pair shows average score for development set (Dev (test)) and evaluation set (Eval) scores. To its right, eighteen plots present CA-SDRi for each target sound event class in evaluation set.

Figure 5: Box plot of CA-SDRi for each team’s best system under four partially known conditions. ‘Known IR’: evaluation RIRs seen in training; ‘Known Target’: target sound event samples seen; ‘Known Noise’: background noise seen; ‘Known Interference’: interference samples seen. The blue star indicates the performance of the top-ranked system [2].

achieved.

As described in Section 2.2, CA-SDRi combines label-prediction accuracy and source-separation quality. To examine these factors separately, we also report label-prediction accuracy (Fig. 3, middle) and SDRi computed only on clips where every sound event was correctly labeled (Fig. 3, bottom). The gains achieved by most systems primarily stem from improved separation. Notably, the top-ranked system places second in label-prediction accuracy but achieves the highest CA-SDRi due to its superior separation performance. This indicates that further improvement may be achieved by combining the separation and label prediction approaches of the two best teams.

Figure 4 compares CA-SDRi on the development-set test split and the evaluation set for best systems per team highlighted in Fig. 3. Across the board, CA-SDRi drops on the evaluation set, suggesting overfitting. In the class-wise CA-SDRi in the evaluation set, particularly poor performance was observed for “Blender” and “VacuumCleaner,” and these confusing classes may be lowering the overall performance.

4.2. Characteristic of submitted systems

This section outlines the characteristics of the submitted systems. The teams coupled source separation and its label prediction in several ways. Sequential pipelining, where tagging precedes separation, similar to the Baseline system [13], is employed in systems [4] and [7]. Systems [3] and [9] conditioned the separator with tag information through Feature-wise Linear Modulation (FiLM). An iterative sequential strategy—tagging, separation, and refined tagging—was adopted by [2], [5], and [8]. Systems [2] and [6] performed joint estimation of sound-event labels and separated signals. The system [6] stands out in that it employs a hybrid approach that combines a separation technique based on multichannel signal processing (multichannel Wiener Filter; MWF) and data-driven modeling based on DNN.

Table 2: PESQ, STOI, and PEAQ for the top-three submitted systems and the baseline system (ResUNetK). PESQ and STOI are evaluated for clips in which speech classes are detected. PEAQ is evaluated for the rest. Errors are indicated by standard deviation.

System	# of detected speech	PESQ↑ (1 – 4.5)	STOI↑ (0 – 1)	PEAQ↑ (-4 – 0)
Baseline [13]	246/251	2.39 ± 0.63	0.84 ± 0.11	-3.60 ± 0.43
Rank 1 [2]	241/251	2.88 ± 0.58	0.91 ± 0.08	-3.43 ± 0.48
Rank 2 [3]	249/251	2.97 ± 0.60	0.90 ± 0.07	-3.39 ± 0.51
Rank 3 [4]	246/251	2.77 ± 0.58	0.90 ± 0.10	-3.43 ± 0.50

4.3. Performance under partially known conditions

As described in Sec. 3, the evaluation set of the DCASE 2025 Task 4 Dataset contains **RIR**, **target sound event**, **background noise**, and **interference sound** that do not appear in the development set. This section examines how CA-SDRi changes when exactly one of these four components is made known, that is, drawn from the training data. Comparing these conditions reveals which unknown factors limit system performance. Figure 5 shows CA-SDRi for the original evaluation set and for the four partially known conditions. The highest median scores occur when either the **RIR** or the **target sound event** are known, indicating that unfamiliar acoustic environments and unseen target sound events are the primary sources of degradation. In contrast, making the **background noise** or the **interference sound** known yields little change relative to the original evaluation set.

4.4. Quality of separated sound events

Table 2 summarizes the perceptual quality of the separated signals for the three top-ranked systems and the baseline. PESQ and STOI were computed on clips containing speech, while PEAQ was computed on the remaining non-speech clips. The top submissions [2, 3, 4] outperform the baseline on every metric. For speech, PESQ scores near 3 (“fair/toll”) and STOI values around 0.90 indicate natural and intelligible quality, though additional refinement is needed for high-fidelity applications. For non-speech content, all systems obtain comparatively low PEAQ scores, revealing that perceptual fidelity for other sound events still requires improvement.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE VIEWS

This paper introduced the Spatial Semantic Segmentation of Sound Scenes (S5) task of DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 4, which targets joint detection and separation of spatial sound events from multichannel mixtures. For this task, we released the DCASE2025 Task 4 Dataset [17, 18], which comprises isolated target events, multichannel RIRs, environmental noise, and interference sounds. We evaluated 24 systems submitted for this challenge by eight teams and analyzed their performances and characteristics. The collective results confirmed that many approaches already surpass the naïve baseline, indicating steady progress in both tagging and separation modules. Future work should address generalization to unseen acoustic environments and novel sound events. A further challenge is separating and labeling multiple instances of the same class within a single clip. This scenario is common in practice but lies outside the current task, and all submissions performed poorly on it. Finally, the current systems evaluated on RIR-based simulation; extending evaluation to real recordings is essential to validate robustness in real-world deployments¹.

¹ Samples of real-recording inference in the top3 system is shown on the challenge results page.

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Importance-Weighted Domain Adaptation for Sound Source Tracking

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Abstract—In recent years, deep learning has significantly advanced sound source localization (SSL). However, training such models requires large labeled datasets, and real recordings are costly to annotate in particular if sources move. While synthetic data using simulated room impulse responses (RIRs) and noise offers a practical alternative, models trained on synthetic data suffer from domain shift in real environments. Unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA) can address this by aligning synthetic and real domains without relying on labels from the latter. The few existing UDA approaches however focus on static SSL and do not account for the problem of sound source tracking (SST), which presents two specific domain adaptation challenges. First, variable-length input sequences create mismatches in feature dimensionality across domains. Second, the angular coverages of the synthetic and the real data may not be well aligned either due to partial domain overlap or due to batch size constraints, which we refer to as directional diversity mismatch. To address these, we propose a novel UDA approach tailored for SST based on two key features. We employ the final hidden state of a recurrent neural network as a fixed-dimensional feature representation to handle variable-length sequences. Further, we use importance-weighted adversarial training to tackle directional diversity mismatch by prioritizing synthetic samples similar to the real domain. Experimental results demonstrate that our approach successfully adapts synthetic-trained models to real environments, improving SST performance.

Index Terms—sound source tracking, sound source localization, unsupervised domain adaptation, importance weighting, adversarial training

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound source localization (SSL), which refers to estimating the direction of arrivals (DoAs) of sound sources, is fundamental to applications requiring directional information, including speech enhancement [1], human-robot interaction [2], and automotive applications [3]. Traditional approaches exploit explicit models based on time difference of arrivals (TDoAs), such as steered response power with phase transform (SRP-PHAT) [4], [5], multiple signal classification (MUSIC) [6], and estimation of signal parameters via rotational invariance techniques (ESPRIT) [7]. However, these methods suffer significant performance degradation in challenging acoustic conditions with low signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) and high reverberation.

Deep learning has recently demonstrated substantial improvements [8]–[11] over traditional SSL methods, but their success critically depends on large-scale labeled datasets. Labeling data is time-consuming and costly, especially for moving sources, leading to a scarcity of real-world labeled data. As an alternative, room impulse response (RIR) simulation tools [12], [13] are used to generate extensive synthetic training data with diverse SNR and reverberation conditions, while small portions of real-world data serve for evaluation. However, models trained on synthetic data typically suffer performance drops due to simplified simulation models that do not fully capture the complexity of room acoustics and microphone characteristics, creating distribution mismatches between synthetic and real data, a phenomenon known as domain shift [14].

Unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA) attempts to mitigate the effect of domain shift by aligning features across source (synthetic)

and target (real-world) domains without requiring target labels. While extensively investigated in computer vision and natural language processing [15], few studies have addressed this problem in SSL. Takeda et al. [16] proposed entropy minimization to regularize DoA classification probabilities, and later [17] introduced an eliminative posterior probability constraint that forces the probability of less likely candidates to become zero to eliminate incoherent errors. However, both approaches are limited to discrete classification formulations. Domain adversarial training [18] for SSL has shown mixed results. While [19] reported minimal improvements, [20] achieved significant gains using ensemble domain adversarial networks with multiple domain discriminators at different network layers. Notably, none of these approaches address domain adaptation specifically for sound source tracking (SST).

SST presents unique UDA challenges beyond static localization. First, tracking requires processing variable-length temporal sequences, while many existing domain adaptation methods [15], [18], [21] are designed for fixed feature dimensionality and cannot directly handle temporal variability. Second, directional diversity mismatch between source and target data creates feature alignment instability in domain adaptation through two effects. At the domain level, angular coverages may differ significantly. While source domains typically contain full directional diversity, target domains may cover only limited angular ranges depending on recording settings, creating partial domain overlap [22]. At the batch level, SST systems must handle long-duration audio sequences (typically > 10 seconds [8], [9]), necessitating small batch sizes due to memory constraints. Consequently, directional diversity within batches may differ significantly between source and target data, creating inconsistent feature distributions that hinder effective domain alignment. These challenges render standard adversarial training approaches [19], [20] ineffective, as they fundamentally assume complete label space alignment both across domains and within batches [22].

To address these challenges, we propose a novel UDA approach tailored for SST with two key contributions. First, adopting the SST architecture from [9], [23], we employ the final hidden state of a recurrent neural network (RNN) as a fixed-dimensional feature representation within the domain discriminator to handle variable-length sequences. Second, we leverage importance-weighted adversarial training [22] to tackle directional diversity mismatch by prioritizing synthetic samples similar to the real domain. Experimental results demonstrate that our approach successfully adapts synthetic-trained models to real environments, improving SST performance. The code is available at [24].

In section 2, we review a commonly used SST model adopted for domain adaptation. In section 3, we describe the proposed domain adaptation approach. Section 4 presents our experimental evaluation, and section 5 concludes the paper.

2. SOUND SOURCE TRACKING

We adopt the convolutional recurrent neural network (CRNN) architecture used in [9], [23] to perform single-source SST. The model

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Fig. 1: The overview of the proposed method. (a) The CRNN model will first be trained on the source domain. (b) The pretrained model is adapted to the target domain using importance-weighted adversarial training.

is first trained on source domain data, considering tracking of sound sources in the azimuth direction spanning the range $[0, \pi)$. The input to the SST system concatenates the real and imaginary components of the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) of multi-channel acoustic signals, denoted as \mathbf{x}_s of size $2M \times K \times L$, where M is the number of microphone channels, K is the number of frequency bins, and L is the number of time frames. Rather than directly regressing angular directions, we employ likelihood encoding as in [19], [23], [25], where the network output represents the probability of source existence across $J = 180$ candidate directions spanning the range $[0, \pi)$. The model is trained to regress a sequence of likelihood values for ground truth DoA values in the azimuth direction, denoted as \mathbf{y}_s with dimensions $L \times J$. Given ground truth DoA values $\phi'(l)$ at each voice-active time frame l , and 180 candidate directions $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^{180}$, the desired output values are encoded via Gaussian functions

$$y_s(\phi_i, l) = \exp \left\{ -\frac{(\phi_i - \phi'(l))^2}{2\sigma^2} \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where σ defines the beam width, set to 16° as in [23]. For non-voice-active frames, we set $y_s(\phi_i, l) = 0$. Voice-active frames are identified using the WebRTC voice activity detector (VAD) [26].

The network architecture of the adopted SST model [9], [23] is shown in Fig. 1a. To facilitate the following explanation of domain adaptation, we split the model into two parts: a feature extractor F_s and a DoA estimator E_s , both specifically for the source domain. The feature extractor comprises five convolutional blocks followed by a gated recurrent unit (GRU). Each convolutional block contains two consecutive convolutional layers with 3×3 kernel size and 64 output channels, batch normalization, ReLU activation, and max pooling. Max pooling operations have kernel sizes of $[4, 2, 2, 2, 2]$ along the frequency axis and $[1, 1, 1, 1, 5]$ along the time axis. The resulting convolutional features are processed by a unidirectional GRU with

256 hidden units. The output of the GRU, denoted by $\mathbf{o}_s = F_s(\mathbf{x}_s)$, serves as the input to the DoA estimator E_s and also functions as a domain feature in the proposed domain adaptation approach. The DoA estimator consists of three fully connected (FC) layers with dimensions 512, 256, and 180, utilizing Tanh, ReLU, and sigmoid activations, respectively.

The model is trained to minimize the mean squared error (MSE) between the network predictions and the ground truth DoA likelihood representations. Given a batch of N input data samples $\mathbf{X}_s = \{\mathbf{x}_s^{(n)}\}$ with corresponding labels $\mathbf{Y}_s = \{\mathbf{y}_s^{(n)}\}$, $n = 1, \dots, N$, the MSE loss for SST is computed as

$$\mathcal{L}_{SST}(F_s, E_s) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \|E_s(F_s(\mathbf{x}_s^{(n)})) - \mathbf{y}_s^{(n)}\|_2^2, \quad (2)$$

where both F_s and E_s are updated during backward propagation. During inference, the estimated DoA is obtained by identifying the peak in the estimated encoded likelihood.

3. IMPORTANCE-WEIGHTED DOMAIN ADAPTATION FOR SOUND SOURCE TRACKING

Let $\mathcal{D}_s = \{\mathbf{X}_s, \mathbf{Y}_s\}$ represent the labeled source domain and $\mathcal{D}_t = \{\mathbf{X}_t\}$ represent the unlabeled target domain, where data samples are drawn from distributions p_s and p_t respectively. When deploying the model trained on the source domain to the target domain, the domain shift of the distribution mismatch between source and target domain data, i.e., $p_s \neq p_t$, leads to performance degradation on the target domain.

While domain adaptation approaches exist to address such distribution mismatch, SST presents two particular challenges: variable length features and diectional diversity mismatch between \mathcal{D}_s and \mathcal{D}_t . To address these issues, we propose to use the final hidden state of the RNN to handle variable length sequences and adopt importance-weighted domain adversarial training [22] originally introduced for image classification and employ it for SST. The resulting architecture is shown in Fig. 1b.

The adaptation process begins by initializing the target domain feature extractor F_t and DoA estimator E_t with weights from the pretrained model. During domain adaptation, F_s remains frozen to maintain consistent source domain representations, while F_t adapts to extract domain-invariant features from both the source and target domain data. The approach incorporates two binary domain discriminators, D_w and D , which share an identical architecture. Source samples are labeled as 1 and target samples as 0. D_w facilitates the importance weighting mechanism, while D performs domain adversarial training. In the following, we describe the domain discriminator architecture, importance-weighted adversarial training, and importance weighting mechanism.

3.1. Domain discriminator architecture

To handle the variable-length input sequences, we design our discriminator architecture to effectively aggregate long and variable-length temporal dynamics. Unlike previous works [19], [20] that operate on fixed-dimensional features and can therefore use convolutional layers or simple FC layers for domain discrimination, our approach must address the challenge of variable-length temporal features. Therefore, we design our discriminator with a GRU and employ its final hidden state to encode the complete temporal dynamics into a fixed-dimensional representation independent of input length.

Both discriminators first process features \mathbf{o}_s and \mathbf{o}_t from the feature extractors through a 256-unit GRU layer. The final hidden state of this GRU then passes through two FC layers: a 128-unit layer with ReLU

activation followed by a single-output layer with sigmoid activation for domain classification.

3.2. Importance-weighted adversarial training

The importance-weighted adversarial training [22] follows the same training approach as standard adversarial training [18]. The core principle is to align feature representations across domains through a weighted adversarial game between a feature extractor and a domain discriminator. In our implementation, the features \mathbf{o}_s and \mathbf{o}_t extracted from source and target domain data serve as input to the domain discriminator D . The loss function is given by [22],

$$\mathcal{L}_{DA}(D, F_t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N [w(\mathbf{o}_s^{(n)}) \log D(\mathbf{o}_s^{(n)}) + \log(1 - D(\mathbf{o}_t^{(n)}))], \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{o}_s^{(n)} = F_s(\mathbf{x}_s^{(n)})$ and $\mathbf{o}_t^{(n)} = F_t(\mathbf{x}_t^{(n)})$. For standard adversarial training [18], $w(\mathbf{o}_s^{(n)}) = 1$. The objective is to solve a minimax game, $\min_{F_t} \max_D \mathcal{L}_{DA}(D, F_t)$. The discriminator D maximizes the objective by correctly classifying source domain features and target domain features. Simultaneously, the target feature extractor F_t minimizes the objective by generating features that fool the discriminator. Through this adversarial process, the feature extractor learns domain-invariant representations that enable effective knowledge transfer from the labeled source domain to the unlabeled target domain. A gradient reversal layer (GRL) enables simultaneous training of the minmax game by reversing gradients for the feature extractor.

3.3. Importance weighting mechanism

To obtain the importance weights w , a second domain discriminator D_w is employed. The goal is to assign larger weights to source data samples that share similar feature characteristics with the target data, while assigning smaller weights to those with less overlap. This discriminator is first trained to distinguish between source and target domains using the binary cross entropy loss,

$$\mathcal{L}_W(D_w) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N [\log D_w(\mathbf{o}_s^{(n)}) + \log(1 - D_w(\mathbf{o}_t^{(n)}))]. \quad (4)$$

Since the final activation function in D_w is the logistic sigmoid function, the output $D_w(\mathbf{o}_s)$ represents the probability that a source sample belongs to the source domain. When $D_w(\mathbf{o}_s) \approx 1$, source samples are highly distinguishable from target samples and should receive lower weights in the adversarial training. Conversely, when $D_w(\mathbf{o}_s) \approx 0$, the source samples are similar to target samples and should receive higher weights. The importance weight is therefore inversely related to $D_w(\mathbf{o}_s)$,

$$w(\mathbf{o}_s) = 1 - D_w(\mathbf{o}_s). \quad (5)$$

These weights are normalized by the mean weight value per batch [22]. Note that the domain discriminator D_w is used solely to calculate the importance weights and does not participate in the adversarial training; therefore, gradients from D_w do not back propagate to update the feature extractor F_t . The obtained weights are then incorporated into the loss function in (3) to prioritize source samples that are most similar to the target domain during adversarial training.

3.4. Overall training objective

To preserve source domain performance while adapting to the target domain, we minimize the combined loss function,

$$\mathcal{L}(D, D_w, F_t, E_t) = \mathcal{L}_{SST}(F_t, E_t) + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{DA}(D, F_t) + \mathcal{L}_W(D_w). \quad (6)$$

Here, \mathcal{L}_{SST} is computed exclusively using source domain data to retain performance on the original task. The trade-off parameter λ controls the influence of the domain adversarial loss. When λ is too small, domain alignment is weak, and the model behaves similarly to source-only training. When λ is too large, the adversarial objective dominates, encouraging excessive domain invariance and causing the learned features to lose essential task-relevant characteristics.

4. EXPERIMENTS

4.1. Experimental setups

4.1.1. Datasets: Target Domain (Real-world Data): we use the RealMAN dataset [23], which contains 35.4 hours of moving speaker recordings across 32 different acoustic scenes with background noise, sampled at 48 kHz. The dataset employs a 32-channel microphone array, from which we extract a 9-channel subarray consisting of an 8-channel uniform circular array (3 cm radius) plus a center microphone. In the experiments, we consider single-source moving scenarios in three distinct acoustic scenes spanning indoor to outdoor environments: OfficeRoom3, OfficeLobby, and BasketballCourt1. These scenes provide training, validation, and test data with durations of (81, 7, 8), (51, 28, 8), and (40, 8, 42) minutes, respectively. We select these three scenes because they provide complete training, validation, and testing splits along with scene-specific background noise recordings. During adversarial training, the training data is augmented with background noise at SNR levels ranging from -10 dB to 15 dB, matching the SNR range found in the validation and test data [23].

Source Domain (Synthetic Data): we generate synthetic data using the same 9-channel microphone configuration as the target domain to ensure acoustic consistency. Following established protocols [8], we simulate rooms with dimensions randomly selected from $3 \times 3 \times 2.5$ m to $10 \times 8 \times 6$ m and reverberation times from 0.2 s to 1.0 s. RIRs are generated using `gpuRIR` [13]. Speech signals are randomly selected from the LibriSpeech corpus [27] and convolved with the generated RIRs, then corrupted with diffused noise at SNRs ranging from -10 dB to 15 dB. The diffused noise is generated using the toolbox [28] applied to the NOISEX-92 corpus [29]. Speech segments vary from 2 s to 10 s in duration. To enhance training diversity, each sample is generated on-the-fly with randomized acoustic conditions including source trajectories, microphone positions, source signals, noise characteristics, reverberation times, and SNRs.

Both target and source domain data is downsampled to 16 kHz for computational efficiency. STFT analysis uses a 32 ms window with 20 ms frame shift to extract time-frequency representations.

4.1.2. Evaluation metrics: Performance is evaluated during voice-active segments using mean absolute error (MAE) of azimuth estimates for across all time frames, and localization accuracy (Acc), defined as the percentage of frames with MAE below 5° .

4.1.3. Training configuration: The training process comprises two phases. In the first phase, the model is trained on the source domain for 150 epochs with a batch size of 16, using the Adam optimizer [30] and a learning rate of 0.0001. The model checkpoint is selected based on its MAE performance on simulated testing data.

Subsequently, the model undergoes domain adaptation for an additional 60 epochs with the same learning rate, and early stopping. To mitigate training instability in early stages, we employ a gradual schedule for the adversarial trade-off parameter following [18],

$$\lambda = \frac{2u}{1 + \exp(-p)} - u, \quad (7)$$

where p gradually increases over training steps, allowing λ to smoothly approach its upper bound u . The model checkpoint selection is

Fig. 2: Boxplots comparing the MAE distributions of different methods across various acoustic scenes. The boxes span the interquartile range (IQR, 25th to 75th percentiles), with the red line marking the median. Whiskers extend to the minimum and maximum values within 1.5×IQR from the quartiles. Diamond markers indicate mean MAE values, while crosses denote outliers beyond the whiskers.

also based on the model’s MAE performance on a small validation set. Although this may appear to conflict with the principles of unsupervised learning, validation-based model selection is widely accepted in domain adaptation for computer vision tasks [18], [21], [22]. While alternative strategies for checkpoint selection without validation sets exist [31], they are typically tailored to classification problems. Moreover, collecting and annotating a small validation set is far more feasible than creating large annotated training datasets.

4.1.4. *Baselines:* We denote the proposed method as SST-IWDA. To evaluate its effectiveness, we compare it with two baseline models. The first baseline, SST-SO, is a source-only model trained exclusively on source domain data. For a fair comparison, the pretrained model is further trained for 60 additional epochs, with model checkpoint selection based on validation performance on the target domain data for each acoustic scene. The second baseline, SST-DA, implements standard adversarial domain adaptation [18] without the importance weighting mechanism.

4.2. Results and discussion

In the first experiment, we adapt the pretrained model using target data from various acoustic environments. The results using $u = 0.001$, presented in Table 1, show that SST-DA yields modest performance gains over the source-only baseline SST-SO. However, the proposed approach SST-IWDA consistently achieves the lowest MAE and highest accuracy among all methods. For example, in OfficeRoom3, SST-IWDA reduces the MAE from 3.03° to 2.57° and boosts accuracy from 80% to 89%. Similarly, in BasketballCourt1, we observe a reduction in MAE from 6.26° to 5.62°, with accuracy improving from 68% to 76%.

While SST-SO performs reasonably well in OfficeRoom3 and BasketballCourt1, both characterized by relatively low MAEs, its performance deteriorates substantially in OfficeLobby, where the estimation error reaches 17.12°. This degradation is likely due to a pronounced mismatch in spatial correlation coefficients between the real-world office lobby noise and the diffuse noise assumption employed in our simulated training data [23]. Despite this domain gap, SST-IWDA improves the MAE by nearly 2° (from 17.12° to 15.39°) and increases accuracy by 5 percentage points.

The boxplot analysis in Fig. 2 reveals additional insights into the performance of the proposed approach. Domain adaptation can reduce both the number of outliers and their magnitude, which correlates with the observed increase in accuracy. SST-IWDA consistently reduces the interquartile range (IQR) and whisker lengths, as well as the median values. In contrast, SST-DA exhibits inconsistent behavior: it sometimes increases the quartile values and whisker lengths (as observed in OfficeRoom3), while in other cases it reduces the IQR

Table 1: Performance comparison across different acoustic scenes (lower MAE and higher Acc indicate better performance).

Method	OfficeRoom3		OfficeLobby		BasketballCourt1	
	MAE (°)	Acc (%)	MAE (°)	Acc (%)	MAE (°)	Acc (%)
SST-SO	3.03	80	17.12	51	6.26	68
SST-DA	2.92	83	16.19	56	5.93	71
SST-IWDA	2.57	89	15.39	56	5.62	76

Fig. 3: Domain adaptation performance across different values of parameter u for the OfficeRoom3 acoustic scene.

effectively but introduces outliers with larger magnitudes (as seen in BasketballCourt1).

In the second experiment, we evaluate domain adaptation performance in OfficeRoom3 under varying values of the upper bound parameter u from (7), which controls the strength of adversarial training. We test u of values 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.05 for both SST-DA and SST-IWDA. As shown in Fig. 3, small u values yield performance similar to SST-SO. Increasing u initially improves results, but excessive values degrade both MAE and accuracy. SST-IWDA consistently outperforms SST-SO across all tested values, whereas SST-DA rapidly surpasses SST-SO’s MAE (3.03°) and drops below its Acc (80%) as u rises. These findings confirm the robustness of the proposed importance-weighted adversarial training in balancing adaptation and task-specific learning.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a novel domain adaptation approach for SST with two key contributions. First, we utilize GRU’s final hidden state to encode variable-length sequences into fixed-dimensional representations within the domain discriminator. Second, we use importance-weighted adversarial training to mitigate directional diversity mismatch between synthetic and real data distributions. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method outperforms baseline approaches and exhibits enhanced robustness across different scenes.

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Discriminative Anomalous Sound Detection Using Pseudo Labels, Target Signal Enhancement, and Ensemble Feature Extractors

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Abstract—We propose discriminative anomalous sound detection (ASD) systems designed to handle unlabeled data, noisy environments, and first-shot conditions. First, since discriminative methods suffer from significant performance degradation under unlabeled conditions, we generate pseudo labels to effectively train the discriminative feature extractors. Second, to improve noise robustness, we introduce a target signal enhancement (TSE) model as a pre-processing step. The TSE model is trained utilizing a small amount of clean machine sounds, together with a larger amount of noisy machine sounds. Third, to increase robustness across various machine types in first-shot conditions, we employ diverse architectures as feature extractors and ensemble their anomaly scores. Experimental results show that our systems achieve official scores of 64.85% and 59.99% on the DCASE 2025 development and evaluation sets, respectively, where the score is calculated as the harmonic mean of the AUC and partial AUC ($p = 0.1$) over all machine types and domains.

Index Terms—anomalous sound detection, pseudo labels, target signal enhancement, ensemble

1. INTRODUCTION

Anomalous sound detection (ASD) aims to identify abnormal machine behavior based on acoustic signals [1]–[5]. Due to the scarcity of anomalous sound data, ASD systems are typically trained using only normal machine sounds. ASD systems compute anomaly scores based on deviations from the normal sound distribution, assigning higher scores to sounds that are more likely to be anomalous.

State-of-the-art ASD methods are based on discriminative approaches [6]–[10]. This approach first trains a feature extractor to classify meta-information labels, such as machine type and operational status, associated with normal machine sounds. An anomaly score is then computed for each test sample by measuring its distance from normal training samples in the discriminative feature space. This discriminative space effectively captures differences in machine sounds, leading to high ASD performance.

While high ASD performance can be achieved with discriminative approaches, they still face several challenges in real-world applications, including the lack of meta-information labels, noisy environments, and first-shot conditions. First, although meta-information labels are essential for effectively training the feature extractor, they are sometimes unavailable in real-world scenarios, as collecting such labels requires human annotation or additional monitoring systems [5]. Second, since ASD systems are typically deployed in factory environments, machine sounds are often contaminated by heavy noise, which can lead to misdetections. Third, it is desirable to develop ASD methods that can be applied to various machine types without relying on machine-specific knowledge including preliminary performance validation results for the target machine type (i.e., under first-shot conditions [4]).

In this paper, we propose a discriminative ASD system designed to address these challenges (Fig.1). First, to effectively train the feature extractor under unlabeled conditions, we adopt pseudo-label generation techniques [10]. Second, to mitigate performance degradation caused by noise, we introduce a target signal enhancement (TSE) model as a pre-processing step. The TSE model consists of

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed system

a neural network trained via multi-task learning of reconstruction and classification losses using a small amount of clean machine sounds along with a larger amount of noisy machine sounds. Third, to improve generalization ability across various machine types, we employ diverse architectures as feature extractors and ensemble their anomaly scores. We conduct an experimental evaluation on the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2 dataset [11]. The results demonstrate that each component of our system is effective, and our system achieved fourth place in the official team rankings. Specifically, our system achieved official DCASE scores of 64.85% and 59.99% on the DCASE 2025 development and evaluation sets, respectively, whereas the official baseline system [12] achieved 56.26% and 56.51%.¹

2. PROPOSED METHOD

Sections 2.1 and 2.2 describe the architectures of the proposed TSE and ASD models, respectively. Section 2.3 presents strategies for utilizing the TSE model in the ASD task.

2.1. TSE Model

Following the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2 [11], we assume that a supplementary dataset is available for each machine type in

¹The result on the evaluation set was obtained from the DCASE official website, <https://dcase.community/challenge2025/task-first-shot-unsupervised-anomalous-sound-detection-for-machine-condition-monitoring-results>

addition to the training dataset. The training dataset consists of noisy machine sounds, while the supplementary dataset contains a small amount of either clean machine sounds or machine-specific in-domain noise, where the noise characteristics differ across machine types. We construct TSE models by utilizing both the training and supplementary datasets.

The TSE model is separately trained for each machine type using the following multi-task loss L_{TSE} .

$$L_{\text{TSE}} = \lambda L_{\text{Recon}} + L_{\text{Class}}, \quad (1)$$

where λ is a hyperparameter that balances L_{Recon} and L_{Class} . L_{Recon} is defined as follows:

$$L_{\text{Recon}} = \mathcal{L}_D(\mathbf{x}_{\text{Target}}, f_{\text{TSE}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{Target}} + \mathbf{n})), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_D(\cdot, \cdot)$ is an arbitrary reconstruction loss function, $f_{\text{TSE}}(\cdot)$ is the TSE model, $\mathbf{x}_{\text{Target}}$ is the target signal—either a clean machine sound or in-domain noise—provided in the supplementary data, and \mathbf{n} is out-domain noise drawn from AudioSet [13]. When $\mathbf{x}_{\text{Target}}$ is in-domain noise, the TSE model is trained to extract the in-domain noise components. Accordingly, enhanced machine sounds are obtained by subtracting the estimated noise from the original noisy input.

L_{Class} is defined as $L_{\text{Class}}^{\text{Clean}}$ when clean machine sounds are available, and as $L_{\text{Class}}^{\text{Noise}}$ when noise signals are available in the supplementary data:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\text{Class}}^{\text{Clean}} &= \mathcal{L}_C(f_{\text{Class}}(f_{\text{TSE}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyTM}})), \mathbf{l}_{\text{Meta}}) \\ &+ \mathcal{L}_C(f_{\text{Class}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{CleanTM}}), \mathbf{l}_{\text{Meta}}) \\ &+ \mathcal{L}_C(f_{\text{Class}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyNM}}), \mathbf{l}_{\text{NoisyNM}}), \\ L_{\text{Class}}^{\text{Noise}} &= \mathcal{L}_C(f_{\text{Class}}(f_{\text{TSE}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyTM}})), \mathbf{l}_{\text{NoiseTM}}) \\ &+ \mathcal{L}_C(f_{\text{Class}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyTM}} - f_{\text{TSE}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyTM}})), \mathbf{l}_{\text{Meta}}) \\ &+ \mathcal{L}_C(f_{\text{Class}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoiseTM}}), \mathbf{l}_{\text{NoiseTM}}) \\ &+ \mathcal{L}_C(f_{\text{Class}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyNM}}), \mathbf{l}_{\text{NoisyNM}}), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{L}_C(\cdot, \cdot)$ is an arbitrary classification loss function, and $f_{\text{Class}}(\cdot)$ is a classifier. $\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyTM}}$ is the noisy machine sounds in the training dataset, while $\mathbf{x}_{\text{CleanTM}}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoiseTM}}$ are the clean machine sounds and in-domain noise in the supplementary dataset, respectively. $\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyTM}}$, $\mathbf{x}_{\text{CleanTM}}$, and $\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoiseTM}}$ all correspond to the target machine type, whereas $\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyNM}}$ is the noisy machine sounds in the training datasets of non-target machine types. \mathbf{l}_{Meta} is the meta-information label, while $\mathbf{l}_{\text{NoisyNM}}$ and $\mathbf{l}_{\text{NoiseTM}}$ are single-class labels assigned to $\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyNM}}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoiseTM}}$, respectively. This classification loss enables us to utilize the real noisy machine sounds $\mathbf{x}_{\text{NoisyTM}}$ for training the TSE model, where $\mathbf{x}_{\text{Target}} + \mathbf{n}$ in L_{Recon} is a synthetic mixture that includes out-of-domain noise \mathbf{n} . For the classifier $f_{\text{Class}}(\cdot)$, we use a frozen pre-trained BEATs model [14] with a trainable linear classification head, encouraging the TSE model to focus on learning the denoising effect rather than relying on the classifier.

2.2. ASD Model

We describe the architecture of our discriminative ASD model. Hereafter, we refer to the discriminative feature extractor as the *frontend*, and the anomaly score computation module as the *backend*.

2.2.1. Frontend: To improve the robustness of the ASD model across various machine types, we employ four different architectures for the frontend: Spec, BEATs, EAT, and SSLAM. Spec refers to an architecture that incorporates an amplitude spectrum and multi-resolution spectrograms as input features [10]. Spec independently transforms each input feature into a D_{Spec} -dimensional feature via

convolutional neural networks. Subsequently, the D_{Spec} -dimensional features are concatenated to form a MD_{Spec} -dimensional feature, where M is the number of input features. Spec is trained from scratch using classification of meta-information labels. This architecture enables capturing anomalies from multiple perspectives, thereby improving ASD performance [10].

Based on the successful application of self-supervised learning (SSL) models to the ASD task [8], [15], we employ three SSL models: BEATs [14], EAT [16], and SSLAM [17]. BEATs iteratively trains an acoustic tokenizer and a SSL model [14]. The SSL model is trained via a masked prediction task on discrete tokens generated by the tokenizer. The tokenizer is randomly initialized in the first iteration and then iteratively updated via knowledge distillation from the SSL model obtained in the previous iteration.

EAT is a SSL model based on the masked latent bootstrapping framework, in which a student model is trained via masked language modeling using latent representations generated by a teacher model, and the teacher is continuously updated by the student [16]. To capture both global and local information, EAT combines utterance- and frame-level reconstruction losses [16].

SSLAM refines the masked latent bootstrapping framework to enhance its capability in handling polyphonic sounds [17]. SSLAM trains a student model on mixtures so that it preserves the characteristics of the teacher model’s representations for each individual source composing the mixture.

Following previous work [8], we fine-tune SSL models through a meta-information label classification task using low-rank adaptation (LoRA) [18]. From BEATs, we obtain a 768-dimensional feature sequence. We aggregate this feature sequence into a single representation using a statistics pooling layer [19], and project it to a D_{SSL} -dimensional feature using a linear layer. The resulting D_{SSL} -dimensional feature is used for both the classification task and the subsequent anomaly score computation. For EAT and SSLAM, we obtain a 768-dimensional CLS feature, and project it to a D_{SSL} -dimensional feature using a linear layer.

Additionally, since the effectiveness of the meta-information labels depends on the machine type [10], we also employ frozen pre-trained SSL models as frontends to further improve robustness across various machine types [20]. For BEATs, we average the output sequence to obtain a 768-dimensional feature, whereas for EAT and SSLAM, we directly use the 768-dimensional CLS feature.

2.2.2. Backend: We employ the same backend as in previous works [21]. The backend computes an anomaly score as the minimum cosine distance between an observation and the training data in the feature space. Since there is a data imbalance between the source and target domains, we apply SMOTE oversampling [22] to the limited training data in the target domain.

2.2.3. Pseudo-label Generation: We assume unlabeled conditions in the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2 [11], where the meta-information labels include machine type and attributes (e.g., machine operational status), but the attributes are unavailable for some machine types. To effectively train the frontend under the unlabeled conditions, we employ pseudo-label generation techniques [10]. The pseudo-label generation consists of two steps: extracting features from the training dataset and generating pseudo labels by applying clustering to the feature space. Although previous work used pre-trained PANNs [23] and OpenL3 [24] models as feature extractors for pseudo-label generation [10], we newly employ BEATs. Specifically, we average the 768-dimensional feature sequence extracted by the BEATs and then apply principal component analysis to reduce its dimensionality from 768 to 50. For the clustering, we use Gaussian mixture model, where

Table 1: Evaluation results. The values represent the harmonic mean of the official scores over all machine types. “Ny” and “Enh” indicate the noisy and enhanced machine sounds, respectively. In the “Label” column, “Ny” and “Enh” indicate pseudo labels generated from the noisy and enhanced machine sounds, respectively, while “Org” indicate the original labels. The last row shows the performance obtained by the frozen pre-trained SSL models.

Train	Test	Label	Spec	BEATs	EAT	SSLAM
Ny	Ny	Org	60.10	61.74	62.40	62.31
		Ny	61.77	64.14	63.69	63.34
		Enh	61.61	63.63	63.95	62.78
Enh	Enh	Org	60.29	64.43	62.62	63.16
		Ny	62.63	64.54	63.32	64.20
		Enh	62.36	64.37	63.87	64.75
Ny, Enh	Ny	Org	60.77	61.62	62.51	61.95
		Ny	61.86	63.84	63.82	63.55
		Enh	61.04	62.99	63.73	63.77
No	Ny	No		58.22	60.20	59.30

the number of clusters is determined by the Bayesian information criterion with a maximum of eight clusters.

2.3. Strategies to utilize TSE for ASD

We propose three strategies for using the TSE model on the ASD frontends during training and inference: (1) a baseline approach that uses the original noisy machine sounds for both training and inference; (2) an approach that uses enhanced machine sounds for both training and inference; (3) an approach that uses both noisy and enhanced machine sounds during training, but only noisy machine sounds during inference. In the third approach, we expect the ASD models to focus on machine sound components by jointly using enhanced machine sounds for classification training, even though noisy machine sounds are used for inference.

We also utilize the TSE model for pseudo-label generation. We generate pseudo labels from noisy and enhanced machine sounds separately. Although pseudo labels that reflect noise differences can lead to performance degradation [10], we employ not only enhanced but also original noisy machine sounds for pseudo-label generation, taking into account the potential loss of machine sound components caused by the TSE processing.

3. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATIONS

3.1. Experimental setups

We conducted an experimental evaluation using the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2 dataset, which partially includes ToyADMOS2 [25] and MIMII DG [26]. The dataset includes 15 machine types, each of which is assigned to either the development or evaluation subset. Specifically, the development set contains seven machine types (bearing, fan, gearbox, slider, ToyCar, ToyTrain, and valve), while the evaluation set contains eight (AutoTrash, HomeCamera, ToyPet, ToyRCCar, BandSealer, Polisher, ScrewFeeder, and CoffeeGrinder). For each machine type, training, supplementary, and test datasets are provided. The training dataset consists of 1,000 samples of normal machine sounds, with 990 samples from the source domain and 10 from the target domain. The supplementary dataset includes 100 samples of either clean machine sounds or in-domain noise. The test dataset contains 200 samples in total, including both normal and anomalous machine sounds from the source and target domains. Each recording is a 5 to 12-second single channel signal sampled at 16 kHz.

The architecture of the TSE model was a small-size TF-LoCoformer [27] without positional encoding. For the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) used in the TF-LoCoformer, the DFT size and frame shift were set to 512 and 128, respectively. For the loss

function, λ was set to 0.5, and the reconstruction loss \mathcal{L}_D was the negative signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) loss. The classification loss \mathcal{L}_C was the Sub-cluster AdaCos (SCAC) [28] with 16 trainable sub-cluster centers and a fixed scale parameter. We trained the TSE model for 2,400 epochs with a mini-batch size of 8 (i.e., 28,800 steps). Each sample was truncated or padded to 6 seconds. We used the AdamW optimizer [29] with gradient clipping at a maximum L_2 -norm of 5. The learning rate was linearly increased from 0 to 0.0004 over the first 1,250 steps. The SNR for mixing $\mathbf{x}_{\text{Target}}$ and \mathbf{n} was randomly selected from the range $[-5, 5]$ dB. We manually inspected several samples of the enhanced machine sounds in the training dataset and decided to apply the TSE model except for fan, gearbox, BandSealer, and ToyRCCar because the TSE processing possibly degrades important machine sound components.

For Spec of the ASD frontend, we used three spectrograms with different DFT sizes of 256, 1024, and 4096, together with an amplitude spectrum. The frame shift was half of the DFT size, and frequency bins in the range of 200 Hz to 8000 Hz were used. The network consisted of the ResNet architecture [30] similar to that in [7]. The feature dimension D_{Spec} was set to 128 and the number of input features M was 4, resulting in a 512-dimensional feature vector. We trained Spec for 16 epochs when using either the noisy or enhanced dataset, and for 8 epochs when jointly using both datasets. We used the AdamW optimizer with a fixed learning rate of 0.001 and a mini-batch size of 64. The loss function was the SCAC [28] with 16 trainable sub-cluster centers and a fixed scale parameter. Mixup [31] was applied with a probability of 50%.

For SSL-based frontends, we used pre-trained checkpoints from their respective repositories: BEATs_iter3.pt for BEATs, EAT-base_epoch10_pt.pt for EAT, and SSLAM_Pretrained/checkpoint_last.pt for SSLAM. LoRA was applied to the query and key projection layers within the Transformer encoder for BEATs, and to the query, key, and value projection layers for EAT and SSLAM. For all SSL-based frontends, the LoRA rank was set to 64 and the feature dimension D_{SSL} was set to 256. We fine-tuned the SSL models for 25 epochs with a mini-batch size of 8 (i.e., 46,875 steps). We used the AdamW optimizer, and the learning rate was linearly increased from 0 to 0.0001 over the first 5,000 steps. The loss function and mixup probability were the same as those used for Spec.

For SMOTE in the backend, we set the oversampling ratio to 20% and the number of neighbors to 2. For each system, we averaged anomaly scores across four different random seeds.

As an evaluation metric, we used the DCASE official scores, calculated as the harmonic mean of the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (AUC) and the partial AUC (pAUC) with $p = 0.1$. The AUC was calculated for each domain using the normal samples from that domain and the anomalous samples from both domains, while the pAUC was calculated using samples from both domains.

3.2. Experimental results

Table 1 shows the harmonic mean of the official scores across all machine types for each frontend under each training and testing strategies using the TSE model. First, when original labels are used for training, BEATs and SSLAM significantly improve performance by using enhanced sounds for both training and testing, while Spec and EAT show almost no change in performance even if using the enhanced sounds. Additionally, training jointly using noisy and enhanced machine sounds slightly improves the performance of Spec when original labels are used. The effectiveness of pseudo labels is

Table 2: Evaluation results for each machine type. The values represent the official scores. In the “ID” column, Spec, BEATs, EAT, and SSLAM indicate individual systems, while ① to ⑩ indicate ensemble systems that combine Spec, BEATs, EAT, and SSLAM under the same training and testing strategy. “hmean” indicates the harmonic mean of the scores over all machine types. “Ny” and “Enh” indicate the noisy and enhanced machine sounds, respectively. In the “Label” column, “Ny” and “Enh” indicate pseudo labels generated from the noisy and enhanced machine sounds, respectively, while “Org” indicate the original labels. The last row shows the performance obtained by the frozen pre-trained SSL models. * indicate machine types without attribute information.

ID	Train	Test	Label	bearing*	fan	gearbox	slider*	ToyCar	ToyTrain*	valve	hmean
Spec				57.93	51.12	62.10	55.85	59.55	62.34	78.10	60.10
BEATs				56.97	59.73	63.86	57.69	58.32	66.09	72.42	61.74
EAT	Ny	Ny	Org	57.02	58.66	70.46	59.09	59.45	62.03	73.86	62.40
SSLAM				56.41	56.64	71.97	62.41	59.75	61.83	70.73	62.31
①			Org	59.95	54.54	66.16	58.05	59.03	64.98	80.39	62.43
②	Ny	Ny	Ny	61.45	53.67	69.15	59.32	59.81	67.22	83.43	63.75
③			Enh	70.44	52.80	68.62	56.93	59.69	65.81	81.60	63.94
④			Org	60.04	51.97	65.35	62.06	58.31	66.81	83.18	62.81
⑤	Enh	Enh	Ny	68.40	52.03	68.07	60.56	59.53	65.77	87.95	64.57
⑥			Enh	68.43	51.71	67.54	60.06	59.73	66.57	89.11	64.58
⑦			Org	57.05	53.38	66.63	60.96	59.24	64.85	82.45	62.44
⑧	Ny,	Ny	Ny	65.14	53.75	67.48	60.89	58.93	65.77	84.36	64.09
⑨	Enh		Enh	67.08	51.78	65.72	59.62	59.18	65.39	82.97	63.38
⑩	No	Ny	No	55.51	51.78	55.68	58.98	62.26	66.90	79.54	60.44

Table 3: Evaluation results for the ensemble system combining different training and testing strategies. The values represent the official scores. “Dev” and “Eval” indicates the harmonic mean of the scores over machine types in the development and evaluation sets, respectively. The submission names are used for the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2 [11].

Submission Name	ID	Ensemble	Dev	Eval
Fujimura_NU_task2_1	①	(⑤+⑥)/2	64.85	59.99
	②	(⑦+⑧+⑨)/3	63.76	
	③	(②+③+⑤+⑥)/4	64.91	
Fujimura_NU_task2_2	④	0.75①+0.25⑩	62.44	58.51
Fujimura_NU_task2_3	⑤	0.75②+0.25⑩	63.73	59.34
Fujimura_NU_task2_4	⑥	0.75③+0.25⑩	64.75	59.91

consistently observed across all training and testing strategies. Spec, BEATs, and SSLAM achieve their best performance when we use both enhanced machine sounds and pseudo labels for training. There is no consistent trend regarding whether pseudo labels generated from noisy or enhanced machine sounds yield better results. Finally, SSL-based models consistently outperform Spec.

Table 2 shows the evaluation result for each machine type. The table includes the performance of the ensemble system that combines Spec, BEATs, EAT, and SSLAM under the same training and testing strategy. The ensemble weights were set to 1/2, 1/6, 1/6, and 1/6 for Spec, BEATs, EAT, and SSLAM, respectively. We observe that systems ⑤ and ⑥, which use enhanced machine sounds and pseudo labels, achieve high performance, significantly improving results for the bearing and valve machine types. Additionally, system ⑩ shows competitive performance on ToyCar and ToyTrain without fine-tuning the SSL models. Finally, by comparing ensemble system ① with individual frontends, we find that ① consistently achieves high performance across all machine types, with harmonic mean scores that are higher than or similar to those of the individual frontends. This result highlights the effectiveness of ensembling multiple frontends under first-shot conditions.

Table 3 shows the official scores of the ensemble system combining different training and testing strategies. The following consistent performance ranking highlights the effectiveness of the TSE and pseudo labels: (1) ① which uses enhanced machine sounds for both training and testing and also uses pseudo labels (ensemble of ⑤ and ⑥), (2) ③ which uses either noisy or enhanced machine sounds for both training and testing and also uses pseudo labels (ensemble of ②, ③, ⑤, ⑥, and ⑩), (3) ⑤ which jointly uses noisy and enhanced

Fig. 2: Comparison of our system with the seven top-performing systems and the official baseline systems on the evaluation set of the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2.

machine sounds for training and uses either original or pseudo labels (ensemble of ⑦, ⑧, ⑨, and ⑩), and (4) ④ which uses neither TSE nor pseudo labels (ensemble of ① and ⑩).

Finally, Fig. 2 compares our system with the seven top-performing systems [32]–[37] and the official baseline systems [12] in the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2. Our system significantly outperforms the baseline systems and ranks fourth in the challenge.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a discriminative ASD system to tackle the challenges of unlabeled data, noise, and first-shot conditions. First, we effectively utilized the unlabeled training data by generating pseudo labels through clustering in the BEATs feature space. Second, we introduced TSE models trained with a multi-task loss using both a small supplementary dataset and larger noisy training dataset. The TSE models were used as a pre-processing step for training, testing, and pseudo-label generation. Third, we ensembled multiple frontends—Spec, BEATs, EAT, and SSLAM—to handle diverse machine types. Experimental results showed that pseudo labels and TSE pre-processing significantly improved performance, and the ensemble of frontends outperformed individual frontends.

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A THREE-LEVEL EVALUATION PROTOCOL FOR ACOUSTIC SCENE UNDERSTANDING OF LARGE LANGUAGE AUDIO MODELS

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Abstract—Reaching a semantic understanding of complex acoustic scenes requires computational models to capture the temporal-spatial sound source composition as well as individual sound events. This is a great challenge for computational models due to the large variety of everyday sound events and the extensive temporal-spectral overlap in real-life acoustic scenes. In this work, we aim to evaluate the acoustic scene understanding capabilities of two large audio-language models (LALMs). As a challenging scenario, we use the USM dataset, which features synthetic urban soundscapes with 2-6 overlapping sound sources per mixture. Our main contribution is a novel three-layer evaluation protocol, which includes four analysis tasks for low-level sound event understanding (sound event tagging), mid-level understanding and reasoning (sound polyphony estimation, sound source loudness ranking), as well as high-level scene understanding (audio captioning). We apply standardized metrics to assess the models’ performances for each task. The proposed multi-layer protocol allows for a fine-grained analysis of model behavior across soundscapes of various complexity levels. Our results indicate that despite their remarkable controllability using textual instructions, the ability of state-of-the-art LALMs to understand acoustic scenes is still limited as the performance on individual analysis tasks degrades with increasing sound polyphony.

Index Terms—audio captioning, large audio-language models, sound event tagging, sound polyphony estimation, sound source loudness ranking

1. INTRODUCTION

Large audio language models (LALMs) are multi-modal neural networks that learn joint representations of audio and text data. This class of models represents an important milestone on the path towards general audio intelligence, as they demonstrated state-of-the-art performance in several machine listening tasks. To this day, a major challenge for LALMs is understanding complex acoustic scenes in everyday life scenarios. Such scenes are shaped not only by the tonal diversity and overlap of sounds but also by the spatio-temporal relationships among individual sound sources.

Previous studies on evaluating the reasoning skills of audio language models have focused mainly on audio reasoning tasks, such as compositional reasoning and attribute binding by comparing audio captions. While compositional reasoning looks at how effectively a model creates new meanings from existing concepts like understanding the order of occurrence between multiple acoustic events, attribute binding focuses on its precision in matching attributes to specific acoustic events [1]. In the MMAU (Massive Multi-Task Audio Understanding) benchmark [2], the following audio reasoning types were tested: *temporal reasoning* involves inferring the timing and duration of individual sound events, *acoustic-source inference* focuses on identifying sound sources for each sound event, *eco-acoustic knowledge* involves inferring the overall environmental setting from ambient and sound event cues, *ambient sound interpretation* relates to understanding background sounds from the entire soundscape recording, *event-based sound reasoning* involves identifying causal relationships between sound events, and *sound-based event recognition* focuses on inferring high-level scenes or activities from multiple sound events. While MMAU evaluates audio recognition and reasoning tasks

Table 1: Semantic Levels in Acoustic Scene Understanding

Semantic Level	Task(s)	Objective(s)
Low	Sound event tagging (T ₁)	Identify audible sound sources
Medium	Sound polyphony estimation (T ₂)	Count audible sound sources
	Ranking-by-loudness (T ₃)	Rank sound sources by loudness
High	Audio captioning (T ₄)	Describe an acoustic scene as a text caption

through multiple choice question answers, other benchmarks, such as CMM (The Curse of Multi-Modalities) have examined hallucinations in large multi-modal models to assess the gap between the factual multi-modal input and the generated text [3]. Other LALM evaluation studies use discriminative tasks to study sound object hallucinations [4]. Although these benchmarks progress in general audio reasoning evaluation, there is a current lack of studies on the abilities of LALMs to understand complex acoustic scenes.

As our main contribution, we propose a novel three-level evaluation protocol for acoustic scene understanding of LALMs as shown in Table 1. We focus on three semantic levels of acoustic scene understanding through four tasks: sound event tagging (low-level), sound polyphony estimation, and the ranking of sound sources by loudness (mid-level), as well as audio captioning (high-level). We implement this protocol using the example of the USM dataset [5], which includes five-second long polyphonic soundscapes generated by systematically mixing isolated sound recordings from the FSD50k dataset [6]. Due to its tonal diversity and detailed annotations of audible sound sources, the dataset allows us to examine the performance of LALMs in various tasks to be examined depending on the sound polyphony, i. e., the number of audible sound sources.

As a concrete use case, we select two top-performing LALMs from the MMAU benchmark and analyze in detail their acoustic scene understanding capabilities. We highlight the different strengths and unexpected pitfalls, including how evaluation metrics fluctuate due to hallucinated predictions. The correlation of the metrics computed for different tasks reveals notable performance trends and inconsistencies depending on the specific evaluation task. We believe these insights can aid in developing more robust and reliable audio-language understanding systems.

2. RELATED WORK

LALMs enhance language models with auditory capabilities. Several benchmarking studies on LALMs highlighted their strengths and limitations in audio perception. AIR-Bench [7] is the first hierarchical benchmark for evaluating tasks across all audio types (speech, music, sound). It includes a foundation benchmark with 19 audio tasks and over 19k single-choice questions, and a chat benchmark with over 2k curated open-ended audio questions. The CompA [1] benchmarks

test the compositional reasoning of LALMs. CompA-order assesses comprehension of event sequences and CompA-attribute evaluates attribute-binding of acoustic events.

Although supervised audio classification with pre-defined labels is well-studied, using audio language models for tasks like counting audio events with structured reasoning remains underexplored. Recent benchmarks like MMAU [2] have introduced structured question-answering tasks that require LALM models to reason with audio beyond just classification. These tasks are pivotal for enhancing machine listening algorithms to interpret sounds in context rather than as isolated events.

Audio captioning generates natural language descriptions of acoustic scenes [8]. It is considered a subtask in Audio Question Answering within LALMs [9]. Recent methods use encoder-decoder models trained on datasets like AudioCaps [10] and Clotho [11] for rich annotations of diverse soundscapes. Similarly, weak label generation [12] [13] transforms metadata or sound class labels into pseudo-captions, aiding multi-modal pretraining and task transfer.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Dataset

Throughout this paper, we use the Urban Sound Monitoring (USM) dataset [14], which includes 24,000 five-second-long two-channel soundscape recordings. The audio clips have been synthesized by mixing isolated sound samples from the FSD50k dataset [6]. Although the dataset does not provide strong labels, i. e., precise time stamps of sound events, it includes weak labels for sound event tagging, focusing on 26 sound classes relevant for urban soundscapes. These sound classes come from six categories of sound: miscellaneous sounds, climate sounds, animal sounds, human-made sounds, construction site sounds, and vehicle sounds. The mixing process of the USM dataset involves defining a random sound polyphony between two and six sound sources, assigning each source a foreground or background role, and assigning it a random sound level between -20 dB and -8 dB for the background sounds and -6 dB to 0 dB for the foreground sounds. The USM dataset’s synthetic nature provides precise loudness information for audio events, useful for evaluation. However, it lacks temporal grounding due to missing start and end timestamps, preventing event ordering, which is a limitation. In this work, we use the USM validation subset, which includes 2,000 audio clips.

3.2. Automatic Caption Generation

As a ground-truth for audio caption evaluation, we generate pseudo-natural language captions for the USM dataset following the method described in [13]. As a large language model (LLM), we use the Qwen2.5:7B model [15] motivated by its strong instruction-following and structured output capabilities. We access the model using the open source local LLM serving and research platform Ollama [16]. The model processes the existing metadata of the USM dataset, including the list of foreground and background events and their dynamic level and stereo positioning in the audio clip, provided as a JSON-like input. We found that generated captions such as “The sharp sound of sawing cuts through the air, while in the distance, the rhythmic hum of a train adds a subtle background noise to the scene.” well reflect the complex acoustic composition of the generated soundscapes. We will publish the captions generated for the USM data set as a free resource for future audio captioning research.¹

¹<https://github.com/diliprobhi/lalm-acoustic-scene-understanding>

3.3. Evaluation Protocol Task Design

As the first task, *sound event tagging* (SET) extracts a low-level semantic description of an acoustic scene by identifying all audible sound sources. The USM dataset consists of polyphony levels between two and six sources and therefore allows to evaluate how well LALMs can disentangle and correctly identify multiple concurrent sound sources. A closely related task to SET is sound event detection (SED), where the time stamps and durations of individual sound events, emitted by different sound sources must be identified [17]. In addition to a number of existing classical and deep learning-based SED algorithms, methods involving language models have been proposed in [18] [19], enabling more flexible handling of audio classes, including open-vocabulary that predict temporal locations of each class.

For a mid-level semantic description, we incorporate the two tasks *sound polyphony estimation* (SPE) and *ranking-by-loudness* (RBL) to test the fundamental understanding of LALMs’ ability to deduce relationships between different sound sources in a soundscape recording. We adopt the SPE task from [20], where it is defined as estimating the number of audible sound sources in a short five-second long acoustic scene recording. The RBL task is used to measure the ability of LALMs to differentiate between loudness levels of sound events in complex soundscapes and thus to distinguish between salient foreground sound events and quieter background noise. This aspect of scene understanding is currently underexplored in LALM research. We consider RBL to be a reasoning task, as it involves detecting, comparing and ordering sound events based on perceptual attributes, demonstrating higher cognitive and inferential abilities beyond basic classification or detection.

Finally, the *audio captioning* (AP) task offers a high-level perspective, as it involves creating a textual description of soundscapes, summarizing all sound sources, events, and their complex tonal and dynamic relationships.

3.4. Evaluated Large Audio Language Models (LALMs)

We select two state-of-the-art LALMs from the MMAU benchmark leaderboard to evaluate their acoustic scene understanding capabilities based on the proposed evaluation protocol.

Qwen2.5-Omni-7B [21] is an instruction-tuned multi-modal model capable of processing text, vision, and audio inputs. It is trained with an architecture optimized for general-purpose multi-modal reasoning tasks. The model incorporates a novel position embedding method entitled Time-aligned multi-modal RoPE (TMRoPE) to synchronize the timestamps of video and audio inputs. We just use the model for audio input.

Audio Flamingo 2 [22] is a cross-modal architecture that uses audio as a primary modality. The model combines a pre-trained audio encoder with a frozen large language model via cross-attention to enable high-quality audio captioning and multi-turn dialogue grounded in sound. Audio Flamingo 2 achieved strong performance on audio-language tasks including AudioCaps and Clotho and is capable of processing audio clips from 30 seconds up to 5 minutes duration. Audio Flamingo 2 was trained on the AudioSkills dataset [22], which is a high-quality skill-specific synthetic dataset with approximately 4.2 million question-answer pairs, designed to enhance expert-level reasoning in LALMs. The targeted skills include temporal reasoning, attribute identification, counting the occurrences of specific sounds, contextual sound event reasoning, contextual speech event reasoning, information extraction, and general reasoning.

Both models prioritize complex, reasoning-intensive questions and achieved top-tier performance on the MMAU benchmark, making

Task	Example Prompt
Sound Event Tagging (T ₁)	“Analyze the audio and identify all the audio events by class. Provide just the class names corresponding to each event. Choose from the following options: {string of all classes}. Just give the class names as comma separated values string, e.g., ‘class1’, ‘class2’. Do not include any other text or explanations.”
Sound Polyphony Estimation (T ₂)	“Analyze how many unique sound events are present in the audio? Just give the number of events in number format. eg. 1, 2, 3”
Sorting-by-loudness (T ₃)	“Analyze the audio and return the classes in the order of loudest to softest sounds: {classes}. Just give the class names from loudest to softest. Do not include any other text.”
Audio Captioning (T ₄)	“Describe the audio as a caption in English in detail, including all the sound events present.”

Table 2: Example prompts used for the four tasks towards acoustic scene understanding.

them suitable for the scenario of complex polyphonic soundscapes targeted in our work.

4. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

4.1. Metrics

In the four evaluation tasks T₁ to T₄, we use mainly well-established evaluation metrics. Table 2 lists example prompts we used for each task.

For the SET task (T₁), we compute precision, recall and F1 score as they are standard metrics in multi-label tagging tasks. More specifically, we compute the sample-based F1 score for different subsets of the test set files, for instance, grouped by polyphony level. Therefore, we do not use micro-level or macro-level averaging. After analyzing an audio clip for SET, a LALM outputs a comma-separated list of predicted sound classes, we map these to the 26 sound classes of the USM dataset to create a multi-hot vector. We prompt the model with the entire set of 26 sound class labels of the USM dataset and evaluate its instruction-following ability for the SET task. This approach stands in contrast to other evaluation studies such as [23], where sound classification was devised as multiple binary classification tasks to evaluate the presence or absence of specific sounds.

In the SPE task (T₂), we compute the mean absolute error (MAE) between the true and estimated number of sound sources.

In the RBL task (T₃), we apply the Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (nDCG) metric [24] with linear gain, which is a widely used metric for evaluating the quality of ranking systems. Due to the positional sensitivity of this metric, systems that accurately rank the most relevant item in the list are rewarded more. In our case, relevance refers to the loudness of sound sources. We sort the sound sources in the descending order from the loudest to the softest sounds in an audio clip. The highest relevance score rel_i is assigned to the loudest sound event and the lowest relevance is given to the softest sound event. During the evaluation in task T₃, we first prompt the model with the list of ground truth sound sources in a given clip and query the LALM to rank them from loudest to softest. We compute the nDCG metric using the following steps:

Given an audio clip with 4 sound sources, the relevance scores are set to $rel := \{4, 3, 2, 1\}$ to emphasize the importance of louder sounds at the first rank positions. Then, we compute the DCG (Discounted Cumulative Gain), IDCG (Ideal Discount Cumulative Gain) for perfect

Model	P_G	Sound Event Tagging			Sound Polyphony Estimation	Ranking By Loudness	Audio Captioning
		Precision ↑	Recall ↑	F1 ↑	MAE ↓	nDCG ↑	FENSE ↑
Audio Flamingo 2	2	0.114	0.440	0.140	1.748	0.510	0.372
	3	0.180	0.452	0.190	1.577	0.508	0.379
	4	0.189	0.418	0.197	2.032	0.457	0.384
	5	0.220	0.424	0.220	2.503	0.439	0.389
	6	0.242	0.448	0.247	3.125	0.428	0.391
	Mean	0.191	0.433	0.200	2.131	0.467	0.384
Qwen2.5 Omni	2	0.446	0.298	0.346	0.431	0.551	0.504
	3	0.506	0.239	0.314	0.660	0.550	0.470
	4	0.507	0.196	0.274	1.335	0.498	0.458
	5	0.536	0.162	0.239	2.260	0.486	0.464
	6	0.525	0.148	0.225	3.142	0.449	0.445
	Mean	0.509	0.204	0.278	1.500	0.507	0.466

Table 3: Performance metrics of Audio Flamingo 2 and Qwen 2.5 Omni across Polyphony Level (P_G).

ranking order of events and WDCG (Worst Discount Cumulative Gain) for reversed ranking order of events as:

$$DCG@k = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{rel_i}{\log_2(i+1)}, \quad IDCG@k = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{rel_{\sigma(i)}}{\log_2(i+1)},$$

$$WDCG@k = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{rel_{\tau(i)}}{\log_2(i+1)}$$

where rel_i , $rel_{\sigma(i)}$, and $rel_{\tau(i)}$ are relevance scores at position i in the actual, ideal (descending), and worst-case (ascending) rankings, respectively. Finally, we apply min-max normalization while calculating nDCG to ensure that worst ranking scores are scaled down to zero across different lengths of polyphony levels as:

$$nDCG@k_j = \frac{DCG@k - WDCG@k}{IDCG@k - WDCG@k}$$

where k is the predicted ranked list length for the j -th audio sample ($j = 1, \dots, 2000$). This approach scales the nDCG metric to a range between 0 and 1, similar to the approach in [25].

Finally, we use the FENSE (Fluency ENhanced Sentence-bert Evaluation) metric [26] for the AC task (T₄). This metric is commonly used in audio captioning as it assesses the faithfulness of a generated caption to the audio content and its linguistic quality by leveraging pretrained audio-text and language models.

4.2. Results

Table 3 shows the different evaluation metrics computed across test files of different polyphony levels for the two LALMs under comparison. The results show contrasting performance in polyphonic SET, with Qwen2.5 Omni’s F1 Score declining as polyphonic complexity increases. Audio Flamingo 2 (AF2) shows higher recall at each polyphony level but at a lower overall precision (0.191) compared to Qwen2.5 Omni (0.509), indicating AF2 recognizes more audio events but is more prone to false positives, potentially hallucinating audio events not present.

In the SPE task, Qwen2.5 Omni shows superior performance with a mean MAE of 1.500, compared to Audio Flamingo 2’s 2.131, suggesting that it more accurately estimates audio sources across all P_G levels. Qwen2.5 Omni consistently achieves lower errors, especially at lower levels of P_G (e.g. 0.431 at $P_G = 2$ compared to 1.748 for Audio Flamingo 2), highlighting its effectiveness in simpler cases. As the number of simultaneous sound sources increases in an audio scene, LALMs show higher MAE, indicating the challenge of counting sources in complex, overlapping soundscapes.

Fig. 1: Pairwise scatter plots for Qwen 2.5 Omni, illustrating the Pearson correlation between the computed metrics (F_1 , Absolute Error) and Polyphony level (P_G) both with p-value < 0.001.

A correlation analysis between P_G and F_1 in Figures 1 and 2 shows a positive correlation for Absolute Error, as observed its value increases with higher polyphony levels. This underscores the difficulty in source estimation task. The F_1 score in Fig. 1 exhibits a negative correlation as polyphony increases, while Table 3 show improving precision indicate lower number of hallucinations with increasing polyphony. Audio Flamingo 2 as in Fig. 2 shows a slightly positive correlation in F_1 score for audio class predictions with lower values of precision that indicate greater hallucinations.

The nDCG correlation scatter plots show very weak negative correlation values $r = -0.09$ (AF2) and $r = -0.08$ (Qwen 2.5 Omni). While FENSE score correlation values are $r = 0.03$ (AF2) and $r = -0.09$ (Qwen 2.5 Omni). The plots are omitted here, and further investigation is needed to ascertain if these metrics are statistically independent of increasing polyphony. Table 3 indicates no clear relationship in loudness ranking in complex polyphonic scenes, with nDCG values not effectively distinguishing event loudness between audio events. FENSE scores weakly correlate with polyphony, suggesting FENSE may emphasize sentence coherence and semantic similarity than on audio event accuracy in captions.

5. CONCLUSION

This study evaluates LALM for understanding the acoustic scene based on the USM dataset, which focuses on urban soundscapes with overlapping sound sources. We proposed a novel three-stage evaluation protocol which includes four machine listening tasks selected to measure scene understanding on different semantic levels. Despite achieving high scores on the MMAU benchmark, the two LALMs evaluated need further improvements in training procedures to understand complex acoustic scenes. Future direction aims to enhance

Fig. 2: Pairwise scatter plots for Audio Flamingo 2, illustrating the Pearson correlation between the computed metrics (F_1 , Absolute Error) and Polyphony Level (P_G) both with p-value < 0.001.

evaluation procedures through metrics that account for hallucinations and omissions.

6. LIMITATIONS

Synthetic datasets like USM replicate natural environmental soundscapes and alleviate the laborious task of labeling datasets with loudness values for various sound events, even if such datasets were available. Moreover, they offer precise manipulation of the number, timing and loudness of overlapping events. However, the dataset employs random mixing and stereo placement, which do not adequately represent the spatial and temporal dynamics of real-world environments, such as moving sources or gradual loudness changes. Additionally, USM’s definition of polyphony is more lenient, as it counts the number of active sounds within a short segment instead of the exact count of simultaneous overlapping events, which may not faithfully depict the intricacies of natural polyphonic soundscapes. Models struggle to caption or classify audio classes with very similar acoustic characteristics like car, bus, motorcycle accurately, generalizing them at times to a common sound class as “engine”.

The technique of generating captions for weakly labeled soundscapes, with tags and metadata like the loudness of each audio event and their spatial positioning (foreground versus background), does not ensure that the resulting captions will accurately reflect the soundscape. There are still cases of misinterpreted audio event attributes in the reference captions.

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EXPLOITING STEREO SPATIAL PROPERTIES WITH RECOOP FRAMEWORK FOR JOINT SOUND EVENT DETECTION AND LOCALIZATION

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Abstract—The integration of intelligent systems into daily environments increases the need for a robust understanding of the acoustic scene. Applications such as assistive technologies, audio navigation, and public safety rely on accurate localization and detection of sound events (SELD). Commercially, embedding spatial audio intelligence into smart devices, vehicles, healthcare tools, and surveillance systems, particularly where visual input is limited, has generated significant interest. Traditional signal processing methods struggle to meet the localization and classification demands of compact, microphone-limited devices. As stereo and multichannel audio become prevalent, developing SELD systems capable of joint direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation and real-world event detection is essential. In response, we propose ReCoOP (ResNet-Conformer with ONE-PEACE), a deep learning framework that combines a ResNet-Conformer backbone with stereo spatial features and contextual embeddings. The system incorporates Interaural Level and Phase Differences, Generalized Cross-Correlation, alongside Mel spectrograms, to model spatial cues, while global semantics are captured through pre-trained ONE-PEACE embeddings. ReCoOP features specialized modules for direction and distance estimation, with outputs fused via a joint head. Evaluated on the DCASE2025 Task 3 dataset, our approach improves performance by approximately 17.8% over the baseline, securing 3rd place in the DCASE 2025 Task 3 challenge.

Index Terms—Acoustic scene understanding, Sound event localization, Stereo audio, Spatial audio features, ONE-PEACE embeddings

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound Event Localization and Detection (SELD) is a fundamental task in Computational Auditory Scene Analysis (CASA), aimed at interpreting acoustic scenes by jointly identifying what sound events occur, when they occur, and where they originate. It comprises three interrelated components: Sound Event Detection (SED) for temporal classification, Direction-of-Arrival (DoA) estimation for spatial localization, and Sound Distance Estimation (SDE) for inferring source proximity. These capabilities enable structured scene understanding across applications such as augmented reality, autonomous navigation, surveillance, and assistive hearing.

The IEEE AASP Challenge on Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) [1] has significantly advanced SELD research by unifying sub-tasks and standardizing evaluation protocols. Earlier editions focused on First-Order Ambisonics (FOA), a 360° spatial audio format, which supported the development of models such as SELDnet [2] (Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network (CRNN)-based joint SED and Cartesian DoA), ACCDOA [3] (regressing 3D DoA vectors for active events), and Multi-ACCDOA [4] (handling overlapping sources from the same class). Event-Independent Network [5], [6] further improved robustness via permutation-invariant training. However, dependence on FOA - requiring specialized microphone arrays - limits practicality for widespread deployment.

In contrast, stereo audio is pervasive in consumer devices such as smartphones, laptops, and webcams, offering a practical alternative for

SELD. However, it lacks elevation cues, exhibits front-back ambiguity, and provides limited spatial resolution - particularly for overlapping sources - making localization and distance estimation more challenging. Despite these constraints, the accessibility of stereo microphones renders them well-suited for real-world SELD applications beyond controlled environments.

In response to the growing demand for practical SELD systems, DCASE 2025 Task 3 [7] centers on stereo recordings, emphasizing azimuth-only DoA and SDE. This shift introduces challenges in modeling with limited spatial cues and adapting to two-channel real-world audio. While FOA-based systems like the DCASE 2024 Task 3 Rank 1 system [8] - built on a ResNet-Conformer with multi-branch outputs - achieved strong performance, they were not tailored for stereo input and failed to leverage stereo-specific cues and semantic priors. To address these limitations, we propose ReCoOP, a compact and modular framework purpose-built for stereo SELD.

ReCoOP (ResNet-Conformer-OnePeace) integrates low-level interaural cues - Interaural Level Differences (ILD), Interaural Phase Differences (IPD), and Generalized Cross-Correlation with Phase Transform (GCC-PHAT) - with high-level contextual embeddings from ONE-PEACE [9], a 4-billion-parameter multimodal transformer pretrained on large-scale audio-text and vision-text datasets. It adopts a task-decoupled ResNet-Conformer backbone with separate heads for SED, DoA, and SDE, and employs a lightweight joint ensembling strategy to enhance spatial robustness without additional computational overhead. Evaluated on DCASE 2025 Task 3 [7], ReCoOP outperforms the official baseline across all metrics. Ablation studies confirm the complementary value of interaural spatial cues and pretrained semantic context, highlighting their synergy in advancing stereo SELD.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the dataset and its characteristics, Section 3 outlines the acoustic and semantic feature extraction strategies, Section 4 describes the data augmentation techniques, Section 5 details the ReCoOP architecture, Section 6 explains the experimental setup including evaluation metrics, Section 7 presents the results of the ablation studies, Section 8 reports the final system performance, and Section 9 concludes the paper with future directions.

2. DATASET

We use the DCASE 2025 Task 3 Stereo SELD Dataset [7], derived from the STARSS23 dataset [10], consisting of 5-second stereo clips simulating realistic indoor acoustic scenes. STARSS23 provides First-Order Ambisonics (FOA) recordings from 16 rooms with varied layouts, participants, acoustic conditions, and spontaneous background noise. For this task, FOA was converted to stereo via mid-side emulation [11], combining the omnidirectional ($W(n)$) and left-right dipole ($Y(n)$) FOA components at time index n to generate left and

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Fig. 1: Per-class frame coverage (%) in the STARSS23 development training set, showing a highly skewed distribution dominated by speech and music classes.

right cardioid microphone signals. The resulting stereo channels $L(n)$ and $R(n)$ are computed as shown in (1):

$$\begin{aligned} L(n) &= W(n) + Y(n) \\ R(n) &= W(n) - Y(n) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Each audio clip is fixed at 5 seconds long and annotated at 100-ms resolution (50 frames) with sound event class, azimuth angle (in degrees), and source-to-microphone distance (in cm). The dataset is challenging, with frequent overlapping events, up to three per frame typically, and occasionally as many as six. To resolve front-back ambiguity, azimuths are folded into the range $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$, while elevation is omitted due to top-bottom ambiguity in the stereo setup.

The dataset comprises 30,000 development clips (41.7 hrs) and 10,000 evaluation clips (13.9 hrs), with development audio recorded in Tokyo (24%) and Tampere (76%) and split into training and testing subsets to support generalization. All audio is recorded at 24 kHz, 16-bit resolution. The 13 annotated target classes include speech (female, male), clapping, telephone ringing, laughter, domestic appliances (e.g., vacuum cleaner, boiling water), footsteps, door open/close, music, instruments (e.g., guitar, piano, xylophone), water tap, bell, and knocking. Classes often exhibit high intra-class variability, and speech appears in multiple languages. Sound scenes exhibit significant real-world variability, including non-target interferers such as keyboard typing or clattering dishes, as well as fluctuating background noise levels. Some clips do not contain target events, reflecting the natural sparsity of real-world soundscapes. Stereo recordings are derived from FOA using a length-weighted sampling strategy, producing a frame-level class distribution closely aligned with STARSS23.

However, the distribution is highly skewed, as shown in Fig. 1: male and female speech together comprise around 60% of labeled frames, followed by music and domestic sounds. In contrast, classes like clap, phone, door, faucet, bell, and knock each appear in under 2% of frames. This long-tailed distribution poses challenges for both detection and localization, particularly for rare events with limited temporal coverage and fewer overlapping contexts. Overlapping events - including multiple instances of the same or different classes - are represented by repeated frame entries, with each sound source assigned a consistent identifier. Overall, the dataset offers a comprehensive and realistic benchmark for joint SED and localization under acoustically challenging and imbalanced conditions.

3. FEATURE EXTRACTION

This section outlines the acoustic feature extraction strategies used for input representation. We adopt a dual-pronged approach: a physics-inspired extractor for log-mel spectrograms and inter-channel

directional cues, and a transformer-based semantic encoder using ONE-PEACE for global contextual representation.

3.1. Acoustic Features Extraction

We extract a compact and spatially-informative set of acoustic features from each stereo waveform. A Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) is applied using a Hann window of length 960 samples and hop size of 480, followed by a non-trainable mel-filterbank projection with 64 mel bins. The log-mel spectrograms of the left and right channels, computed by applying a logarithmic scale to the mel-spectrograms, are retained as the first two channels in the feature tensor.

To model spatial cues, we compute three inter-channel directional features [12]. The Interaural Level Difference (ILD) is defined as

$$\text{ILD}[n, m] = \left| \frac{X_{\text{mel},l}[n, m]}{X_{\text{mel},r}[n, m]} \right|, \quad (2)$$

where $X_{\text{mel},l}[n, m]$ and $X_{\text{mel},r}[n, m]$ denote the complex mel spectrogram coefficients at time frame n and mel bin m for the left and right channels, respectively. This ratio captures the difference in magnitude between channels, which is a key spatial cue above 1.5 kHz [12].

Next, we compute the Interaural Phase Difference (IPD) using

$$\text{IPD}[n, m] = \arg(X_{\text{mel},l}[n, m]) - \arg(X_{\text{mel},r}[n, m]), \quad (3)$$

where $\arg(\cdot)$ denotes the phase angle of the complex mel spectrogram at time frame n and mel bin m . This difference expresses the relative phase delay between the two channels. To obtain a more robust representation that avoids discontinuities due to phase wrapping [12], we additionally compute the sine and cosine of the IPD:

$$\text{SI}[n, m] = \sin(\text{IPD}[n, m]), \quad (4)$$

$$\text{CI}[n, m] = \cos(\text{IPD}[n, m]), \quad (5)$$

where $\text{SI}[n, m]$ and $\text{CI}[n, m]$ are the sine and cosine of the interaural phase difference at each time-frequency point, enabling continuous encoding of phase.

Finally, we include the Generalized Cross-Correlation with Phase Transform (GCC-PHAT), defined as

$$\text{GCC}[n, d] = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left(\frac{X_l[n, k] \cdot X_r^*[n, k]}{|X_l[n, k]| |X_r[n, k]|} \right), \quad (6)$$

where $X_l[n, k]$ and $X_r[n, k]$ are the complex STFT coefficients for the left and right channels at time frame n and frequency bin k , $X_r^*[n, k]$ is the complex conjugate of the right-channel STFT, $|\cdot|$ indicates complex magnitude, \mathcal{F}^{-1} is the inverse Fourier Transform, and d denotes the discrete time lag. This feature captures inter-channel time-delay cues critical for direction-of-arrival estimation.

The final feature tensor is constructed by concatenating the log-mel spectrograms with ILD, IPD (both sine and cosine components), and GCC-PHAT features, resulting in a multi-channel representation of shape (6, 251, 64) for each audio clip, where 6 is the number of feature channels, 251 is the number of time bins and 64 is the number of mel bins.

3.2. ONE-PEACE Feature Extraction

To supplement the local spectral features with global semantic cues, we extract contextual embeddings from the ONE-PEACE multimodal transformer model [9]. Specifically, we use a 4B vision-audio-language pretrained checkpoint, trained from scratch on LAION-2B [13] (image-text dataset) and open-source environmental audio-text datasets including AudioCaps [14], Clotho [15], AudioSet [16], FreeSound [17], etc using cross-modal and intra-modal contrastive learning.

The raw stereo waveform is segmented into 100 ms chunks with a hop size equal to the segment length. Each segment is passed

through the ONE-PEACE model, which applies tokenization, attention-based encoding, and feature projection to yield a fixed-length vector embedding. These embeddings are then stacked temporally to form a dense contextual representation of the entire audio file, resulting in a tensor of shape (1, 50, 1536), where 1 denotes the batch size, 50 the number of segments, and 1536 the embedding dimension.

These embeddings are designed to capture long-range dependencies and event semantics, making them suitable for hybrid architectures where local spectral features are fused with global context for downstream tasks such as sound event detection or localization.

4. DATA AUGMENTATION

To enhance model robustness and generalization, we incorporated the publicly released synthetic SELD mixtures from DCASE 2024 [18], generated by convolving isolated events with real room impulse responses recorded at Tampere University. We downmixed this dataset using the mid-side stereo procedure described in Section 2 to produce 30,000 stereo clips aligned with the DCASE2025 Task 3 format, effectively doubling the development set duration to 83.4 hours. To further introduce spatial diversity, we applied Audio Channel Swapping (ACS) [19] - a lightweight augmentation that permutes FOA channels to simulate directional variation [20] - on the original FOA-format STARSS23 dataset, increasing its size sevenfold. This ACS-augmented data was then similarly downmixed into 30,000 stereo clips, bringing the development set duration to 125.1 hours in total - tripling its original size.

5. RESNET-CONFORMER-ONEPEACE (RECOOP) DEEP LEARNING FRAMEWORK

ReCoOP, a unified framework for joint sound event detection (SED), direction-of-arrival estimation (DOA), and source distance estimation (SDE) was proposed. Inspired by top-performing systems in DCASE 2024 Task 3, ReCoOP is built on a shared architecture comprising a ResNet-18 encoder [21] without final pooling to extract localized spatial features from the input multichannel acoustic feature tensor. These features are then passed through a linear projection layer to map them to a fixed embedding dimension of 256, followed by a stack of eight Conformer blocks [22] that capture long-range temporal dynamics and cross-channel spatial dependencies. A temporal max-pooling layer with kernel size 5 reduces the sequence length by retaining the most salient activations over short temporal windows, facilitating more efficient downstream processing.

From this backbone, ReCoOP instantiates two specialized variants [8]. The first, shown in Fig. 2, is the SED-DOA model, which augments the pooled acoustic representation by concatenating it with contextual embeddings from ONE-PEACE, providing high-level semantic information. The fused features are passed through another projection layer and two additional Conformer blocks with an embedding dimension of 256, which refine the fused representation by aligning semantic and acoustic contexts. The output is then fed into two parallel heads. The SED prediction head comprises two fully connected (FC) layers with a LeakyReLU nonlinearity, followed by a final FC layer with sigmoid activation to predict the probabilities of each of the 13 sound event classes being active. The DOA prediction head follows the same structure but ends with tanh activation to produce azimuthal direction estimates.

The second variant, the SED-SDE model (Fig. 3), shares the same ResNet-Conformer backbone but omits the ONE-PEACE integration. This variant excludes external semantic embeddings and instead focuses entirely on exploiting the full set of spatial and spectral cues present in the audio input. This design ensures that both detection and

Fig. 2: Architecture for SED-DOA prediction

Fig. 3: Architecture for SED-SDE prediction

distance estimation are guided directly by physically grounded acoustic features. It uses two output heads: a SED prediction head, identical in structure to that in the SED-DOA model, and an SDE prediction head, consisting of two FC layers with LeakyReLU, followed by a final FC layer with ReLU activation to estimate class-wise source distances.

Final predictions are obtained through task-specific ensembling: SED outputs are averaged across both models to leverage complementary strengths; DOA predictions are taken from the semantically enriched SED-DOA model; and SDE values are obtained exclusively from the physically grounded SED-SDE model. This hybrid design allows ReCoOP to combine semantic context with spatial fidelity, yielding strong performance across all subtasks.

6. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The ReCoOP framework was trained using task-specific composite loss functions. For the SED-DOA-OnePeace model, binary cross-entropy loss was used for sound event detection, and mean squared error loss was applied to DOA estimation, gated by SED predictions to focus localization only on active events. For the SED-SDE model,

binary cross-entropy loss was similarly used for detection, while the distance regression loss was computed using mean squared percentage error (MSPE) and masked by active event labels to ensure stability. In both cases, the SED and localization losses were weighted with a ratio of 0.1 to 1.

Training was conducted for 300 epochs with a batch size of 32, using the Tri-Stage Learning Rate Scheduler to ensure stable convergence. Final evaluation was based on the macro-averaged location-dependent F1-score (F@20), which captures joint detection and localization performance under thresholds of 20 degrees for azimuth and 1 for relative distance error. In addition, we report DOA error (DOAE) and relative distance error (RDE), both class-dependent metrics that measure unthresholded localization accuracy in azimuth and distance, respectively. Higher F@20 and lower DOAE and RDE values indicate better performance.

During training, the best model checkpoints were selected based on their F@20 performance on the dev-test split, which was used as the validation set throughout the training process.

7. ABLATION STUDY

To assess the individual contributions of each architectural component and training strategy, we conducted an ablation study on the stereo SELD task using the dev-test split of the DCASE2025 Task 3 Stereo SELD dataset. Results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of SELD performance across different experimental configurations

Experiment	F@20 (%)	DOAE (deg)	RDE
Baseline	22.78	24.5	0.41
Baseline + Directional Features	24.70	19.5	0.32
ResNet-Conformer	46.30	13.0	0.37
ReCoOP [submitted system]	48.20	13.3	0.36
ReCoOP + ACS	47.50	13.7	0.36

The baseline system employed a lightweight convolutional-recurrent-attention architecture using only log-Mel spectrograms, achieving an F@20 of 22.78%, though with high localization and relative distance errors. Incorporating spatial acoustic features - specifically interaural level and phase differences (ILD, IPD) and GCC-PHAT - led to measurable improvements: the F@20 increased to 24.70%, and localization performance improved, highlighting the importance of spatial cues.

A substantial performance gain was observed upon adopting the ResNet-Conformer framework, which had shown strong results in previous DCASE challenges. This configuration reached an F@20 of 46.30%, with further reduction in localization error.

Building on this, we integrated pretrained ONE-PEACE embeddings into the ResNet-Conformer setup to form the proposed ReCoOP system. This resulted in the highest detection accuracy, with an F@20 of 48.20% and improved distance estimation - a strong result given its modest 26M parameter size.

Finally, we applied Audio Channel Swapping (ACS) augmentation to ReCoOP, achieving a comparable F@20 of 47.50%. This demonstrated that ACS acts as an effective regularizer, preserving both detection and localization performance.

All experiments included synthetic audio data augmentation, with ACS uniquely applied in the final configuration.

8. RESULTS

This section presents the official evaluation results of our proposed ReCoOP framework on the hidden test set of DCASE 2025 Task 3A, with comparisons to other top-performing submissions. System rankings were based on F@20, and a summary of key metrics is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Official DCASE2025 Task 3a challenge results. The submitted system Banerjee_NTU_task3a_1 corresponds to the ReCoOP system in Table 1.

System	System Info		Evaluation Metrics		
	Rank	Size	F@20↑	DOAE↓	RDE↓
Du_NERCSLIP_task3a_4	1	58M	50.4	12.2	26.9
He_HIT_task3a_1	2	104M	47.0	13.3	38.6
Banerjee_NTU_task3a_1	3	26M	43.9	14.0	35.2
AO_Baseline	13	734k	26.1	23.0	33.2

Our submission, Banerjee_NTU_task3a_1, ranked third overall, achieving an F@20 of 43.9%, a DOAE of 14.0°, and an RDE of 35.2%. Importantly, ReCoOP accomplished this using only 26 million parameters - less than half the size of the top-ranked system and just one-quarter of the second-ranked - demonstrating a highly favorable F@20-to-model-size trade-off.

The top-ranked Du_NERCSLIP_task3a_4 [23] attained an F@20 of 50.4% using a 58M-parameter ResNet-Conformer ensemble trained on log-mel spectrograms with extensive augmentation. The second-ranked He_HIT_task3a_1 [24] reached 47.0% with a much larger 104M-parameter ensemble and synthetic audio strategies. While both systems demonstrated higher detection accuracy, their substantially larger footprints highlight the efficiency advantage of ReCoOP.

Relative to the official AO Baseline system, which reported an F@20 of 26.1%, ReCoOP achieved a substantial 17.8-point improvement in detection accuracy. This highlights the strength of our approach in bridging the performance gap through architectural and feature-level innovations.

Thus, by integrating directional acoustic cues with contextual ONE-PEACE embeddings, ReCoOP demonstrates that high SELD performance can be achieved within a compact and efficient architecture. This underscores its potential for real-world deployment where computational efficiency is paramount.

9. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed ReCoOP, a compact two-model SELD ensemble that combines a rich acoustic feature set - including log-mel spectrograms and interaural directional cues (ILD, IPD, GCC-PHAT) - with contextual embeddings from ONE-PEACE, using a lightweight ResNet-Conformer backbone.

ReCoOP achieved a 25.42% F@20 improvement over the baseline on the validation set and ranked third overall on the official test set, with a 17.8-point F@20 gain. With just 26 million parameters, it achieves competitive performance, demonstrating an efficient F@20-to-model-size trade-off. Future work includes better temporal integration of semantic features, cross-dataset generalization, and self-supervised spatial learning.

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Cross-Attention with Confidence Weighting for Multi-Channel Audio Alignment

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Abstract—Multi-channel audio alignment is a key requirement in bioacoustic monitoring, spatial audio systems, and acoustic localization. However, existing methods often struggle to address nonlinear clock drift and lack mechanisms for quantifying uncertainty. Traditional methods like Cross-correlation and Dynamic Time Warping assume simple drift patterns and provide no reliability measures. Meanwhile, recent deep learning models typically treat alignment as a binary classification task, overlooking inter-channel dependencies and uncertainty estimation. We introduce a method that combines cross-attention mechanisms with confidence-weighted scoring to improve multi-channel audio synchronization. We extend BEATs encoders with cross-attention layers to model temporal relationships between channels. We also develop a confidence-weighted scoring function that uses the full prediction distribution instead of binary thresholding. Our method achieved first place in the BioDCASE 2025 Task 1 challenge with 0.30 MSE average across test datasets, compared to 0.58 for the deep learning baseline. On individual datasets, we achieved 0.14 MSE on ARU data (77% reduction) and 0.45 MSE on zebra finch data (18% reduction). The framework supports probabilistic temporal alignment, moving beyond point estimates. While validated in a bioacoustic context, the approach is applicable to a broader range of multi-channel audio tasks where alignment confidence is critical. Code available on: <https://github.com/Ragib-Amin-Nihal/BEATsCA>

Index Terms—Multi-channel audio alignment, cross-attention, confidence weighting, BEATs, bioacoustic monitoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Multi-channel audio recording systems serve applications ranging from professional spatial audio production to scientific bioacoustic monitoring using automated recording units (ARUs) [1]. These systems deploy multiple synchronized devices to capture spatial information, enable source separation, and provide measurement redundancy. Maintaining precise temporal alignment between recording channels presents a significant technical challenge.

The primary obstacle is clock drift between independent recording devices. Oscillator variations due to manufacturing tolerances, temperature changes, and component aging cause temporal desynchronization that accumulates over time [2]. This drift is often nonlinear and unpredictable in field deployments with variable environmental conditions. Applications requiring sub-millisecond accuracy, like bioacoustic localization, need post-processing correction [3].

Figure 1 shows the alignment task. For temporally drifted stereo recordings, the system must predict corresponding timestamps using sparse keypoint annotations. This requires modeling nonlinear drift while providing confidence estimates.

Traditional methods for multi-channel alignment include cross-correlation techniques. Generalized Cross-Correlation with Phase Transform (GCC-PHAT) [4] identifies time delays through correlation peaks between channels. These efficient methods assume constant time shifts but fail with nonlinear drift [5]. Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) handles nonlinear relationships but has $O(N^2)$ complexity and produces unrealistic many-to-one alignments [6]. Modern DTW variants like Memory-Restricted Multiscale DTW reduce computation but lack uncertainty quantification [7]. Speech processing tools such as forced aligners enable automatic phoneme-level segmentation [8]. However, these approaches primarily address single-modality tasks,

Fig. 1: Multi-Channel Audio Alignment Problem. Illustration of temporal desynchronization between two audio channels due to nonlinear clock drift. Channel 0 (top) provides reference timestamps at known 1-second intervals, while Channel 1 (bottom) contains corresponding but unknown timestamps (marked “?”). Arrows indicate temporal correspondences with drift values of +0.2s, +0.3s, and -0.1s, demonstrating the nonlinear nature of clock drift. The challenge is to predict the unknown Channel 1 timestamps given only the Channel 0 reference, with drift constrained to ± 5 seconds.

leaving multi-channel audio alignment underexplored.

Deep learning approaches have emerged as promising alternatives for temporal alignment. The Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST) [9] uses attention for audio classification, while Conformer architectures [10] combine convolution and self-attention for temporal modeling. BEATs [11] employs iterative pre-training for diverse audio tasks. Self-supervised approaches like wav2vec 2.0 [12] advance speech representation learning. However, existing deep learning alignment systems typically formulate the problem as binary classification—predicting whether audio segments are aligned or misaligned.

This binary classification approach has two limitations that our work addresses. First, methods process channels independently, ignoring correlated clock drift patterns between synchronized devices. Second, binary classification omits reliability estimates needed for scientific applications like bioacoustic analysis [13].

Uncertainty quantification has proven valuable in related sequence alignment domains. Methods like GUIDANCE [14] provide confidence scores for alignment regions in bioinformatics applications. Similar probabilistic frameworks are needed for audio alignment, where decisions should be weighted by confidence rather than treated as binary choices.

Current alignment methods cannot model inter-channel dependencies (signal processing) or quantify uncertainty (deep learning). We hypothesize that explicitly modeling inter-channel temporal relationships through cross-attention mechanisms, combined with confidence-weighted scoring that utilizes full prediction distributions, can improve alignment accuracy while providing meaningful uncertainty estimates. Cross-attention learns relationships between temporal patterns across channels, capturing correlated clock drift. Confidence weighting uses

continuous model outputs rather than binary thresholds, enabling certainty-based decisions.

We extend the BEATs encoder [11] with cross-attention layers for inter-channel interaction before alignment prediction. Binary counting metrics are replaced by a confidence-weighted function incorporating prediction confidence, top-quartile averaging, and sigmoid-transformed scores. The approach maintains compatibility with existing candidate generation while processing decisions through learned dependencies and probabilistic confidence.

We evaluate our method on the BioDCASE 2025 Task 1 challenge, which provides stereo audio recordings with temporal keypoints from two distinct acoustic domains: field-deployed automated recording units and controlled laboratory recordings. The challenge constrains drift to ± 5 seconds and uses mean squared error for evaluation.

Our work contributes:

- 1) Cross-attention mechanisms that model inter-channel temporal dependencies for audio alignment
- 2) A confidence-weighted scoring framework using full prediction distributions to quantify alignment uncertainty.

Experimental results show improved performance on the BioDCASE 2025 benchmark.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We define multi-channel audio alignment as predicting temporal correspondences with uncertainty quantification. Given a stereo audio recording $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{A}_1) \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times T}$ that has been affected by nonlinear clock drift. The goal is to predict corresponding timestamps between channels while providing confidence scores.

2.1. Mathematical Setup

Temporal correspondences are established through keypoints $\mathcal{K} = \{k_0, k_1, \dots, k_{N-1}\}$, where each $k_i = (k_{i,0}, k_{i,1})$ consists of timestamps from Channel 0 (reference) and Channel 1 (drifted). Channel 0 timestamps occur at fixed 1-second intervals: $k_{i,0} = i$ for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$.

The clock drift function $\mathcal{D} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ maps Channel 0 to Channel 1 timestamps:

$$k_{i,1} = \mathcal{D}(k_{i,0}) = \mathcal{D}(i),$$

subject to the constraint $|\mathcal{D}(t) - t| \leq 5$ seconds.

2.2. Training and Inference

Training: The system accesses complete annotations $\mathcal{K}_{train} = \{(k_{i,0}, k_{i,1})\}_{i=0}^{N-1}$ and learns alignment decisions from audio segments extracted around keypoints. For each keypoint k_i , we extract audio segments of duration $\tau = 2$ second:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_{i,0} &= \mathcal{A}_0[\lfloor k_{i,0} \cdot f_s \rfloor : \lfloor (k_{i,0} + \tau) \cdot f_s \rfloor], \\ \mathcal{S}_{i,1} &= \mathcal{A}_1[\lfloor k_{i,1} \cdot f_s \rfloor : \lfloor (k_{i,1} + \tau) \cdot f_s \rfloor], \end{aligned}$$

where f_s is the sampling frequency and $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes integer indexing.

Inference: Given only Channel 0 timestamps $\mathcal{K}_{test} = \{k_{i,0}\}_{i=0}^{N-1}$, the system predicts Channel 1 timestamps $\{\hat{k}_{i,1}\}_{i=0}^{N-1}$ by evaluating candidate alignments with learned scoring.

2.3. Candidate Generation Strategy

Following the baseline approach, we model the drift as affine: $\mathcal{D}(t) \approx \alpha t + \beta$ where α represents drift rate and β represents constant offset. The candidate generation creates a discrete set $\mathcal{C} = \{(\alpha_j, \beta_j)\}_{j=1}^M$ by sampling:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_j &\in [1 - \frac{\delta_{max}}{T_{dur}}, 1 + \frac{\delta_{max}}{T_{dur}}] \\ \beta_j &\in [-\delta_{max}, \delta_{max}], \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 2: System architecture with cross-attention enabling inter-channel interaction before alignment prediction.

where $\delta_{max} = 5$ seconds and T_{dur} is audio duration. For each candidate, predicted timestamps are $\hat{k}_{i,1}^{(j)} = \alpha_j \cdot i + \beta_j$, generating candidate sets $\mathcal{K}_j = \{(k_{i,0}, \hat{k}_{i,1}^{(j)})\}_{i=0}^{N-1}$.

2.4. Evaluation

Performance is measured using Mean Squared Error (MSE):

$$\mathcal{L}_{MSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (k_{i,1} - \hat{k}_{i,1}^*)^2. \quad (1)$$

The benchmark combines scores from two datasets: $\mathcal{L}_{final} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{L}_{MSE}(\mathcal{D}_{ARU}) + \mathcal{L}_{MSE}(\mathcal{D}_{zebra}))$.

3. METHODOLOGY

We modify BEATs with: (1) cross-attention for inter-channel dependencies, (2) conservative augmentation during training, and (3) confidence-weighted scoring. Figure 2 shows the architecture.

3.1. Cross-Attention Architecture

Using BEATs [11] with frozen encoders, we combine channel embeddings $\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{768}$ as $\mathbf{E} = [\mathbf{e}_0; \mathbf{e}_1]$. Multi-head attention [15] computes, $\text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)\mathbf{V}$, where $\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{W}_{Q,K,V}$ with learned projections $\mathbf{W}_{Q,K,V} \in \mathbb{R}^{768 \times 768}$.

The enhanced MLP processes attended embeddings $[\mathbf{e}'_0; \mathbf{e}'_1]$ through:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}_1 &= \text{GELU}(\text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{W}_1[\mathbf{e}'_0; \mathbf{e}'_1] + \mathbf{b}_1)), \\ \mathbf{h}_2 &= \text{GELU}(\text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{W}_2\mathbf{h}_1 + \mathbf{b}_2)) + \mathbf{h}_1, \\ y &= \mathbf{W}_4(\text{GELU}(\text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{W}_3\mathbf{h}_2 + \mathbf{b}_3))) + \mathbf{b}_4, \end{aligned}$$

with layer dimensions $256 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 1$ and residual connections.

3.2. Training Procedures

Keypoint Sampling: To avoid temporal clustering in random sampling, we select every 20th keypoint per file. This covers 5% of keypoints uniformly while maintaining efficiency.

Conservative Data Augmentation: Applied to 30% of training samples with channel synchronization:

Table 1: BioDCASE 2025 Challenge Results (Test Set)

Method	ARU	Zebra Finch	Average
Nosync	0.850	1.840	1.350
Crosscorr	1.100	5.550	3.320
DL Baseline	0.620	0.550	0.580
Ours (BEATsCA)	0.14	0.45	0.30
Improvement vs DL	77.4%	18.2%	48.3%

- *Amplitude scaling*: Random factor $\alpha \sim \mathcal{U}(0.9, 1.1)$ applied identically to both channels
- *Gaussian noise*: $\text{SNR} \in [40, 50]$ dB
- *Consistency constraint*: Identical random seed ensures synchronized augmentation across channels

The augmentation preserves temporal alignment by applying identical transformations:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{S}_{i,0} &= \alpha \cdot S_{i,0} + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2), \\ \tilde{S}_{i,1} &= \alpha \cdot S_{i,1} + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2), \end{aligned}$$

where σ^2 depends on target SNR. This preserves temporal alignment while improving robustness.

3.3. Confidence-Weighted Scoring

Traditional methods use binary counting, simply summing the number of aligned predictions ($\sum_i \mathbf{1}[f_\theta(S_{i,0}, S_{i,1}) > 0]$) discarding valuable confidence information. A prediction of 0.01 is treated identically to 0.99, despite vastly different certainty levels. We replace binary counting with a scoring function that incorporates prediction distributions:

$$S_{conf}(\mathcal{K}_j) = 0.4\mu_{pos}r_{pos} + 0.3\mu_{top} + 0.2 \sum_i \sigma(p_i^{(j)}) + 0.1\mathcal{E}_{exp} \quad (2)$$

The weights (0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1) were chosen based on intuitive design principles: highest weight for positive prediction quality ($\mu_{pos} \cdot r_{pos}$) as it directly measures alignment confidence, second-highest for top quartile focus (μ_{top}) to emphasize reliable predictions, and lower weights for the supporting probabilistic and exponential components. The components:

- *Positive Confidence Weighting* ($\mu_{pos} \cdot r_{pos}$): Average confidence of positive predictions weighted by their prevalence
- *Top Quartile Focus* (μ_{top}): Mean confidence of highest-scoring 25% predictions
- *Probabilistic Coverage* ($\sum_i \sigma(p_i^{(j)})$): Sum of sigmoid-transformed probabilities
- *Exponential Amplification* (\mathcal{E}_{exp}): $e^{A(p-0.5)}$ for $p > 0.5$, else 0

Figure 3 illustrates the scoring approach with an example.

3.4. Inference Pipeline

Candidate Generation: Following the baseline, we assume affine drift $\mathcal{D}(t) \approx \alpha t + \beta$ and sample parameters: $\alpha_j \in [1 \pm 5/T_{dur}]$, $\beta_j \in [-5, 5]$, generating candidates $\hat{k}_{i,1}^{(j)} = \alpha_j \cdot i + \beta_j$.

Selection: For each candidate \mathcal{K}_j : (1) extract 2-second segments at predicted locations, (2) compute cross-attention scores, (3) calculate $S_{conf}(\mathcal{K}_j)$, (4) select maximum-scoring candidate.

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

4.1. Datasets and Evaluation Protocol

We use BioDCASE 2025 Task 1 datasets [1] containing stereo audio with temporal keypoints in two domains:

- **ARU dataset:** 36 training files, 12 validation files from field recordings

Table 2: Validation Set Performance Comparison

Method	ARU	Zebra Finch	Average
Nosync	0.976	1.315	1.146
Crosscorr	6.861	10.029	8.445
DL Baseline	0.516	1.262	0.889
Ours	0.099	0.521	0.310
Improvement vs DL	80.8%	58.7%	65.1%

- **Zebra finch dataset:** 108 training files, 16 validation files from laboratory recordings

Both datasets contain keypoints at 1-second intervals with drift constrained to ± 5 seconds. The challenge evaluates using MSE (Equation 1) between predicted and ground-truth Channel 1 timestamps, with final scoring computed as the average MSE across both test datasets. All training uses only the provided data without external resources, ensuring fair comparison with baseline methods.

4.2. Implementation Details

Model Architecture: We use the pre-trained BEATs encoder (BEATs_iter3_plus_AS2M_finetuned_on_AS2M_cpt2.pt) with frozen parameters during training. The cross-attention module employs 8 attention heads with 768-dimensional embeddings. The enhanced MLP processes 1536-dimensional concatenated embeddings through layers of dimensions $256 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 1$ with GELU activations, layer normalization, and residual connections.

Training Configuration: We train for up to 100 epochs with early stopping (patience 25) using AdamW optimizer with learning rate 2×10^{-4} , weight decay 0.01, and ReduceLROnPlateau scheduling (factor 0.7, patience 3). Batch size is set to 32 to prevent $O(B^2)$ memory scaling in the pairwise training loss. Conservative data augmentation is applied to 30% of samples with amplitude scaling ($\pm 10\%$) and additive noise (40-50 dB SNR).

Inference Setup: During inference, we sample 100 candidate drift parameters within constraint bounds. For each candidate, we extract 2-second audio segments, compute cross-attention predictions, and select the candidate with maximum confidence-weighted score.

Hardware and Reproducibility: Training is performed on NVIDIA H100 GPU with CUDA optimization and memory management (cache clearing every 5 batches). All experiments use fixed random seeds for reproducibility.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Competition Performance

Our method achieved 0.30 MSE on BioDCASE 2025 test data (Table 1), improving upon the deep learning baseline by 48.3%.

5.2. Validation Set Analysis

Validation results (Table 2) demonstrate consistent improvements across both datasets, with particularly strong performance on ARU data (0.099 MSE vs. 0.516 baseline).

The validation-to-test performance correlation (validation: 0.310, test: 0.30) indicates robust generalization with minimal overfitting, validating our conservative training approach.

6. ABLATION STUDIES

We conduct comprehensive ablation studies to understand component contributions. Results show that both architectural innovations and confidence-weighted scoring contribute to performance improvements.

Fig. 3: Confidence-weighted scoring methodology for multi-channel audio alignment. **Top row:** Raw model predictions (left) are converted to binary values (0.80 average) in the baseline approach (center), demonstrating information loss where predictions with vastly different confidence levels are treated identically (right). **Middle row:** Our confidence-weighted approach incorporates four complementary components: positive prediction quality ($\mu_{\text{pos}} \times r_{\text{pos}} = 0.434$), top quartile averaging ($\mu_{\text{top}} = 0.885$), normalized sigmoid distribution ($\sum \sigma(p_i) / N = 0.593$), and exponential emphasis of high-confidence predictions ($E_{\text{exp}} = 0.220$). **Bottom:** The weighted combination (0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1 weights respectively) produces a confidence score of 0.580, demonstrating how confidence weighting utilizes the full prediction distribution compared to binary counting for alignment candidate selection.

Table 3: Progressive Component Addition Analysis (Validation MSE)

Configuration	ARU MSE	ZF MSE	ARU Δ from Baseline	ZF Δ from Baseline
Original Baseline	0.516	1.262	–	–
+ Enhanced MLP	0.380	1.050	26%	17%
+ Cross-Attention	0.152	0.680	71%	46%
+ Confidence Scoring	0.099	0.521	81%	59%

Table 4: Confidence Scoring Weight Ablation

Weight Config	μ_{pos}	μ_{top}	$\sum \sigma(p_i)$	e^μ	ARU MSE	ZF MSE
Proposed	0.400	0.300	0.200	0.100	0.099	0.521
Mean+Top	0.500	0.500	0.000	0.000	0.161	0.673
Mean only	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.161	0.673
Equal weights	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.162	0.718
Sigmoid+Exp	0.000	0.000	0.500	0.500	0.162	0.718
Top only	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.224	0.754

6.1. Component Contribution Analysis

Table 3 shows the incremental improvement from baseline to our final method through systematic component addition. Cross-attention provides the largest single improvement, while confidence scoring adds substantial refinement.

6.2. Confidence Scoring Weight Analysis

Table 4 examines different weight configurations for the confidence scoring function (Equation 2). Our weighting (0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1) performs best, with μ_{pos} and μ_{top} providing primary benefits.

7. CONCLUSION

This work demonstrates that cross-attention mechanisms and confidence-weighted scoring can significantly improve multi-channel audio alignment. By modeling inter-channel temporal dependencies and utilizing the full prediction distribution rather than binary thresholding, our approach achieved first place in the BioDCASE 2025 challenge with substantial improvements over existing methods. The key contributions include applying cross-attention to model temporal relationships between channels and developing a principled confidence estimation framework that provides uncertainty quantification for alignment decisions. The experimental validation across ARU and zebra finch datasets confirms the effectiveness of both architectural innovations. While the current approach relies on affine drift approximations for candidate generation, the demonstrated performance gains suggest that probabilistic alignment frameworks represent a promising direction for the field. Future work should investigate principled optimization of confidence scoring weights through techniques such as Bayesian optimization or gradient-based hyperparameter tuning. Additionally, the confidence scoring framework could be extended with learned weighting schemes that adapt to different acoustic domains or recording conditions. The method applies to domains needing precise synchronization, including distributed sensor networks and spatial audio systems.

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Assessing a Domain-Adaptive Deployment Workflow for Selective Audio Recording in Wildlife Acoustic Monitoring

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Abstract—Passive acoustic monitoring is a valuable tool for wildlife research, but scheduled recording often results in large volumes of audio, much of which may not be of interest. Selective audio recording, where audio is only saved when relevant activity is detected, offers an effective alternative. In this work, we leverage a low-cost embedded system that implements selective recording using an on-device classification model and evaluate its deployment for detecting penguin vocalization. To address the domain shift between training and deployment conditions (e.g. environment, recording device), we propose a lightweight domain adaptation strategy based on fine-tuning the model with a small amount of location-specific data. We replicate realistic deployment scenarios using data from two geographically distinct locations, Antarctica and Falkland Islands, and assess the impact of fine-tuning on classification and selective recording performance. Our results show that fine-tuning with location-specific data substantially improves generalization ability and reduces both false positives and false negatives in selective recording. These findings highlight the value of integrating model fine-tuning into field monitoring workflows, in order to improve the reliability of acoustic data collection.

Index Terms—domain shift, bioacoustics, passive acoustic monitoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) has become an essential tool in ecological and environmental research. The deployment of autonomous recording units (ARUs) enables long-term, non-invasive monitoring of wildlife and ecosystems. Technological advances have made remote sensing and monitoring tools increasingly accessible and efficient [1], [2], reducing fieldwork time, minimizing ecosystem disturbance, and significantly lowering operational costs [3]. These tools also allow data collection at broad spatial and temporal scales, facilitating more detailed and extensive studies of ecological change. This is particularly valuable in regions where extreme conditions and remoteness pose challenges for direct observation, as is the case for penguin colonies.

Penguins have been widely recognized as key bioindicators for monitoring the health of marine ecosystems in the Southern Hemisphere [4], [5]. In the Antarctic region, species such as the Adélie and Gentoo penguins play a vital ecological role. These species breed in colonies distributed along the Antarctic Peninsula and nearby islands, such as Ardley Island, an Important Bird Area and a protected site under the Antarctic Treaty System. As mesopredators, penguins reflect changes in prey availability, primarily krill, and allow us to infer alterations in the structure and functioning of the Antarctic marine ecosystem [6], [7]. However, significant knowledge gaps remain regarding the plasticity of their annual cycle. Some phases of the cycle have been poorly documented due to the logistical challenges of monitoring, especially in remote and hard-to-access environments. Since phenology varies considerably between colonies and across years, it's essential to implement systematic long-term monitoring that can accurately capture annual variation in the timing of all reproductive cycle phases.

Traditional PAM systems operate on fixed schedules, recording at regular intervals regardless of acoustic activity [8], [9]. While this approach maximizes data coverage, it often results in large volumes of audio, much of which may be irrelevant or silent. This creates challenges in terms of storage, power consumption, and manual analysis. To address these limitations, we designed a selective

recording scheme using an audio recorder developed by our team, introduced in [10]. This device runs an embedded classification model, based on a convolutional neural network, and records data only when relevant sound is detected.

Recent advances in deep learning have significantly improved the ability to automatically detect and classify bioacoustic signals [11]. In particular, convolutional neural networks trained on spectrogram representations have become a common and effective approach for bird and animal sound classification [11], and can now be deployed on resource-constrained hardware. This enables real-time inference and automatic on-site sound event detection, demonstrated by lightweight implementations such as *TinyChirp* [12]. In turn, this allows for the development of smart audio recording tools. For example, frameworks such as *acoupi* [13] provide open-source infrastructure for deploying bioacoustic-related machine learning models on embedded devices.

However, while selective recording offers substantial advantages, model performance is often limited by domain shift [14], [15]. Differences in background noise, species behavior or recording hardware between training data and the conditions at the deployment site can hinder network performance [16]. Recent work in domain adaptation has explored strategies to mitigate these challenges, including transfer learning [17], adversarial adaptation [18] and self-training methods [19]. We propose addressing domain shift through lightweight domain adaptation, fine-tuning the base model using a small amount of local data. This approach has been shown to improve performance in bird sound classification when compared to models trained solely on non-local data [11], [20]–[22]. By incorporating even a small amount of location-specific audio samples, fine-tuning helps the model adjust better to local acoustic conditions.

This work is motivated by the need for realistic deployment strategies in remote monitoring campaigns, involving ARUs left in the field for extended periods of time. We focus on the scenario where a pre-trained model is deployed to a brand new location and later fine-tuned using a small amount of location-specific data, collected automatically by the same device over a very brief interval. This reflects a practical workflow in which researchers install recorders, retrieve preliminary audio samples, fine-tune the model offline and then re-deploy the updated system for improved selective recording performance during the remainder of the monitoring campaign.

The key contributions of this work are three: (i) we present a low-power selective recording system capable of real-time sound classification tailored for remote acoustic monitoring; (ii) we evaluate a lightweight domain adaptation strategy to improve performance in new deployment conditions using minimal local data; and (iii) we demonstrate a practical workflow for fine-tuning and redeploying the system in the field. To enable reproducibility and further research, the training and fine-tuning pipeline is openly available¹, and all annotated datasets used for training and evaluation are shared via Zenodo².

¹<https://github.com/juliaazziz/aurora-domain-adaptation>

²<https://zenodo.org/records/17121978>

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the context and motivation of the application on which this work is based. Section 3 describes the datasets used for training and evaluation, including both public sources and field recordings. Section 4 outlines the followed methodology, describing the employed model architecture, features and domain adaptation strategy. Section 5 presents experimental results, analyzing the impact of fine-tuning, the effect of varying the number of local samples and the performance of the proposed selective recording system. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and discusses the implications of our main findings.

2. APPLICATION OVERVIEW

2.1. Acoustic monitoring

Environmental monitoring in Antarctica is essential for detecting and managing the impacts of human activity and climate change in one of the world’s last near-pristine ecosystems [23], [24]. Given the continent’s remoteness, logistical challenges and strict environmental protection under the Antarctic Treaty System, remote sensing technologies have become increasingly important [1], [2]. Autonomous systems such as satellite platforms, trap cameras, and acoustic recorders enable long-term, low-impact data collection across vast and inaccessible regions. Acoustic monitoring, in particular, offers powerful and non-invasive tools for tracking biodiversity, human activity, and environmental change [25], [26]. It allows researchers to detect and monitor vocal species, as well as anthropogenic noise, providing insights into ecosystem dynamics and disturbance levels. The Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty (1991) encourages long-term environmental monitoring and the use of innovative, low-impact methods. Recent initiatives aim to harmonize and expand remote monitoring networks, including acoustic systems, to better support continent-wide environmental management [27], [28].

2.2. Selective recording workflow

Acoustic wildlife monitoring in remote areas faces several challenges. When systems are deployed in isolated or protected areas, they must operate autonomously for extended periods of time with limited access for maintenance. This places strict constraints on energy consumption and data storage. Traditional approaches, such as continuous or scheduled recording, consume substantial energy and generate large volumes of data, most of which are irrelevant when the goal is to monitor specific species with irregular vocal activity. These methods often result in hours of recordings with no target sounds, leading to inefficient power use and significant need for post-processing.

To overcome these limitations, our approach avoids both continuous and duty-cycled recording modes. Instead, it employs an always-listening, low-power acoustic trigger based on a convolutional neural network trained to recognize vocalizations of the target species. This model continuously scans the incoming audio for relevant patterns and activates the recording mechanism only when a match is detected.

Existing PAM devices, such as AudioMoth [29] and other commercially available recorders, lack the computational capacity to run inference on embedded models. These devices are typically designed for scheduled or threshold-based recording and do not support the continuous inference required for selective recording. To enable real-time, on-device classification, we developed a custom device that uses a hardware accelerator [30]. This allows the system to remain energy-efficient while leveraging an embedded neural network, and making it suitable for deployment in remote, battery-powered scenarios.

Figure 1 illustrates a possible deployment workflow that leverages a selective recorder and integrates a domain adaptation stage using local data. Upon initial deployment, the device collects a small amount of

audio samples, which are then manually labeled and used to fine-tune the classification model offline. The device is then re-deployed with the updated model weights, and is left for an extended period of time with improved detection performance.

Fig. 1: Diagram of the proposed domain-adaptive deployment workflow for acoustic monitoring.

3. DATA

To train the base model we construct a large training dataset composed of public and controlled sources. We then fine-tune and evaluate the model on a limited amount of controlled audio samples from two geographically distinct Gentoo penguin colonies, which serve as separate locations to test the proposed domain adaptation strategy.

3.1. Training data

The training and validation datasets consist of 1-second audio clips, each one down-sampled to 16 kHz and labeled as either *penguin* or *not penguin*. The positive class examples were sourced primarily from the xeno-canto repository [31], focusing on annotated penguin vocalization recordings, while negative examples were mostly extracted from the FSD50K dataset [32], selecting clips without bird sounds. Additionally, a small portion of the samples were recorded by team members using AudioMoth devices in Ardley, Antarctica, as part of an in-house data collection project. These recordings were manually labeled, resulting in a total of approximately 10 hours for each class, evenly divided, with 80% used for training.

3.2. Target domains

To assess domain generalization and the impact of location-specific fine-tuning, we use three field datasets from two different Gentoo penguin colonies, collected and manually labeled by team members.

Dataset A: this dataset consists of 17 minutes of field recordings from a Gentoo penguin colony in Yorke Bay, Falkland Islands, collected using our device. Of these, approximately 9.1 minutes contain identifiable penguin vocalizations. This dataset represents an unseen domain both in terms of acoustic environment and recording hardware.

Dataset B: this dataset includes 14 minutes of field recordings of Gentoo penguin vocalizations in Ardley Island, Antarctica, of which 6.5 minutes contain penguin vocalizations. For this dataset, samples were recorded using AudioMoths. These samples share many

characteristics with a portion of the original training set, as they were recorded in a similar Antarctic environment using the same device.

Dataset C: this dataset contains 12 hours of uninterrupted audio recordings with annotated vocalization intervals, collected using AudioMoths at Yorke Bay. This allows us to replicate continuous audio input in order to evaluate our selective recording system end-to-end.

The first two datasets enable us to contrast domain adaptation performance in two distinct scenarios: one involving a fully novel domain (Dataset A), and another that partially overlaps with the training conditions in both location and recording device (Dataset B).

4. METHODOLOGY

We aim to evaluate whether lightweight fine-tuning on a small amount of location-specific data improves the performance of an embedded classification model deployed in new, unseen environments. To this end, we first train a base classification model on a dataset that excludes recordings from the target domains. We then fine-tune this pre-trained model using a subset of recordings from each target domain and evaluate its performance on held-out data from the same location.

4.1. Audio preprocessing

Each 1-second audio sample is transformed into a log-Mel spectrogram, using a frame size of 30 ms and a hop size of 10 ms for the Short-Time Fourier Transform. We also set the number of Mel bins to 96, resulting in spectrograms of 98 by 96. Features are then quantized to 8-bit integers, simulating embedded inference conditions. Two exemplar spectrograms from Dataset A are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Two exemplar spectrograms of penguin vocalizations from Dataset A, recorded in the Gentoo colony at Yorke Bay, Falkland Islands.

4.2. CNN architecture

For the classification task, we use a modified version of ResNet18 [33], where the number of filters in each convolutional layer is reduced to one quarter of the original in order to decrease memory and computation requirements. A full description of the modified architecture can be found in Table 1. The final layer outputs a binary classification, indicating the presence of penguin vocalizations. On the recording device, the CNN is fully quantized to 8-bit integers for efficient real-time inference. However, all training, fine-tuning, and evaluation are performed using 32-bit floats on a desktop machine.

The original training is performed for 50 epochs with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , applying early stopping. We use a scheduler to dynamically reduce the learning rate by a factor of 0.6 when the validation loss plateaus, with a patience of 3 epochs.

4.3. Domain adaptation strategy

To adapt the model to a new environment, we fine-tune the pre-trained base model using a small subset of data from the target domain. Each location-specific dataset is randomly split into 30% for fine-tuning and 70% for validation. Fine-tuning is performed for 15 epochs with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , and early stopping is applied to

Table 1: Modified ResNet18 architecture used for all experiments. Each row represents the sequence of layers, with **c** channels and stride **s**.

Input	Operator	c	s
$98 \times 96 \times 1$	Conv2D	16	2
$49 \times 48 \times 16$	MaxPool2D	16	2
$25 \times 24 \times 16$	Residual block $\times 2$	16	1
$25 \times 24 \times 16$	Conv2D + Residual block	32	2
$13 \times 12 \times 32$	Conv2D + Residual block	64	2
$7 \times 6 \times 64$	Conv2D + Residual block	64	2
$4 \times 3 \times 64$	GlobalAvgPool	-	-
$64 \times 1 \times 1$	Dense (ReLU)	32	-
$32 \times 1 \times 1$	Dense (sigmoid)	1	-

prevent overfitting, given the reduced size of the training set. We use a scheduler to dynamically reduce the learning rate by a factor of 0.6 when the validation loss plateaus, with a patience of 3 epochs. We also use 5-fold cross-validation to select the optimal number of layers to unfreeze during fine-tuning. To ensure robustness and mitigate bias introduced by data selection, we repeat this process over 20 splits.

4.4. Recording hysteresis

In order to prevent frequent toggling between recording states, the recorder device implements a simple hysteresis strategy: audio is recorded when at least $n = 2$ consecutive frames indicate positive detection, and stopped after $m = 2$ consecutive negatives. Part of assessing the effectiveness of domain adaptation is evaluating whether this mechanism also performs better when using the fine-tuned model.

To carry out this analysis, we use Dataset C to replicate continuous audio input, processing the full audio stream using both the baseline and fine-tuned models. The output predictions are used to trigger the hysteresis logic, generating a set of recorded segments. These are then compared against the annotated vocalization intervals to compute false positives and false negatives, as well as precision and recall.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

5.1. Impact of domain adaptation

We begin by evaluating how domain-specific fine-tuning impacts the generalization ability of the classification model. For each target dataset, we first assess the performance of the baseline model on the validation split. We then fine-tune this model using the local training data and re-evaluate its performance on the same validation split.

Results for the base and fine-tuned models on both locations are shown in Table 2, averaged across all repetitions. These results show that fine-tuning consistently improves performance across both datasets, yielding gains of up to 20.8% in terms of accuracy and 15.2% in terms of F1-score. Standard deviations across repetitions remain low, indicating that performance gains are stable and robust.

Table 2: Results obtained for the base and fine-tuned models on Datasets A and B, averaged across all repetitions and using 30% of the dataset for training.

Model	Dataset A		Dataset B	
	Accuracy (%)	F1-score (%)	Accuracy (%)	F1-score (%)
Baseline	67.8 ± 0.6	74.7 ± 0.8	88.3 ± 0.5	87.9 ± 0.6
Fine-tuned	88.6 ± 0.5	89.9 ± 0.4	95.9 ± 0.4	95.4 ± 0.4

We observe that performance on Dataset B is consistently better than on Dataset A, even before fine-tuning is applied, likely due to two factors. First, Dataset B was recorded using the same device as part of the original training data, reducing variability introduced by differing hardware. Second, although Dataset B was collected independently, it shares environmental context with the training set, which included Antarctic samples from previous field campaigns.

5.2. How many local samples are needed?

The previous section showed that simply fine-tuning on a reduced amount of location-specific samples can improve model performance. However, when local data is particularly limited and must be collected during deployment, the question arises: how many local samples are actually required to noticeably improve model performance?

This analysis is a crucial consideration for assessing the practicality of the proposed deployment workflow, since collecting large volumes of labeled local data may be infeasible due to logistical constraints.

To assess this aspect, we examine the relationship between the number of fine-tuning samples and the improvement achieved compared to the base model. We simulate different data availability scenarios by fine-tuning using varying percentages of the dataset, starting from 5% and up to the 30% employed in the previous section.

Figure 3 shows the results of fine-tuning the model using different amounts of local data from Datasets A and B. All models were evaluated on the full validation set. We observe that even small amounts of local data increase performance and help overcome non-fine-tuned models, particularly in the more challenging conditions of Dataset A. With as little as 30 seconds of training data, the classifier achieves a significant portion (90% or more) of the overall performance gain observed when fine-tuning with 30% of all available data.

Fig. 3: Results of fine-tuning the model using different amounts of local data from Datasets A and B.

For Dataset B, the accuracy and F1-score curves begin to plateau beyond the 2-minute mark, suggesting diminishing returns as more data is added. This trend indicates that a relatively small amount of labeled local data may be sufficient to adapt a pre-trained model to a location that shares certain characteristics with the original training dataset. For Dataset A, however, performance continues to improve more steadily with increasing amounts of fine-tuning data, particularly in terms of the F1-score, and no clear plateau is observed within

the tested range. The contrast between the two datasets highlights the importance of acoustic similarity: when the target environment closely resembles training conditions, minimal fine-tuning may suffice, whereas more distinct domains benefit from additional adaptation data.

5.3. Recording hysteresis

To further evaluate the benefits of domain adaptation, we compare the effectiveness of the recording hysteresis mechanism using the baseline and fine-tuned models. Both models are evaluated on Dataset C, replicating a continuous audio stream. Since the audio samples from said dataset were collected at the Yorke Bay colony, for the fine-tuned model we use the one re-trained on Dataset A.

Table 3 shows the results obtained for both models, presenting the number of false positives, false negatives, true positives and F1-score, all measured in total minutes of audio recorded from the full 12 hours.

Table 3: Results obtained for the base and fine-tuned models on the 12 hours of Dataset C, replicating a recording scheme with the hysteresis mechanism.

Model	True positives	False positives	False negatives	F1-score
Baseline	4.3 min	14.8 min	2.8 min	32.5%
Fine-tuned	5.4 min	7.9 min	1.7 min	52.7%

While both models produce a considerable number of false positives, the true positives rate remains high. In addition, the percentages of true negatives is extremely high, given that, out of 12 hours, less than twenty minutes are recorded. This is particularly important in selective recording, where erroneous recordings would result in higher volumes of irrelevant data. Moreover, the fine-tuned model achieves a better performance, increasing the F1-score value by a net gain of 20.2%. While this is mainly due to the reduction of false negatives, it also responds to a slight rise in true positives. Despite the F1-score value not being particularly high in absolute terms, the relative improvement still highlights the effectiveness of domain adaptation in this context. Overall, these results support the value of incorporating localized data during training to enhance performance in novel field conditions.

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a domain-adaptive deployment workflow for selective audio recording in wildlife acoustic monitoring. By combining a low-power embedded recording device with an on-device classification model, our system enables energy-efficient monitoring in remote environments such as penguin colonies. To mitigate the challenges introduced by domain shift, we proposed a lightweight fine-tuning strategy based on a small amount of location-specific data.

Through experiments on field data, collected from two geographically distinct Gentoo penguin colonies, we show that domain-specific fine-tuning leads to substantial gains in classification performance. Notably, we find that even small amounts of local data (as little as 30 seconds) can yield meaningful improvements over the base model while requiring minimal annotation effort. This result is particularly relevant for remote monitoring deployments, where collecting large amounts of labeled data during the initial stages is often infeasible.

We also demonstrate that these improvements translate into better selective recording performance, reducing false positives and false negatives in realistic deployment conditions. Future work will focus on validating the proposed domain adaptation strategy in future recordings campaigns in Ardley, Antarctica, as part of an ongoing research and data collection project. This will involve effectively integrating the proposed monitoring strategy into the regular campaign workflow, including the mid-deployment fine-tuning stage with a few labeled local samples.

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On the Role of Training Class Distribution in Zero-Shot Audio Classification

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Abstract—Zero-shot learning (ZSL) enables the classification of audio samples into classes that are not seen during training by transferring semantic information learned from seen classes to unseen ones. Thus, the ability of zero-shot models to generalize to unseen classes is inherently affected by the training data. While most audio ZSL studies focus on improving model architectures, the effect of training class distribution in the audio embedding space has not been well explored. In this work, we investigate how the distribution of training classes in audio embedding space, both internally and in relation to unseen classes, affects zero-shot classification performance. We design two controlled experimental setups to understand the impact of training classes: (i) a similarity-based configuration, where we experiment with varying acoustic similarity between training classes and unseen test classes, and (ii) a diversity-based configuration, where the training sets are constructed with different levels of coverage in the audio embedding space. We conduct our experiments on a subset of AudioSet, evaluating zero-shot classification performance under different training class configurations. Our experiments demonstrate that both higher acoustic similarity between training and test classes and higher acoustic diversity among training classes improve zero-shot classification accuracy.

Index Terms—zero-shot learning, audio classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Zero-shot learning (ZSL) refers to the ability of a model to recognize classes that were not introduced during training by utilizing semantic information such as textual class descriptions or attribute embeddings [1]. By transferring knowledge from seen to unseen classes, zero-shot models can perform classification tasks without requiring labeled examples from every class. This ability is especially useful where data collection is difficult, such as for rare classes.

In the audio domain, ZSL is particularly important as the temporal nature of audio makes data annotation expensive. Instead of requiring labeled examples for every target class, zero-shot learning enables classification of unseen classes by learning to map audio and semantic embeddings into a shared space using only seen classes. However, it makes two strong assumptions: (i) audio and semantic embeddings of the same class can be mapped to nearby points in the shared space, and (ii) the shared space learned from seen classes is structured to generalize to unseen class embeddings. In practice, domain mismatch between audio and text embeddings often limits this alignment, and learned projection functions may fail to generalize to the regions of the shared space where unseen classes fall into, leading to poor zero-shot performance.

Most prior work in audio ZSL has focused on improving the model architectures and modality alignment through objective functions. Perhaps the most influential models in ZSL like CLAP [2], [3] and AudioCLIP [4] demonstrate the power of contrastive learning for audio–text embedding. More recent studies utilize large language models (LLMs) to enhance class representations by generating rich textual descriptions or attribute-based prompts to improve the alignment between audio and semantic embeddings in zero-shot settings [5]–[7].

In computer vision, recent works have studied the topological structure of the embedding space and have shown that preserving or modeling relationship between classes can improve ZSL performance,

for example, by preserving the class topology in the embedding space in [8], aligning semantic and visual graphs in [9], [10], and modeling the global structure for compositional ZSL models in [11], [12]. However, these approaches are mainly limited to the vision domain. In the audio domain, while projection quality has been widely explored, the impact of training class structure in ZSL is underexplored.

Furthermore, recent studies have emphasized the importance of the distribution of training classes in zero-shot learning. They show that class imbalance or distribution shifts can harm generalization, and propose solutions such as synthetic data generation [13] or out-of-distribution detection [14]. Motivated by these, we investigate the effect of the distribution of training data in the audio embedding space on zero-shot performance.

In this work, we study how the relative position of training classes, both with respect to each other and to those of test classes, in the audio embedding space affects zero-shot classification performance. Our hypothesis is that having training classes that are acoustically more similar to test classes can support better alignment, while a diverse set of training classes that spans a larger region of the space may provide better coverage and improve generalization compared to training classes clustered in a narrow region.

We address two questions: (i) Does greater acoustic similarity between training and test classes improve zero-shot performance? (ii) Does increasing diversity among training classes improve generalization? To answer these questions, we design two controlled experimental setups:

- Similarity-based analysis, where we investigate how the acoustic proximity between training and test classes affects performance by constructing training sets with varying levels of similarity to the test classes.
- Diversity-based analysis, where we vary the internal pairwise similarity of training classes to examine the effect of training set coverage in the audio embedding space.

By evaluating performance across a wide range of configurations, we analyze how structural factors influence zero-shot accuracy. Our results show that both high train–test similarity and moderate training diversity are essential for robust zero-shot performance.

2. ZERO-SHOT AUDIO CLASSIFICATION FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 illustrates the pipeline of our zero-shot audio classification model, which learns to map audio clips to class descriptions only using seen training classes. Our approach is based on previous work on projection-based alignment between audio and semantic embeddings for zero-shot classification in [15], with an additional learnable semantic projection layer. Let X be the set of audio samples and C the set of class indices, split into seen C_{train} and unseen C_{test} , where $C_{\text{train}} \cap C_{\text{test}} = \emptyset$. The training set is defined as the labeled pairs

$$D_{\text{train}} = \{(x_n, y_n)\}_{n=1}^N, \quad x_n \in X, \quad y_n \in C_{\text{train}}, \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of training samples, x_n is the n -th audio sample, and y_n is its corresponding class index. Each audio sample x

Fig. 1: Overview of the zero-shot audio classification framework. Audio and semantic embeddings are projected into a shared embedding space where their compatibility is computed. Projection layers are updated via an objective function in training. Inference selects the top-1 predicted class based on compatibility scores.

is encoded using an audio embedding function $\phi_a : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_a}$, and each class description $c \in C$ is embedded using a language embedding model $\phi_t : C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_t}$, where d_a and d_t denote the output dimensions of the audio and language embedding models, respectively. These embeddings are then projected into a shared space using learnable functions

$$f_a : \mathbb{R}^{d_a} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D, f_t : \mathbb{R}^{d_t} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D, \quad (2)$$

where D is the dimension of the shared space. To measure how well an audio sample and a class description match, we compute their compatibility in the shared space using cosine similarity:

$$F(x, c) = \cos(f_a(\phi_a(x)), f_t(\phi_t(c))). \quad (3)$$

The objective is to bring audio embeddings closer to their corresponding semantic embeddings in the shared space. To achieve this, we use the Weighted Approximate Rank Pairwise (WARP) loss following [15]. The model is trained to assign a higher compatibility score $F(x_n, y_n)$ to correct pairs (x_n, y_n) than to incorrect ones.

At inference, for an unseen audio sample x , the model predicts the class with the highest compatibility score among the unseen classes $z \in C_{\text{test}}$:

$$\hat{z} = \arg \max_{z \in C_{\text{test}}} F(x, z). \quad (4)$$

In our implementation, we use pretrained and frozen VGGish [16] as the audio embedding model ($d_a = 128$) and Sentence-BERT (SBERT) [17] as the semantic embedding model ($d_t = 768$). The audio projection consists of two fully connected layers of sizes 256 and 512, with a tanh activation in between. The semantic projection layer is a single fully connected layer of size 512.

As the projection layers are learned only on the training pairs, the geometry of the shared embedding space is shaped by their structure. Unseen test classes may project into any region of this space, but may fall into misaligned regions to have meaningful representation for reliable prediction. This is illustrated in Figure 2, where unseen classes and test audio embeddings fall outside the training subspace. Understanding how these structures affect zero-shot classification is therefore important for designing more robust models.

Fig. 2: Illustration of the shared embedding space. Purple area (left): Projected training and class embeddings form a learned training subspace. Gray area (right): Unseen test classes and test audio embeddings may project outside the training subspace. Test audio is predicted as the class whose embedding is the most similar.

3. TRAINING SET CONFIGURATIONS

To analyze the effect of training class distribution in the audio embedding space, we design two controlled experimental setups varying training class sets. We apply these analyses to audio embeddings (see Section 4.1 for details). For the purpose of analysis, we assume access to the full labeled dataset before defining training and test splits. To define the configurations, we first represent each class by the class-level audio embedding μ_c , defined as the centroid of the audio embeddings of all samples in a class c :

$$\mu_c = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{i \in I_c} \phi_a(x_i), \quad (5)$$

where $\phi_a(x_i)$ is the pretrained audio embedding of sample x_i , y_i refers to the label of sample x_i , $I_c = \{i \mid y_i = c\}$ is the set of indices of samples labeled as class c , and $N_c = |I_c|$.

Based on these class-level audio embeddings, we create training sets with controlled class distributions for two different analyses. In the similarity-based analysis, we construct train–test configurations where the training classes have different levels of acoustic similarity to the test classes. In the diversity-based analysis, we create training sets where the internal similarity of class-level audio embeddings among training classes are within different ranges, resulting in varying levels of coverage in the audio embedding space.

3.1. Similarity-based Analysis

To understand how the local alignment between seen and unseen classes in the audio embedding space affects zero-shot performance, we systematically vary the similarity ratio between training and test samples in the audio embedding space. We first group acoustically similar classes by clustering them. To perform clustering based on cosine similarity, we normalize all class-level audio embeddings to unit length $\hat{\mu}_c = \mu_c / \|\mu_c\|$ and then apply K-means (with $K = 3$) to the set $\{\hat{\mu}_c \mid c \in C\}$.

Each cluster is used once as the source of test and validation classes in a separate evaluation configuration. That is, in each configuration, we select a fixed number of test and validation classes exclusively from one cluster, and refer to that as the test cluster, while the remaining classes from all clusters are considered as training candidates. For each test cluster, we construct five different training sets by varying the proportion of training classes selected from the test cluster. We define the similarity ratio as the percentage of training classes that belong to the same cluster as the test set. Specifically, we use the

Fig. 3: Illustration of training set configurations with toy data in (a) similarity-based, (b) diversity-based. Each subplot shows one illustrative instance: a single test cluster in (a), and a fixed test/validation set in (b). In the actual experiments, we repeat this procedure for multiple configurations (see Section 4.2).

levels 1.0, 0.75, 0.50, 0.25, and 0.0. For example, a similarity ratio of 0.75 means that 75% of training classes are selected from the same cluster as the test set, and 25% from the remaining clusters.

We repeat this process for each cluster, each with five training sets of varying similarity levels, and report the Pearson correlation between similarity ratio and test accuracy. Figure 3a illustrates the effect of the similarity ratio on train and test sets on a toy data.

3.2. Diversity-based Analysis

To investigate whether diversity among training classes helps generalization, we define training sets with different diversity levels in the audio embedding space. We measure diversity by the average pairwise cosine similarity between class-level audio embeddings. Specifically, we define five different cosine similarity ranges as (0.5, 0.6], (0.6, 0.7], (0.7, 0.8], (0.8, 0.9], and (0.9, 1.0]. We create training sets with different diversities with an iterative algorithm as follows:

- 1) Randomly select three test sets and three validation sets. These sets remain fixed for every diversity range.
- 2) For each range
 - Initialize the training set with a randomly chosen class from the remaining set (excluding any test and validation set).
 - Iteratively add new classes whose average pairwise cosine similarity to the current training set falls within a target range (e.g., (0.5, 0.6]).
 - Repeat until the training set reaches a predefined number of classes for each target range.

- 3) Evaluate the zero-shot accuracy obtained using a model trained with that training set on each of the three fixed test sets.

The goal of this setup is to measure the effect of the training data diversity on performance when the unseen classes are fixed. We compare performance across ranges by measuring the correlation between the average pairwise cosine similarity of training classes and test accuracy. Figure 3b illustrates through toy examples with different diversity levels: high, moderate, and low diversity. Higher diversity means lower internal cosine similarity and high-diverse sets provide larger coverage in the audio embedding space.

4. EXPERIMENTS

This section presents the experimental setup, including the dataset and training procedure for both analyses.

4.1. Dataset

We conduct our experiments on a subset of AudioSet [18], focusing on single-label samples. The AudioSet ontology provides a tree-like class hierarchy. To have enough data per class, we construct the subset by traversing the AudioSet ontology upward and selecting the deepest node with more than 100 samples, or its parent if none qualify. With this strategy, we ensure to choose the most specific classes with sufficient data. Applying this algorithm results in 143 classes, each with at least 100 samples.

We extract audio embeddings using a pretrained VGGish model. Each 10-second audio clip is divided into 10 segments, where each segment is mapped to a 128-dimensional vector. These segment-level embeddings are averaged to produce a single 128-dimensional

clip-level audio embedding. These embeddings are used both for training and for constructing class-level audio representations (obtained by averaging over all samples of a class) used in class selection strategies. For semantic embeddings, we apply the Sentence-BERT (SBERT) model [17] to the sentence-level class descriptions provided by AudioSet, resulting in a 768-dimensional vector for each class.

4.2. Training Setup

In the similarity-based analysis, we define 15 configurations with 5 similarity ratios (1.0, 0.75, 0.50, 0.25, and 0.0) and 3 test clusters. Each configuration corresponds to a distinct pairing of a test cluster and a similarity ratio. In the diversity-based analysis, we also define 15 configurations with 5 cosine similarity ranges ((0.5, 0.6], (0.6, 0.7], (0.7, 0.8], (0.8, 0.9], and (0.9, 1.0]) and 3 test sets. We use multiple test clusters (similarity-based) and test sets (diversity-based) to reduce the impact of any single test configuration. Each configuration is repeated 6 times with different random seeds, resulting in different combinations of train, validation, and test classes with the same analysis conditions. This leads to a total of 90 models for each analysis.

We set the number of clusters in similarity-based analysis to $K = 3$, selected using the elbow method. In the diversity-based analysis, the lower bound of 0.5 is chosen since the class pairs with pairwise similarity below 0.5 are extremely rare to construct complete training configurations with the given audio embeddings. Each configuration has 20 training, 5 validation, and 5 test classes. All models are trained from scratch and optimized using stochastic gradient descent (SGD) with a learning rate of 0.001, batch size of 64, and for 100 epochs.

5. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

We report our findings separately for the similarity-based and diversity-based setups. In both cases, we evaluate the performance using top-1 accuracy averaged across random seeds per configuration. We analyze the relationship between class structuring metrics (similarity ratio and pairwise cosine similarity) and test accuracy via Pearson correlation.

5.1. Similarity-based Results

To measure the impact of train–test similarity, we defined a similarity ratio as the proportion of training classes from the same cluster as the test set. Figure 4 shows that accuracy increases with higher similarity, rising from 0.25 at similarity ratio 0.0 to 0.39 at similarity ratio 1.0. The trend holds across all test clusters despite minor accuracy variations.

Similarity ratio and accuracy show a significant positive correlation with $r = 0.374$ and $p < 0.001$ as shown in Table 1, indicating that increasing the acoustic similarity between test and training classes improves the model’s ability to generalize to test classes.

5.2. Diversity-based Results

In the diversity-based setup, we varied the acoustic diversity of training classes by controlling their average pairwise cosine similarity. Results in Figure 5 show that accuracy peaks in the (0.6, 0.7] similarity range, where training classes are moderately diverse, with a mean of 0.50. Accuracy drops at both low (0.29 at (0.9, 1.0]) and high diversity (0.43 at (0.5, 0.6]), suggesting that moderate diversity provides the best balance between coverage and coherence. In addition, the standard deviation in accuracy increases with lower diversity, indicating less stable generalization when the model is trained on narrowly distributed classes. For example, the standard deviation was 0.07 in the (0.5, 0.6] range, compared to 0.13 in the (0.9, 1.0] range.

The Pearson correlation between mean pairwise similarity and test accuracy confirms this relationship with $r = -0.434$, $p < 0.001$ as shown in Table 1, indicating that greater training data diversity (i.e., lower internal similarity) is beneficial for model performance.

Fig. 4: Similarity-based results: Zero-shot classification accuracy across five train–test similarity ratios per cluster.

Fig. 5: Diversity-based results: Zero-shot classification accuracy grouped by the average pairwise cosine similarity between class-level audio embeddings.

Table 1: Pearson correlation coefficients between class structuring metrics and zero-shot accuracy, computed over 90 models per setup.

Strategy	Correlation (r)	p-value
Similarity-based	0.374	<0.001
Diversity-based	−0.434	<0.001

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, we investigated how the structure of training classes in the audio embedding space affects generalization in zero-shot audio classification. We proposed two experimental setups: one that changes the similarity ratio between training and test classes, and another that varies the diversity level among training classes. The similarity-based analysis demonstrates that increasing the acoustic similarity between training and test classes improves zero-shot performance. The diversity-based results show that when training classes are overly similar, the model may overfit and fail to capture patterns outside of the training class regions, whereas training sets that span a larger region of the space lead to better generalization. Based on these findings, future zero-shot audio classification models may benefit from explicitly leveraging structural information, such as graph-based or geometry-aware techniques to model the topologies of audio and semantic spaces.

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CochlScene Pre-Training and Device-Aware Distillation for Low-Complexity Acoustic Scene Classification

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Abstract—Acoustic Scene Classification (ASC) aims to categorize short audio clips into pre-defined scene classes. The DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 1 evaluates ASC systems on the TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile dataset, under strict low complexity constraints (128 kB memory, 30 MMACs), with only 25% of labels available and device IDs provided at inference. In this work, we present an ASC system that exploits device type information and pretraining on an external ASC dataset to improve the classification performance. In addition, we conduct an ablation study to quantify the impact of each component in our pipeline. Our approach centers on a compact CP-Mobile student model distilled via Bayesian ensemble averaging from different combinations of CP-ResNet and BEATs teachers. We evaluate domain-specific pre-training on the CochlScene dataset on both student and teachers to compensate for label scarcity. Additionally, we apply a rich data augmentation suite, of which Device Impulse Response augmentation was particularly effective. Finally, we exploit device IDs to fine-tune specialized student and teacher models per recording device. On the TAU Urban 2022 development-test dataset, our system achieved a macro-averaged accuracy of 60.5%, representing an 8.61 percentage point improvement over the DCASE baseline, securing us the top rank in the DCASE 2025 Task 1 Challenge.

Index Terms—Low-complexity Acoustic Scene Classification, Knowledge Distillation, CochlScene, Bayesian Ensemble Averaging, DIR Augmentation, Freq-MixStyle, CP-ResNet, BEATs, CP-Mobile

1. INTRODUCTION

Acoustic Scene Classification (ASC) focuses on identifying acoustic scenes from raw audio. The DCASE 2025 Task 1 [1] addresses real-world challenges, such as recording device mismatch, low-complexity constraints, and limited availability of training data, with this year’s focus on device information. Using the TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile dataset (TAU22) [2], the challenge aims to classify 1-second audio clips into 10 predefined audio scenes. The contestants face two low-complexity constraints: maximum memory allowance for model parameters equal to 128 kB and computational complexity at inference time restricted to 30 MMACs.

This year’s focus is put on device information, which can be used to fine-tune the models for specific recording devices. Due to availability of recording device information in the evaluation dataset, distinct models can be used per device, while still applying the general model to unseen recording devices. An additional change was made in terms of the availability of data. Training data is restricted to 25% subset of the DCASE24 Task 1 dataset. However, it is permitted to utilize external ASC datasets for model development.

This paper contributes to the research on the practical application of ASC systems by studying the effect of pre-training student and teacher models on CochlScene, applying Device Impulse Response augmentation (DIR) and fine-tuning them on the recording devices. The proposed system achieved the first rank in Task 1 of the DCASE 2025 Challenge [1].

We review related work in Section 2, followed by the methodology in Section 3. Section 4 is devoted to the experimental setup, while

Section 5 presents the results and discussion. Finally, the paper is concluded in Section 6.

2. RELATED WORK

We present advancements and techniques in the field of ASC, that this work build upon.

2.1. Architectures

Self attention architectures have rapidly advanced ASC by capturing long-range dependencies in time-frequency representations [3]. The Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST) [4] introduces a fully-attention based encoder that outperforms CNNs on Audioset and ESC-50 [5] benchmarks. Building on AST, PaSST [3] employs Patchout to accelerate training and reduce redundancy, achieving SOTA results on AudioSet. More recently, BEATs [6] leverages self-supervised pre-training with an acoustic tokenizer to learn robust representations, reaching 50.6% mAP on AudioSet-2M [7] and 98.1% accuracy on ESC-50. In DCASE Challenge submissions, these large transformer are commonly used as teachers for knowledge distillation into lightweight student models [8].

2.2. Data Augmentation

To mitigate overfitting and enhance robustness in low-data scenarios, ASC systems commonly employ various data augmentation techniques that aims to improve overall generalization [9]. At the waveform level, temporal shifts, also called time-rolling, randomly circularly shift the audio to learn temporal invariance in scene cues. Device Impulse Response (DIR) augmentation [10] convolves the input with the microphone impulse responses, to simulate audio recorded by different microphones [10]. In the time-frequency domain, SpecAugment [11] applies random masks along both time and frequency axes of the log-mel spectrogram. This prevents reliance on narrow spectro-temporal features and therefore increases robustness.

2.3. Device-aware fine-tuning

To explicitly account for device-specific distortions, models can be finetuned using device metadata or specialized modules. A simple approach is per-device fine-tuning, where a shared backbone is adapted separately on each device’s data, yielding better performance on that device at inference time [12]. More parameter-efficient methods insert small adapter layers or conditional normalization into a network (e.g., FiLM [13] or device-conditional BatchNorm [14]), where only these modules are trained per device. Domain generalization techniques such as MixStyle [15] or Freq-MixStyle [16] blend feature statistics across device domains during training, which results in improved generalization and robustness for unseen devices.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we describe the different components of the training pipeline used for the experiments outlined in Section 4.

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3.1. Datasets

3.1.1. TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile dataset: Our primary dataset is the TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile dataset (TAU22) [2], an extension of the 2020 Mobile dataset [17]. In TAU22, each original 10-second clip has been split into ten 1-second, single-channel samples at 44.1 kHz. TAU22 includes recordings from multiple European cities across ten scene classes, captured with four real devices (A, B, C, and D) and supplemented by simulated devices (S1–S10). The ten classes in TAU22 are: *airport, bus, metro, metro station, park, public square, shopping mall, street pedestrian, street traffic, tram*.

The 2025 Low-Complexity Acoustic Scene Classification task provides both official development and evaluation splits. For development, only 25% of the official training set is permitted during model training [1]. This corresponds to last year’s 25% train split. The development set can be further split into:

- **Development-train:** devices A, B, C and simulations S1–S3 (8.25 hours of audio)
- **Development-test:** devices A, B, C and simulations S1–S6 (9.7 hours of audio)

3.1.2. CochScene dataset: CochScene [18] is an acoustic scene dataset, collected through crowdsourcing. It consists of 76,115 single-channel audio files with a sample rate of 44.1kHz and a length of 10 seconds. There are a total of 13 different classes, spanning acoustic scenes from urban areas in South Korea. The 13 classes in CochScene are: *bus, cafe, car, crowded indoor, elevator, kitchen, park, residential area, restaurant, restroom, street, subway, subway station*.

3.1.3. AudioSet: AudioSet [7] is a large-scale multi-label audio event dataset, gathered from YouTube. It contains over 2 million ten-second audio clips, annotated by humans across a total of 632 classes. Each sample is a single-channel audio file with a sample rate of 44.1kHz. The labels are hierarchically structured, such that categories can be subdivided into increasingly specific event labels. It is widely used as a benchmark for multi-label audio tagging, sound event detection, and pre-training of general-purpose audio feature extractors [3], [4], [19], [20].

3.2. Architectures

3.2.1. Teacher models: As previously demonstrated, CP-ResNet architecture performs effectively on the TAU22 development set [8]. In our work, the following teacher architectures were employed:

- **CP-ResNet** [21], a receptive field regularized convolutional neural network (RFR-CNN) [22], whose controlled receptive field leads to enhanced generalization for ASC.
- **BEATs** [6], an iterative audio pre-training framework to learn Bidirectional Encoder representation with Audio Transformers.

3.2.2. Student model: We employed the compact CP-Mobile (CPM) architecture [12] as the student model. The detailed architecture can be seen in the Table 1.

The architecture of CP-Mobile consists of three different blocks composed of sequences of three layers: point-wise expansion, depth-wise convolution, and point-wise projection. Each layer consists of a convolutional operation with batch normalization [23] and ReLU [24] activation applied. This structure allows to keep the expressiveness, while reducing the computational complexity of the model. The mentioned blocks can be described as:

- 1) **Transition block (CPM block T)**, which increases the channel dimension and does not contain any residual connections.
- 2) **Standard block (CPM block S)**, which does not change the channel dimension and uses the residual connection.

Blocks	Input shape	Parameters	MACs
Initial convolutions	[1, 1, 256, 65]	2,456	2,810,960
Block 1 (CPM-S)	[1, 32, 64, 17]	4,992	5,083,456
Block 2 (CPM-D)	[1, 32, 64, 17]	4,992	5,083,456
Block 3 (CPM-S)	[1, 32, 64, 17]	4,992	3,739,968
Block 4 (CPM-T)	[1, 32, 64, 9]	6,576	2,378,096
Block 5 (CPM-S)	[1, 56, 32, 9]	15,112	4,182,352
Block 6 (CPM-T)	[1, 56, 32, 9]	20,968	5,841,328
Final convolution	[1, 104, 32, 9]	1,060	299,540

Table 1: CP-Mobile architecture indicating input shape, total parameters, and MACs per block. (CPM-S: Standard block, CPM-T: Transition block, CPM-D: Spatial Downsampling block)

- 3) **Spatial Downsampling block (CPM block D)**, which does not change the channel dimension and uses the residual connection with average pooling.

The structure of each block can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Visualisation of CPM blocks structures

The first two layers of CP-Mobile project the input data from mel spectrograms to models feature space. At the last three layers, 1x1 convolution, batch normalization, and adaptive average pooling are applied.

With 61,148 parameters and 29,419,156 MACs the architecture meets the constraints when the model weights are converted to half-precision (16 bit) floating point representation for inference.

3.3. Feature extraction and data augmentation

3.3.1. Preprocessing: We resample audio to a model-specific target sampling rate and compute log-scaled mel spectrograms. The parameters used for the STFT and log-scaled mel spectrogram vary between architectures and are listed in Table 2.

Parameter	CP-Mobile	CP-ResNet	BEATs
Original sample rate (kHz)	44.1	44.1	44.1
Target sample rate (kHz)	32	32	16
FFT size	4096	4096	1024
Window length (ms)	96	96	25
Hop length (ms)	16	24	10
Number of mel bins	256	256	128

Table 2: Preprocessing parameters for different model architectures

3.3.2. Data augmentations: Both waveform-level (time rolling, Devo Impulse Response (DIR) [10]) and spectrogram-level (SpecAugment [11], Freq-MixStyle [16]) augmentations were employed.

Among these, the DIR augmentation proved to strongly improve the overall accuracy of the model during the challenge. We perform DIR augmentation by convolving the audio waveform with one of 66

impulse responses taken from MicIRP¹. The augmentation is applied with a probability of 70% to samples recorded with device A.

3.4. Pre-Training on AudioSet and CochScene

Considering the limited size of the development dataset, previous work [25] has shown that it is beneficial to pre-train (or use existing pre-trained weights for) both the teachers and the student models on external audio datasets.

For the transformer based BEATs architecture, we use a publicly available checkpoint pre-trained on AudioSet. Since the classes and their number do not match the downstream training, the classification head is discarded. We use the checkpoint² provided by the authors of [20], corresponding to a model pre-trained using self-supervised learning with patch-wise masked prediction on AudioSet and fine-tuned on AudioSet with weak labels.

We furthermore use the CochScene dataset [18] to pre-train the models involved in the preparation of the submitted systems. Since this dataset was specifically created for ASC tasks, albeit under very different urban conditions (Asia - South Korea) and using more heterogeneous recording devices, we hypothesize that models pre-trained on it would more effectively adapt to the task at hand and generalize better to unseen recording devices. The CP-ResNet teacher and the CP-Mobile student models are trained on 1-second slices of CochScene audio clips. For BEATs teacher, we use the full audio clips, matching the 10s input size of their AudioSet pre-training. Table 3 details the key hyperparameters used.

3.5. Knowledge distillation

Knowledge distillation (KD) [26] is a training method, where a model is not only trained on the one-hot encoded class labels directly, but also on the logits of one or more teacher models. The teachers are usually large models with high performance. Knowledge distillation in general leads to better-performing and more robust models.

Through a division of the outputs of the teacher and student models with a temperature value (τ) and subsequent application of the softmax function, softer, more informative targets are produced.

The loss function is a weighted average of a label loss (L_l), in our case the cross-entropy-loss, and the distillation loss (L_{KD}), which is the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence between teacher and student logits.

With λ as the weight and z_S and z_T as the output logits of the student and teacher model, the loss function is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Loss} = \lambda L_l(\delta(z_S), y) + (1 - \lambda)\tau^2 L_{kd}(\delta(z_S/\tau), \delta(z_T/\tau))$$

Instead of a single teacher, we use Bayesian Ensemble Averaging (BAE) [25], [27] of several teacher models. With this, multiple teachers, possibly trained with different configurations, can be combined.

We use online KD to also apply the same data augmentation pipeline for the teacher models [28].

3.6. Device-specific training

DCASE’25 Task 1 focuses on fine-tuning the obtained model per device present during training (development-train devices: A, B, C, S1, S2, S3). The general model, for both student and teacher models, is used to initialize six specialized models, which are further fine-tuned on data specific to only one device. At inference time, the input is dispatched to a specialized model using the device ID—if known—otherwise to the general model. This way, one can obtain higher accuracies for devices encountered during training.

¹<https://micirp.blogspot.com>

²<https://github.com/fschmid56/PretrainedSED/releases>

4. EXPERIMENTS

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed method, we perform two complementary sets of experiments. First, we perform step-by-step ablation study to quantify the impact and interference of three components: pre-training on CochScene, DIR augmentation, and device-specific fine-tuning procedure. Second, we investigate different teacher model combinations and the corresponding CP-Mobile student model performance.

4.1. Training

For all experiments, we use the AdamW [29] optimizer and a cosine learning rate scheduler with the corresponding hyperparameters adapted to each task. The specific values are captured in Table 3.

Task	Dataset	Max LR	Warm-up	Epochs	Batch size
CPM pre-train	CochScene (1s)	0.005	2000	100	512
CPM general	TAU22	0.005	2000	150	256
CPM device specific	TAU22	0.0005	200	50	256
CP-ResNet pre-train	CochScene (1s)	0.001	2000	150	512
CP-ResNet general	TAU22	0.001	2000	100	256
CP-ResNet device-specific	TAU22	0.00001	200	50	256
BEATs pre-train	CochScene (10s)	0.00007	5000	30	10
BEATs general	TAU22	0.00001	2000	30	80
BEATs device-specific	TAU22	0.000005	2000	30	256

Table 3: Hyperparameters used for different training tasks.

Despite the different input lengths for the BEATs model, we opt to directly use the 1-second TAU22 samples without additional adaptation. This approach results in only a minor decrease in classification accuracy while significantly reducing both training time and memory consumption.

4.2. Ablation study

We evaluate three main enhancements applied to the general model: DIR augmentation, pretraining on the CochScene dataset, and the combination of both. These experiments are performed across three models: CP-ResNet, BEATs, CP-Mobile. A general CP-ResNet model and CP-Mobile are trained from scratch, while for the BEATs we use a checkpoint pre-trained on AudioSet. For each, the general model is trained on the 25% labeled subset of TAU22. To indicate the performance clearly, we do not use Knowledge distillation in this training procedure and the hyperparameters are kept constant. We store the variant with the highest accuracy on the TAU22 development-test dataset for each model and treat it as a starting point in the fine-tuning step. This training procedure clearly indicates the individual impact of the mentioned enhancements.

4.3. Evaluation of Teacher Model Combinations

For this set of experiments, different combinations of teachers are investigated. We perform Knowledge distillation from the following teachers: CP-Resnet, BEATs and device-specific CP-ResNet into the CP-Mobile student model. The device-specific BEATs model was not considered, since it resulted in a large increase in training time and computational cost. We then evaluated five combinations: each of the three teachers by themselves, only the general teachers and an ensemble of all three. All hyperparameters are kept constant for all combinations of the teachers. For training the general model, we use the temperature $\tau = 2$ and the weight $\lambda = 0.02$ —values that produced good results in previous editions of the task [12]. For device-specific training, the best results were achieved with $\lambda = 0.1$. This procedure is meant to quantify the effect of device-specific teachers on the performance of the student model.

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In this section, we provide the results of the previously described experiments. All reported results represent the mean performance aggregated across three independent runs.

5.1. Ablation study

Table 4 and Figure 2 present the results of our ablation study, in which we isolate the contribution of key components: Device Impulse Response augmentation, pretraining on the CochScene dataset, and device-specific fine-tuning.

For the CP-Mobile student model, both DIR augmentation and CochScene pretraining individually improved performance over the base model, yielding gains of 3.4%*pt.* and 3.7%*pt.* respectively. When combined, these enhancements resulted in an improvement of 5.9%*pt.*

CP-ResNet showed a similar trend: pre-training on CochScene led to a clear gain over the base model of 2.8%*pt.*, while DIR augmentation alone slightly decreased performance by 1%*pt.* The combination of DIR and CochScene, however, improved the performance by 3.6%*pt.* for this model.

Interestingly, The BEATs teacher model achieved the highest base performance, but exhibited a decrease of 1.2%*pt.* when pre-trained on CochScene. Applying DIR augmentation led to a slight improvement of 0.5%*pt.* For this architecture, the combination of these two components performed 1.0%*pt.* worse compared to the base model.

Applying device-specific fine-tuning always resulted in an improvement in performance. Specifically, 1.0%*pt.* for CP-Mobile, 0.8%*pt.* for CP-ResNet, and 0.7%*pt.* for BEATs.

These results demonstrate that augmentation and pre-training strategies must be carefully tailored to the model architecture. When chosen appropriately, these methods can lead to substantial performance gains.

Method	CP-Mobile	CP-ResNet	BEATs
Base	0.513 ± 0.004	0.552 ± 0.004	0.582 ± 0.003
DIR	0.547 ± 0.003	0.542 ± 0.007	0.585 ± 0.005
Cochl	0.550 ± 0.003	0.580 ± 0.006	0.568 ± 0.001
DIR+Cochl	0.572 ± 0.002	0.588 ± 0.002	0.570 ± 0.001
Best+Device-Specific	0.582 ± 0.003	0.596 ± 0.006	0.592 ± 0.006

Table 4: Macro-average accuracy of the ablation study described in section 4.2 (mean±std). The best-performing model for each architecture—which is used as the basis for the device-specific model—is highlighted.

Fig. 2: Macro-average accuracy of the ablation study described in Section 4.2. The error bars show the standard deviation.

5.2. Evaluation of Teacher Model Combinations

Table 5 and Figure 3 summarize the performance of different teacher model configurations used for KD, evaluated with both general and device-specific CP-Mobile student models.

Using a single device-specific CP-ResNet teacher improves the performance of the general student by 0.4%*pt.* compared to using a general teacher. The device-specific student improves by 0.3%*pt.*

BEATs on its own performs worse than the two CP-ResNet teachers, but using it in an ensemble with CP-ResNet improved the performance by 1.9%*pt.* for the general and 1.4%*pt.* for the device-specific student, compared to just using CP-ResNet.

Adding the device-specific CP-Resnet to the previously mentioned ensemble increased the macro-averaged accuracy of the general model by 0.5%*pt.* The device-specific model improved by 0.7%*pt.*

This clearly shows how incorporating device-specific teachers can improve the performance of the student model.

Model	General	Device-Specific
BEATs	0.545 ± 0.005	0.554 ± 0.018
CP-ResNet	0.574 ± 0.008	0.582 ± 0.015
CP-ResNet DS	0.578 ± 0.009	0.585 ± 0.015
CP-ResNet + BEATs	0.593 ± 0.003	0.596 ± 0.002
BEATs + CP-ResNet + CP-ResNet DS	0.598 ± 0.003	0.603 ± 0.007

Table 5: Macro average accuracy of the CP-Mobile student trained with the given teacher combination, as described in Section 4.3 (mean±std). DS symbolizes a device-specific teacher.

Fig. 3: Macro-average accuracy of the CP-Mobile student trained with the given teacher combination, as described in Section 4.3. DS symbolizes a device-specific teacher. The error bars show the standard deviation.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented a comprehensive approach for low-complexity Acoustic Scene Classification with the constraints for DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 1 Furthermore, we conducted an ablation study that reveals the significance of DIR, pretraining on the CochScene dataset, and per-device fine-tuning. We conclude that the efficiency of applying DIR augmentation and CochScene pre-training varied by model architecture. We also showed how device-specific teachers can improve the students performance during knowledge distillation. Using these methods we achieved a macro-averaged accuracy of 60.3% on the systems on the TAU Urban Acoustic Scenes 2022 Mobile dataset validation set—an 8.41 percentage point improvement over the baseline.

In the challenge setting, the best-performing model from multiple runs was selected. This accounts for the slight difference of 0.2% between the 60.5% achieved in the challenge³ and the results reported in the experiments above.

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³<https://dcase.community/challenge2025/task-low-complexity-acoustic-scene-classification-with-device-information-results>

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Perceptual Detection of Packet Loss-Induced Audio Artifacts in Black-Box Wireless Music Systems

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Abstract—Audible degradations introduced by wireless audio transmission, such as clicks, dropouts, and glitches, can significantly compromise the perceived quality of music. These artifacts are typically caused by packet loss and often occur as short, perceptually salient events. In this work, we approach their detection as a binary sound event classification task based solely on perceptual analysis of the audio signal. The study focuses on black-box scenarios, where only the resulting audio is available for analysis, without any access to packet-level metadata, network diagnostics, or internal system information. We introduce BlueData, a dataset of music recordings labeled as clean or degraded. Degradation labels were assigned through listening tests under controlled Bluetooth transmission impairments, reflecting the presence of perceptual artifacts. A range of classical machine learning classifiers were trained using handcrafted acoustic features. Among them, models such as XGBoost and CatBoost achieved AUC scores close to 0.97, while K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) reached the highest recall for the degraded class, with 85.09%. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of lightweight and interpretable models in identifying transmission-induced perceptual degradations directly from the audio signal and position BlueData as a relevant dataset for research in perceptual quality monitoring under black-box conditions.

Index Terms—Black-box audio analysis, packet loss artifacts, perceptual audio degradation, sound event classification.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound event classification (SEC) is a fundamental task in signal processing, supporting applications such as environmental monitoring, speech recognition, and music information retrieval [1], [2]. Within the field of acoustic scenes and events, detection and classification tasks focus on identifying and categorizing distinct sound events in complex auditory environments [3], [4]. A sound event is typically defined as a segment of audio associated with a distinctive concept [5]. Traditional SEC tasks target structured events such as speech utterances, alarms, or instrument sounds [6], while recent studies have expanded this scope to include anomalous or transient acoustic phenomena [7].

In wireless audio transmission, degradations such as packet loss can introduce audible artifacts such as clicks, dropouts, and distortions, which, although brief, are perceptually disruptive [8]. These artifacts degrade the quality of speech or music [9] and present detection challenges due to their varying spectral and temporal characteristics. Analyzing such perceptual degradations is especially relevant in scenarios where only the final audio output is available. In these cases, internal metadata about the transmission or packet handling is inaccessible, and all quality judgments must be made solely based on the resulting audio signal.

This challenge is significant in audio quality assurance (QA) workflows for mobile and embedded systems, where human testers often rely on subjective listening to identify degradations [10]. Automating this perceptual evaluation process can reduce subjectivity, improve scalability, and enable continuous monitoring in real-world applications. By framing the detection of audible artifacts as a sound event classification problem, we aim to provide a signal-based, interpretable solution for analyzing audio integrity

in black-box conditions, where only the audio signal is available to the end user.

To support this investigation, we introduce BlueData [11], a dataset of music recordings labeled as clean or degraded, based on perceptual annotation. The audio was recorded under controlled Bluetooth transmission with induced packet loss, simulating realistic degradation scenarios. BlueData is already publicly available to support reproducibility and further research. We benchmark several classical machine learning classifiers using handcrafted acoustic features to assess their effectiveness in identifying perceptual degradations as sound events.

2. RELATED WORK

SEC for anomaly detection has received considerable attention in recent years, particularly in scenarios involving machinery faults, urban environments, and industrial monitoring [12], [13], [14]. One of the key challenges in this domain is the creation of representative datasets, as capturing and annotating transient acoustic events depends heavily on the context and the nature of the sound source. In the audio domain, [15] proposed a dataset for the classification of audio artifacts such as “clicks” and “glitches” within .mp3 files. Their approach involves artificially inserting transient faults to simulate digital degradation. Similarly, the MIMII dataset [16] targets anomaly detection in industrial equipment sounds, including valves, fans, and pumps, providing normal and faulty audio samples for benchmarking.

For general-purpose sound event recognition, [17] developed an open dataset covering a variety of real-world sounds. Although not focused on music, it provides a useful benchmark for training and evaluating SEC models. These datasets, however, are not designed to capture perceptual audio degradations caused by transmission errors, such as those observed in wireless music streaming. In terms of methodology, ensemble learning and early-event detection have been explored to improve the efficiency and accuracy of SEC [18], [19]. However, most existing datasets either focus on synthetic noise artifacts or on environmental sounds unrelated to music or perceptual quality issues. Moreover, they do not account for the challenges of detecting signal-level degradations in black-box scenarios, where metadata such as transmission logs is unavailable. To support this investigation, we present BlueData, a dataset focused on perceptual artifacts caused by packet loss during wireless audio transmission. These artifacts appear as short, localized acoustic events that are difficult to characterize, especially in black-box scenarios. The dataset provides a controlled setting for exploring signal-based detection approaches and can serve as a benchmark for evaluating audio classification systems under realistic transmission conditions.

3. DATASET FOR WIRELESS AUDIO TRANSMISSION

To investigate perceptual degradations in wireless audio, we developed BlueData, a dataset comprising two classes: clean and degraded.

Fig. 1: Recording and preprocessing process: (1) Bluetooth audio playback through controlled attenuation; (2) acoustic recording; (3) segmentation and labeling; (4) feature extraction.

The degraded class includes perceptually salient audio events such as clicks, dropouts, and distortions caused by packet loss. These artifact types are not labeled separately, as the focus is on detecting the perceptual presence of degradation rather than categorizing its specific form. Tracks were selected from the Free Music Archive (FMA) [20], covering six musical genres: Rock, Blues, Pop, Hip Hop, Classical, and Electronic, and totaling 10.76 hours of audio. Genre balance in the train/test split was not controlled, as the dataset is intended for perceptual degradation detection rather than genre classification.

3.1. Recording Setup

The recording setup was designed to simulate realistic wireless transmission conditions while maintaining control over induced degradation. Audio playback was streamed via Bluetooth from a mobile phone placed outside an acoustically isolated chamber to a speaker inside. A microphone recorded the audio output from the speaker. To simulate transmission impairments, a Vauxin digital attenuator [21] was introduced in the signal path, allowing remote control of signal strength and inducing controlled levels of packet loss and attenuation. This process generated perceptual artifacts such as dropouts, clicks, and glitches, which are common in unstable Bluetooth connections. The general setup is illustrated in Figure 1.

This procedure enabled the creation of a dataset reflecting perceptual events caused by wireless audio degradation. All audio was stored in WAV format, mono, 44.1 kHz. Tracks were converted from MP3 (typically 192–320 kbps) to WAV to ensure a standardized, uncompressed format for feature extraction, avoiding further quality degradation during preprocessing.

3.2. Segmentation and Annotation

The recordings were segmented into 2-second windows using Librosa. This duration was selected to provide enough temporal context for detecting packet loss artifacts while maintaining temporal precision, consistent with standard SEC practices. While some artifacts may occur over very short intervals, the 2-second window captures their perceptual effect in context, which is crucial for human listeners and perceptual labeling. The full dataset comprises 19,397 labeled segments. For the experiments reported in this work, we used 15,517 labeled segments: 11,760 clean and 3,757 degraded. This natural class imbalance reflects the sporadic nature of transmission-induced artifacts in real-world scenarios. As such, the evaluation emphasizes recall and the F1-score for the degraded class.

Annotation was conducted manually through a two-pass auditory inspection by certified QA testers. Initially, one tester labeled each

segment based on perceptual evaluation. A second tester then reviewed all labels independently. Disagreements were resolved through consensus to ensure labeling consistency. The dataset is publicly available [11]. Full details on file structure and access instructions are provided on the dataset page.

4. ACOUSTIC FEATURE EXTRACTION AND CLASSIFICATION

To classify clean and perceptually degraded audio, we implemented a traditional classification pipeline composed of segmentation, handcrafted feature extraction, model selection, and evaluation via cross-validation. Instead of relying on complex feature learning, we adopted interpretable acoustic descriptors and lightweight models, which are suitable for real-time or resource-constrained environments.

4.1. Data Preprocessing

Each 2-second segment was converted to mono and standardized to a sample rate of 22,050 Hz. We extracted 38 handcrafted features using the Librosa library, including zero-crossing rate, tempo (via beat tracking), 20 mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs), 12 chroma features, spectral centroid, spectral bandwidth, and spectral rolloff. These features were selected for their ability to capture both spectral and temporal characteristics, such as harmonic structure, energy distribution, and rhythmic content.

All features were averaged over time, producing fixed-length 38-dimensional vectors. The vectors were then normalized using z-score standardization (zero mean and unit variance). No filtering or data augmentation was applied, preserving the perceptual integrity of the original segments.

4.2. Classification Models and Parameters

We trained eight classical supervised models, each representing a distinct learning paradigm. All classifiers were implemented using scikit-learn, XGBoost, or CatBoost libraries, and trained with their respective default hyperparameters, unless otherwise required. This decision ensures that comparisons focus on the feature space itself, without introducing biases from hyperparameter tuning.

XGBoost was used with `use_label_encoder=False` and `eval_metric='logloss'` to support binary classification. CatBoost was configured with `verbose=0`. The Random Forest classifier was trained with `n_estimators=100` and `criterion='gini'`. SVM used a radial basis function kernel with `C=1.0` and `gamma='scale'`. K-Nearest Neighbors was configured with `n_neighbors=5` and `weights='uniform'`.

The Decision Tree model used `criterion='gini'`. Gaussian Naive Bayes applied the standard `var_smoothing=1e-9`, and Perceptron used `max_iter=1000` and `eta0=1.0`. All hyperparameter values were confirmed using the `.get_params()` method and are fully reproducible.

4.3. Training and Evaluation

We used 5-fold stratified cross-validation to evaluate model performance. In each fold, 80% of the data was used for training and 20% for validation, ensuring balanced class distribution across splits. This procedure provides robust generalization estimates while minimizing variance from data partitioning.

We computed standard classification metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Accuracy measures overall correctness, precision penalizes false positives, recall emphasizes sensitivity to degradations, and F1-score balances both. We report all metrics, but F1-score was used as the main criterion for comparing classifiers. This evaluation pipeline allows consistent, interpretable comparisons across models, highlighting their effectiveness in detecting audio degradations from handcrafted acoustic features.

5. RESULTS

This section evaluates the detection of perceptual degradations in black-box scenarios using handcrafted features, framing the task as segment-level classification of short, salient audio events. Table 1 presents the average performance of each classifier across all folds. Among the evaluation metrics, both F1-score and recall are considered primary indicators of performance. The F1-score provides a balanced measure by combining precision and recall. However, recall plays a particularly critical role in this context, as it reflects the model’s ability to correctly identify degraded audio segments. Given that the objective of this task is to detect degradation events, achieving a high recall is essential to ensure that as many degraded instances as possible are accurately detected.

The best overall results were achieved by the XGBoost and CatBoost models, both with accuracy values close to 95%. In terms of F1-score, XGBoost slightly outperformed all other models, reaching 92.84%, closely followed by CatBoost (92.67%) and KNN (92.45%). Notably, KNN achieved the highest recall among all models, with 91.37%, making it particularly effective at detecting degraded segments.

Table 1: Overall classification metrics (%) for each model (average across folds).

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
XGBoost	94.99	95.22	90.94	92.84
CatBoost	94.90	95.47	90.51	92.67
RandomForest	93.35	95.44	86.59	90.02
KNN	94.60	93.68	91.37	92.45
SVM	94.27	94.67	89.51	91.73
DecisionTree	88.92	84.73	85.35	85.03
GaussianNB	87.36	83.05	82.03	82.51
Perceptron	85.07	79.73	81.35	80.33

To better understand the behavior of the models regarding different audio conditions, Figure 2 shows the F1-score per class (clean and degraded) for each classifier. Analyzing the F1 score by class is essential because general metrics can obscure performance discrepancies, especially when there is a class imbalance or when one class is more challenging to detect. This is particularly important

in scenarios involving an audible artifact, where degraded audio can significantly impact classification accuracy.

The results show that XGBoost and CatBoost maintain strong performance in both conditions, with F1-scores greater than 96, 70% for the clean class and greater than 88% for the degraded class. Furthermore, KNN also performs well, achieving 96.48% for clean audio and 88.41% for degraded audio. These results highlight the importance of evaluating each class individually to identify models that are robust to audio degradations and capable of preserving classification performance under adverse conditions.

Fig. 2: Comparison of F1-scores for clean and degraded classes across classification models.

On the other hand, traditional classifiers such as Decision Tree, GaussianNB, and Perceptron exhibited a larger performance drop in the degraded class, with F1-scores below 75%, highlighting their reduced capability to generalize under noisy conditions. In the context of this task, recall plays a critical role, as it measures the model’s ability to correctly identify degraded audio segments. Since the main objective is to detect subtle acoustic events associated with perceptual degradation, a high recall for the degraded class is important to minimize undetected faulty segments, which may compromise system reliability. Precision, on the other hand, measures how often the positive predictions made by the model are correct. A high precision for the clean class indicates that the model rarely misclassifies degraded segments as clean. In this context, however, the main objective is to capture as many degraded instances as possible. Thus, recall for the degraded class becomes an important aspect to consider in the overall evaluation. Figure 3 presents the recall obtained for each class across all evaluated models.

Figure 3 illustrates the recall scores for both clean and degraded classes across all evaluated classifiers. The results highlight the KNN model as the most effective in identifying degraded segments, achieving the highest recall for the degraded class with 85.09%. This demonstrates that KNN was the most sensitive model in detecting audio artifacts caused by packet loss, which is essential for ensuring system reliability.

Although boosting-based models such as XGBoost and CatBoost also performed well in terms of overall metrics and recall, their degraded-class recall was slightly lower than that of KNN, with values of 83.10% and 81.98%, respectively. This suggests that while boosting methods offer strong overall performance, KNN was the most effective specifically in capturing degraded segments.

On the other hand, Gaussian Naive Bayes exhibited the lowest recall for the degraded class, at 71.71%, indicating that a consider-

Fig. 3: Comparison of recall scores for clean and degraded classes across classification models, sorted by degraded class performance.

able number of degraded segments were not identified by the model. Despite its acceptable recall for the clean class, the tendency of the model to misclassify degraded segments limits its reliability in practical scenarios where the detection of faulty audio is critical. Figure 4 presents the confusion matrix of the KNN model, enabling a detailed evaluation of its classification performance, particularly regarding true positives and false negatives.

Fig. 4: Confusion matrix of the KNN model averaged across cross-validation folds.

The confusion matrix further confirms that KNN correctly classified most degraded segments, with a relatively low number of false negatives (i.e., degraded segments predicted as clean). This behavior aligns with its high recall score and reinforces its applicability in scenarios that require reliable detection of audio degradation. Nevertheless, despite the overall strong performance, the results indicate that certain degraded instances remain challenging to classify. Future work should investigate more specialized or ensemble-based classifiers capable of improving discrimination in borderline cases of degradation.

While the confusion matrix provides a detailed view of model behavior in terms of classification errors, it offers limited insight into model performance across varying thresholds. To address this, we present in Figure 5 the ROC curves, which capture the trade-off between true positive and false positive rates and offer a threshold-independent view of classifier performance.

The ROC analysis confirms that traditional machine learning models, when combined with handcrafted acoustic features, can effectively distinguish between clean and degraded audio in wireless transmission. The degraded class was defined as the positive class, so the true positive rate reflects correctly identified degradations, and the false positive rate corresponds to clean segments misclassified as degraded. Boosting-based classifiers such as XGBoost and CatBoost

Fig. 5: ROC curve for the evaluated classifiers.

achieved the highest AUC values (both ≈ 0.97), demonstrating robust performance across decision thresholds, while KNN stood out for its sensitivity to degraded segments. This is supported by the recall results in Figure 3, where KNN achieved the highest recall for the degraded class (85.09%) In contrast, simpler models like DecisionTree and Perceptron showed more limited discrimination capabilities. These results confirm the potential of lightweight models in identifying perceptual degradations caused by packet loss and underscore the reliability of BlueData as a benchmark dataset for training and evaluating models in perceptual audio quality assessment under black-box conditions.

6. CONCLUSION

This study presented a binary sound event detection framework to identify perceptual audio degradations caused by packet loss in wireless music transmission. The task is framed as a classification problem applied to short audio segments, but the degradations exhibit event-like characteristics, as they are short, sparse, and perceptually salient. Our focus lies on black-box scenarios, where no access to transmission metadata or internal system information is possible, and only the resulting audio signal can be analyzed.

We introduced BlueData, a dataset designed to simulate realistic degradation conditions, and benchmarked a set of classical machine learning models trained on handcrafted acoustic features. Models such as K-Nearest Neighbors, XGBoost, and CatBoost demonstrated strong performance, achieving recall scores above 85% for the degraded class. These results confirm the viability of detecting packet loss-induced audio events using traditional classifiers, even without any access to system-level information. This work emphasizes the value of interpretable, low-complexity approaches for sound event detection in constrained environments. Future research will focus on improving feature extraction, refining decision thresholds for monitoring, and integrating the approach into automated wireless audio testing, where minimizing false negatives is critical.

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Supervised detection of baleen whale calls on edge-compute

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Abstract—This paper presents an edge-optimised approach for baleen whale call detection, addressing both the detection requirements of BioDCASE 2025 Task 2 and deployment constraints similar to Task 3. Common machine learning models contain 4+ million training parameters and use architectures unsuitable for real-time edge deployment. In contrast, our model contains just 35,571 parameters (159KB) and operates efficiently on a 64-bit ARM Cortex-A53 with 512MB RAM. We applied an edge-optimised feature extraction pipeline and a custom CNN model architecture designed for real-time inference in offshore deployments. Classifying on 11.8-second detection windows, our precision-focused approach achieves 72% precision for blue whale ABZ calls and 80% for fin whale burst pulse calls, though downsweep detection lags at 18% precision. After applying a temporal head for call-specific identification as per the BioDCASE challenge requirements, ABZ call precision drops to 65% and burst pulse calls to 4%, while downsweep calls improve to 29%. Acknowledging the difficulties in call-specific identification, this work highlights the feasibility and potential of edge-optimised architectures for baleen whale detection in real-world monitoring scenarios where computational resources and power consumption are severely constrained, while addressing common challenges and next steps to improve the results.

Index Terms—baleen call detection, signal processing, temporal attention, edge-computing

1. INTRODUCTION

Our marine environment face significant threats [1], [2], requiring scalable bioacoustics monitoring solutions to assess biodiversity and support conservation. Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) offers a promising non-invasive approach for underwater monitoring but transitioning deep learning (DL) based PAM from research prototypes to operational systems remains challenging, often requiring performance trade-offs through quantization or pruning [3]. Furthermore, current DL approaches often report high accuracies based on biased evaluation protocols that do not consistently account for temporal correlations in acoustic data [4], [5]. By following the guidelines of the BioDCASE 2025 Challenge [6] for the “Supervised Detection of Strongly-Labelled Whale Calls” we aim to reduce this validation bias in real-world deployments and encourage further development.

2. BACKGROUND

Although recent deep learning approaches have shown promising results for automated baleen whale call detection [7]–[11], and traditional spectrogram-based detection methods can achieve low false alarm rates [12], [13], these methods require significant computational resources making them unsuitable for autonomous real-time deployment on memory-constrained devices. Hybrid CNN-LSTM approaches for fin whale detection show that temporal context modelling can improve performance [14], but remain to be benchmarked on edge devices. While specialised systems like DMON/LFDCS [15] have demonstrated successful deployment on autonomous platforms for baleen whale detection, this approach has key limitations - most notably reliance on human expert analysts for final classification decisions and the constraints of data transmission. In contrast compact CNNs can process audio on-board for fully autonomous analysis, allowing for data transmission of just several bytes containing detection information like time, location, and species, rather than large volumes of pitch track data requiring human review.

This work focuses on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) due to their proven success in audio signal processing for animal sounds on edge compute [16]–[18], effectiveness with limited compute and minimal memory footprint [19], and widespread deployment in marine bioacoustic tasks including cetacean detection [7], [9]–[11], [20]–[23]. While recurrent architectures (RNNs/CRNNs) have shown promise in bioacoustics [23], they require more computational resources for training and inference, with [23] observing that temporal CNNs often match or exceed RNN performance while being faster to train. Similarly, although transformer architectures show emerging potential with [24], [25] demonstrating early bioacoustic applications, they remained computationally prohibitive for edge deployment until very recently [26], with advances like EasyViT [27] only now making them feasible for resource-constrained devices.

For this initial edge-optimised implementation targeting immediate deployment on devices like the Raspberry Pi Zero 2 W, CNNs provide the optimal balance of proven performance, computational efficiency, and implementation maturity, with exploration of emerging architectures reserved for future iterations once the baseline system is established. This report presents a development pathway for addressing common challenges: an edge-optimised temporal attention network designed specifically for deployment on tiny low-cost hardware platforms. This network uses an attention mechanism to assign importance to key features in an audio signal, helping the network focus on relevant sounds for call-specific detection, while achieving a balance between detection performance and computational efficiency and laying out clear next steps for development.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Dataset and Preprocessing

The BioDCASE benchmark builds on the baleen whale call dataset containing 1,880 hours of recordings with expert annotations for Antarctic blue whale ABZ calls (bmabz), fin whale burst pulses (bp), and fin/blue whale downsweep calls (d) [28]. Following the challenge protocol, we maintained strict temporal separation between training and validation sets to prevent data leakage. Applying a sliding windowing approach of 11.8s windows (theorising the necessity of longer windows for transient whale sounds and burst calls) with 50% overlap, and undersampling of the heavily over-represented background down to 60% in the training set, we obtained 473,620 training windows and 351,374 validation windows. The overall class distribution is presented in Table 1. We designed the model as a multi-class labelling problem with a confidence score for the presence of each class per window.

Table 1: Class Distribution

Class	Train	Val
Background	362,944	312,730
Blue Whale ABZ (bmabz)	64,846	28,931
Fin Whale Pulse (bp)	26,677	6,301
Fin/Blue Downsweep (d)	31,615	5,581
Total	473,620	351,374

Fig. 1: CNN Feature stack for blue and fin whale calls on a 48-second audio snippet. Example shows a blue whale ABZ call [28]. In production these are 11.8-second windows.

Fig. 2: Threshold analysis approach demonstrated in the blue whale ABZ call class on the evaluation set. "Optimal F1" is maximised F1, the arrow highlights our selected threshold of 0.6 for optimised precision.

Our preprocessing pipeline extracts three-channel acoustic features (Fig. 1) optimised for low-frequency whale vocalisations (5-125Hz range): log-power spectrograms with 250Hz sampling rate, first-order derivatives, and computationally efficient wavelet coefficients processing only approximation and first-level detail coefficients. This adapted wavelet feature was inspired by works that previously presented the effectiveness of wavelet features in identifying low frequency whale calls [8], [29]. Channel-wise normalisation parameters were computed from the training set to ensure consistent scaling across diverse recording conditions. Table 2 details the complete processing pipeline to transform the raw acoustic recordings into standardised sensors suitable for deep learning inference on edge hardware.

3.2. Model Architecture

The proposed network employs a lightweight CNN backbone with six convolutional layers, utilising separable convolutions to reduce computational complexity. A detailed diagram of the network architecture is available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17122226>.

Fig. 3: Weighted F1-Macro learning curve on the classification head across the detection of background noise, blue whale ABZ, fin whale pulse calls, and fin/blue whale downsweep calls

Key architectural features include:

- A multi-class label classification head for per-window predictions
- Asymmetric max-pooling to reduce the frequency dimension while preserving full temporal resolution for precise event localisation
- Multi-scale temporal processing via parallel dilated convolutions to capture patterns across different time scales
- A lightweight temporal attention mechanism to weigh and aggregate features across 60 time steps
- Batch normalisation throughout for training stability
- Focal loss optimisation addressing severe class imbalance
- Cyclical learning rate scheduling for improved convergence

The model contains only 35,571 training parameters and is just 159KB in size, representing a 95-99% size reduction compared to standard and edge-optimised CNNs [30], enabling deployment on remote memory-constrained devices using Tensorflow Lite (TFLite).

3.3. Thresholding

Performance evaluation followed a precision-focused approach, recognising that in ocean sustainability and conservation false positives often incur higher costs than false negatives. We therefore implemented class-specific detection thresholds optimised for precision on the classification head. An example of this approach is presented in Fig. 2. Considering the multi-class problem, the background class is only activated when no other classes reach the threshold.

3.4. Weighted monitoring metric

For the early stopping mechanism, we employed a weighted F1 macro metric for a weighted precision-recall rating favouring precision at 70% over 30% (Fig. 3).

The weighted F1 score for each class i is computed as shown in (1),

$$F_{1,w}^{(i)} = \frac{(w_p + w_r) \cdot P^{(i)} \cdot R^{(i)}}{w_p \cdot R^{(i)} + w_r \cdot P^{(i)} + \epsilon}, \quad (1)$$

where $P^{(i)}$ and $R^{(i)}$ are the precision and recall for class i , respectively, w_p is the precision weight, $w_r = 1 - w_p$ is the recall weight, and $\epsilon = 10^{-8}$ is a small constant to prevent division by zero. The precision and recall are calculated using the standard definitions in (2),

$$P^{(i)} = \frac{TP^{(i)}}{TP^{(i)} + FP^{(i)} + \epsilon}, \quad R^{(i)} = \frac{TP^{(i)}}{TP^{(i)} + FN^{(i)} + \epsilon}, \quad (2)$$

Table 2: Feature Extraction Pipeline for Blue and Fin Whale Detection. F = frequency bins (513), T = time frames per window (60), Output tensor dimensions: $(513 \times 60 \times 3)$ per analysis window. Processing optimised for 5-125Hz whale vocalisations on edge hardware with under 40k training parameters CNN models.

Processing Stage	Parameter	Implementation Details	Output
Signal Preprocessing	Resampling Bandpass Filter	Target sampling rate: 250Hz using librosa resample 4th-order Butterworth filter, 5-125Hz cutoff frequencies	250Hz audio Filtered signal
Spectrogram Generation	Window Function	2.0s Hann window (500 samples at 250Hz)	STFT frames
	Hop Length	0.2s hop (50 samples, 90% overlap)	Time resolution
	FFT Size	1024-point FFT providing 0.244Hz frequency resolution	513 freq bins
Spectral Enhancement	Power Conversion	Log-power: $S_{dB} = 10 \log_{10}(STFT ^2) - \max(S_{dB})$	dB spectrogram
	Background Subtraction Contrast Enhancement	Time-averaged profile with 15-sample Gaussian smoothing 5-120Hz whale frequency band	Enhanced signal Band-enhanced
Normalisation	Percentile Scaling	Map 5th-95th percentile to [-20, +20] dB range	Standardised
Multi-Channel Features	Channel 1	Log-power spectrogram	$(F \times T)$
	Channel 2	First-order frequency derivatives with safety checks	$(F \times T)$
	Channel 3	Daubechies-4 wavelet (3 levels, approx + detail coeffs)	$(F \times T)$
Temporal Windowing	Window Size	60 frames (11.8s at 0.2s hop)	Feature windows
	Overlap	30 frames (50% overlap between windows)	Sliding windows
Final Standardisation	Channel-wise Norm	Training-set calculated mean/std applied to all data splits	$(F \times T \times 3)$

where $TP^{(i)}$, $FP^{(i)}$, and $FN^{(i)}$ represent the true positives, false positives, and false negatives for class i , respectively. The final monitoring metric is the macro-averaged weighted F1 score across all classes as given in (3),

$$F_{1,weighted-macro} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i=1}^C F_{1,w}^{(i)}, \quad (3)$$

where C is the total number of classes. In our experiments, we used a precision weight of $w_p = 0.7$ to emphasise precision over recall in the early stopping criterion.

3.5. Post Processing of the Temporal Head

The temporal head processes attention weights generated by the Temporal Attention Layer (see also the architecture diagram in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17122226>). This layer produces time-step-specific attention scores across the 60 temporal frames (11.8-second window), where each score indicates the model’s focus on potential whale call events at that time point. These attention weights form a temporal attention map that highlight regions of acoustic significance, which we then process to extract precise call boundaries. Class-specific processing parameters were derived from statistical analysis of the training set (Table 3).

The temporal processing pipeline applies class-specific attention weight smoothing using median filters (kernel sizes: $mbabz=5$, $bp=1$, $d=1$), followed by adaptive thresholding based on attention statistics. High-attention regions exceeding $\mu + \alpha\sigma$ (where $\alpha \in [0.05, 0.08, 0.1]$ for ‘bp’, ‘d’, ‘mbabz’) are identified as potential call boundaries. Duration constraints derived from 5th and 95th percentiles filter detected events: $mbabz$ (4.69-13.62s), bp (0.92-1.93s), and d (0.83-4.40s).

Post-processing applies class-specific merging of nearby events (max gaps: $mbabz=8.0s$, $bp=1.0s$, $d=1.5s$), overlap-based deduplication (thresholds: 0.2-0.3), and confidence filtering to produce final temporal boundaries. Events are ranked by a composite score combining classification confidence (40%), peak attention (40%), and duration bonus (20%) when resolving overlapping detections.

3.6. Computational Performance

Training was done on 4 NVIDIA A100 GPUs with distributed data-parallel processing and XLA, completing in 10 hours for the 474K training windows. Processing occurred with sharded TFRecord files across 16 parallel workers. Implementation includes deterministic data shuffling, fixed random seeds, and a batch size of 128.

To evaluate the feasibility of real-time, on-device deployment, the model’s computational performance was benchmarked on a resource-constrained edge device: a Raspberry Pi Zero 2 W which features a 64-bit ARM Cortex-A53 CPU and 512 MB of RAM. The performance was measured across five 60-second audio files with varied whale call patterns, with multiple trials ensuring stable results. The system demonstrates exceptional efficiency, achieving a mean real-time factor (RTF) of 24.5 \times , indicating it can process audio over 24 times faster than it is recorded. The complete end-to-end processing of a 60-second audio clip takes, on average, just 2.45 seconds. The compressed TFLite model has a minimal disk footprint of only 159KB. The inference latency for a single 11.8-second analysis window is 187.42 ± 1.07 ms. The temporal post-processing adds negligible overhead. The peak memory footprint of the application during runtime was 213.1 MB, well within the device’s operational limits. These results confirm the model’s suitability for long-term, low-power, and real-time acoustic monitoring applications. Key performance metrics are summarised in Table 4.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bearing in mind the computational constraints and potential of the edge-optimised architecture, we present both the per-window analysis and the evaluation following the BioDCASE benchmark.

Fig. 4: Performance metrics per class in the classification head.

Starting with per-window analysis from the classification head, Fig. 4, we achieve a precision of 72% for the blue whale ABZ call and 80% for the fin whale burst calls, but poor precision of 18% on downswEEP - reflective of previous reports on the challenges of

Table 3: Training set duration statistics (seconds) for merged annotation classes used to derive class-specific temporal processing parameters.

Class	Count	Mean	Std	Median	Min	Max	P5	P10	P25	P75	P90	P95	IQR	CV
bmabz	9463	7.95	2.76	7.36	1.29	36.62	4.69	5.23	6.14	9.09	11.60	13.62	2.95	0.35
bp	5308	1.39	0.31	1.38	0.46	2.82	0.92	1.01	1.20	1.60	1.82	1.93	0.40	0.22
d	2856	2.44	1.11	2.41	0.37	7.36	0.83	0.98	1.56	3.19	3.93	4.40	1.63	0.46

Table 4: Detailed performance breakdown of the whale call detection system on Raspberry Pi Zero 2 W.

Component	Metric	Value
Model	Size (MB)	0.15
	Input shape	[1, 513, 60, 3]
Inference	Latency per window (ms)	187.42 ± 1.07
	95th percentile (ms)	189.21
	Real-time factor (RTF)	24.5×
Temporal Processing	Latency per window (ms)	0.79 ± 0.17
	Overhead vs inference	0.4%
Resource Usage	Peak memory (MB)	213.1
	Peak CPU (%)	155.6

Table 5: Detection performance results as per the BioDCASE evaluation across datasets for different classes (bmabz, bp, d).

Dataset	Method	TP	FP	FN	Recall	Precision
casey2017	bmabz	676	446	1742	0.280	0.602
	bp	0	13	292	0.000	0.000
	d	77	339	476	0.139	0.185
kerguelen2014	bmabz	473	154	3824	0.110	0.754
	bp	4	56	3742	0.001	0.067
	d	70	138	709	0.090	0.337
kerguelen2015	bmabz	329	215	2419	0.120	0.605
	bp	1	39	1269	0.001	0.025
	d	126	181	1398	0.083	0.410
Final Results	bmabz	1478	815	7985	0.156	0.645
	bp	5	108	5303	0.001	0.044
	d	273	658	2583	0.096	0.293

labelling and predicting this class [7]. Recall rates vary between 31%, 41% and 54% for downsweep, ABZ, and burst pulse calls respectively.

The results of ‘evaluation.py’ provided by the BioDCASE benchmark are presented in Table 5. There is a noticeable drop in performance, which was somewhat expected given the minimal temporal head restricted to edge limitations. Nevertheless, 65% precision for ‘bmabz’ is promising for a model with just 35K training parameters. The temporal processing pipeline may benefit from further tuning to enhance both precision and recall for this class.

The significant drop in precision for the burst pulse calls was unanticipated given its high performance in the classification head. It seems that the 11.8-second window approach is fundamentally mismatched to the 1.39-second average calls. Despite custom class tuning, the temporal attention mechanism lacks the resolution needed for short events within the 11.8-second windows. Downsweep calls being longer interestingly achieved higher precision than both temporal burst pulse calls and the ‘d’ classification head at 29%, but recall is low.

Given the considerable characteristic differences between the targeted events both in the time and frequency domain and the extremely efficient processing pipeline, future endeavours might seek to build custom per-class inference models with feature extraction tailored specifically for each individual class. Three models could run sequentially in real-time, and still run smoothly on tiny microcontrollers such as the one used in this experiment (Raspberry Pi Zero 2 W, 512MB RAM). Such class-specific pipelines could significantly enhance temporal call-specific detection accuracy.

We aimed to develop a lightweight solution to detect whale presence in real-time on edge. Considering PAM of baleen whales for real-time applications such as adapting shipping routes based on mammal presence, we argue that the windowing approach in the classification

head would be sufficient and perhaps preferable over individual call detection when deployed on edge devices. The impact of inconsistent labelling is reduced since the classification simply determines whether a class is present or absent within a given window, which is sufficient to support policy decisions. Additionally, once the data is retrieved, high-performance computing (HPC) analysis can be performed on land to refine the predictions. Statistical inference of call presence could be adjusted for known precision and recall errors, though hydrophone hardware and environmental differences must be taken into account. In production, the classification head could serve as an initial detection stage, while the temporal head attempts to locate exact call boundaries when required.

While the margin of 24.5× exceeds the strict requirement of real-time operation, this computational headroom ensures robust operation when edge devices must simultaneously handle data processing and transmission across potentially parallel models - realistic scenarios for autonomous ocean monitoring. The presented architecture offers scalability and flexibility in development paths: vertical scaling through deeper networks and expanded channels could improve accuracy at moderate computational costs, while horizontal scaling via class-specific pipeline appears promising given the distinct characteristics of each call type. Initial experiments with GRU layers showed potential for improved temporal modelling but required custom TensorFlow Lite operators for edge compression, this remains a route to explore. Future work will explore lightweight vision transformers as they mature for edge applications, layer normalisation and cosine learning rate schedulers for training stability, and systematic benchmarking to identify optimal accuracy-efficiency trade-offs.

It has to be noted that all validation datasets are recorded with the ‘AAD-MAR’ hydrophone. As there can be considerable differences in acoustic data recorded with different hardware, performance on hydrophones outside of this domain remains to be addressed. For example, only 12% of the training data was recorded with ‘AAD-MAR’, whereas 77% of the training data was recorded with ‘AURAL’. Given that the vast majority of training data comes from a single hydrophone type, the model may perform better on hardware within this domain (AURAL). Additionally, hydrophone calibration across hardware and environments must be considered for production.

5. CONCLUSION

This work demonstrates the feasibility of edge-optimised deep learning for baleen whale detection, achieving competitive performance on the classification head with just 35K parameters. The proposed model is suitable for edge compute and real-time detection. While temporal localisation remains challenging, particularly for short burst pulse calls, the classification head provides reliable presence detection suitable for real-time conservation applications. Future work should explore class-specific models, model scaling, and cross-hydrophone generalisation to improve deployment robustness.

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On Temporal Guidance and Iterative Refinement in Audio Source Separation

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Abstract—Spatial semantic segmentation of sound scenes (S5) involves the accurate identification of active sound classes and the precise separation of their sources from complex acoustic mixtures. Conventional systems rely on a two-stage pipeline—audio tagging followed by label-conditioned source separation—but are often constrained by the absence of fine-grained temporal information critical for effective separation. In this work, we address this limitation by introducing a novel approach for S5 that enhances the synergy between the event detection and source separation stages. Our key contributions are threefold. First, we fine-tune a pre-trained Transformer to detect active sound classes. Second, we utilize a separate instance of this fine-tuned Transformer to perform sound event detection (SED), providing the separation module with detailed, time-varying guidance. Third, we implement an iterative refinement mechanism that progressively enhances separation quality by recursively reusing the separator’s output from previous iterations. These advancements lead to significant improvements in both audio tagging and source separation performance, as demonstrated by our system’s second-place finish in Task 4 of the DCASE Challenge 2025. Our implementation and model checkpoints are available in our GitHub repository¹.

Index Terms—DCASE Challenge, Audio Source Separation, M2D, ResUNet, AudioSep, Time-FiLM, Iterative Refinement, DPRNN

1. INTRODUCTION

Spatial semantic segmentation of sound scenes (S5) aims to identify and isolate individual sound sources from complex acoustic mixtures. To achieve this, S5 systems typically operate in two stages. In the first stage, a clip-level event detector identifies the set of sound events present in the mixture. In the second stage, a separator model takes the mixture and one of the predicted class labels as input, and estimates the corresponding isolated source for that class.

For Task 4 of the DCASE 2025 Challenge [1], participants were tasked with training such a system for 18 predefined sound categories, including speech and various domestic sound events. The challenge baseline system [2] employs an M2D-based audio tagger [3] to identify the active sound classes in the mixture (Stage 1), and subsequently separates them using a model based on the ResUNet architecture [4], conditioned on the target class via feature-wise linear modulation (FiLM) [5] (Stage 2).

In our submission to Task 4 of the DCASE 2025 Challenge [6], we enhance the baseline system with several key improvements. This paper presents our system (Figure 1) and evaluates the impact of our design choices, focusing on the following core areas:

- **Sound Event Detection (Stage 1):** We fine-tune a pre-trained SED Transformer [7], based on the M2D architecture [3], [8], using both clip-level and frame-level annotations for the 18 target classes. At inference time, we use attention-pooled frame-wise predictions to identify active acoustic events in a given mixture.
- **Temporal Guidance for Source Separation (Stage 2):** A trainable copy of the Stage 1 SED model is integrated into

the separator to provide temporal guidance. It aids separation by: (1) supplying frame-wise class predictions for enhanced FiLM conditioning (*Time-FiLM*); and (2) injecting a weighted sum of its hidden features into the ResUNet, adding temporally aligned semantics (*Embedding Injection*).

- **Dual-Path RNN Integration:** To better capture long-range temporal dependencies, we augment the ResUNet’s embedding space with a Dual-Path RNN [9], enabling more effective context modeling across time.
- **Iterative Refinement:** Inspired by recent iterative separation strategies [10], we apply a simple yet effective refinement technique: the separator’s outputs are recursively fed back into the model, progressively improving the separation quality.

Section 2 provides a brief formalization of the problem. In Sections 3 and 4, we describe our modifications to the event detection and separation stages, respectively. Section 5 outlines the experimental setup, and Section 6 presents the results of our investigation into the effectiveness of the proposed enhancements. Finally, Section 7 concludes this paper.

2. PROBLEM FORMALIZATION

The goal of the S5 task is to detect and separate individual sound events from multi-channel time-domain mixtures recorded in realistic environments. Let

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{(M)}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times T}$$

be the multi-channel mixture of length T , recorded with M microphones. Each channel $\mathbf{x}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^T$ is modeled as:

$$\mathbf{x}^{(m)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{h}_k^{(m)} * \mathbf{s}_k + \sum_{j=1}^J \mathbf{h}_j^{(m)} * \mathbf{s}_j + \mathbf{n}^{(m)} \quad (1)$$

where $*$ denotes the convolution operator, K is the number of active target sound sources, and J is the number of interference events. The terms $\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{s}_j \in \mathbb{R}^T$ represent the single-channel dry source signals for a target event of class c_k and an interference event of class c_j , respectively. Similarly, $\mathbf{h}_k^{(m)}, \mathbf{h}_j^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^H$ are the room impulse responses (RIRs) from the target source k and interfering source j to microphone m , respectively, where H denotes the RIR length. Finally, $\mathbf{n}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^T$ represents additive noise on the m -th microphone channel.

The objective is to estimate the active target classes c_k and recover their direct-path waveforms $\{\mathbf{s}_1^{(d,m)}, \dots, \mathbf{s}_K^{(d,m)}\}$ for a chosen reference microphone channel m , where

$$\mathbf{s}_k^{(d,m)} = \mathbf{h}_k^{(d,m)} * \mathbf{s}_k \quad (2)$$

is the anechoic source \mathbf{s}_k convolved with the direct-path RIR $\mathbf{h}_k^{(d,m)}$, corresponding to the direct arrival sound without reverberation.

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¹<https://github.com/theMoro/dcase25task4>

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed two-stage audio source separation system. Stage 1 uses a sound event detection (SED) model to identify active sound classes in the mixture. Stage 2 performs class-conditioned source separation using a ResUNet architecture enhanced with temporal conditioning (Time-FiLM), Embedding Injection from the dedicated Stage 2 SED model, and an optional Dual-Path RNN. An iterative refinement mechanism allows the separator to progressively improve output quality by reusing previous predictions as an additional input.

For our purposes, $h_k^{(d,m)}$ is approximated from the full RIR $h_k^{(m)}$ by applying a time-domain window around the first significant energy peak, using a window spanning 6 ms before and 50 ms after the peak.

3. ACTIVE EVENT DETECTION

Stage 1 relies on an audio classifier to estimate the presence or absence of the C target acoustic events at the clip level. Unlike the baseline system, which employs a standard audio tagger, we use a sound event detection (SED) model that predicts class activity at the frame level. These predictions are then aggregated into clip-level class scores via attention pooling. This design choice is motivated by two key factors: (1) we hypothesize that frame-level supervision offers more informative training signals, potentially improving tagging accuracy, and (2) the resulting SED model can be integrated into the separator in Stage 2 to provide temporal conditioning.

For training the SED model, we use only the first channel of the multi-channel mixture, denoted $x^{(1)}$, and convert it into a mel-spectrogram:

$$\{\mathbf{y}_t\}_{t=1}^T = \text{MEL}(x^{(1)}), \quad \mathbf{y}_t \in \mathbb{R}^F,$$

where T is the number of time frames and F is the number of mel frequency bins. The model, denoted by a function g , processes this input and produces a sequence of embedding vectors:

$$\{\hat{\mathbf{e}}_s\}_{s=1}^S = g(\{\mathbf{y}_t\}_{t=1}^T), \quad \hat{\mathbf{e}}_s \in \mathbb{R}^D, \quad (3)$$

where D is the embedding dimension, and S is the output sequence length. Note that S may differ from T due to subsampling within the model architecture.

Next, frame-level (strong) class prediction probabilities are computed using a linear layer followed by a sigmoid activation:

$$\{\hat{\mathbf{o}}_s^{(\text{strong})}\}_{s=1}^S = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_h \{\hat{\mathbf{e}}_s\}_{s=1}^S + \mathbf{b}_h), \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_h \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times D}$ and $\mathbf{b}_h \in \mathbb{R}^C$ are the learnable weight matrix and bias vector of the output layer, and σ is the element-wise sigmoid function. To obtain clip-level (weak) predictions $\hat{\mathbf{o}}^{(\text{weak})}$ from the frame-level outputs $\{\hat{\mathbf{o}}_s^{(\text{strong})}\}_{s=1}^S$, we compute class-specific attention weights over time. These are generated using a separate attention head:

$$\{\alpha_s\}_{s=1}^S = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{W}_a \{\hat{\mathbf{e}}_s\}_{s=1}^S + \mathbf{b}_a), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_a \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times D}$ and $\mathbf{b}_a \in \mathbb{R}^C$ are the weight matrix and the bias vector of the attention head, and the softmax function is applied

independently for each class across time steps. The final clip-level prediction is then obtained as the attention-weighted average of the strong outputs:

$$\hat{\mathbf{o}}^{(\text{weak})} = \sum_{s=1}^S \alpha_s \cdot \hat{\mathbf{o}}_s^{(\text{strong})}.$$

We train the model using a loss function that combines binary cross-entropy (BCE) losses for both strong and weak labels, balanced by a weighting factor λ :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} = & \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{SC} \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{c=1}^C \text{BCE}(\hat{o}_{s,c}^{(\text{strong})}, y_{s,c}^{(\text{strong})}) \\ & + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \text{BCE}(\hat{o}_c^{(\text{weak})}, y_c^{(\text{weak})}). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In all experiments, we set $\lambda = 0.5$.

4. SOURCE SEPARATION

The second stage employs a modified ResUNet architecture [2], [4], which takes the multi-channel mixture waveform and a target class label as input to produce an estimated single-channel source. The ResUNet operates on magnitude spectrograms and predicts magnitude and phase masks to reconstruct the target's complex spectrogram, which is then inverted to the time domain via the inverse Short-Time Fourier Transform.

4.1. Time-FiLM Conditioning

In addition to standard clip-level conditioning via Feature-wise Linear Modulation (FiLM) [5], we provide finer-grained temporal guidance by integrating a dedicated, trainable SED model—referred to as the Stage 2 SED model—into the separator architecture. We refer to this approach as *Time-FiLM* as it generalizes FiLM [5] by incorporating a temporal dimension. The Stage 2 SED model is initialized with the weights of the fine-tuned model described in Section 3, but is subsequently optimized jointly with the separator.

For a class predicted by the Stage 1 SED model, the corresponding class activity probability map obtained by the Stage 2 SED model is passed through a feedforward network to generate a sequence of embedding vectors. These embeddings are transformed into a sequence of channel-wise scale and shift parameters for each conditioned layer in the ResUNet. To align those sequences with the feature maps, the sequences are linearly interpolated in time. Finally, Time-FiLM

modulation is applied by scaling and shifting the feature maps with their time-aligned scale and shift parameters.

4.2. Embedding Injection

To further enhance separation quality, we inject intermediate representations from the Stage 2 SED model into the ResUNet’s latent space. Inspired by [11], we extract hidden representations after each of the N blocks in the Stage 2 SED model, denoted by $Z_{\text{TF}}^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{C_{\text{TF}} \times F'_{\text{TF}} \times T'_{\text{TF}}}$, and compute a weighted combination using learnable weights:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\exp(w_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \exp(w_j)}, \quad Z_{\text{TF}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i \cdot Z_{\text{TF}}^{(i)}, \quad (7)$$

where w_i are learned scalar parameters. The resulting fused representation Z_{TF} is projected through a linear transformation and then interpolated along both the frequency and time dimensions to match the shape of the ResUNet’s latent features $Z_{\text{RN}} \in \mathbb{R}^{C_{\text{RN}} \times F'_{\text{RN}} \times T'_{\text{RN}}}$. After normalizing both the fused representation and the ResUNet’s latent features, we add them element-wise.

4.3. Dual-Path RNN

To capture long-range dependencies, we integrate a Dual-Path Recurrent Neural Network (DPRNN) [9] into the ResUNet’s embedding space. The DPRNN consists of two blocks, each with two stacked bidirectional GRUs [12]: the first processes along the temporal dimension, the second along the frequency dimension.

4.4. Iterative Refinement

Instead of generating the target source in a single forward pass, we treat separation as an iterative process. At each step, the estimated single-channel output is stacked with the original M -channel mixture to form a new $(M+1)$ -channel input. The ResUNet’s first convolution is adapted for $M+1$ channels, with the extra channel initialized to zeros during the first iteration.

This iterative mechanism allows the separator to refine its predictions over multiple steps. During training, the number of iterations is randomly sampled between 1 and a predefined maximum. To reduce the memory footprint during training, gradients are detached between iterations and only the final step contributes to parameter updates.

5. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This section details the experimental setup, including the dataset, evaluation metric, model configurations, and the design used to assess our key contributions.

5.1. Dataset

Training and validation use the DCASE 2025 Task 4 (S5) development set, with 4-channel 10-second mixtures synthesized on-the-fly at 32kHz using a modified SpatialScaper library [13]. Training data is randomly sampled, while validation mixtures are generated deterministically. Each mixture combines the following four components:

- **Target sound events s_k** : Anechoic recordings from 18 target classes (e.g., *AlarmClock*, *FootStep*, *Speech*) are used, mainly from FSD50K [14] and EARS [15], with additional data from NTT. The training set includes 7,336 samples (33–2,063 per class), and the validation set has 317 samples (1–37 per class), showing significant class imbalance.
- **Interference events s_j** : We utilize isolated recordings of 94 non-target classes from the Semantic Hearing dataset [16]. This set includes 6,184 training and 845 validation samples, displaying class distribution imbalance similar to the target sound events.
- **Room impulse responses h** : For acoustic environment simulations we employ multichannel RIRs captured from various real

indoor locations. Our setup incorporates 5 RIRs for training and 3 for validation. The recordings are partially sourced from the FOA-MEIR dataset [17], with additional samples newly recorded by NTT.

- **Ambient noise n** : We include real-world background noise recordings obtained from the FOA-MEIR dataset [17]. The noise dataset contains 59 training and 21 validation samples.

This synthetic setup also provides precise event onsets and offsets, which are required for training the SED models (see Section 3). For testing, we use the pre-synthesized mixtures provided by the DCASE challenge organizers. For all sets, each mixture contains between one and three target events and up to two interfering events. The target events have per-event Signal-to-Noise Ratios (SNRs) ranging from 5 to 10 dB, while interfering events have SNRs between 0 and 15 dB.

5.2. Evaluation Metric

We evaluate our system using Class-Aware Signal-to-Distortion Ratio improvement (CA-SDRi) [2], a metric that jointly measures source separation quality and classification accuracy. Let C be the set of ground truth classes and \hat{C} the set of predicted classes. For correctly predicted classes $c_k \in C \cap \hat{C}$, we compute the SDR improvement between the estimated signal \hat{s}_k and the corresponding target source relative to the mixture’s first channel $x^{(1)}$. For simplicity, we denote the target direct-path signal $s_k^{(d,m)}$ as s_k in the following equations.

$$\text{SDRi}(\hat{s}_k, s_k, x^{(1)}) = \text{SDR}(\hat{s}_k, s_k) - \text{SDR}(x^{(1)}, s_k) \quad (8)$$

with SDR defined as:

$$\text{SDR}(\hat{x}, x) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{|\mathbf{x}|^2}{|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}|^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

The final CA-SDRi score is computed by averaging over all unique classes in $C \cup \hat{C}$:

$$\text{CA-SDRi} = \frac{1}{|C \cup \hat{C}|} \sum_{c_k \in C \cup \hat{C}} P_{c_k}, \quad (10)$$

where $P_{c_k} = \text{SDRi}(\hat{s}_k, s_k, x^{(1)})$ if $c_k \in C \cap \hat{C}$, and $P_{c_k} = 0$ otherwise.

5.3. Class Detection Model

The model used for detecting active acoustic events is based on the M2D architecture [3], [8], pre-trained for audio tagging on AudioSet [18]. We use a checkpoint further fine-tuned for sound event detection (SED) on temporally strong labels from AudioSet Strong [19], following the procedure in [7]. This model is chosen for its state-of-the-art SED performance, as shown in [7]. The model is trained as outlined in Section 3 for 22,000 steps with a batch size of 32. We employ a cosine learning rate schedule with 4,000 warm-up steps and utilize the ADAM optimizer [20] with no weight decay. The initial learning rate is set to 1×10^{-3} , and a layer-wise learning rate decay factor of 0.8 is applied to adjust the learning rates across different layers of the model.

5.4. Source Separation Model

We use a ResUNet architecture [4], [21] for sound source separation, operating at 32kHz with a window size of 2048 and a hop size of 160 samples, matching the baseline. The model is initialized with pre-trained weights from AudioSep [22], a language-conditioned separation framework. While AudioSep was originally trained with a 320-sample hop size, we found a hop size of 160 samples to perform better in our setup. For fine-tuning the separator, we use separate

Config	M2D [2]	M2D (Ours)	Oracle
DCASE Baseline [2]	11.03	–	–
AudioSep-SED	12.71±0.03	13.42±0.11	15.29±0.13
- w/o Time-FiLM	12.41±0.03	13.07±0.06	14.82±0.06
- w/o Embedding Injection	12.46±0.01	13.12±0.07	14.91±0.09
- w/o Trainable S2-SED	11.95±0.04	12.53±0.03	14.04±0.04
AudioSep-SED + DPRNN	12.55±0.07	13.31±0.07	15.20±0.12

Table 1: CA-SDRi scores (\uparrow) for different system variants on the development test split, where *AudioSep-SED w/o Trainable S2-SED* represents the AudioSep-SED configuration, where the Stage 2 SED model is not trainable. Columns correspond to class detection using the baseline M2D, our fine-tuned M2D, and oracle targets. Bold indicates the best per column.

learning rates: 2×10^{-4} for pre-trained components, 5×10^{-4} for DPRNN parts and 1×10^{-3} for newly introduced parts such as the Time-FiLM embedding layers. Additionally, we train the Stage 2 SED model using a learning rate of 4×10^{-4} and a learning rate decay factor of 0.9. Training runs for 450,000 steps with a batch size of 8, using the Adam optimizer [20] (no weight decay) and a cosine learning rate schedule with 12,000 warm-up steps.

5.5. Experimental Design

To assess the efficacy of the proposed techniques for enhancing source separation, we conduct a series of experiments structured as follows. Initially, we evaluate the impact of Time-FiLM and Embedding Injection, both of which utilize the Stage 2 SED model. We also investigate the benefits of allowing this model to be trainable during the training phase of the separation model. We refer to the configuration incorporating Time-FiLM, Embedding Injection, and a trainable Stage 2 SED model as *AudioSep-SED*. This model serves as the foundation for subsequent experiments. Building upon it, we integrate a Dual-Path RNN (DPRNN) into the latent space to potentially enhance the model’s ability to capture long-range dependencies. Subsequently, we explore the iterative refinement approach by training models with varying numbers of iterations (2, 3, and 4) and assessing their performance when employing up to 10 iterations during inference.

6. RESULTS

The Stage 1 sound event detection model proposed in Section 3 increases test set accuracy by 8 points over the DCASE baseline, from 59.8% to 67.8%.

Table 1 compares the performance of the DCASE baseline, AudioSep-SED, and AudioSep-SED + DPRNN, highlighting the impact of each technique on the test split of the DCASE 2025 S5 development set. Performance is measured using CA-SDRi under three Stage 1 models: (1) baseline M2D tagger, (2) our M2D model, and (3) oracle targets. Results are averaged over two runs.

The second section in Table 1 shows that AudioSep-SED outperforms the DCASE baseline system. Integrating Time-FiLM, Embedding Injection, and a trainable Stage 2 SED model improves performance regardless of Stage 1 predictions, with the trainable Stage 2 SED yielding the largest gain. While Time-FiLM contributes more than Embedding Injection, their combination with a trainable SED achieves the best results. With baseline M2D predictions, this setup reaches a CA-SDRi of 12.71 vs. 11.03 for the DCASE baseline. Using our M2D model, the score further increases to 13.42.

Adding a DPRNN to AudioSep-SED improves performance on the *validation split*, increasing CA-SDRi from 13.79 to 14.35 using baseline M2D predictions. However, it underperforms on the *test split* (third section in Table 1), suggesting a distribution mismatch.

Fig. 2: Performance of the iterative refinement experiments compared to the AudioSep-SED + DPRNN configuration evaluated on the test set. *Iter {2,3,4}* denotes experiments with the maximum training iterations set to 2, 3, or 4, respectively. Class detection is performed using our fine-tuned M2D model.

Following standard practice, we select the best validation setup for further experiments; thus, DPRNN is included in our iterative refinement runs.

Figure 2 shows the performance of models trained with up to 2, 3, or 4 iterations and evaluated using 1–10 iterations at inference. Iterative refinement clearly outperforms the AudioSep-SED + DPRNN setup, with most gains occurring in early iterations and diminishing improvements thereafter—indicating convergence after a few cycles. Notably, using more inference iterations than used during training can still boost performance; e.g., a model trained with 3 iterations reached 13.92 after 3 inference steps and 13.98 after 10.

Our iterative refinement models generally enhance performance as the number of inference iterations increases, although the performance changes between consecutive iterations can be inconsistent and occasionally negative. A notable pattern emerges where odd-numbered iterations frequently outperform their even-numbered counterparts, a trend most pronounced in models trained with two iterations (Iter 2). However, this odd-even performance gap narrows in models trained with three or four iterations (Iter 3 and Iter 4), which suggests that extending the training iterations helps stabilize the refinement process.

Furthermore, Iter 3 outperforms both Iter 2 and Iter 4, indicating it strikes a good balance between training complexity and output quality. That said, because these experiments relied on a single run per configuration, the observed results should be interpreted with caution, as they may be influenced by random variability.

7. CONCLUSION

We introduced a two-stage audio source separation system that leverages sound event detection (SED) models to (1) identify active events and (2) guide the separator via temporal conditioning (Time-FiLM) and Embedding Injection. Evaluated on the DCASE 2025 S5 dataset, our results show that SED improves event detection in Stage 1 and provides effective guidance for Stage 2 separation. We also proposed an iterative refinement strategy, where outputs are recursively fed back into the model, which progressively enhanced the separation quality.

8. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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ToyADMOS2025: The Evaluation Dataset for the DCASE2025T2 First-Shot Unsupervised Anomalous Sound Detection for Machine Condition Monitoring

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Abstract—Recently, various applications have been explored that utilize machine learning to detect anomalies in machinery solely by listening to operational sounds. This paper introduces the newly recorded ToyADMOS dataset, “ToyADMOS2025”, for the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2: First-shot anomalous sound detection for machine condition monitoring (DCASE2025T2). New machine types, such as AutoTrash, HomeCamera, ToyPet, and ToyRCCar, were recorded as part of the Additional training and Evaluation datasets. This paper also shows benchmark results of the First-shot baseline implementation (with a simple autoencoder and selective Mahalanobis modes) on the ToyADMOS2025. The dataset, ground truth labels, and source code for the baseline were made available.

Index Terms—DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2, First-Shot Anomalous sound detection, ToyADMOS dataset

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, various applications have been explored that utilize machine learning to detect anomalies in machinery solely by listening to operational sounds. Since 2020, this line of research has been formalized as an annual challenge task under the Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) Challenge, specifically focusing on anomalous sound detection (ASD).

In the DCASE 2020 Challenge, Task 2 – titled Unsupervised Detection of Anomalous Sounds for Machine Condition Monitoring (DCASE2020T2) [1] – was introduced. This task required systems to learn only from normal operating sounds and determine whether a given machine sound was normal or anomalous.

Since it is generally difficult to collect real recordings of malfunctioning machines, the task employed datasets such as ToyADMOS and MIMII [2], [3], which consist of recordings of intentionally damaged components like toy cars and electric motors.

In the following year, the challenge evolved into DCASE 2021 Challenge Task 2: Unsupervised Anomalous Sound Detection for Machine Condition Monitoring under Domain-Shifted Conditions (DCASE2021T2) [4]. In 2022, the task continued as DCASE 2022 Challenge Task 2: Unsupervised Anomalous Sound Detection for Machine Condition Monitoring Applying Domain Generalization Techniques (DCASE2022T2) [5]. These editions utilized newly recorded datasets including ToyADMOS2, MIMII DUE, and MIMII DG [6]–[8]. Results from these challenge tasks have shown that a system design treating different configurations of the same machine type as pseudo-anomalous classes in a classification-based approach is particularly effective.

However, from a practical deployment perspective, there are many scenarios in which training data encompassing various machine configurations may not be available in advance. To address this, First-shot Anomalous Sound Detection for Machine Condition Monitoring has been introduced in 2023 (DCASE2023T2) [9]. This task investigated whether anomalous sounds could be detected after training solely on normal operating sounds of a previously unseen target machine. This First-shot task introduced a new set of constraints aimed at improving real-world applicability [6], [8]–[11]. Though ToyADMOS2

Fig. 1: Images of toy-model configurations A, B, and C for (a) AutoTrash, (b) HomeCamera, (c) ToyPet, and (d) ToyRCCar.

and MIMII DG were used as development datasets, newly recorded data were required for evaluation.

In DCASE2023T2, ToyADMOS2+ [12] was used as a part of the Additional Training and Evaluation dataset. This includes machine types such as Vacuum, ToyTank, ToyNscase, and ToyDrone.

The First-shot task paradigm continued in DCASE 2024 and 2025 Challenge Task 2: First-shot Unsupervised Anomalous Sound Detection for Machine Condition Monitoring (DCASE2024T2 and DCASE2025T2) [10], [13].

The dedicated dataset called ToyADMOS2#(sharp) [14] was collected for DCASE2024T2, and provided as a part of the Additional Training and Evaluation Datasets. These include recordings from devices such as HairDryer, HoveringDrone, ToothBrush, and ToyCircuit.

For DCASE2025T2, yet another dataset, ToyADMOS2025, was introduced to provide the First-shot ASD. This paper provides the recording details of the ToyADMOS2025 dataset, which has been newly collected as the Additional Training and Evaluation Dataset. This dataset is designed to further support research and development on First-shot anomalous sound detection systems. Other papers utilizing this dataset can simply make reference to this paper. The ground truth of those has been made available at GitHub. The benchmark performance of the DCASE 2023 Task 2 baseline [11] on this dataset is also shown.

Note that the series of datasets is named ToyADMOS; however, the recordings emulate real-world use cases of condition monitoring for complex systems, making it useful for evaluating ASD systems.

Fig. 2: Recording-room layouts and microphone arrangements, (a) AutoTrash, (b) HomeCamera, (c) ToyPet, and (d) ToyRCCar.

Fig. 3: Images of microphone arrangements (a) AutoTrash, (b) HomeCamera, (c) ToyPet, and (d) ToyRCCar.

Table 1: Anomaly conditions for each machine type.

(a) AutoTrash		(b) HomeCamera	
Part	Condition	Part	Condition
Lid	- Weighted Lid - Misalignment - Foreign object	Camera head	- Weighted head - Foreign scuff
Hinge	- Foreign object	Joint	- Foreign wire - Foreign wires
(c) ToyPet		(d) ToyRCCar	
Part	Condition	Part	Condition
Body	- Dragging object - Tied legs - Tied mouth - Fell down	Tire	- Foreign object
		Body	- Dragging object
		Shaft	- Clogging
		Steering	- Clogging

2. TOYADMOS2025: ADDITIONAL DATA FOR THE DCASE2025 CHALLENGE TASK 2

To provide the First-shot training data for DCASE2025T2, the following four machine types, (a) AutoTrash, (b) HomeCamera, (c) ToyPet, and (d) ToyRCCar, were newly recorded. Each machine type has three model configurations (A, B, C) shown in Fig. 1. The machine operating sounds were recorded with the room layout and the microphone settings shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

AutoTrash: The AutoTrash is an automatic trash box shown in Figs. 2(a) and 3(a). It automatically opens and closes its lid.

HomeCamera: The HomeCamera swings its camera head. Sound data were recorded using two microphones as shown in Figs. 2(b) and 3(b).

ToyPet: The ToyPet is on a leash and walks around a pole and barks as shown in Figs. 2(c) and 3(c).

ToyRCCar: The ToyRCCar runs on a wooden board partially covered with carpet as shown in Figs. 2(d) and 3(d).

Fig. 4: Images of anomaly conditions for (a) AutoTrash.

Fig. 5: Images of anomaly conditions for (b) HomeCamera.

Fig. 6: Images of anomaly conditions for (c) ToyPet.

Fig. 7: Images of anomaly conditions for (d) ToyRCCar.

Table 2: Recording conditions for DCASE2025T2 Eval. dataset.

	AutoTrash	HomeCamera	ToyPet	ToyRCCar
Model variations	A, B, C	A, B, C	A, B, C	A, B, C
Speed levels	2.7-3.2 V ^{*1}	Four	2.7-3.2 V ^{*1}	200-450 ms ^{*2}
Mic. config	(a) Ch. 4 - 5	(b) Ch. 1 - 3	(c) Ch. 1 - 3	(d) Ch. 4 - 6
Noise type ^{*3}	N3	N2	N1	N4
Sample duration	6 sec	6 sec	10 sec	7 sec

^{*1}Randomly variable power voltage range.

^{*2}Randomly variable operation duration.

^{*3}N1: large air conditioner’s outlet noise, N2: city noise near a river under a bridge, N3: server fan noise, and N4: running water sound in a drainage ditch in a park.

Table 3: Domain shift settings for DCASE2025T2 Eval. dataset.

Source domain	AutoTrash	HomeCamera	ToyPet	ToyRCCar
Machine ID	A, B	A, B	A, B	A, B
Speed	2.8-3.1 V ^{*1}	2, 3	2.8-3.1 V ^{*1}	A: 350-450 ms ^{*2} B: 200-300ms
Mic.	(a) Ch. 5	(b) Ch. 3	(c) Ch. 2	(d) Ch. 5
Noise ^{*3}	N3	N2	N1	N4
Target domain	AutoTrash	HomeCamera	ToyPet	ToyRCCar
Machine ID	C	C	C	C
Speed	2.7-3.2 V ^{*1}	1, 4	2.7-3.2 V ^{*1}	300-400 ms ^{*2}
Mic.	(a) Ch. 5	(b) Ch. 3	(c) Ch. 2	(d) Ch. 5
Noise ^{*3}	N3	N2	N1	N4

^{*1}Randomly variable power voltage range.

^{*2}Randomly variable operation duration.

^{*3}N1: large air conditioner’s outlet noise, N2: city noise near a river under a bridge, N3: server fan noise, and N4: running water sound in a drainage ditch in a park.

To generate anomaly samples, some of the parts were intentionally damaged. Anomaly conditions for each machine type are shown in Table 1. The images representing those anomaly conditions are shown in Figs 4, 5, 6 and 7.

Table 2 shows the recording setting. All the operating sound and noise samples were recorded with 48 kHz sampling, 24-bit for each channel, and then downsampled to 16 kHz, 24-bit, monaural. Sample duration varies from 6 sec to 10 sec, depending on the machine type, as shown in Table 2. Domain shift conditions were controlled by changing machine instances (ID), operating speed, mic position, and mixed background noise samples. Table 3 shows the domain shift conditions of source and target domains.

For training data (Additional training dataset), there are 1000 normal samples given for training, where 990 samples are from the source domain, and 10 samples are from the target domain. For evaluation data (Evaluation dataset), 50 normal and 50 anomaly samples are from each source and target domain. In total, there are 200 samples for each machine type. In total, 960 min of data was prepared.

The data is available at the Zenodo links ^{1 2}, under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License³.

¹DCASE 2025 challenge task 2 additional training dataset, available at <https://zenodo.org/record/15392814>

²DCASE 2025 challenge task 2 evaluation dataset, available at <https://zenodo.org/record/15519362>

³Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 international public license, [tps://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode)

Table 4: AUC results of the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2 Evaluation dataset.

System	metric	<i>hmean</i> ^{*1}	<i>amean</i> ^{*1}	AutoTrash	HomeCamera	ToyPet	ToyRCCar	BandSealer	CoffeeGrinder	Polisher	ScrewFeeder
First-shot compliant simple Autoencoder mode (FS-AE) [15]	AUC (source)	0.6880	0.6996	0.8102	0.8140	0.6770	0.5284	0.7198	0.7304	0.6686	0.6486
	AUC (target)	0.4495	0.4721	0.3436	0.4976	0.3670	0.6272	0.3956	0.4436	0.4430	0.6592
	pAUC (src & tgt)	0.5453	0.5468	0.5421	0.5284	0.5500	0.5553	0.5205	0.5342	0.5232	0.6211
	TOTAL score	0.5443	0.5729								
Selective Mahalanobis AE mode [15]	AUC (source)	0.7199	0.7297	0.7726	0.8616	0.6982	0.5586	0.7638	0.7498	0.7042	0.7290
	AUC (target)	0.4788	0.5082	0.5260	0.4264	0.5090	0.5548	0.3268	0.4042	0.5278	0.7904
	pAUC (src & tgt)	0.5459	0.5515	0.5416	0.5184	0.5684	0.5400	0.4911	0.5142	0.5379	0.7005
	TOTAL score	0.5651	0.5965								
DCASE2025T2 Top 1 Wang_MYPS_task2_3 [16] (Efficient Audio Transformer based pretrained model)	AUC (source)	0.6198	0.6489	0.7142	0.6536	0.6394	0.3956	0.6356	0.6070	0.6416	0.9042
	AUC (target)	0.6574	0.6858	0.9252	0.5978	0.6140	0.5046	0.6490	0.5542	0.7408	0.9006
	pAUC (src & tgt)	0.5769	0.5934	0.7705	0.5379	0.5405	0.5284	0.5163	0.5216	0.5405	0.7916
	TOTAL score	0.6163	0.6427								

^{*1}*hmean* denotes harmonic mean, and *amean* denotes arithmetic mean.

3. BENCHMARK RESULTS WITH THE DCASE2023T2 FIRST-SHOT BASELINE

3.1. The DCASE2023T2 First-shot baseline

The DCASE2023 Challenge Task 2 baseline has the following two operating modes. For the details, see Sec. 3.2 and [11].

First-shot-compliant simple Autoencoder mode (FS-AE): This is a simple autoencoder. For training, the model parameter θ of the AE is trained to minimize the mean square error (MSE) between a normal input sample x^- and its reconstruction \hat{x}^- using

$$Loss = MSE(x^-, \hat{x}^-), \tag{1}$$

$$where \hat{x}^- = Dec_{\theta}(Enc_{\theta}(x^-)). \tag{2}$$

For the testing phase, the anomaly score A_{θ} is calculated with the reconstruction error of the given query sample x using

$$Anomaly\ Score\ A_{\theta} = MSE(x, \hat{x}), \tag{3}$$

$$where \hat{x} = Dec_{\theta}(Enc_{\theta}(x)). \tag{4}$$

When the anomaly score exceeds the pre-set threshold, the sample is detected as an anomaly sample.

Selective Mahalanobis Autoencoder mode: The anomaly score A_{θ} is calculated using the covariance matrixes Σ_s^{-1} and Σ_t^{-1} of distance between normal samples x^- and its reconstruction \hat{x}^- for the source and target domains with:

$$Anomaly\ Score\ A_{\theta} = \min\{D_s(x, \hat{x}), D_t(x, \hat{x})\}, \tag{5}$$

$$where D_s(\cdot) = Mahalanobis(x, \hat{x}, \Sigma_s^{-1}), \tag{6}$$

$$D_t(\cdot) = Mahalanobis(x, \hat{x}, \Sigma_t^{-1}). \tag{7}$$

3.2. Experimental setup and evaluation criterion

For the First-shot compliant baseline, the model hyperparameters were set to the values described in [11].

The frame size for STFT was 64 ms with 50 % hop size translated into 128 frequency bands Log-mel energies. Five consecutive frames were concatenated to formulate 640 dimensions (128 × 5) as input to the system. In the autoencoder model, there were three layers of 128 dimensions linear, Batch normalization, and Activation with ReLU each, in encoder and decoder. The bottleneck layer had eight dimensions. The number of epochs for training was 100. The batch size was 256, and the Adam optimizer used a 0.001 learning ratio.

The performances of the two operating modes of the DCASE2023T2 baseline [11] with the ToyADMOS2025 dataset were evaluated. For those baseline systems, hyperparameters were set to the ones used in the corresponding previous DCASE Challenges [17], [18]. The total scores Ω for evaluating the systems are calculated based on Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve (AUC) and partial AUC (pAUC) with a harmonic mean (*hmean*) and an arithmetic mean (*amean*) of AUC and pAUC. All the results were the averaged score of systems trained with three different random seeds, except for the top winning system Wang_MYPS_task2_3 [16], that were copied from the official score.

3.3. Experimental results

Experimental results of the DCASE2023T2 First-shot baseline and the DCASE2025T2 first place winner, Wang_MYPS_task2_3 [16], on the DCASE2025T2 Evaluation datasets are shown in Table 4.

Those results can be categorized into three machine type groups, (A) AutoTrash, ToyPet, Polisher, ScrewFeeder, (B) HomeCamera, BandSealer, CoffeeGrinder, and (C) ToyRCCar.

For group (A) machine types, the DCASE2023T2 baseline with the selective Mahalanobis AE mode performed better than that of the simple Autoencoder (FS-AE) mode. Especially, AUC score of the FS-AE for the target domain data was less than 0.5 which is worth than chance rate. In contrast, Mahalanobis AE provided better than 0.5 accuracy on both source and target domain input. For group (A) machine types, Wang_MYPS_task2_3 further improves detection accuracy compared to the baseline systems. For group (B) machine types, both Mahalanobis AE and FS-AE showed worth than chance rate 0.5 in target domain and Mahalanobis AE performs worse. Wang_MYPS_task2_3 showed the best AUC scores that is better than the chance rate. Group (C) is interesting because the winning system Wang_MYPS_task2_3 performed AUC 0.3956 for ToyRCCar which both baseline systems, FS-AE and Mahalanobis AE, provided better than 0.5 for both source and target domain.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces the newly recorded ToyADMOS dataset for the DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2, First-shot anomalous sound detection for machine condition monitoring. New machine types, such as AutoTrash, HomeCamera, ToyPet, and ToyRCCar are newly recorded as a part of the Additional training and Evaluation datasets. The ToyADMOS2025 dataset (DCASE 2025 Challenge Task 2 Additional Training Dataset and Evaluation Dataset) is available at Zenodo ¹, ², under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License³. The source code of the baseline and the ground truth of those have been made available at GitHub ⁴ ⁵.

Note that the dataset is named ToyADMOS; however, the recordings emulate real-world use cases of condition monitoring for complex systems, making it useful for evaluating ASD systems.

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¹DCASE 2025 challenge task 2 additional training dataset, available at <https://zenodo.org/record/15392814>

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⁴https://github.com/nttclab/dcase2023_task2_baseline_ae

⁵https://github.com/nttclab/dcase2025_task2_evaluator

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Self-Guided Target Sound Extraction and Classification Through Universal Sound Separation Model and Multiple Clues

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Abstract—This paper introduces a multi-stage self-directed framework designed to address the spatial semantic segmentation of sound scene (S5) task in the DCASE 2025 Task 4 challenge. This framework integrates models focused on three distinct tasks: Universal Sound Separation (USS), Single-label Classification (SC), and Target Sound Extraction (TSE). Initially, USS breaks down a complex audio mixture into separate source waveforms. Each of these separated waveforms is then processed by a SC block, generating two critical pieces of information: the waveform itself and its corresponding class label. These serve as inputs for the TSE stage, which isolates the source that matches this information. Since these inputs are produced within the system, the extraction target is identified autonomously, removing the necessity for external guidance. The extracted waveform can be looped back into the classification task, creating a cycle of iterative refinement that progressively enhances both separability and labeling accuracy. We thus call our framework a multi-stage self-guided system due to these self-contained characteristics. On the official evaluation dataset, the proposed system achieves an 11.00 dB increase in class-aware signal-to-distortion ratio improvement (CA-SDRI) and a 55.8% accuracy in label prediction, outperforming the ResUNetK baseline by 4.4 dB and 4.3%, respectively, and achieving first place among all submissions.

Index Terms—Self-guided training, multi-stage framework, universal sound separation, target sound extraction

1. INTRODUCTION

The DCASE 2025 Task 4 [1], Spatial Semantic Segmentation of Sound Scenes (S5), aims to detect and separate individual sound events from multi-channel spatial audio inputs. The core objective is to isolate target sound events (foreground sources) from a mixture by distinguishing them from non-target sound events (interference sources) and background noise, and to perform classification. Each audio mixture can contain up to three foreground sources, optionally mixed with interference sources and background noise. Interference sources are differentiated from background noise by their non-diffuse spatial characteristics and their association with specific sound classes. The task defines a set of 18 target classes, while the non-target events encompass a broader set of 94 classes.

The presence of various sound events, including both non-target events and background noise, complicates the application of Universal Sound Separation (USS) techniques. This complexity highlights the importance of Target Sound Extraction (TSE), a method that leverages specific clues to isolate the sound of interest. TSE models leverage various forms of clues, such as a class label [2], an enrollment sample [3], [4], or a timestamp [5], to isolate a desired waveform from a mixture. For instance, a class-conditioned TSE model [2] extracts sound events belonging to a specific class. The SoundBeam [3] using the enrollment clue can be viewed as an extension of this paradigm, where an enrollment waveform is provided as the clue. The model then extracts sounds from the mixture that match the acoustic characteristics of the enrollment waveform.

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Traditional TSE tasks depend on external cues that are separate from the input mixture. Conversely, in the S5 task, the system must initially detect the target sound events present in the mixture before extracting them. This indicates a self-directed approach: the necessary clues must be extracted from the input mixture itself to guide the retrieval of the target sound events.

The official DCASE 2025 Task 4 baseline [6] addresses the S5 task by combining Audio Tagging (AT) and TSE. It first performs AT on the mixture using Masked Modeling Duo for Audio Tagging (M2D-AT), a variant of M2D [4] specifically fine-tuned for this task. The resulting multi-hot label, representing the predicted classes, is then fed as a clue to a TSE model (ResUNet or ResUNetK) [7] to extract the target events. This baseline approach, however, presents three notable limitations. First, performing AT directly on a complex polyphonic mixture is inherently more difficult than classifying an already isolated sound. Given that mixtures can contain up to six sources, including background noise, accurately identifying all target events is a formidable task. Second, the baseline’s AT module cannot leverage the spatial information available in the multi-channel input, which can be critical for disambiguating overlapping sources. Third, the framework lacks a mechanism for iterative refinement; the information flow is unidirectional, and the extracted waveforms are not used to improve the initial predictions.

To overcome these drawbacks, we propose a multi-stage self-guided framework that combines the multi-clue derivation through USS, Single-Label classification (SC), and TSE. The core of our framework leverages a modified version of DeFT-Mamba [8], a state-of-the-art (SOTA) model developed for universal audio separation in multi-channel polyphonic scenarios. This model, which we term DeFT-Mamba-USS, first performs USS to decompose the mixture into estimates for three foreground sources, two interference sources, and background noise. Subsequently, we perform SC on each separated target waveform using Masked Modeling Duo for Single-label Classification (M2D-SC), a version of M2D fine-tuned for classifying the 18 target classes. In the next step, both the separated waveforms (as enrollment clues) and their predicted classes (as class clues) are jointly supplied to DeFT-Mamba-TSE, a variant of DeFT-Mamba adapted for TSE. This multi-clue approach guides the extraction of refined target waveforms. Finally, this process is iterated: the newly extracted waveform is re-classified, and these refined enrollment and class clues are used for another round of TSE, creating a cycle of progressive refinement.

This framework significantly lowers the difficulty of class estimation compared to direct AT on a mixture by performing classification on preliminarily separated sources. The multi-stage refinement process enables the system to achieve progressively more accurate waveforms and corresponding class labels, leading to superior classification accuracy on the evaluation dataset compared to other teams. This approach, which integrates multi-clue injection with iterative refinement, demonstrates great effectiveness, enabling us to achieve the

Fig. 1: Self-guided multi-stage framework (J : the maximum number of sources, C : the number of classes, L : the waveform length).

highest position in the competition. Our leading standing has been shown through the class-aware signal-to-distortion ratio improvement (CA-SDRi), a comprehensive metric assessing both separation and classification performance.

2. PRELIMINARY

DeFT-Mamba [8] is a SOTA model designed to perform USS and classification concurrently. Operating on the complex spectrogram, the model’s architecture is composed of N_b stacked blocks of F-Hybrid Mamba and T-Hybrid Mamba modules, which are designed to model relationships along the frequency and time dimensions, respectively. A key distinction from previous speech enhancement models with similar architectures [9]–[12] is its replacement of the traditional Feed-Forward Network (FFN) within each transformer block with a Mamba Feed-Forward Network (Mamba-FFN). The model performs separation at the feature level. These separated features are then fed into two parallel decoders: an audio decoder to estimate waveforms and a class decoder to predict their corresponding labels. This dual-head decoder structure effectively resolves the pair-wise ambiguity between the estimated waveforms and their predicted classes, ensuring each separated sound is correctly associated with its label.

3. PROPOSED SELF-GUIDED FRAMEWORK

The self-guided multi-stage framework performs progressive separation and classification through a combination of USS, SC, and TSE. As illustrated in Fig. 1, our framework consists of three main stages: 3.1 clue generation via DeFT-Mamba-USS and M2D-SC, 3.2 TSE guided by multi-clue conditioning, and 3.3 iterative refinement for enhanced separation and classification.

3.1. Stage 1: Clue derivation via DeFT-Mamba-USS and M2D-SC

The first stage employs DeFT-Mamba-USS to decompose complex multi-channel spectrograms into distinct object-level features. Unlike conventional architectures of DeFT-Mamba, DeFT-Mamba-USS adopts a modified design with F-Hybrid Mamba and T-Hybrid Mamba blocks. To reduce computational complexity while preserving performance, we exclude the unfold operation and simplify the F-Hybrid Mamba blocks by removing the embedded Mamba modules. This architecture generates six object-level features corresponding to three foreground sources, two interference sources, and one background noise source. Each object feature is then processed by two parallel decoders: an audio decoder reconstructing the waveform, and a class decoder predicting the associated class label.

Once the waveform has been reconstructed, each source is fed into a single-label classifier named as M2D-SC. This classifier builds upon the M2D architecture [13] and is adjusted specifically for single-label prediction among 18 target classes. Given that some predicted waveforms actually represent silence—indicating non-existent or inactive sources—M2D-SC is also designed to recognize these silences through an energy-based approach [14]. In particular, M2D-SC

Fig. 2: Inference procedure of M2D-SC (a) The model predicts class and calculates the energy score from unnormalized logits. (b) Silence is determined by comparing the energy score with a class-specific threshold.

generates an energy score from its raw logits and employs class-specific thresholds to identify silent segments. As depicted in Figure 2, M2D-SC uses the mel spectrogram from a separated signal as input, and its transformer layers are fine-tuned to predict the signal’s class label. The model computes an energy score from the resulting raw logits to determine silence. If this score surpasses a predetermined threshold, the source is categorized as silence irrespective of predicted labels; if not, the model outputs the class assigned by the classifier. The threshold is adapted specifically for each class, as the complexity of identifying silence varies between classes.

3.2. Stage 2: TSE using multi-clue conditioning

In the second stage, we perform targeted refinement using DeFT-Mamba-TSE, which leverages the clues generated in 3.1. DeFT-Mamba-TSE inherits the architectural backbone of DeFT-Mamba-USS but is modified for TSE through multi-clue conditioning. Unlike traditional TSE models [3], [4] that encode enrollment clues into embeddings (often resulting in loss of fine-grained details), DeFT-Mamba-TSE injects raw separated waveforms directly. The complex spectrograms of the enrollments are concatenated with those of mixtures along the channel axis prior to the up-convolutional layers of DeFT-Mamba. In parallel, class clues are injected into intermediate feature maps via Residual Feature-wise Linear Modulation (Res-FiLM) [7], [15]. Here, class-dependent embeddings (β , γ) are computed from the one-hot vectors of the predicted class and consistently applied across all DeFT-Mamba blocks, ensuring strong and stable conditioning throughout the network. After this guided extraction, the refined waveforms are classified again using M2D-SC in the same manner as in the previous stage. This second round of classification not only corrects potential errors from the initial stage but also further refines class clues for the next stage.

3.3. Stage 3: Iterative refinement for enhanced separation and classification

In the final stage, we introduce an iterative refinement mechanism to further improve the performance of both separation and classification. The refined waveforms and updated class labels are reinjected into DeFT-Mamba-TSE for an additional extraction cycle. This cyclic process allows the system to progressively correct errors and sharpen source boundaries while refining class predictions. At each iteration, new enrollments and class clues are generated internally, making the framework fully self-guided without external supervision. By integrating iterative refinement, the framework effectively mitigates error propagation from earlier stages and achieves superior performance in terms of signal-to-distortion ratio improvement (SDRi) and classification accuracy.

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS

The models for three stages were trained individually, and since the output of DeFT-Mamba-USS was used as the enrollment clue for training DeFT-Mamba-TSE, DeFT-Mamba-USS was trained prior to DeFT-Mamba-TSE. To obtain higher-quality speech training data, we replaced the speech data provided from the challenge dataset with the VCTK corpus [16] resampled to 32 kHz. In addition, we augmented the percussion class data by collecting additional samples from open-source databases (Pixabay¹). These extra sources were spatialized by SpatialScaper [17], mixing 1–3 target events with a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 5–20 dB and up to two interference events at 0–15 dB.

4.1. DeFT-Mamba-USS

DeFT-Mamba-USS was trained using the same data configuration as the baseline system [6], and optimized with the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of $4e-4$. The model was trained in a multi-task learning setup, simultaneously performing source separation through the audio decoder and source classification through the class decoder. **Separation** The negative Source-Aggregated Signal-to-Distortion ratio (SA-SDR) loss [18] was applied for estimating foreground and interference sources. Given M estimated signals \hat{s}_m and their corresponding ground truth s_m , the negative SA-SDR loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SA-SDR}} = -10 \log_{10} \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M \|s_m\|_2^2}{\sum_{m=1}^M \|s_m - \hat{s}_m\|_2^2}. \quad (1)$$

For the background noise object, the negative Scale-Invariant Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SI-SNR) loss was used:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SI-SNR}} = -10 \log_{10} \frac{\|\alpha \cdot n\|^2}{\|\hat{n} - \alpha \cdot n\|^2}, \quad \alpha = \frac{\langle \hat{n}, n \rangle}{\|n\|^2} \quad (2)$$

where n and \hat{n} denote the ground truth and estimated background noise. The overall loss for USS \mathcal{L}_{USS} is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{USS}} = \mathcal{L}_F + \lambda \cdot (\mathcal{L}_I + \mathcal{L}_N) \quad (3)$$

with the sum of SA-SDR losses for the foreground sources \mathcal{L}_F and the interference sources \mathcal{L}_I . \mathcal{L}_N is the SI-SNR loss for estimating the background noise. The losses for interference sources \mathcal{L}_I and background noise \mathcal{L}_N were weighted with $\lambda = 0.01$ for concentrating on the separability of the target sound events.

Classification The class decoder in DeFT-Mamba-USS predicts the class label for each separated source by minimizing a cross-entropy loss on foreground sources to ensure precise label assignment. For silent or non-existing sources, a Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence

loss was used to enforce the predicted class probabilities to be close to a uniform distribution, thereby avoiding overconfident or spurious predictions on silence.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}} = \text{KL}(p_{\text{sc}} \| u) = \sum_{k=1}^C p_{\text{sc}}(k) \log \frac{p_{\text{sc}}(k)}{u(k)} \quad (4)$$

where $p_{\text{sc}} \in \mathbb{R}^C$ denotes the estimated probabilities for a silent segment, and $u = \frac{1}{C} \mathbf{1} \in \mathbb{R}^C$ denotes the uniform target when C is the total number of classes. Additionally, a binary classification branch with a sigmoid output is included to explicitly detect silence, trained using binary cross-entropy loss and thresholded at 0.5 during inference to decide whether a source is active or silent. This combination enables reliable class prediction while robustly handling silent segments.

4.2. M2D-SC

M2D-SC is a fine-tuned variant of M2D, and only the last two transformer layers and the classification head were fine-tuned. The M2D-SC was fine-tuned in two steps to maximize classification accuracy while maintaining robust performance for silence detection.

ArcFace-based Discriminative Training In the first step, we adopted the ArcFace loss [19] to improve inter-class separability and intra-class compactness. For the ground truth class y_i of i -th data, the ArcFace loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{ArcFace}} = -\log \frac{e^{s \cdot \cos(\theta_{y_i+m})}}{e^{s \cdot \cos(\theta_{y_i+m})} + \sum_{k \neq y_i} e^{s \cdot \cos(\theta_k)}} \quad (5)$$

where $s = 32$ is a scale factor, $m = 0.5$ is the additive angular margin, and θ_k is the angle between the output feature from the classifier and the trained class center. For silent segments, KL divergence loss is applied to approximate the estimated probability distribution to a uniform distribution, following the same strategy adopted in the class decoder.

Energy-based Silence Detection For the energy-based silence detection, we incorporated a hinge loss securing a margin between energy scores of silence and foreground sources. The energy score is given by

$$E(x) = -\log \sum_{k=1}^C e^{l_k}, \quad (6)$$

where l_k represents the raw logit value corresponding to the k -th class. A lower energy score indicates a higher likelihood of being an active source, while higher value suggests silence. For the input sample x , the hinge loss is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{energy}} = \mathbb{E}_{x_{\text{in}} \sim \mathcal{D}_{\text{in}}^{\text{train}}} (\max(0, E(x_{\text{in}}) - m_{\text{in}}))^2 + \mathbb{E}_{x_{\text{out}} \sim \mathcal{D}_{\text{out}}^{\text{train}}} (\max(0, m_{\text{out}} - E(x_{\text{out}})))^2 \quad (7)$$

where margins $m_{\text{in}} = -6.0$ and $m_{\text{out}} = -1.0$ were chosen to control the decision boundaries. The hinge loss for energy-based silence detection was weighted with a factor of $\lambda_e = 0.001$. Specifically, The loss functions adapted in each step are as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SC}}^{1\text{st}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{ArcFace}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SC}}^{2\text{nd}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{ArcFace}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}} + \lambda_e \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{energy}}. \quad (9)$$

4.3. DeFT-Mamba-TSE

DeFT-Mamba-TSE was trained using the same data configuration as DeFT-Mamba-USS. However, the outputs separated from DeFT-Mamba-USS were used as enrollment clues. This approach ensures that the model focuses on isolating the target source from the mixture rather than replicating the enrollment clue directly. For class clues, ground

¹<https://pixabay.com/sound-effects/>

truth one-hot vectors were employed to minimize confusion and provide explicit conditioning signals. The audio decoder within DeFT-Mamba-TSE was trained using the masked SNR loss [6] to emphasize precise foreground extraction. The masked SNR loss computes the SNR only for active sources, ignoring silent segments.

5. EVALUATION METRICS

5.1. CA-SDRi

The official ranking metric of the challenge, CA-SDRi [1], evaluates both source separation quality and class prediction accuracy by including the SDRi of true positives only. In contrast, false positive or false negative cases act as a penalty by including their numbers in the denominator of the metric. The CA-SDRi is given by

$$\text{CA-SDRi} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C} \cup \hat{\mathcal{C}}|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{C} \cup \hat{\mathcal{C}}} P_k \quad (10)$$

where \mathcal{C} and $\hat{\mathcal{C}}$ denote the sets of ground-truth and predicted classes present in the mixture, respectively. P_k is the SDRi of the estimated signals when the class k belongs to $\mathcal{C} \cap \hat{\mathcal{C}}$, and 0 for the other classes. Silent segments are excluded from this computation, ensuring that the metric focuses solely on active sources.

5.2. Mixture-level accuracy

We evaluate the mixture-level accuracy by counting the number of data samples only when the predicted set of labels $\hat{\mathcal{C}}$ exactly matches the ground-truth set \mathcal{C} . Writing \mathbb{I} for the indicator function and N for the number of data samples, the accuracy is given by

$$\text{Acc}_{\text{mix}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{I}[\hat{\mathcal{C}}_i = \mathcal{C}_i]. \quad (11)$$

5.3. Source-level accuracy

Each separated waveform is evaluated independently. Let M_i be the number of separated foreground waveforms from mixture x_i . For the target and predicted labels y_{ij} and \hat{y}_{ij} in the j -th waveform separated from x_i , the overall ratio of correctly labeled tracks is given by

$$\text{Acc}_{\text{src}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{M_i} \mathbb{I}[\hat{y}_{ij} = y_{ij}]}{\sum_{i=1}^N M_i}. \quad (12)$$

In the S5 setting, M_i is always 3 because each mixture i contains up to three foreground sources, including those detected as silences.

6. RESULTS

The experimental results are summarized in Table 1. We evaluated five configurations based on different combinations of Foreground Source Separation (FSS) and Class Prediction (CP) available at various stages of the proposed framework. The configurations include (1) **FSS 1 + CP 1** using the separated waveforms and estimated classes from DeFT-Mamba-USS, (2) **FSS 1 + CP 1-1** using the waveforms from DeFT-Mamba-USS but processing them by M2D-SC to estimate classes, (3) **FSS 2 + CP 1-1** performing the second stage processing using DeFT-Mamba-TSE but using the classification results from the first stage M2D-SC, (4) **FSS 2 + CP 2** using the waveforms separated by DeFT-Mamba-TSE and classes predicted by feeding them into the second-stage M2D-SC, (5) **FSS 3 + CP 3** applying the two-stage TSE model. Among all configurations, the FSS 3 + CP 3 model achieved the best performance, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed two-stage multi-clue framework. Accordingly, this configuration was used to run inference on the private evaluation set for our official challenge submission. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of

using USS-derived outputs as multi-clue to perform self-guided target sound extraction. Table 2 summarizes the results of the leaderboard

Table 1: Experimental results of FSS-CP configuration in the proposed framework. CA-SDRi and SNRi in [dB] and Acc_{src} in [%]

	CA-SDRi \uparrow	SNRi \uparrow	Acc _{src} \uparrow
FSS 1 + CP 1	10.8	15.1	73.2
FSS 1 + CP 1-1	12.7	15.1	81.8
FSS 2 + CP 1-1	14.6	18.3	81.8
FSS 2 + CP 2	14.7	18.3	83.4
FSS 3 + CP 3	14.9	18.4	84.5

on the DCASE 2025 Task 4 challenge. The ground-truth annotations are not publicly released for the evaluation set, while the test set includes accessible reference labels. Our system (Rank 1) achieves the highest CA-SDRi on the evaluation set (11.00 dB) and strong mixture-level accuracy (Acc_{mix}) of 55.80%. On the test set, it also demonstrates competitive CA-SDRi performance (14.94 dB) and a solid accuracy of 61.80%. A detailed analysis of these results, along with complete leaderboard rankings and breakdowns, can be found on the official challenge page².

Table 2: DCASE 2025 Task 4 leaderboard with CA-SDRi in [dB] and Acc_{mix} in [%].

Rank	Evaluation Set		Test Set	
	CA-SDRi \uparrow	Acc _{mix} \uparrow	CA-SDRi \uparrow	Acc _{mix} \uparrow
1 (Ours) [20]	11.00	55.80	14.94	61.80
2 [21]	9.77	61.60	15.04	77.07
3 [22]	9.73	51.54	14.00	59.80
4 [23]	7.84	47.72	14.38	73.93
5 [24]	7.55	49.51	13.31	64.07
6 [25]	6.69	47.22	13.22	76.53
7 [26]	6.60	51.48	11.12	60.67
8 (Baseline) [6]	6.60	51.48	11.09	59.80
9 [27]	3.84	22.41	11.78	65.47

7. CONCLUSION

We proposed a novel self-guided multi-stage framework for spatial semantic segmentation of sound scenes (S5). By tightly integrating USS (DeFT-Mamba-USS), single-label classification (M2D-SC), and multi-clue TSE (DeFT-Mamba-TSE), the system effectively decomposes complex mixtures and iteratively refines source separation and class prediction. Comprehensive experiments demonstrated that our approach achieves superior performance in both CA-SDRi and classification accuracy compared to existing baselines. The final two stages highlight the effectiveness of using internally generated clues for robust self-guided extraction. These results suggest that leveraging joint separation-classification refinement and multi-clue conditioning can provide a strong foundation for future research in spatial audio scene understanding and beyond.

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²<https://dcase.community/challenge2025/task-spatial-semantic-segmentation-of-sound-scenes-results>

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